

Partnership for the Assessment of Risks from Chemicals

Deliverable D1.10

AWP Y4 including PARC Project Portfolio

WP1 – T1.2

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¹ PU = Public

PP = Restricted to other programme participants (including the Commission Services)

RE = Restricted to a group specified by the consortium (including the Commission Services)

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Document history

Version	Date	Reviewer name/Institutions	Short description of changes
1	04/10/2024	WP co-leaders, Task co-leaders and Project managers and partners involved in their WPs and Tasks	First draft with modifications in track changes
2	18/10/2024	WP co-leaders and PARC CT only	Review of the first draft
3	25/10/2024	PARC CT only	Review of the first draft
4	08/11/2024	GB and GSB members	Review of the first draft
5	13/12/2024	WP co-leaders, Task co-leaders and Project managers	Update of the draft taking into account GB and GSB's comments and addition of the new projects to validated to be started Y4
6	03/01/2025	WP co-leaders and PARC CT only	Final review of the draft AWPY4
7	11/02/2025	PARC CT only	Final review of the draft AWPY4 Addition of the financial sections of the AWPY4
8	27/06/2025	WP co-leaders, Task co-leaders, Project managers and PARC CT	Comments received from HaDEA were taken into account and budget information have been updated (Table 2.3.a, 2.3.b and 2.3.c)

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Abstract

This Annual Work Plan (AWP) describes the activities to be implemented during the 'PARC year', including the updated Project Portfolio. The AWP covers the period from May 2025 to April 2026 (M37-M48) which are referred to as 'PARC years'.

Key Words

Work Plan, Project Portfolio Period M37-M48

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List of abbreviations

AA: Anti-Androgenicity	ML: Machine Learning
ADME: Absorption, Distribution, Metabolism and Excretion	MIEs: Molecular Initiating Events
AE: Affiliated Entity	MoA: Mode of Action
AEP: Aggregated Exposure Pathways	MS: Member States
AI: Artificial Intelligence	MTA: Material Transfer Agreement
AO/ AON/ AOP: Adverse Outcome/ AO Network/ Pathway	M4M: Metadata 4 Machines
API: Application Programming Interfaces	MRA: Mixture Risk Assessment
ASR/ AWP: Annual Summary Report/Work Plans	NAMs: New Approach Methodologies
BBB: Blood Brain Barrier	NGRA: Next Generation Risk Assessment
BCSFB: Blood-cerebrospinal Fluid Barrier	NGTxC: Non-Genotoxic Carcinogens
BIODA: Documentation of Biological Organisms	NHs: National Hubs
BMD: Benchmark dose	NHCs: National Hub Coordinators
BNNs: Bayesian Neural Networks	NHCPs: National Hub Contact Points
BPR: Biocides Products Regulation	NTS: Non-Targeted Screening
CA: Consortium Agreement	OECD: Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development
CEC: Chemicals of Emerging Concern	OO: Operational Objectives
CDIF: Cross-Domain Implementation Framework	OoC: Organ-on-Chip
CG: Core Group	OORF: OECD Omics Reporting Framework
CL/ ML: Chemical Leader/ Methodology Leader	OSOA: One Substance One Assessment
CLP: Classification, Labelling and Packaging	PDB: Protein Data Bank
CMS: Content Management System	PEC: Predicted Environmental Concentrations
COPCSD: Common Open Platform on Chemical Safety Data	PEH: Personal Exposure and Health
CPDC: Common Platform for Data on Chemicals	PFAS: per- and polyfluoroalkyl substances
CSS: Chemicals Strategy for Sustainability	PFDP: PARC FAIR Data Policy
CT: ANSES PARC Coordination Team	PBK: Physiologically Based Kinetic
DILI: Drug-Induced Liver Injury	PBMC: Peripheral Blood Mononuclear Cells
DEPB: Data and Ethics Protection Board	PBPK: Physiologically Based Pharmacokinetic
DBS: Dried Blood Spots	PBTK: Physiologically Based Toxicokinetic
DL: Deep Learning	PM: Project Manager
DMP: Data Management Plan	PMT: Persistent Mobile and Toxic
DNT/ANT: Developmental and Acute Neurotoxicity	

DoA: Description of Action	PoC: Prof of Concept
DTA: Data Transfer Agreement	POD: Point of Departure
EATS: Estrogen, Androgen, Steroidogenesis, and Thyroid	POP: Persistent Organic Pollutant
EBD: Environmental Burden of Disease	3PPF: Three-Point FAIRification Framework
EC: European Commission	PPPR: Plant Protection Products Regulation
ECHA: European Chemicals Agency	PT: Proficiency Testing
ED/ EDCs: Endocrine Disrupters / endocrine disrupting compounds	QA/QC: Quality Assurance / Quality Control
EDA: Effect-Directed Analysis	QAWG: Quality Assurance Working Group
EFSA: European Food Safety Authority	QIVIVE: Quantitative in vitro / in vivo Extrapolation
EMG: Effect Marker Group	QSAR: Quantitative Structure Activity Relationship
EOSC: European Open Science Cloud	RA/RM: Risk Assessment / Risk Management
ERA: Environmental Risk Assessment	RAiD: Research Activity Identifier
EWS: Early Warning System	REAL: Real Exposure Concentrations
FAIR: Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable	R&I: Research and Innovation
FIP: FAIR Implementation Profiles	RQ: Risk Quotient
FIT: FAIR Implementation Taskgroup	RRM: Rapid Response Mechanism
GA: Grant Agreement	SAM: Stress Addition Model
GB: Governing Board	SCCS: Scientific Committee on Consumer Safety
GDPR: General Data Protection Regulation	SDGs: Sustainable Development Goals
GEQUAS: German External Quality Assessment Scheme	S2PD: Science-to-Policy Dialogue
GFF: Go Fair Foundation	SAICM: Strategic Approach to International Chemicals Management
GIVIMP: Good In Vitro Methods Practices	SF: Stakeholder Forum
GNN: Graph Neural Networks	SG: Specialty Group
GPR: Gaussian Process Regression	SO: Specific Objectives
GS: Grant Signatory	SPM: Suspended Particulate Matter
GSB: Grant Signatory Board	SRIA: Strategic Research and Innovation Agenda
GUPRIs: Global Unique Persistence Resolvable Identifiers	SS: suspect screening
HA: Hazard Assessment	SSbD: Safe-and-Sustainable-by-Design
HBM: Human BioMonitoring	SSO: Single-Sign-On
HBM GV: Health-based Guidance Values	STOP: Source to Outcome Pathways
HIA: Health Impact Assessment	SOP: Standard Operating Procedures
HRMS: High Resolution Mass Spectrometry	SVM: Support Vector Machine
IATA: Integrative Approaches for testing and Assessment	
IB: International Board	

IPR: Intellectual Property Rights	SWB: Silicone Wristbands
IVIVE: <i>in vitro</i> - <i>in vivo</i> extrapolation	T/TL: Task/Task co-leaders
JRC: Joint Research Centre	TTC: Toxicological Threshold of Concern
KIC: Knowledge and Innovation Communities	THSD: Thyroid Hormone System Disruptors
KEs: Key Events	TKTD: Toxicokinetic-toxicodynamic modelling
KERs: Key Event Relationships	TRC: Test Readiness Criteria
LCA: Life-cycle assessment	TRL: Technology Readiness Level
MAF: Mixture Assessment Factor	UCWG: Use Case Working Group(s)
MB: Management Board	UNEP: United Nations Environment Programme
MCRA: Monte Carlo Risk Assessment	US-EPA: US Environmental Protection Agency
MDC: Metabolic Disrupting chemicals	US-NTP: US National Toxicology Program
MEA: Multi Electrodes Array	WGCNA: Weighted Gene Corralation networks for analysis
MEC: Measured Environmental Concentrations	WHO: World Health Organization
	WoE: Weight-of-Evidence
	WP/ WPL: Work Package / WP co-leaders
	WWTP: Wastewater treatment plants
	ZFe: Zebrafish embryo

Structure of the Annual Work Programme

1. Coherence with part B of the proposal

1.1 Annual Work Plan (AWP) objectives

The objectives of this fourth year are aligned with the specific objectives of PARC.

S01 - To achieve a high scientific policy and societal impact, EU and national risk assessors and regulatory entities come together with the scientific community in a cross-disciplinary network to set priorities for research and innovation in chemical Risk Assessment (RA)

001-Maintaining a high management level through meeting of Boards. For the year 4, meetings of the PARC governance bodies will be organised to discuss the PARC progression, indicators, sustainability, as well as the strategy for the AWPY5.

002-National Hubs (NHs) will continue their activities to gather national needs, encourage cooperation and identify potential synergies. At the national levels, the discussion will focus on the ways to elaborate sustainable framework for the prioritized PARC activities to share options with the Governing Board (GB), Management Board (MB) and Grant Signatory Board (GSB).

003-Based on the work done during Y3 on the prioritisation process and review of needs, the review of new projects and monitoring on on-going ones will be performed. Several projects and case studies will end during Y4 while others will start. Some of the new projects will take the handover of previous ones. The lessons learned from the first year of PARC will be also discussed for further improvement of the process.

004-Using PARCopedia, the chemical RA community will be enabled to find, co-create and discuss knowledge on all matters related to chemical RA and Next Generation RA (NGRA). Chemical and Methodology leaders (CL/MLs) will follow and report on the work developed within PARC. Particular attention will be paid to increasing the amount of knowledge shared and co-created by the community.

005-Cooperation with other programmes and initiatives will be encouraged. The identification of potential synergies, facilitation of information exchange between external projects and PARC and the establishment of collaborations and synergies with relevant scientific/regulatory/policy initiatives at national, EU and international levels will continue.

006- Communication and dissemination of knowledge produced by PARC will be performed via the website, the open access to scientific publications. The communication and dissemination strategy will be revised.

S02 - European and national RA entities and their scientific networks carry out a joint research and innovation programme to respond to the agreed priorities in chemicals RA.

007-Work programme. The programme will be monitored and 18 new projects are starting Y4. Several on-going projects will continue to perform their testing and modelling activities to generate data and 23 projects will be extended to pursue the work implemented in the previous years.

008-Monitoring capacity development. The HBM sampling phase will continue. The selection of the best, state-of-the-art exposure biomarkers and analytical methods will be performed according to the identified needs for implementation from Y4. The chemical analysis plan will be approved and implemented. A PARC-German External Quality Assessment Scheme (GEQUAS) Quality Assurance / Quality Control (QA/QC) programme will begin in the last quarter of Y3. A first list of qualified laboratories will be established. Add-on studies on per- and polyfluoroalkyl substances (PFAS) will start.

For occupational studies (health sector, e-waste), candidate laboratories for the analysis of samples for the exposure and effect biomarkers will assess their internal performance and a proficiency test will be organised by PARC in case of lack of proficiency test providers for biomarkers selected. Analysis of some samples is expected to start.

For the environmental projects, the monitoring activities developed, the chemical analyses will be completed and reported according to the formats and procedures developed. The collection of existing PFAS data for the “baseline part” will be completed.

0010-To implement Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable (FAIR) data practices,

The PARC data management plan (DMP) will be adapted using the selected tool and the choices defined by domain specific. 'Training through doing' and development of the PARC Data Hub will continue as FAIR Steering and implementation of prioritised use cases.

0012-Innovative concepts, models and tools. Some reports will be delivered end of Y4 on the work done on new approach methodologies, integrative approaches for testing and assessment (IATA), New approach methodologies (NAMs), physiologically based models (PBK) and systems toxicology. Reports on aggregate exposure for general population and workers and source to dose modelling, real-life mixtures will be provided. Activities performed on the concept of HIA will be reported. The core work in Y4 is finalizing the collection of data, beyond the one that will be processed and reported at the end of Y3. New projects will start to fill some gaps in line with the 2nd PARC priority list.

S03 - European risk assessors, their scientific network and the wider stakeholder community have access to the research and innovation capacities required to implement innovative chemical RA

009-Use of PARC results. PARCopedia and PARC Toolbox, trainings, webinars, scientific publications and sharing of guidances support the achievement of this objective as well as the international collaboration.

0011-Networks of laboratories and research centres. During Y4, the Human BioMonitoring (HBM) laboratory network will be the first implemented in the dashboard. For the upcoming years, the dashboard will be fed continuously with updated information and new networks. Feedback from WP4 and WP5 on the implementation of QA/QC guidances will be collected.

0013-Capacity building. During Y4, the implementation of the 1st PARC training plan (AD9.1) will be pursued, developed to cover the topics identified by partners and stakeholders. This includes two in-person training courses (1. New approach methodologies; and 2. AOPs and IATAs). PARC partners will also develop additional high-quality e-learning materials on topics identified for non-formal learning. PARC partners will continue to work on the identification of external training (outside PARC), namely events and online resources on relevant topics.

1.2 Expected impacts

Table 1: Links between projects/activities and objectives

SPECIFIC OBJECTIVES (SO)	OPERATIONAL OBJECTIVES (OO)	PROJECTS/TRANSVERSAL ACTIVITIES CONTRIBUTING
S01 - cross-disciplinary network to set priorities for R&I in chemical RA	OO1: Set-up and operate a high-level group to strategically steer PARC	WP1 - T1.1; T1.4; WP2 - T2.1; T2.2; WP3 - T3.1; T3.3; WP4 - P4.3.4.a;
	OO2: Expand long-term sustainable network of National Hubs (NH)	WP2 - T2.3; WP4 - P4.3.2.b; P4.3.4.a;

<p>003: Define common R&I strategies with transparent criteria and a prioritisation strategy</p>		<p>WP2 – T2.1; T2.2;</p> <p>WP4 – P4.1.1.4.b*; P4.2.a; P4.2.b; P4.3.1.a; P4.3.1.c; P4.3.2.a; P4.3.2.b; P4.3.3.b; P4.3.4.a;</p> <p>WP5 - P5.1.1.a; P5.1.1.b; P5.1.1.d*; P5.1.2.a; P5.1.2.b; P5.2.a*; P5.2.1.a; P5.2.1.c; P5.2.1.d; P5.2.1.e; P5.2.1.g*; P5.2.1.h*; P5.3.1.a; P5.3.2.a; P5.3.4.a; P5.3.4.b*;</p> <p>WP6 - P6.1.1.b; P6.1.1.c; P6.1.1.d; P6.2.4.b; P6.2.4.c; P6.2.4.d; P6.3.1.a; P6.3.1.b; P6.3.2.a; P6.4.2.d*; P6.4.4.a;</p> <p>WP7 – T7.1;</p> <p>WP8 – T8.1;</p>
<p>004: Actively foster regulatory uptake of PARC knowledge</p>		<p>WP2 – T2.2; T2.3;</p> <p>WP3 – T3.1; T3.2; T3.3;</p> <p>WP4 – P4.1.c; P4.1.1.3.a*; P4.1.1.3.c*; P4.1.1.4.d; P4.1.3.1.a; P4.1.3.1.b*; P4.1.4.2.a; P4.2.a; P4.2.b; P4.3.4.a;</p> <p>WP5 - P5.1.1.a; P5.1.1.b; P5.1.1.c; P5.1.1.d*; P5.1.2.a; P5.1.2.b; P5.1.2.c*; P5.2.a*; P5.2.1.a; P5.2.1.c; P5.2.1.d; P5.2.1.e; P5.2.1.f*; P5.2.1.g*; P5.2.1.h*; P5.3.1.a; P5.3.2.a; P5.3.4.a; P5.3.4.b*;</p> <p>WP6 - P6.1.1.a; P6.1.1.b; P6.1.1.c; P6.1.1.d; P6.1.1.e*; P6.1.1.f*; P6.2.1.b; P6.2.3.a; P6.2.4.b; P6.2.4.c; P6.2.4.d; P6.3.1.a; P6.3.1.b; P6.3.2.a; P6.4.1.a; P6.4.1.b; P6.4.1.d*; P6.4.2.a; P6.4.2.b; P6.4.2.d*; P6.4.2.e*; P6.4.3.a; P6.4.3.b; P6.4.4.a; P6.4.4.d; P6.4.4.e;</p> <p>WP7 – T7.2;</p> <p>WP8 – T8.3;</p>
<p>005: Promote cooperation with other R&I initiatives</p>		<p>WP2 – T2.2;</p> <p>WP3 – T3.3;</p> <p>WP4 – P4.1.c; P4.1.1.3.a*; P4.1.3.1.a; P4.1.3.1.b*; P4.1.4.2.a; P4.2.a; P4.2.b P4.2.c, P4.3.1.b; P4.3.1.c; P4.3.1.d; P4.3.2.a; P4.3.2.b; P4.3.3.a; P4.3.3.b;</p> <p>WP5 - P5.1.1.a; P5.1.1.b; P5.1.1.d*; P5.1.2.a; P5.1.2.b; P5.1.2.c*; P5.2.a*; P5.2.1.a; P5.2.1.b; P5.2.1.c; P5.2.1.d; P5.2.1.e; P5.2.1.g*; P5.2.1.h*; P5.3.1.a; P5.3.2.a; P5.3.4.a; P5.3.4.b*;</p>

		<p>WP6 - P6.1.1.a; P6.1.1.b; P6.1.1.c; P6.1.1.d; P6.1.1.e*; P6.1.1.f*; P6.2.1.a; P6.2.2.a; P6.2.4.a; P6.2.4.b; P6.2.4.d; P6.3.1.a; P6.3.1.b; P6.3.2.a; P6.4.1.a; P6.4.1.b; P6.4.1.d*; P6.4.2.a; P6.4.2.b; P6.4.2.d*; P6.4.2.e*; P6.4.3.a; P6.4.3.b; P6.4.4.a; P6.4.4.d; P6.4.4.e;</p> <p>WP8 – T8.1;</p> <p>WP9 – T9.1; T9.2; T9.3; T9.4;</p>
	<p>006: Communicate & disseminate PARC knowledge to increase citizen's understanding/awareness of chemical RA</p>	<p>WP2 – T2.2; T2.3;</p> <p>WP3 – T3.2;</p> <p>WP4 – P4.1.c; P4.1.1.3.a*; P4.1.1.3.b*; P4.1.1.3.c*; P4.1.1.4.c; P4.1.3.1.a; P4.1.3.1.b*; P4.1.4.2.a; P4.2.a; P4.3.1.a; P4.3.1.c; P4.3.2.a; P4.3.2.b; P4.3.4.a;</p> <p>WP5 - P5.1.1.a; P5.1.1.b; P5.1.1.d*; P5.1.2.a; P5.1.2.b; P5.2.1.a; P5.2.1.c; P5.2.1.d; P5.2.1.e; P5.2.1.f*; P5.2.1.g*; P5.2.1.h*; P5.3.1.a; P5.3.2.a; P5.3.4.a;</p> <p>WP6 - P6.2.1.b; P6.2.3.a; P6.2.4.c; P6.2.4.d; P6.3.1.a; P6.3.1.b; P6.3.2.a; P6.4.3.a; P6.4.3.b;</p> <p>WP7 – T7.1; T7.2; T7.3</p>
<p>S02 - carry out a joint R&I programme to respond to the agreed priorities in chemical RA</p>	<p>007: Develop/ implement annual R&I work programmes to respond to identified needs in chemical RA</p>	<p>WP1 – T1.1;</p> <p>WP2 – T2.1;</p> <p>WP4 - P4.1.1.2.a; P4.1.1.3.a*; P4.1.1.4.c; P4.1.1.4.d; P4.1.3.1.a; P4.1.3.1.b*; P4.1.3.3.a; P4.2.a; P4.2.b; P4.2.c; P4.3.1.c; P4.3.1.d; P4.3.2.a; P4.3.2.b; P4.3.3.b;</p> <p>WP5 - P5.1.1.a; P5.1.1.b; P5.1.1.c; P5.1.1.d*; P5.1.2.a; P5.1.2.b; P5.1.2.c*; P5.2.a*; P5.2.1.a; P5.2.1.b; P5.2.1.c; P5.2.1.d; P5.2.1.e; P5.2.1.h*; P5.3.1.a; P5.3.2.a; P5.3.4.a</p> <p>WP6 - P6.1.1.a; P6.1.1.b; P6.1.1.c; P6.1.1.d; P6.1.1.f*; P6.2.1.a; P6.2.2.a; P6.2.4.a; P6.2.4.b; P6.2.4.c; P6.2.4.d; P6.3.1.a; P6.3.1.b; P6.3.2.a; P6.4.2.c; P6.4.2.d*; P6.4.2.e*; P6.4.3.a; P6.4.3.b; P6.4.4.c; P6.4.4.c; P6.4.4.e;</p> <p>WP8 – T8.2;</p>
	<p>008: Develop monitoring capacity by extending the HBM platform created in HBM4EU and supporting the provision of environmental and</p>	<p>WP4 - P4.1.1.2.a; P4.1.1.3.a*; P4.1.1.3.b*; P4.1.1.3.c*; P4.1.1.4.c; P4.1.1.4.d; P4.1.3.1.a; <u>P4.1.3.1.b*</u>; P4.1.3.3.a; P4.1.4.2.a; P4.1.5.a;</p>

	<p>multisource data for regulatory purposes</p>	<p>P4.2.a; P4.2.c; P4.3.1.c; P4.3.1.d; P4.3.2.a; P4.3.2.c; P4.3.2.b; P4.3.3.a; P4.3.3.b; P4.3.4.a;</p> <p>WP5 - P5.1.1.d*;</p> <p>WP6 - P6.2.1.a; P6.4.4.a; P6.4.4.c; P6.4.4.c;</p> <p>WP9 - T9.1; T9.2; T9.3;</p>
	<p>0010: Implement FAIR data practices and enhance innovation in complex data analysis for RA</p>	<p>WP4 - P4.1.c; P4.1.1.2.a; P4.1.1.3.a*;</p> <p>P4.1.1.3.b*; P4.1.1.3.c*; P4.1.3.1.a;</p> <p>P4.1.3.1.b*; P4.1.3.3.a; P4.1.4.2.a; P4.2.a; P4.2.b; P4.2.c; P4.3.1.c; P4.3.1.d; P4.3.3.a; P4.3.4.a;</p> <p>WP5 - P5.1.1.a; P5.1.1.b; P5.1.1.d*; P5.1.2.a; P5.1.2.b; P5.1.2.c*; P5.2.1.a; P5.2.1.b; P5.2.1.c; P5.2.1.d; P5.2.1.e; P5.2.1.f*; P5.2.1.g*;</p> <p>P5.2.1.h*; P5.3.1.a; P5.3.2.a; P5.3.4.a;</p> <p>P5.3.4.b*;</p> <p>WP6 - P6.1.1.a; P6.1.1.b; P6.1.1.c; P6.1.1.d;</p> <p>P6.1.1.e*; P6.2.1.a; P6.2.2.a; P6.2.4.a; P6.2.4.b; P6.2.4.c; P6.2.4.d; P6.3.1.a; P6.3.1.b; P6.3.2.a; P6.4.1.a; P6.4.1.b; P6.4.1.d*; P6.4.2.e*;</p> <p>P6.4.3.a; P6.4.3.b; P6.4.4.a; P6.4.4.c; P6.4.4.c; P6.4.4.d;</p> <p>WP7 - P7.2.2.a; P7.2.2.b; P7.3.3</p>
	<p>0012: Develop models and innovative concepts for RA and deliver toolboxes to promote their acceptability and uptake</p>	<p>WP4 - P4.1.c; P4.1.1.3.a*; P4.1.1.4.c; P4.1.3.1.a;</p> <p>P4.1.3.1.b*; P4.1.3.3.a; P4.2.b; P4.2.c; P4.3.1.c; P4.3.1.d; P4.3.2.a; P4.3.3.a; P4.3.3.b;</p> <p>WP5 - P5.1.1.c; P5.1.1.d*; P5.1.2.b; P5.1.2.c*;</p> <p>P5.2.1.a; P5.2.1.b; P5.2.1.c; P5.2.1.d; P5.2.1.e;</p> <p>P5.2.1.f*; P5.2.1.g*; P5.2.1.h*; P5.3.1.a;</p> <p>P5.3.2.a; P5.3.4.a; P5.3.4.b*;</p> <p>WP6 - P6.1.1.a; P6.1.1.b; P6.1.1.c; P6.1.1.d;</p> <p>P6.1.1.e*; P6.1.1.f*; P6.2.1.a; P6.2.1.b; P6.2.2.a;</p> <p>P6.2.3.a; P6.3.1.a; P6.3.1.b; P6.3.2.a; P6.4.1.a;</p> <p>P6.4.1.b; P6.4.1.d*; P6.4.2.b; P6.4.2.e*;</p> <p>P6.4.3.a; P6.4.3.b; P6.4.4.a; P6.4.4.c; P6.4.4.c;</p> <p>P6.4.4.d; P6.4.4.e;</p> <p>WP7 - T7.3</p> <p>WP8 - T8.1; T8.3;</p>
<p>S03 - access to R&I capacities required to implement</p>	<p>009: Develop tools to facilitate the acceptance and use of PARC's results in regulatory RA processes and support (existing) standardisation and validation</p>	<p>WP4 - P4.1.c; P4.1.1.3.a*; P4.1.1.4.d;</p> <p>P4.1.3.1.a; P4.1.3.1.b*; P4.1.3.3.a; P4.2.b;</p> <p>P4.3.1.b; P4.3.1.c; P4.3.2.c; P4.3.3.a;</p>

innovative chemical RA	processes for innovative approaches to RA.	<p>WP5 – P5.1.1.c; P5.1.1.d*; P5.1.2.a; P5.1.2.b; P5.2.a*; P5.2.1.a; P5.2.1.b; P5.2.1.c; P5.2.1.d; P5.2.1.e, P5.2.1.f*; P5.2.1.g*; P5.2.1.h*; P5.3.1.a; P5.3.2.a; P5.3.4.a; P5.3.4.b*;</p> <p>WP6 - P6.1.1.a; P6.1.1.b; P6.1.1.c; P6.1.1.d; P6.1.1.e*; P6.1.1.f*; P6.2.1.b; P6.2.2.a; P6.2.3.a; P6.2.4.b; P6.2.4.d; P6.3.1.a; P6.3.1.b; P6.3.2.a; P6.4.1.a; P6.4.1.d*; P6.4.2.a; P6.4.2.b; P6.4.2.c; P6.4.2.d*; P6.4.2.e*; P6.4.3.a; P6.4.3.b; P6.4.4.c; P6.4.4.d; P6.4.4.e;</p>
	OO11 : Consolidate existing and develop new networks of laboratories and research centres	<p>WP4 – P4.1.c; P4.1.1.3.a*; P4.1.1.4.d; P4.1.4.2.a; P4.2.a; P4.2.c; P4.3.1.b; P4.3.1.c; P4.3.1.d; P4.3.2.a; P4.3.2.c*; P4.3.2.b; P4.3.3.a; P4.3.4.a;</p> <p>WP5 - P5.1.1.a; P5.1.1.b; P5.1.1.d*; P5.1.2.a; P5.1.2.b; P5.2.a*; P5.2.1.a; P5.2.1.b; P5.2.1.c; P5.2.1.d; P5.2.1.e; P5.2.1.f*; P5.2.1.g*; P5.2.1.h*; P5.3.2.a; P5.3.4.a; P5.3.4.b*;</p> <p>WP6 - P6.1.1.a; P6.1.1.b; P6.1.1.c; P6.1.1.d; P6.1.1.e*; P6.4.1.d*;</p> <p>WP9 – T9.1; T9.2; T9.3;</p>
	OO13 : Build capacities by developing and carrying out training and exchange programmes in chemical RA	<p>WP4 - P4.1.1.3.a*; P4.1.1.3.c*; P4.1.1.4.d; P4.1.3.1.b*; P4.1.4.2.a; P4.3.1.c; P4.3.2.b; P4.3.4.a;</p> <p>WP5 - P5.2.a*; P5.2.1.b; P5.2.1.f*;</p> <p>WP6 - P6.2.1.a; P6.2.1.b; P6.2.3.a; P6.2.4.b; P6.2.4.d; P6.3.1.a; P6.3.1.b; P6.3.2.a; P6.4.2.b; P6.4.4.d;</p> <p>WP7 - P7.2.2.b;</p> <p>WP9 – T9.1; T9.4;</p>

* = Projects proposals submitted for a start in Y4.

1.3 Correspondence with part B of the proposal

For this fourth AWP, the actions initiated in the form of projects, case studies and those activities corresponding to recurrent tasks are presented by WP and tasks using the structure described in Part B. AWPY4 has been designed to be intrinsically linked and complementary to the seven-year activity plan (Description of Action or DoA). It will provide the necessary basis on which to continue building the Partnership in the following years. This is true for the specific challenges, the scope of PARC as well as for the activities that will be initiated during the fourth year of PARC.

1.4 Update of the PARC Project Portfolio

The PARC Project Portfolio constitutes an overview of the PARC Projects, providing detailed information on timelines, outputs, etc. The PARC Project Portfolio is administered by the Coordinator and updated each year to integrate new Projects and follow those that have been implemented. The Project Portfolio annexed to this 4th AWP is a compilation of all projects' summaries concerned that are already implemented and those additional ones that have been proposed and reviewed under task 2.1 and validated to start during the 4th year of PARC.

Table 2: New projects Year 4 - 18 Projects have been submitted to be started Y4

Project ID	Schedule
P4.1.1.3.a_Y4_PFAS Mother milk_LNS_BPI	M37-M81
P4.1.1.3.b_Y4_PFASChildren_SpF	M37-M81
P4.1.1.3.c_Y4_TimePatternEU_VITO	M37-M72
P4.1.3.1.b_Y4_Health-based-IA-GV_LNS_NCPHP	M37-M81
P4.2.d_Y4_Siloxanes_AU_INERIS	M37-M60
P5.1.1.d_Y4_PlasticLeach_NIPH	M37-M81
P5.1.2.c_Y4_TG+MP_ANSES	M37-M60
P5.2.a_Y4_RegNAMs_ANSES	M37-M81
P5.2.1.f_Y4_DART-ED_DTU	M37-M81
P5.2.1.g_Y4_DIT-NAM_INSERTM	M37-M81
P5.2.1.h_Y4_SDHEPATOX_ANSES	M37-M60
P5.3.1.b_Y4_grOMICS_UL-LACDR	M37-M81
P5.3.4.b_Y4_RESUPT_RIVM	M37-M81
P6.1.1.e_Y4_FISH-THSD_Uantwerpen	M37-M81
P6.1.1.f_Y4_HumanRelevance_RIVM	M37-M81
P6.4.1.d_Y4_RE-MIX_UBA_Eawag	M37-M81
P6.4.2.d_Y4_RegulatoryNAMs_ISS	M37-M81
P6.4.2.e_Y4_READYAI_UNIBAS	M37-M81

Table 3: 26 Projects and case studies planned to end Year 4

Project ID	Schedule
P4.1.1.4.c_Y1_HealthCareSurvey_TTL_SRU	M1-M48
P4.1.1.4.d_Y1_OccupWaste_ENSP_TTL	M1-M48

P4.3.2.a_Y1_H01-Perinatal exposure_INRAE	M1-M48
P4.3.3.a_Y1_E01-Wastewater based epidemiology_UFZ-UBATH	M1-M48
P4.3.4.a_Y2_F02-Food items exposure_ANSES	M13-M48
P5.1.1.a_Y1_Toxins_BfR_UNIVIE	M1-M48
P5.2.1.b_Y1_MD-EDC_BfR	M1-M48
P5.2.1.c_Y1_EDThDisruption_DTU	M1-M48
P5.2.1.d_Y1_Immunotox_Inserm	M1-M48
P5.2.1.e_Y1_DNT-ANT_UFZ_IUF_NIPH	M1-M48
P5.3.1.a_Y1_SystemsToxicology_UL-LACDR	M1-M48
P5.3.2.a_Y1_AOPDevelopment_Inserm	M1-M48
P5.3.4.a_Y1_PBK_Kinetics_Fraunhofer	M1-M48
P6.2.1.b_Y1_Aggregate_AnSES	M1-M48
P6.2.2.a_Y1_PBPk_INERIS_AUTH	M1-M48
P6.2.3.a_Y1_RealLifeMixtures_RIVM	M1-M48
P6.3.1.a_Y1_SubstanceRA_SU	M1-M48
P6.3.1.a_Y1_SubstanceRA_SU_CS12_MethodOSOA_SU	M1-M42
P6.3.1.b_Y1_EffectRA_BPI	M1-M48
P6.3.1.b_Y1_EffectRA_BPI_CS11_GenotoxCarc_ISS	M1-M48
P6.3.1.b_Y1_EffectRA_BPI_CS17_ED-in vitro_BPI	M1-M48
P6.3.1.b_Y1_EffectRA_BPI_CS18_ED-classes_BPI	M1-M48
P6.3.2.a_Y1_ToolsRA_SU	M1-M48
P6.3.2.a_Y1_ToolsRA_SU_CS20_Y3_PESTNAM_ISS	M25-M48
P6.4.1.a_Y1_OPREMIXCS1_BRUNEL_RWTH	M1-M40
P6.4.1.b_Y1_MONAMMIXCS2_UFZ	M1-M40

Table 4: 23 Projects and case studies initially planned to end Y3 or Y4 that requested an extension

Project ID	Initial Schedule	Comments	Rationale for projects that have been extended
P4.1.3.1.a_Y1_DerivationofHBM-GVs_UBA	M1-M36	This project up to M81 has been broken down at M36 to assess what has been achieved. Request for an extension until M81	The justification for the project as such and the continuation is as follows: a consistent and comprehensible health-based interpretation of HBM results is required within the framework of PARC and beyond in order to be able to use HBM to provide meaningful policy advice on chemicals and product regulation. The derivation of further additional HBM-GVs/HBM-EECRs is associated with additional time and additional costs, which were, however, already provided for and estimated in the original planning of the project.
P4.1.4.2.a_Y1_DataAnalysisHBM4EU_VITO	M1-M36	Request for an extension from M37 to M48	The actions related to the initiation of the statistical analysis, the geospatial analysis and the training of the data owners took more time than anticipated. This should not affect the overall project budget.
P4.2.a_Y1_ENVMonitoringPilotSurvey_INERIS_AU	M1-M36	Request for a limited extension from M37 to M42 (6 months)	The third part of the project (extensive collection of existing PFAS data to establish a European baseline) has been more time consuming than expected due to curation work on heterogeneous data sets. No impact on the budget. All activities will be performed as planned
P4.2.b_Y2_Monitoringframe_AU_INERIS	M13-M30	Request for a limited extension from M31 to M36 (6 months)	The working group took more time than anticipated to align with the concept of prioritisation, to agree on common terminology, and establish a common understanding. No impact on the budget and on actions planned.
P5.1.2.b_Y1_BPAalternatives_BPI_MU	M1-M42	Request for a limited extension from M43 to M48 (6 months)	The experimental work has started with a delay mainly due to time-consuming procedures followed for chemicals order (centralized order for all PARC partners) and difficulties faced by several partners in hiring personnel. No impact on the budget and on the planned actions
P6.1.1.c_Y1_IATA_GENTOX_Sciensano	M1-M36	Request for an extension from M37 to M48	During the first year of the project, many meetings and discussions with the partners were organized to divide the work and harmonize the methodology. It resulted in some delays. A small increase in the budget (<15%) for 3 partners is required.
P6.1.1.d_Y1_IATA_STOT_UL-LACDR	M1-M36	Request for an extension from M37 to M48	The delay is partially related to a later start of postdocs and PhD students appointed in the project and some actions related to transcriptomics data took longer than expected. No additional budget is required.

P6.2.1.a_Y1_SourcetoDose_VITO	M1-M36	Request for a limited extension from M37 to M42 (6 months)	The additional 6 months will allow us to finalize case studies and publications, and to integrate with 6.2.1b, which will benefit the collaboration in Y5 project on activity 6.2.1. The requested additional budget is 11 % of the initial budget.
P6.3.1.b_Y1_EffectRA_BPI (M1-M48)_CS10_ED-cosmetics_VUB	M8-M32	Request for an extension from M33 to M43	Delays related to human resources reasons in the project lead team. The additional time required will not lead to any modification of the objectives of the project, nor will there be any change in the financial demand on PARC.
P6.3.1.b_Y1_EffectRA_BPI (M1-M48)_CS15_DNT_SU	M1-M36	Request for an extension from M37 to M48	Modification of the objectives of the project: evaluation of a second behavioural outcome, i.e. the auditory startle reflex, in our collection of 54 guideline DNT studies. Development of graphical tools and statistical code to facilitate this. Request of Extension of budget > 15%.
P6.3.2.a_Y1_ToolsRA_SU (M1-M48)_CS1_CARB_SYKE	M1-M36	Request for an extension from M37 to M48	Necessary to deepen the comparative analysis on PFAS regulatory thresholds in food and water after 2 years by evaluating the potential development needs of regulatory RA of PFAS and implications to RM, also considering additional regulatory frameworks and their interlinkages. No extension of budget.
P6.3.2.a_Y1_ToolsRA_SU(M1-M48)_CS4_SecPoisoning_INERIS	M2-M38	Request for an extension from M39 to M48	Delays related to both technical and human resources reasons. Regarding technical reasons, it was planned first to use rodenticides which are recognised as bio accumulative substances. Then it was considered to align the selection of chemicals with the substances used in CS07 (covering all other environmental compartments). No extension of the budget is required.
P6.3.2.a_Y1_ToolsRA_SU (M1-M48)_CS7_REGPREP_EAWAG	M1-M36	First proposal was to have 2 project phases: 1st phase M1-M36, 2nd phase M37-M81	As outlined in the original description of our case study, the case study was planned to have 2 phases: a first project phase on surface water and sediment and a second one on soil and air. Soil and air would be during the last 4 year. The budget was already provided for and estimated in the original planning of the case study.
P6.3.2.a_Y1_ToolsRA_SU (M1-M48)_CS8_OccupReproDev_KI	M1-M36	Request for an extension from M37 to M48	Delays related to human resources reasons in the project lead team. Hence, to get additional time to work on analysis of findings and write up the results an extension is requested. No additional budget is requested.
P6.3.2.a_Y1_ToolsRA_SU (M1-M48)_CS16_UncertaintyRA_ULUND	M1-M36	Request for an extension from M37 to M48	The participants have not been able to work as originally planned in the case study. No extension of budget is required.
P6.4.2.b_Y1_NGRApractice_VKM_NIPH	M1-M36	This project up to M81 has been broken down at M36 to assess what has been	The project was originally developed for the whole 7-year PARC period. To be able to complete the different parts of the project, request for this

		achieved. Request for an extension until M81	extension to be able to finalise the ongoing work in the best way. The budget included in the original 7-year proposal will remain the same.
P6.4.4.a_Y1_CRNCS1_KEMI	M1-M42	This project up to M81 has been broken down at M42 to assess what has been achieved. Request for an extension until M81	This project explores and develops new frameworks for risk characterisation that support system-based approaches to RAERA of chemicals (ERA). In years 4-7, PARC 6.4.4.a will continue to build collaborations, platforms, and engage stakeholders to ensure that projects “Design the right things” before “Design things right.” The budget included in the original 7-year proposal will remain the same.
P6.4.4.b_Y1_PPPEXPCS2_RPTU	M1-M36	This project up to M81 has been broken up into 2 phases. The first phase was planned to end M24 but was extended until M36. Request for an extension until M81	Extending the project duration will allow to realise the planned objectives in the three major areas, facilitate the improvement of the scientific basis of ERA with the aim to streamline the approval process and provide the (exposure) building blocks for the prioritization process in the RA in the EU towards a systems-based ERA of PPP. Additional budget for project management at RPTU in the amount of 48+ PMs and extension of budget for project partners for Y4-7.
P6.4.4.c_Y1_PPPEFFCS3_UFZ	M1-M36	This project up to M81 has been broken down at M36 to assess what has been achieved. Request for an extension until M81	This project explores and develop new frameworks for risk characterisation that support system-based approaches to RA by expanding the current ERA approaches. Continuous dialogue is needed from including regulatory risk assessors, to managers and risk manager at regulatory agencies and eventually also policy makers. The budget included in the original 7-year proposal will remain the same.
P6.4.4.d_Y1_PPPBENCHCS4_UKOLD	M1-M42	This project up to M81 has been broken down at M42 to assess what has been achieved. Request for an extension until M81	PARC 6.4.4.d focused on identifying products rejected under the re-authorisation procedure of 1107/2009 and scrutinised the factors that led to their rejection. A conceptual framework for benchmarking PPP ERA has been developed. The alignment with stakeholder activities coordinated by project 6.4.4.a and with other PARC projects will ensure regulatory relevance and uptake of the benchmarking results and novel methods. The budget included in the original 7-year proposal will remain the same.
P6.4.4.e_Y1_PPPOSCS5_ISCIII	M1-M42	This project up to M81 has been broken down at M42 to assess what has been achieved. Request for an extension until M81	The main aim of this project is moving the ERA paradigm from single chemical-crop combination to landscape-based ERA integrating landscape structures and aggregated (several crops) and combined (several pesticides) exposures into the current RA methods. The conceptual model has been already published in a high-impact scientific journal and eight case

			studies, four terrestrial and four aquatic, have been selected and are ongoing. Considering the achievements, it is proposed to continue with the implementation of the case studies and the integration of the information generated through the case studies, the interaction with the other projects and through the feedback from the publication. In line with the continuation of the project through this request for extension, there is a need for confirming the budget allocation for M43 to M84.
P7.2.2.a_Y1_chemicals-in-environment_MU_VITO	M1-M36	Request for a limited extension from M37 to M42 (6 months)	A need to extend the duration of the metadata schema workshops has been identified by the project partners to thoroughly discuss the metadata requirements and structure for chemical occurrence data. The list of planned actions remains unchanged. No impact on the budget
P7.2.2.b_Y1_HBMdatasets_VITO	M1-M42	Request for a limited extension from M43 to M48 (6 months)	Due to reorganisation of the project team at VITO (new project leader, people leaving and newly hired in the team), some of the actions will be prolonged with 6 months. No impact on the budget.

2. Annual Work Programme Activities

2.1 Annual Work Programme

2.1.1 Structure of the Annual Work Programme

The structure of the AWPY4 is based on the work packages (WP) description of transversal activities as well as more specific activities that are related to projects.

2.1.2 Timing of the different programmed activities and their components

The fourth AWP will cover a duration of 12 months (M37-M48) from 1 May 2025 to 30 April 2026. All WPs will be active in Y4.

2.2 Detailed work description

For all the WPs, the full description of work by projects is available in the PARC Project Portfolio in Annex II.

Table 2.2.a: Annual Work Programme Activities for each set of activities

WP N°	WP1	Lead Beneficiary	ANSES
WP title	Coordination and Management		
Partner N°	1	1.1	1.2
Partner short name	ANSES	INSERM	INRAE
PM/partner 1	122.7	0.5	0.4
Start	M37	End	M48
	1.4	1.5	1.6
	2	1.7	1.8
	SpF	3.1	3.2
	EAA	3.3	3.4
	3	3.5	3.6
	AGES	3.7	3.8
	4	3.9	3.10
	VITO	3.11	3.12
	4.2	3.13	3.14
	5	3.15	3.16
	6	3.17	3.18
	7	3.19	3.20
	MOH-CY/SGL	3.21	3.22
	8	3.23	3.24
	MU	3.25	3.26
	DEPA	3.27	3.28
	10	3.29	3.30
	10.1	3.31	3.32
	11	3.33	3.34
	12	3.35	3.36
	13	3.37	3.38
	14	3.39	3.40
	15	3.41	3.42
	16	3.43	3.44
	17	3.45	3.46
	18	3.47	3.48
	20	3.49	3.50
	20.6	3.51	3.52
	21	3.53	3.54
	22	3.55	3.56
	24	3.57	3.58
	25	3.59	3.60
	25.2	3.61	3.62
	25.4	3.63	3.64
	25.6	3.65	3.66
	25.7	3.67	3.68
	26	3.69	3.70
	26.4	3.71	3.72
	27	3.73	3.74
	29	3.75	3.76
	29.1	3.77	3.78
	30	3.79	3.80
	31	3.81	3.82
	32	3.83	3.84
	33	3.85	3.86
	34	3.87	3.88
	34.5	3.89	3.90
	35	3.91	3.92
	35.6	3.93	3.94
	35.7	3.95	3.96
	35.9	3.97	3.98
	36	3.99	4.00
	36.2	4.01	4.02
	37	4.03	4.04
	50	4.05	4.06
	59	4.07	4.08
	61	4.09	4.10
	64	4.11	4.12
	IPHMNE	4.13	4.14

¹ PMs have been allocated to the Grant Signatories for the management of their affiliated entities and their role of NHCP. In some cases, the Grant Signatories do not have any PM as they do not manage any AEs and are not NHCP in PARC.

Objectives

The main goal of WP1 is to ensure the coordination, the strategic scientific and administrative management of PARC, including impact evaluation and the ethical issues management, in cooperation with the different governance bodies of the Partnership. The specific objectives of WP1 for year 4 are:

- Task 1.1: Maintain an effective management and governance framework for the PARC consortium in compliance with the legal, ethical, financial and administrative rules and regulations and in compliance with the agreed timelines ensuring the highest quality standards;
- Task 1.2: Manage the tools to ensure the Partnership's progress and guide the PARC consortium and its activities in maintaining the course set out in the Grant Agreement, to achieve milestones and produce the agreed deliverables, within the defined budget and abiding by the highest quality standards;
- Task 1.3: Maintain and update the monitoring framework for the Partnership;
- Task 1.4: Ensure communication and collaboration between the Data and Ethics Protection Board (DEPB), notably composed of Ethics and Data contacts points from WP4, 5 and 7 and the PARC Consortium, and ensure that the PARC Participants follow the Ethics Charter in order to reduce and/or address ethical issues that may arise during the Partnership implementation.

Description of work

Task 1.1: Overall executive management and support of the Partnership

Leader: ANSES (FR)

Partners: All GSB members and WP co-leaders (as stated above)

The activities of this task are managed by the PARC Coordination Team (CT) composed of the PARC Coordinator, the Deputy-Coordinator and the ANSES Project managers. The PARC CT ensures an efficient management of the PARC activities and associated administrative and budgetary issues.

Management of the consortium and organisation of the Governance Bodies meetings:

- Ensuring the respect and proper implementation of the "Terms of reference and rules of procedure" by the PARC GB and of the Consortium Agreement (CA) by the PARC GSB in compliance with the agreed timelines.
- Setting the dates and organising the Governance Bodies meetings (MB, GB and GSB) to take place during the 4th year of PARC.

For the GB:

- Meetings of the GB are foreseen in April, September and November 2025, among them one physical meeting. The objectives will be to provide input and opinions on the PARC progression and discuss progress, indicators, relevant policy/regulatory outputs, sustainability, as well as the strategy for the AWPY5. Further to initial contact done in October 2024, representatives from Montenegro have been invited to attend the November 2024 GB meeting as observers.
- Additional virtual GB meeting(s) and/or written consultation(s) (through forms, poll, and emails) may be organised on other specific topics if needed.

- Ahead of each GB meeting, the coordination team will prepare working documents with the GB co-chairs for each topic planned to be addressed during the meeting. These documents are tailored to fit with the GB level of understanding needed.
- Non-mandatory GB workshops will also be organised to provide the opportunity to develop further thematics of interest to the GB.

For the GSB:

- A meeting of the GSB will be organised end of 2025 in order to discuss and validate the AWPY5 and its associated budget.
- Additional virtual GSB meeting(s) and/or written consultation(s) (through forms, poll, and emails) may be organised, if needed.

For the MB:

- Monthly MB meetings will be organised throughout the year, with two physical meetings, including one back-to back to a physical GB meeting.
- The other MB meetings will take place online.

Follow-up of the Partnership's activities and budget:

- Managing the information system (EMDESK) for the monitoring of the budget and help the financial administrators of the PARC institutions to ensure a proper and efficient use of the system.
- Granting access rights to the PARC Consortium SharePoint to new individuals involved in PARC when requested in order to ensure that all individuals involved in PARC have access to internal working documents and calendar of meetings and actions to be done for the year 4 of PARC.
- Assisting participants on specific administrative and financial issues.
- Updating on request the Partnership handbook describing the internal requirements and specifying the common rules to be followed by all PARC Participants.

Contractual documents generated by PARC activities:

- Pursuing the preparation of contractual documents generated by PARC activities, when relevant: Intellectual Property Rights (IPR), Material Transfer Agreement (MTA) and Data Transfer Agreement (DTA); preparing, signing, and managing, when relevant, other PARC related agreements (e.g., confidentiality and collaboration agreements) that will arise during the 4th year.
- Establishing PARC collaboration agreements with external initiatives or organisations to support synergies
- Ensuring the follow-up of the collaboration agreements signed with external initiatives or organisations, especially with JRC and NORMAN, through dedicated meetings.

Communication:

- Updating the internal and external communication rules of the Partnership handbook, in collaboration with WP3, when relevant.
- Providing articles and news items to feed the PARC website in close collaboration with the WP3.
- Providing rules and repositories to the PARC Participants for internal and external communication.
- Providing WP1 bulletins every 3 months in order to provide information about recent and ongoing general and WP1 processes.

Task 1.2: Scientific steering and implementation of Annual Work Plans

Leader: ANSES (FR)

Partners: All WP co-leaders, NHCPs, NHCs,

The activities of this task are managed by the PARC CT in close collaboration with the MB, GB, GSB, National Hub Coordinators (NHCs) and the CL/MLs. The MB specifically plays an active role to ensure the efficient setting up of the monitoring of the scientific progress and of the overall strategy of the Partnership, making sure that the PARC activities, resources and AWP are aligned. It also ensures the relevance of the PARC work plan with regard to external events with WP3 (projects, initiatives, EU policies linked to the PARC objectives).

Scientific steering:

- Moderating the MB meetings and ensuring the cross-cutting scientific links between WPs
- Assisting the PARC NHCs in coordinating the NH contributions and activities in PARC
- Proposing amendments of the GA or solutions / redress actions to resolve any issues, and escalating unresolvable risks or issues to the relevant boards.
- Aligning work programmes to policy needs as defined by EU Agencies and partner countries.

Synergies:

- Ensuring the follow-up of opportunities for synergies (with WP3) (projects, initiatives, EU policies linked to the PARC objectives, National, EU and international initiatives ...)

Preparation and submission of AWPY5 with the Project Portfolio in Annex, Periodic Technical and Financial Report for the second period of PARC and ASRY4:

- Coordinating the preparation, collection and submission to HaDEA of:
 - The Periodic Technical and Financial Report (PTFR) for the second period of PARC (M19-M36) in June 2025.
 - The AWPY5 and updated PARC Project Portfolio in Annex, in December 2025.
 - The ASRY4 in December 2025.

The preparation of those reports will be done in close collaboration with the MB members, the Task co-leaders, the Project managers, the Task 2.1 partners, and in consultation with the relevant PARC governance bodies (see task 1.1 for the organisation of the Governance Bodies meetings).

The PARC CT will organise a review meeting with HaDEA and experts involved in the review of the 2nd PTFR after its submission and assessment.

Follow-up of deliverables, additional deliverables and milestones:

- Ensuring respect of the different deadlines, and achievement of milestones, deliverables and additional deliverables according to the established review process.

Task 1.3: Impact evaluation and Monitoring of the performance indicators of the Partnership

Co-Leaders: DOMG (BE), INSA (PT)

Partners: All WP co-leaders

The monitoring frame and set of indicators will be further refined to ensure the key useful and impact-generating results and relevant target groups are clearly identified in order to maximise PARC's impact and exploitation.

Activities to be performed in the 4th year include:

- Identifying potential barriers that could undermine the achievement of desired outcomes and impacts.
- Continuing the inter-tasks meeting with WP2 – task 2.3 on sustainability –T4.1 – P4.1.5.a_Y1_SustainHBMSys_VITO – to continue the discussion on the sustainability of PARC in support of sustainable indicators.
- Finalise the definition of impact indicators and collecting information for the outcome and impact indicators in collaboration with MB, GSB and GB, NHs and stakeholders.
- In close collaboration with WP3, task 3.2, continuing the development of easily interpretable indicator leaflets and communication elements on outcome and impact indicators that provide and communicate the link between the objectives, key results and (expected) impacts of PARC.
- Presenting the results of the indicator framework (12 output indicators, 8 outcome indicators and 8 impact indicators) to the MB/GB and disseminating these among WPs for awareness.
- Continuing the discussions with the European Environment Agency to ensure input from PARC in, and synergies with, the Chemical Strategy for Sustainability (CSS) indicator framework being developed by the EC.
- Preparing and submitting D1.11 Revised list of indicators (M40).

Task 1.4: Ethics framework

Co-Leaders: NIJZ (SI), EHESP (FR)

Partners: All WP co-leaders

This task aims at maintaining an ethical perspective throughout all the Partnership’s activities and set up collaborative and constructive processes to ensure ethical considerations are properly taken into account.

Activities to be performed in the 4th year include to:

- Continuing consultations and dialogue between the DEPB and the MB through the WPs’ Ethics contacts points who have been nominated in order to ensure and facilitate the uptake of proper ethics and data protection processes.
- Ensuring that the PARC Participants are aware of and acknowledge the Data and Ethics Protection Policy developed by the PARC CT and the Task 1.4 co-leaders in collaboration with the DEPB during year 1.
- Organising of an internal workshop on Artificial Intelligence to better assess AI use in PARC activities and to ensure they remain in line with ethics requirements and good practices. Other internal workshops may potentially be organised if key ethics issues are identified. Organising at least two DEPB meetings (likely one physical and one online) with the option to schedule extraordinary online meetings if it proves necessary. DEPB members may also be invited to speak during other Governance Bodies meetings (MB, GSB, GB) on ethics and/or data relevant topics.

Deliverables:

D1.11 Revised list of indicators – Leader: DOMG (M40)

D1.12 Mid-term Impact and performance evaluation – Leader: DOMG (M40)

D1.13 Update of the Ethics & Data Protection Policy – Leader: ANSES (M42)

D1.14 ASRY4 – Leader: ANSES (M44)

D1.15 AWP Y5 including PARC Project Portfolio – Leader: ANSES (M44)

Additional Deliverables:

NA

WP N°	WP2	Lead Beneficiary	EAA/EEA
WP title	A common science-policy agenda		
Part ner N°	1	1.1	2
	3	3.6	4.2
	5.2	6	7
	8	10	11
	12	14	15
	15.2	16	16.1
	17	18	21
	22	24	25
	26	26.1	26.2
	26.3	26.4	27
	29	29.2	29.3
	29.4	30	31
	32	34	34.5
	35.7	35.10	36
	36.2	36.3	48
	49	50	52
	59		

Part ner shor t nam e	PM/ part ner	Star t	
ANSES	12.0	M37	
INSERM	4.5		
SpF	3.0		
EAA	4.5		
UG-AT	1.0		
DOMG	1.3		
EV-ILVO	1.0		
GIPH	0.5		
MOH-CY/SGL	0.5		
MU	3.0		
DEPA	0.5		
HB	0.5		
EEA	13.0		
TTL	0.5		
UBA	5.6		
UFZ	1.0		
BfR	18.3		End
Fraunhofer	1.0		
NCPHP	5.5		
UI	1.7		
RSU	0.5		
NPHSL	0.5		
LNS	3.5		
RIVM	0.5		
NIPH	2.0		
IMR	1.0		
STAMI	0.7		
NILU	1.0		
NIVA	0.1		
NIOM	1.5		
INSA	14.0		
DGS	1.0		
ENSP	4.0		
UAVR	1.0		
SZU-SK	1.0		
JSI	0.7		
NIJZ	2.0		
ISCH	0.5		
IISPV	1.0		
KEMI	1.0		
SLU	1.0		
AUTH	36.0		
GGSL	5.0		
NKUA	1.0		
ECHA	24.0		
EFSA	5.0		
UKHSA	1.0		
Cefas-Defra	1.0		
UOB	1.0		

Objectives

The main goal of WP2 is to establish a dialogue and priority-setting process bringing together regulatory entities and RA agencies in Europe (European and national entities and agencies) to develop a strategic R&I agenda for chemicals RA in collaboration with the scientific and regulatory community, to promote the uptake of innovative NGRA methodology into policy and regulatory practice and to ensure the sustainability of the partnership.

The specific objectives of WP2 for year 4 are:

- Task 2.1:
 - o Documenting the prioritisation strategy in a deliverable (D2.13 2nd Mapping of Needs Report, Deadline in M42, 31/10/2025) and through a publication.
 - o Ensuring that the list of potential future activities is well disseminated among the PARC consortium.
 - o Following the implementation of the project review process and providing input for the on-going one, as well as new projects in terms of chemical RA and regulatory and policy needs.
 - o Supporting the PARC Coordination in the elaboration of the PARC AWPY4 including the Project Portfolio.
 - o Preparing scoping documents for the different areas of activities in PARC (whether for group of substances, endpoints of methods), in collaboration with Task 2.2 and chemical and methodology leaders. The scoping documents will be drawn up using the factsheets already produced.
 - o Processing new requests under the Rapid Response Mechanism (RRM).
- Task 2.2:
 - o To establish PARCopedia, the knowledge management and community platform for the Chemical Risk Assessment (CRA) community, launched in November 2023, as a primary web resource for co-creating and discussing knowledge on all matters related to CRA and its innovation, to actively promote the transition. After further developing PARCopedia technically and functionally in PARC Y3, in Y4 particular attention will be paid to increasing the amount of knowledge shared and co-created by the community.

- To actively support the finalisation of the European Commission's (COM) "roadmap towards phasing out animal testing in chemical assessments" via the activity "NGRAroute", engaging with other related projects/activities as well as a broad range of relevant stakeholders/institutions from different sectors, in- and outside of PARC, via participation in the COM roadmap working groups.
- To further develop NGRAroute, in cooperation with WP6 and possibly further WPs, into a platform for the practical implementation of NGRA frameworks integrating human health and the environment into regulatory practice.
- To follow, support, and report on the work being developed within PARC for the priority chemicals and methodologies for the nominated CLs and MLs.

Task 2.3:

- Maintaining the continuous dialogue with the NHCPs and translating their needs into actions,
- To elaborate sustainable frameworks for the prioritized roadmap activities of PARC
- To share sustainability options with the MB and GB, and to further discuss with the relevant DGs and agencies.
-

Description of Programmed Activities

Task 2.1: Priority setting

Co-leaders: ANSES (FR), ECHA (EU), EFSA (EU)

Key Partners: EAA (AT), EEA (EU), UBA (DE), BfR (DE), ISS (IT), GCSL (EL), DGS (PT)

Task 2.1 will ensure the link between the high-level priorities and the activities that will be implemented in PARC through projects providing input in terms of RA and regulatory and policy needs. New projects will have to indicate which need they meet, based on the list of priorities established during the second prioritisation cycle.

Task 2.1 will continue to follow the on-going projects and their outcomes and will apply the review process to new submitted projects, including criteria on the regulatory relevance of the projects. This will ensure that the work currently developed through the projects described in the Project Portfolio, will improve the process for the development of future strategies in terms of policy implementation in Risk Management (RM) and governance of chemicals legislation in Europe and at National level.

Task 2.1 will identify tools to make interlinks with projects within PARC and interactions with projects outside PARC, together with T3.3 (SYNnet) and this will be included in the ASR. It will be done also by reaching out to the project managers of each project, to better engage with other WPs and outside projects/initiatives. The suggestion of having webinars to key external partners as well as policymakers was well received by other management board members. Task 2.1 will also participate whenever possible, in other WPs meetings to ensure an adequate science to policy link with the projects, for example co-organising WP6's meeting in May 2025.

For the projects that require an extension, Task 2.1 will apply the process in case of extension (of time and/or of budget, and/or of the objectives) of the project, including the review of the addendum to the project description document.

Task 2.1 will develop and submit, on schedule, a deliverable detailing the mapping of needs and prioritisation strategy for PARC's second prioritisation round (D2.13: 2nd Mapping of Needs Report' Deadline in M42, 31/10/2025). Feedback on this prioritisation cycle will also be collected from the parties concerned, with a view to continuous improvement.

T2.1 will prepare, with the appointed CLs, background documents that will formulate the regulatory problems and introduce how the PARC projects contribute to addressing them. These contributions will then be updated on a yearly basis in the scoping documents (T2.2). For methods/tools, policy and regulatory needs will be documented with the support of MLs. For projects that will end in Y4 or achieve key landmarks, Task 2.1 with the support of WP3 will promote key results and recommendations by organizing workshops and/or support the release of science or policy briefs. T2.1 aims at producing 3-5 policy briefs in Y4, starting with SSbD and NTS.

Task 2.1 will continue to process requests submitted under the Rapid Response Mechanism (D2.5. Rapid Response Report, submitted M19, December 2023). The aim of the mechanism is to allow the inclusion of new and urgent needs for information on chemicals in the EU policy community and at national level, outside of the formal timeframes for project nomination. Task 2.1 will coordinate the eligibility and feasibility checking of the requests. In this framework, Task T2.1 will follow the progress of the new project on the evaluation of the extent of exposure to mono-n-hexyl phthalate (MnHexP), at European level and to understand the potential sources of this phthalate metabolite, whose occurrence in human urine is unwanted. Based on previous experiences of RRM submission, T2.1 will evaluate how this process can be improved and aim at a quicker turnover of answers.

Task 2.2: Knowledge management and uptake into policy

Co-leaders: BfR (DE), INSA (PT)

Key Partners: AUTH (EL), UOB (UK), ANSES (FR), DEFRA (UK), EAA (AT), EEA (EU), ENSP (PT), GCSL (EL), EV-ILVO (BE), ISS (IT), JSI (SI), MU (CZ), NILU (NO), SOM (EE), STAMI (NO), UBA (DE), UKON (DE)

A2.2.1 PARCopedia

PARCopedia has been launched in the second half of PARC Y2 (November 2023). Throughout PARC Y3, the technical functionalities, workflows and user experience have been continuously improved, and this will be continued in PARC Y4. Yet, although more than 960 users had registered to the platform by the end of November 2024, autonomous community activities have been limited. In PARC Y4, substantial efforts will be made to support community building and activation (both among PARC partners and the PARCopedia community outside of PARC) as well as to provide a critical mass of content on the platform to incentivise increased user activity. In addition, the potential for integration of content from other platforms via APIs (Application Programming Interfaces), e.g. information about chemicals from the NICEATM ICE platform, from the National Toxicology Program of the U.S. Department of Health and Human Services, will be explored and implemented. We are continuously monitoring PARCopedia to ensure its relevance and

effectiveness. Key indicators include the number of registered users (with a steady growth observed despite a recent slowdown), visitor traffic and page views (which spike during newsletters and presentations), direct user actions (which are steadily increasing), and the most visited pages to identify popular content.

A2.2.2 NGRARoute

PARC Y3 has seen the initiation of the work on the EU Commission's "Roadmap towards phasing out animal testing in chemical safety assessments" (COM roadmap) as well as the establishment of PARC Task 2.2, NGRARoute, as a partner in this work, is already represented in two of the three COM roadmap working groups (WGs on Human Health and Environmental Safety Assessment). At the end of September 2024, the Deliverable AD2.1 was finalised and submitted to the European Commission, formulating 10 guiding principles for the development of a future overarching NGRA framework, allowing for the replacement of animal testing for complex endpoints as well as integrating new regulatory workflows for human health and environmental risk assessment (ERA). In addition, based on a comprehensive consultation process with a broad circle of stakeholders from within and outside of PARC, possible work streams for the further roadmap work were identified and important discussion points for these work streams were summarised, inter alia as an input for the second COM roadmap conference on 25th October 2024.

During the first half of 2024, the Commission mainly carried out discussions within a dedicated interservice group (diverse COM DGs and EU agencies, ECHA, EFSA and EMA) to determine how to best set up the working structure for the roadmap. As a result, first meetings of the WGs have taken place before and shortly after the summer break. While NGRARoute will be a relevant partner in these groups, it is not yet clear at the time of drafting this report what exactly will be the tasks assigned to PARC Task 2.2 under the European Commission's roadmap. Details of how NGRARoute will contribute to this process, and what its tasks will be are still open for discussion.

Task 2.2 is actively contributing to the process in the working groups, e.g. task 2.2 recently volunteered to initiate, together with ECHA, a pilot on acute oral toxicity in the HH WG. Also, task 2.2 anticipates a strong role in the preparation of the upcoming roadmap-related workshops in the first half of 2025. In addition, PARC projects have been proposed regarding the environmental side of NGRA, and details will become clear in the coming months, if these projects are approved.

NGRARoute could, for example, help with taking over certain conceptual work (overarching NGRA framework), the drafting of certain parts of the roadmap text and/or by serving as a hub connecting the roadmap work with PARC partners or other Stakeholder groups. Moreover, assistance, both technical and conceptual, with organising workshops and other meetings could be a possible contribution, as a substantial budget has been reserved for such activities under Task 2.2. Ultimately, however, these decisions will be at the discretion of the interservice group steering the COM roadmap and a clearer picture of the future role of NGRARoute will only emerge step by step, over the following months. It is ultimately the COM's role to draft the roadmap. However, for this to be successful, substantial input will necessarily come from the EU agencies and key stakeholder representatives, including PARC, EPAA, and ASPIS.

As mentioned above, NGRARoute is currently undergoing restructuring following the European Commission's announcement of the 'Roadmap for phasing out animal testing in chemical safety

assessments.' As a result, a separate NGRAroute roadmap, initially planned for delivery as PARC Deliverable D2.11 by the end of April 2025, has become obsolete. Additionally, since a status/progress report was already submitted at the beginning of October 2024, submitting another one at that same time would not add significant value. Task 2.2, therefore, proposes an amendment to move Deliverable D2.11 to the end of PARC Y4 (April 2026). By then, it will provide a comprehensive summary of NGRAroute's contributions to the Commission Roadmap, along with a detailed work plan on how NGRAroute will support its implementation during PARC years 5-7.

In parallel to the roadmap work itself, and to a degree inspired by the formulation of a need to conceptualise an overarching framework integrating human health and the environment under Task 2.2, work has been intensifying in other PARC WPs such as WP4 and 6 to build a platform for NGRA. Work has been initiated recently to transform the NGRAroute roadmap activity into an NGRA platform activity for connecting people and projects working towards regulatory implementation of NGRA. This activity is currently planned to be located under Task 2.2, but in close cooperation with WP6 (Tasks 6.3 and 6.4). While this activity will be elaborated in detail in the second half of 2025, the following features are envisaged:

- provide a hub for connecting NGRA-related activities in- and outside of PARC;
- aim for integration of HH and ENV assessments from a holistic perspective acc. to the "One Health" paradigm;
- carry out conceptual work for designing and implementing regulatory NGRA frameworks and workflows acc. to the principles formulated in Additional Deliverable AD2.1 and in support of the European Commission's "roadmap towards phasing out animal testing for chemical safety assessments",
- organize a workshop between T6.3 and T2.2 to discuss in detail future actions;
- use PARCopedia as a platform for these activities and organise topicline and in person.

A2.2.3 CLs/MLs

CLs and MLs will continue their work and, when necessary, support the work involving the chemicals or methodologies across the several PARC WPs. Meetings with the CLs and MLs will be organised regularly to keep track of the work being developed. Furthermore, activity planning reports will be developed (M37, June 2025) and incorporated into the Scoping Documents, to support their work across PARC (M40, September 2025). A report on the work done will be prepared at the end of Y4 (D2.15, January 2026). Assessment of further needs concerning CLs and MLs will be conducted and, if deemed necessary, nomination of CLs and/or MLs for additional chemicals and/or methodologies will be performed.

Table 5 and 6 show the CLs and MLs roles already filled in and the missing ones.

Table 5: List of nominated CLs and open vacancies for nomination

Chemical	Chemical Leader for Human Health	Chemical Leader for the Environment
Bisphenols and alternatives	not nominated	not nominated

EDCs	not nominated	Nikiforos Alygizakis
Metals	not nominated	not nominated
Pesticides and biocides	not nominated	not nominated
PFAS	Thorhallur Ingi Halldorsson	Lutz Ahrens
Nanomaterials	Iseult Lynch	Susana Loureiro
Microplastics	Dorte Herzke	not nominated

Table 6: List of nominated MLs and open vacancies for nomination

Methodology	Methodology Leader for Human Health	Methodology Leader for the Environment
Adverse Outcome Pathways (AOPs)	not nominated	not nominated
PKB modelling	Sylvia Escher	Vikas Kumar
	Spyros Karakitsios	
Pre-validation of new methods	Miriam Jacobs	
NG-ERA	-	Johan Axelman
		Romana Hornek-Gausterer
Omics	Martin von Bergen	Josef Daniel Rasing

To address the issue of the chemicals and/or methods that are missing a CL/ML, the task co-leaders are looking into a solution by approaching the activity leaders and project managers. There will be one final request for CLs/MLs after summer, with more refined criteria in the hope the missing positions can be filled in. Otherwise, a decision will need to be taken on whether to drop CLs/MLs for certain topics. Furthermore, this topic will be discussed in the MB.

Task 2.3: Sustainability

Co-leaders: INSERM (FR), NCPHP² (HU)

Partners: ANSES (FR), SpF (FR), EAA (AT), DOMG (BE), MU (CZ), EEA (EU), UBA (DE), BfR (DE), NIOM (PL), FMUL (PT), INSA (PT), JSI (SI), NIJZ (SI)

A2.3.1 National hubs needs & peer-to-peer learning

The mapping of needs of NHs is a living process. A new survey based on criteria-driven scoping documents will be created and launched in the fourth year of the Partnership to identify the new needs and expectations of the NHs based on the inputs of the NHCPs. The responses will be used to reflect on possible improvements to the progress of the development of the NHs, the way we ask questions or collect input from the NHCPs and the NHs and to the implementation of activities such

² AMD-101057014-80: The Beneficiary 'Nemzeti Népegészségügyi Központ' (abbreviation in Hungarian: NNK; full name in English: National Public Health Center; abbreviation in English: NPHC) was changed to 'Nemzeti Népegészségügyi és Gyógyszerészeti Központ' (abbreviation in Hungarian: NNGYK; full name in English: National Center for Public Health and Pharmacy; abbreviation in English: NCPHP) as of 1st August 2023. The acronym NPHC was replaced by NCPHP in the WPs where they are contributors.

as capacity building or sharing good practices that would support the NHs and their structuring at the national level.

The peer-to-peer learning process established in the first year of the Partnership will continue to support the sustainable development of the NHs. This activity will be performed in close collaboration with WP9 'Building infrastructural and human capacities. The process will be coordinated and the development of the NHs will be monitored by the NHCs. Besides the annual survey, the needs of the NHs will be collected and discussed during the annual meeting. Based on the results of the 2nd and 3rd survey mapping the needs of the NHs and the needs reported by the NHCPs during the NHCP meetings, recommendations will be formulated and actions will be taken. These results, along with the recommendations and actions addressing the identified needs, will be described in D2.14.

A2.3.2 Exit strategy

Following the first deliverable on the exit strategy (D2.9), which includes the prioritised PARC activities to be sustainable, targeted meetings were held with the different task and WP leaders.

A physical workshop on the exit strategy took place in Copenhagen in February 2025 with the involvement of T2.3 partners and MB members. The workshop was structured to focus on individual tasks and WPs before seeking broader overarching strategies, ensuring tailored solutions rather than a one-size-fits-all approach. Discussions also addressed the need for an overarching, integrated European programme to support sustainability.

The following steps include continued discussions with WP leaders, European agencies, the GB, where several presentations have already been made. Once a common understanding is reached, the next phase will involve engaging with different DGs and policy makers to build an operational plan.

Following these meeting, options for the exit strategy will be further elaborated and discussed with stakeholders. The following activities will be carried out in Year 4:

1. Task 2.3 partners will write an interim report summarizing discussions during and following the February 2025 Copenhagen meeting and elaborating different scenarios for the exit strategy concerning e.g. HBM, toxicology/NAMs, environmental monitoring, safe and sustainable by design, data access. The report will be discussed with the MB, the GB and the NHs.
2. The work on HBM sustainability will be carried out in close collaboration with project P4.1.5 of task 4.1. This activity will be aligned with the ongoing discussions at the EU level on the OSOA framework.
3. Different scenarios for the sustainability of toxicology activities will be discussed. Specifically, the set-up of a European Toxicology Programme inspired by the US National Toxicology programme will be discussed with EU agencies, JRC, and with EU infrastructures, in particular EIRENE. The different activities of such a programme will be determined and further discussed with the EU commission.
4. Similar approaches will be carried out for environmental monitoring, safe and sustainable by design, early warning systems and data access.

5. Since PARC has been able to achieve a network of excellence in chemical risk assessment, the sustainability of a coordination framework of the activities and agencies/institutes involved in risk assessment and covering most PARC activities mentioned above, will be examined and discussed with stakeholders in Y4. We propose to call this putative framework the European Risk Assessment Programme (EURAP).
6. Following discussions with the PARC coordinators, MB and WP3, and depending on the ability of PARC partners to reach a consensus during Y4, a meeting at the EU parliament or one of the MS delegations in Brussels could be held to present PARC activities and prospects. If more internal discussions are needed, this meeting could be postponed to Y5.

Deliverables:

D2.11 PARCroute roadmap2 – Leader: BfR (initially planned M36, postponed M48)

D2.12 Exit Strategy Plan 2 – Leader: INSERM (FR), NCPHP (HU) (M40)

D2.13 2nd Mapping of Needs report – Leader: ANSES (M42)

D2.14 2nd Report on national needs – Leader: NCPHP (M42)

D2.15 3rd Annual CL/ML reports' coordination and submission – Leader: INSA (M45)

Additional Deliverables:

NA

WP N°	WP3				Lead Beneficiary				INSA/GCSL																
WP title	Synergies, collaborations and awareness																								
Partner N°	1	2	3	3.1	3.8	4	4.2	6	7	8	10	11	12	14	15	16	17	18	19	20	20.4	20.6	21	22	24
Partner short name	ANSES	SpF	EAA	AGES	UMIT	VITO	DOMG	CIPH	MOH-CY/SGL-MU	DEPA	HB	EEA	TTL	UBA	BfR	NCPHP	UI	MOH	ISS	IUSS	UNINA	RSU	NPHSL	LNS	
PM/partner	1.0	0.5	4.7	2.0	2.0	1.0	2.0	1.0	1.0	2.5	1.0	1.0	13.0	1.0	2.8	0.9	14.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	0.1	1.0	1.0	2.0

Partner N°	25	26	26.2	27	28	29	29.1	29.3	29.5	30	31	31.2	31.2	32	34	35.7	35.9	36	36.1	36.2	36.3	36.4	37	38	50	59
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Partner short name	PM/partner	Start	End	M48
RIVM	1.9	M37		
NIPH	1.0			
STAMI	4.3			
NIOM	1.0			
FMUL	4.6			
INSA	36.6			
APA	3.5			
ENSP	3.0			
UAVR	2.6			
SZU-SK	1.0			
JSI	1.5			
NIB	3.0			
NIC	1.5			
NIJZ	5.5			
ISCIH	2.0			
KEMI	1.0			
SLV	1.0			
AUTH	10.0			
EFET	5.5			
GCSL	19.0			
NKUA	10.5			
UOC	3.9			
BPI	2.5			
FOPH	1.0			
UKHSA	2.0			
UOB	1.0			

Objectives

The main goal of WP3 is to boost the impact of PARC outcomes through the diffusion of the knowledge produced within the Partnership while fostering synergies and collaborations with other projects/programmes at national, EU and international levels. The specific objectives of WP3 for year 4 are:

- Task 3.1: Running the International Board (IB) and Stakeholder Forum (SF), and facilitate their effective interaction with PARC's projects, through the development of dynamic strategies and follow up actions.
- Task 3.2: Continue the implementation of the communication strategy for PARC and promote its continuous improvement based on specific requirements from WPs,
- Task 3.3: Continue the identification of potential synergies, facilitation of information exchange between external projects and PARC and the establishment of collaborations and synergies with relevant scientific/regulatory/policy initiatives at national, EU and international levels.

Description of Programmed Activities

Task 3.1: Building effective interactions

Co-Leaders: EAA (AT): SF; AUTH (EL): International Board

Partners: ANSES (FR), EEA (EU), UBA (DE), IUSS (IT), LNS (LU), STAMI (NO), FMUL (PT), INSA (PT), APA (PT), NIB (SI), NKUA (EL), UOC (EL), GCSL (EL)

Activity 3.1.1. Running of SF

In year 4 of PARC, the SF (established in year 1) will be continuing the work with the members of the SF. The SF Co-chair(s) and Task Leaders (TLs) will lead the work of members and partners to

develop and refine the strategy on information flow and of inclusion of SF members' perceptions taking into account the respective SF groups/interests (NGOs, industry associations and other interested associations). Following the collection of priorities for the second half of PARC, a mechanism for the collection of the SF inputs, comments and suggestions on planned activities, research projects or other topics of interest will be developed. Topics of interest for the SF to be presented in the two SF meetings will be selected based on the discussions and outputs of the first three SF meetings and in close collaboration with SF Co-chair and WP Co-leaders, Tls and Project Managers (PMs). One of the annual meetings will be planned together with SF members, preferably as a physical full day meeting, allowing for in-depth exchange and discussions. SF members will be further encouraged to participate in existing PARC channels and communication tools (PARCopedia, SYNnet...), to offer them the possibility to articulate their needs and interact with the PARC consortium and other stakeholders. Partners involved: EAA, INSA, GCSL, UBA, STAMI, FMUL, APA, NIB, NKUA and UOC.

SF members will be encouraged to get deeper involved and provide (industrial) data and insight on current and future activities within their organisations in the relevant section of the factsheets on potential future priorities provided by the CT (EAA, INSA, GCSL, ANSES). In addition, interactions with industry, particularly on the subjects of NAMs and of Safe and Sustainable by Design (SSbD), under WP5 and WP8 respectively, will be promoted through the SF, which has representatives of industry associations and also through other relevant stakeholders and potential synergies (collaboration with Tasks 2.2 and 3.3), based on specific consultations and participation in dedicated meetings (AUTH, ANSES).

Stakeholder interests brought to the attention of Task 3.1 will be taken up, discussed and forwarded to other WPs, Tasks or projects of specific interest (all partners). Those projects of interest that are proposed by Stakeholder Forum members will be communicated to the respective fora (MB, GB, GSB) and the relevant project managers.

Activity 3.1.2. Running of the International Board (IB)

Tls and partners will work in close collaboration to promote the interaction between the IB members and PARC WPs. Feedback on scientific steering needs will be collected from the WPLs into a dedicated form that will be distributed in advance (two months prior the next IB meeting). A similar form will be distributed to the IB members, providing topics of key scientific interest in the field of chemicals RA, so as to enrich the list of available topics. The collected WP needs and the IB topics of key scientific interest will be discussed and prioritized by the Task 3.1.2 partners, who will decide after consultation of the MB on the topics of the forthcoming IB meetings. 4 meetings (one physical organized back-to-back with the in-person MB Meeting in mid 2025 and the other 3 online) will be organized to present the work progress and the main outcomes and to get feedback from the IB on the projects within PARC. Those meetings will also stimulate the interactions between PARC and external bodies (all partners). Particular emphasis will be put on the analysis and the provision on the future needs for PARC.

Partners involved: AUTH, UBA, IUSS, LNS, STAMI, FMUL, INSA, NKUA, UOC, GCSL.

Task 3.2: Communication, dissemination, and awareness

Co-Leaders: EEA (EU), NCPHP (HU)

Partners: ANSES (FR), SpF (FR), EAA (AT), AGES (AT), UMIT (AT), VITO (BE), DOMG (BE), CIPH (CR), MOH-CY/SGL (CY), MU (CZ), HB (EE), TTL (FI), UBA (DE), BfR (DE), UI (IS), MOH-IL (IL), ISS (IT), UNINA (IT), RSU (LV), NPHSL (LT), LNS (LU), RIVM (NL), NIPH (NO), STAMI (NO), NIOM (PL), FMUL (PT), INSA (PT), APA (PT), ENSP (PT), UAVR (PT), SZU (SK), JSI (SI), NIB (SI), NIC (SI), NIJZ (SI), ISCIII (ES), KEMI (SE), SLV (SE), FOPH (CH), UKHSA (UK), UOB (UK), AUTH (EL), EFET (EL), NKUA (EL), UOC (EL), BPI (EL), GCSL (EL)

A3.2.1 Website and social media channels

The PARC website and the social media channels (LinkedIn, X, Facebook and Instagram accounts) will be maintained and updated regularly with new content, including up to date information about upcoming events, progress updates, interviews, and results (EEA, NCPHP, INSA, EFET, NKUA, NIJZ, BPI, and GCSL). New developments will be implemented on the PARC website including the visualisation of new indicators, a new section on chemicals, and interactive maps of environmental laboratories. The thematic areas will also be further developed (EEA, NCPHP).

A3.2.2 Development and implementation of the communication and dissemination strategy

The communication and dissemination strategy developed at the beginning of PARC will be reviewed (D3.6). Continuous dialogue will be maintained with all WP co-leaders, WP3 contact points and NHCPs to translate the latest PARC results and the agenda into communication and dissemination outputs, ensuring a coherent approach. The roadmap for the development of communication materials will be updated. New communication materials and activities, such as promoting the first research and policy briefs on the projects' outputs provided by the different WPs, will contribute to increase PARC's visibility, build and grow the PARC brand and engage stakeholders. The monthly Science Digest listing the latest peer-reviewed scientific PARC articles will continue to be produced, while the PARC Sampler bringing together all the latest news, interviews, science impact and much more will continue to be published twice a year. All public project deliverables produced under the project will be made available via the PARC website (UMIT, EEA, NCPHP, STAMI, FMUL, INSA, APA, ENSP, UAVR, NIB, NIJZ, EFET, NKUA, UOC and GCSL).

A3.2.3 Surveys and other tools to assess stakeholders' perception and concerns

Outreach activities will be carried out to raise awareness of specific target groups. New focus groups will be organized to collect more in-depth information about citizens' perceptions and concerns about PARC-related subjects. The countries hosting focus groups will be selected in an internal call. The results of the first citizens' survey will be further analysed and published. Communication with the scientific community and with all stakeholders, including the general public, regulators and policy makers will be done in dialogue through the different communication channels (website, social media, newsletters, PARCopedia, workshops and other events) and with the involvement of the NHs (EEA, ENSP, FMUL, GCSL, INSA, NCPHP, NIB).

A3.2.4 Risk communication

The results of the survey mapping the risk perception of different stakeholders on risk communication will be published by EFET and NIJZ. A series of webinars on risk communication will be launched, tailored to a wide range of stakeholders (ENSP, FMUL, EFET, NIJZ, NIC).

A.3.2.5 Monitoring of indicators

Monitoring of indicators defined for the communication and dissemination activities will continue to feed into Task 1.3 by DOMG, EEA, GCSL, INSA and NCPHP. The bibliometric analysis will be updated by UOC. Indicator values will be updated on the website.

Task 3.3: Networking and Synergies

Co-Leaders: INSA (PT), NKUA (EL)

Partners: ANSES (FR), MU (CZ), UBA (DE), FMUL (PT), APA (PT), ENSP (PT), UAVR (PT), JSI (SI), NIB (SI), NIC (SI), NIJZ (SI), EFET (EL), UOC (EL), BPI (EL), GCSL (EL)

A3.3.1 Inventory of scientific activities relevant to PARC

Monitor the online form created for the external partnerships, projects, networks and activities to express interest to collaborate with PARC. Update of the established database of external partnerships, projects, networks and activities that have expressed interest in collaborating with PARC (NKUA, INSA, ANSES, MU, UBA, FMUL, APA, ENSP, UAVR, JSI, NIB, NIC, NIJZ, EFET, UOC, BPI, GCSL).

Contact the relevant WP/Task co-leaders to request their evaluation of the external projects/activities and to organize brainstorming sessions between researchers from PARC and from the external initiatives (NKUA, INSA).

A3.3.2 Development of SYNnet strategy and roadmap for promotion of synergies

Continue updating SYNnet with the information gathered in the form created to register the established synergies and work on expanding the network to include new partnerships, projects, etc. and respond to PARC demands for synergies (NKUA, INSA, ANSES, MU, UBA, FMUL, APA, ENSP, UAVR, JSI, NIB, NIC, NIJZ, EFET, UOC, BPI, GCSL).

Revise and update the interaction strategy between SYNnet and WPs in order to identify and address internal needs and gaps (FMUL, APA, NKUA, GCSL, INSA, UBA).

The third SYNnet Forum foreseen to take place in Y4 will be organized back-to-back with a relevant scientific event (EUROTOX 2025) to promote dialogue and knowledge sharing among scientists (NKUA, UOC, INSA, GCSL, BPI, EFET).

SYNnet activities will be announced and published at the PARC website increasing the visibility of joint activities and of the external projects themselves (NKUA, INSA). Another workshop on Synergies with External Initiatives will be organized in Y4 and external activities or projects considered relevant will be invited to participate (NKUA, INSA).

Development of the SYNnet dashboard for the visualization of the synergies at the website and contributing to the output and outcome indicators (NKUA, INSA, ANSES, MU, UBA, FMUL, APA, ENSP, UAVR, JSI, NIB, NIC, NIJZ, EFET, UOC, BPI, GCSL).

Deliverables:
D3.6 Review of Communication and Dissemination Strategy – Leader: NCPHP (M40)
Additional Deliverables:
NA

WP N°	WP4	Lead Beneficiary	UBA/SpF
WP title	Monitoring and exposure		
Part ner N°	1		
Part ner short name	ANSES		
PM/partner	51.0		
	12.1	INSERM	
	44.9	INRAE	
	6.0	CEA	
	15.2	INERIS	
	1.0	CNRS	
	13.3	INRS	
	18.9	ONIRIS	
	0.8	OFB	
	7.8	BRGM	
	0.2	LNE	
	4.4	CSTB	
	16.7	EHESP	
	71.1	SpF	
	5.5	EAA	
	24.4	MUI	
	2.0	MUW	
	2.0	UG-AT	
	6.2	UNIVE	
	48.8	VITO	
	11.4	KU Leuven	
	2.0	UH	
	5.0	PIH	
	3.3	OVAM	
	31.0	ISSEP	
	21.9	UAntwerpen	
	11.8	SCIENSANO	
	0.9	EV-ILVO	
	1.0	CIPH	
	28.8	MOH-CY/SGL	
	51.0	MU	
	12.9	SZU-CZ	
	7.6	VSCHT	
	0.4	JU	

Partner N°	10.1		
Partner short name	AU		
PM/partner	37.1		
	15.0	REGIONH-RH	
	2.9	UCPH	
	12.5	UT	
	0.8	SYKE	
	22.4	TTL	
	4.2	FFA	
	1.1	UOULU	
	2.0	UEF	
	77.7	UBA	
	1.3	BfG	
	30.3	UFZ	
	5.2	KUM	
	5.0	Fraunhofer-IBMT/IME	
	14.0	NCPHP	
	5.2	UI	
	6.0	MOH	
	15.4	ISS	
	3.0	CNR-IRSA	
	4.5	UMIL	
	2.1	UNINA	
	2.0	UNIPD	
	33.0	RSU	
	3.0	UL	
	0.3	NHPSL	
	6.2	LSMU	
	77.9	LNS	
	14.8	UnILU	
	0.1	RIVM	
	3.2	KWR	

Partne r N°	25.2		
Partne r short name	TNO		
	25.5	UU-IRAS	
	25.6	VUA	
	25.7	WR	
	25.9	SRU	
	26	NIPH	
	26.2	STAMI	
	26.3	NILU	
	26.7	UNN	
	27	NIOM	
	27.3	WULS- SGGW	
	29	INSA	
	29.3	ENSP	
	30	SZU-SK	
	31	JSI	
	31.4	ULFFA	
	32	NIJZ	
	32.2	NLZOH	
	33	CSIC	
	33.4	ULPGC	
	33.3	UGR	
	34	ISCHII	
	34.1	EASP	
	34.2	FISABIO	
	34.5	IISPV	

PM/ partner	0.5	5.6	19.6	9.4	10.5	30.2	7.2	9.0	0.3	1.9	12.3	30.7	0.5	6.5	54.3	2.3	10.4	0.2	40.9	0.4	19.0	37.8	5.3	0.7	2.2
Partner N°	34.6	34.8	35.2	35.3	35.4	35.6	35.8	35.9	35.10	35.11	36	36.2	36.3	37	38	40	41	45	47	50	54	55	56		
Partner short name	INNST	UPV-EHU	KI	ULJUND	ORU	SU	IVL	SLV	SLU	UMU	AUTH	GCSSL	NKUA	BPI	FOPH	UNISANTE	EAWAG	USI	SECO	UKHSA	EA	HSE	IOM		
PM/ partner	1.3	7.0	3.5	13.8	9.7	8.5	19.2	1.0	11.0	2.0	31.9	1.0	10.5	16.8	1.0	5.0	20.9	6.2	0.8	3.0	1.0	6.0	1.1		
	Start					M37							End					M48							

Objectives

The main goal of WP4 is to monitor chemicals guided by clearly defined regulatory and policy challenges both in humans and in the environment, considering different sources, chemical fates and exposure pathways, and linking with international activities. Specifically, WP4 aims to coordinate with the WHO EHP on HMB launched in Budapest in July 2023. The specific objectives of WP4 for year 4 are:

- Task 4.1: Continuation of an EU-wide general population HBM survey, continuing occupational surveys in health care sector and waste sector, developing targeted surveys (design and supporting materials), preparing and implementation of following aspects in above mentioned surveys: effect biomarkers, innovative (sampling) techniques for HBM in a tiered approach starting with state of the art analyses, update and integration of QA/QC aspects and analyses plan in the HBM surveys, evaluation of new chemical analysis methods needs, derivation of HBM guidance values (HBM-GV).
- Task 4.2: Complete a first monitoring study on PFAS and endocrine disrupting chemicals (EDCs) and evaluate the process with regard to future monitoring studies. Continue a study on human exposure to organic chemicals from environmental non-food sources. Initiate an environmental monitoring study on siloxanes and transversal activities with a view to a joint T4.2-T4.3 project.
- Task 4.3: Novel methodologies will be developed in a tiered approach to improve and renew current monitoring approaches, with a focus on early life stages and on early warning systems for the timely observation of the occurrence of chemicals of emerging concern along the interlinked pathways in environment, food and human matrices. The work will be covered in 4 ongoing projects (started in year 1) and 3 projects started in year 2 and 1 project starting in year 3.

In year 4 a specific attention will be given to transversal activities inside WP4 to ensure that the different tasks (4.2 and 4.3) align their activities and prepare new projects considering the outcome

of the “mapping of needs” to enhance the efficient use of monitoring approaches by combining targeted analytical methods with innovative methods, such as screening and effect-based methods. The project 4.2.c is a collaboration between T4.1 and T4.2 and includes links to T4.3 and will integrate human and environmental monitoring networks.

Description of Programmed Activities

Task 4.1: HBM

Co-Leaders: VITO (BE), ISCIII (ES)

Partners: ANSES (FR), AU-PH (DK), AUTH (EL), BPI (EL), CEA (FR), CSIC (ES), EAA (AT), EHESP (FR), FFA (FI), TTL (FI), FISABIO (ES), FOPH (CH), HSE (UK), KI (SE), IMROH (HR), INRAE (FR), INRS (FR), INSA (PT), INSERM (FR), INSST (ES), IOM (UK), KUM (DE), ISS (IT), ISSeP (BE), IVL (SE), JSI (SI), KU Leuven (BE), LNS (LU), LSMU (LT), MOH-CY/SGL (CY), MOH (IL), MU (CZ), MUI (AT), MUW (AT), NIJZ (SI), NIOM (PL), NIPH (NO), NLZOH (SI), NPHSL (LT), ONIRIS (FR), UKHSA (UK), PIH (BE), REGIONH-RH (DK), RSU (LV), SRU (NL), SCIENSANO (BE), SLU (SE), SpF (FR), STAMI (NO), SZU-CZ (CZ), SZU-SK (SK), THL (FI), UAntwerpen (BE), UBA (DE), UGent (BE), UGR (ES), UH (BE), ULFFA (SI), ULPGC (ES), ULUND (SE), UMU (SE), UMIL (IT), UNINA (IT), UNIPD (IT), UNISANTE (CH), UNIVIE (AT), UNN (NO), UOULU (FI), UOC (EL), UPV/EHU (ES), USI (CH), UU-IRAS (NL), WULS-SGGW (PL), CIPH (HR), SHSO (CY), SDU (DK), Fraunhofer-IBMT (DE), UFZ (DE), NCPHP (HU), UI (IS), VSCHT (CZ), EASP (ES), SECO (CH), UCD³ (IE)

A4.1.1 Design, alignment and fieldwork of HBM studies

The implementation of a general population HBM survey is ongoing and will be further supported (linked to P4.1.1.2.a_Y1_GenHBMSurvey_VITO). Small-scale research components, in the general survey will be initiated they are referred to as add-ons. The topics are: i) implementation of effect biomarkers (linked to P4.1.3.3.a_Y1_RoadmapLinkingHBMhealth_SpF_VITO), ii) identify the contribution of specific environmental compartments, products to internal exposure levels (in collaboration with T4.2 - in project P4.2.c_Y3_HumanExposure_INERIS_AU), and (iii) apply innovative screening methods (Suspect screening (SS), Non targeted screening (NTS)) (in collaboration with T4.3 - in project P4.3.2.c_Y3_H03 Complementary developments_JSI/UAntwerpen).

During the Y3 of PARC occupational surveys focusing on the waste management sector (P4.1.1.4.d_Y1_OccupWaste_ENSP_TTL) (phthalates, metals, flame retardants, bisphenols) and the health care sector (P4.1.1.4.c_Y1_HealthCareSurvey_TTL_SRU) (HMPs and disinfectants) have progressed to sampling phase. Samplings performed in different countries follow the harmonised sampling procedures in accordance with the procedures for the PARC Aligned Studies. Samplings related to these studies will continue until the end of first quarter of Y4 for the waste management

³ AMD-101057014-118: The University College Dublin – PARC acronym “UCD”, PIC number 999974359 entered as new Beneficiary in PARC as of 01/10/2024 with the agreement that the ‘Environment Protection Agency’ – PARC acronym “EPA” remains the only member of the Grant Signatory Board and takes over responsibility for coordinating Ireland’s engagement in PARC in the same way as other grant signatories with AE do. The starting date for the eligibility of the costs for UCD is on 01/10/2024 and UCD specifically contributes as partner in the PARC Aligned Studies under WP4 (P4.1.1.2.a_Y1_GenHBMSurvey_VITO).

sector (AU, INSA, ENSP, ISS, KUL, LNS, MOH-CY/SGL, NIOM, STAMI, UMIL, UNIPD, UNINA, UNISANTE, WULS-SGGW, ULUND, TTL) and the health care sector (TTL, SRU, MU, UGR, INRS, ISS, UMIL, UNINA, UNIPD, RSU, LNS, HSE, INSST, INSA.). Samplings will include also samples collected according to harmonised and quality assured Standard Operating Procedures (SOPs) for effect marker analyses (link to P4.1.3.3.a) and applying new innovative methods (T4.3: linked to P4.3.2.b_Y2_H02). During Y4 chemical analyses of collected samples will be performed, data collected following the codebook, templates and tools provided by T4.1.4 and statistical analyses will be performed according to the statistical analysis plan created in T4.1.4 (TTL, INSA, INRS, STAMI, LNS).

S4.1.1.1-supporting materials for a harmonized HBM conduct:

No projects were planned since it is a transversal activity. The Y4 work plan will focus on the elaboration of effective communication materials for reporting the research results to participants (CIPH, CSIC, EAA, EASP, FOPH, Fraunhofer-IBMT, IMROH, INSA, ISCIH, ISS, ISSeP, JSI, LNS, LSMU, MOH-IL, MUW, NIJZ, NIOM, PIH, RSU, SpF, STAMI, THL, UBA, UGR, ULUND, UMU, UOULU, UPV).

S4.1.1.2. General population survey:

Details per project:

- P4.1.1.2.a_Y1_GenHBMSurvey_VITO [M1-M81]

Partners that will contribute to the PARC Aligned Studies in children (6-11 years) are UKHSA, RegionH-RH, RSU, UT, HB, WULS-SGGW, SZU-CZ, NCPHP, ISCIH, INSA, AUTH, JSI, MOH-CY/SGL, UBA, SpF, EAA, LNS. Partners that will contribute in teenagers (12-17 years) are UKHSA, RegionH-RH, NIPH, ULUND, KI, UMU, RSU, NIOM, JSI, AUTH, INSA, UBA, SPF, VITO/PIH, SZU-SK and partners that will contribute in adults (18-39 years) are UKHSA, LSMU, RSU, UT, HB, UI, NIPH, SZU-CZ, NIOM, NCPHP, EASP, UPV, AUTH, INSA, MOH-CY/SGL, ISS, UBA, SpF, ISSeP, LNS, MOH-IL, RIVM, UCD.

Substance groups prioritized for analysis are **in children:** Phthalates and substitute DINCH, Bisphenols, Pesticides (Neonicotinoids, Pyrethroids, Organophosphates) metals in urine, Mercury (hair), **in teenagers:** PFAS, Phthalates and substitute DINCH, Bisphenols, arsenic species, Pesticides (Pyrethroids, Organophosphates) **in adults:** Phthalates and substitute DINCH, bisphenols, PFAS, metals in urine/blood, Pesticides (Neonicotinoids, Pyrethroids, Organophosphates, Glyphosate/AMPA). In all age groups cotinine, creatinine and specific gravity will be assessed.

The sample owners listed above will have to choose the labs that will actually perform the analytical measurements. All sample analysis must be completed by M59 (March 2027 ~ end of PARC Y5) (L3). Sample collection activities as detailed in the table below must be finalized by the end of PARC Y4 (M48 April 2026) (L2).

Table 7: Sample collection activities to be finalized by the end of Y4

Partner	Children		Teenagers		Adults	
	N	Status	N	Status	N	Status
EAA	200	Started	/		/	
VITO with PIH	/		300		/	
ISSeP	/		/		300	
MOH-CY / SGL	150		/		>=150	
SZU-CZ (NIPH)	200	Started	/		200	
Region-RH	150		150		/	
UT	150		/		150	
SpF	300		300		300	
UBA	300		300		300	Finalized
AUTH	300		300		300	
NCPHP	300	Started	/		150	
UI	/		/		150	
MOH-IL	/		/		150	
ISS	/		/		300	
RSU	200		200		300	
LSMU	/		/		300	
LNS	150		/		150	
NIPH	/		200	Started	200	Started
RIVM	/		/		300	
WULS-SGGW	300		/		/	
NIOM	/		300		300	
INSA	300		300		300	
JSI with NIJZ	150	Started	150	Started	/	
ISCIH	300		/		/	
EHU/UPV	/		/		150	
EASP	/		/		150	
ULUND with KI and UmU	/		150		/	
UKHSE	150		150		150	
SZU-SK*	/		160- to be confirmed		/	
UCD*	/		/		150	
	±N		±N		±N	

*Discussions on potential contribution from Ireland (UCD) and Slovakia (SZU-SK) are ongoing. Overall coordination will be taken up by VITO supported by ISCIH, UBA, SpF, LNS, INSA, RegionH-RH. This includes the organization of a physical project meeting with all project partners (M37).

All project partners will continue the following tasks:

- Prepare supporting documents to implement the HBM studies on national regional level based on PARC supporting materials developed. This includes translations and adaptations to national context;
- Obtain and demonstrate ethical approval for the HBM studies. This includes preparing and submitting the application to an ethics committee. Completing the PARC ethics template, and saving copies of relevant documents on PARC SharePoint to support ethics audit;
- Recruit study participants;
- Sample study participants i.e., collecting biological samples, collection questionnaire information;

- Sample storage and shipment to laboratories for analysis as prioritized under PARC;
- Complete study metadata;
- Initiate the preparation of individual level data in harmonized PARC format and upload of data to Personal Exposure and Health (PEH) platform;

The statistical analyses of the data generated within this project will be prepared, research questions will be elaborated, and the distribution of the analyses will be discussed by the following key partners (VITO, JSI, MU, NIPH, UU-IRAS).

A subset of the PARC Aligned Studies will contribute to the add-on “effect biomarker implementation”. Following partners with HBM studies in children will implement effect biomarkers: WULS-SGGW, AUTH, ISCH, LNS, UBA, JSI, NIJZ, NCPHP, RSU, MOH-CY/SGL.

Following partners with HBM studies in teenagers will implement effect biomarkers: AUTH, JSI, NIJZ, RSU, NIPH, VITO, PIH, SpF, NIOM, UBA.

The following partners with HBM studies in adults will implement effect biomarkers: AUTH, LNS, NCPHP, RSU, MOH-CY/SGL, NIPH, SPF, NIOM, EASP, ISSeP, LSMU, SZU-CZ.

The table below indicates the effect biomarker analysis planned per age group.

Note: not all partners listed above will analyze all effect biomarkers.

Table 8: Effect biomarker analysis planned per age group

Effect biomarker	Children	Teenagers	Adults
NAG (N-acetyl- β -D glucosaminidase)	X		
A1MG (α 1-microglobulin)	X		
albumin to creatinine ratio	X		
Kim-1 (kidney injury molecule-1)	X		
RBP4 (Retinol-binding protein 4)	X		
8-OHdG (8-hydroxy-2'-deoxyguanosine)	X		X
ft3 (free triiodothyronine)		X	X
ft4 (free Thyroxine)		X	X
TSH (Thyroid stimulating hormone)		X	X
T3 (Triiodothyronine)		X	X
T4 (Thyroxine)		X	X
TG (Triglycerides)		X	X
Chol (total cholesterol)		X	X
HDL (high-density lipoprotein)		X	X
LDL (low-density lipoprotein)		X	X
Kisspeptin (kisspeptine 54)		X	X
BDNF (Brain Derived Neurotrophic factor)		X	X
IgG			X
IgM			X
IgE			X

Interleukins 1			X
Interleukins 1B			X
Interleukins 6			X
Interleukins 8			X
LTB4 (Leukotriene B4)			X
TNF α (Tumor necrosis factor alfa)			X
IFN- γ (Interferon gamma)			X

A subset of the PARC Aligned Studies will contribute to the add-on “personal environmental samples”. The following partners will collect personal environmental samples from the HBM participants under project (P4.2.c_Y3_HumanExposure_INERIS_AU): VITO, PIH, LNS, RSU, ISSeP, MOH-CY/SGL, AUTH, JSI, ISCHII.

A subset of the PARC Aligned Studies will contribute to the add-on “innovative screening methods”. The following partners will make human biological samples available for (Suspect screening (SS), Non targeted screening (NTS)) under project (P4.3.2.c_Y3_H03_Complementary_developments_JSI/UAntwerpen): List still to be decided.

S4.1.1.3 Targeted Surveys

- P4.1.1.3.a_Y4_PFAS Mother milk_BPI_LNS [M37-M81]

The project aims to implement a longitudinal HBM survey, comprising three follow-ups, to address the most vulnerable population group: pregnant women and new-borns. It will investigate their exposure to relevant PFAS across various biological samples, including identification of emerging PFAS, with particular emphasis on breast milk samples. The results will cover a specific series of countries including Luxembourg, Greece, Czechia, The Netherlands, Austria, Slovenia, Spain, Cyprus and potentially Latvia at a later stage.

In the first year of the project (Y4): 1) Partners will review current knowledge of PFAS in the context of pregnancy and breast milk in order to design the study (M1-M6), this review will include the occurrence (detection, trends, and tendencies) of PFAS in breast milk and other biological fluids of pregnant women, the analytical methods used, suspect screening analysis for identifying emerging PFAS, and potential effect biomarkers related to PFAS exposure. Based on this review, PFAS substances to be analysed in the specific matrices will be selected, considering a harmonized and recommended scope by all partners, chain length and half-life of PFAS need specifically to be considered for breast milk and urine. 2) For targeted analysis, PFAS will be analysed with harmonized analytical methods following established QA/QC approach, therefore in the first months of the project (M2-M12) the analytical laboratories will define the analytical scope, SOPs for sample preparation and chemical analysis will be generated, an inter-laboratory comparison will be performed between the labs, organized by an already accredited laboratory of the consortium (ONIRIS France). In the same context, QC samples will be prepared by the same lab and distributed among partners for use throughout the project implementation. For suspect screening (SS), labs with expertise in liquid-chromatographic high-resolution mass spectrometric (LC-HRMS) will harmonize

their SS workflow and a QA/QC approach will be pursued. The sensitivity of SS HRMS methods will be contrasted to the one of the tandem mass spectrometric (MS/MS) methods (obtained from triple quadrupole instruments) in order for LC-HRMS and LC-MS/MS to function in parallel. Finally, connection to Task 4.3 will be realized since pertinent analyses are carried out within PARC (PARC-Task_4.3.2.a_H01_Perinatal Exposure). 3) The recruitment and sample collection will be initiated (M6-M30 of the project), including biobanked samples (M6-M18). MTA for samples of the study will be issued; biobanked samples will be recorded in a registry (Excel file), and special attention will be given for the harmonisation of the sampling procedures (for mother milk sampling the protocol developed by WHO/UNEP Human Milk Survey on POPs will be followed, for blood and urine samples the SOPs developed in the task 4.1 (activity 4.1.1.1 – Supporting materials)). Partners involved: LNS, BPI, MU, RIVM, MUW, JSI, UGR, ONIRIS, SGL/MoH-CY.

- P4.1.1.3.b_Y4_PFASChildren_SpF [M37-M81]

Due to difficulty to generalize the collection of blood samples from children for all participating studies in project P4.1.1.2 (GenHBMSurvey), this new project for Y4 (P4.1.1.3b PFAS_Children) will address this lack by collecting new data on PFAS exposure for children. As an extension of the work of P4.1.1.2 to PFAS among children, this project aims to build on existing national HBM capacities foreseeing to collect serum samples among European children on a period between May 2024 and December 2026. The resources and methodologies developed under the GenHBMSurvey project will be used to obtain comparable data across EU countries.

Before the project officially start, involved partners are mobilized in the Aligned studies project (P4.1.1.2a) by designing and harmonizing their studies. Some of them already started implementing the fieldwork. All phases of participating studies have been upfront harmonized in the framework of the GenHBMSurvey project (P4.1.2.2), including harmonized materials and questionnaires, sampling timeframe, target population. The project 4.1.1.3b (PFAS_Children) relies on this work.

In the first year of the project (Y4 of PARC), partners [SpF (FR), RegionH (DK), University Tartu (EE), Health Board (EE), AUTH (EL), JSI (SI), NIJZ (SI), UBA (DE), LNS (LU)] will be involved in the collection of blood samples from children and data collection from questionnaires. This project will collect more than 1,000 children (6-11 years) blood samples from 7 countries distributed in 3 European geographical areas (north, south and west). During Y4, targeted PFAS will be selected by all partners in coherence with PFAS compounds selected for teenagers and adults within the P4.1.1.2.a_GenHBMSurvey project as well as additional PFAS that we will define later in the project. The selection will be based on the analytical capacities of laboratories.

- P4.1.1.3.c_Y4_TimePatternEU_VITO [M37-M72]

In the HBM4EU and PARC project, several human biomonitoring data has and will be generated in children, teenagers, and adults. Although significant insights have been obtained so far, efforts dedicated to investigating the time patterns of internal exposure levels of environmental pollutants in the EU were limited. Determining the trend of population level exposure concentrations across time is crucial to monitor the impact of policies, regulations, and interventions. The findings from this study would trigger EU and country level regulatory measures. Foremost, regulatory agencies of respective country and region could use the findings to evaluate the impact of previous policies

and update future policies aimed at reducing human exposure to environmental pollutants. Furthermore, determining the trend would push regulatory enforcement of existing policies to monitor and control pollutant sources. It would also guide the design and implementation of targeted public health interventions aiming at raising awareness about the risks associated with environmental pollutants and promoting healthier lifestyle choices to decrease personal exposure.

In PARC year 4 (first year of the project), data harmonization will be performed. Data from partner institutes will be validated and harmonized to have a standardized dataset that integrates diverse sources of human biomonitoring data across Europe, ensuring consistency and reliability for subsequent analysis. This will help us to decide whether we need analysis of biobank samples to have more data points. Potential errors and noise in the data will be identified and corrected using validation techniques developed by VITO (<https://hbm.vito.be/tools/tool-data-validation>). All partners with data will be involved in this activity: KI, MU, NIPH, RegionH-RH, SFA, SpF, SZU-CZ, UBA, UI, ULUND, ISS, VITO. At the end of Y4 a validated and harmonized dataset will be available for analysis and further use. Summary statistics will be calculated using the harmonized data, which will then be integrated into the Information Platform for Chemical Monitoring IPCHEM (<https://ipchem.jrc.ec.europa.eu/>) and the European Human Biomonitoring (HBM) dashboard (<https://hbm.vito.be/eu-hbm-dashboard>). All partners with data will be involved in this activity: KI, MU, NIPH, RegionH-RH, SFA, SpF, SZU-CZ, UBA, UI, ULUND, ISS, VITO. In addition, existing data will be evaluated to determine their suitability for pooled analysis. This includes assessing biomarkers, analytical methods, and target populations across different studies, which will guide the data analysis phase.

Furthermore, method development activities will commence on Q2 of Y4 (PARC M40). This activity helps to develop robust statistical methodologies and automated tools for analyzing the harmonized dataset, ensuring accurate identification of exposure patterns and trends using heterogeneous data. Method will be elaborated for time patterns/trends analysis of a statistical analysis plan for task 4.1, outlining the possible options and recommended methodologies to be used. MU, VITO, UH, UBA will be involved in this activity. Method development will not be finalized in Y4.

S4.1.1.4. Occupational surveys:

- **P4.1.1.4.a_Y1_OccupFeasability_TTL [M1-M29]:** The project has been finalized in M29
- **P4.1.1.4.b_Y1_SentinelSystem_KULeuven: [M1-M36]:** The project has been finalized in M36
- **P4.1.1.4.c_Y1_HealthCareSurvey_TTL_SRU [M1-M48]**

The sampling campaign has started fall 2024 and is expected to continue to the first quarter of Y4. Collected samples will be shipped to laboratories for analysis. The aim is to include altogether 20 hospitals and up to 650 workers. Samples are collected from hospital settings in 11 countries by the following partners: TTL (FI), SRU (NL), MU (CZ), UGR (ES), INRS (FR), ISS (IT), UMIL (IT), UNINA (IT), UNIPD (IT), RSU (LV), LNS (LU), HSE (UK), INSST (ES), INSA (PT). Also, STAMI (NO) will participate in their own cost increasing the number of countries to 12. Analysis of samples begins

already in Y3 but continues to Y4. Chemical substance groups prioritized for analysis are cytotoxic drugs, anesthetic substances (fluranes and N2O) and disinfectants (ethanol and isopropanol). Effect Biomarkers prioritized for analysis are markers for genotoxicity (reticulocyte and PBL micronuclei), oxidative stress and inflammation. The analyses of exposure and effect markers have been shared between the partners having analytical capability. List of exposure (bio)marker analyses to be performed in the study is provided below together with laboratories performing the analysis of either their own samples or receiving samples also from other countries with no laboratory capabilities for the given (bio)marker for analysis (common analysis laboratories).

Table 9: exposure biomarkers and external exposure markers analysed in P4.1.1.4.c_Y1_HealthCareSurvey_TTL_SRU and analytical laboratories

Exposure group	Compound	Biological matrix	Common analysis laboratory	Partners analyzing their own samples	
Cytotoxic drugs	Total platinum	Urine	ISS/IT	TTL/FI, HSE/UK, RSU/LV, INRS/FR	
	Cyclophosphamide, Isophosphamide, Methotrexate, Doxorubicine, Gemcitabin, Docetaxel, Paclitaxel, Etoposide, Cytarabine	Urine	SRU/NL	ISS-UNINA/IT HSE/UK (cyclophosphamide/ifosfamide only)	
	alpha-fluoro-beta-alanine (FBAL)	Urine	INRS/FR		
Anaesthetic gases	Parent compounds	Urine (Desflurane, Isoflurane, Nitrous oxide)	UMIL/IT	TTL/FI, HSE/UK (not N2O), UGR/ES	
		Exhaled air (Desflurane, Isoflurane, Sevoflurane, Nitrous oxide)	TTL/FI	HSE/UK	
	Metabolites	Urine (Hexafluoroisopropanol)	UMIL/IT	HSE/UK	
Disinfection products	Ethanol, IPA	Exhaled air	SRU/NL	HSE/UK (not ethanol)	
Cytotoxic drugs	Total platinum	Surface wipe	MU/CZ	HSE/UK	
		Dermal wipe	TTL/FI	HSE/UK	
		Air	SRU/NL	ISS/IT	
	Cyclophosphamide, Isophosphamide, Methotrexate, Doxorubicine, Gemcitabin, Docetaxel, Paclitaxel, Etoposide, Cytarabine	Surface wipe		MU/CZ	HSE/UK (cyclophosphamide/ifosfamide only)
		Dermal wipe		TTL/FI	HSE/UK (cyclophosphamide/ifosfamide only)
		Air		SRU/NL	ISS/IT
Anaesthetic gases	Desflurane, Isoflurane, Sevoflurane	Air	UMIL/IT	HSE/UK	

	Nitrous oxide	Air	UMIL/IT	HSE/UK
Disinfection products	Ethanol, IPA	Air	TTL/FI	HSE/UK (not ethanol)

In addition, effect marker analyses will be performed. The list of effect biomarkers included in the occupational healthcare study is provided in the table below with analysing laboratories.

Table 10: Biomarkers of effect P4.1.1.4.c_Y1_HealthCareSurvey_TTL_SRU and analytical laboratories

Exposure group	Assay	Biological matrix	Common analysis laboratory
Cytotoxic drugs exposed workers	PBL Micronuclei	Whole blood	UGR/ES
	RET Micronuclei	Whole blood	TTL/FI
	Comet assay	Whole blood	INSA-Porto/PT
Anaesthetic gases exposed workers	PBL Micronuclei	Whole blood	UGR/ES
	RET Micronuclei	Whole blood	TTL/FI
	Buccal micronuclei	Buccal cells	TTL/FI
	Comet assay	Whole blood	INSA-Porto/PT
	Oxidative stress (Glutathione)	Whole blood	LNS/LU
	Inflammatory markers	Plasma	RSU/LV
	Epigenetics	Whole blood	UNIPD/IT

- P4.1.1.4.d_Y1_OccupWaste_ENSP_TTL [M1-M48]

Sampling campaigns for this study started in the beginning of Y3 of PARC. Final samplings are expected to be performed during the first quarter of PARC Y4. Samples are collected in 13 countries by: ENSP-UNL (PT), AU (DK), ISS(IT), UNIPD (IT), UMIL (IT), UNINA (IT), WULS-SGGW (PL), ULUND (SE), STAMI (NO), AUTH (EL), INSA (PT), TTL (FI), LNS (LU), MOH-CY (CY), NIOM (PL), IOM (UK), HSE (UK) and UGR (ES). The aim is to cover 40-50 companies and up to 700 workers. Analysis of samples will begin in Y3 but continue to Y4. Chemical substance groups prioritized for analysis are metals, Flame retardants, Phthalates, Bisphenols, PFAS, plasticizers. Exposure markers to be analysed in P4.1.1.4.d_Y1_OccupWaste_ENSP_TTL are listed in the following table together with laboratories performing the analysis of either their own samples or receiving samples also from other countries with no laboratory capabilities for the given (bio)marker for analysis (common analysis laboratories).

Table 11: Exposure biomarkers and external exposure markers analysed in P4.1.1.4.d_Y1_OccupWaste_ENSP_TTL and analytical laboratories

Chemical class	Compound	Biological matrix	Common analysis laboratory	Partners analyzing their own samples
Metals	Cadmium, Lead	Blood	TTL/FI	STAMI/NO, ULUND/SE, DHP-UNINA-ISS/IT, KU Leuven/BE, UNIPD/IT,

				LNS/LU, NIOM/PL, AUTH/GR, HSE/UK
	Cadmium, Lead, Chromium, Mercury, Cobalt, Aluminium	Urine	STAMI/NO, LNS/LU	ULUND/SE, DHP-UNINA-ISS/IT, KU Leuven/BE, UNIPD/IT, TTL/FI, AUTH/GR, NIOM/PL, HSE/UK
Flame retardants	Brominated	Serum	LNS/LU	
	OPFRs metabolites	Urine	LNS/LU	ULUND/SE, HSE/UK
PFAS	PFHxA, PFOA, PFHpA, PFNA, PFDA, PFUnDA, FDoDA, PFBS, PFHxS, PFHpS, PFOS	Plasma	UMIL/IT	ULUND/SE
Bisphenols	A, F, S	Urine	AUTH/GR	ULUND/SE
Phthalates + DINCH	MEP, MBzP, MiBP, MnBP, MCHP, MnPeP, MEHP, 5OH-MEHP, 5oxo-MEHP, 5cx-MEPP, MnOP, OH-MiNP, cx-MiNP, OH-MiDP, cx-MiDP, DINCH	Urine	AUTH/GR	ULUND/SE
PAHs	1-hydroxypyrene	Urine	TTL/FI	ULUND/SE
Metals	Cadmium, Lead, Chromium, Mercury, Cobalt, Aluminium	Air	STAMI/NO	KU Leuven/BE, TTL/FI, ULUND/SE, LNS/LU, ISS/IT, AUTH/GR, NIOM/PL, HSE/UK
	Cadmium, Lead, Chromium, Mercury, Cobalt, Aluminium	Settled dust	LNS/LU	ISS/IT
	Cadmium, Lead, Chromium, Mercury, Cobalt, Aluminium	Dermal wipes	LNS/LU, TTL/FI, KU Leuven/BE	ISS/IT, AUTH/GR, HSE/UK
Flame retardants	PBDEs(#28,#47, #99, #100, #153, #154, #183, #209) / OPFRs (EHDPP, TBP, TPP, TBEP, TCEP, TdCPP, TEHP)	Settled dust	LNS/LU	

Effect Biomarkers prioritized for analysis are markers for genotoxicity, oxidative stress and inflammatory markers. These are analysed by the partners as described in the following table.

Table 12: Biomarkers of effect in P4.1.1.4.d_Y1_OccupWaste_ENSP_TTL and analytical laboratories

Biomarker	Matrix	Common analysis laboratory
PBL micronuclei	Blood	INSA/LISBON-PT, TTL/FI
Buccal micronuclei	Buccal cells	UNISANTE/CH

Frozen comet assay	Blood	INSA/PORTO-PT
Global DNA methylation	Blood	KU Leuven/BE
Gluthathione	Blood	LNS/LU
Inflammatory markers	Blood	KU Leuven/BE

A4.1.2 Laboratory analysis and quality assurance

There is no project for this activity since it is a transversal activity.

During Y4, work will be done in the selection of the best, state-of-the-art exposure biomarkers and analytical methods for those needs identified in the PARC HBM Targeted Studies that will be implemented in T4.1 as from Y4 (projects recently submitted for evaluation) (AU, AUTH, BPI, CEA, EHESP, FFA, FISABIO, IMROH, INSA, ISCIH, ISS, JSI, KU Leuven, KUM, LNS, LSMU, NIOM, NIPH, NPHSL, UKHSA, RSU, SRU, SpF, STAMI, SZU-SK, THL, UAntwerpen, UGR, ULFFA, ULPGC, ULUND, UMIL, UNN, UOC, UOULU, USI, VSCHT). In addition, the evaluation and selection of biomarkers will be also performed if new substances are included in the HBM studies as a result of the new activities, like the second prioritisation exercise, currently under consultation in the Governing Bodies in PARC.

If new biomarkers are included in the studies, the Quality Assurance Working Group (QAWG) (AU, ISCIH, NIPH, UAntwerpen, and WR) and collaborating partners (LNS) will work in close collaboration with T9.1 and T9.3 to develop and implement the required QA/QC measures to keep ensuring the quality and comparability of the HBM data generated under T4.1.

The PARC QA/QC programme will continue in year 4, two rounds of the programme are scheduled each year, and its duration will be aligned with the timeline of HBM surveys planned. The programme will adapt to new requirements both in terms of new biomarkers and concentration ranges to cover the needs of all the studies. The list of qualified laboratories that can analyse HBM samples in PARC will be updated as the results of the rounds are available. The QA/QC aspects related to the innovative sampling techniques will be evaluated and included in the add ons for the HBM surveys (ISCIH, LNS, MU, ONIRIS, UAntwerpen, UGR, UNIVIE, and UOC) as these activities are currently taking shape. The working group on reference analytical methods (ISCIH, ISS, LNS, MUI, NIPH, SCIENSANO, UAntwerpen, ULUND, UNIVIE, and UOC) will continue updating the inventory to identify strong/weak points related to the analytical methods for the selected substances and the needs to harmonise important preanalytical issues. This activity led to the design in Y3 of two activities on method development and harmonization that will continue in Y4. These two activities are:

- Monitoring urinary mono-n-hexyl phthalate and its secondary metabolites. Coordinated by NIPH; partners: UAntwerpen, RegionH, ULUND, and LNS; external expert Dr. Holger Koch (Institute of the Ruhr-University Bochum, IPA). The tasks include the method development (Autum 2024 - Summer 2025, with the following activities: (a) Mapping urinary biomarkers for exposure determination of DnHexP; (b) Checking availability of standards and internal standards of the biomarkers and initiation of custom synthesis of standards if required; (c) Inclusion of biomarkers in the existing phthalate methods, validation of the methods for new biomarkers; (d) Inter-laboratory comparison between

the involved PARC partners) and the analysis of MnHexP in a subset of selected populations such as HBM4EU aligned studies 2016-2017 and PARC Aligned Studies (Summer 2025- Spring/Summer 2026).

- Polar PFAS in human samples. Coordinated by NIPH; partners: UAntwerpen, ISS, ULUND, and LNS. The tasks include the method development (Year 2025, with the following activities: (a) Selecting PFASs that are important to include of ultrashort and short PFAS (C1-C6); (b) Acquiring selected standards and internal standards of the biomarkers; (c) Establishment and validation of method; (d) Inter-laboratory comparison will be performed between the involved PARC partners) and the analysis of of polar PFASs in in a subset of selected populations (Year 2026; with the following activities: (a) Selection of most suitable matrix for HBM in a small pilot study, (b) Sample analysis).

In Y4 the chemical analysis plan will be already implemented (LNS, MU, NIOM, RSU, SRU, SCIENSANO, SpF, THL, TTL, UAntwerpen, UBA, UGR, and ULUND). The information collected from laboratories and the progress of chemical analyses will be regularly updated. The implementation of effect biomarkers will take place under P4.1.3.3.a_Y1_RoadmapLinkingHBMhealth_SpF_VITO, and details are provided below.

A4.1.3 Link exposure and health related information

No transversal activities under A4.1.3, all captured in projects.

Details per project:

- P4.1.3.1.a_Y1_Derivation of HBM-GVs_UBA [M1-M81] (The project has been extended from M36 to M81)

Health-Based HBM-GVs will be derived for a third set of prioritised substances (ANSES, AUTH, MOH-IL, NIJZ, NIPH, TTL, UBA, Unisante, SECO, LNS). HBM-GVs for selected substances or their specific exposure biomarkers will be derived according to the strategy agreed under HBM4EU and described by Apel et al. (2020; <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijheh.2020.113622>). In principle, all lead experts conduct a literature search on the substance under consideration to determine the current state of toxicological/epidemiological knowledge. Depending on the data basis, the experts decide whether epidemiological data, or else a recognized external toxicity reference value respectively occupational exposure limit, or a point of departure from an experimental study together with toxicokinetic information is used to derive the HBM-GV. Thus, HBM data are only included in the derivation if studies are available that show a relationship between human internal exposure and health effects. If additional data is needed WP 5 will be involved to fill the data gaps.

The substance dossiers including the derived values will afterwards be reviewed by project partners and other experts involved via the NHs.

NIPH and TTL will work on mercury. It is to be examined whether and, if so, which significant published toxicological findings need to be added to the dossier in the HBM4EU Deliverable D5.12 (Deliverables – HBM4EU – science and policy for a healthy future). The findings on the toxicology of

mercury presented in the HBM4EU Deliverable D13.7 (Deliverables – HBM4EU – science and policy for a healthy future) should also be taken into account. Based on this, it should be clarified whether the provisional HBM-GVs for the general population (7 µg Hg/l urine, 3.5 µg Hg/l blood) which were derived within HBM4EU can be adopted. AUTH offered support regarding modelling work.

ANSES will check whether the derivation of HBM-GV for arsenic is possible and will work on HBM-GV for cis-/trans-DCCA as metabolites of various pyrethroids. A working group led by MOH-IL and involving NIPH, possibly LNS and WP 6 partners (6.2.3., case study on mixture RA) will evaluate whether/which further work is needed to reassess PFAS HBM guidance values as part of PARC. With the aim of deriving HBM-GV, UBA will work on Acetamiprid/N-desmethyl acetamiprid and the phthalate substitute DEHA (di(2-ethylhexyl)adipate). It is planned that dossiers and reports for the abovementioned substances are included in AD4.3.

- P4.1.3.1.b_Y4_Health-based-IA-GV_LNS_NCPHP [M37-M81]

For a health-related interpretation of human indoor air exposures data and for effective risk management, guideline values are needed that have been derived epidemiologically or toxicologically and relate directly to the measured indoor air concentrations. Methodological harmonization and sufficient coverage of relevant substances with indoor air guideline values is lacking, in order to allow systematic and health-based evaluation of indoor air pollution by national risk assessors, public health institutes or European regulatory bodies.

In the first year of the project (Y4), partners (LNS, NCPHP, UBA, VITO, TTL, EAA, MU, KI, INSA, ENSP) will review and summarize the existing initiatives and methodologies to derive health-based indoor air guideline values and a mutually agreed methodology how to derive indoor air guideline values based on toxicological and/or epidemiological data will be proposed in alignment with regulatory accepted standards to achieve harmonization. The work on an inventory of indoor air guideline values will be initiated. Existing (inter)national guideline values should be identified with main emphasis on substances prioritized in the 4.2_HumanExposure and 4.1_General Survey projects. Furthermore, criteria will be developed to prioritize substances relevant for indoor air and compiling a substance prioritisation list. Project partners will also initiate contact to other relevant (inter)national initiatives outside PARC to explore synergies in methodological harmonisation and derivation of indoor air guideline values.

- P4.1.3.3.a_Y1_RoadmapLinkingHBMhealth_SpF_VITO [M1-M52]

Part 1: Health Outcomes

Partners involved in this part of the project: [SpF (lead), VITO (lead), BPI, IDAEA-CSIC, EAA, EHESP, Fraunhofer-IBMT, INSST, JSI, KU Leuven, LNS, NIJZ, UKHSA, RSU, TTL, UBA, UPV/EHU].

In Y4, the feasibility study will be performed to explore the link between past exposures and health effects (biological and clinical). This feasibility study will be conducted using data from existing cohorts. These cohorts must include exposure measurements as well as the evaluation of health outcomes. Additionally, biological samples, stored in biobanks, must be available for further analysis of effect biomarkers. Two partners have already expressed their interest in being involved in this

study: VITO with the 3xG cohort (Belgium) and UPV/EHU with the INMA Projeet (Spain). Other partners have been contacted.

After the launch of the feasibility study at the end of Y3, during the Y4 we will work on:

- Selecting and defining study criteria for the measurements of exposures, health outcomes, and effect biomarkers.
- Developing a data analysis approach in collaboration with A4.1.4-Data management and analysis and WP7.
- Measuring the selected effect biomarkers in available biological samples, in collaboration with VITO - P4.1.3.3.an Identification of effect biomarkers.
- Initiating data analysis to link past exposures, effect biomarkers, and health outcomes with participating studies.

Part 2: Identification of effect biomarkers

Partners involved in this part of the project: Core partners: VITO (lead), SpF, AU, AUTH, EAA, INRS, INSA, Inserm, ISCIII, JSI, LNS, MU, SECO, TTL, UGR. Additional partners: BPI, CEA, IDAEA-CSIC, KU Leuven, LSMU, NIJZ, NIOM, NLZOH, UKHSA, SRU, Sciensano, STAMI, UGent, ULPGC, UNINA, UNIPD, UOC, UOULU, USI, WULS-SGGW.

In year 4, VITO will continue to lead the implementation of effect biomarkers in PARC surveys. Together with the project partners, VITO will support approved targeted studies for inclusion of effect biomarker analyses and/or health outcomes implementation. Based on the final implementation plan (submitted M22), the general survey project established an overview on which studies will measure which biomarkers of effect together with information on the tools they use for health outcome assessment. UGR will continue the selection of labs to measure the effect biomarkers, together with T4.1.2 (ISCIII) and supported by VITO. The QA/QC aspects for effect biomarker measurements and derivation of respective SOPs are organized by UGR with support of ISCIII and T9.3, as documented in "Design and implementation of a quality assurance/quality control (QA/QC) laboratory program for the implementation of effect biomarkers". In year 4, the actual QA/QC program will be initiated and will run in alignment with the requirements of the studies and the laboratories involved.

A4.1.4 Data management and analysis

Details for transversal activities:

- Data management: the T4.1 data management team (VITO, MU, SPF, UBA, TTL, PIH) will further support all HBM related data management activities in T4.1. That is the development of the codebooks, the validation of the biomarker list, feedback and testing of the tools on data validation, calculation of derived variables and calculation of summary statistics (<https://hbm.vito.be/tools>), feedback on the integration of aggregated data into the European HBM dashboard and IPCHEM, definition of metadata for HBM studies and feedback on user interface for the collection of metadata, support in development of project DMP, helpdesk for data management activities.

- Statistical working group: the statistical working group (VITO, UU-IRAS, MU, JSI, AU-PH, SPF, UBA, NIPH, INRAE, INSA, TTL, UH) will further elaborate the statistical analysis plan for the ongoing 4.1 projects. The statistical working group (WG) gives support and advice to research leads in performing the statistical analyses.

- During Y4, statistical analyses related to targeted occupational projects (P4.1.1.4.d_Y1_OccupWaste_ENSP_TTL) and (P4.1.1.4.c_Y1_Occuphealthcare_TTL_SRU) are planned to be performed (during the last quarter of Y4). These will be performed following the statistical analysis plan created in T4.1.4 (TTL, INSA, INRS, STAMI, LNS).

Details per project:

- P4.1.4.2.a_Y1_DataAnalysisHBM4EU_VITO [M1-M48] (the project has been extended from M36 to M48)

Reason for extension: For the further analyses of the HBM4EU MoM-study, the SPECIMEn study and the HBM4EU occupational studies, a delay was caused in the initiation of the statistical analysis, due to capacity issues at the involved partners' institute. For the geospatial analysis of the HBM4EU aligned studies, it took some time to come up with the best technical solution to derive geospatial variables from the geolocation of the participants, and for the development of this tool. And now some time will be needed to allow the data owners to train themselves and implement the tool. For the exposure-effect analyses of the HBM4EU aligned studies, the approval of the data requests took longer than anticipated.

Results achieved so far: For the exposure-effect analyses of the HBM4EU Aligned Studies, two manuscripts were published. For the geospatial analyses of the HBM4EU Aligned Studies, a tool was developed to retrieve geospatial variables from the geocoordinates of participants. For all the other research questions, statistical analyses were initiated.

Plans year 4: The project is extended with one year, making year 4 the final year of the project and will be devoted to finalizing the statistical analyses of the data and the interpretation and discussion of the results. Scientific peer-reviewed publications will be elaborated and submitted. Results will be reported and communicated to the PARC community (AD4.11). Partners involved: AU-PH, AUTH, BPI, EASP, INRAE, INRS, INSA, ISCIH, ISSeP, JSI, LNS, LSMU, MU, NIJZ, NIPH, Sciansano, SpF, SZU-SK, TTL, UBA, UGR, UU-IRAS, VITO.

A4.1.5 Preparation of a sustainable monitoring and surveillance system for Europe

No transversal activities under A4.1.5, all captured in projects.

Details per project:

- P4.1.5.a_Y1_SustainHBMSystem_VITO [M1-M66]

This project will be continued in Y4. The project's goal is the preparation of a sustainable HBM and surveillance system for Europe.

Following actions are planned for Y4:

Foster interaction with international key players in HBM to exchange experiences and improve international collaboration and comparison of HBM data. Continued engagement with the PARC GB to develop a roadmap for sustainable HBM after PARC. The project is co-led by VITO and SpF. Other partners involved in the actions are FOPH, INSA, ISCIII, LNS, LSMU, MOH-CY/SGL, NIPH, UBA. This project will be run in close collaboration with WP2 and the PARC Exit Strategy. Participation in inter-task meetings on sustainability (T1.3, T2.3 and P4.1.5.a_Y1_SustainHBMSystem). Organization of a workshop to share experiences on policy uptake of HBM results (HBM4EU results).

Task 4.2: Environmental and multisource monitoring

Co-leaders: INERIS (FR), AU (DK)

Partners: ANSES (FR), BfG (DE), BRGM (FR), CNRS (FR), CNR-IRSA (IT), CSIC (ES), CSTB (FR), EA (UK), EAWAG (CH), EFET (EL), Fraunhofer-IME (DE), FISABIO (ES), INRAE (FR), INSERM (FR), ISS (IT), ISSeP (BE), IVL (SE), JSI (SI), LNS (LU), MU (CZ), NKUA (EL), OFB (FR), ONIRIS (FR), OVAM (BE), SCIENSANO (BE), SLU (SE), SYKE (FI), UAntwerpen (BE), UBA (DE), UCLM (PT), UFZ (DE), UL (LV), ULFFA (SI), UniLU (LU), VITO (BE), VSCHT (CZ), ISCIII (ES), VUA (NL), NILU (NO), UKCEH (UK), BPI (EL), NMBU (NO), SpF (FR), DCU⁴ (IE)

The work in T4.2 will proceed in the following projects and transversal activities in Y4:

- P4.2.a_Y1_ENVMonitoringPilotSurvey_INERIS_AU [M1-M42] (the project has been extended from M36 to M42)

This project focuses on PFAS and EDCs with the purpose of establishing and validating environmental monitoring structures for the long-term work in T4.2. Comprehensive monitoring campaigns across air, water, soil, and biota using bioassays, target analysis, and suspect screening have been performed. The PFAS study involves baseline analyses of existing monitoring data from 10 countries and 19 case studies exploring PFAS transport, transformation, environmental factors, and source identification through fingerprinting methods. Originally planned for three years, a six-months extension into Y4 has been sought for the project. These six months will concentrate on the last two steps in the project, i.e. 4.2.5 Data analysis and transfer and 4.2.6 Feedback mechanism. The data analysis and transfer will be a continuation and finalization of the work started in Y3, according to a workflow for data transfer to the NORMAN database (as defined with WP7) with integrated QA/QC steps and a statistical analysis plan for the data treatment. Lessons learnt will be addressed in the feedback mechanism including all steps of the process. The collection of information has been started in Y3 and will include different perspectives, i.e. from T4.2 partners, project leaders, task co-leads, WP co-leads and collaboration partners outside of WP4, as well as different topics, such as (but not limited to), i) internal organization, ii) timelines, iii) collaboration outside of T4.2, iv) technical challenges, v) expected and real outputs, vi) level of scientific progress, vii) impacts and products.

⁴ AMD-101057014-118: Dublin City University – PARC acronym “DCU”, PIC number 999892588 entered as new Beneficiary in PARC as of 01/10/2024 with the agreement that the ‘Environment Protection Agency’ (EPA) remains the only member of the Grant Signatory Board and takes over responsibility for coordinating Ireland’s engagement in PARC in the same way as other grant signatories with AE do. The starting date for the eligibility of the costs for DCU was on 01/10/2024 and DCU will contribute under T4.2.

Partners involved: (The list of partners involved in this activity may change depending on the development of the work). SLU; BfG; NKUA; UFZ; MU; SCIENSANO; AU; INERIS; IVL; EAWAG; INRAE; SYKE; CSIC; CNR-IRSA; ONIRIS; OVAM; UAntwerp; VSCHT; INSERM; BRGM; FISABIO; UBA. The project will be concluded with a project report (R1; D4.4; M42).

- P4.2.b_Y2_Monitoringframe [M12-M36] (the project has been extended from M30- M36)

This project has been finalized in M36.

- P4.2.c_Y3_HumanExposure_INERIS_AU [M25-M72]

This project has the aim to support the T4.1 project (P4.1.1.2.a_Y1_GenHBMSurvey_VITO) with personal exposure data to chemicals from environmental samples (e.g. dust, soil) and to generate knowledge of the exposure to chemicals from non-food environmental sources. As one central activity, the work in Y4 will focus on the actual monitoring activities, i.e. the collection and analysis of samples with associated QA/QC. Furthermore, the activity on 4.2.5 Data transfer and analysis will be started in parallel, as it requires close coordination with the data collection and treatment in T4.1. The activity will also build on procedures and material developed in P4.2.a_Y1 with regard to transfer of environmental data to NORMAN, adjusting them to the purpose of this project. Partners involved: AU; INERIS; LNS; CSTB; NILU; AUTh; VITO; ISCIII; UBA; UAntwerp; MOH-CY/SGL; MU; JSI; IDAEA-CSIC; ISS; ISSeP; IVL; NKUA; OVAM; RSU; UL; UniLU; UFZ; UPV/EHU; VSCHT (The list of partners needs final confirmation).

Furthermore, T4.2 and T4.3 envision at least one joint project starting in Y5, related to the proposed "PARC Future Activities" that would particularly benefit from coordinated approaches involving innovative methods and environmental monitoring. One candidate topic is related to chemicals in soil in the context of the new regulatory framework foreseen in this field and has already been addressed with preliminary preparatory work in T4.3. A second topic relates to the leaching of plastic additives. For this, coordination with project 6.4.3.1 "A comprehensive review and application of databases and testing methods for substances of concern in consumer products and materials" will be pursued.

Given the complexity of the field and the multi-partner organisational framework, T4.2 and T4.3 plan a joint one-year transversal activity in Y4 dedicated to the development of at least one combined project. The work will include a comprehensive mapping of research and monitoring activities recently initiated at EU and national level, to ensure complementarity of efforts and create structures for efficient information exchange. The timing of the transversal activity in Y4 will allow to build on results of the first projects in T4.2 and T4.3, including the use of newly developed strategies, techniques and materials. Partners for the transversal activities will still have to be selected.

- P4.2.d_Y4_Siloxanes_AU_INERIS [M37-M60]

The objective of the project is to generate environmental data for siloxanes, a chemical group of high regulatory relevance, taking into consideration that the chemical analysis of siloxanes poses several challenges. As PARC includes partners with this chemical expertise, it is the idea with this project to create a network of expert laboratories (together with WP9), address the state-of-the-art regarding

these chemical analyses, including possibilities and limitations, and produce data on siloxanes in a selection of relevant matrices. The work in Y4 will focus on evaluating the technical feasibility of generating environmental data to support regulatory actions. Should this phase conclude that obtaining siloxane measurements of sufficient analytical quality for regulatory purposes is not feasible, the project will be discontinued. The second phase, contingent on the results of the first, will involve conducting a monitoring campaign.

A tentative list of partners includes AU, INERIS, IVL, NILU, NKUA, IDAEA-CSIC, UBA, MU, UAntwerp, ISCIII and WUR.

T4.2 will also continue to contribute to relevant horizontal activities in PARC. For example, the PARC QA/QC core group (initiated by WP9) and potential substance-specific working groups. T4.2 will collaborate with WP7 and WP9 on all activities regarding inventorying and automated retrieval of data from external data sources, as well as storage of monitoring data generated by T4.2 projects.

Task 4.3: Innovative methods and tools for monitoring and surveys

Co-Leaders: INRAE (FR), VUA (NL)

Partners: ANSES (FR), AU (DK), BfG (DE), BRGM (FR), CEA (FR), CNRS (FR), EAWAG (CH), EHESP (FR), INERIS (FR), INRS (FR), IRFM (IT), JSI (SI), KWR (NL), LNS (LU), MU (CZ), MUI (AT), ONIRIS (FR), ORU (SE), SLU (SE), SpF (FR), UAntwerpen (BE), UBA (DE), UBAH (UK), UCPH (DK), UFZ (DE), UGR (ES), UniLU (LU), UNIVIE (AT), VITO (BE), WR (NL), AUTH (EL), BPI (GR), CNR-IRSA (IT), CSIC (ES), EA (UK), EV-ILVO (NL), FMUL (PT), GCSL (GR), GeoZS (SI), CSIC (ES), IISPV (ES), ISCIII (ES), ISS (IT), IVL (SE), JU (CZ), KUM (DE), LNE (FR), NIB (SI), NIJZ (SI), NILU (NO), NIOM (PL), OFB (FR), STAMI (NO), SU (SE), SYKE (FI), THL (FI), TNO (NL), TTL (FI), UEF (FI), UG-AT (AT), UG-PL (PL), UKCEH (UK), UL (LV), ULFFA (SI), UNIABDN (UK), VSCHT (CZ), WULS-SGGW (PL), UEF⁵ (FI)

A4.3.1 Transversal actions

Details per project:

- **P4.3.1.a_Y1_T01-Concept Paper_MU [M1 - M12]:** The project has been finalized in M12

- **P4.3.1.b_Y1_T02-QA/QC_WR [M1 - M60] (The project has been extended from M36 to M60)**

This project will define minimum QA/QC requirements to be used specifically for chemical screening methods based on chromatography coupled to High Resolution Mass Spectrometry (HRMS) and biological effect-directed analysis (EDA) and will be closely linked to the activities in T9.3 (Joint activities – harmonisation, and its project: towards harmonised QA/QC in laboratory testing). In this, existing international standards (e.g. ISO/IEC 17025, OECD GLP) are taken into account and serve as a basis for more detailed and dedicated protocols/procedures (and where appropriate criteria). In addition, there are also links with projects in T4.2. In year 4 the prioritized

⁵ AMD-101057014-118: The University of Eastern Finland - PARC acronym “UEF”, PIC number 991207984, entered in PARC as new affiliated entity as of 01/05/2024 with the Finnish Institute of Occupational Health - PARC acronym “TTL”, acting as Beneficiary. The starting date for the eligibility of the costs for UEF was on 01/05/2024. UEF contributes in the project P4.3.2.b_Y2_H02-Occupational exposure of the WP4 (task 4.3), by providing innovative nontargeted screening approach for analysis of conventional blood samples by non-targeted UHPLC-MS method and in task 9.4 with their participation in the mapping of existing training, and in the outline of PARC training plan.

focus on (1) the proposal of one (or more) common mixture(s) of QA/QC markers to be used for harmonized method performance assessment purpose and reporting across laboratories with the perspective of a medium term and sustainable objective, and (2) the proposal of operational strategies for improving the semi-quantitative performances typically obtained with these screening approaches with the perspective of increasing the resulting data interpretability and usefulness under a support to policy context will continue by the working groups established in Y3. Additionally, in Y4, an inventory and review of existing QA/QC in bioeffect assay/EDA approaches will be initiated.

Partners involved: Lead: WR (NL). Partners: INRAE (FR), ANSES (FR), AU (DK), BfG (DE), BRGM (FR), EAWAG (CH), EHESP (FR), INRS (FR), JSI (SI), KWR (NL), LNS (LU), MU (CZ), MUI (AU), ONIRIS (FR), ORU-MTM (SE), SLU (SE), UAntwerpen (UA), UBA (DE), UCPH (DK), UFZ (DE), AUTH (EL), EV-ILVO (BE), CSIC (ES), LNE (FR), WULS-SGGW (PL).

- P4.3.1.c_Y1_T03-EWStools_SLU [M1 - M60]

This project will support the development of an Early Warning System (EWS) in T8.2 by ensuring that data generated by innovative (self) sampling methods in combination with SS/NTS/effect-direct-analysis (EDA) approaches can be used to identify and to prioritize hazardous substances. In year 4, a reinforced focus will be operated to formulate a set of operational criteria for the categorization of annotated data to be integrated in the EWS format, as a basis to further elaborate a global decision tree aiming at guiding the way from the lab data to the useful support to policy with regard to these new innovative methodological approaches and will be summarized in a perspective article on innovative approaches as a contribution to an EWS.

Lead: SLU (SE), Participants: INRAE (FR), VUA (NL), ANSES (FR), BRGM (FR), EAWAG (CH), JSI (SI), MUI (AT), ORU-MTM (SE), UAntwerpen (BE), UBA (DE), UCPH (DK), UFZ (DE), UniLU (LU), AUTH (EL), ISS (IT), NILU (NO).

- P4.3.1.d_Y1_T04-Data Processing Workflow_EHESP [M1 - M60]

This project consists in developing a comprehensive, user-friendly and semi-automated pipeline for SS/NTS/EDA related data processing, to be used as a harmonized provision across laboratories contributing to a more rapid and efficient interpretability of the generated data for research and support to policy purposes. In Y4, all the data generated via the collaborative trial performed in Y3 using 3 real data sets covering both the environmental, food and human monitoring fields will be analysed in order to make the selection of the best data pre-processing options and provide robust QA/QC associated to data pre-processing. A tool that generates automatic report QA/QC for data pre-processing will be developed (Python) and included in the Galaxy workflow. In Y4, the generation of tools for the automatization of the suspect screening will be validated and valorized. In Y4, it is planned also to start building the Galaxy workflow with all partners using existing tools and the newly developed tools. Tasks will be given to the different partners in this aim.

Lead: EHESP, Participants: INRAE (FR), MUI (AT), UFZ (DE), ANSES (FR), UniLU (LU), WR (NL), VUA (NL), INRS (FR), ONIRIS (FR), MU (CZ), UCPH (DK), JSI (SI), KWR (DE), UBA(DE).

A4.3.2 Human samples-based proof-of-concepts

Details per project:

- P4.3.2.a_Y1_H01-Perinatal exposure_INRAE [M1 - M48]

The objective of this project is to develop a proof-of-concept permitting to assess the performances of selected innovative sampling (silicone wristbands, dried blood spots) and chemical profiling methods (HRMS based SS/NTS and EDA) and elucidating biasing factors in comparison with those of conventional and targeted approaches with a specific focus on perinatal exposure. During Year 4, after generating and compiling the results from the chemical SS/NTS profiling of urine, blood, and maternal milk samples from the 30 pregnant women, an extensive and comprehensive data analysis will be conducted. This analysis will allow us to produce a consolidated list expressing the real exposure profiling. These results, combined with the findings from the inter-lab assay, will help us to further harmonize methodologies through the proposal of updated or refined SOPs. A second round of SS/NTS analysis is planned for the second half of Y4, following a call for new sample sourcing. Regarding innovative sampling methods, the literature reviews on silicone wristbands (SWB) and dried blood spots (DBS) will be finalized, and the methodological testing phase for SWB will be performed, including an evaluation of different pre-treatment and clean-up procedures. Additionally, the conception and execution of a similar testing phase for DBS will be an important component of the Y4 work plan.

Lead: INRAE (FR), Participants: EHESP (FR), CEA (FR), VUA (NL), KUM (DE), UNIVIE (AT), UFZ (DE), WR (NL), JSI (SI), MUI (AT), UAntwerpen (BE), UGR (ES), AU (DK), UniLU (LU), LNS (LU), UNIADBN (UK), MU (CZ), ISPV (ES), VSCHT (CZ), BPI (GR), VITO (BE), CSIC (ES), ISCIII (ES), ISS (ES), SU (SE), AUTH (EL).

- P4.3.2.b_Y2_H02-Occupational exposure_INRS/LNS [M13-M60]

The project aims to develop and validate innovative sampling methods and HRMS-based screening techniques for assessing occupational exposure to chemicals of emerging concern. This will be done using a tiered approach, starting with knowledge reviews and integrating these new methods into conventional occupational exposure studies (T4.1). Key objectives include: (1) Evaluating the performance of innovative sampling methods (e.g., SWB, DBS) and HRMS-based analysis compared to conventional methods. (2) Identifying new exposure markers linked to occupational exposure. During Y4, the project will focus on: (1) Reporting and evaluating results from an interlaboratory assay (H02) conducted at the end of Year 3 for HRMS-based analysis in collaboration with H01/H03. These results will contribute to method performance assessment which will be discussed and published with project partners; (2) Developing a strategy for analyzing conventional and innovative samples collected under the 4.1 project, which were postponed from Year 3. 4.1 project partners will complete sample collection during Y4. Based on the outcomes of the first interlaboratory assay and the analytical capabilities assessed during Y2, a strategy will be developed for samples analyses. This strategy will outline how the samples will be distributed for SS/NTS

analysis, ensuring optimal use of available resources and analytical techniques. (3) The collaboration with the H01 project will continue to refine methodologies and literature reviews for SWB and DBS. [Lead: INRS (FR), LNS (LU), participants: WULS-SGGW (PL), INRAE (FR), MUI (AT), UGR (ES), STAMI (NO), UAntwerpen (BE), TTL (FI), UEF (FI), MU (CZ), JSI (SI), WR (NL), BPI (GR), AUTH (EL)].

- P4.3.2.c_Y3_H03-Complementary developments_JSI/UAntwerpen [M25 - M72]

This project will elaborate and conduct a set of actions complementary to those already running in the previous project H01 and H02 that cannot address all necessary aspects of innovative method assessment and improvement regarding to their application to human samples. One primary project objective is to evaluate the effectiveness of complementary methodological strategies including orthogonal liquid chromatography separation systems (e.g. HILIC adapted to highly polar compounds/metabolites), alternative sample preparation protocols directly impacting the analytical results (e.g. deconjugation, phospholipid removal), and the use of alternative non-invasive matrices (e.g. hair or saliva), finally leading to potential additional SOPs of interest. A second objective is to start capitalizing on main results and lessons learnt originated from our transversal projects related in particular to QA/QC and data processing issues, as a means to apply those gained outputs to new batches of real samples as an extended illustration of their usefulness. To that end, a direct link will be established to PARC task 4.1 aligned studies to source a set of supporting samples already planned to be analysed through conventional targeted methods for complementing these analyses with innovative screening results. Building on the initial investigations in Y3 regarding the benefits of HILIC for expanding chemical space, Y4 will focus on designing a proof-of-concept study. This phase will be closely aligned with Task 4.1 Aligned Studies, specifically detailing sample sourcing and coordinating the shipment of samples to laboratories for BoE analysis, which will begin in Y5. For alternative matrix analyses, a targeted multi-residue method for hair analysis developed in Y3 will be adapted for NTS/SS screening in Y4 and tested on actual hair samples. Additionally, the project will continue advancing cross-cutting priorities. Based on the results and lessons learned from the interlaboratory assays conducted by H01 and H02, and identifying any knowledge or data gaps, H03 will lead the organization of a third interlaboratory assay in Y4. Results are expected by early Y5, paving the way for testing laboratories to participate in proof-of-concept analyses of samples sourced by Task 4.1 Aligned Studies.

Lead: JSI (SI), UAntwerpen (BE), Participants: AUTH (GR), BPI (GR), CEA (FR), IISPV (ES), ISCIII (ES), ISS (IT), LNS (LU), MU (CZ), MUI (AT), SU (SE), UFZ (DE), VITO (BE), VSCHT (CZ), VUA (NL), WR (NL), WULS (PL), INRAE (FR), CNRS (FR), CSIC (ES), INRS (FR), AU (DK).

A4.3.3 Environment samples-based proof-of-concepts

Details per project:

- P4.3.3.a_Y1_E01_Wastewater based epidemiology_UFZ-UBATH [M1 - M48] (The project has been extended from M36 to M48)

This project addresses both human and environmental exposure, focusing on fingerprinting of wastewater treatment plant influents as a proxy for community wide human exposure assessment

and on screening of wastewater treatment plants (WWTP) effluents to assess the release of Chemicals of Emerging Concern (CECs) into the water cycle. In year 4, we will continue the work on a pan-European study to capture both human and environmental exposures to hazardous chemicals. This will include further development of targeted and non-targeted screening methods including validation for the assessment of human exposure.

Partners involved: UFZ (DE), UBATH (UK), MUI (AT), UCPH (DK), EAWAG (CH), KWR (NL), UniLU (LU), INERIS (FR), BfG (DE), BRGM (FR), IRFM (IT), ORU-MTM (SE), SLU (SE), UAntwerpen (BE), JSI (SI), WULS-SGGW (PL), JU (CZ), UG-PL (PL).

For the environmental exposure assessment, the prioritization of features and patterns from screening data will be finalised

Partners involved: UFZ (DE), UBATH (UK), MUI (AT), UCPH (DK), EAWAG (CH), ORU-MTM (SE), SLU (SE), JSI (SI), KWR (NL), UniLU (LU), VUA (NL), INERIS (FR), BfG (DE), VITO (BE), BRGM (FR), WULS-SGGW (PL), JU (CZ), MU (CZ), INRAE (FR), OFB (FR), UL (LV), UG-PL (PL).]. The Method for high-throughput EDA [Partners involved: UFZ (DE), UCPH (DK), EAWAG (CH), ORU-MTM (SE), SLU (SE), KWR (NL), VUA (NL), ISS (IT), INERIS (FR), BfG (DE), VITO (BE), UL-FFA (SI), JU (CZ), INRAE (FR), UG-PL (PL)]

and the data mining methods and proof of concept on existing datasets

Partners involved: UFZ (DE), UBATH (UK), MUI (AT), UCPH (DK), EAWAG (CH), KWR (NL), UniLU (LU), INERIS (FR), BfG (DE), BRGM (FR)] will be developed.

WBE-based human exposure to chemicals will be assessed across Europe via the development of Wastewater Based Epidemiology (WBE) workflows and their application in samples collected across European towns and cities. Finally, the (bio-)analytical results of the pan-European study will be linked and evaluated for use in future publications and recommendations for decision making.

- P4.3.3.b_Y2_E02-Sentinel animals_ONIRIS [M13-M60]

This project will elaborate and conduct a proof-of-concept demonstrating the potential use of sentinel animal species for capturing human exposure to emerging chemicals along the food chain. During Y4, the three defined Actions will be conducted in parallel. Within Action 1 on aquatic invertebrates (mussel/gammarids) led by SU (SE) and ONIRIS (FR), samples set data to be used will be selected, the necessary MTA elaborated, samples shipped, and data shared from sample owners to receivers. Sample analysis will be started, taking advantage of P4.3.1.b_Y1_T02-QA/QC recommendations. Action 2 on bees and bees products led by JSI (SI) and ANSES (FR) will be launched through a PhD-project, starting with bibliography and sampling. Contributions from other partners will be defined and aggregated to the Action. Action 3 relating to the drafting of a systematic review article on animal sentinel species for chemical hazards in the environment and food, led by ONIRIS (FR) with support from OFB (FR), will be subjected to back and forth with the partners. The perspective of developing this project in a support to policy context (e.g., contribution to early warning system through the capture of chemical hazards of concern for ecosystem and human health will be pursued.

Lead : ONIRIS (FR), Participants : ANSES (FR), AU (DK), BfR (DE), Eawag (CH), CSIC (ES), INRAE (FR), JSI (SI), JU (CZ), OFB (FR), ORU-MTM (SE), SU (SE), UFZ (DE), UG-AT (AT), VUA (NL).

A4.3.4 Food samples-based proof-of-concepts

- P4.3.4.a_Y2_F02- Food items exposure_ANSES [M13 - M48]

This project will elaborate and conduct a set of complementary studies to illustrate the facility of innovative screening approaches (SS/NTS/EDA) to investigate real life complex co-exposures and emerging chemicals from food items. During Y4, the results obtained by the partners involved in the interlaboratory assay will be gathered by the project leaders. These results will be processed in order to compare qualitatively and quantitatively analytical strategies and SS/NTS workflows (from food sample preparation to data acquisition and data processing). Hence, the assessment of their complementarities or overlap in terms of captured exposure markers (known, emerging and unknown chemicals) in food is expected. From the results of the interlaboratory study, a working group made up of interested partners will then work on proposing harmonized/consensual SOPs for sample preparation, data acquisition and data processing. The perspective of developing this project in a support to policy context (e.g. contribution to early warning system through the capture of chemical hazards of concern associated to food exposure) will be pursued.

Lead: ANSES (FR). Participants: INRAE (FR), VUA (NL), BfG (DE), CEA (FR), CNRS (FR), EAWAG (CH), CSIC (SP), ISS (IT), JSI (SI), MUI (AT), Oniris (FR), SLU (SE), UAntwerpen (BE), UL-FFA (SL), VSCHT (CZ), WR (NL), WULS (PL), EV-ILVO (BE), GCSL (EL).

Deliverables:

D4.2 1st Proof-of-concept assessing the usefulness of innovative (self-) sampling combined with integrated suspect/NTS/EDA approaches - Leader: VUA, initially due M35 is postponed to M48

D4.4. 1st Progress report on on-going monitoring projects – Leader: AU, initially due M36 is postponed to M42. This will be included in the next amendment of the GA.

D4.5 2nd Proof-of-concept assessing the usefulness of innovative (self-) sampling combined with integrated suspect/NTS/EDA approaches - Leader: INRAE (M48)

D4.6 1st Progress report on targeted surveys - Leader: VITO (M48)

D4.7 1st Progress report on occupational surveys - Leader: TTL (M48)

D4.8 2nd Progress report on the general survey - Leader: VITO (M48)

Additional Deliverables

AD4.11 Progress report statistical analyses (P4.1.4.2.a_Y1_DataAnalysisHBM4EU_VITO, initially planned M36 but postponed to M48) - Leader: VITO

WP N°	WP5	Lead Beneficiary	ANSES/BfR

WP title	Hazard Assessment																																					
Part ner N°	1	1.1	1.2	1.4	1.5	1.6	3.4	3.9	4.1	4.7	5	5.1	5.3	8	10.2	10.5	14	15.1	15.2	15.7																		
Part ner short name	ANSES	INSERM	INRAE	INERIS	CNRS	INRS	MUI	UNIVE	KU Leuven	UAntwerpen	SCIENSANO	UGent	VUB	MU	DTU	SDU	TTL	BfG	UFZ	UDE	BfR	Fraunhofer	KIT	IUF	RPTU	UKON	TiHo	UHC	NCPHP	ISS	IRFM	UMIL	LIH	LIST	RIVM	UL-LACDR	UU-IRAS	VUA
PM/partner	78	134.0	85.6	38.2	61.0	8.6	13.9	12.8	7.3	36.0	27.3	16.8	36.5	26.5	68.1	23.6	0.5	9.5	47.9	10.3	97.6	14.2	26.9	29.0	12.0	0.5	6.8	33.6	25.9	13.5	13.8	23.1	60.0	3.0	13.7	60.4	30.7	8.0

Part ner number	25.7	25.8	26	26.1	26.2	26.3	26.4	26.5	26.6	27.1	27.2	29	29.3	29.5	31	31.2	31.3	31.4	31.5	33	33.2	33.4	34	34.5	35.2	35.6	35.10	35.12	36	37	46	50	54
Part ner short name	WR	WU-TOX	NIPH	IMR	STAMI	NILU	NIVA	NMBU	NVI	IEP-NRI	UG-PL	INSA	ENSP	UAVR	JSI	NIB	NIC	ULFFA	MFUM	CSIC	UNAV	UPO	ISCHII	IISPV	KI	SU	SLU	UU	AUTH	BPI	UNIBAS	UKHSA	EA
PM/partner	4.5	17.1	60.0	4.2	9.0	1.0	12.3	11.1	12.0	14.3	23.2	32.5	0.5	16.1	7.0	41.5	23.0	2.0	0.3	54.8	24.0	6.0	34.8	17.0	1.0	6.5	12.0	25.5	25.0	51.2	3.0	1.5	0.5
Start	M37										End										M48												

Objectives

The main goal of WP5 is to focus on Hazard Assessment (HA) for human and environmental health on three different directions: fill data gaps (task 5.1), develop and/or improve methodologies for HA to progress towards NGRA (task 5.2) and to work on AOPs, quantitative systems toxicology and physiologically based toxicokinetic (PBTK) modelling (task 5.3). The specific objectives of WP5 for year 4 are:

Task 5.1: The core work in Y4 is finalizing the collection of data, beyond the one that will be processed and reported in our first “First Closing Data Gaps report” Deliverable 5.4 (M36), for human health (prioritised compounds are Bisphenol A (BPA) alternatives/analogues and *Alternaria* toxins and enniatins) and the environmental health (prioritised compounds are BPA alternatives, including mixtures, cyanotoxins and mycotoxins). Any outcome or need detected in our Deliverable 5.4 (M36) will be addressed in Y4. The project P5.1.1.c started in Y3, will gather the first results in Y4. Also, our first end of a WP5 project will be in this task: P5.1.2.a Natural Toxins Aqua. New: we

are in the process of welcoming the project P5.1.1.d “Leachates of Plastics” starting in Y4.

Task 5.2: Advancing and refining innovative methodologies for hazard identification continues to be the aim of this task in Y4. In human health, we will continue focusing on five different endpoints and effects: immunotoxicity, non-genotoxic carcinogenicity, (developmental) neurotoxicity, endocrine disruption (with a focus on thyroid) and metabolic disruption. In environment, we will be creating NAMs in four primary areas employing i) *in silico* and modelling tools, ii) invertebrate animal models, iii) vertebrate models, and newly iv) complex microbial community.

Regarding our transversal project initiated in Y4 and with a focus on regulatory readiness of NAMs, we will work on the points mentioned below:

- Expand ReadEDtest to analyse methods for other endpoints
- Independent peer-review of readiness of NAM developed in WP5 (SOPs, results of ReadEDtest...)
- Support validation activities for willing partners
- Writing a manuscript based on further guidance, respective deliverables and the position paper “Validation-related activities within PARC to progress new methods and approaches for hazard and risk assessment of Chemicals” in Annex II of our Deliverable D5.1; Marx-Stoelting et al., 2023, Link: [here](#).

Task 5.3: The objectives for Y4 are to keep fostering the different core or extended groups established in Y1-Y3 that are relevant for the activity of this task: omics, AOPs, bioinformatics, effect markers, PBTK, and *in vivo/in vitro* mode of action. We will use and update when needed our inventory and mapping established in Y1-Y3 of available knowledge, reference *in vivo*/human datasets, activities and models in systems biology, PBTK and AOP frameworks and prioritising additional studies. We will also continue the studies initiated in Y1-Y3 to characterise core-regulated gene networks, for already published AOPs (to make them quantitative) and linking chemicals to available AOPs, linking omics data to human physiopathology, generating high quality data. New projects under revision: P5.3.1.b grOMICS (M37-M84); P5.3.4.b ResUpt (M37-M84). In Y4 two deliverables will be submitted by this task: D5.7 Systems Toxicology (and AOPs) report (M48) and D5.6 Second New PBK Models report (M48).

Description of Programmed Activities

Task 5.1: Toxicity testing addressing data gaps of concern

Co-leaders A5.1.1: NIPH (NO), INSA (PT), Co-leader A5.1.2: BPI (EL)

Participants:

Activity 5.1.1: ANSES (FR), BfR (DE), BPI (EL), CNRS (FR), Fraunhofer-IBMT (DE), IMR (NO), INRAE (FR), INRS (FR), INSA (PT), INSERM (FR), ISCIII (ES), ISS (IT), LIH (LU), MUI (AT), NIB (SI), NILU (NO), NIPH (NO), NVI (NO), Sciensano (BE), SDU (DK), STAMI (NO), TTL (FI), TUB (DE), ULFFA (SI), UMIL (IT), UNAV (ES), UNIVIE (AT), WU-TOX (NL)

Activity 5.1.2: BPI (EL), EAWAG (CH), IEP-NRI (PL), IISPV (ES), INERIS (FR), INRAE (FR), NIB (SI) NIVA

(NO), SDU (DK), SLU (SE), SU (SE), UAVR (PT), UFZ (DE), UG-PL (PL), UGent (BE), UU (SE), Cefas-Defra (UK), UOB (UK)

A5.1.1 Closing data gaps of concern for human health

We look forward to continuing the lab-based activities in year 4 and to having time to discuss and interpret the results and disseminate our findings to regulatory EU and national agencies (e.g EFSA, ECHA, EMA) to ensure regulatory uptake of the results. Results will also be shared with some institutions which showed interests in these activities (Health Canada, Ontario University and RIVM). For both projects 5.1.1a and 5.1.1.b, we are in close contact with partners within PARC, especially 5.2, 5.3 and WP6 to exchange data.

For year 4 is planned the publication of the results in peer-reviewed journals, presentation of data in conferences, meetings (e.g. SETAC, WP5 annual on site meeting), and the preparation of new projects.

In Year 4 the project P5.1.1.c_Y3_TG+EnnB1_ANSES “TG+ enniatin B1” will start experimental work.

Details per project:

- P5.1.1.a_Y1_Toxins_BfR_UNIVIE [M1-M48] (project extended from M36 to M48)

The enniatins A, A1, B and B1 as well as Beauvericin have testing priority. Alternariol, Alternariol monomethylether, Altertoxin I, Altenuene, Tentoxin and Tenuazonic acid are among the prioritized compounds for the *Alternaria* study program.

The *in vitro* studies agreed upon natural toxins (enniatins and *Alternaria* toxins) to close data gaps will include genotoxic, endocrine and immunotoxic effects, as well as other potential endpoints/target organs. In Y4 we will focus on continuing the experimental work and start follow-up activities based on the results of the tier 1 or tier 2 studies:

- Genotoxicity/mutagenicity: SOS/umu for *Alternaria* toxins (+/- S9) [UNAV (ES)]; AMES assay for enniatins, as well as AOH [BfR (DE), NIB (SI)]; continuing on micronucleus assay for enniatins and *Alternaria* toxins [Sciensano (BE), INSA (PT)], yH2Ax assay for AOH [BfR (DE)], HPRT assay with *Alternaria* toxins [Fraunhofer (DE)]; comet assay will be performed if tier 1 studies indicate a need and if time and budget is available [INSA (PT)].
- Endocrine effects: H295R steroidogenesis assay (acc. OECD TG 456) on *Alternaria* toxins (start of activity if serum supplement Nu-serum will be delivered) [BfR], continuing work with enniatins [ISS (IT)]; agonistic and antagonistic activity of enniatins and *Alternaria* toxins on AR (AR STTA, acc. OECD TG 458) [BPI (EL)], agonistic and antagonistic activity of enniatins and *Alternaria* toxins on ER (ER STTA, acc. OECD TG 455) [INRS (PT)]; continuing work for MIE of thyroid metabolism (TPO, DIO1, NIE, DLR of TRalpha) with enniatins and *Alternaria* toxins [BfR (DE)]; E-screen assay [BfR (DE), BPI (EL)] and expression of estrogenic, androgenic and steroid hormone genes via qPCR [BPI (EL)] will be performed if tier 1 studies indicate a need and if time and budget is available;
- Immunotoxicity: immunotoxic effects in 3D inhalation model (e.g. EpiAirway) including transcriptomics and epigenomics on *Alternaria* toxins [STAMI (NO)]; continuing work on THP-1-Lucia-NF-kB reporter assay on enniatins and *Alternaria* toxins [UNIVIE (AT)];

continuing work on cytokine response in non-tumorigenic (HCEC-1CT) and tumorigenic (Caco-2) intestinal cells (+/- I1 β -stimulus) with enniatins and *Alternaria* toxins [UNIVIE (AT)]; continuing work on TLR and Dectin reporter assay in HEK293 cells with *Alternaria* toxins [STAMI (NO)]; Immunotoxic effects in 3D tissue model of the human small intestine (EpiIntestinal 3D *in vitro* Microtissues/MatTek Life Sciences) [NVI (NO)]; Immunosuppression of enniatins and *Alternaria* toxins *in vitro* in human blood cells [NIPH (NO)].

- Other activities: *In silico* analyses and toxicity ranking [IMR (NO)]; Multiomics mechanistic analysis for AOP development [IMR (NO), Sciensano (BE)]; Absorption, permeability and metabolism of enniatins [ANSES (FR), NVI (NO), WU-TOX (NL)]; Effects of enniatins on human gut microbiota will be performed if time and budget is available [ISS (IT)].

Overall, the studies will provide needed *in vitro* data and identify critical toxicological effects of enniatins and *Alternaria* toxins. Experimental work started for some test substances in late Y2, and for some substances in early Y3 due to the sourcing process including the procurement process that was very time consuming. Due to the delays in obtaining the test substances, a 1-year extension of the project length has been required in Y2, therefore, the planned ending date for this project is now M48.

We are in contact with the scientific officer from the feed and contaminants unit from EFSA regarding the availability of data on enniatins and beauvericin program since EFSA is searching for new data to possibly update its current opinion. We are in contact with the OECD AOP project to exchange information.

The monthly online project meetings will continue as previously.

[Participants: ANSES (FR), INRS (FR), Sciensano (BE), WU-TOX (NL), NIPH (NO), IMR (NO), STAMI (NO), INSA (PT), NIB (SI), UNAV (ES), BPI (EL), Fraunhofer (DE), ISS (IT), NVI (NO), TUB (DE)]

- P5.1.1.b_Y1_BPA_HumTox_BfR [M1-M54] (project extended from M36 to M54)

The test substances for the set of *in vitro* studies continue to be: BPZ, BPE, BPP, BPAP, BPPH, and BPS-MAE. Using BPA as a reference substance and for metabolism halogenated analogues as TBBPA and Pergafast 201. The aim is to fill up data gaps in the five selected endpoints and provide new mechanistic data for AOP development. Experiments are ongoing.

Results will be shared with Physiologically Based Pharmacokinetic (PBPK) modelers in 5.3. We are in contact with both ECHA, RIVM and Health Canada/Ontario University to avoid duplication of efforts. Contact has been made with the EURION cluster regarding endocrine disruption studies.

In Y4, all the experimental work for up to M36 would have been collected, processed, and shared in the D5.4 First Closing Data Gaps report. Any experimental work pending or any need highlighted after the report will be addressed in Y4 for each of the five endpoints.

1. Metabolism bioactivation routes and kinetics: will continue the *In vitro* study of the metabolic fate and bioactivation pathways of key BPA alternatives [INRAE (FR)] and isoform specific metabolism and biokinetic studies as input of PBK modelling [ISS (IT)].

2. Endocrine effects: *In vitro* Human H295R Steroidogenesis Assay (OECD TG 456) [ISS (IT)], Cytotoxicity of TCBPA, TBBPA; assessment of 17 β -estradiol and testosterone in conditioned media of H295R cells treated with BPP, BPAP, BPS-MAE, TCBPA, TBBPA [ISS (IT)].

Effect of BPA alternatives in thyroid hormone synthesis key events using *in vitro* test (under consideration by EURL ECVAM that includes:

I. Calculation of Inhibition/ IC50 of the Thyroid Hormone transport by MCT8 transporter in MDCK-hMCT8 cells.

II. Calculation of Inhibition/IC50 of the Iodide transport by NIS transporter in MDCK-hNIS cells [ISCIII (ES)]. Analysis of the data by assay calculation of EC50 for cytotoxicity of TCBPA and TBBPA

- Calculation of EC50 and statistical analysis of significant Fold changes for 17 β -estradiol and testosterone levels [ISS (IT), INRAE (FR), ISCIII (ES)].

4. Developmental Neurotoxicity: For *in vitro* screening: tests of cellular viability following exposure to BPA, BPP, BPS-MAE and TCBPA. Cellular effects of BPA alternatives on neuronal network formation, synaptogenesis. Collection of samples for LIH for methylation studies and INRAE for studies on TH signaling. [CNRS (FR), INRAE (FR), LIH (LU)]. Other molecular and epigenetic analyses: Finalization of the analyses for exposure to BPA, BPAP, BPE and BPZ [LIH (LU)].

5. Immunotoxicity: Identification of immune cell targets and effects of bisphenols on immune functions [UMIL (IT)]. Investigation of the relationship between bisphenols immunotoxicity and their effect on the inflammation-induced tryptophan breakdown and related immunobiochemical pathways such as inflammation-induced tryptophan breakdown (in human PBMC and/or relevant human monocyte-derived cell lines; the preliminary information on cytotoxicity and cell viability has been shared). Investigation in a lung epithelial model will be performed in a limited set of compounds. [MUI (AT)]. Investigate the relationship between bisphenols immunotoxicity and their effect on the glucocorticoid system using THP-1 cells; Jurka cells transfected with active isoform of GR α and on lymphoblastoid cell lines obtained from different donors to assess interindividual variability [ULFFA (SI)]. Provide new mechanistic data for AOP development, by evaluating the effects of BPA analogues on the intracellular calcium homeostasis of both resting and stimulated immune cells (on Jurka cell, ongoing for 2 compounds) [ISS (IT)].

6. Carcinogenicity: *In vitro* test as foreseen in the battery of genotoxicity testing [INSA (PT), ISS (IT)], *in vitro* genotoxicity of BPA and BPA alternatives and relevant metabolites will be assessed on hepatic 2D and/or 3D (spheroids) cell models developed from HepG2 using micronucleus, comet and transcriptomic assays (collaboration with T5.2a) [INSA (PT), Fraunhofer (DE), NILU (NO)], non-genotoxic carcinogenicity of BPA and BPA alternatives will be assessed by Bhas 42 cell transformation assay (following OECD guidance document) [INRS (FR), INSA (PT), ISCIII (ES), TTL (FI), NILU (NO)].

New Action: We welcome a new action in our project collecting data with whole organism (zebrafish). Assays are being performed in the project P5.2.1.b. Partners are joining our monthly meetings since May 2024 to exchange data and align. This is an effort to bring down silos between HumTox and Environment [Partner: UFZ (DE)].

Project Monthly meetings: every 4th Wednesday of the month all partners are meeting and two are

selected to give updates. If a partner cannot attend, a deputy is welcome and the presentation and agenda with minutes is distributed to keep all informed. We also have a committed folder in the SharePoint for these meetings presentations/agendas

[Participants: ISS (IT), UMIL (IT), INRAE (FR), TTL (FI), ULFFA (SI), MUI (AT), ISCIII (ES), INRS (FR), Fraunhofer (DE), CNRS (FR), LIH (LU), NILU (NO), INSA (PT), UFZ (DE)]

- P5.1.1.c_Y3_TG+ EnnB1_ANSES [M25 to M60]

The purpose of this project is to fill an *in vivo* data gap on Enniatin B1 identified by EFSA by subcontracting a TG408 study under GLP. The tissues originating from this study will also be used for further analyses by WP5 partners, which will increase confidence in NAMs. In Y4, the 14-day dose range finding study is expected to be performed, and tissues originating from this study will be sent to WP5 partners for additional analysis. Based on the results of the 14-day study, the doses will be set for the TG 408 study, and the TG 408 study will be initiated. This is a provisional timeline at this stage.

[Participants: ANSES (FR), BfR (DE), NIPH (NO), INSA (PT), INSERM (FR), NVI (NO), TUB (DE), UNAV (ES), WU-TOX (NL)]

- P5.1.1.d_Y4_PlasticLeach_NIPH [M37-M81]

The aim of this project is to identify the most hazardous chemicals leaching from selected plastics (both additives and non-intentionally added chemical residues) for both the environment and human health. Where relevant interactions with the CUSP cluster will be sought. Specific objectives for the first year are:

1. Preparation of leachates from plastics: Set selection criteria for plastics to be studied, justification document and discussion with stakeholders. Preparatory meeting scheduled for 14th January 2025. Kick off meeting planned for 15th May 2025, Oslo. End by June 2026, Landmark L-PlasticLeach1 Preparation of extracts completed. Lead by [NIPH, (NO)]. All partners are involved.

2. General toxicity: Utilize a range of NAMs being developed and tested in other PARC WP5 projects to test the leachates —including those for cell toxicity, genotoxicity, DNT, immunotoxicity as well as OECD-compliant assays. [INRS, (FR); IEP-NRI, (PL); UAVR, (PT), NIPH (NO, INSA (PT), KIST-Europe⁶ (DE), NIB (SL), BPI (GR)]. Assess ecological toxicity using aquatic and terrestrial bioindicators, including *Daphnia magna* and *Aliivibrio fischeri*. [IEP-NRI, (PL)]

This action will be refined in PARC Y4 but officially starts in August 2026 Landmark L-PlasticLeach2 Start hazard testing in selected NAMs.

Participants: NIPH (NO), INSA (PT), KIST-Europe* (DE), ANSES (FR), UU (NL), IEP-NRI (PL), UAVR (PT), NIB (SL), INRS (FR), NIVA (NO), WU (NL), BPI (EL).

A5.1.2 Toxicity assessment addressing data gaps of concern (Environment)

⁶ modalities of collaboration are still under discussion

Details per project:

- **P5.1.2.a_Y1_NaturalToxinsAqua_Ugent [M1-M36]. This project ended in M36.**

- **P5.1.2.b_Y1_BPAalternatives_BPI_MU [M1-M48] (this project has been extended from M42 to M48)**

Toxicity testing of bisphenol alternatives selected during Y1 on certain organisms has been started and will continue during Y4. It is noted that the experimental work started with a delay mainly due to time-consuming procedures followed for chemicals order (centralized order for all PARC partners) and difficulties faced by several partners in hiring personnel. Therefore 6 more months of the project's duration is requested. A list of 26 assays (OECD TG, ASTM and ISO) are being conducted by the involved partners covering a wide range of organisms (*e.g.*, fish, aquatic invertebrates, alga, marine bacteria, earthworms, soil microorganisms, xenopus, *C. elegans*) and effects (*e.g.*, acute effects, effects on reproduction and on endocrine system). In Year 4 we will mainly focus on experiments with mixtures, and testing of individual substances will be finalized. The mixtures to be tested have been selected based on the results of tests with individual substances. In addition, the mixtures have also been selected considering also the occurrence of bisphenols in different environmental compartments (*i.e.*, surface water, soil, sediment) as revealed by reviewing the available literature data and the results from monitoring activities that will be carried out in the frame of PARC WP4. Partner UU (SE) reported problems in carrying out their originally planned experiments (effects on adipocyte development in zebrafish), and as it is taking a long time to get the ethic approvals, they propose to determine metabolic rate using Alamar blue assay adapted for zebrafish embryos (described in Renquist B. et al (2013), [doi: 10.1089/zeb.2012.0841](https://doi.org/10.1089/zeb.2012.0841)). The studies will be focusing on changes in metabolic rate in 0-4 days old zebrafish exposed to the following BPA alternatives: BPAF, BPC, BPS, TMBPA, and DAB. It is urgent to collect data on metabolic effects of BPA replacement products in early life stages since BPA is suggested to alter metabolic programming in children, which may lead to metabolic disorders at older ages.

[Participants: BPI (EL), SLU (SE), IISPV (ES), SDU (DK), INERIS (FR), NIB (SI), IEP-NRI (PL), UU (SE), UG-PL (PL), UAVR (PT), EAWAG (CH), NIVA (NO), UFZ (DE), SU (SE), Cefas-Defra (UK)]

- **P5.1.2.c_Y4_TG+MP_ANSES [M37-M60]**

The start of this project will be subject to the conclusions of the PARC Helicopter document on microplastics.

This project would be the second TG+ study of WP5. The objectives are twofold: filling data gaps on the bioaccumulation in fish of microplastic particles and additives, and assessing the applicability domain of *in vitro* bioaccumulation assessment methods, by subcontracting studies following OECD guidelines under GLP. Additionally, using tissues from the TG studies performed under GLP, non-targeted metabolomics and/or proteomics analyses will be performed to define biomarkers of exposure and to characterize possible biological pathways triggered or suppressed after the bioaccumulation of the tested plastic additives.

During PARC Year 4, the objectives are:

- Publishing the public tender to subcontract studies under GLP, and procurement of substances. Selection of Contact Research Organisations (CROs).

- Hold a workshop with stakeholders on selection of additives
- Start of preliminary study on translocation of particles in fish to assess the particle size range for which translocation occurs and identification of influencing factors, based on partner's budget

Task 5.2: Innovative methods and tools for toxicity testing and modelling

Co-leaders A5.2.1: DTU (DK), VUB (BE), Co-leader A5.2.2: MU (CZ)

Participants:

Activity 5.2.1: AIT (AT), ANSES (FR), BfR (DE), DTU (DK), IfADo (DE), INRAE (FR), INSA (PT), INSERM (FR), IRFM (IT), ISCIII (ES), IUF (DE), LIH (LU), LIST (LU), MU (CZ), MUI (AT), NIB (SI), NILU (NO), NIPH (NO), NMBU (NO), NCPHP (HU), RIVM (NL), SDU (DK), TiHo (DE), UAntwerpen (BE), UFZ (DE), UG-PL (PL), UDE⁷ (DE), RPTU (DE), UKON (DE), UL-LACDR (NL), ULFFA (SI), UNAV (ES), UOB (UK), UU (SE), UU-IRAS (NL), VUA (NL), VUB (BE), WR (NL)

Activity 5.2.2: BfG (DE), BPI (EL), EAWAG (CH), IISPV (ES), INERIS (FR), MU (CZ), MUI (AT), NIB (SI), NIC (SI), NIVA (NO), SDU (DK), SLU (SE), UAntwerpen (BE), UFZ (DE), UG-PL (PL), UPO (ES), CSIC (ES), INRAE (FR)

- P5.2.a_Y4_RegNAMs_ANSES [M37-M81]

In order to support some validation activities for some selected NAMs, the following actions will be taken and during PARC Y4 and are described below. These activities will be coordinated with other projects and initiatives (e.g. EU-NETVAL), JRC, to create synergies as well as WP6 and the methodology leader on validation (ML) in PARC.

- Expand ReadEDTest, currently dedicated to assessing *in vitro* and fish embryo assays triggering endocrine disruption (<https://readedtest.u-paris-sciences.fr/>). By PARC WP5 partner labs involved in the development of NAMs (e.g. [INSERM (FR)]).
- Assess test methods under development for other endpoints,
- Organize independent peer review of NAMs developed in WP5
- Support validation activities of NAMs for willing partners. The selection will be based on regulatory relevance and therefore discussed with the EU agencies.

A5.2.1 Innovative methods and tools for toxicity testing and modelling (Human Health)

Details per project:

- P5.2.1.a_Y1_NGTXCs_INRAE [M1-M60]

The development of some tests that can identify tissue and substance specific effects related to distinct aspects of non-genotoxic carcinogenesis will need to be continued in Y4, i.e. for novel methods that are still in a rather early developmental status. For example: UL-LACDR will not only finalize biological replicate experiments with SRXN1-GFP oxidative stress response reporter

⁷ AMD-101057014-118: Professor Dr Kathrin Thedieck, who was the main scientific contact involved in the activities of PARC WP5 for the Austrian affiliated entity University of Innsbruck - PARC acronym "UIBK", left the University of Innsbruck and started working for the University of Duisburg-Essen in Germany - PARC acronym "UDE", on 01/04/2024. Consequently, UIBK withdrew from PARC on 01/04/2024 and UDE entered in PARC as affiliated entity of UBA on 01/04/2024.

hepatocyte-like cells but will analyze the single cell sequencing data of mammary organoids exposed to estradiol (E2) and complement the analyses by targeted transcriptomics on liver and mammary gland progenitor cells exposed to endpoint specific controls and compounds of interest. Optionally, they will use ICAM1-GFP and FUCCI HCLs to measure the effects of compounds of interest on inflammation and cell cycle distribution and further explore if TP53 loss sensitizes liver and mammary gland progenitors to non-genotoxic carcinogens using transcriptomics and/or other readouts, such as assays that measure genomic instability. UNAV will conduct time-course experiments for oxidized chemicals that were not detected under the conditions used in Year 3 and perform the CTA and assess histone H2AX and H3 phosphorylation in a selection of compounds. The NIB team will complete the flow cytometry experiments and will perform the experiments evaluating the mRNA expression of selected genes involved in the studied pathways (proliferation, cell cycle regulation, oxidative stress response, apoptosis, epigenetic changes, DNA damage response and oncogenesis) using the same testing approach as for the first set of chemicals. RPTU will continue and finalize the testing with endpoint-specific compounds. The used intestinal cell models will be further characterized with regard to their metabolic competence and nuclear receptor expression. Furthermore, a multiplexing approach will be tested to simultaneously assess the endpoints oxidative stress, proliferation and genomic instability.

However, the main focus of year 4 will be the analysis of the data obtained with the first set of reference data and at least two and up to 10 substances for each of the 5 different selected MoA (proliferation, cytotoxicity inducing regenerative proliferation, nuclear receptor activation, inflammation and changes in cellular morphology indicative for cell migration). The data will be reported in an already agreed common data template for each chemical and compiled to analyse the sensitivity and specificity of the various assays for a given Mode of Action (MoA), including a comparison of the minimal concentration needed to detect a significant effect. These analyses will facilitate the (further) development of prediction models for each assay to i.e. define thresholds that allow identification of physiological/ biological and regulatory relevant activities and to develop a complementary and predictive test battery. Additional testing / method optimization will be necessary in the course of this process. Here, the reference substances used in other tasks (5.1: BPA alternatives; mycotoxins and 5.2: Inflammation, ED-Met) might be tested to better define the applicability domain of the methods, support the other PARC projects, in particular to check if our methods/ batteries come to comparable conclusions or can support regulatory decision making in a broader (more data rich) context.

[Participants: INRAE (FE), BfR (DE), ANSES (FR), INSERM (FR), NIB (SI), UL-LACDR (NL), UNAV (ES), IRFM (IT), RIVM (NL), RPTU (DE), NILU (NO), MU (CZ)]

- P5.2.1.b_Y1_MD-EDC_BfR [M1-M48]

In Year 4 we will continue with the development of a battery of metabolic disrupting chemicals (MDC)-specific NAMs based on human as well as non-human models.

Partners will continue testing the BPA-alternatives prioritized in PARC WP5: 0-BPA, 1-BPZ, 2-BPE, 3-BPS-MAE, 4-Pergafast 201, 5-BPP, 6-BPAP, 7-TCBPA, 8-TBBPA.

1. Functional and structural characterization of Nuclear Receptor (NR and bisphenols interactions)

[INSERM (FR)]

In Year 3, using reporter cell lines (Hela and U2OS), we identified several bisphenols active on CAR. In Year 4, the CAR activity of bisphenols will be further characterized, in particular by carrying out a structural study using crystallization.

The effect of halogenation (bromination and chlorination) will be analysed on some of the bisphenols studied in year 3, such as BPA, BPAF, BPS and Pergafast. During preliminary experiments carried out in year 3, it was seen that halogenation increased the ability of these bisphenols to activate certain NRs such as PXR and PPAR α , depending on the degree of halogenation (1 to 4 bromine or chlorine atoms). The aim of the study will be to confirm the preliminary observations and to explain them, in particular through structural studies.

2. *In vitro* assays for screening MBD

2.1 The Mammalian target of rapamycin (mTOR) activity is being addressed by quantitative high-resolution mass spectrometry (HR-MS) and immune assays [currently University Duisburg-Essen (UDE (DE), previously IUBK (AT))].

MD screenings jointly with the partners will continue, in particular, the comparative characterization of the mTOR network response to BPA versus BPF and further MD substances.

2.2 High-throughput screening assay for phospholipidosis in human liver cells [BfR (DE)]

It is planned a detailed characterization of the 3D liver model to be implemented in year 4. Subsequently, the phospholipidosis assay established in 2D will be transferred to the 3D liver model. Therefore, compounds already screened in 2D were analysed in 3D for comparison. A manuscript is intended to be published in year 4 about the phospholipidosis assay in HepaRG (2D) and the outcome of its screening (performed in Y3).

2.3 Test system for pancreatic beta cell signaling and function disruption by MDCs [BfR (DE)]

The testing of additional chemicals including malathion, monocrotophos will be carried out in Y4. In addition, a review outlining substances targeting the function and signalling of beta cells will be published as well as the results of the investigation of novaluron.

2.4 Development and optimization of adipocyte models to study adipocyte differentiation and response to test chemicals [UU-IRAS (NL)]

Similar to Y3, the optimization of the 96-well plate adipogenic differentiation model will continue but this time in serum free conditions using model chemicals including ROSI, MEHP, TPP, TBT, TBBPA and fludioxinil. This will allow to compare the adipogenic potential of the cells in serum free condition compared to FCS. Additionally, the optimization of an *in vitro* co-culture model will start to study the interaction between the endocrine and immune systems, as well as the 2D optimization and transition to 3D model. This model will be optimized testing different culture conditions and according to the serum compatibility of the models. For the co-culture model, not only the adipogenic endpoints will be considered, but some immune endpoints will be also included to elucidate the interaction of the two systems in our model. All the experiments are to be performed in triplicates with three independent replicates.

2.5 Unravel the molecular consequences of BPA alternatives exposure in adipocytes [UFZ (DE)]

The assay will be extended to evaluate the PARC priority -listed BPA alternatives and obtained results will be published.

2.6 Development of an *in vitro* methodology and phenotoxicity score for safety assessment based on cell profiling of compounds using the Cell Painting protocol [UU (SE)]

2.7 Assessment of MDC effect on cultured primary human hepatocytes and human iPSC [IfADo (DE)]

3. Whole organism

3.1 Development of early life stage zebrafish metabolic disruption test [UAntwerpen (BE)]

In Y1-3 UAntwerpen developed a zebrafish larval feeding trial (exposure to BPA published) and a zebrafish embryo test (exposure to BPA, rosiglitazone and T0070907 published) for investigating metabolic disruption. In Y4, UAntwerpen will conduct a larval feeding trial with exposure to rosiglitazone to further facilitate comparison of results obtained with these two test methods. The exposure will be conducted both in wildtype zebrafish and in zebrafish where paraoxonase 1, a gene that has been associated with obesity, is knocked out. The exposure to rosiglitazone will be combined with administration of a western diet.

New Action starting in Y4

In silico screening of kinetic interaction of MDCs [BfR (DE)]

- It will be conducted an *in silico* screening of all MDCs currently investigated in this project that are relevant for liver steatosis with regard to potential kinetic interaction. This screening will predict metabolically interacting MDCs, *i.e.* those that share CYP enzyme interactions, and active transport, *i.e.* permeability glycoprotein (P-gp), substrates and inhibitors.

- The substances prioritized for further investigation based on this screening will be listed for a literature evaluation of realistic oral exposure concentrations.

- The Organ-on-Chip (OoC) test system for GIT-liver testing will be established.

Internal project meetings: monthly online meetings will continue, where partners share preliminary results (one partner per meeting). The management of this project has been updated from September 2024 on (M29), with a new expert from BfR joining and continuing the in-kind contribution by INRAE.

Dissemination activities: similar to Y2 and Y3, in Y4 several articles characterizing the interaction of bisphenols and their halogenated analogues with different nuclear receptors will be written.

[Participants: INRAE (FR), BfR (DE), INSERM (FR), IfaDo (DE), UU-IRAS (NL), UAntwerpen (BE), UU (SE), UDE (DE), UFZ (DE)]

- P5.2.1.c_Y1_EDThDisruption_DTU [M1-M48]

In Y4, efforts to optimize and characterize molecular mechanisms and develop *in vitro* and *in silico* assays for NAM-Thyroid Hormone System Disruptors (THSD) testing will continue, as outlined in the project description:

Action 1: Mapping of the activities of the different groups to the existing THSD AOP network [All

partners]

Action completed. Mapping of all partner activities has been completed, and a project article has been published (Ramhøj et al., 2023, <https://doi.org/10.3389/ftox.2023.1189303>). This action enables all project activities to make a relevant contribution to the existing THSD AOP network.

Action 2: Characterization of evolutionary conservation of the TH-axis [UAntwerpen (BE)]

This action will be completed by the end of Y3. The case study of data-rich model compounds has shown the potential for cross-species extrapolation for THSD, but also that data gaps, such as the lack of thyroid hormone measurements in fish, complicate qualitative extrapolation between species. Efforts are underway to explore possible adjustments to address this.

Action 3: Optimization and characterization of assays to develop more extensive test batteries of NAMs

3.1: Screening assays for thyroid hormone (TH)-disruption for early-phase liver developmental toxicity (2D) [VUB (BE), INSERM (FR)]

The 2D stem-cell based model will be further optimized and tested with reference compounds, including methimazole (MMI), propylthiouracil (PTU), Tetrabromobisphenol A (TBBPA), and perfluorooctane sulfonate (PFOS). The chemicals have been specifically selected to compare the observed *in vitro* THSD effects with those obtained in fetal rat livers (Action 5). Once completed, a publication will be prepared.

3.2 Overexpressing cell lines for thyroid hormone transporters OATP3A1 (2D) [VUA (NL)]

Action completed.

3.3 Integrated model for measuring thyroid hormone transport inhibition across the blood-cerebrospinal fluid barrier (3D) [VUA (NL)]

Action completed.

3.4 Thyroid follicle model for identification of TH biosynthesis disruption (3D) [BfR (DE)]

The pig-derived thyroid follicle model will be further optimised and used for chemical testing. Chemicals to be tested, will be chosen from molecular initiating event (MIE)-specific screenings (e.g. DIO1, TPO and NIS). Two additional chemicals that will be tested are TBBPA and PFOS, to form a connection to the DTU animal model (Action 5).

3.5 Identifying inhibitors of thyroperoxidase, deiodinase type 1,2,3 and dehalogenase as potentially relevant MIE of TH pre-receptor control (*In vitro* & *In chemico* assay) [BfR (DE)]

Studies on TBBPA and PFOS will be finalized and data submitted to partner DTU (DK). Further cooperative work will be conducted for subtask P5.1.1.a (natural toxins) and a subset of *in vitro* assays will be applied on Enniatins and Alternaria toxins to close data gaps.

3.6 *In silico* models for TH system disrupting properties [DTU (DK)]

Quantitative Structure Activity Relationship (QSAR) models for MCT8 inhibition (TH transport across membranes), TTR binding (TH distribution), TRHR (thyrotropin releasing hormone receptor antagonist) and DEHAL1 (Iodide recycling) inhibition will be finalized for a more comprehensive set

of QSAR models for TH system disruption.

Action 4: Communication / Deliverables / outputs

As a TH workshop was held at DTU in March 2024 to discuss and disseminate our work, only regular TH meetings (every 6 weeks) will continue and manuscripts will be prepared. The TH project will end Y4 (M48).

[Participants: DTU (DK), VUB (BR), BfR (DE), SDU (DK), UAntwerpen (BE), VUA (NL), ISCIII (ES), INSERM (FR)]

Action 5: Whole organism model: zebrafish larvae and embryo & *In vivo* rat study

5.1 *In vivo* rat data (studying TBBPA and PFOS substances) [DTU (DK), INSERM (FR)]

The analysis of the multi-organ transcriptomics study of the effects of PFOS and TBBPA will be finalized and a manuscript prepared. The developmental effects of THSD PFOS and TBBPA will be contrasted to the effects of PTU, a THSD acting through a different mechanism, converging or contrasting effects will be studied using molecular biology techniques. Translational studies of THSD effects in fetal rat livers will be compared to effects in the stem-cell based early-phase liver developmental toxicity assay [VUB (DE), INSERM (FR), DTU (DK)].

5.2 Zebrafish and snail (*L. stagnalis*) assays with metformin and BPE [SDU (DK)]

Combined DNT endpoints sensitive to THSD in zebrafish 5 days post hatch, including behaviour and brain and eye morphology, will be evaluated after exposure to BPA alternatives, BPE, BPAP, and BPS-MAE. The outcome will add to the vertebrate cross-class comparison of THSD effects. The morphological and behavioural endpoints will be compared to gene expression data on genes relevant for THSD and DNT. Investigation of a THS-like system in the mollusk *Lymnaea stagnalis* will continue with BPA alternatives (e.g., BPE, BPAP, BPZ, BPS-MAE).

5.3 Comparative assessment of thyroid hormone system disruption in mammals and fish [UAntwerpen (BE)]

A comparative assessment of THSD in mammals and fish will be written up. The comparison is based on rodent and fish data from the literature on 4 data-rich model compounds (MMI, PTU, iopanoic acid, perchlorate). Responses are compared between fish and rodents at the level of the MIEs, KEs and AOs that are part of the THSD AOP network. Specific attention is going to a comparison of baseline TH levels, and directionality as well as the extent of the changes in response to the model compounds. The work highlights similarities and differences in responses as well as data gaps that currently impede a thorough (quantitative) comparison of responses between fish and rodents.

5.4 Zebrafish embryo and larvae assay [ISCIII (ES)]

The zebrafish embryo (ZFe) assay to assess the disruption of iodide and TH accumulation will be optimized, utilizing radiolabeled iodide derivatives to evaluate the effects of reference substances such as perchlorate (ClO_4^-), MMI, bromosulphophthalein (BSP), and silychristin. Additionally, the impact of endocrine disruptors, including bisphenol A (BPA) and tetrabromobisphenol A (TBBPA), will be investigated. The effects of these compounds on the expression of genes associated with the hypothalamus-pituitary-thyroid (HPT) axis will also be analyzed using quantitative PCR (qPCR) in

zebrafish embryos.

Action 6: Data Analyses [INSERM (FR)]

Processing of the obtained *in vitro* and *in vivo* rat data set for the different compounds tested will be continued.

- P5.2.1.d_Y1_Immunotox_Inserm [M1-M48]

In year 4, based on the results from Y3 the optimization of the methodology will continue and be finalized, as much as possible. Note that a follow-up project has been submitted to complete the NAM development after the end of Y4. During the regular online meetings from September to January 2024, each partner is presenting its results, followed by a discussion which will guide the future work (for Y4) and how to finalize it for the use in specific IATA or ITS. ECHA has joined those meetings from September to give input on regulatory needs. Depending on the PARC review process, the DIT project may have started with the same partners and others and will need discussion concerning ongoing NAM development and likely transfer of methodology.

Depending on the methods, we plan also to upgrade some NAMs by including co-culture [NCPHP (HU), UFZ (DE), ULFFA (SI)], or new readout (Cytokines) [MUI (AT)], immune cell activation [INSA (PT), INSERM (FR)], genes [WR (NL), MUI (AT)], EVs [NCPHP (HU), INSERM (FR)]. Furthermore, new compounds will be tested on the optimized NAM (see below reference compounds) to produce the necessary historical data from a validation perspective.

Table 13: Main compounds used to develop the NAMs within this project

Biocides	chloramine-T, piperazine
BPA alternatives	BPA, BPS-MAE, BPZ, BPB, TCBPA, BPAP, Bis-Z, BPPH, BPG, BPS-MPE, PF201, BTUM, BPE, BPP
Mycotoxins	Deoxynivalenol, fumonisin B1, aflatoxin B1, enniatin A, A1, B, B1, ochratoxin A, zearalenone, alternariol, tenuazonic acid, tentoxin
Therapeutic substances	dexamethasone, chloroquine, sirolimus (rapamycin), cyclosporine A, tacrolimus (FK506), doramapimod, hydrocortisone, dapsone
Perfluorinated substances	PFOA, PFOS, PFDA, PFNA, PFHxS, PFUnDA and mixture
Other	BP3, MIKB, B[a]P, TCDD,

New Reference compounds: common compounds related to specific immune key characteristics will have been chosen by May 2025 to be tested on the NAMs developed in the project. Some lists have already been discussed and published (sub-group resp sensitizer, Hargitai R., Parráková L. et al, 2024, doi: [10.3389/tox.2024.1331803](https://doi.org/10.3389/tox.2024.1331803)), some lists are in discussion in other projects (outside PARC like projects from the new ENKORE cluster) where partners are involved in, and some lists will be newly defined.

Partner involved in each action (1-respiratory sensitization [MUI (AT), NCPHP (HU), RIVM (NL)],

LIST (LU), UMIL (IT)], 2-immunosuppression [INSERM (FR), NIPH (NO), INSA (PT), UU-IRAS (NL), UFZ (DE), ULFFA (SI), WR (NL), UMIL (IT)], 3-immunostimulation [UFZ (DE), INSA (PT), UU-IRAS (NL)] will compare their results. This might also allow the choice of the most relevant NAM for similar AOP-key events (detected with different models) based on the results with the reference compounds.

The whole group will also help the discussion on the development of an online questionnaire to evaluate the Test Readiness Criteria (TRC) of each method, similar to the ReadEDtest for EDs, devoted specifically to immunological endpoints.

Dissemination activities: articles and specific congresses such as SOT (March 2026), Eurotox and ÖGMBT (September 2025).

[Participants: INSERM (FR), NIPH (NO), MUI (AT), NCPHP (HU), RIVM (NL), UU-IRAS (NL), ULFFA (SI), UMIL (IT), INSA (PT), UFZ (DE), WR (NL), LIH (LU), LIST (LU)]

- P5.2.1.e_Y1_DNT-ANT_UFZ_IUF_NIPH [M1-M48]

The 96 chemicals, selected in collaboration with the EC_JRC, and including positive and negative controls, will be distributed by January 2025 and tested by all partners. Some partners have capacity for the entire list, others for a subset. This task was slightly delayed, from year 3 to year 4, due to the challenges in compiling the list, taking into account regulatory advice from ECHA and JRC to ensure the generation of reliable data and facilitate later publication, and the procurement process, which requires an external bidding process.

In year 4, partners with developed DNT (Developmental Neurotoxicity) or ANT (Adult Neurotoxicity) NAMs will start testing chemicals. Partners with less well developed NAMs will continue to optimize them, using positive control chemicals and a subset of reference compounds. In addition, a large group of partners are evaluating NAMs to identify the applicability domain from a mode-of-action perspective, with a continued focus on endocrine disruption or epigenetic modifications. Year 4 will center on data generation using reference chemicals from the DG JRC using partner-specific NAMs (see Project Description in the Annex).

Project 5.2.1.e has been extended to year 4 to generate comparable data on the 96 chemicals test set. These data are necessary for a future data integration phase, described below. Improved characterization of the models for the presence and function of transporters/receptors is also planned. All partners will continue their participation.

One new partner ANSES (FR) joined in September 2024. Their research in P5.2.1.e aims to promote microfluidics-based OoC technology combine to Multi Electrodes Array (MEA) as NAMs for DNT. Their actions for the project period have been defined in alignment with the overall goals of P5.2.1.e.

The DNT-ED Action will be strengthened by [UU (SE) and IUF (DE)] based on scientific insights and method/endpoint development from the EURION cluster projects ENDpoiNTs and ATHENA.

Project follow up request: to enable a comparative study on performance, sensitivity, specificity, and redundancy once the data has been generated. And for participants with less well developed NAMs in year 4 to screen the test set.

[Participants: INSERM, UU, NIPH, IUF, UKON, RIVM, UFZ, ISCHII, TiHo, AIT, NMBU, UG-PL, UOB, TiHO,

BfR, ANSES]

- P5.2.1.f_Y4_DART-ED_DTU [M37-M84]

Action 1 Zebrafish embryo-based NAMs for endocrine disruptor (ED) strengthening and expanding the assay

1.1 Addressing cross-species extrapolation potential for non-mammalian NAMs to human health, continuing the work already performed under P5.1.1c TG+ EnnB1.

1.2 Developed existing NAMs further to cover multiple ED modalities relevant for developmental and reproductive toxicity (DART), such as:

1.2.1 vitellogenin gene and protein expression in response to EAS agonism/antagonism,

1.2.2 fluorescent read-outs in AR or ER-sensitive transgenic reporter lines,

1.2.3 expression of ED-responsive genes (ER/AR/THR) related to developmental and reproductive processes, and

1.2.4 brain-derived neurotrophic factor (BDNF), which has not yet been investigated in fish.

1.3 Evaluate the effects of mixture exposure to known EATS-active chemicals in fish at different life stages. Compare the types of effects (and effect sensitivity) in later (non-protected) stages with those observed in the non-protected eleuthero embryo stage (0-5 dpf), including:

1.3.1 assessments of target organ histopathology (brain, thyroid, eye, gonad, etc.),

1.3.2 protein expression, standard developmental and morphological markers, transcriptomics, and early reproductive markers.

Action 2 Enhance ED identification relevant to male reproductive toxicity via human testis organoids (OECD Tier 2 improvement)

2.1.1 Assess stage-specific effects on testis function by developing hiPSC-derived 2D Leydig cell cultures and 3D testicular organoid models in bioreactors. In the following years this cell lines will be used to develop serum-free and contact-free co-cultures.

2.1.2 Readouts will be compared against the OECD TG456 H295R steroidogenesis assay, AR assays (e.g., TG 458), and other non-EATS modalities such as the retinoid signaling pathway

2.1.3 RNA-seq analysis of control and exposed organoids to gain novel mechanistic insights.

2.2 to assess multiple DART-relevant modalities simultaneously, a novel assay using prostate cells (rats) containing ER, ER, and RAR at specific developmental stages will be tested. Next, in the following years, immortalize prostate cells will be compared and evaluated with in-vivo situations.

2.3 Develop additional predictive QSAR models for 'RAR agonism' and 'RXR agonism' for the incorporation of retinoic signaling as a modality (R) to test in NAMs.

Action 3 NAMs to assess in vitro effects on placental angiogenesis using a co-culture of human BeWo cells (first trimester trophoblasts), a human cell line capable of fusing to form syncytiotrophoblasts, and HUVEC cells

3.1 Angiogenic (e.g., VEGF) and endocrine biomarkers (e.g., β -hCG) will be defined to enhance the

utility of a placental angiogenesis assay for ED testing

- P5.2.1.g_Y4_DIT-NAM_INSERTM [M37-M84]

Action 0, Project coordination (month 37-84)

- Regular project meetings. [All partners]
- Annual and periodic reporting. Lead by [NIPH (NO), INSERM (FR)]
- Synergy with other PARC activities, external DIT activities. [All partners]

Action (Subproject) 1. Physiological maps (month 37-84)

- Literature review, based on existing animal and human data. It will also generate an updated list of DIT reference chemicals. In collaboration with the CAAT in vitro DIT initiative [All partners].
- Physiological map, resulting from the literature review, this will be a starting point for the DIT AOP task that is planned for Y5-7. The physiological map will be a living document which can be adapted when new data are available and allows contribution also from non-PARC research initiatives, first draft by M48. With contributions from partners led by [IUF, (DE)].

Action (Subproject) 2. Development of novel test battery, NAMs based on HSC or hiPSC (month 37-84) adaptation of existing tests and development of novel haematopoietic stem cell and hiPSC-based models will be explored:

- Combination of existing, well-characterized assays for screening and prioritisation purposes (in close collaboration with WP5.2.1d immunotoxicity NAM development activities)
- HSC systems by [NCPHP (HU), LIH (LX)]
- hiPSC for toxicity testing by [NIPH, (NO) WFSR, (NL)]
- Other models by [MUI (AU), UMIL (IT), UFZ (DE), RIVM (NL), NMBU (NO)]

- P5.2.1.h_Y4_SDHEPATOX_ANSES [M37-M60]

To improve current *in vitro* methods for assessing chemical-induced hepatotoxicity by integrating sexual dimorphism parameters in different hepatic cell models (primary human hepatocytes, HepaRG, hepatic cells derived from multipotent stem cells (mSC) and induced pluripotent stem cells (iPSC)). The detailed actions for PARC Y4 are as follow:

Action 1.1 Establishment and characterization of sexual dimorphism in *in vitro* hepatic models by [ANSES (FR)] Development of sexually-oriented primary human hepatocytes (PHH) (3 male and female donors) and HepaRG cell line and characterisation of their liver functionality (CYP450 activities, urea synthetises, nuclear receptor activities, metabolomics profile). HepaRG cells and PHH will be incubated with medium supplemented with male or female serum and/or hormones to induce a sexual dimorphism.

Action 1.2 Characterization of general hepatic maturity (e.g. CYP and albumin expression) by [VUB (BE)]. Development of human multipotent stem cell-derived hepatic cells (mPSC-Hep) with sex-specific features and characterisation of their baseline hepatic functionality with focus on lipid metabolism. mPSc-Heps will be incubated with medium supplemented with male or female serum

and/or hormones to induce a sexual dimorphism.

Action 1.3 Development of sex-specific models of the human liver based on hepatic organoids differentiated from induced pluripotent stem (iPS) cells by [BfR (DE)]. For this, hepatic organoids generated from iPS cells of male and female donors will be exposed to male or female serum and/or hormone in an attempt to elicit sex-specific cellular physiology on both the genetic and environmental level. Resulting phenotypes will be characterised based on marker expression and functional properties (e.g. CYP enzyme and drug transporter activities).

A5.2.2 Innovative methods and tools for toxicity testing and modelling for Environmental Toxicology / Ecotoxicology

Details per project:

5.2.2 Joint project: P5.1.2.b_Y1_BPAalternatives_BPI_MU [M1-M48]

In Year 4 (M37-M48), the project will successively build on the developed strategy in the previous year to deliver new advanced methodologies. The final stage of the project, and specifically WP 5.2.2 activity, will be to finalize the method optimization and increased regulatory readiness. The obtained data from all completed assays will be disseminated through scientific publications. In addition to a scientific publication and dissemination effort, the developed methodologies will also be published as SOPs at open repositories (e.g. Zenodo). It is expected that the incoming partners in year 3, i.e. INRAE (developing methods connected with complex microbial communities and high-throughput metabolomics in aquatic periphyton) and CSIC (methods with daphnia spp. to assess cardiotoxicity, neurotoxicity, and metabolic disruption, and methods with zebrafish liver spheroid models, and behavioural endpoints in zebrafish) will also complete their work in year 4 and publish their methods. The final progress report will be published in M48 (originally planned for M42), as the project has applied for six months extension.

All activities will be in the closest link with other PARC tasks: specifically, Task 5.3 for AOP development and modelling, Tasks 6.1 and 6.2 for building NAMs confidence for regulatory applications, as well as WP7 for data management and WP9 for project internal synergies as well. Year 4 will also be a time period where partners will discuss the follow-up projects that will align with PARC priorities.

[Participants: BfG (DE), BPI (EL), EAWAG (CH), IISPV (ES), INERIS (FR), MU (CZ), MUI (AT), NIB (SI), NIC (SK), NIVA (NO), SDU (DK), SLU (SE), UAntwerpen (BE), UFZ (DE), UG-PL (PL), UPO (ES), CSIC (ES), INRAE (FR), CNRS (FR)]

Task 5.3: Quantitative systems toxicology and development of new AOPs

Co-leaders: UL-LACDR (NL), SCIENSANO (BE), INSERM (FR), Fraunhofer-ITEM (DE)

Participants:

Activity 5.3.1 and 5.3.3: AUTH (EL), BPI (EL), IISPV (ES), INSERM (FR), IRFM (IT), ISCIII (ES), ISS (IT), KIT (DE), MUI (AT), NIPH (NO), NCPHP (HU), Sciensano (BE), UFZ (DE), UGent (BE), UG-PL (PL), UDE (DE), UL-LACDR (NL), UMIL (IT), UNIABDN (UK), UOB (UK), WR (NL)

Activity 5.3.2: ACES/SU(SE), AU (DK), AUTH (EL), BfG (DE), BPI (EL), Cefas-Defra (UK), DTU (DK), IISPV (ES), INSERM (FR), IRSN (FR), ISS (IT), KI (SE), KIT (DE), KU-Leuven (BE), LIST (LU), MUI (AT), NILU

(NO), NIPH (NO), NCPHP (HU), Sciensano (BE), SDU (DK), UAntwerpen (BE), UGent (BE), UG-PL (PL), UHC (DE), UDE (DE), UL-LACDR (NL), UMIL (IT), UNIVIE (AT), WR (NL)

Activity 5.3.4: ANSES (FR), AUTH (EL), Cefas-Defra (UK), EA (UK), ETHZ (CH), Fraunhofer-ITEM (DE), IISPV (ES), INERIS (FR), INSERM (FR), ISCIII (ES), ISS (IT), NIPH (NO), NVI (NO), UFZ (DE), UHC (DE), UNIVIE (AT), WR (NL), WU-TOX (NL), UNISANTE (CH), STAMI (NO)

A5.3.1 Prioritized NAM-based mechanistic hazard characterisation & A5.3.3 Translation to human pathophysiology

A5.3.3 (Systems toxicology approaches for mechanism-based chemical safety assessment) were combined in a single project for coherence purposes.

Details per project:

- P5.3.1.a_Y1_SystemsToxicology_UL-LACDR [M1-M48]

In Y4, partners will finalize the 4 identified case-studies and publish the main findings (how systems toxicology can contribute to CS1 – Read-across, CS2 – ab initio studies, CS3 – temporal responses, C4 – human translation). In particular CS1 will in Y4, evaluate the inclusion of other *in vitro* assays in addition to transcriptomics (e.g., ToxCast), include in the RAX study *in vivo* data also accessed via the OECD QSAR toolbox and ECHA database. CS2 is carrying out a comparison on how different systems toxicology approaches identify and assess hazard. In Y4 CS2 will finalize a publication comparing several interpretation methods and benchmark modelling approaches and include feedback from regulators regarding the confidence over different Benchmark Concentration (BMC) estimates. In addition, this publication will include an automated reporting system for systems toxicology data analysed with benchmark dose methods. CS3 aims to define best practices for time course experiments in systems toxicology. In Y4 the analysis including Weighted Gene Correlation networks for analysis (WGCNA)-based methods will be expanded. CS4 will continue analysis the preservation results to derive a subset of gene co-expression modules that are found to be shared by human *in vivo* kidney data and human *in vitro* proximal tubule cell lines.

[Participants: UGent (BE), MUI (AT), ISCIII (ES), INSERM (FR), ISS (IT), UL-LACDR (NL), BPI (EL), KIT (DE), NCPHP (HU), WR (NL), Sciensano (BE), NIPH (NO), UNIABDN (UK), UFZ (DE), UG-PL (PL), IRFM (IT), UDE (DE), UMIL (IT), AUTH (EL), UOB (IK), IISPV (ES)]

- P5.3.1.b_Y4_grOMICS_UL-LACDR [M37-M84]

This project aims at proposing an operational system to incorporate HTTr and HTPP for Rax and grouping applications by including: 1) efficient reporting 2) test systems specific and robust interpretation 3) guidelines supported by case studies to merge structural and (physio)chemical (including metabolism), mode of action (from HTTr) and cellular morphology (HTPP). The actions planned for PARC Year 4 are detailed below:

Action 1: To design and develop a database system to streamline reporting of HTTr and HTPP experiments and to query and navigate reporting data (M37 to M55)

1.1 Annotate current version of the OORF based on user fill in scenario. PARC M37 to M49, by [UL (NL), IISPV (ES), BfR (DE)]

Action 2: To improve the interpretation framework of omics data by developing a tox-oriented,

interoperable ontology of pathways, gene sets and gene networks. (M37 to M65)

2.1 Develop test-systems specific models integrating HTTr and HTPP datasets of MCF7 and U2OS cell lines. PARC M37 to M49, by [UL (NL), INSERM (FR), UFZ (GE)], metadata support from WP7.

Action 3: To propose a framework to synergistically incorporate structural, cellular morphology -based and mode of action -based similarities for read-across and grouping applications, with a particular emphasis of MIE/early KEs prediction (M37 to M81)

3.1 Collection of physiochemical properties, HTTr, HTPP and relevant in vivo ADME properties and toxicological endpoints. PARC M37 to M49, by [UL (NL), IRFM (IT), IISPV (ES), Sciensano (BE), BHAM (UK)]

A5.3.2 AOP development based on integration of in vivo and in vitro data sets

Details per project:

- P5.3.2.a_Y1_AOPDevelopment_Inserm [M1-M48]

In year 4 the core group of this project (CG) will continue to develop new innovative tools supporting AOP development, based on artificial intelligence (AI) and text mining tools, in collaboration with WP8. The CG will continue to support the work of the Specialty groups (SGs) to help them to finalize the design of new AOPs. A workshop with training is planned (to be organized by AUTH in the spring 2026 for integration of NAM/IATA/AI for AOP, as well as a topic collaborative publication. The priorities will continue using D5.3 and the inventory of available AOPs identified on AD5.5: SG1 will focus on AOPs in the fields of respiratory sensitization, immunosuppression and non-genotoxic carcinogenesis and will collaborate with P5.2.1.d and P5.2.1.a. SG2 will focus on AOPs in the fields of endocrine disruption and metabolism and will collaborate with P5.2.1.b and P5.2.1.c. SG3 will focus on AOPs in the field of Neurotoxicity (ANT and DNT) and will collaborate with P5.2.1.e. The SG1 (Immunotoxicity), SG2 (Endocrine and metabolic disruption), SG3 (Neurotoxicity) and the Effect Marker Group (EMG) are structured into subgroups corresponding to the themes of SG1, SG2 and SG3 as well as a subgroup on epigenetics. Each group meets every 6 weeks on average to monitor the progress of the work. New AOPs or improved AOPs will be submitted to the AOP-Wiki database. It has to be noted that all CG partners are also involved in the SGs so that their technical support is made easier. A following AOP activity (Y5-7) will be discussed among the partners.

[Participants: SU (SE), AU (DK), AUTH (EL), BfG (DE), BPI (EL), DTU (DK), IISPV (ES), INSERM (FR), IRSN (FR), ISS (IT), KI (SE), KIT (DE), KU-Leuven (BE), LIST (LU), MUI (AT), NILU (NO), NIPH (NO), NCPHP (HU), UG-PL (PL), SDU (DK), Sciensano (BE), UAntwerpen (BE), UGent (BE), UKK/UoC (DE), UDE (DE), UL-LACDR (NL), UMIL (IT), UNIVIE (AT), WR (NL), Cefas-Defra (UK)]

A5.3.4 PBK models and quantitative systems toxicology

Details per project:

- P5.3.4.a_Y1_PBK_Kinetics_Fraunhofer [M1-M48]

From the seven case studies running in year 3, the following will continue in year 4: 01- Xenobiotic metabolism in human_microbiome (planned activity: reevaluation of existing microbiome-competent PBK models using the established optimized methodology), 06 - bioavailability of Alternaria toxins and 07- bioavailability of Enniatins (the partners will finalize the acquisition of *in*

vitro data (clearances, fractions unbound) and *in vivo* (plasma) Tk data necessary to develop and validate PBK modeling using a read across approach for this family of mycotoxins for which no model (useful for RA) currently exist). In Y4 a new case (08) study will be started to develop *in vitro* ADME models to predict the placental uptake of compounds. In addition, case study 09 will integrate new mechanisms of metabolic disruption from P5.2.1.b_MD-ED and link them to PBK modelling.

It In year 4, the case studies will spend most of the time on the integration of *in vitro* Absorption, Distribution, Metabolism and Excretion (ADME) data into the PBK models, the *in vitro* to *in vivo* extrapolation and the uncertainty and sensitivity analysis of the PBK models.

[Participants: UNISANTE (CH), ANSES (FR), ETHZ (CH), IISPV (ES), INERIS (FR), INSERM (FR), ISCIII (ES), ISS (IT), Fraunhofer (DE), NVI (NO), UKK/UoC (DE), WR (NL), WU-TOX (NL), EA (UK), AUTH (EL), Cefas-Defra (UK), NIPH (NO), STAMI (NO), UNIVIE (AT), UDE (DE)]

- P5.3.4.b_Y4_RESUPT_RIVM [M37-M84]

Below the specific actions of PARC Y4 of this project are detailed. The aim is to enhance our understanding of how *in vitro* respiratory models can be applied to study respiratory uptake, which is crucial for evaluating the systemic toxic effects of inhaled substances.

Activity 1: Data gap analysis on air liquid dosimetry, *in vitro* biokinetic approaches and permeability models. The aim of this activity is to collect the knowledge on transporters in respiratory epithelium, both *in vitro* and *in vivo* and mechanisms of uptake of the selected substances. This will provide the basis for choosing relevant models (including transporters) to assess respiratory uptake and relevant options for dosimetry. For novel substances, uptake mechanisms are unknown. Therefore, an approach will be developed to aid selection of a model to assess respiratory uptake.

- Results will be gathered in report R-RESUPT.1 Data gap analysis on air liquid dosimetry, *in vitro* biokinetic approaches and permeability models, PARC M43 by [RIVM (NL), ITEM, INERIS (FR), UG-PL/QSARLab, STAMI]

- The selection of test chemicals will be performed and input gathered in report R-RESUPT.2 Selection of test compounds. PARC M43 by [All partners]

Activity 2: Data measured for 4 model compounds on plastic binding and evaporation for *in vitro* biokinetic modelling. Quantitative Structure-Property Relationships (QSPR) models, along with or other *in silico* tools (i.e. read-across to predict kinetic for target chemicals based on similar source compounds), will be used for PBK model parameterisation. This approach will help overcome the limitations in the broader application of PBK models, which are often restricted due to gaps in chemical-specific input data. Additionally, computational techniques, such as molecular docking, will be employed to estimate parameters such as protein binding. By predicting how a compound interacts with proteins, models help in determining their bioavailability and distribution, which are the key factors affecting the transport of chemicals across biological membranes.

-Results will be gathered in report R-RESUPT.3 Data measured for 4 model compounds on plastic binding and evaporation for *in vitro* biokinetic modelling. PARC M43 until M54 by [INERIS (), AUTH ()]

Activity 3: Data measured for 4 model compounds on barrier models and integrated into PBK

models. The aim of this activity is to collect experimental data on the respiratory uptake of pesticides and reference substances, and to parameterize PBPK models with respiratory uptake data

All activities mentioned above will feed Activity 4 that therefore will start at a later point of the project.

Activity 4: Guidance document on dosimetry and the use of respiratory in vitro models for uptake assessment. The aim of this task is to ensure regulatory applicability of in vitro models and PBPK models for assessment of respiratory uptake.

Deliverables:

D5.5 2nd New approach methodologies report – Leader: BfR (initially due M36 is postponed to M48)

D5.6 2nd new PBK models report – Leader: Fraunhofer-ITEM (M48)

D5.7 Systems Toxicology and AOPs report – Leader: INSERM (M48)

Additional Deliverables

AD5.8. Study report – Leader: ANSES (M41) (linked to the project P5.1.1.c_Y3_TG+ EnnB1_ANSES (M25-M60))

WP N°	WP6										Lead Beneficiary				RIVM/KEMI																			
WP title	Innovation in regulatory RA																																	
Partner N°	1	1.1	1.2	1.4	1.6	1.14	1.12	1.13	3	3.1	3.4	4	4.5	4.6	4.7	5	5.1	5.3	7	8	10.1	10.2	10.3	10.4	10.5	11.2	13.1	14	14.2	15	15.2	15.5	15.7	15.8
Partner short name	ANSES	INSERM	INRAE	INERIS	INRS	ASNR	CSTB	EHESP	EAA	AGES	MUI	VITO	OVAM	ISSEP	UAntwerpen	SCIENSANO	UGent	VUB	MOH-CY/SGL	MU	AU	DTU	REGIONH-GE	UCPH	SDU	UT	SYKE	TTL	Tukes	UBA	UFZ	UOS	UDE	RWTH
PM/partner	75.5	9.7	8.0	10.5	3.0	3.0	1.5	4.5	1.5	13.8	1.5	30.7	0.3	13.0	11.0	47.1	6.0	4.7	1.0	52.8	11.3	19.4	23.5	6.3	3.0	18.0	4.6	8.6	1.0	29.5	33.3	5.3	19.5	6.4

Partner N°	16.1	16.6	18	20	20.1	20.3	20.4	20.5	20.7	23	24	24.2	25	25.1	25.2	25.4	25.5	25.6	25.7	25.8	25.9	26	26.2	26.3	26.4	27	27.1	27.2	28	29	29.3	29.4	29.5	31	31.1
Partner short name	Fraunhofer-IBMT/IME	RPTU	UI	ISS	ICPS	IRFM	IUSS	UMIL	UNIPD	LSMU	LNS	LIST	RIVM	KWR	TNO	UL-LACDR	UU-IRAS	VUA	WR	WU-TOX	SRU	NIPH	STAMI	NILU	NIVA	NIOM	IEP-NRI	UG-PL	FMUL	INSA	ENSP	UC	UAVR	JSI	GEoZS

PM/partner	Partner N°	Partner short name	PM/partner	Start
4.0	32	NIJZ	15.8	M37
31.5	32.1	OI	6.2	
1.3	32.2	NI/ZOH	0.2	
19.5	33	CSIC	27.0	End
7.8	33.3	UGR	5.0	
6.3	34	ISCHII	30.0	
6.0	34.3	FINBA	25.3	
3.0	34.5	IISPV	19.5	
1.0	34.7	UCLM	12.5	
2.5	35.2	KI	8.3	
5.6	35.3	ULJUND	0.6	
2.0	35.4	ORU	3.0	
57.1	35.5	RISE	8.7	
2.7	35.6	SU	61.5	M48
9.8	35.7	KEMI	17.0	
8.9	35.8	IVL	10.2	
22.6	35.10	SLU	10.5	
14.5	36	AUTH	14.5	
3.8	37	BPI	40.7	
3.0	38	FOPH	0.5	
8.0	40	UNISANTE	14.0	
19.9	41	EAWAG	2.3	
17.0	44	FOEN	6.0	
2.5	45	USI	2.0	
16.5	46	UNIBAS	6.0	
19.0	49	EFSA	4.0	
25.2	53	UKGEH	17.2	
15.0	54	EA	0.6	
4.6	59	UOB	4.3	

Objectives

The main goal of WP6 is to drive innovation in regulatory RA by strengthening its scientific basis, with implementation of NGRA as ultimate goal. The specific objectives of WP6 for year 4 are:

- Task 6.1: To refine (quantitative) networks of AOPs for genotoxicity, endocrine disruption (thyroid dysfunction) and liver toxicity (liver fibrosis) To re-design, based on this work, regulatory relevant Integrated Approaches to Testing and Assessment (IATAs) for genotoxicity, endocrine disruption and liver toxicity in close collaboration with relevant stakeholders and (re-)evaluate the applicability of developed IATAs by means of dedicated case studies in an iterative way. To refine, through regulatory relevant case studies, a previously drafted workflow for the assessment of human relevance of toxicological pathways and associated NAMs, with focus on quantitative aspects.
- Task 6.2: To further develop and apply innovative methods, tools and concepts to perform integrative risk and health impact assessment (HIA)s based on internal and external human exposures to single chemicals and mixtures in integrating multiple sources and routes from general and occupational environments.
- Task 6.3: To continue implementation and further refinement of case studies reviewing selected methodologies and approaches for regulatory RA.
- Task 6.4: To develop efficient and protective regulatory workable RA methods through in-depth analysis of collected data for mixtures, articles, NAMs and biodiversity.

Description of Programmed Activities

WP6 annual workshop

The joint annual WP6 workshop with WP and TL, partners, and relevant stakeholders (e.g. EU and national authorities) will be organized to discuss activities, focusing on ongoing work and proposals for developments and new case studies to ensure the regulatory relevance. The workshop will be planned together with partners from WP2 to strengthen the science-to-policy frame of the workshop. This will be reflected in the program of the workshop. Also, partners from WP2 will chair a session on how to plan for impact related to project results. The WP6 workshop will be hosted by AGES (AT) and take place on 19-21 May, 2025 (M37). In preparation for the annual WP6 workshop, webinars will be organised (in April/May 2025) where research results from all tasks in WP6 will be presented. Similar to previous years, relevant regulatory stakeholders (ECHA, EFSA, EEA, JRC, DGs) will be invited to provide feedback in a separate webinar, to present priorities and regulatory needs as well as recent and upcoming developments regarding chemical RAs. This feedback and input will be used to provide support for discussions on how WP6 can further contribute to addressing these needs and meet the regulatory challenges. Collaborations with other WPs, in particular WP2, will be continued to optimize the output [KEMI, RIVM, all WP6 partners].

Task 6.1: Integrated Approaches to Testing and Assessment of Chemicals

Co-Leaders: SCIENSANO (BE), UL-LACDR (NL)

Partners: AUTH (EL), BPI (EL), CEFAS-DEFRA (UK), DTU (DK), ENSP (PT), Fraunhofer-ITEM (DE), IISPV (ES), INRAE (FR), INSERM (FR), IRFM (IT), IRSN (FR), ISS (IT), KI (SE), KWR (NL), LIST (LU), MU (CZ), MUI (AT), NILU (NO), NIPH (NO), RIVM (NL), SDU (DK), STAMI (NO), UAntwerpen (BE), UGent (BE), UG-PL (PL), UKHSA (UK), UKCEH (UK), VUB (BE), WR (NL), WU-TOX (NL)

A6.1.1: Development of IATAs for regulatory purposes

In Y4, we will further work on the development of IATAs for genotoxicity, endocrine disruption (with focus on thyroid hormone system disruption (THSD)) and liver toxicity (with focus on liver fibrosis) for selected regulatory framework(s) and specific population groups. In Y4, AOP networks (AON), which were created based on existing AOPs and existing NAMs for each of these endpoints, will be refined and quantified, where relevant for the problem formulation at hand. The IATAs will be tested in relevant case studies; the outcomes will be reported in the final project report (genotoxicity and liver toxicity) or in the annual progress report (endocrine disruption). Additionally, we will work on further improvement and refinement of a draft workflow for human relevance assessment. Both the work on this workflow and the IATA development for genotoxicity, endocrine disruption and liver toxicity will be an iterative process consisting of various cycles of optimization, thereby taking into account the feedback from different stakeholders (A6.1.3).

Details per project:

- **P6.1.1.a_Y1_HumanRelevance_RIVM [M1 – M36]:** this project was finalised in M36
- **P6.1.1.b_Y1_IATA-ED_UAntwerpen [M1 – M36]:** this project was finalised in M36
- **P6.1.1.c_Y1_IATA_GENTOX_Sciensano [M1 – M48; the project has been extended from M36 to M48]**

IATA development for genotoxicity. In Y4, this project will continue to characterize KERs within the AON for genotoxicity based on evidence collected using the harmonized strategy. We will explore whether the qAOP for DNA alkylation leading to increases in mutations and structural and numerical chromosome aberrations developed for a reference alkylating agent can be extended to other compounds. Moreover, we will characterize the uncertainties related to genotoxicity methods. Also, we will identify the main drivers of variability. Based on all these activities, the project will design an IATA for genotoxicity. This project will also execute two case studies for genotoxicity, making use of existing as well as newly generated data. [Partners: Sciansano (BE), INRAE (FR), VUB (BE), UL-LACDR (NL), WU-TOX (NL), ISS (IT), IBMT (DE), UG-PL (PL), STAMI (NO), LIST (LU), BPI (EL), IRSN (FR), RIVM (NL), KWR (NL), NILU (NO), IRFM (IT), NIPH (NO), WR (NL), MUI (AT)].

- P6.1.1.d_Y1_IATA_STOT_UL-LACDR [M1-M48; the project has been extended from M36 to M48 due to initial delays of personnel hiring and delays in experimental data generation]

IATA development for liver toxicity. In Y4, we will finish execution of case studies which have been designed on the basis of the first case study, i.e., the gene expression measured at 24h following exposure to fibrosis-related chemicals in four liver cell test systems (in 2D and 3D). Given the known critical involvement of several other cell types in liver fibrosis, i.e. Kupffer cells and stellate cells, the aim is to utilize an IATA with mixed cell systems (by the involved project partners and by FDA's organ-on-a-chip 'Emulate') to study and quantify late key events in the relevant AOP. qAOP development, performed in collaboration with the Horizon 2020 project RISK-HUNT3R, will be finalized in Y4, first on the basis of existing *in vivo* data, and subsequently on the basis of project case study data. [Partners: UL-LACDR (NL), WU-TOX (L), INSERM (FR), Ugent (BE), AUTH (EL), MU (CZ), IISPV (ES), STAMI (NO), ISS (IT), IRFM (IT), WR (NL)]

- P6.1.1e_Y4_FISH-THSD_UAntwerpen [M37-M81]

This project builds upon the output of the PARC T6.1 ED IATA project (P6.1.1.b_Y1_IATA-ED_UAntwerpen), in which AON were constructed and evaluated as a basis for developing THSD assessment strategies, and relevant methods for assessing THSD were identified and mapped to the AON. This project aims to develop and test an AON-based approach for the identification of thyroid hormone system disrupting chemicals (THSDCs) in fish. This work addresses important gaps in the currently available tools for the identification of THSDCs by integrating *in silico*, *in vitro* and *in vivo* fish test data for the T modality in a tiered testing approach that is aligned with the ECHA-EFSA Guidance for the identification of endocrine disruptors. Specifically, the project will provide an integrated approach for the identification of THSDCs in fish that is supported by OECD-endorsed AOPs and executed using assays that are currently under OECD and EU-NETVAL validation. The project will focus on integrating (1) the measurement of thyroid hormone levels, thyroid histopathology, eye development, swim bladder inflation and behaviour in zebrafish embryos and zebrafish larvae as additions to existing OECD Test Guidelines (TG 236 and TG 210), (2) the *in vitro* measurement of a selection of relevant THSD mechanisms, (3) QSAR model data. The approach will be designed in a tiered fashion that allows the implementation of a decision tree logic. A series of specific case studies will be developed and executed in collaboration with ECHA, EFSA and other stakeholders, generating new data and re-using existing data for selected chemicals that are relevant in the context of specific legislations. The project outcomes will be applicable to the REACH and Classification, Labelling and Packaging (CLP) legislations as well as the Plant Protection Products

Regulation (PPPR) and the Biocidal Products Regulation (BPR), by providing a framework for using *in silico*, *in vitro* and fish test data for THSDC identification. Based on the timelines of the OECD and EU-NETVAL validation efforts that are currently ongoing for the fish and *in vitro* methods that will be used in this project, it is expected that the timeline to implementation into regulatory frameworks is around 5 years. [Partners: UAntwerpen (BE), UKHSA (UK), SDU (DK), MU (CZ), CEFAS-DEFRA (UK), RIVM (NL), UG-PL (PL), IRFM (IT), VU (NL)]

- P6.1.1.f_Y4_HumanRelevance_RIVM [M37-M81]

This project is aimed at establishing a harmonized workflow for assessing the human relevance of AOPs and NAMs related to key events (KEs) and key event relationships (KERs). Building on previous PARC work (*i.e.*, P6.1.1.a_Y1_HumanRelevance_RIVM), the project aims to further standardize the process for assessing human relevance. Besides improving qualitative aspects of the workflow, it will address quantitative aspects, *i.e.*, cross-species comparisons and *in vitro* to *in vivo* extrapolations. These objectives will be achieved through case studies. In Y4, two case studies will be selected in close collaboration with ECHA and EFSA: one case study that is likely to be relevant to humans, and another case study that is likely to be less relevant to humans. For both case studies, the project team will focus on the question if and how quantitative aspects can best be addressed in the workflow. Evidence collected will be subjected to a structured weight of evidence (WoE) assessment. Where needed and feasible, we will seek support from WP7, for support on WoE assessment and uncertainty analysis. Templates (developed in the previous PARC project) for collecting and evaluating evidence will be modified where needed. During Y4, the project managers will have regular meetings with EFSA and ECHA, to discuss progress and challenges encountered. In addition, we will pro-actively work on dissemination of this PARC activity, by reaching out to other relevant stakeholders, such as the Working Group of National Co-ordinators of the OECD Test Guidelines Programme (WNT) and the Working Party on Hazard Assessment (WPHA), and through the SF (in collaboration with WP2). [Partners: AUTH (EL); RIVM (NL); ENSP (PT); BPI (EL); WU-TOX (NL); NIPH (NO); STAMI (NO); IRSN (FR); ISS (IT); IISPV (ES); LIST (LU)].

A6.1.2: Evaluation of IATAs through case studies

The draft versions of the IATAs for genotoxicity, endocrine disruption (with focus on thyroid hormone synthesis disruption) and liver toxicity as well as the draft workflow for human relevance assessment developed in A6.1.1 will be evaluated through (additional) case studies. The respective case study teams will investigate the previously defined case study regulatory hypotheses with the selected relevant case study compounds. To arrive at meaningful conclusions through WoE assessments, we will closely collaborate with WP7; approaches used for WoE evaluations will be discussed upfront with regulatory agencies. For ultimate integration of the data into Quantitative *in vitro* / *in vivo* Extrapolation (QIVIVE), we will further strengthen the link with the experts and tools established in T5.3. For the latter, dedicated discussions will be organized between T6.1 and T5.3, with the aim to determine how to best organize this collaboration. Reports on the case study modeling and experimental activities will be submitted for review via the project management system under T2.1 (M48). In the IATA case studies, the lessons learned by different stakeholders

from previous case studies mapped in T6.3 will also be implemented as soon as this information becomes available. [Partners: AUTH (EL), BPI (EL), CEFAS-DEFRA (UK), DTU (DK), ENSP (PT), Fraunhofer (DE), IISPV (ES), INRAE (FR), ISS (IT), KI (SE), KWR (NL), MU (CZ), MUI (AT), RIVM (NL), SCIENSANO (BE), SDU (DK), UAntwerpen (BE), UG-PL, UKHSA (UK), UL-LACDR (NL), VUB (BE), WR (NL), WU-TOX (NL)]

A6.1.3: Stakeholder engagement

For each of the health effects addressed we will continue the interactions with relevant related (research) initiatives, such as ENKORE, RISK-HUNT3R, ONTOX, PrecisionTOX and HESI GTTC, established in Y1-Y3. For a wider stakeholder involvement, the progress made on AOP/AON and IATA development for genotoxicity, endocrine disruption and liver toxicity as well as on the workflow for human relevance will be discussed with a diverse group of stakeholders in the annual two-day WP6 workshop (May 2025). For the progress made and challenges encountered related to the projects on IATAs and the workflow for human relevance, we will continue to actively interact with ECHA, EFSA, JRC and OECD, to maximize regulatory impact. This will be mainly achieved through online meetings. Additionally, ECHA, EFSA, JRC and OECD will be consulted regarding additional IATAs for complex endpoints (described in AD6.9 (M30)), in terms of considerations to be taken into account when designing projects for the final phase of PARC. [Partners: RIVM (NL), Sciensano (BE), UL-LACDR (NL), STAMI (NO), ISS (IT), UG-PL (PL), BPI (EL)]

Task 6.2: Integrative exposure and RA

Co-Leaders: ANSES (FR), VITO (BE)

Partners: AU (DK), ARSO (SI), AUTH (EL), BPI (EL), CSTB (FR), DTU (DK), EFSA (IT), EHESP (FR), ENSP (PT), FINBA (ES), TTL (FI), FMUL (PT), FOPH (CH), Fraunhofer (DE), GEoSZ (SI), ICPS (IT), CSIC (ES), IISPV (ES), KI (SE), INERIS (FR), INRAE (FR), INRS (FR), INSA (PT), IRFM (IT), ISCIII (ES), ISSeP (BE), IUSS (IT), IVL (SE), KWR (NL), LNS (LU), MOH-CY/SGL (CY), MU (CZ), NIJZ (SI), NIOM (PL), NIPH (NO), NLZOH (SI), OI (SI), ONIRIS (FR), OVAM (BE), RIVM (NL), SRU (NL), SCIENSANO (BE), SECO (CH), SLU (SE), STAMI (NO), TNO (NL), UAVR (PT), UBA (DE), UGR (ES), UG-PL (PL), UNIPD (IT), UNISANTE (CH), USI (CH), UoB (UK), UU-IRAS (NL), WR (NL)

Year 4 will be dedicated to finalize the application to case studies of prioritized chemicals (in particular PFAS, pesticides, metals, phtalates) of the strategy and approaches developed during year 1, 2 and 3 in the different projects of the task T6.2. Results will be analyzed, strengthened, and case studies extended in regards of regulatory needs. Synergies between T6.2 projects case studies will continue to deploy the integrative and dynamical way to model single and mixture aggregate exposure and perform HIA. The implementation of the developed approaches and methods in the different T6.2 projects for mixture, aggregate, kinetics (PBK models) and HIA as well as the data needed will continue with the help of T8.3 to provide an operational tools to perform integrative exposure and RA in the PARCToolBox(MCRA) for PARC partners and stakeholders such as regulatory agencies. In addition, the TLs, PLs and the case study leaders will continue to discuss the impact of the case studies with regulators from DG SANTE, DG ENV, DG EMPL and their needs in the futur to implement the proposed strategy and methds. Four deliverables will be delivered by month 36 (end year 3).

- D6.1 Report on aggregate exposure for general population and workers, and source to dose models applied to case studies (P6.2.1)
- D6.2 Report on innovative methods based on PBK models (P6.2.2)
- D6.3 Report on innovative approaches for real-life mixture RA (P6.2.3)
- D6.4 Report on environmental burden of disease (EBD) and health impact indicators and their policy implications (P6.2.4)

In year 4, we will disseminate and discuss the outcome of the deliverables with European and national/regional regulators, by organizing webinars and other dissemination fora.

A6.2.1 Aggregated exposure assessment from multiple sources and routes for general population and workers

Details per project:

- P6.2.1.a_Y1_SourcetoDose_VITO: SourcetoDose_VITO [M1-M36] (extended from M1-M36 to M1-M42)

In the extended period (M37-M42) we will complete and publish case studies that were started in year 3 (i.e. case studies on source to dose in outdoor environment such as metals and PFAS in hotspots, and indoor environment on plasticizers), and will work together with T8.3 on the integration of the models in PARC toolbox, and we will collaborate with P.6.2.1b_Y1_Aggregate_ANSES in order to foster the integration of the source to dose models in aggregate exposure. Contributors: RIVM (NL); ANSES (FR); IVV (DE); CSTB (FR); KWR (NL); IVL (SW); NIJZ (SI); FOPH (CH); GeoZS (SI); FMUL (PT), IISPV (ES), OVAM (BE); ISSeP (BE), ARSO (SI)].

- P6.2.1.b_Y1_Aggregate_ANSES [M1-M48]

The application of the strategy to assess aggregate exposure through different sources from general and occupational environments and different routes of entry (inhalation, dermal, ingestion) will continue for prioritized case studies: Cd, pyrethroids, PFAS and phthalates (All partners). More sources and routes will be added from the data collection done during year 3 and general and occupational environments will be connected. With the help of partners from the 6.2.2.a project, PBK models will be applied to aggregate the routes of exposure and to compare simulated internal exposure with available HBM data. In collaboration with T8.3, selected exposure models from the scoring process that has followed the inventory of the associated models and tools will continue to be implemented and connected in the ParcToolBox (MCRA) (WR-BIOM and UNISANTE, ANSES, TNO, VITO, RIVM, FOPH, TTL, BPI). The decision tree developed to decide on aggregation needs will continue to be tested with the prioritized case studies. Aggregate exposures and associated risk will be produced for several European populations. The innovative approach developed to aggregate exposures and its application to several case studies will be published in several scientific papers. Several meetings by project subworking groups (method/model connection/different case studies) are planned at least every two months and at least one preferably physical meeting for the whole project. [Lead: ANSES (FR) Unisanté (CH). Case study/method lead : ANSES (FR), UNISANTE (CH), WUR-BIOM (NL), TNO (NL), TTL (FI), IVL (SE), ISCIII (ES), FOPH(CH) Contributors: CSTB (FR), INRS

(FR), CSIC (ES), IISPV (ES), INSA (PT), ENSP-UNL (PT), FMUL (PT), VITO (BE), ISSeP (BE), OVAM (BE), LNS (LU), SRU (NL), WR-BIOM (NL), KWR (NL), IVV (DE), MU/RECETOX (CZ), NIOM (PL), NIJZ (SI), GeoZS (SI), ARSO (SI), BPI (EL), AUTH (EL), UOB (UK), NIPH (NO), STAMI (NO), AU (DK), EFSA (EU), UoB (UK)

A6.2.2 Modelling exposure through life

Details per project:

- P6.2.2.a_Y1_PBPk_INERIS [M1-M48]

In the first three years, an inventory of PBPk models and their gaps, as well as refinement in PBPk models to account for lifetime exposure in terms of physiology and exposure routes were made for pesticides (pyrethroids and organophosphates), metals (Cd, As, Pb, Hg), bisphenols and PFAS. In year 3, the aim was to extend the parameterisation of PBPk models for these compounds to address identified gaps and needs for human lifetime exposure, including sensitive populations. Year 4 will focus on the availability of PBPk models and their application in RA. We will aim to provide guidance and training to risk assessors and other partners of PARC in a FAIR implementation of models in the integrative ParcToolBox (MCRA/Integra) in collaboration with T8.3 (WR-BIOM). Extensive parameterisation of newly generated data in PARC (e.g., in WP5) will continue. The involvement of 6.2.2 partners in the different case studies of task 6.2 will continue. In these case studies, several topics will be particularly addressed under the scope of this project: (i) the impact of bioavailability differences related to age, gender and route of exposure, (ii) the impact of changes in legislative limits to persistent compounds in internal exposure in different age groups, and (iii) the use of *in vitro* assays hazard assessment metrics versus internal dose associated to real life exposure scenarios for delivering risk characterization. One whole meeting is expected to be organised every 3 months, and one meeting per thematic working group every 2 months. [Partners involved: INERIS (FR), AUTH (EL), IISPV (ES), ANSES (FR), RIVM (NL), SLU (SE), NIPH (NO), VITO (BE), WR-BIOM (NL), WR (NL), IRFM (IT), IVL (SE), TNO (NL), ONIRIS (FR), IUSS (IT), KWR (NL), UniSanté (Switzerland)]

A6.2.3 Mixture exposure and RA

Details per project:

- P6.2.3.a_Y1_RealLifeMixtures_RIVM [M1-M48]

The year 4 will be consecrated to strengthen and finalize the first application of the developed strategy in each case study (e.g., pesticides and neurotoxic effects, PFAS and immune effect, metals and kidney effects, metals and developmental effects) to perform Mixture Risk Assessment (MRA) using several HBM dataset from different European general and occupational populations. With the help of data owners, we will continue to harmonize and upload in PARCToolBox (MCRA) the remaining HBM data such as occupational ones. Adjustment will be made on MCRA on contextual information related to working hours and working circumstances, in order to prepare data for their use in the different case studies. Thus, the integration in the PARCToolBox (MCRA) of the input data (HBM, hazard, kinetic parameters), the statistical and kinetic models as well as the updated risk metrics needed for each case studied will be finalized. Risk drivers will be identified drivers and efforts to connect with EFSA results on risk drivers from dietary exposure will continue. The five

case studies' results will be published in scientific journals and disseminated on international congresses. We will also work on the MRA dashboard to show aggregated HBM MRA results on the basis of the information published. The case studies will be then extended to propose higher tier scenarios and to include other chemicals with co-exposures and common effects. Trainings for national hubs, for members of the PARC SF will be given. The case study leaders and project leaders will continue to discuss and integrate results in synergy with in particular with EFSA, EEA and ECHA. In year 4, the project will also explore the link between HBM data and sources of exposure as indoor and outdoor exposure. This will be done as joint activity with P6.2.1.b_Y1_Aggregate_ANSES project and the PARC Task 4.2 (environmental and multisource monitoring) as well as PARC Task 8.3 (Integrative modelling network). Jointly with P6.2.1.b_Y1_Aggregate_ANSES, the project will identify risk drivers and sources for informing risk managers. Potential risk mitigation measures will be discussed with regulators.

[Lead: ANSES (FR), RIVM (NL). Case study and method WG lead: ANSES (FR), RIVM (NL), BPI (EL), UGR (ES), VITO (BE) Contributors: AU (DK), AUTH (EL), CSIC (ES), IISPV (ES), DTU (DK), EASP (ES), EFSA (EU), EHESP (FR), FINBA (ES), ICPS (IT), JSI (SI), INERIS (FR), INSERM (FR), ISCIII (ES), IVL (SE), LNS (LU), MOHCY/SGL (CY), MU (CZ), NIJZ (SI), NIPH (NO), SRU (NL), SLU (SE), STAMI (NO), TTL (FI), UBA (DE), UG-PL (PL), UNIPD (IT), UU-IRAS (NL), VITO (BE), WR (NL), INRAE (FR), KWR (NL), FMUL (PT), GeoZS (SI), UNIVIE (AT), IRFM (IT) INRAE (FR), Oniris/INRAE (FR)].

A6.2.4 Human, EBD, HIA and risk indicators

In this task on environmental burden of disease (EBD) and HIA the project on case studies (P6.2.4.c_Y1_HIACaseStudies_UU-IRAS) functions currently as a central hub to which other projects (P6.2.4.a_Y1_HIADDataAvailability_VITO; P6.2.4.b_Y1_HIAMethod_UU-IRAS; P6.2.4.d_Y1_HIAIndicators_VITO) are linked. Starting from the case studies, data are gathered to perform EBD calculations, hurdles in the methodology are described and indicators are developed when finalizing the case studies. D6.4 is submitted at M36 (end year 3), consisting of all performed work regarding methodological improvements, data availability, case studies, and indicators on HIA and EBD. In year 4, we will work on finalizing case studies, publications, harmonizing methods and implementation of methods in MCRA toolbox where possible (for those aspects that can be generalized/harmonized across case studies), and discuss the outcome with regulators.

Overarching project meetings will be organized with all partners every 2 months, and each case study will have roughly meeting every 4/6 weeks.

Details per project:

- P6.2.4.a_Y1_HIADDataAvailability_VITO [M1-M66]

In Y4, the project will continue the exploration of possibilities to gather data and fill data gaps for data-poor chemicals identified and prioritized in year 1. In Y4, focus will be on exposure data (external & internal), health data, exposure-response data and data on socio-economic status. The availability of data will be linked to the case studies where data and data gaps will be identified.

Case studies can be proposed by the partners, and will undergo selection and review according to the established procedures (MCDA and expert opinion). [Project lead: VITO (BE) UU-IRAS (NL). Contributors: ANSES (FR), AUTH (EL), DTU (DK), ENSP (PT), FMUL (PT), IISPV (ES), INSA (PT), ISSeP (BE), IVL (SE), KI (SE), MU (CZ), NIJZ (SI), NIPH (NO), NLZOH (SI), OI (SI), SRU (NL), Sciensano (BE), STAMI (NO), USI (CH)]

- P6.2.4.b_Y1_HIAMethod_UU-IRAS [M1-M66]

. A working paper on methodological topics, challenges in EBD calculations was composed. Several of these topics are addressed in case-studies that have been proposed in Y3 and will be conducted in Y4. The findings from the working paper on the methodological challenges for calculating the EBD related to chemical exposure will be incorporated in the case studies. Some have started in Y3 and will continue in Y4. Case studies specifically dedicated on methodological issues will continue in Y4 as well. More in detail:

- Incorporating a time-to-event model to improve the prediction of age of onset or death (lead RIVM)
- Probability modeling in burden of disease (lead UBA)

Other methodological improvements identified and prioritized in previous years may be initiated as well in Y4; feasibility of addressing those during the course of PARC will be assessed and activities will be planned accordingly. [Project lead: UU-IRAS/UBA Contributors: ANSES (FR), AUTH (EL), DTU (DK), ENSP (PT), FMUL (PT), IISPV (ES), INSA (PT), IVL (SE), KI (SE), MU (CZ), NIPH (NO), OI (SI), RIVM (NL), Sciensano (BE), UBA (DE), USI (CH), UU-IRAS (NL), VITO (BE), WR- (NL)].

- P6.2.4.c_Y1_HIACaseStudies_UU-IRAS [M1-M42]

In year 4, we will finalize case studies started in year 2 or 3, and start new case studies. Case studies included at least one of the following aspects: to calculate HI, BD, risk/benefit and/or cost/benefit focusing on chemicals, exposure-(biomarker of) effect relationships, exposure scenarios, and methodological improvements and innovations prioritized.

Case studies already discussed in Y2 and starting in Y3 are exposure to PFAS and related immune effects (leading partner VITO), exposure to metals and chronic kidney disease (leading partner Sciensano, RIVM).

Other possible case studies starting in Y4 will be presented and selected through a multi-criteria decisions analysis (MCDA) tool developed during Y1. In Y3, modifications were made to the MCDA tool to promote case studies focusing on mixtures and neurotoxic, immunotoxic, and endocrine disruptive effects. For Y4, partners will have time to submit their case study proposals until the end of March 2025; after which the proposals will be evaluated using the updated MCDA procedure, with the selection, results expected by the end of April, thereby giving partners one year to work on and finish their approved case study (until the start of Y5).

Case studies selected for Y4:

- Possible impact of glyphosate-based herbicides and diabetes in EU countries (lead IRAS)
- Impact of exposure to PFAS and infectious diseases (lead VITO)

- Exposure to cadmium and chronic kidney disease (lead Sciansano)
- Exposure to a mixture of cadmium and lead and nephrotoxicity (lead Sciansano)

[Project lead: ANSES (FR), VITO (BE) Contributors: AUTH (EL), BPI (EL), DTU (DK), ENSP (PT), FMUL (PT), IISPV (ES), INSA (PT), KI (SE), NIPH (NO), OI (SI), SRU (NL), Sciansano (BE), SPF (FR), STAMI (NO), UU-IRAS (NL)].

- P6.2.4.d_Y1_HIAIndicators_VITO [M1-M42]

In year 4, the project will focus on the development and implementation of indicators (proposed in former years) to assess the human health risk and/or impact of selected exposure scenarios to inform policy makers. In Y4, we will continue developing indicators (for other substances, cfr. case studies), which will aid the translation of science to policy and answer policy-related questions (e.g.; in collaboration with EEA). Main focus will be on indicators coming from the case studies.

[Project lead: VITO (BE) UU-IRAS (NL) Contributors: ANSES (FR), FMUL (PT), Sciansano (BE), DTU (DK), OI (SI), VITO (BE) Contributors: AUTH (EL), ENSP (PT), INSA (PT), IVL (SE), MU (CZ), NIJZ (SI), UU-IRAS (NL), WR (NL)].

Task 6.3: Review of RA methodology

Co-Leaders: BPI (EL)

Partners: UCL (UK), INSA (PT), EAA (AT), EAWAG (CH), TTL (FI), FOEN (CH), INERIS (FR), INSERM (FR), INRAE (FR), IRFM (IT), ISS (IT), ISSeP (BE), JSI (SI), KI (SE), LSMU (LT), DTU (DK), REGIONH (DK), UCPH (DK), RSU (LV), SCIENSANO (BE), STAMI (NO), NILU (NO), SYKE (FI), UBA (DE), ULUND (SE), VUB (BE), UNIBAS (CH), KEMI (SE), SU (SE), BPI (EL), UMIL (IT), UNIPD (IT), EFSA (EU), UT (EE)

The projects under T6.3 will continue during M37-M48, with further refinement of reviews and analysis through case studies as well as further exploration of stakeholder interactions. The interactions with ECHA, EFSA, SCCS, JRC and OECD on their involvement in the task, either to follow or actively take part in specific case studies, will continue, focusing both on input to ongoing and planned work as well as to disseminate results and increase regulatory uptake. Possibilities to disseminate results to national authorities will be explored. The need to describe regulatory relevance of the projects and case studies will continuously be highlighted. Case studies will be ongoing for two to five years. Due to delays related to e.g., further data collection needs, unexpected findings, unexpected obligations, parental or sick leave, one case study (CS10) planned to end M32 will continue until M42, five case studies (CS1, CS4, CS8, CS15 and CS16) planned to end M36 will continue until M48. For the CS7, the first phase of the study was finalised in M36 and the second phase will be initiated in M37, lasting until M81.

One to two project meetings to present and discuss the progress of the case studies will be organized during Y4 [Partners involved: BPI (EL), KEMI (SE), All partners].

Case study-specific meetings for planning and progress updates will be organized by the case study leaders as needed.

A6.3.1 Substance and effect specific reviews

Details per project:

- P6.3.1.a_Y1_SubstanceRA_SU [M1-M48]

Case studies reviewing substance-specific RA depending on intended use [M1-M48]. The reviews of substance-specific assessments depending on intended use will continue through one case study. The case study is described below and will evaluate differences and similarities, and subsequent implications, across legislations. The outcomes of this project may serve as a ground for adjustments of the relevant regulations. The identification of dissimilarities in testing requirements and hazard assessments of substances depending on specific uses will offer valuable information for the implementation and potential impacts of the “One Substance One Assessment” (OSOA) approach on regulations targeting specific uses of chemicals. Further, the potential barriers and opportunities, and available methods, for harmonisation in a systematic way will be presented. [Partners involved: SU (SE), UCL (UK), SCIENSANO (BE), IRFM (IT), KI (SE)].

- CS12_MethodOSOA_SU: We are currently discussing with PARC, JRC, ECHA and EFSA what the next study focus will be. We have had a meeting with PARC, JRC and ECHA and a meeting with EFSA is planned for. We have developed a number of suggestions, which they are considering. (SU (SE), KI (SE))
- CS13_PlasticizersRA_UCL: M1-M36 (finalised). (UCL (UK), SCIENSANO (BE), IRFM (IT)).
- CS14_BiocidesRA_SU: M1-M24 (finalised). (SU (SE), KI (SE)).

- P6.3.1.b_Y1_EffectRA_BPI [M1-M48]

Case studies reviewing effect-specific RA [M1-M48]. The reviews of effect-specific assessments will continue through six case studies. The case studies are described below and will include aspects such as sensitization and developmental neurotoxicity as well as use of non-animal methods for identification of endocrine disruption, genotoxicity, and carcinogenicity. The project will evaluate and suggest opportunities for improving and harmonising aspects of RA methodology, including *in vitro* short-term tests and structure-activity based methodologies. The project will analyse and discuss relevant gaps and research needs and, when relevant, propose improvements and harmonization of the testing requirements, criteria, recommendations, and best practices across EU regulations. The results will be made available to and discussed with regulatory agencies. These case studies reviewing RA methodology concerning specific priority endpoints will contribute to conclusions on the need for innovation in regulatory RA to rapidly and effectively identify chemicals with hazardous properties for human health and the environment through a more effective, accurate and harmonised across silos OSOA approach. [Partners involved: REGIONH (DK), STAMI (NO), SU (SE), IRFM (IT), UNIBAS (CH), VUB (BE), ISS (IT), NILU (NO), INSA (PT), BPI (EL), KI (SE), INSERM (FR), INERIS (FR), EAA (AT), UBA (DE), INRAE (FR), UT (EE)].

- CS9_SKINSENSIRISK_REGIONH: In Y4 the case study on successes and failures in RA of skin sensitizer will be completed. Results will be used for suggesting improvements in regulatory practices and highlight gaps of knowledge [REGIONH (DK), STAMI (NO), SU (SE), IRFM (IT), UNIBAS (CH)]. The results will be published in a peer-reviewed scientific journal and a report will be made. A Ph.D. thesis will be written and presented based on the entire project. (REGIONH (DK), STAMI (NO), SU (SE), IRFM (IT), UNIBAS (CH)).

- CS10_ED-cosmetics_VUB: In Y4 (until finalisation in M42), it is planned to finish the NGRA of octocrylene; run the 'ab initio' NGRA on systemic toxicity of the UV filter 4-methyl benzylidene campher and additionally, also perform a protective and predictive NGRA of the hair dye HCY13. When all dossiers are completed, a meeting is planned within the SCCS and with the PARC reviewers and a final report will be made available. Two publications are foreseen to be ready in that time period: one general article on the lessons learned with respect to the use of NGRA for systemic toxicity of cosmetic ingredients with ED concern and one on the specific topic of using NGRA to enrich standard safety assessment of cosmetic ingredients. (VUB (BE), INRAE (FR)).
- CS11_GenotoxCarc_ISS: In Y4 the following activities will be finalized: global report on the review and comparison of regulatory practices for genotoxicity and carcinogenicity classification and assessment [ISS (IT), IRFM (IT), NILU (NO), INSA (PT)]; inventory of NAMs for genotoxicity and carcinogenicity assessment [ISS (IT), IRFM (IT), NILU (NO), INSA (PT)], including analysis of their regulatory readiness [ISS (IT), IRFM (IT), NILU (NO), INSA (PT)] and evaluation of their possible use to fill existing gaps, reduce uncertainties and improve animal welfare [ISS (IT), IRFM (IT), NILU (NO), INSA (PT)]; evaluation of selected *in silico* methodologies for their potential use in identifying known human carcinogens (i.e., CLP/GHS class 1A) [ISS (IT), IRFM (IT)], including application of OECD QSAR Assessment Framework (QAF) to selected cases [ISS (IT), IRFM (IT)]; FAIR-compliant table mapping relevant documentation and literature [ISS (IT) and all]. The possibility of demonstrating potential gaps and inconsistencies within or across the various regulations using real cases will be explored and, if feasible, will be showcased [ISS (IT), IRFM (IT), NILU (NO), INSA (PT)].
- CS15_DNT_SU: Y4 will be devoted to the refinement of initial ideas and models for a graphical and statistical assessment of motor activity data from 54 guideline DNT study reports, for 53 compounds of which 51 are pesticide active substances and two other substances. For a graphical analysis, focus is on displaying data that allow an intuitive understanding of effects, on total motor activity or on the (ontogeny of) habituation, on both the population mean as well as on potentially sensitive subpopulations. Regarding statistical methods, we foresee that linear mixed-effects models will be the overall method of choice because these models accommodate the experimental design. The detailed structure of the models will be tested and discussed, and recommendations will be made. We will reach out primarily to EFSA to present and discuss our approaches at an early stage, and to be able to consider their needs and opinions. A scientific manuscript is expected to be submitted in M41. R code for performing graphical and statistical analyses will be made available, likely as supporting material to the open-access publication. Work on a second behavioural outcome, the auditory startle reflex, will be initiated with the extraction of data from the same 54 guideline DNT study reports. (SU (SE)).
- CS17_ED-in vitro_BPI: Y4 will be devoted to further development and implementation of reliability and relevance criteria for the evaluation of prioritised *in vitro* methods on estrogen, androgen, steroidogenesis, and thyroid (EATS) modalities on selected studies from the open literature. A manuscript will be submitted based on work completed in previous years and an additional manuscript will be prepared. This project has been extended and activities originally planned in Y3 will be implemented in Y4. (BPI (EL), KI (SE), INSERM (FR), INERIS

(FR), UBA (DE)).

- CS18_ED-classes_BPI: Y4 will be devoted to exploring how available *in vitro*, *in silico* and read-across approaches can be used for classification (or not) of a substance under the new CLP criteria for ED, through implementation of specific examples of regulated chemicals. The outcomes will contribute to the harmonized implementation of the new CLP criteria on hazard classes for ED taking into consideration all available methods and tools. A manuscript will be submitted based on work completed in previous years on T-modality and an additional manuscript will be prepared on EAS modalities. This project has been extended and activities originally planned in Y3 will be implemented in Y4. (BPI (EL), INSERM (FR), EAA (AT), IRFM (IT), VUB (BE), UT (EE)).

A6.3.2 Use of tools, criteria, and methods reviews

Details per project

- P6.3.2.a_Y1_ToolsRA_SU [M1-M48]

Case studies reviewing tools, criteria, and methods used in regulatory RA [M1-M48]. The reviews on the use of tools, criteria, and methods in regulatory RA will continue through six case studies. The case studies are described below and include general aspects such as application of risk-based benchmarks and uncertainty analysis as well as aspects related to occupational RA and Environment RA (ERA). The project can contribute to identification of coordination needs related to RA methodology across legislations, providing support for future design of legislation on chemical RA, focusing on sustainable management of chemical risks, as well as the implementation of the OSOA approach. The project will provide regulators, legislators, and other stakeholders an in-depth understanding of the commonly used decision benchmarks and the significance of their appropriate foundation and application. The project will provide new knowledge about the practical challenges in using quantitative expressions of uncertainty in assessment, as well as pedagogical examples on how to implement quantitative expressions of uncertainty and the benefit of these in assessment and communication. The project will provide recommendations for harmonizing data gap-filling approaches in relevant EU legislations. [Partners involved: SYKE (FI), ISSeP (BE), SU (SE), STAMI (NO), UBA (DE), JSI (SI), UCL (UK), TTL (FI), KI (SE), RSU (LV), INERIS (FR), KEMI (SE), ULUND (SE), BPI (EL), LSMU (LT), EAWAG (CH), FOEN (CH), DTU (DK), UCPH (DK), UMIL (IT), UNIPD (IT), EFSA (EU)].

- CS1_CARBSYKE: We intend to deepen our previous analysis of PFAS thresholds by evaluating the potential development needs of regulatory RA of PFAS and their implications to risk management, also considering additional regulatory frameworks and their interlinkages. This will be carried out through a literature study and stakeholder consultation. We intend to publish the results in a scientific paper. In addition, we aim at publishing a policy brief based on our results. (SYKE (FI), ISSeP (BE)).
- CS2_RiskReduction_SU: M1-M36 (finalised). (SU (SE), UBA (DE), STAMI (NO), UCL (UK), JSI (SI)).
- CS16_UncertaintyRA_ULUND: Collection of information on practical challenges through a questionnaire with follow up interviews will be finalised. We will make a policy brief

including justifications for expressing uncertainty quantitatively by % probability (or bounded probabilities) and how to manage uncertainty captured in scenarios or assumptions, as well as unknown unknowns. A list of examples of applications of uncertainty analysis has been created and will be expanded based on support from the community of experts. As an outreach activity and to support implementations of uncertainty analysis, sources introducing uncertainty will be listed in a publicly accessible group on PARCopedia with explanatory text and videos, together with guidance on how to express and combine quantitative expressions of uncertainty in combination with scenarios or worst-case assumptions. We will ask for and compile examples where uncertainty analysis done with quantitative expressions have been beneficial to an assessment. (ULUND (SE), KI (SE), BPI (EL), UBA (DE)).

- CS19_DataGapFilling_KEMI-DTU: M13-M30 (finalised). (DTU (DK), UCPH (DK), KEMI (SE), SU (SE)).
- CS7_REGPREP_EAWAG: During Y4 the results and insights of the analysis of the comparison of PPP RA under different regulations for surface water and sediment will be published. A similar comparison for soil RA will be started. (EAWAG (CH), FOEN (CH), INERIS (FR), UBA (DE)).
- CS20_PESTNAM_ISS: During Y4, a critical review of the actual implementation of NAMs within EFSA's evaluation of the approval of active substances in plant protection products in the area of human health and environmental hazard characterisation over the last 10 years will be performed and data gaps will be identified. The assessment will start with EFSA opinions, registration reports, Vol. 1 of the DAR (Addenda) and then focus on Vol. 3 for study description. The AOP concept, PBK modelling, mechanistic studies (human relevance for specific MoAs), the assessors'/EFSA's evaluation of the reliability and acceptance of the studies, as well as the type of data (OECD TG, not yet validated, literature data) and GLP status, will be included in the data extraction. All information/data will be correlated with the data requirements in force at the time of the assessment. Potential data gaps, including regulatory or knowledge gaps (missing relevant scientific information/data), will be identified. In this context, the project team consider key involving OECD, together with EFSA, as an advisory board to the project. (ISS (IT), UMIL (IT), UNIPD (IT), BPI (EL), EFSA (EU)).
- CS4_SecPoisoning_INERIS: The analysis of the main areas where harmonization is needed will continue, using examples and identifying the consequences of the lack of harmonization in the main legislations considered, i.e. chemical regulations which already have a clear framework for secondary poisoning assessment and the Water Framework Directive which also gives provisions for secondary poisoning. Further development and data collection for the substance imidacloprid, selected in collaboration with CS7, will be performed to test the hypothesis of borderline cases e.g. substances which do not meet persistent (P), bioaccumulative (B) and toxic (T) or POP criteria, but that may still cause a risk because highly exceeding one of the P or B criteria. Imidacloprid would qualify as sufficiently bioaccumulative for testing the hypothesis. The use of TK modelling to improve the definition of the trophic network, including apex species, will also continue. Stakeholder interactions will be further explored, including e.g. surveys, interviews or a dedicated workshop. (INERIS (FR)).

- CS8_ OccupReproDev_KI: Y4 will focus on compiling the findings of the OEL survey (published) and the partners substance-specific reviews into a final report. Based on a literature review the report will also contain a chapter that discusses the issue of threshold vs non-threshold reproductive effects. A review regulatory status of substances with a harmonised classification as reproductive toxicants (1A or 1B) will be used to suggest potential prioritisation lists for consideration for OEL-setting. (KI (SE), TTL (FI), LSMU (LT), STAMI (NO), RSU (LV)).
- CS3_WorkplaceRA_TTL: M1-M36 (finalised). (TTL (FI), KI (SE), JSI (SI), STAMI (NO), RSU (LV)).

Task 6.4: Transposing results to regulatory RA methodologies

- Co-leaders: AGES (AT), UNIBAS (CH)

Partners: ANSES (FR), INERIS (FR), OFB (FR), EAA (AT), AGES (AT), MU (CZ), AU (DK), REGIONH-GR (DK), UT (EE), EFSA (EU), SYKE (FI), Tukes (FI), UBA (DE), UFZ (DE), UDE⁸ (DE), Fraunhofer (DE), UCPH (DK) UI (IS), ISS (IT), IRFM (IT), LSMU (LT), VUA (NL), NIPH (NO), STAMI (NO), NIVA (NO), NIOM (PL), IEP-NRI (PL), UG-PL (PL), INSA (PT), ENSP (PT), UC (PT), UAVR (PT), ISCIII (ES), UCLM (SI), RWTH⁹ (DE), ULUND (SE), RISE (SE), KEMI (SE), SLU (SE), NLZOH (SI) AGROSCOPE (CH), EAWAG (CH), FOEN (CH), UNIBAS (CH), BUL (UK), UKCEH (UK), UOB (UK), EA (UK), UBATH (UK) BPI (EL), DTU (DK)

A6.4.1. Develop regulatory relevant approaches and methods for chemical mixtures

Details per project:

- P6.4.1.a_Y1_OPREMIXCS1_BRUNEL_RWTH[M1-M40]

The Project has been extended until M40. The remaining period will be used to finalize the AD.6.17 Optimizing regulatory RA including the use of monitoring data and NAMs and management of chemical mixtures in Europe and prepare publication of the conducted case studies. Additionally, a meeting with stakeholders is planned, where relevant outcomes from OPREMIX and MONAMMIX Projects will be shared. The organisation of this meeting starts in the end of Y3, the meeting will take place in Y4.

(Lead partner: RWTH, BUL, Participants: AGES, BPI, EAWAG, UBA, UI, NIVA, EA, ENSP, LSMU, NIOM, UAVR, KEMI, UKCEH, NLZOH).

⁸ AMD-101057014-118: Professor Dr Ralf Schäfer, who was involved in the activities of WP6, especially in Task 6.4 (P6.4.4.c_Y1, P6.4.4.d_Y1 and P6.4.4.e_Y1), for the German affiliated entity University of Kaiserslautern-Landau - PARC acronym "RPTU", left the University of Kaiserslautern-Landau and started working for the University of Duisburg-Essen in Germany - PARC acronym "UDE", on 01/07/2024. The amendment is a hand over of all the PARC activities performed by Ralf Schäfer at the University of Kaiserslautern-Landau to the University of Duisburg-Essen as of 01/07/2024

⁹ AMD-101057014-118: Professor Thomas Backhaus, who was the main scientific contact involved in the activities of PARC WP6 (P6.4.1.a_Y1_OPREMIXCS1_BRUNEL_UGot) for the Sweden affiliated entity University of Gothenburg - PARC acronym "UGot", left the University of Gothenburg and started working for the RWTH Aachen University in Germany - PARC acronym "RWTH", on 01/11/2023. Consequently, UGot withdrew from PARC on 01/11/2023 and RWTH entered in PARC as affiliated entity UBA on 01/11/2023.

- P6.4.1.b_Y1_MONAMMIXCS2_UFZ [M1-M40]

The project has been extended until M40. The remaining period will be used to finalize the AD6.17 Optimizing regulatory RA including the use of monitoring data and NAMs and management of chemical mixtures, which is part of the D6.18: Final report on RA and management methods for chemical mixtures across legislations (M81). Additionally, a meeting with stakeholders is planned, where relevant outcomes from OPREMIX and MONAMMIX Projects will be shared. The organisation of this meeting starts in the end of Y3, the meeting will take place in Y4. (Lead partner: UFZ, UBA Participants: AGES, BPI, UI, NLZOH, UKCEH, ENSP, UOB, NIVA, EA, EAWAG, UBATH).

- P6.4.1.c_Y3_Skinsenmix_RegionH [M24-72]

This project will develop new tools for RA and management of mixtures of skin sensitizers/irritants. In the second year of this project the main experiments will be initiated NAMS,3D skin cell models and in vivo/patient samples. A review of the literature regarding current knowledge and practices regarding assessment of mixture exposures for skin sensitizers will be initiated. It is foreseen to have 4 meetings, one every 3. months. For now, no changes in the budget are foreseen.

(Lead partner: RegionH-DK, STAMI, participants: UCPH, AGES)

- P6.4.1d_Y4_REMIX_UBA_EAWAG will be implemented in Y4 [M37-M81]

This project aims to improve the assessment, regulation and management of risks due to co-exposures and combined effects of multiple chemicals to the environment and human health across regulatory areas. A kick-off Workshop will be held in May 2025 (M1) where the results of the previous projects 6.4.1a_Y1_OPREMIX and 6.4.1.b_Y1_MONAMMIX will be discussed with the focus on identifying remaining open issues before the developed evidence, methods and tools can be used in regulation. In addition, regulators will be asked to communicate their current needs. Based on the workshop results followed by a landscaping exercise. The core regulatory areas of the project will be defined and specific project goals will be set. Further workshops may be organized on specific topics by the project partners.

Re-mix will be guided by a regulatory core group consisting of AGES, UBA and KEMI. The regulatory core group will foster the formation of individual case studies to address the specific project goals. Case studies will involve data analyses, comparisons of different methods as well as conceptual analyses and comparisons of different regulatory options and needs and will be performed by the project partners, starting from M1 to M40. A list of already identified case studies that will start or continue under REMIX can be found in the project description.

(Lead partners: UBA (DE), EAWAG (CH), Partners: AGES (AT), BPI (EL), UKCEH (UK), ENSP (PT), KEMI (SE), LMSU (LT), NILZOH (SI), NIOM (PL), NIVA (NO), UFZ (DE), UI (IS), RWTH (DE), UOB (UK), ULUND (SE), DTU (DK))

A6.4.2. Facilitate the regulatory acceptance and practical use of new methods

Details per project:

- P6.4.2.a_Y1_LandscapingSurv_UNIBAS [M1-M36] (finalised in M36)

- P6.4.2.b_Y1_NGRApractice_VKM_NIPH [M37-81]

This project aims to develop evidence-based tools and guidance for hazard/RA of NAMs, which will be integrated in an overall evidence-based NGRA framework across chemical sectors. The lead partner is NIPH (represented by VKM). The other partners involved in the work Y4 are BPI, ISS, and UNIBAS. The project has a scientific advisory group including 15 participants from the following institutions/organisations/projects: Karolinska Institutet, OECD, US EPA, CAAT at Johns Hopkins, EBTC at Johns Hopkins, Radboud University, EFSA, JRC, University of California San Francisco, 3Rs Management and Consulting, NIEHS, ECHA, Vrije Universiteit Brussel, University of New South Wales, and Charité – Universitätsmedizin Berlin_BIH QUEST Center, as well as observers from WP2 (BfR) and WP3 (AUTH).

As reported in the table 4 of AWPY4 (PARC_D1.10_AWPY4_including_Project_Portfolio.pdf), the project was originally developed for the whole 7-year PARC period. To be able to complete the different parts of the project, an extension was requested to be able to finalise the ongoing work in the best way. The budget included in the original 7-year proposal will remain the same.

Actions that will be performed year 4

- The tool for assessment of internal validity of in vitro studies: INVITES-IN

A beta version of INVITES-IN will be created in the ongoing project, and the user test will also be performed as part of the ongoing project. In the period M37-M48 the user test study will be completed, the data will be analysed, and the user test publication will be prepared and submitted. In addition, the beta version of the tool will be revised, and the release version will be published. A checklist containing an overview of issues that should be reported for in vitro studies to fulfil the information need to assess the internal validity will be prepared and published.

-The tool for the assessment of external validity of in vitro studies: INVITES-EX

The protocol for the creation of the tool for assessment of external validity will be prepared and submitted. The creation of the tool will be started when the protocol is accepted for publication.

-The cross-mapping of core systematic review and chemical RA terms

The study will be finalised, and the manuscript will be prepared and submitted. For all tasks that will be performed, the “VKM team” will perform the main work and draft the publications, plan all meetings, and also have separate meetings for the different tasks. BPI, ISS and UNIBAS participates active with ideas, suggestions, and discussions, and through reading and commenting on documents, and also critical review of publications.

Publications planned for 2025:

- Protocol for the creation of a tool for assessment of external validity (01.10.2025)

- The INVITES-IN tool: User test study (01.10.2025)
- The checklist for reporting of in vitro studies for internal validity assessment (01.10.2025)
- The release version of INVITES-IN (a tool for assessment of internal validity of in vitro studies) (01.10.2025)

The project team will continue having weekly meetings. The “VKM team” will have monthly meetings with the scientific advisory group.

- **P6.4.2.c_Y1_NAMAM_UT [M1-M36]**: this project was finalized in M36

- **P6.4.2.d_Y4_RegulatoryNAMs_ISS [M37-M81]**

This project aims to test and demonstrate how a NAM-based approach for regulatory hazard and RA of chemical substances may work and could be implemented in different regulatory frameworks and for several different regulatory purposes.

In the first phase of the project an overview of related scientific and regulatory initiatives and projects (within and outside PARC) will be created, and we will establish a common ground for the work through agreeing on terminology and methods to be used in a series of case studies. Following this, case studies addressing the aspects considered of highest priority will be developed and initiated. In the CSs different steps in hazard or RA for selected endpoints will be addressed using only information from NAMs; the outcomes in terms of predictive or protective capacity will be subsequently compared to traditional (mostly animal-based) assessments as currently performed under e.g. the CLP or PPP, or will highlight new grounds on which regulatory requests for different purposes (e.g. hazard identification) should be identified.

A regulatory core steering group will be established. The role of the core steering group is to e.g. coordinate the case studies, plan stakeholder interactions and engagement in order to ensure regulatory relevance of all case studies etc. ECHA and EFSA so far have expressed interest to participate in the core steering group.

Partners involved: KEMI (SE); RIVM (NL); ISS (IT); BPI (EL); UNIBAS (CH); MU (CZ); KI (SE); SCIENSANO (BE); STAMI (NO), IISPV (ES), IRFM (IT), KWR (NL), UL-LACDR (NL), SU (SE), TTL (FI)

- **P6.4.2.e_Y4_READYAI_UNIBAS [M37-M48]**

Establishment of readiness criteria for Artificial Intelligence/Machine Learning (AI/ML)-based tools for supporting the RA process.

This project addresses the challenges of using in silico NAMs based on ML/AI for regulatory purposes, focusing on RA and various applications like evidence management, toxicity prediction, and exposure assessment. AI/ML tools are advancing rapidly, but there's uncertainty about their reliability in chemical regulation. In a joint effort of AI tool developers together with regulatory scientists, the project aims to establish readiness criteria and a scoring system for in silico NAMs based on ML/AI, similar to those developed for in vitro methods, to help regulatory scientists gauge their reliability, validity, reproducibility and predictivity. The project will create a readiness check questionnaire for AI/ML tools, supporting regulations across sectors and nations.

The project will begin in the first year with the formation of a Core Steering Group, which will lead and oversee the initiative.

A series of project meetings will follow, including a face-to-face kick-off meeting as part of the PARC WP6 workshop in 2025. These meetings aim to foster a shared understanding among all participants, especially in terms of terminology, and to outline a detailed action plan for the project. Concurrently, there will be efforts to map related initiatives and projects, both within and outside the PARC framework, ensuring alignment and the leveraging of existing work.

A stakeholder meeting will be held, bringing together AI/ML tool developers and regulatory scientists to establish common ground for the project's objectives. During Y 4 case studies that evaluate specific AI/ML-based tools, analyzing their effectiveness and relevance will be developed and initiated. Regular meetings will be organized with stakeholders from both national and international agencies to assess whether the established criteria meet the needs of the regulatory community, ensuring that the outcomes of the project are practical and beneficial. Partners involved: UNIBAS (CH); UT (EE); UG-PL (PL); UoB (UK); IRFM (IT); possibly KEMI (SE); AGES (AT);

A6.4.3. Developing information transfer structures and enforcement methodology for chemicals in articles to support the transition to a circular economy

The activity has an overall objective to improve chemical RA and management by more efficient use of available information structures in combination with new analytical tools. A specific focus is placed on supporting enforcement of chemicals and product legislation and the use of chemical information structures in exposure assessment and evaluation of product circularity and sustainability is also explored.

Biweekly meetings with all partners will be held to monitor and discuss the progress of individual actions steering towards the overarching aim of A6.4.3. Focused working meetings will be held in between the biweekly meetings when needed. A connection with the forum for exchange of information on enforcement (ECHA forum) for enforcement has been established and the project will disseminate the results and continuously receive feed-back on the methods being developed under 6.4.3b. An internal PARC working group focusing on chemicals in products will be used to disseminate results and share data across different WPs. Dissemination will also occur via the agencies directly involved in the project (KEMI and TUKES).

Details per project:

- **P6.4.3.a_Y1_SuProM_MU [M1-M36]**: this project was finalised M36

- **P6.4.3.b_Y3_ENFORCE_KEMI [M25-M72]**

This project will be continued during Y4. The project will evaluate the applicability of methods of chemical identification for use in the enforcement of chemical safety legislation, to fulfil crucial needs identified in project 6.4.3a. For effective enforcement rapid screening methods that cover a wide

range of restricted/SVHC substances that can be applied to a variety of sample matrices are typically needed. In evaluating methods, this project will further test to what extent databases reviewed in P6.4.3.a capture the chemical composition of articles. By developing and applying rapid analytical techniques for screening and validation the project will provide a proof-of-concept methodology that could be used in enforcement of chemicals legislation. The project will have a specific focus on additives in high volume plastics and per- and polyfluoroalkyl substances in articles identified as major use categories. Progress in P6.4.3.b is continuously communicated with representatives from ECHA forum to ensure that the developed methods will be relevant for enforcement purposes.

Lead partner: KEMI, Participants include MU KEMI, RISE, TUKES, VUA, New partners in A6.4.3 SU and ORU.

Planned Y4 of PARC:

Key action 1. Based on the developed workflow and initial testing of articles and chemical products completed during Y3 a subset of 5-10 samples will be selected for a small inter laboratory comparison between RISE, SU and ÖRU. The data produced will be evaluated to determine the level of agreement between different laboratories and evaluate the readiness of the method. Together with the extensive testing of individual articles and products completed during Y3 the interlaboratory comparison will be used to assess the overall applicability of the proposed workflow for compliance testing of a broad PFAS restriction. The report delivered M54 will also provide recommendations for further validation and standardization that could be achieved by PARC to support the implementation of a broad PFAS restriction. Participants include KEMI, MU, RISE, TUKES, VUA, SU and ORU

Key action 2. Method development will be continued based on the initial testing of optimal extraction procedures completed during Y3. Focus during Y4 will primarily be on generating suspect target lists for different plastic materials/product categories from relevant databases and establishing quality assurance criteria that would make suspect screening applicable to enforcement. Participants include KEMI, RISE, TUKES, VUA, ORU

A6.4.4. RA to support and promote efficient overall protection of biodiversity

As reported in the table 4 of AWPY4 (PARC_D1.10_AWPY4_including_Project_Portfolio.pdf), the projects 6.4.4. a- e were originally planned to cover the entire length of the project, i.e. up to M81. This was due to the interdisciplinary nature of the research question and the involvement of multiple stakeholders. Working towards a paradigm shift necessitates a collaborative process in small steps. Projects a, c, d, e have been broken down at M42 to assess the project's progress as a basis for a decision to continue the projects until M81; similarly the project b has been broken up into 2 phases (i.e. a first phase was planned to end M24 but was extended until M36). The rationale for the extension of the projects is also available in the Annexes to the PDDs.

The extensions requested for the PARC P6.4.4 projects (a-e) are grounded in both the need to complete originally scoped activities and the significant achievements made until M 42 (or 26 for project 6.4.4.b). The projects aim to support a transition towards systems-based environmental risk

assessment (ERA), initially for plant protection products (PPPs), with a focus on enhancing ecological relevance, regulatory applicability, and operational efficiency.

Across the various projects, substantial progress has been made but limitations remain and most projects are midway through their conceptual-to-practical transitions, with key outputs—such as refined models, benchmarking databases, and case study results—still in development. The iterative stakeholder engagement central to these efforts requires more time to mature, especially given regulatory timelines and the complexity of integrating diverse type of information and data.

In a nutshell, achievements and ways forward are as follow:

- **Project 6.4.4.a** explored and developed new frameworks for risk characterization that support system-based approaches for the ERA of chemicals. PARC 6.4.4.a will continue to build collaborations, platforms, and engage stakeholders to ensure that projects “Design the right things” before “Design things right.” It will also pursue its role of coordination and umbrella project for the 4 research projects (b-e).
- **Project 6.4.4.b** conducted large-scale comparisons between predicted and measured environmental concentrations, showing that simpler exposure models can perform as well as complex ones, thereby supporting model streamlining. Extending the project duration will allow to facilitate the improvement of the scientific basis of ERA with the aim to streamline the approval process and provide the (exposure) building blocks for the prioritization process in the RA in the EU towards a systems-based ERA of PPP.
- **Project 6.4.4.c** advanced novel assessment tools such as the SPEAR and SAM models, which help isolate pesticide effects and predict multi-stressor impacts. These tools have been validated across diverse environments and shared with regulatory bodies. This project will continue to explore and develop new frameworks for risk characterization that support system-based approaches to RA by expanding the current ERA approaches. Continuous dialogue is needed from including regulatory risk assessors, and risk manager and eventually also policy makers.
- **Project 6.4.4.d** identified the ERA drivers of PPP rejection under EU regulation and proposed a conceptual benchmarking framework. It highlighted inconsistencies in higher-tier data and laid the groundwork for comparative risk assessments. The alignment with stakeholder activities coordinated by project 6.4.4.a and with other PARC projects will ensure regulatory relevance and uptake of the benchmarking results and novel methods.
- **Project 6.4.4.e** developed and published a comprehensive conceptual model for landscape-level ERA and initiated eight geographically and ecologically diverse case studies. Organised a series of field-based case-studies linked to the conceptual framework. Considering the achievements, it is proposed to continue with the implementation of the case studies and the integration of the information generated through the case studies, the interaction with the other projects and through the feedback from the publication.

In summary, the proposed extensions will enable: (1) finalisation and validation of tools and frameworks; (2) integration of exposure, effect, and benchmarking approaches; (3) alignment with evolving EU regulatory priorities; and (4) broader regulatory and stakeholder uptake. Coordinated timelines across all subprojects are essential to ensure coherence and to maximise impact across the ERA landscape.

In summary, the first three years have yielded solid scientific progress and stakeholder engagement. The extensions are necessary to transform this foundation into regulatory practice, fulfilling PARC's long-term objectives of efficient and ecologically grounded chemical risk assessment.

Details per project:

- P6.4.4.a_Y1_CRNCS1_KEMI [M1-M42]: this project has been extended from M42 to M81

Iterative and collaborative knowledge-building to Clarify Regulatory Needs (Project CRN)

An extension of the project has been proposed from M43 to continue the project throughout the lifetime of PARC as originally planned. The identified regulatory needs from AD 6.7, will guide the continued work of the projects in PARC 6.4.4 (6.4.4.a-e) and foster collaboration with external projects, including and beyond Horizon Europe projects SYBERAC and PollinERA.

Science-policy scoping surveys and workshops with stakeholders will be organised and used to further develop the interim report *Clarifying regulatory needs and preliminary recommendations for new ERA guidance documents* (M46). It will encompass a systems-based framework and methodologies to efficiently integrate data and expertise to address the key regulatory needs within a substance-by-substance framework as well as future more integrated assessments that address e.g. combined effects, spatio-temporal effects (landscape). The final results and conclusions of the project will be reported in D6.21 *Recommendations for new ERA guidance*.

PARC 6.4.4.a will continue to build collaborations, platforms, and engage stakeholders. The involvement of key stakeholders in problem formulation and reformulation follows the strategic recommendations for transition of the EFSA PERA Roadmap. PARC 6.4.4.a will seek to establish a dedicated dialogue-group on reducing unnecessary complexity in regulatory ERA involving key engaged stakeholders and external projects; it will do so in close cooperation with the other projects of PARC 6.4.4. Target stakeholders for engagement in this process will be key regulatory agencies at the national and EU levels, such as ECHA and EFSA.

Coordination and alignment will continue to be strengthened especially with PARC WP2 and WP3, e.g. through joint activities with partners from WP2 and WP6 connected to the transversal roles MLs for NG-ERA. Continued mapping of projects of relevance within PARC and external projects will thus be pursued during year 4 in order to establish new and deepen existing collaborations.

The CRN project will also continue to coordinate the four other projects in PARC A6.4.4 with regular coordination meetings with project leaders, Forum for Exchange meetings and an Activity 6.4.4 Workshop during year 4.

(Lead partners: KEMI and UBA; Participants: FOEN, EFSA, ANSES, UOS, ULUND, NIVA)

- P6.4.4.b_Y1_PPPEXPCS2_RPTU [M1-M36]: this project has been extended from M36 to M81

Informed by the insights from the previous work and results of the 6.4.4.b project and executive summary reports, our strategic aim has evolved to encompass the systems-based contextualization of measured and predicted environmental concentrations (MECs & PECs) within the ERA regulatory framework. The focus for years 4-7 is on bridging the gap between assumed, unknown real exposure concentrations (RECs) and both PECs and MECs, which is essential for a protective and expedient

plant protection product (PPP) ERA. Key components of this strategy are: (1) the evaluation of spatio-temporal exposure distributions (based on MECs) to improve the predictability of REC distributions for PPP in space and time, (2) identifying and closing knowledge gaps regarding PEC model scenarios taking into account the potential drivers for exposure for a variety of PPPs while evaluating exposure model complexity (parsimonious and landscape-level) under consideration of their sensitivity and protectiveness and (3) incorporating all findings, esp. the representativeness of PECs and key risk drivers for the distribution of PPP PECs into the regulatory context of the authorization of PPPs (EC 1107/2009), and (4) inform the development of the overarching deliverable D.21 *Recommendations for new ERA Guidance* on feasible level of detail in regulatory ERA.

The specific activities for year 4 will be defined in collaboration with targeted stakeholders to address questions and issues raised by engaged ERA experts from relevant national and EU agencies. These stakeholder activities (Survey and Workshops with regulatory risk assessors for Regulation EU (No) 1107/2009) are currently ongoing (Year 3) and led by project 6.4.4.a. The adaptive planning process in setting specific research question is an integral part of the coordinated approach of Activity 6.4.4 to ensure regulatory relevance of the deliverables. Year 4 will also follow-up on internally identified research questions; sensitivity analyses of model parameters, scenario-based identification of MEC datasets and inclusion of more substances in comparisons between PECs and MECs.

The overall aim in concordance with projects 6.4.4.a, 6.4.4.c, 6.4.4.d and 6.4.4.e is to strengthen the scientific basis of ERA, streamline the assessment or evaluation process by focussing ERA on key risk drivers and providing the building blocks for a feasible expansion of the scope of ERA to address biodiversity, as well as facilitate the prioritization of substances evaluations in EU plant protection product (PPP) within in the current regulatory framework.

Lead Partner: RPTU (DE)

Participants: SLU (SE), Fraunhofer IME (DE), EAWAG (CH), NIVA (NO), ULUND (SE), IEP-NRI (PL), UoB (UK). Regulatory core group: KEMI (SE), UBA (DE), FOEN (CH), ANSES (FR), EFSA (EU.)

- P6.4.4.c_Y1_PPPEFFCS3_UFZ [M1-M36]: this project has been extended from M36 to M81

An extension of the project has been proposed to continue the project throughout the lifetime of PARC as originally planned. This project aims to contribute towards a more protective and streamlined assessment process linking with the other projects especially in P6.4.4.

Phase 1 identified relevant mechanisms and processes through ecosystem monitoring and effect modelling, enabling a field validated extrapolation of laboratory to ecosystem effects.

Phase 2 focuses on developing a revised RA framework by: (i) assessing especially insecticide effects as model compounds in EU freshwaters using the SPEARpesticides indicator, (ii) conducting multi-stress RA with the Stress Addition Model (SAM) and extending this from aquatic to terrestrial ecosystem, (iii) creating the basis for a streamlined adaptation-based RA linking sub-organismic, NAMs and standard test systems to communities at the ecosystem level. This framework is being adapted, tested and made available to the regulatory authorities for optimised, validated and

reproducible ERA. The initial aquatic focus will be extended to terrestrial effect assessment using comparable approaches and link to relevant EU projects such as SYBERAC. (Lead partner: UFZ Participants: UC (PT), EAWAG (CH), SLU (SE); UDE (DE); ULUND (SE), NIVA (NO), UCLM (ES), UOS (DE), ISCIII (ES), Regulatory core team: KEMI (SE), UBA (DE), FOEN (CH), EFSA (EU), ANSES (FR), UKCEH (UK).

- P6.4.4.d_Y4_PPPBENCHCS4_UDE [M1-M42]: this project has been extended from M42 to M81

The results of the Y1-3 will include the compilation of a database for comparable risk quotients (RQs) of authorised and non-authorised PPPs and three papers that provide the conceptual foundation of benchmarking and empirical results on the internal benchmarking exercise regarding the comparison of tiers and areas of risk. Moreover, substance toxicity and physicochemical data from the current ERA regulatory process have been compiled, and use data for exposure calculations has been retrieved from the EFSA Conclusion with additional support from other national pesticide registries in different member states. Based on these data, alternative ways to conduct comparable ERAs is currently being tested for the prospective data for internal benchmarking, which will be completed by Y4. In Y4, the outcome will be benchmarked to monitoring and field data in collaboration with projects 6.4.4.b, 6.4.4.c and 6.4.4.e. Prototype comparative databases for external benchmarking will be used as templates for further development. In detail, The RQs will be calculated from measured pesticide concentrations in environmental compartments (water and soil) and any observed biological effects on non-target organisms. Comparison between prospective and monitoring RQs will aid in choosing appropriate benchmarks for evaluating ERA accuracy. Established benchmarks for acceptable deviation levels between ERA and monitored data will identify pesticides where significant discrepancies exist and provide recommendations for further regulatory review. (Lead partner: UDE, Participants: UFZ, ISCIII, NIVA, EAWAG and ULUND). Regulatory core team: KEMI (SE), UBA (DE), FOEN (CH), ANSES (FR), EFSA (EU))

- P6.4.4.e_Y3_PPPOCS5_ISCIII [M1-M42]: this project has been extended from M42 to M81

An extension of the project has been proposed from M43 to continue the project throughout the lifetime of PARC as originally planned. Following the publication of the Landscape conceptual model, the focus will be on continuing the implementation of the eight selected case studies, covering the terrestrial and aquatic compartments, to test different options and tools for landscape ERA. During this period, each case study will also start the interaction with the local stakeholders. In addition, a new partner AGS, will conduct a review on the mitigation of pesticide risk associated to ecological infrastructures. The annual activities will also include the evaluation of the feedback received from the Landscape conceptual model and the interaction with the other 6.4.4. projects and the relevant EFSA and EU projects selected in coordination with the regulatory core team. (Lead partner: ISCIII Participants: UFZ (DE), UDE (DE), NIVA (NO), IEP-NRI (PL), OFB (FR), UCLM (ES), ULUND (SE), Uni Osnabrück UOS (DE), UOB (UK), UKCEH (UK), EA (UK), UAVR (PT), SYKE (FI), INERIS (FR), UC (PT), EAWAG (CH), AGS (CH). Regulatory core team: KEMI (SE), UBA (DE), FOEN (CH), ANSES (FR), EFSA (EU))

Deliverables:

D6.5 1st Report on IATAs and associated case studies – Leader: Sciensano (M42)

D6.6 1st Report on conclusions from case studies reviewing RA methodologies – Leader: KEMI (M42)

Additional Deliverables

AD6.17 Optimizing regulatory risk assessment and management of chemical mixtures in Europe (P6.4.1.a_Y1_OPREMIXCS1_BRUNEL_RWTH and P6.4.1.b_Y1_MONAMMIXCS2_UFZ, initially planned M36 but postponed to M40) - Leader: RWTH (M36 postponed to M40)

WP N°	WP7														Lead Beneficiary				VITO/UOB																																		
WP title	FAIR Data																																																				
Partner N°	1		1.1		1.6		1.10		4		4.7		6.1		8		9		15		15.2		24.3		25.1		25.2		25.4		25.7		26		26.4		27.2		31		32		34.5		35.2		35.12		36		49		59
Partner short name	ANSES		INSERM		INRS		BRGM		VITO		ISSeP		IMROH		MU		UZIS		UBA		UFZ		UnilLU		KWR		TNO		UL-LACDR		WR		NIPH		NIVA		UG-PL		JSI		NIJZ		IIPV		KI		UU		AUTH		EFSA		UOB
PM/partner	29.7		3.1		2.0		2.5		53.4		6.4		2.0		76.9		0.6		3.3		1.0		2.0		1.1		4.1		27.4		1.3		2.0		3.9		12.6		25.6		6.0		24.0		0.5		8.2		4.0		2.0		5.0
Start	M37														End				M48																																		

Objectives

The main goal of WP7 is to support innovation and transparency in CRA through improved exchange and re-use of data between different RA actors and disciplines, and through innovative data analytical approaches. The specific objectives of WP7 for year 4 are:

- Task 7.1:
 - Updating the PARC-level DMP with reference to clusters of project-level DMPs, using the selected online DMP tool (DSW) as well as the (preferred) choices defined by the domain specific FAIR Implementation Profiles (FIPs).
 - Enable the FIPs to DMP implementation (toxicology, HBM, environmental), training of the data liaisons for further assistance to the projects for finalisation of the project-level DMPs.
 - Finalisation of white paper on PARC FAIR ambitions and implementation roadmap reflecting the choices made to date and the tools developed in PARC or elsewhere to support domain-specific implementation
 - “Training through doing” for Data Champions, Liaisons and FAIR Implementation Taskgroup (FIT) on use of online DMP tooling and FAIRification (FIP/M4M) to ensure collection of project-specific DMPs, to build the PARC domain-specific and cross-domain tools to enable FAIR metadata and data. Prioritized areas for Y4 are toxicology and biostudies/ assays, HBM and environmental data, as well as extension to cross-domain topics such as RA and

hydrological modelling for early warning systems.

- Development of governance structures for all of PARC WP7 outputs and outcomes, including addressing short-term needs such as FIP to DMP and PARC FAIR data policy (PFDP), vocabularies, and longer-term issues relating to sustainability, legacy etc.
- Task 7.2:
- Continued development of the FAIR PARC data hub, including complete documentation of all tools and workflows involved, and expanding it with new functionalities such as visualisation of protocols metadata linked to datasets
 - FAIR Steering and Implementation Teams: Continued identification and implementation of prioritised use cases
 - Semantic Implementation Team: Continued implementation of controlled vocabularies at PARC level, as well as domain-specific standards
 - Implementation of cross-domain interoperability framework for CRA
 - Orchestration of FAIR Resources, such as operational publishing of vocabularies and automated integration of unique identifiers into PARC FAIR data flows.
 - Design and implementation of an automated approach to FAIR Data integration between data and models; on specific models (e.g. in the exposure or PBPk projects), supporting the coupling of data and models in the PARC Integrated Model Network, and also as a practical implementation on a cross-domain project such as the Early Warning Systems Framework.
- Task 7.3:
- Progressing implementation of identified uncertainty and data analysis use cases and ongoing identification of new use cases.
 - Continued development of user guidelines for different statistical analytical (meta-, pooled etc.) techniques and demonstration of the utility and feasibility of different approaches via the selected use cases.
 - Gap analysis of uncertainty assessment methodologies and demonstration of the process with domain specific uses cases.
 - Development of a harmonised FAIR evidence representation framework for computed entity associations (FAIR AOP data template)
 - Building a consistent data exchange schema according to the FAIR principles to integrate and assemble information from wider sources.
 - Harmonising use of existing and new ontologies (starting AOP ontology development) in text mining for AOP development. Scoping, gap analysis and initial benchmarking of data / knowledge mining and AI/ML tools.
 - Enriching existing background knowledge resources for chemical RA through multi-modal data analysis.

The activities planned for Y4 in WP7 are summarized schematically in Figure 1.

Task 7.1 - Data policy and implementation	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Governance of all WP7 outputs (data, tools, Access etc.) ➤ Data Management Plan (DMP) – updating and implementing for new projects <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ FAIR PARC protocols ➤ Updating of PARC Data Policy and PARC-level DMP (interim version) 	
<p style="text-align: center;">Task 7.2 – Data Libraries</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Environmental Data Project <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • PFAS in the environment • Non-target screening ➤ HBM Data Project <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • HBM survey, monitoring and occupational hazards • Guidance Values / HBM Data Analysis ➤ Toxicology Cluster <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Regulatory / NAMs, AOPs, • Omics / Image data ➤ PARC Data Hub <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Metadata services & registry • CRA Dashboards • FAIR tools implementation, including Protocols.io ➤ Cross-domain implementation case studies <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Early warning system • Bioassays for water quality monitoring ➤ FAIR implementation / Semantic implementation 	<p style="text-align: center;">Task 7.3 - Innovative analyses</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Heterogeneous data integration: use cases <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Metabolomics data from multiple cohorts • Real-life mixtures • Multi-omics integration (protein, gene, metabolite) • Environmental exposures and effects • Phenotypic enrichment via text mining ➤ Uncertainty characterisation: use cases <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Physiologically based kinetic (PBK) models • Bioassay response to risk uncertainty • Cell painting and conformal prediction for hazard • Benchmark dose (BMD) modeling ➤ Novel computational methods: use cases <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Pipeline for text mining integration for FAIR AOPs • Gene expression pathway analysis via ontology ➤ Horizon-scanning for innovative approaches <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Pharmacophore modelling - Blood Brain Barrier permeation • Scoping study of computational NAMs for use in NGRA • AI-based prediction of Biochemical Parameters • Read-Across Through Transcriptomics Data

Figure 1: High level summary of the activities planned within each of the Tasks of WP7 during Y4. The case studies in Task 7.3 are linked to the Toxicology Cluster and the Environment and HBM Projects (and their follow-up activities) and thus there is strong integration across the Data and Tools / Analyses aspects.

Description of Programmed Activities

Task 7.1: FAIR Data policy and implementation

Co-leaders: TNO (NL), UOB (UK)

Partners: ANSES (FR), BRGM (FR), VITO (BE), MU(CZ), UZIS (CZ), UBA (DE), ISS (IT), KWR (NL), UL-LACDR (NL), NIVA (N), UG-PL (PL), JSI (SI), KI (SE), AUTH (EL), ISSEP (BE)

Sub-contractors: GFF (NL)

No project submitted for this task.

A7.1.1 PARC Data Policy and Data Management Plan

The first version of the PFDP was finalized (M18), although some key issues need further elaboration, including the detailed analysis of the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC) FAIR data levels, and how achievable these are for the different sub-domains of PARC. In Y3, the PFDP has been formatted into a scientific paper, which will be submitted by the end of 2024. Additional possible future content relevant to the PFDP has been proposed in the publication using Large Language Models and a semi-quantitative analysis of the relevance of the different PFDP topics for different stakeholders was executed. [Partners involved: KI, UBA, KWR, UoB, VITO, TNO, NIVA]. It is foreseen that in Y4, the publication may require some additional effort, once reviewed by the journal.

In collaboration with WP2 (PARCopedia) the PARC WP7 Glossary of key terms will be further updated as the various WP7 use cases produce formalised vocabularies. This, to ensure that the

various A-Zs presented in PARCopedia are fully consistent and aligned with these community developed standards that are agreed with the domain experts from across PARC WPs 4-8 and formalised via the controlled vocabularies. [Partners involved: UoB, KWR, MU].

An ongoing activity throughout Y4 will be implementation of the project-level DMPs. The initial data management sections of the PARC project proposals and implementation plans (developed in Y2) will be further elaborated, documented via the selected online DMP tool (DSW), into the final project DMPs, summarising how data have been managed, stored, archived and made FAIR. The further development of a FIP e.g., as foreseen for toxicology in Y4, will be helpful as it enables the immediate annotation of metadata etc. in the DMP. Further, the implementation of RAiDs (research activity identifier) and Protocols.IO (Protocols.io is “a secure open access platform for developing and sharing reproducible methods. Users can create, publish, and read public protocols” (<https://www.protocols.io/>)) and associated protocol identifiers into this environment will help the findability and foster the machine readable and actionability of completed PARC DMPs (on top of the metadata and identifier derived from DSW). The PARC protocols will also be integrated into the overall PARC exit strategy discussions.

The WP7 data liaisons (see also T7.2) will support the responsible partners in the projects from the R&I WPs (e.g., represented by the Data Champion) to fill in the project specific DMPs (after training) [Partners involved: VITO, UOB, MU, UG-PL, UL-LACDR, IISPV, AUTH, TNO, ISSEP, UFZ, KI, UBA, JSI]. This work will directly feed into starting with updating and reviewing the overarching DMP (1st review of the Data Management Plan, due M42) [Partners involved: TNO, ANSES, VITO, UBA, UL-LACDR, MU, ISS].

The process for monitoring of the KPI on the number of datasets FAIRified will be extended as outlined in D1.3. The approaches for tracking dataset re-use will be elaborated to support monitoring of the outcomes and impacts of the PARC FAIR efforts and the PARC Data Hub.

A governance structure will be defined and implemented focussing on immediate needs and decision processes and longer-term aspects of PARC FAIR tools, resources and outputs (e.g., PARC Data Hub) sustainability, cross-domain interoperability and legacy. The governance processes will also require inputs from other WPs and the PARC coordination team, and some external organisations (such as the GFF and CoDATA representing the International Science Council who are leading the development of the Cross-Domain Implementation Framework - CDIF) as some of the decisions will have implications beyond WP7. The scope, remit and operating principles for the PARC Governance of FAIR will be elaborated and refined.

A7.1.2 Communication and Training: organisation and delivery across PARC¹⁰

The dedicated training programme has been completed in Y2, led by GFF, resulting in a set of trained Data Liaisons and FAIR implementation Task group, which has led to a set of facilitators and trainers able to deliver additional training in FIP, and Metadata 4 Machines (M4M). In Y4, the participants will further develop the domain-specific FIPs for PARC, in particular on toxicology, as well as develop

¹⁰ The name of the activity was modified compared to AWPY2. The previous name in AWPY2 was: Training and organisation

tools and solutions to support the implementation of FAIR in PARC. [Partners involved: ISSeP, UL-LACDR, MU, TNO, UoB with support of GFF].

The FAIR Implementation Team (see also T7.2) has implemented a process for finalising documentation and deployment (roll-out) of the tools and approaches to increase data management efficiency and facilitate data use and re-use within PARC and beyond. As tools / approaches are finalised and documented, including with WP-specific training materials, these will be rolled out to WPs / project clusters via hands-on training sessions tailored to the needs of the individual WPs / project clusters, on a rolling basis. Deployed and documented tools will also be discussed with WP2 for integration into PARCopedia, with WP8 for integration into the SSbD Toolbox and the EWS, with WP9 for integration into the PARC-wide training activities and inventories, and WP3 for communication and dissemination beyond PARC. [Partners involved, PL-UG, ISS, MU, UoB].

A7.1.3 FAIR Data Use Case Coordination

For increased consistency and follow up this activity has been integrated into activity 7.2.3.

Task 7.2: Data libraries

Co-Leaders: MU (CZ), VITO (BE)

Partners: ANSES (FR), AUTH (EL), BRGM (FR), EFSA (EU), EV-ILVO (BE), IISPV (ES), ISS (IT), ISSeP (BE), JSI (SI), KI (SE), MU (CZ), NIVA (NO), TNO(NL), UFZ (DE), UG-PL (PL), UBA (DE), UL-LACDR (NL), UNILU (LU), UOB (UK), UU (SE), UZIS (CZ), KWR (NL), WR (NL)

Sub-contractors: GFF (NL) and CoDATA (FR)

For Task 7.2 two projects were submitted in Y1. These projects encompass a broad and integrated approach towards two specific *a priori* identified domains and cut across the different activities defined under 7.2. Additional to these projects, use cases, where possible clustered for specific domains, are identified through the established horizontal links between WP7 and R&I WPs and projects, and are added on a rolling basis. Therefore, no additional project has been defined. Actions related to these additional use cases and clusters identified in Y2 and Y3 are added under the respective activities A7.2.1 to A7.2.4 as transversal activities.

Details per project

- P7.2.2.a_Y1_chemicals-in-environment_MU_VITO [M1-M42] (the project has been extended from M36 to M42)

[Participants: MU, VITO, UFZ, BRGM, UniLU, ISSEP, JSI, ANSES, NIVA, UBA, KWR, AUTH]. The project is linked to activities under 4.2 (multiple exposure monitoring, PFAS baseline use case and ECDs) and specific activities under 6.4 such as the collection of existing exposure monitoring data on pesticides and chemicals in the articles and environment, and to some extent with A7.2.1 (the environmental component of the CRA landscaping).

A 6-months extension (end date shifted from M36 to M42) of the project and related activities have been requested to allow for sufficient discussions with domain experts, feedback from stakeholders, and adequate time to finalize the project reports. In the project, the environmental (FAIR) data landscape has been mapped by identification of major databases, data platforms and FAIR enabling

and supporting resources used by the community. As part of the mapping activity, FAIR implementation profiles (FIP) of the major resources have been prepared and will serve as a basis for future development of reference FIP. Gaps have been identified and consequently, workshops with WP7 data experts and domain experts from R&I WPs were organized to develop metadata schema for (meta)data concerning occurrence of chemicals in the outdoor environment. The schema has been developed and it is currently under review by domain experts. The blue print of the dashboard for environmental data (the environmental component of PARC Data Hub) has been prepared and it is further refined.

In Y4, metadata schema for data concerning chemical occurrence in the outdoor and indoor environment, and in consumer products will be discussed and further developed.

Two project reports will be finalized: i) R-ENVIROdata.1: The level of FAIRness of the existing major data resources on chemicals in the environment; and ii) R-ENVIROdata.2: FAIR solutions to manage newly generated environmental data. The first report will describe the (PARC) environmental data landscape, including major databases and platforms, and their FIPs, as well as other existing FAIR enabling and supporting resources relevant for chemical occurrence data and PARC, identified gaps, resources developed in PARC, and how will these be integrated in the environmental component of PARC Data Hub. The second report will present solutions identified or developed during the project towards FAIR management of environmental (chemical occurrence) data.

There will still be a need to provide support and develop solutions for FAIR management of chemical occurrence data in PARC after the project ends. Therefore, in Y4, an “environmental cluster” will be established as a set of transversal activities and will involve data experts from WP7, as well as domain experts from R&I WPs. The cluster will further develop FAIR enabling and supporting resources, and identify and manage use cases according to the needs of the PARC community. It will also contribute to further iterations of the development of PARC Data Hub, and integration with IPCHEM and COPCSD.

- P7.2.2.b_Y1_HBMdatasets_VITO [M1-M48] (the project has been extended from M42 to M48)

[Participants: VITO, MU, UBA, ISSeP, JSI, WR]

Reason for extension: Due to reorganization of the project team at VITO (new project leader, people leaving and newly hired in the team), an extension of 6 months was requested for the P7.2.2.b_Y1_HBMdatasets_VITO project (from M42 to M48).

Results achieved so far: Maintenance and improvement PEH Data Platform, development of tools for harmonisation and data validation, calculation of derived variables and summary statistics. Report on HBM data landscape and report on assessment of federated systems for privacy-preserving analysis. Finalisation of defining content for HBM metadata. Finalisation of the conceptual part of the HBM ontology work, first validated versions of vocabularies and a consolidated PARC biomarker list.

Plans year 4: The WP7 HBM datasets project will build on the Y1-Y3 selection of relevant HBM datasets and linked communities, and the roadmap for FAIRification that has been developed (see table 1.4). Projects that will use these datasets include different 4.1.1 activities (HBM survey,

monitoring and occupational hazards), Activity 4.1.3 (Guidance Values) and Activity 4.1.4 (HBM Data Analysis) in WP4, several WP6 projects (A6.2.3 -real life mixtures- and A6.4.1 -regulatory RA-) and the T8.2 (EWS) and T8.3 (integrative modelling network) Tasks in WP8. Online project meetings will be organised to fit the needs of the project.

Table 14: Planned actions for P7.7.2.b in Y4

Parts (Schedule)	Actions	Participant Institution(s) (Country)
1. Transfer HBM4EU to PARC (M1 to M42)	Operation of PEH data platform	VITO
2. Use case management (M1 to M48)	Use case working group	VITO, MU, UBA, ISSEP, JSI, WR
	Collaboration/exchange with IPCHEM	VITO
	Collaboration with other related data initiatives	VITO, MU
3. Implementation and testing (M18 to M48)	<p>Implement use of data model, metadata schema and ontology</p> <p>Set up HBM data platform and services, integrating tools and pipelines for harmonization, processing and quality control of existing and newly generated datasets;</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> 7. integration of the HBM (meta)data model in a more generic catalogues of variables 8. creation of interoperable data packages 9. Smart data aggregation and extraction 10. Automated semantic annotation 11. integration with models (WP8) 12. pipeline for sharing of data with IPCHEM (and, in future, the EEA) 13. connection to geospatial data 14. connection to environmental data 15. HBM dashboard 	VITO, MU, ISSEP, JSI, WR, UBA

As mentioned, *domain-specific clusters* have been identified in Y2 and Y3, among which data management activities on toxicology data and bioassay data, and integration of cross-domain aspects such as hydrological modelling of pollutant mobilisation of the EWS of WP8. Activities on toxicology data (e.g. the implementation of a toxicology specific FIP, formalisation of the Toxicology vocabulary and ontology, toxicology metadata standards, documentation of biological organisms (BIODA) will be further coordinated by UoB, with support from BfR (WP5) UL-LACDR TNO, and MU. Work plans drafted and embarked upon in Y2 and Y3, will flow further into Y4.

Additionally, a need to establish a cross-domain cluster for NTS data has been identified, and this will be started in Y4. This activity will be coordinated by MU, with support of other partners from WP4 and will span the Toxicity and Environment Cluster activities. The work plans will be further discussed, also based on the inventory of resources and community needs carried out by WP9.

A7.2.1 Mapping the PARC Data Landscape

[Lead: MU, Partners involved: UOB, ISS, ISSEP, UL-LACDR, UNILU, ANSES, VITO, NIVA]

A7.2.1 Identifies existing databases or repositories that may be appropriate to store newly generated data for the different CRA domains. This activity is in close collaboration with WP9, where WP7 is focused mainly on the assessment of FAIRness and sustainability, and support in FAIR management of inventories (see A7.2.2) carried out by WP9 with support of WP7, or other R&I WPs in collaboration with WP9.

The landscape will be enriched further with newly identified resources resulting from specific clusters and use cases. In Y4, a major focus will include detailed assessment of the PARC data landscape for Regulatory Toxicology, Omics (sequencing data, MS NTS data, phenomics), NAMs, Mixture Toxicology and RA Modelling. [Partners involved: UoB, ISS, UL-LACDR, ANSES, MU, VITO, NIVA]. Also, the focus will be on mapping the cross-domain NTS data landscape and identifying community needs and gaps in available solutions [MU, partners from WP4].

The FAIRness of the prioritised databases/repositories' systems, standards, and methods of operations will be assessed following application of the 'as is' FIPs developed by the FAIR Implementation Team (who were trained in Activity 7.1.2). [Partners involved: UOB, ISSeP, UniLU, UL-LACDR, ANSES, MU]. Their sustainability will be assessed as well.

In parallel, the activities at the EC level related to the Common Platform for Data on Chemicals (CPDC) roadmap and implementation, will be further followed up and the proposed approaches followed to ensure the coherence of actions in the common European open data space. [Partners involved: MU, VITO, UFZ, UoB, UniLU, ANSES].

A7.2.2 PARC FAIR data hub

[Lead: MU/VITO, Partners involved: UOB, BRGM, UFZ, WR, ISS, JSI, ISSEP, NIVA, UL-LACDR]

Metadata Service – Data Catalogue of the Data Hub [Lead: MU/VITO, Partners involved: UFZ, UoB, WR, ISS, JSI]

The data catalogue module of the Data Hub will be further enhanced. We must improve the server infrastructure to make it a production-grade metadata catalogue deployment (using the open source CKAN data management software -<https://ckan.org/>). This will involve the second iteration of

server infrastructure to support larger volumes of dataset records and manage rich metadata descriptors. Optimization efforts will focus on complex search functionality to ensure that rich metadata descriptors do not hinder performance. Filtering criteria will also be customized to include both general filters and data type/domain-specific filters.

Additionally, the metadata ingestion user interface will be further optimized to improve user-friendliness. The focus will be on ingesting datasets related to the outdoor environment, HBM indoor environments, toxicology, and consumer products. New metadata standards will also be adopted to ensure the platform stays current with regulatory and research needs.

We expect the need to curate the content of the data catalogue to access individual domains and provide examples of good data management practices.

Work related to progressively include the inventories on existing datasets and databases taking place in R&I WPs and in WP9.

Chemical RA Dashboards [Partners involved: MU, VITO UFZ, UoB, WR, ISS, JSI]

According to feedback, the existing chemical RA dashboards will receive minor updates to improve their usability and functionality. Meanwhile, new dashboards will be developed in collaboration with the key WPs:

- A models' dashboard will be developed in collaboration with WP8.
- A dashboard focused on the indoor environment will be developed with WP9 and WP6.
- A consumer products dashboard will also be created in collaboration with WP9 and WP6.

To further support data and information exchange across the PARC project, the Data Hub will enable better integration with other WPs, notably WP2, WP8, and WP9. Based on inputs from WP9, the Data Hub will also host the results of their landscaping activities.

A FAIRification toolbox component will be developed to provide the necessary tools for data providers to increase the FAIRness of their data (see 7.2.3). A tool/module to visualise FAIRness of datasets or underlying resources will be further developed. Conversion tools for interfacing towards established regulatory platforms (i.e., the CPDC, including ECHA, EFSA, EEA databases and IPCHEM) and other established domain-specific and national/local data platforms will be integrated. [Partners involved: VITO, MU, UoB, BRGM, ISSEP, NIVA, UL-LACDR].

Development of FAIR Tools [Partners involved: MU, VITO, UoB, JSI].

We plan to focus on the development of several tools aimed at enhancing the FAIRness of the data managed within the PARC Data Hub:

- Metadata template generators will be built based on existing metadata schemas, vocabularies, and codebooks, allowing for the standardization of metadata creation.
- Data and metadata validators will be implemented to ensure data integrity and compliance with FAIR standards.
- Development and customization of SKOS vocabularies will be a priority. SKOS (Simple Knowledge Organization System) is W3C (World Wide Web Consortium) recommended standard for describing controlled vocabularies (<https://www.w3.org/TR/skos-reference/>). This will include tools for reference resolution and the automatic assignment of Global Unique Persistence Resolvable Identifiers (GUPRIs), ensuring that all terms are uniquely identifiable and resolvable across systems.

- Tools for data and metadata enrichment.
- Additional tools will be developed to support the smooth adoption of both semantic and technical standards, facilitating broader data FAIRification efforts.

Collaboration with IPCHEM and EU-Level Agencies [Partners involved: MU, VITO, UoB].

Collaboration with IPCHEM and other EU-level agencies will continue to be a priority. Ongoing meetings with the IPCHEM team will help ensure alignment with EU initiatives and maintain progress on metadata standards. Additionally, the team will actively follow and contribute to the development of emerging metadata standards, ensuring that the PARC Data Hub remains compliant and interoperable with regulatory frameworks across Europe.

Feedback will be collected from the various types of data hub stakeholders to ensure a positive evolution in terms of meeting users' requirements, alignment with the wider landscape and useability. [Partners involved: MU, UoB].

The development of the Data Hub will be in close collaboration and feedback of both WP7 projects P7.2.2.a_Y1_chemicals-in-environment_MU_VITO, and P7.2.2.b_Y1_HBMdatasets_VITO and newly created clusters (toxicology, environment, other).

A7.2.3 Solutions for FAIR data: development and implementation

(For increased consistency in resource allocation and follow up, Task 7.1.3 has been integrated here from Y3 onwards)

[Lead: VITO, Partners involved: MU, AUTH, GU-PL, IISPV, ISS, ISSeP, JSI, TNO, UBA, UL-LACDR, UOB, WR, NIVA, EV-ILVO, UG-PL, UFZ]

Use case and cluster identification [Partners involved: VITO, MU, AUTH, GU-PL, IISPV, ISSeP, JSI, TNO, UBA, UL-LACDR, UOB, WR, NIVA, EV-ILVO] The communication channels and decision structures are now in place for WP7 to be made aware of the needs of PARC projects and regulatory stakeholders and be able to prioritise them into priority data domains (clusters) or use cases. Several of these have been identified, represent ongoing work and are mentioned in other sections of this document, others are in the process of being integrated in one of the FAIR or Semantic teams. This process of identification, triage and selection will continue in Y4. The Data Liaisons have also started an awareness initiative in Y3 on FAIR data and good Research Data Management that will possibly bring more use case candidates to the surface.

Development and implementation of solutions Bottlenecks for data reuse and synergies with existing data platforms have been identified. FAIR Implementation Profiles and associated roadmaps and machine-actionable metadata have been or are being developed in close collaboration between domain experts from the R&I WPs, WP7 Data Liaisons and the FAIR Implementation Team in use case or cluster-based working groups (facilitated by the Facilitators and Trainers who have been trained and certified as part of T7.1.2 by the Go FAIR Foundation, and who constitute the FAIR Implementation Team). In Y4 this will be further developed for toxicology and bioassays

A FAIRification methodology was developed that builds upon and goes beyond the GFF Three-Point FAIRification Framework (3PFF) and this is now being implemented as both a technical data structure and a set of tools to facilitate interaction with the data, starting from the well-known

domains in P7.2.2.a_Y1 (environmental data) and P7.2.2.b_Y1 (HBM data) and then expanding to domains where similar needs present themselves (toxicology, bioassays).

Generic artefacts, solutions and tools developed in the projects P7.2.2.a_Y1 and P7.2.2.b_Y1 (such as lists of variables, chemical identifiers, (meta)data validation tools, tools for harmonisation, conversion between standards, semantic annotation, FAIR publication, ...) will be repurposed for other domains. Domain-specific FAIR enabling resources (such as metadata schema, data templates, harmonisation standards, data reporting interfaces) will further be elaborated and implemented. This approach allows systematic co-creation of domain-, use-case or project-specific roadmaps for development and implementation of FAIR metadata and data based on the current level of maturity of the specific case (e.g., RA is further advanced than NAMs).

One generic functionality, for domains that have adopted the PARC FAIRification methodology, that we will develop in Y4 is a standardised and automated approach to creating FAIR (meta)data packages.

In terms of the development of domain-specific resources, we will follow the demand, available expertise and FAIR Steering Team prioritisation, but expect that exposure data and model metadata, NTS data and health guidance values will be among the topics addressed in Y4.

In addition, we intend to explicitly concentrate on the data and model interoperability aspects of CRA research and contribute with our FAIR (meta)data formats to the technical implementation of interoperability between data and models in the PARC Integrative Model Network (T8.3) and the EWS (T8.2) Framework.

Apart from P7.2.2.a_Y1 and P7.2.2.b_Y1, clusters and use cases selected in Y1 and Y2 are supported further in implementing their workflows, i.e.,

- making available scientific data sources for (re)use in regulatory RA, i.e., development and implementation of user-friendly tools (interfaces) to make occurrence and hazard data available in formats supported by the CPDC (i.e., IPCHEM (meta)data formats (see P7.2.2.a and P7.2.2.b), IUCLID, OECD Harmonised templates, EFSA templates, national templates, ...); [Partners involved: ISS, UL-LACDR, NIVA, MU].
- addressing domain-specific data needs and related workplans and actions identified in Y2 that address the management of hazard and toxicological data that span across WP5 and WP6 and require cross-WP alignment (coordinated by UoB, with support from BfR (WP5) and UL-LACDR). These include:
 - Regulatory toxicology (EFSA, ECHA) where endpoints are well-defined: refinement of existing harmonised templates; [Partners involved: ISS, UL-LACDR, UOB, WR, MU, NIVA].
 - Updating of metadata, and development of new templates for novel in vitro endpoints and approaches as developed for NAMs (aligned with OECD requirements for validation of methods) [Partners involved ISS, UL-LACDR, UoB, NIVA, MU, KWR, TNO] In particular for in vitro methods applicable to SSbD. This will involve the development of a toxicology FIP.
 - Development of a community standard for documentation of toxicological study systems (animals, organisms, organoids, cell culture systems etc.) and accompanying

- sampling protocols, formalised via a European Committee for Standardization (CEN) Workshop Agreement or other appropriate means [Partners involved: UOB, MU, UL-LACDR, TNO, NIVA]
- Collaboration with the FAIR AOP cluster on FAIRification of the AOP Framework to support (i.e., development of FAIR Implementation Profile and FAIR Enabling Resources) to support the development of the new “AOP-Wiki 3.0” and AOP-related terms and concepts; [Partners involved: IISPV, UOB, UG-PL, ISS, MU, NIVA]
 - Workflows for documentation and FAIRification of omics / systems toxicology modelling data to support its integration into RA; this will be done in collaboration with the ASPIS cluster (<https://aspis-cluster.eu/>) and the ELIXIR Toxicology Community implementation project (<https://elixir-europe.org/communities/toxicology>). [Partners involved: INSERM, UoB, KI, UL-LACDR, IISPV, NIVA, TNO].
 - Further elaboration of the workflow, templates and data repository for ecotoxicological data for broad use by the PARC community and beyond, and testing in dedicated use cases [Partners involved: NIVA, UoB, members of FIT]
- Metadata for MS NTS data, analytical workflows and data processing (cross-WP effort in collaboration with EMBL) [Partners involved: MU, additional partners to be confirmed during Y3].
 - Implementation of Protocols.IO (Protocols.io is “a secure open access platform for developing and sharing reproducible methods. Users can create, publish, and read public protocols” (<https://www.protocols.io/>)) for documentation of PARC data generation protocols, to increase findability (discovery), re-usability and overall FAIRness of the workflows and protocols underpinning PARC datasets. Analysis of Protocols.IO as a FAIR Enabling Resource is underway in Y3, and is included as a critical element of the PARC Toxicology FIP, with applicability to Environment (and potentially HBM) datasets also. As noted earlier, integration as a PARC Data Hub workflow to is also envisaged. Training and support for all PARC partners on use and implementation of their protocols will be provided via WP7 in collaboration with the Protocols.IO team.
 - Continued work on use cases on FAIR elements common to many projects: finetune and improve tools for metadata management, for schema-based validation of harmonised templates, for semantic annotation, taking into account new domains and use cases; [Partners involved: VITO, MU, additional T7.2 partners to be confirmed].
 - Further elaboration and implementation/selection of a tool for automated FAIR assessment [Partners involved: MU, UoB, VITO].
 - Depending on concrete workplans defined in Y3 and the progress in the respective WP8 Tasks, develop and implement workflows and tools to facilitate data availability and interoperability for tools developed in T8.1 - Safe and Sustainable by Design; T8.2 - Early Warning Systems and T8.3 - Integrative Modelling Network. [Partners involved: AUTH, WR, other WP7 partners to be determined during Y3]. At the Annual meeting for WP7, it was agreed to spec out two additional cross-domain / cross-WP case studies as follows:
 - Integration of hydrological data for predicting pollutant movements (hotspots, hot moments) and the impacts of droughts, floods and these rivers/river basins, together

with water quality monitoring data to feed into the EWS being developed in WP8 [Lead contributors UoB, Contributors: ANSES, BRGM, AUTH].

- A use case on implementation of bioassays for water quality monitoring and decision support will be developed also – this idea emerged at the WP7 Annual Meeting in October 2024, so will be fleshed out over the coming months (prior to start of Y4) [Lead: ANSES, Contributors: UoB, EFSA and others to be determined]

The ongoing work will be coordinated and monitored by the FAIR Implementation Team [Partners involved: AUTH, UG-PL, ISSeP, JSI, MU, UL-LACDR, UOB, VITO], while the FAIR Steering team prioritises and assigns new work where needed. [Partners involved: VITO, UOB, IISPV, MU, TNO, UL-LACDR, WR]

All tools that are developed in 7.2.3 to facilitate FAIRification and reuse of data, will be made available for use in the FAIRification Toolbox via the PARC FAIR Data Hub.

Support from WP7 (partners UoB, UL-LACDR, NIVA, MU, VITO) for the WP5 project starting in Y4 "Fostering the use of omics and phenotypic profiling for grouping and read-across in RA" which is planning to:

- develop a database system and interface of the proposed OECD Omics reporting framework (OORF), the OORF to allow seamless completion of reporting information, browsing and querying study characteristics;
- develop a standardized, interoperable and toxicologically-oriented pathways and gene set ontology, to be applied to test systems specific co-expression models and bridge to the AOP framework, when possible;
- propose guidelines on how to integrate structural and physiochemical similarity measurements and mode of action features derived from omics and phenotypic profiling.

A7.2.4 Standards and harmonisation

[Lead: VITO, Partners involved: IISPV, JSI, MU, UBA, UOB, VITO, WR, NIJZ, NIVA, EV-ILVO, AUTH, UL-LACDR]

The activities are planned and followed up in the Semantic Implementation Team. [Partners involved: IISPV, JSI, MU, UBA, UOB, VITO, WR].

This activity supports harmonisation and FAIRification for the use cases in 7.2.3 by providing controlled vocabularies, ontologies, harmonised metadata and data standards. The combined bottom-up (use cases and projects) and top-down (community standards and shared ontologies) approaches will be used to further enrich the consolidated set of controlled vocabularies at PARC level as well as domain-specific standards. Several artefacts have already been created, both domain specific and PARC-level generic ones and in Y4 we will concentrate on consolidating these resources, ensuring they fit together and have sensible interdependencies. Both the vocabularies themselves and the validation and harmonization tooling that supports (and lowers the barrier in adopting) these standards and interfaces will be published as recommended tools in the PARC DataHub.

Corresponding documentation will be published on PARCopedia. [Partners involved: IISPV, JSI, MU, UBA, UOB, VITO, WR, NIVA, EV-ILVO, UG-PL, UL-LACDR].

A durable list of data, metadata and project standards will be compiled and published in appropriate repositories (PARC-independent ones, such as FAIRsharing.org or FAIR Connect and PARC-specific ones, such as the PARC Data Hub or PARCopedia (WP2), providing guidance and background info to set up training on these standards (WP9) and supporting projects with strong important collaborative components in adopting a standards-based approach (WP8) [Partners involved: IISPV, JSI, MU, UBA, UOB, VITO, WR, NIJZ, AUTH]

Lessons from the WorldFAIR CDIF (<https://zenodo.org/record/7378109>) on an overarching interoperability framework (lingua franca) and recommendations for implementation, will be incorporated as a means to interoperate across the toxicants, HBM, Environment, Toxicology, CRA and SSbD domains of PARC. WorldFAIR recommendations will be applied / road-tested and where relevant integrated into PARC Data Hub and FAIRification toolbox [Partners involved: UoB, MU, VITO, UL-LACDR, NIVA with support of CoDATA].

(Meta)data schema activities (in maintenance, ongoing and planned):

- PARC metadata schema
- HBM metadata schema
- ENV metadata schema
- Toxicology metadata schema
- Research Activities metadata (RAiD standard)
- (Regulatory) Toxicology/Omics data schemas (e.g., the BIODA and OECD ORF together with WP5)
- AOP data schema

Vocabulary & Reference list activities (in maintenance, ongoing and planned):

- CRA domains
- Chemical Entities
- FIP2DMP controlled vocabularies
- HBM metadata vocabularies

In-Progress Ontology Development activities:

PBPK Ontology (PBPKO) (Lead Partner IISPV): PBPK Models are extensively employed in pharmaceutical and environmental fields to evaluate xenobiotic kinetics. Harmonization techniques like ontology which offer a formal, explicit specification of a shared conceptualization, can help to facilitate models FAIRification solution. PBPKO annotates both physiological and biochemical parameters pertinent to PBPK modeling.

AOP Ontology (AOPont) (Lead Partner IISPV, Contributors: UL-LADCR, UoB): AOP (Adverse Outcome Pathway) ontology development is an activity focused on creating a structured, formal representation of knowledge about how certain biological events can lead to adverse outcomes,

following exposure to chemicals or other stressors. This process involves several key steps like Domain Analysis, ontology design, Formalization, Annotation, validation, etc. This activity will be done in collaboration with the ECHA led AOP cluster and Methods2AOP group.

PEH Ontology (Lead Partner UOB): The PEH Ontology is an effort to create a formal ontology from the HBM data and metadata structures developed in PARC, while maintaining compatibility with interoperability standards, such as the LinkML modeling language, the concept of standardised observation variables (cfr. I-ADOPT Framework) and a generic, harmonised approach to persisting atomic observational data.

Aggregate Exposure Modelling (Lead Partner WR): A Conceptual Model has been created that can express aggregate exposure events and context and be used to drive exposure simulations. The next logical step is the integration in an operational system as well as the creation of an ontology.

Task 7.3: Innovative analyses

Co-Leaders: IISPV (ES) and UOB (UK)

Partners: ANSES (FR), AUTH (EL), EV-ILVO (BE), IMROH (CR), INRS (FR), INSERM (FR), ISSeP (BE), JSI (SI), KWR (NL), MU (CZ), NIVA (NO), UFZ (DE), UL-LACDR (NL), UOB (UK), UU (SE), UZIS (CZ), VITO (BE), WR (NL)

All scoping studies and use cases performed in T7.3 will be reported in deliverable D7.4 1st Evaluation of innovative analytical approaches and uncertainty approaches for introduction in chemical RA.

A7.3.1 Innovative methods for combined analyses of FAIR (heterogeneous) data

(Partners involved: AUTH, VITO, IISPV, ANSES, UFZ, IMROH, INRS, UOB, UL-LACDR, UNIVIE, NIVA, MU, WR).

A.7.3.1.a Combined (meta-, Pooled) data analyses

In Y2, the scoping review on innovative methods for combining heterogeneous data (“Advancing RA through Heterogeneous Data Integration: Challenges, Methodologies, and Future Trends”) has been finished, including different statistical approaches and computational tools for meta- and pooled analysis (such as Network analysis (Bayesian Network (e.g. combined with expert knowledge), frequentist network and mixed comparison), Bayesian Hierarchical meta-analysis model, and hybrid models like multilevel meta-analysis and Structural Equation modelling), In Y2-Y3, for the implementation and evaluation of these methods, 5 use cases have been defined and started, based on inputs from WP4, 5, 6 and 8. These use cases cover methods for pooling/meta-analyzing different datasets (A.7.3.1.a) and/or methods for combining different types of (heterogeneous) data (A.7.3.1.b). In Y4, the proposed methods will be evaluated by applying them in the use cases. More details on the planned work in Y4 for the different case studies is provided under A.7.3.1.b. [Partners involved: AUTH, VITO, IISPV, KI, ANSES, IMROH, INRS, UOB, UL-LACDR, NIVA, MU].

A.7.3.1.b Methodologies to combine and integrate hazard and exposure-response information across and within evidence domains.

Potential Use Cases (Partners involved: AUTH, VITO, UL-LACDR, IISPV, KI, ANSES, UFZ, IMROH, INRS, UOB, NIVA, MU, WR)

Proposed use cases involve the integration of different data sources within or across domains, and thus the variability and uncertainty of heterogeneous data need to be considered, which is consistent with the overall goal of T7.3 and a potential synergy with A7.3.2. In Y4, we will further evaluate these potential case studies and extend their models to generate a refined approach for integrating incoming extensive, heterogeneous data input.

Use case 1 (Lead AUTH, Partners involved: VITO, INRS, IMROH, UoB): A first potential use case will combine metabolomics data from multiple cohorts and/or multiple technologies (e.g., LC-MS AND NMR). Epidemiological data, HBM data and metabolomics data will be integrated and linked with health outcomes. The plethora of tools mentioned in the scoping review completed in Y2 will be integrated into a pipeline that will collect this data and, by combining machine learning approaches as well, will derive and conclude about health outcomes. VITO will focus on a metabo-lipidomics analysis to unravel mechanisms underlying the association between chemical mixture exposure and immune-related effect markers. The case study will use metabolomics and lipidomics measured by both LC-MS and NMR and will cover methodologies for different levels of data integration, 1) the analysis of a broad chemical mixture including exposure biomarkers measured in blood and/or urine 2) the combined (within-omics) analysis of high-dimensional omics measurements from different technologies (LC-MS and NMR), 3) the (cross-omics) integration of multiple omics layers (metabolomics and lipidomics). Literature on suitable methods has been collected and initial steps in analysis have been taken Y3 but will be further developed in Y4.

Use case 2 (Lead VITO, Partners involved: AUTH, IISPV, JSI, WR, KWR): A second potential use case linked to T6.3.2 (Real-life mixtures project) is on multiple-exposure pathway analyses which can integrate multiple mediators and/or multiple outcomes. The application of such multivariate mediation methods can help to unravel biological mechanisms as they enable the assessment of combined effects and relative importance of the various mixture components and the identification of relevant biomarkers in the pathway between exposure and health effect. Part 1 of this use case (finished) has pooled data from two studies (FLEHS II and III) and focused on the setting of a single exposure biomarker, because many of the existing multivariate mediation methods cannot handle multiple exposures (in the sense that they don't do penalization/variable selection on exposures). Part 2 of this use case will integrate data from a hotspot (3M study in Zwijndrecht) and a reference population (FLEHS IV) and will focus on methods which can handle multiple mediators as well as multiple exposure biomarkers and will be performed by a PhD student.

Use case 3 (Lead: UL-LACDR, Partners involved: UoB, IISPV, VITO): A Case study on multi-omics integration for in vitro assays including transcriptomics, metabolomics, and phenotypic imaging data. Traditional animal tests and non-animal in vitro toxicological studies combine typically multi-omics readouts namely transcriptomics, metabolomics and other functional readouts (imaging, plate

reader, ©Seahorse, FACS, etc). During Y3, we have collected data and ideas over 3 case studies, in collaboration with other initiatives as well:

- Dataset from RISK-HUNT3R using the HEPG2 test system exposed to a group of Drug-induced liver injury (DILI) substances. The effect of these chemicals was captured using targeted high-throughput transcriptomics (©TempO-Seq) and metabolomics combined with ©Seahorse measurements. Additional dataset (transcriptomics and metabolomics) generated from Primary Human Hepatocytes exposed to chemicals with different concentrations and time points.
- Dataset from Exposome-Scan NL using the HepG2 test system exposed to a library of oxidative stress inducers. Imaging, metabolomics and transcriptomics data will be collected. Concentration-response effects of high throughput transcriptomics, metabolomics and functional imaging (using fluorescent reporter cells) will be assessed at different time points.
- Rat Exposome-Scan NL dataset generated by exposure to environmental air samples and fine particulate matter (PM). This dataset involves multi-omics dataset, including rat RNA-Seq and histopathological slide images, as well as lipidomics and metabolomics. Furthermore, there is RNA-Seq dataset from the ischemia–reperfusion study is also available for case studies.

While much effort will be made in standardizing and harmonizing the data production and collection workflow, the integration tools mentioned in the scoping review will be used for these heterogeneous datasets. This will include the adoption of the OECD reporting template for multi-omics, ensuring consistency in data documentation and facilitating regulatory submission. Additionally, connections between multi-omics and imaging data will be streamlined to provide a more holistic view of biological responses. The analysis phase will involve testing multiple computational and statistical methods to evaluate how the outputs align with regulatory requirements, ensuring that the results support RA and decision-making processes. There has been some delay in the progression of this case study due to hiring, now solved for Y4.

Use case 4 (Lead: NIVA, Partners involved: IISPV): Case study to integrate heterogeneous environmental exposure and effects data into a (cumulative) RA workflow by 1) Standardise and harmonize reporting of environmental exposure and ecotoxicological bioassay data into controlled vocabularies and ontologies (P5.2.2, P7.2.2a, A7.2.4), 2) Develop UI based import tools and data repositories to FAIRify data for consistent reporting, mapping, transfer and linkage between data sources (P5.2.2, T7.2.3), 3) Develop data and metanalysis pipelines to integrate (A7.3.1b), analyse and visualize heterogeneous data sets representative of AEPs and AOPs (A7.3.1b) and 4) identify and parametrize selected STOPs to predict cumulative risk for environmentally- and regulatory-relevant exposure scenarios (in collaboration with T.6.4.1 and T8.3). The proposed work is anticipated to involve different environmental exposure scenarios, be organized as a multi-year initiative that aligns with activities in tasks under 7.3.1-7.3.3 and in extension supports developing the PARCopedia model environment (T8.3). The work in Y3 have largely been focused on developing data reporting formats and UIs for reporting of (eco)toxicological effects data (A7.2.3, in collaboration with P5.2.2), organising national exposure (monitoring) data for use in the case studies (in collaboration with P.6.4.1), parametrizing a PBPK model (for Atlantic halibut) (A7.2.4). Further development of data and metadata reporting through UI development and alignment with available controlled vocabularies, ontologies and identifiers (P5.2.2, A7.2.2a, A7.2.4) will continue into Y4, as will

development of UIs (A7.2.3), establishing analysis pipelines for characterising variability and uncertainty in environmental exposure and hazard data (in collaboration with A7.3.2 partners) and integrate AEPs and AOPs into STOPs (in collaboration with T8.3 will be continued in Y4.

Use case 5 (Lead: UOB, Partners involved: IISPV) Enriching existing background knowledge resources for chemical RA through multi-modal data analysis. This use case is developing a methodology and workflow that is bottom-up and can be applied across WPs / projects easily. It is a multi-year use-case that spans across Tasks 7.3.1-7.3.4 but is presented here as its overarching goal is development of enhanced methodologies for data FAIRification for RA. Key steps will include:

5a. Development of an approach to enable generation of “provenance networks” for scientific datasets and facts through post hoc analysis, which can be considered as a means of 'retrospectively FAIRifying science' by establishing the provenance of data/facts/etc. Given that many of the PARC projects are using literature curated datasets / grey literature, this sub-task will also explore opportunities for tracking the spread of false information (e.g., down-playing toxicity of specific chemicals or sensationalisation of results, or identification of subsets of data that contribute to overfitting for example).

5b. Based on the landscape mapping performed in T7.2.1, prioritised pubmed / biomedical / toxicological databases will be parsed for relevant toxicological entities (based on the community agreed ontology / structured vocabulary developed in Task 7.2.2); Following this, UoB will use our novel methods for identifying significant associations between pairs or groups of terms, such as sequences of key events in adverse outcome pathways, or deviations from expected patterns of occurrence that might indicate alternative pathways, supporting also the collaboration with the AOP Cluster / development of AOP-Wiki 3.0;

5c. The next step will be enrichment of the putative AOPs with clinical / toxicological data and digital phenotyping. Inversely, the use case will explore whether AOP data could be used for healthcare tasks, e.g., differential diagnosis or supporting epidemiological analyses, as a means to bridge toxicological and medical datasets more effectively.

5d. A final step, through engagement with the breadth of PARC projects will be identification of demonstration adverse outcomes / diseases, whereby the workflow and tools developed will be benchmarked, documented and applied in complex real-world settings.

A7.3.2 Methods for uncertainty characterisation, propagation and quantification as a basis for harmonisation in RA (Partner Involved: IISPV, ANSES, KWR, MU, WR, NIVA)

Following the initial conceptual design, planning, and primarily data collection in Y2, activities regarding detailed implementation of selected use cases will continue. For their implementation and evaluation use cases for exposure, hazard, risk, HIA, and IATAs in collaboration with WP4, WP5, and WP6, will be further refined and developed. Eventually relevant outcomes will be implemented in the PARC integrative model toolbox in collaboration with T8.3. This activity will focus on qualitative and quantitative estimation of uncertainties at the different steps of the domain specific process and methodological approaches used for uncertainty propagation. Domain specific use case groups have been selected and they will be working to define the scope of each use case study. The report will

recommend promising methods for further evaluation and refinement if needed. [Partners involved: KWR, WR, NIVA].

Following three use cases are currently implemented and will continue in Y4.

Use case 1: Assessment of uncertainty in PBK models of PFAS exposure in humans and reverse dosimetry (uncertainty in PFAS exposure) (Lead: MU, Partners involved: IISPV, WR)

The aim of the case study is to assess uncertainty through all workflow of when comparing results of a PBK model for internal exposure and a dietary model for external exposure to PFASs. The PBK model is used for a reverse dosimetry, modelling daily intake from known blood PFASs concentration whereas food frequencies, portion sizes and PFASs concentrations in different food items and drinking water over the European countries are used to estimate daily intake from external sources. Uncertainty in all inputs is quantified and advanced methods for sensitivity and uncertainty propagation are used to quantify the uncertainty in daily intakes estimated by both models.

In past 2 years of the case study (Y2 and Y3), 4 PFASs were selected for the case study (PFOA, PFOS, PFNA, FHxS), the PBK model for the first subpopulation (teenagers) was selected (RIVM model) in collaboration with T6.2.2, the external exposure (dietary) model was constructed and data from European food were collected (over 7,400 records). The parametrization of the selected model will be finished in collaboration with T6.2.2 in Y3 and estimates of uncertainty of all the parameters will be suggested and discussed among the case study partners. Before the end of Y3 also the final version of a review of the uncertainty and sensitivity treatment methods will be finalized.

Planned activities for Y4 consist of a comparison of different methods of the uncertainty propagation within the external exposure model and a comparison of results of the PBK model reverse dosimetry with the results of the external exposure model for teenagers. Further, a thorough comparison of results of the reverse dosimetry with the results of external exposure modelling, including their uncertainties, distributions and discussion of the results will happen. First of the two suggested scientific papers should be submitted during the Y4. In the following year, a similar workflow will be realized for other subpopulations (adults and potentially also pregnant women) and the second suggested paper will be submitted.

Use case 2: From Bioassay Response to Risk Uncertainty (Lead: KWR, Partners involved: IISPV, NIVA), First three years of work has been completed and results has been published in a scientific article (<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envint.2024.108733>). Second phase of this work will continue in year 4 and in collaboration with WP4. Bioassays in water or food quality monitoring can measure effects induced by chemical mixtures. Such chemicals, that induce bioassay responses, have different levels of toxicity for different human or other organisms' endpoints. This means that there is uncertainty in interpretation of the possible risks associated with a measured effect in a bioassay. Although a derived trigger value can pinpoint a response at which risk is low, information on risk magnitude and uncertainty in it is good to have at any bioassay response. The case will showcase a method to quantify these risks and uncertainties. Use case 3 Control Coefficient analysis of PBPK model (Lead: IISPV, Partners involved: TBD): Sensitivity coefficients quantify the effects of (small) changes in any parameter on any dependent variable, whereas a control coefficient quantifies the

extent to which a catalytic/biochemical process determines a system variable. The scoping study of this use case started in year 3 to develop the system biology approach that is called Metabolic Control Analysis (MCA) for PBPK and investigate the control coefficients that are most relevant for a toxicokinetic system. Application of this methodology to selected PBPK models will continue in Y 4.

Use case 3: Enhancing Hazard Prediction with Cell Painting and Conformal Prediction (Hazard_cellpainting_uncertainty, Lead Partner: UU (ola Spuijth, Partners: IISPV): AI models are emerging as important components when assessing hazard and risk of chemicals. With this case study, we focus on the data-rich and yet inexpensive in vitro assay Cell Painting and aim to demonstrate the value of using conformal predictions to deliver prediction intervals instead of point predictions as output of AI models. This has the potential to improve the reliability and interpretability in chemical hazard assessments.

In this case study, we integrate Cell Painting assays with conformal prediction methods to improve hazard prediction in AI modeling. Cell Painting is a high-content imaging technique that captures comprehensive morphological profiles of cells exposed to various compounds. By leveraging these rich phenotypic datasets, we train machine learning models to predict toxicological outcomes of new chemical entities. To address the inherent uncertainty in AI predictions, we employ conformal prediction—a statistical framework that provides confidence measures for individual predictions. This combination allows us to generate not only accurate hazard predictions but also quantifiable uncertainty estimates, enhancing the trustworthiness of the AI model.

The case study is linked to and based on data generated in PARC 5.2.1b and T5.2.1e. AI model sharing and discovery is linked to PARC T8.3.

Use case 4: Benchmark dose (BMD) Modeling of Omics Data: understanding and harnessing uncertainties

(BMD_uncertainty_modelling, Lead: UL-LACDR ; Partners involved: ANSES)

BMD modeling is a key tool in toxicological RA, providing estimates of doses that elicit a predefined biological response. In this case study, we focus on omics-based BMD modeling, where high-dimensional transcriptomics data is used to predict dose-response relationships. However, the variability between different gene sets can introduce uncertainty in BMD estimates, complicating their use in regulatory decision-making. To address this uncertainty, we are planning: 1) to focus on a network-centric modelling approach rather than gene set approach, 2) to integrate omics data with advanced ML approaches. By utilizing models such as Random Forests, BNNs, and Gaussian Process Regression (GPR), we aim to enhance the accuracy and reliability of BMD estimates while providing uncertainty quantification for each prediction. These approaches (network-centric modelling and ML techniques) allow us to account for the inherent variability in gene sets, improving model robustness.

In this case study, we leverage gene expression data generated using the human breast cancer cell line (MCF7) and available via the CompTox and EPA reference datasets (<https://comptox.epa.gov/dashboard/>), along with their respective weighted correlation network analysis derived models, to train ML algorithms. The combination of high-content omics data and probabilistic ML approaches enables us to generate not only precise benchmark dose (BMD) estimates but also confidence intervals for each prediction. This enhances the interpretability of the

results and provides regulators with a clearer understanding of the uncertainties involved in omics-based BMD modelling.

By addressing the variability and uncertainty in transcriptomics-based BMD estimates, this case study demonstrates the potential for more accurate and transparent toxicological assessments, ultimately improving the integration of omics data in regulatory frameworks.

There has been some delay in the progression of this case study due to hiring, now solved for Y4.

A7.3.3 Novel computational methods for integrating and extracting knowledge from non-structured data

Details per project:

- P7.3.3.a_Y3_ALT-IST_IISPV [M1-M60]

After completing the scoping study for methodologies, tool development, and applicability domains, tool development began in Year 2, resulting in a prototype that will continue to be refined in Year 4. This year, the tool will be implemented in ongoing case studies, specifically WP 5.3 (immunosuppression and adult neurotoxicity), as well as in new case studies currently under discussion including in WP6 and WP8. During testing of the tool prototype with specific use cases, several limitations were identified. In response, a more advanced information extraction and text mining system will be developed to meet the requirements of AOP development.

The case studies initiated in Year 3 will continue in the coming years, providing further insights to optimize the text mining system and clarify requirements. Additionally, the writing of scientific articles, and presentations at scientific congresses and SFs will continue in Year 4. [Partners involved: IISPV (ES), UoB (UK), ANSES (FR), INSERM (FR), JSI (SI), AUTH (EL), MU (CZ), UL-LACDR (NL), KI (SE), NIVA (NO)]

Specific actions for year 4 include:

- Drafting a whitepaper outlining a comprehensive pipeline for integrating additional data into text mining evidence, focusing on ensuring relevance and meeting the required evidence level for regulatory use. This pipeline will be designed to accommodate diverse data types, such as multi-omics and imaging, while maintaining alignment with regulatory standards. Key enhancements will include advanced meta-data filtering to prioritize high-quality, regulatory-relevant data and reduce redundancy. A version control system will also be incorporated, allowing periodic updates and re-indexing of evidence to reflect the latest scientific findings. Additionally, tools will be harmonized to ensure smooth integration with standardized reporting frameworks, such as OECD templates for multi-omics data. The white paper will also propose customization options for specific regulatory domains, ensuring that the pipeline meets the unique evidence-level standards required for areas like toxicogenomics and RA. [Participant: UL-LACDR, IISPV]
- Text mining framework will further be optimized to make it scalable for a wider usability by the community. Addition of meta-data filtering to reduce redundant results. Integration of index versioning system to allow periodic indexing of information. Further, harmonization

- and integration of developed tools into a single platform and customization for the domain specific requirement [Participants: IISPV, UoB]
- Planning of a harmonised FAIR evidence representation started in Year3 will transition to implementation phase in year 4 where ontology-based framework will be developed to represent an event information. [Participants: UOB/IISPV]
 - Development of hybrid text mining approach integrating ML and grammatical syntax parsing techniques for relation extraction [Participants: UOB/IISPV]
 - Systematic evaluation of methods for deriving binary and typed relationships between biomedical / toxicological entities based on transactional occurrence data will continue in year 4. [Participants: UOB/IISPV]
 - Building a consistent data exchange schema according to FAIR principle and mapping of diverse data sources to build the knowledge graphs started in year 3, will continue to the implementation phase in Year 4. [Participants: UOB/IISPV]
 - Development of FAIR AOP planned in year 3 will shift to implementation phase in Y4 by adopting a new bottom-up approach using nanopublications.

Use case 2 (Partners involved: UL-LACDR). Gene expression data is characterized by some accepted ontologies at the gene/protein level (e.g., NCBI Gene, UniProt) and some at the pathway or functional levels (e.g., Gene Ontology, WikiPathways, ..). However, both levels are at the moment sub-optimal to inform RA as they are either too detailed and not informative (gene level) or redundant and not pertinent to the toxicological experiments (pathway and functional level). Gene co-expression networks defined on the basis of exposure-derived experiments represent a good starting point to obtain data that is fitting the RA domain and that achieve data dimensionality reduction, however the annotation of such co-expression networks is at the moment not standardized but expert-based and time consuming. In Y3 we will develop an automated ontology naming application, including additional data sources for genes or gene sets. These would include compound modulation and pathology information, using existing datasets (e.g., DisGeNET) and text mining on literature and clinical trials. The to-be-developed FAIR (connection to 7.2.4) ontology will be tailored for RA use and will link to the information sources used (provenance). The ontology terms with knowledge on the function of individual genes and interactions between genes/proteins within modules can then be compared to existing literature and data repositories using text mining tools.

A7.3.4 Identify additional needs in PARC for innovative analyses and promising evolutions in the data science landscape, and translate them in use cases for evaluation

The objective of this activity is to identify emerging needs in PARC for innovative analyses on one hand, and promising innovative techniques on the other hand. For the annual plan year 4, scoping and testing of new methods will continue. Based on this implementation planning will be executed with the steps mentioned below with collaborating partners.

Use case 1 (7.3.4.a): Pharmacophore modelling using machine learning for screening Blood Brain Barrier (BBB) permeation of xenobiotics [Partners involved: IISPV, UFZ, JSI]: This use case aims to investigate the effectiveness of different fingerprints generated based on pharmacophore modelling in deciphering the BBB permeation of xenobiotics. With pharmacophore modelling, this study will explore the influence of the P-gp protein in the transportation process. Scoping and testing with limited data sources have been completed and the work is published

(<https://doi.org/10.3390/ijerph192013471>). There is some delay with new data collection and work will continue in year 3 and 4 with specific focus on identifies chemical groups in the PARC.

To achieve this objective, the use case will perform the following activities:

- The collection of chemical data from reviewed literature sources and databases, followed by a filtering and standardization process to obtain a stabilized 3D structure.
- A scaffold of the collected data will be generated to analyze the distribution of the core structure of the chemical responsible for permeability.
- Stabilization and hydration of the protein retrieved from the protein data bank (PDB) will be undertaken, for docking purposes.
- Different methods will be explored to generate pharmacophore fingerprints including receptor-based and ligand-based methods. The residue-based pharmacophore will be generated by docking the P-gp substrates and extracting the most common residues involved in the interaction. Whereas, the interaction-type pharmacophore will be generated using the docked chemical molecules, which will further be processed with the proLIF library to generate a 9-bit fingerprint and Rdkit.
- The generated fingerprint and classical fingerprint will then be trained on a classical algorithm, such as Support Vector Machine (SVM), RF (Random Forest), and naïve Bayes, for comparison. New generation of ML method like graph model will also be implemented for methodological comparison.

This use case has been developed in consultation with WP5 and WP8 and activity will be complemented with BBB experimental data generated in Task 5.3.4a (P5.3.4.a_Y1_PBK_Kinetics_Fraunhofer) and the computational tools for early warning system in Task 8.2.

Use case 2 (7.3.4.b): Scoping study of AI&ML-driven computational NAMs for use in NGRA [Partners involved: UFZ, JSI, IISPV]: Activity 7.3.4 will also collaborate with A6.4.3 with a selected project P6.4.2.c_Y1_NAMAM_UT: AI&ML-driven computational NAMs for use in NGRA lead by UT (EE) and work on landscaping and readiness of NAMs based on advanced AI&ML approaches for use in chemical RA. This activity is a collaborative activity between two WPs and WP7.3 will support and provide input to the planned activity of A6.4.2. Here the focus is on the documentation of the data feeding into these models, and of the predictions coming out, and how to ensure transparency of these and their FAIRness.

Use Case 3 (7.3.4.c): AI-based Methods to Predict Biochemical Parameters such as Fraction Unbound in Plasma (IISPV, UG-PL): This use case focuses on developing ML and deep learning (DL) models to predict the fraction unbound (fu) in plasma based on critical structural features of chemicals. The fraction unbound (fu) is a key biochemical parameter in the development and analysis of PBPK models, providing insight into the portion of a xenobiotic that binds to plasma proteins. This binding affects how much of the chemical remains in circulation to exert its biological effects. Accurate prediction of fu is essential as it influences chemical interactions across different tissues, impacting drug efficacy and safety profiles.

To achieve this, it is crucial to explore and understand the chemical structures that determine plasma protein binding. In vitro data for fu is available from various chemical databases such as ChEMBL and DrugBank, offering a solid foundation for model training.

Objectives: The aim of this use case is to build predictive models by utilizing machine learning and deep learning approaches to better understand how structural features influence fu values. Specifically, the activities will include:

- **Data Retrieval:** Gather in vitro fu data from publicly available chemical databases like ChEMBL, DrugBank, and relevant literature.
- **Data Cleaning and Validation:** Cross-validate fu data from different sources, checking for discrepancies, and rectify any inconsistencies to ensure data quality and accuracy for model training.
- **Feature Extraction:** Calculate structural features of chemicals using conventional cheminformatics descriptors (via tools such as RDKit and Mordred). Additionally, generate graph-based embeddings to capture more nuanced structural information of the molecules, providing an enhanced feature set for model training. Additionally, development of evolutionary algorithms and ML techniques (i.e. genetic algorithms, SHAP) to extract the most relevant features affecting the modeled variable (fu), which will have the direct impact on the overall models' predictive abilities and stability.
- **Machine Learning Model Development:** Train predictive models for fu using conventional machine learning regression algorithms like Random Forest, XGBoost, and Support Vector Machines (SVM). The input features will be based on cheminformatics descriptors and graph embeddings, providing a robust representation of the chemical structures. The descriptors will be computed on several levels of theory, i.e., at the level of quantum chemical calculations, simple representational identifiers (like SMILES, empirical formulas), with an aim to determine which level of theory is required to develop meaningful structure-relationship models.
- **Deep Learning Approach:** We will evaluate deep learning approaches by developing advanced neural network models and its variants such as graph neural networks (GNN) and using pretrained models and compare the performance and accuracy of deep learning models against conventional machine learning methods to determine the most effective approach.

Outcome: By leveraging both traditional machine learning and cutting-edge deep learning techniques, this use case aims to deliver highly accurate models for predicting the fraction unbound (fu) in plasma. These predictions will provide valuable insights into the role of structural features in chemical-protein interactions, improving PBPK model development and aiding drug discovery efforts.

Use Case 4 (7.3.4.d): Read-Across Through Transcriptomics Data (IISPV, UG-PL, UoB)

This use case focuses on employing and integrating two distinct approaches—structural similarity analysis and MoA—to perform Read-Across of chemical compounds. The aim is to benchmark these methods, validate them, and establish a standardized pipeline for Read-Across in NAMs for RA.

A. Structural Similarity Analysis: This approach involves clustering chemicals based on their structural representation using cheminformatics tools. The chemical structures are characterized by molecular fingerprints, which serve as input for clustering algorithms. Key activities include:

- **Clustering:** Apply various clustering techniques such as K-means and hierarchical clustering to group chemicals based on structural similarity. Development of novel implementation of fuzzification algorithms (soft clustering) in terms of similarity analysis, which will be particularly useful in the context of read-across analyses and their justification for the domain expert, leveraging the idea of probability of existing of one chemical structure to several groups at once. The implementation will be followed with development of an interactive tool for this purpose.
- **AI-Based Structural Similarity:** Use advanced AI methods, such as graph-based models, to generate molecular embeddings that capture complex structural information. These embeddings will be used to cluster chemicals in a more nuanced way, potentially revealing deeper structural relationships.

B. Mode of Action (MoA): This approach leverages transcriptomics data to group chemicals based on their biological effects, particularly their impact on gene expression profiles. The steps involved in this approach include:

- **Transcriptomics Data Processing:** Implement a bioinformatics pipeline for handling transcriptomics data. Key tasks include quality control (e.g., removing adapter contamination and filtering out low-read data) and processing the data for alignment and mapping to a reference transcriptome.
- **Gene Expression Analysis:** Quantify gene expression levels and perform differential gene expression analysis to identify changes in gene activity upon exposure to different chemicals.
- **Functional Enrichment and Pathway Analysis:** Conduct functional enrichment analysis to identify the key biological pathways and molecular mechanisms affected by chemical exposure. These pathways may be linked to AOPs, offering insight into the MoA.
- **Toxicophore Modeling:** Develop toxicophore models by mapping the structural features of chemicals to their interaction with targeted proteins involved in AOPs. This will help elucidate the relationship between chemical structure and molecular activity.

Integration of Approaches and Benchmarking:

Integration: Combine the results from structural similarity analysis and mode of action clustering to perform an integrated Read-Across of chemical compounds. This dual approach helps to consider both structural and biological effects in the assessment.

Benchmarking and Validation: Benchmark the performance of different clustering and AI models to identify the most effective approaches for Read-Across. The validation process ensures that the results are reliable and can be used to develop a standardized pipeline for Read-Across in NAMs.

Outcome: This use case aims to provide a validated and standardized pipeline for performing Read-Across based on both chemical structure and transcriptomics data. By comparing different methods, it will identify the most accurate and reliable approaches, facilitating improved chemical RA within the framework of NAMs.

This use case is strongly in alignment with the running CS1 in the P5.3.1.a_Y1_SystemsToxicology_UL-LACDR, and with the new submitted P5.3.1.a_Y4_grOMICS_UL-LACDR.

Deliverables

D7.5 1st review of the Data Management Plan (DMP) – Leader: TNO (M42)

Additional Deliverables:

NA

WP N°	WP8					Lead Beneficiary			AUTH/UNINA	
WP title	Concepts and toolboxes									
Partner N°	1.1	4	4.6	8	12	14	14.5	15	20.4	25
Partner short name	INSERM	VITO	ISSeP	MU	EEA	TTL	TAU	UBA	IUSS	RIVM
PM/ partner	0.2	3.0	0.5	21.6	3.8	5.0	6.0	4.6	19.0	12.0
Partner N°	25.4	26.4	29.2	31.3	34.6	35.8	35.11	36	36.3	52
Partner short name	UL-LACDR	NIVA	DGS	NIC	INSST	IVL	UMU	AUTH	NKUA	Cefas-Defra
PM/ partner	1.9	1.0	1.0	7.0	2.0	7.5	15.2	73.0	7.5	0.7
Start	M37				End		M48			

Objectives

The overall goal of WP8 is to support the development and consolidation of concepts and tools for chemical RA, also considering Safe and Sustainable by Design (SSbD) chemicals and materials and their operationalisation. The specific objectives of WP8 for year 4 are:

- Task 8.1: Further improve the functionalities of the V1.0 of the SSbD toolbox and assess its applicability through new case studies
- Task 8.2: Further develop the PARC computational EWS and the validation framework to support the EWS based on the completion of the identification framework
- Task 8.3: Implement case studies to advance the development of the PARC model network, based on an updated conceptual framework and inventory of models and tools, and deliver an enhanced version of the initial beta of the PARC model network

Description of Programmed Activities

Task 8.1: Safe and sustainable by design (SSbD)

Co-Leaders: RIVM (NL), EMPA (CH), AUTH (EL)

Partners: INERIS (FR), BNN (AT), MU (CZ), DTU (DK), SYKE (FI), TTL (FI), UBA (DE), ISS (IT), IRFM (IT), IUSS (IT), UNINA (IT), NILU (NO), NMBU (NO), UG-PL (PL), FMUL (PT), NIC (SI), INSST (ES), IVL (SE), BUL (UK), Cefas-Defra (UK), TAU (FI)

A8.1.1. Translate EC SSbD criteria & methodology towards operationalisation

The work plan in year 4 includes the activities below:

Continuing and deepening the interaction with industry and (internal/external) PARC experts

1. Scaling-up PARC internal and external expert involvement

Here we will expand and deepen the existing efforts and activities focused on involving experts from PARC, and external scientists from academia and industry. Safe-and-Sustainable-by-Design (SSbD) requires complex risk and sustainability assessments and decision-making processes within an innovation context. The JRC Methodological Guidance has detailed the development of a “Scoping analysis” step that sets the goal and scope for the whole SSbD assessment and redesign process. We found in the company interviews and several references that in the actual industrial context, such a scoping step occurs within a multidisciplinary team of experts where available information is used to “scope” the assessment and redesign problem, use information, tools and expert judgement to arrive at the best available conclusions for the innovation stage. By performing the scoping analysis within a team-based context, we can address the limited availability of information at early innovation stages. This scoping process is at the core of the SSbD problem definition and defines for a large part the steps that need to be taken to do a full SSbD assessment. Performing SSbD starts with a good scoping exercise, that is identifying the SSbD question at hand, identifying and defining the system boundaries, identification of the lifecycle and the involved stakeholders, finding hotspots and prioritize SSbD topics, gathering basic information, making an information assessment, etc. Building a scoping approach has two important aims. First of all, to learn from current practices in early screening. We set out to learn from experts how they deal with read-across approaches, how to prioritize and determine hotspots, how to include and deal with expert judgement.

Focus will be on the applied reasoning and the principles the reasoning is based upon. Thus, enhanced interaction with specialist will also add to the wider detailed understanding of the SSbD-approach.

Activities proposed included:

1. Developing an approach that enables a process to perform an SSbD assessment in a multidisciplinary team. This approach can be seen as a fictive role-play as of an innovation team within a company (serious game/workshop/designathon).
2. Organising (PARC) internal development/test workshops make use of a specific case in point. As the scoping approach will utilise a specific case study (chemical/product/process), this work will be performed in collaboration with 8.1.3.
3. Investigate the possibility of testing the approach in a company or value chain environment.
4. Translate the results to requirements for the toolbox.
 2. Continued interaction with other EU projects (HE 2023-24), and expansion of the overview of SSbD to knowledge developed in previous (and terminated) EU projects

Aim is to analyse the knowledge development and examine and establish links to operationalization of SSbD (8.1.1), the toolbox (8.1.2), case studies (8.1.3), Knowledge and education platform (8.1.4).

Activities included:

1. Drafting overview and subsequent analyses of relevant projects.
2. Active information exchange with running SSbD relevant projects (e.g. meetings, regular presentations at regular PARC SSbD meetings) (RIVM, IVL, AUTH).
 3. Development of a NAM-SSbD relevant knowledge base

Several developments in chemical RA are of crucial importance for SSbD. NGRA is a paradigm that can be useful for the operational development of SSbD. Additionally, in-vitro NAMs play a role in NGRA and potentially in SSbD as well.

Activities included:

1. Analyses and exploration of the SSbD and NGRA concepts to identify similarities and potential connections.
2. Development of insight in the current (in-vitro) NAMs and the way they can be used in the context of SSbD.
3. (Outline of) an scientific article (RIVM).
4. Completing the analysis on links between chemical regulation and SSbD.

We will finalise the current paper that we are working on (RIVM, EEA, UBA, JRC, AUTH, BNN, EMPA, UNINA)

- Continued discussion and interaction with industry (RIVM, AUTH, EMPA, IVL, Unina, IUSS). A two-way communication with potential users through software development ensures that the innovation context and user needs are accurately captured, while garnering wider acceptance for SSbD framework and toolbox. Through implementing a bespoke interview and focus group approach, we have arrived

at many insights on chemical innovation and the operationalization of SSbD. These will be further updated by the identification of user expectations and requirements for the SSbD toolbox (AUTH, EMPA, IUSS), including feedback of the toolbox experience from various user groups. As a follow up, we will develop a workshop to seek user feedback on the translation of the SSbD framework for operationalization, toolbox features, workflow, user interface and the case studies.

- Regulators and risk assessors have vast experience in the application of safety assessment approaches and in the interpretation of results. In workshops we will interact with regulators and risk assessors to discuss the current developments in SSbD, the SSbD-toolbox and its possible uses. We will explore questions focused on the use of SSbD seen from a regulatory context, interpretation of SSbD-results in early development stages, and balancing the outcomes from a safety and sustainability point of view. The goal of the workshops is twofold: raising awareness on the topic of SSbD in the world of regulators and risk assessor and exploring questions and issues around early innovation/low Technology Readiness Level (TRL) assessments (RIVM, AUTH, EMPA, IVL, Unina, IUSS).
- The PARC consortium and the broader community have vast collective experience on safety and sustainability assessment methods. We will engage in in-depth technical discussions with various experts on various safety, sustainability, and socioeconomic assessment methods to further deepen the technical credibility of the toolbox and allowing incorporation of methods that can soon be implemented in the toolbox.
- We shall build a collaboration scheme with newly funded projects under Horizon Europe 2023-24 (in collaboration with WP3 and CT on synergies) in the chemical and nanomaterial domains (AUTH, RIVM). Moreover, new projects and their case studies could be invited to present their vision and goals in task 8.1 meetings and periodic project updates will be set up with a view to incorporate eventually novel methods/tools under development in these projects into the PARC SSbD toolbox. We shall collaborate with the IRISS project to this end.

A8.1.2. Toolbox development

During year 4 work will focus on the further improvement of the Version 1.0 of the toolbox (AUTH, RIVM, EMPA, BNN, MU, DTU, SYKE, IRFM, IUSS, UNINA, IVL) that will have been delivered in the end of year 3 (based (a) on the further experiences that will be obtained through the more in depth analysis of the bisphenols and alternatives case studies (with a particular focus on NAMs), as well as the additional case studies streamlined by A8.1.3. and (b) from stakeholder input, with a particular focus on the toolbox users (SMEs, industry etc). The feedback form that is already in place, available for the users, ensures a continuous feedback loop where users of the tools can report issues or suggest SSbD-related improvements. Inclusion of additional state-of-the-art knowledge on developments and instruments applicable for exposure (WP4), hazard (WP5) and RA (WP6) (RIVM, EMPA, AUTH, INERIS, ISS, IRFM, IUSS, UNINA, UG-PL, FMUL, NIC, INSST, IVL, BUL, Cefas-Defra) will be implemented. Regarding sustainability assessment, where existing tools are not adaptable, open-source platforms like Python-based LCA tools can be customized to include SSbD metrics or regulatory requirements. (AUTH, INERIS, BNN, MU, DTU, SYKE, UBA, NILU, NMBU, NIC, INSST, IVL, BUL, EMPA). Particular focus will be paid on the development of a more informative decision support system, that will facilitate the development of new molecules, incorporating functionality modelling to effectively support the multi criteria decision analysis (AUTH, EMPA, SYKE). Towards this direction, machine learning models to predict the safety and sustainability of

chemicals in early design stages will be implemented (IRFM, AUTH, EMPA), while also implement predictive models that use existing data to suggest design or process alternatives aligned with sustainability goals.

The development of the toolbox will continue to follow a concurrent engineering and iterative approach (AUTH, IUSS). Within Y4 further, we efforts to further elaborate the workflow of available tools for early and late innovation stages, with an emphasis on tools amenable for use by SMEs, will continue.

The further identification and adaptation of existing tools will be continued, either within the PARC consortium (MU, AUTH, IRFM, UG, DTU, BUL, IUSS, FMUL, TTL, NILU, ISS, INSST, NMBU, IVL, CEFAS-Defra, RIVM), or outside PARC (EMPA, RIVM, IUSS, UNINA, BNN), as well as the development of new tools, aiming to fill the implementation gaps that will be highlighted by the new case studies. In addition, new models for quantitative hazard metrics for assimilating results of NAMs (and in particular omics), such as bioinformatics and systems biology models (AUTH, IUSS) will be incorporated in the array of available models.

The toolbox will continue to be built upon modular segments (e.g., LCA module, safety module, functionality module) that can be updated independently without affecting the entire system, however, ensuring modularity of so different tools can be seamlessly integrated (AUTH, IRFM, IUSS). However, expanding on the input-output relationships that have been reviewed in Y2, they will be further explored through the case studies of PARC. This will result in a larger number of established (manual) pipelines to address issues of both substitution and redesign. This will be in line with the “SSbD toolbox wizard” that will guide the user through the assessment. In addition, automated pipelines will be developed based on sets of questions and answers through the wizard, aiming to cover successfully some SSbD cases. In this direction, tools like Kubeflow, MLflow, or Airflow to automate the pipeline from data ingestion to model deployment will be explored.

Efforts for the FAIRification of the SSbD toolbox will continue in Year 4 – in particular this will allow future models to be readily used within the same framework on the basis of a standardized input / output protocol, in relation to the ongoing work of the ontologies group in PARC and beyond, ensuring that the toolbox provides thorough documentation and user guides on how the SSbD toolbox should be used, including examples, sample datasets, tutorials, and workflows. Critical in this direction is to provide data provenance, i.e. clearly document where the data comes from, any transformations applied, and any assumptions made during their application in the various models and simulations and (b) ensure that workflows and analyses within the toolbox are fully reproducible, by providing version-controlled datasets and models, offering workflow templates that guide users through standard procedures for SSbD, so as to ensure consistent and reproducible results. In this directions, the usability of tools like Jupyter notebooks or RMarkdown for reproducible documentation and analysis will be tested.

To ensure the successful operation of the toolbox, linking with more databases that will feed with data the models (AUTH, IUSS, RIVM, EMPA, IRFM). In this direction, additional collaboration efforts with WP7 will include the use of FAIRified data, while blockchain-based systems will promote secure data sharing initiatives, that are necessary for industrial and SME users. For the practical implementation of the blockchain, encryption protocols will be developed, ensuring that only authorized parties can access specific pieces of information (AUTH).

A summary of the timeline of the toolbox development activities is outlined in the following Gantt Chart

Actions	M37	M38	M39	M40	M41	M42	M43	M44	M45	M46	M47	M48
Further elaborate models for delivering quantitative hazard metrics using NAMs												
Continue linking modelling tools outside PARC												
Additional models for chemical RA functionally linked using docker containers												
Develop additional pipelines for key safety assessment scenarios												
Develop pipelines to accelerate (re)design of chemicals												
Continuous efforts for PARC toolbox FAIRification												
Continuous update of the wizard												
Development of the {ARC SSbD toolbox DSS												

48.1.3. Towards operationalization: Use case & indicators

Version 0.1 of the PARC SSbD toolbox, implemented during year 3 according to the feedback from stakeholders and the added value gained in the bisphenols use case will be further, enriched, operationalized and applied in additional use cases in the field of task 8.1.3. The aim of such activities will be to operationalize the integration of the toolbox benefitting from the experience gained in selected case studies (IVL, AUTH, IUSS, UBA, FMUL, UNINA, TTL, EEA, KI, BNN, Cefas-Defra, RIVM).

Additional use cases will be selected based on the already initiated connection with newly established SSbD HE projects and other external projects (e.g. Mistra SafeChem)(IVL, UNINA, AUTH, EMPA, RIVM).

Focus of the use case selection will be on the specific policy need from a safety/sustainability point of view, specific needs for further toolbox development and testing, and availability of user-based test networks.

In the fourth year of the project, the emphasis will remain on chemical substances, with a particular focus on those of high societal relevance, such as alternatives to PFAS. When choosing substances for case studies we will also aim to include both substances that are within and out of applicability domain of the available tools. Additionally, the ambition will be to include more new tools, such as NAMS and tools for early innovation to complement those tools already tested in the case studies, and to create new links between new and existing tools with the aim of creating new tool/model pipelines.

Work in year 4, will refine already acquired learnings regarding:

- i. features that make a tool useful in the context of SSbD, i.e. to determine what criteria should be

- used when evaluating the tools;
- ii. information required at each stage of SSbD;
- iii. endpoints useful in SSbD.

According to an iterative approach, specific attention will be enforced to define workflow and involvement of tools for early and late innovation stages, with an emphasis to be used by SMEs.

During Y4 we will also investigate how the uptake of the PARC toolbox can be monitored in activities in society. This will be put in practice by a number of 8.1 internal workshops aiming at answering the question how to observe the uptake and what indicators that can be used to follow the uptake (IVL, UNINA, AUTH, EMPA, RIVM).

Specific actions during Y4 will include:

1. Define new cases beyond those case studies already compiled and try to find collaboration partners, inside and outside PARC (IVL, UNINA, AUTH, EMPA, RIVM).
2. In collaboration with 8.1.1 apply and further develop the scoping approach in selected case studies. (IVL, RIVM, EMPA, AUTH, UNINA)
3. Define the indicators to be considered in the use cases, taking into account the inventory of indicators in the JRC framework and in the tools revised to prepare the version 1.0 of the toolbox
4. Encourage the use and uptake of the SSbD PARC toolbox in projects outside PARC, e.g. HORIZON projects, and relevant projects on National levels.
5. Compile an initial inventory about sector-specific tools for sustainability assessment that may simplify Step 4 in early stages of innovation (IVL, NILU, RIVM)
6. We will, in case studies, compare different alternatives based on the 8 SSbD design principles, how the different alternatives comply with the design principles, such as energy efficiency, bio-based, etc. (MU, AUTH, IRFM, UG, DTU, BUL, IUSS, FMUL, TTL, NILU, ISS, INSST, NMBU, IVL, CEFAS-Defra, RIVM)
7. Evaluate whether we have enough and the right tools in the toolbox and identify areas where tool development is needed. We also want to assess which tools are applicable in which contexts, i.e. identify the applicability domain of the tools where this is not stated. (IVL, UNINA, AUTH, EMPA, RIVM).
8. Publication of the results of the ongoing case study activities. (MU, AUTH, IRFM, UG, DTU, BUL, IUSS, FMUL, TTL, NILU, ISS, INSST, NMBU, IVL, CEFAS-Defra, RIVM)

A8.1.4 Knowledge sharing & Education as key factors for efficient SSbD operationalization

Building on the results of Year 3, work on the establishment of the knowledge sharing platform on SSbD will be continued (RIVM, TTL, UBA, UNINA, FMUL, INSST, AUTH, IUSS). Cooperation within PARC (Tasks 2.2, 3.2, 9.4) and outside (IRISS, JRC) will be continued and strengthened as well.

Based on the blueprint deduced for the knowledge sharing platform and its elements elaborated and drafted in Y3, together with identified contribution to a learning agenda, the technical execution of the knowledge sharing platform will continue in close cooperation with Task 3.2. Continuous interchange within 8.1 will be carried on to cover all interests of task members regarding knowledge sharing and

education and to ensure information flows on relevant documents and materials for the knowledge sharing platform. Interlinks, e.g. to the PARC SSbD toolbox will be made sure. Draft landing pages developed in Year 3 will be complemented with additional and more elaborate information and material that will arise over time (RIVM, TTL, UBA, UNINA, FMUL, INSST, AUTH, IUSS). The procedure for material collection will be continued further and applied (RIVM, UBA, FMUL, INSST). Upon the experiences using PARCopedia groups and the knowledge exchange with Task 2.2, a public SSbD group at PARCopedia will be set up to serve as dedicated user community hub on SSbD (RIVM, UBA, IVL, FMUL, INNST, AUTH, TTL, IUSS, UNINA). This will feature one branch of the future knowledge sharing platform. Another branch of work that will concentrate on in Year 4 is the element of education and training within the knowledge sharing platform (RIVM, UBA, FMUL, INSST). Together with Task 9.4 work on the joint selection tool for education and training material will be intensified and launched via the PARC website. This selection tool will feature material for education and training related to RA in general based on the repository of Task 9.4, but also the material for education on SSbD based on the already existing repository in 8.1.4. This repository will be expanded with further material identified and that arise over time. Repositories will be aligned and merged to serve as database for the selection tool both at the training page at the PARC website but also at the SSbD knowledge sharing platform.

Further cooperation within PARC will be continued, i.e. with regard to FAIR data and data management, and how to consider that in the SSbD knowledge sharing platform.

Collaboration with JRC and RTD with regard to establishing a series of joint training schools on SSbD (“bootcamp”) started in Year 2 (RIVM, UBA, AUTH) and was continued in Year 3. The 2nd bootcamp organised and hosted by AUTH included hands on training on the PARC SSbD toolbox. A continuation of the bootcamp for Year 4 of PARC is planned and will be organised by JRC with strong support by PARC 8.1. Networking with partners outside of PARC will also continue in Year 4 in order to strengthen their contribution to the knowledge sharing platform by their own information/training/education material. This includes partners of running SSbD projects and programs/materials of partners involved in these projects (e.g. in IRISS), but also JRC.

Task 8.2: Scientific and technical basis for an Early warning system (EWS) on chemical risks

Co-Leaders: SLU (SE), INSERM (FR)

Partners: INRAE (FR), AU (DK), UBA (DE), ISS (IT), IRFM (IT), UniLU (LU), VUA (NL), WR (NL), NILU (NO), NMBU (NO), UG-PL (PL), DGS (PT), NIC (SI), IISPV (ES), INSST (ES), ORU (SE), IVL (SE), SLV (SE), UMU (SE), EA (UK), AUTH (EL), EFET (EL), GCSL (EL) NKUA (EL), UOC (EL)

A8.2.1 EW monitoring tools

The EW monitoring tools will be further refined and updated for the matrices of the abiotic environment (Task 4.2) including indoor environment and food, humans (T4.1) and products (T8.1). Hereby, it will be attempted to integrate the different prioritization components as described in AWPY1 and AWPY2 into a comprehensive scheme. Toxicity and NTS methods will be integrated towards an EDA (SLU, ORU). Mixture toxicity data from human and ecotoxicity (ISS) will be linked to NTS data (SLU, NKUA) (WP5). NTS data will be uploaded to digital data banks, for example the NORMAN digital sampling freezing platform (NKUA, AU). A machine-learning driven non-targeted approach, which is based on the quantification of the potential toxicity of chemical features, will be implemented to evaluate early warning signals of chemical compounds in food for emerging risk identification (WFSR). Prioritization components also include source

tracing tools, e.g. for PFAS (T4.2). Furthermore, trend analysis in biotic and biota matrices as a prioritization tool will be further developed (NKUA, SLU, ORU, AU) (T4.1; T4.2). The EW monitoring tools will be integrated with a computational framework (A8.2.4). Ultimately, the applicability and performance of the EW monitoring tools will be validated in case studies (A8.2.3). Additional actions include enriching the MS data (e.g. with better annotated sources, infrared data, or adding information to improve the interpretation of the MS data) and explore the feasibility of using pretrained machine learning model on HRMS data for predicting of toxicity using MS2 data and the possible use of additional mechanistic data on biological effects of chemicals leading to toxicity (such as information on AOPs).

A8.2.2: Identification framework

The prioritization framework will be further developed in Y4 also including the following activities: i) Connection with other prioritization work in PARC and elsewhere, ii) potential adjustments in the conceptual approach and the technical content, based on developments in Y3, iii) checks of its applicability (AU and others). Further synergies with the prioritization activities in T4.2 will be explored, as well as relevant innovative methods (T4.3) and regulatory RA methodologies (T6.4) for integration in the EWS approach (AUTH, NKUA, UMU). In collaboration with T8.2.1, the partners will review new scientific information of relevance for EWS and will update the memo that has been delivered in Y3 for internal use with potential updates of previously described concepts and technical EWS content. Focus points will include, but not be limited to, a) efficient links between monitoring data, innovative methods (e.g. non-target screening) and toxicity-based signals (with a particular emphasis on NAMs) in an EWS concept, b) chains of actions from an EWS signal (also including discussions of potential ethical questions of data sharing), c) potential obstacles encountered in the development process, and (d) integration of machine learning methods towards more post-processed EWS information to stakeholders. The latter will also be linked to assessments of the applicability of the prioritization approach and the EWS framework, focusing on the needs and expectations of environmental agencies and other stakeholders. Studies into applicability will also be linked with the case studies in T8.2.3.

A8.2.3: Applicability and performance testing of EW toolbox

The applicability of an EWS is tested through pilot case studies including one or several of the different EWS components, i.e. prioritization framework, EW monitoring tools, and computational framework. The first case study has started in Y3 using SPM samples collected from German rivers over an extended period (2005 to 2021) by UBA, Germany. In Y4, applicability testing of EW tools will be performed to explore toxic micropollutants in the aquatic environment through a time-trend analysis of SPM, utilizing EDA with both LC-HRMS and GC-HRMS non-target screening (NTS), and selected bioassay tests (SLU, ORU, UBA, AU). A second case study started in Y3 using fish samples from Greece collected by NKUA, is planned to be finalized in Y4, using effect-based monitoring (SLU, ORU) suspect screening (SS) and NTS by SLU (LC-HRMS), ORU, and AU (GC-HRMS). RA will be performed by EFET. Connections with other tasks include T8.1 and T8.2 (SPM case study), utilizing computational tools to validate the results. Additional collaboration with WP6 will involve in silico studies, comparing these results with in vitro bioassays. Moreover, collaboration with the 4.3 case studies will link the Greek Fish Study results to HBM efforts.

A8.2.4: Computational framework to support the EWS

An interface of the computational EWS will be released in Y4 using the SSbD toolbox as a starting point (AUTH, UMU, NKUA). The interface will incorporate a computational framework implementing tools for

Big Data Analytics (AUTH, IRFM, NKUA, UMU, INSERM). The framework will include suitable models for predicting exposure and hazard (AUTH, NKUA, IISPV, UMU). It will also include the automatic retrieval of exposure from high-resolution mass spectrometry data that will be achieved through API link with Digital Sample Freezing Platform (NKUA, SLU, AUTH, UMU). Moreover, efforts will be put towards the early detection of signals. A key source of information for early detection of potentially emerging chemicals is patent data. Methodologies to collect and analyze patent data will be tested and developed (UMU). The activity also aims at reading and translating chemical structure information embedded in patent data to function in fate and hazard model platforms (UMU). Another activity is the design of a new predictive model based on a methodology previously developed by INSERM, which has been experimentally validated. This method is to be updated and adjusted for the use in EWS, such as prediction of putative effects of chemicals on human health. In Y4, INSERM aims to develop a prototype. The framework and individual model components of the computational framework of the EWS will be tested and further developed using case studies (all partners). These are planned to apply data from the experimental case studies of WP8.2 but also using data from 4.2 or literature data. Further improvements of the existing components for chemical RA in the context of EWS will continue by translating the needs of the identification framework (AUTH, NKUA, UMU), as well as from the experience gained from the previous and ongoing case studies within Task 8.2. Case studies will enable testing of the pilot system and further improvement (AUTH, NKUA, UMU, AU, SLU). Additional efforts for integrating models developed in other work packages of PARC including WP6 and methods to include NTS data (NKUA, AU, SLU) steamed from WP4. Additional input for the needs of the computational platform will come from stakeholder input and requests and the respective interaction forum will continue to operate (UMU, IVL), so as to align with current and coming legislation to ensure the applicability of the EWS and that the output can be effectively used. This will be evaluated using the output of pilot studies (IVL). The stakeholder questionnaire that was devised during Y3 will be sent out and the results evaluated to ensure that the EWS is aligned with the stakeholders' needs and the decided EU EWS (IVL, EFET, AUTH, OVAM, SLU, SEPA). Work will continue with guidance for the evaluation of signals within the EWS (IVL, AUTH, UBA, NKUA, AU).

Task 8.3 Integrative models

Co-Leaders: WR (NL), AUTH (EL)

Partners: ANSES (FR), INERIS (FR), ISSeP (BE), MU (CZ), DTU (DK), SYKE (FI), TTL (FI), IRFM (IT), IUSS (IT), UL-LACDR (NL), WU-TOX (NL), NIVA (NO), NMBU (NO), NIC (SI), IISPV (ES), INSST (ES), UU (SE), UOC (EL)

A.8.3.1: Design, implementation and application of the PARC integrative model network

In year 4 development of the model network will concentrate on two key actions as detailed in D8.3 and AD8.4 to implement user-friendly and transparent (PARC) workflows for integrative RA. First, the general framework for integrating models in workflows will be applied and evaluated (AUTH, WR, IISPV, UU, NIVA, MU). Second, model improvements and connections between models will be developed or refined, addressing specific case study needs (AUTH, WR, ANSES, INERIS, ISSeP, MU, DTU, SYKE, TTL, IRFM, IUSS, UL-LACDR, WU-TOX, NIVA, NMBU, NIC, IISPV, INSST, UU, UOC). On-line meetings foreseen in Y4: bi-weekly core group meetings (AUTH, WR), 4-6 x T8.3 plenary meetings possibly one in person (all partners), bilateral meetings between partners.

More specifically, the first action involves applying the general framework for model integration to case studies (WR, AUTH, ANSES, NIVA, IISPV, UU). This approach will outline for each case study the key entities for model linkage, map and align relevant data and modeling tools, and identify options for connecting these into workflows. The framework will be updated iteratively to address any identified gaps. Additionally, the development of a framework for FAIR PBK modeling will continue (WR, INERIS, IISPV, AUTH, NIVA). The evaluation and enhancement of the generic framework will incorporate (user) requirements from various PARC WPs (main links: T6.2 (and its connection with EFSA), WP7, T8.1), and the Task 8.3 case study on bisphenols (see below). Input on (future) PARC model network requirements will also follow from collaboration with WP2 (AUTH).

The inventory of models/tools within the PARC model network will be updated based on these developments. This will be achieved by direct participation in T8.3 (ANSES, INERIS, ISSeP, MU, DTU, SYKE, TTL, IRFM, IUSS, UL-LACDR, WU-TOX, NIVA, NMBU, NIC, IISPV, INSST, UU, UOC) or by links with other PARC projects (AUTH, WR, ANSES, VITO). A first prototype for a general interface / access point to the model network via the inventory will be developed (AUTH, WR). Additionally, integration of the model inventory with the PARC data hub from WP7 will continue to be explored (MU, WR).

The development of the PARC integrative model network will continue through the implementation and refinement of workflows in the case studies. The case studies guide the implementation of the necessary model improvements and links and validation of the model network. Human and environmental-relevant workflows will connect models across various domains, including aggregate and cumulative exposure assessment (WR, AUTH, ANSES, NIVA), HBM analysis (AUTH, WR, MU, ANSES), development and use of PBK models (AUTH, WR, INERIS, IISPV, IUSS, ANSES, MU, NIVA), QSAR models (IRFM), hazard characterization (IUSS, UL-LACDR, IRFM, WR, NIVA), RA (WR, AUTH, NIVA), EBD (WR, ANSES, VITO), and uncertainty analysis (MU, WR, IISPV, NIVA). In this process model platforms such as INTEGRA (AUTH), MCRA (WR), RSExpo (ANSES), VEGA HUB (IRFM) and STOP (NIVA) will be further refined and interconnected with other tools (and each other) to enhance coverage of important regulatory domains in chemical RA. Additionally, model harmonization efforts (in association with WP7) will be evaluated and updated.

The main case studies currently in view are the bisphenols case study in this activity (lead from T8.3: AUTH), case studies in T6.2 (lead from T8.3: WR), T6.4.2 on Environmental exposure, hazard and RA (NIVA), the VEGA-MCRA case study (lead by IRFM), and a case study on uncertainty in PFAS exposure modeling from T7.3.2 (lead from T8.3: MU). Efforts for harmonization of the workflows within these case studies will be initiated.

The case study on human integrative RA supporting T6.2 will continue (T8.3 lead: WR; partners: ANSES, INERIS, VITO). The workflow for HBM-based mixture RA in MCRA will be refined based on methodological developments and requirements in T6.2.3 (real-life mixtures) and will support assessing mixtures of PFASs, pesticides and metals by T6.2.3 users. Depending on T6.2.3 developments, integration of environmental monitoring data (T4.2) will be explored (WR, VITO). Connections will be made between the HBM-based mixture RA workflow and those developed in T6.2.1 and T6.2.2, for example to compare modelled (external) exposures to HBM measurements (WR, ANSES, VITO). Integration of FAIR PBK models in MCRA will be improved, and PBK models selected in T6.2 will be linked (WR, ANSES, VITO, INERIS). Work linked to T6.2.1 will focus on maintaining and improving MCRA's connections to other models for aggregating exposures (WR, ANSES, VITO), considering data import or complete model

integration options (WR). Models from the RSEXPo tool (ANSES) are being evaluated for integration (WR, ANSES), with a proof-of-principle for PFOA and Cadmium planned (ANSES). Additionally, linking to project 6.2.1.a, integration of source-to-dose models in the network will be explored (VITO, WR). Linking EBD methods to MCRA will be extended in collaboration with T6.2.4 (WR, ANSES, VITO). Finally, presentation of results to external stakeholders, such as through a dashboard, will be explored (WR, ANSES).

The case study of bisphenols (BPA and BPA alternatives) in A.8.3.1 will continue in Y4 (T8.3 lead: AUTH) with the collection of relevant data started in Y2 (AUTH). Additional data outside PARC and HBM4EU will also be included in order to expand the chemical space of bisphenols, as well as alternative (AUTH, IUSS, UoC). Exposure reconstruction is also under further development, so as to improve the respective algorithm available in the INTEGRA model, which is part of the PARC model network (AUTH). Significant efforts will also focus on developing modules to integrate NAMs, facilitating the use of read-across approaches in collaboration with T5.3.1, as well as incorporating quantitative AOPs (qAOPs) to model toxicodynamics, linking MIEs to downstream key events (AUTH, UL-LACDR, WU-TOX, IUSS, NIVA).

The case study on uncertainty in PFAS exposure modeling from T7.3.2 will conclude in Y4, with finalization of all related activities (MU, WR). The development of uncertainty assessment methods for the case study will continue, followed by the integration of uncertainty analysis and implementation of the workflow into MCRA, accompanied by relevant guidance. This guidance should have the potential for broader application across various PBK models and compounds. Optionally, the PFAS PBPK model and PFAS occurrence dataset could also be incorporated into MCRA. In the final phase, the case study will expand the uncertainty analysis to encompass broader model networks, investigating how uncertainty propagates between domains and how this can be quantified and assessed throughout the data flow across domains (MU). The process already started with the development of a review that outlines uncertainty analysis approaches across model network domains. Based on this document, a comprehensive strategy and guidance for uncertainty analysis across domains—focusing on uncertainty propagation in workflows involving multiple linked models—will be developed.

The VEGA-MCRA case study will continue in Y4 with the goal to perform a cumulative RA on CAGs (IRFM, WR). VEGA supports the hazard identification, covering a wide range of (eco)toxicological endpoints. New models will be applied to improve the assessment of the endocrine disruptors. We will also identify a AOP network applicable for this case study (IRFM).

The integrated environmental case study for cumulative RA will continue in Y4, in T5.2, T6.4.2, T7.2 and T7.3 (NIVA), exploiting data-rich exposure data sets from selected national monitoring programs (T6.4.2), developing multi-species hazard assessments predictions (T5.2 and T6.4.2) from available (eco)toxicity sets (Ecotox db, Toxcast, available predicted no-effect concentration and environmental quality standard threshold values etc.), expanding QSAR estimates to a broader set of (eco)toxicological endpoints (IRFM), incorporating AOP/quantitative AOP information (T5.2), exploring uncertainty analysis (T7.3, NIVA), incorporating ecological-relevant PBPK models (NIVA) and supporting better linkage between human and environmental models for aggregate exposure pathways (NIVA, WR).

We will initiate a new case study (AI-SERVE) for FAIR serving of resource-demanding AI models based on SciLifeLab Serve (Lead: UU), jointly with uncertainty modeling (T7.3) and demonstrated on image-based in vitro data for NAM generated in T5.2.1e (DNT) and T5.2.1b (MD). Serving of PBPK models will be explored.

Deliverables:

D8.5 1st Report on the testing and operability, uptake and impact of the PARC EWS – Leader: INSERM initially planned M36 was postponed M48. This will be included in the next amendment of the GA.

D8.7 Advancing SSbD Implementation: Uptake, Testing and Integration of the PARC Toolbox through Case Studies, Stakeholder Engagement and Knowledge Sharing – Leader: EMPA (M48) (Given the feedback from HADEA—which highlights the need to better reflect the richness and breadth of WP8 activities beyond just the testing of the toolbox—a more comprehensive and representative title for Deliverable D8.7 has been proposed. This will be included in the next amendment of the GA

Additional Deliverables:

NA

WP N°	WP9										Lead Beneficiary				ISCIII/MU							
WP title	Building infrastructural and human capacities																					
Partner N°	1	1.1	1.2	1.4	1.7	1.10	1.11	2	3.8	3.9	4.6	5	6.1	8	8.2	10.1	14.4	15	17	20.3	21	22
Partner short name	ANSES	INSERM	INRAE	INERIS	ONIRIS	BRGM	LNE	SpF	UMIT	UNIVIE	ISSEP	SCIENSANO	IMROH	MU	VSCHT	AU	UEF	UBA	NCPHP	IRFM	RSU	NPHSL
PM/partner	0.9	3.0	2.2	0.1	1.4	3.8	3.6	3.0	1.0	4.6	3.7	5.1	1.0	44.3	3.9	5.0	1.0	3.1	3.0	0.4	0.4	8.9

Partner N°	24	25.7	26	26.2	26.7	28	29	29.3	29.5	30	30.1	31	31.4	32	33	34	34.2	34.4	35.2	36	36.2	37	50
Partner short name	LNS	WR	NIPH	STAMI	UNN	FMUL	INSA	ENSP	UAVR	SZU-SK	UK	JSI	UL FFA	NIJZ	CSIC	ISCIII	FISABIO	FNS	KI	AUTH	GCSSL	BPI	UKHSA
PM/partner	8.2	6.0	1.9	5.1	1.1	4.5	16.5	3.0	2.8	1.3	1.2	3.3	1.0	2.5	17.8	31.4	2.0	3.2	2.0	3.2	3.1	3.7	1.0
Start	M37										End				M48								

Objectives

The overall goal of WP9 is to further develop human capacities and existing and new infrastructures related to laboratory and monitoring networks including reference laboratories, join activities and exposure monitoring networks and databases. The specific objectives of WP9 for year 4 are:

Task 9.1: Laboratory networking

- Collaborate with T7.2 and T9.2 on developing the interactive platform presenting catalogues of laboratories and other relevant information collected in T9.1 and 9.2
- Keep the catalogues created on exposure laboratories up to date
- Extend the catalogues to include additional laboratory networks (Y4 priority fields: soil and sediment, food and feed, (eco)toxicological and articles/consumer products, and finish the ongoing air and water)
- Detect needs for laboratory network strengthening and promotion
- Define tools to promote and coordinate laboratory networks and start with their implementation
- Include the information of laboratories from air and water on the laboratory interactive map on the PARC website.
- Include the information of laboratories from different fields on the laboratory network dashboard within the PARC data Hub

Task 9.2: Building exposure monitoring capacities

- Collaborate with T7.2 and T9.1 on developing the interactive platform presenting catalogues of HBM studies, cohorts, environmental projects, networks and other relevant information collected in T9.1 and 9.2
- Continue with the inventory of environmental contamination resources (Y3 priority: water and sediment monitoring networks and projects, indoor studies and consumer products data)
- Collaborate with relevant WPs and Tasks to collect information on and outcomes of the ongoing surveys
- In collaboration with T7.2 and relevant WPs contribute to the development of the harmonised templates for future surveys
- Interact with other WPs to identify the needs for future catalogues (toxicology, models etc.).

Task 9.3: Joint activities – harmonisation

- Disseminate guidances drafted in M36 (D9.4) to WP4 and WP5
- Collect feedback from WP4 and WP5 on 9.3 QA/QC guidances, their implementation, and needs for chemicals prioritized in second half of PARC
- Align with and review project-specific WP4 and WP5 QA/QC activities

Task 9.4: Training

- In collaboration with training (scientific) coordinators, implement PARC training plan for Y4, as defined in AD9.1.
- Provide the necessary logistical support to organizers of local training events.
- Update PARC website to feature information on (external) existing training of potential interest to partners and stakeholders.

Description of Programmed Activities

Task 9.1: Laboratory networking

Leader: ISCIII (ES)

A9.1.1 Identify existing laboratory networks, draw up and maintain up-to-date and active a database of the laboratory networks

Partners: CSIC, SZU-SK, ANSES, AU, BPI, BRGM, FISABIO, FMUL, INERIS, INSA, ISCIII, LNE, MU, NIPH, NPHSL, SCIENSANO, STAMI, FINIBIC¹¹, VSCHT, GCSL, RSU, UK, ONIRIS

To update the networks already created (HBM, air and water) with new laboratories or updated information of those already included, or to collect data from any laboratory interested in joining the PARC networks, a communication channel is established through the PARC website. The search of laboratories working on the domain articles/consumer products started during Y3 in collaboration with WP6 will continue during Y4 and the catalogue will be created.

Due to the low rate of response from water laboratories, the work to create this network was extended more than planned, trying to reach new laboratories in different ways (including the creation of a specific Water Working Group). In consequence, the work on the fields soil and sediment and food and feed, previously planned for Y3, has been postponed to Y4. The first catalogues will be available by M42. During Y4, the new strategies defined to expand the networks and to include new laboratories which started to be implemented in Y3 (including publications on social media, announcements in relevant conferences and congresses and contacts with the already existing networks) will continue. These have already proven effective but further evaluation will continue being carried out in order to identify measures that can increase the interest of laboratories.

During Y3, the work on the identification of (eco)toxicological European resources started in collaboration with Task 9.2, using a survey. The obtained information on the laboratories working in this field and their capacities will be analyzed during Y4, and these results will be included in the two tools (interactive map and dashboard) on an ongoing basis.

The information collected from the HBM laboratory network (including name, contact, country, substances and matrices analyzed) was translated into an interactive map in May 2024, developed by Task 3.2 and hosted on the PARC website. During the rest of Y3 the information and visualization was polished. The work to include new networks in the map has been foreseen for Y4, starting with air laboratory network and following with water field.

A9.1.2 Promote the development of new laboratory networks and support their consolidation

Partners: led by FISABIO with collaboration from INERIS, AU, BRGM, FMUL, INSA, ISCIII, MU, NPHSL, LNS, NIPH, SCIENSANO, ISSeP, FNS, VSCHT, GCSL, NMBU

The list of criteria to identify the level of development, experience, extension, etc. of the networks was created during Y3, which will allow us to identify the weak points that need to be improved/developed to achieve better interaction among laboratories. During Y4, these points/criteria will be applied to the laboratory networks created, to establish their different level of development. The list will serve as a living document and will be updated alongside the gradual

¹¹ AMD-101057014-118: The Spanish affiliated entity Fundación Profesor Novoa Santos - PARC acronym "FNS", has changed its name to Fundación Pública Galega de Investigación Biomédica INIBIC (FINIBIC) as of 06/05/2024. The list of affiliated entities must be updated accordingly. The acronym FNS must be replaced by FINIBIC in the WP9 where they are contributors

creation of the networks. The analysis of the alternatives to the sustainability of the networks (out of research projects) will continue during Y4.

A9.1.3 Facilitate the coordination and linkage of existing and new laboratory networks

Partners: led by CSIC with collaboration from INERIS, BRGM, FMUL, INSA, LNE, MU, LNS, STAMI, ISCIII, ISSeP, FINIBIC, VSCHT, GCSL, NMBU

Initial strategies and tools to achieve the coordination and linkage of the networks were defined during Y2 and Y3, however due to the process of laboratory network creation was longer than expected, no activities of coordination have been yet carried out. During Y4, the first activities will be implemented.

A9.1.4 Develop an interactive tool (dashboard) to show the capacities of the laboratory networks

The concept and design of the dashboard was established in Y2 in collaboration with Task 3.2, Task 7.2 and all the Task 9.1 partners.

The PARC Data Hub is under development together with Task 7.2 and Task 9.2 and will show, during Y4, the information on the laboratory networks, including the laboratories integrating each network and their analytical capacities, among other information. This will be a very useful tool for users to search and find laboratories of interest by country, matrices or chemical substances analyzed, sample quantity, quantification limit, etc.

The HBM laboratory network will be the first implemented on the dashboard. For the upcoming years, the dashboard will be continuously fed with updated information and new laboratory networks.

Task 9.2: Building exposure monitoring capacities

Leader: MU (CZ)

A9.2.1 Mapping of exposure monitoring capacities

Partners: ANSES, Inserm, Oniris, LNE, SpF, ISSeP, Sciensano, IMROH, MU, VSCHT, AU, NCPHP, NPHSL, LNS, UU-IRAS, STAMI, FMUL, INSA, ENSP, SZU-SK, CSIC, ISCIII, AUTH, BPI, GCSL

Mapping of the existing biomonitoring and environmental exposure monitoring networks initiated in the first three years in close collaboration with WP 4.1 and 4.2 will continue in Y4 with indoor exposure mapping. Together with Task 7.2 and Task 9.1, first prototype of PARC Data Hub will be developed, drawing from the experience with the Power Bi tool presenting the outcomes of ongoing surveys. Specific attention will be paid to the harmonisation of parameters (such as biomarkers) collected across various surveys. Surveys mapping capacities (networks, projects, databases) on toxicology resources, initiated in Y3 will be further developed and updated. First visualisations of consumer product databases will be developed, in cooperation with WP6.

A9.2.2 Strengthening of exposure monitoring capacities

Partners: ANSES, LNE, SpF, ISSeP, Sciensano, IMROH, MU, VSCHT, AU, LNS, UU-IRAS, FMUL, INSA, ENSP, JSI, CSIC, ISCIII, GCSL

Joint development and update of PARC Data Hub with Task 9.1, Task 7.2 and relevant WP4 partners will provide new tools not only for presenting data on existing biomonitoring and environmental monitoring networks, laboratories and databases but for assessment of gaps and future needs. This will provide a base for better targeting of research initiatives in WP4 but also for setting priorities and development of surveys in other WPs.

Task 9.3: Joint activities – harmonisation

Leader: WR (NL)

Partners: UNIVIE (AT), SCIENSANO (BE), MU (CZ), VSCHT (CZ), UBA (DE), RegionH (DK), AU (DK), CSIC (ES), ISCHII (ES), FINIBIC (ES), INRAE (FR), ANSES (FR), BRGM (FR), INERIS (FR), LNE (FR), ONIRIS (FR), BPI (GR), GCSL (GR), LNS (LU), NIPH (NO), UNN (NO), STAMI (NO), NMBU (NO), INSA (PT), JSI (SI), NLZOH (SI)

Transversal activity: Towards harmonised QA/QC in laboratory testing

This activity focuses on quantitative chemical analysis methods and toxicity assays. Suspect- and non-target screening and bioanalytical assays are dealt with in T4.3. In Y1-3 inventories on existing QA/QC regarding sampling, chemical analysis, and toxicity testing/toxicokinetics studies were done. Subsequently, five working groups (see below) drafted the first guidance documents with minimum requirements on various QA/QC parameters focussing on sample types and substances/techniques prioritised/used in WP4 and WP5 in the first half of PARC. In Y4 the guidance documents will be disseminated in WP4 and WP5, through the relevant task- and project leaders, through PARC internal laboratory contact lists, and to the wider community/stakeholders via the PARC website and/or PARCopedia. Online meetings will be held for project leads and people responsible for QA/QC in WP4 and WP5 to discuss the guidances for their implementation, and to collect feedback and needs. This will be used to initiate revision and extension of the guidance documents. Further 9.3 online meetings foreseen in Y4: core group (WG co-leads) 2-3x, WG meetings (4-10 per WG), and T9.3 plenary 1-2x, of which one in person.

Working groups and contributors:

WG-1: Overarching QA/QC working group on Sampling. Includes: fit-for-purpose sampling, passive sampling, pretreatment, storage/stability, artifacts, uncertainty. Lead: AU, LNE. Partners: ANSES-LSAI PCPPA, ONIRIS, INERIS, BRGM, LNE, Sciensano, MU, AU, LNS, STAMI, NMBU, UNN, INSA, JSI, CSIC, ISCHII, FINIBIC, BPI.

WG-2: Overarching QA/QC working group on Performance criteria chemical analysis. Includes: limit of detection and quantification (LOD/LOQ), identification, trueness/precision criteria, calibration, validation, batch control, measurement uncertainty. Lead: MU. Partners: ANSES, INRAE, ONIRIS, INERIS, BRGM, LNE, UNIVIE, Sciensano, MU, VSCHT, RegionH, UBA, LNS, WR, NIPH, STAMI, NMBU, UNN, INSA, JSI, BPI, GCSL.

WG-3: Overarching QA/QC working group on Assessment of interlab comparability chemical analysis. Includes: (evaluation of) protocols for proficiency testing (PT/ICI/EQUAS), small-scale interlab comparisons, catalogue for PT providers, catalogue (C)RMs. Lead: ANSES, LNE. Partners:

ANSES, ONIRIS, INERIS, BRGM, LNE, Sciensano, MU, VSCHT, UBA, LNS, WR, NIPH, INSA, JSI, CSIC, ISCIII, BPI, GCSL.

WG-4: Overarching QA/QC working group on Reporting and acceptability of results from chemical analysis. Includes: reporting requirements, normalisation of results, acceptability of lab data, criteria for qualification of labs. Lead: ONIRIS, LNS. Partners: ANSES, INRAE, ONIRIS, INERIS, BRGM, LNE, UNIVIE, Sciensano, MU, VSCHT, AU, UBA, LNS, WR, NIPH, NMBU, INSA, JSI, CSIC, BPI, GCSL.

WG-5: QA/QC EDA, moved from T9.3 to T4.3

WG-6: Overarching QA/QC working group on Toxicity testing & kinetic studies. Includes: in vivo and in vitro test systems (novel approach methods, NAMs), reporting. Lead: NIPH, STAMI. Partners: ANSES, INERIS, Sciensano, LNS, WR, NIPH, STAMI, NMBU, INSA, FINIBIC.

Task 9.4: Training

Leader: INSA (PT)

Partners: ANSES (FR), INRAE (FR), ONIRIS (FR), BRGM (FR), LNE (FR), UMIT (AT), Sciensano (BE), MU (CZ), VSCHT (CZ), IRFM (IT), RSU (LV), NPHSL (LT), LNS (LU), STAMI (NO), NMBU (NO), ENSP (PT), UAVR (PT), JSI (SI), ULFFA (SI), NIJZ (SI), CSIC (ES), ISCIII (ES), FINIBIC (ES), IMM-KI (SE), BPI (GR), GCSL (GR), UEF (FI)

In order to achieve a flexible and dynamic training plan, adjusted to PARC progress and stakeholder needs, by Y4, Task 9.4 will again request to NHCs the distribution of 2nd training needs online survey (refined on the basis of the results obtained in the 1st survey) to all NH members (PARC and beyond). Data obtained will be thoroughly analysed by partners under the coordination of NPHSL (LT) and INSA (PT) and used to build the 2nd PARC Training Plan (AD9.2, to be submitted by M42, Oct 2025), that will cover M43 to M66 (Nov 2025 to Oct 2027).

Up to October 2025, Task 9.4 will continue the implementation of the 1st PARC training plan (AD9.1), developed to cover the topics identified by partners and stakeholders. This includes two in-person training courses (1. New approach methodologies; and 2. AOPs and IATAs) carried out under the scientific coordination of MU, CZ and KI, SE, respectively, and aimed at both PARC partners and stakeholders. The local organizers of training events to be carried out under PARC will receive support from Task 9.4 members, covering dissemination, registration, preparation and distribution of certificates, preparation, distribution of training evaluation surveys, and training evaluation assessment (activity coordinated by NIJZ, SI). Task 9.4 partners will also develop additional high-quality e-learning materials on topics identified for non-formal learning, upon partner availability and potential synergies emerging under SYNET to ensure continuous innovation.

To foster on the job training, Task 9.4 partners will continue to encourage staff exchange amongst PARC partners. A close follow-up of this activity will be carried out to ensure proper dissemination of the initiative, and new strategies will be implemented in case of need.

In parallel, task partners will continue to work on the identification of external training (outside PARC), namely events and online resources on relevant topics under the coordination of UAVR (PT); all events/materials found relevant will be indicated on PARC website.

A summary of all training activities carried out from M30 to M42 will be presented and discussed in D9.9, Report on training activities M30 to M42, to be submitted by M45.

Deliverables:

D9.9: Report on training events Y3, initially due M36 is modified in “Report on training activities M30 to M42” and is postponed to M45 (leader: INSA) in order to describe all activities from M30 to M42 (end of PARC 1st training plan). This modification will be included in the next amendment of the GA

D9.10: Report on training events Y4, initially due M48 is cancelled. This will be included in the next amendment of the GA.

Additional Deliverables:

AD9.2: Training plan, version 2 - Leader: INSA (M42)

Table 2.2.b: AWP Set of Activities

Activity No	Activity Title	Lead Participant No	Short name of lead participant	Person-Months	Start Month	End month
1	Coordination and management	1	ANSES	239.0	37	48
2	A common science-policy agenda	3/12	EAA/EEA	190.5	37	48
3	Synergies, collaborations and awareness	29/36.2	INSA/GCSL	189.9	37	48
4	Monitoring and exposure	15/2	UBA/SpF	1 461.7	37	48
5	Hazard Assessment	16/1	BfR/ANSES	1 769.0	37	48
6	Innovation in regulatory RA	25/35.7	RIVM/KEMI	1 241.3	37	48
7	FAIR Data	4/59	VITO/UOB	310.4	37	48
8	Concepts and toolboxes	36/20.6	AUTH/UNINA	194.0	37	48
9	Building infrastructural and human capacities	34/8	ISCIH/MU	229.0	37	48
			TOTAL	5 824.8		

Table 2.2.c: Additional Deliverables List

WP	AD N°	Related Task and project(s)	AD name	Lead participant Short name	Type[1]	Dissemination level[2]	Delivery date
4	AD4.11	T4.1 (P4.1.4.2.a_Y1)	Progress report statistical analyses	VITO	R	PU	Initially planned M36, postponed M48
5	AD5.8	T5.1 (P5.1.1.c_Y3)	Study Report	ANSES	R	PU	M41
6	AD6.17	T6.4 (P6.4.1.a_Y1 and P6.4.1.b_Y1)	Optimizing regulatory risk assessment and management of chemical mixtures in Europe	RWTH	R	PU	Initially planned M36, postponed M40
9	AD9.2	T9.4	Training plan, version 2	INSA	R	PU	M42

2.3 Resources to be committed

Table 2.3.a: Summary effort table

	WP1	WP2	WP3	WP4	WP5	WP6	WP7	WP8	WP9	Total PMs per partner
1-ANSES	122.7	12.0	1.0	51.0	78.0	75.5	29.7	0.0	0.9	370.8
1.1-INSERM	0.5	4.5	0.0	12.1	134.0	9.7	3.1	0.2	3.0	167.1
1.2-INRAE	0.4	0.0	0.0	44.9	85.6	8.0	0.0	0.0	2.2	141.2
1.3-CEA	0.0	0.0	0.0	6.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	6.0
1.4-INERIS	0.4	0.0	0.0	15.2	38.2	10.5	0.0	0.0	0.1	64.4
1.5-CNRS	0.0	0.0	0.0	1.0	61.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	62.0
1.6-INRS	0.0	0.0	0.0	13.3	8.6	3.0	2.0	0.0	0.0	26.9
1.7-ONIRIS	0.0	0.0	0.0	18.9	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	1.4	20.3
1.8-IRSN	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	3.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	3.0
1.9-OFB	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.8	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.8
1.10-BRGM	0.0	0.0	0.0	7.8	0.0	0.0	2.5	0.0	3.8	14.1
1.11-LNE	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.2	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	3.6	3.8
1.12-CSTB	0.0	0.0	0.0	4.4	0.0	1.5	0.0	0.0	0.0	5.9
1.13-EHESP	0.0	0.0	0.0	16.7	0.0	4.5	0.0	0.0	0.0	21.2
2-SpF	6.7	3.0	0.5	71.1	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	3.0	84.3
3-EAA	5.1	4.5	4.7	5.5	0.0	1.5	0.0	0.0	0.0	21.3
3.1-AGES	0.3	0.0	2.0	0.0	0.0	13.8	0.0	0.0	0.0	16.0
3.2-AIT	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0
3.3-BNN	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0
3.4-MUI	0.0	0.0	0.0	24.4	13.9	1.5	0.0	0.0	0.0	39.8
3.5-MUW	0.0	0.0	0.0	2.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	2.0
3.6-UG-AT	0.0	1.0	0.0	2.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	3.0
3.7-UIBK	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0
3.8-UMIT	0.0	0.0	2.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	1.0	3.0

3.9-UNIVIE	0.0	0.0	0.0	6.2	12.8	0.0	0.0	0.0	4.6	23.6
4-VITO	5.9	0.0	1.0	48.8	0.0	30.7	53.4	3.0	0.0	142.8
4.1-KU Leuven	0.0	0.0	0.0	11.4	7.3	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	18.7
4.2-DOMG	3.3	1.3	2.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	6.6
4.3-UH	0.0	0.0	0.0	2.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	2.0
4.4-PIH	0.0	0.0	0.0	5.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	5.0
4.5-OVAM	0.0	0.0	0.0	3.3	0.0	0.3	0.0	0.0	0.0	3.6
4.6-SSeP	0.0	0.0	0.0	31.0	0.0	13.0	6.4	0.5	3.7	54.6
4.7-UAntwerpen	0.0	0.0	0.0	21.9	36.0	11.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	68.9
5-SCIENSANO	0.6	0.0	0.0	11.8	27.3	47.1	0.0	0.0	5.1	91.7
5.1-UGent	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	16.8	6.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	22.8
5.2-EV-ILVO	0.0	1.0	0.0	0.9	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	1.9
5.3-VUB	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	36.5	4.7	0.0	0.0	0.0	41.2
6-CIPH	1.1	0.5	1.0	1.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	3.6
6.1-IMROH	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	2.0	0.0	1.0	3.0
7-MOH-CY/SGL	1.1	0.5	1.0	28.8	0.0	1.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	32.4
7.1-SHSO	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0
8-MU	4.7	3.0	2.5	51.0	26.5	52.8	76.9	21.6	44.3	283.3
8.1-SZU-CZ	0.0	0.0	0.0	12.9	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	12.9
8.2-VSCHT	0.0	0.0	0.0	7.6	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	3.9	11.5
8.3-OU	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0
8.4-JU	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.4	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.4
9-UZIS	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.6	0.0	0.0	0.6
10-DEPA	1.5	0.5	1.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	3.0
10.1-AU	0.4	0.0	0.0	37.1	0.0	11.3	0.0	0.0	5.0	53.7
10.2-DTU	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	68.1	19.4	0.0	0.0	0.0	87.5

10.3-REGIONH	0.0	0.0	0.0	15.0	0.0	23.5	0.0	0.0	0.0	38.5
10.4-UCPH	0.0	0.0	0.0	2.9	0.0	6.3	0.0	0.0	0.0	9.2
10.5-SDU	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	23.6	3.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	26.6
11-HB	1.2	0.5	1.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	2.7
11.1-SOM	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0
11.2-UT	0.0	0.0	0.0	12.5	0.0	18.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	30.5
12-EEA	4.0	13.0	13.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	3.8	0.0	33.8
13-THL	0.1	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.1
13.1-SYKES	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.8	0.0	4.6	0.0	0.0	0.0	5.4
14-TTL	1.5	0.5	1.0	22.4	0.5	8.6	0.0	5.0	0.0	39.5
14.1-FFA	0.0	0.0	0.0	4.2	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	4.2
14.2-Tukes	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	1.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	1.0
14.3-UOULU	0.0	0.0	0.0	1.1	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	1.1
14.4 - UEF	0.0	0.0	0.0	2.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	1.0	3.0
14.5 - TAU	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	6.0	0.0	6.0
15-UBA	4.8	5.6	2.8	77.7	0.0	29.5	3.3	4.6	3.1	131.3
15.1-BfG	0.0	0.0	0.0	1.3	9.5	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	10.8
15.2-UFZ	0.0	1.0	0.0	30.3	47.9	33.3	1.0	0.0	0.0	113.5
15.3-IPA	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0
15.4-UKOLD	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0
15.5 - UOS	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	5.3	0.0	0.0	0.0	5.3
15.6 - KUM	0.0	0.0	0.0	5.2	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	5.2
15.7 - UDE	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	10.3	19.5	0.0	0.0	0.0	29.8
15.8 - RWTH	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	6.4	0.0	0.0	0.0	6.4
16 - BfR	5.9	18.3	0.9	0.0	97.6	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	122.7
16.1 - Fraunhofer	0.0	1.0	0.0	5.0	14.2	4.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	24.2
16.2 - KIT	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	26.9	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	26.9
16.3 - IUF	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	29.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	29.0
16.4 - IfADo	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0

16.5 - MLU	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0
16.6 - RPTU	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	12.0	31.5	0.0	0.0	0.0	43.5
16.7 - TUB	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0
16.8 - UKON	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.5	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.5
16.9 - TiHo	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	6.8	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	6.8
16.10 - UKK	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	33.6	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	33.6
17 - NPHC	1.8	5.5	14.0	14.0	25.9	0.0	0.0	0.0	3.0	64.2
18 - UI	1.5	1.7	1.0	5.2	0.0	1.3	0.0	0.0	0.0	10.7
19 - MOH	0.0	0.0	1.0	6.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	7.0
20 - ISS	0.7	0.0	1.0	15.4	13.5	19.5	0.0	0.0	0.0	50.1
20.1 - ICPS	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	7.8	0.0	0.0	0.0	7.8
20.2 - CNR-IRSA	0.0	0.0	0.0	3.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	3.0
20.3 - IRFM	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	13.8	6.3	0.0	0.0	0.4	20.5
20.4 - IUSS	0.0	0.0	1.0	0.0	0.0	6.0	0.0	19.0	0.0	26.0
20.5 - UMIL	0.0	0.0	0.0	4.5	23.1	3.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	30.6
20.6 - UNINA	3.0	0.0	0.1	2.1	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	5.2
20.7 - UNIPD	0.0	0.0	0.0	2.0	0.0	1.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	3.0
21 - RSU	1.2	0.5	1.0	33.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.4	36.1
21.1 - UL	0.0	0.0	0.0	3.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	3.0
22 - NPHSL	1.0	0.5	1.0	0.3	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	8.9	11.7
23 - LSMU	0.0	0.0	0.0	6.2	0.0	2.5	0.0	0.0	0.0	8.7
24 - LNS	2.5	3.5	2.0	77.9	0.0	5.6	0.0	0.0	8.2	99.7
24.1 - LIH	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	60.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	60.0
24.2 - LIST	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	3.0	2.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	5.0
24.3 - UniLU	0.0	0.0	0.0	14.8	0.0	0.0	2.0	0.0	0.0	16.8
25 - RIVM	5.0	0.5	1.9	0.1	13.7	57.1	0.0	12.0	0.0	90.2
25.1 - KWR	0.0	0.0	0.0	3.2	0.0	2.7	1.1	0.0	0.0	7.0
25.2 - TNO	0.3	0.0	0.0	0.5	0.0	9.8	4.1	0.0	0.0	14.7
25.3-RUMC	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0

25.4-UL-LACDR	0.3	0.0	0.0	0.0	60.4	8.9	27.4	1.9	0.0	98.9
25.5-UU-IRAS	0.0	0.0	0.0	5.6	30.7	22.6	0.0	0.0	0.0	58.9
25.6-VUA	0.4	0.0	0.0	19.6	8.0	14.5	0.0	0.0	0.0	42.5
25.7-WR	0.4	0.0	0.0	9.4	4.5	3.8	1.3	0.0	6.0	25.3
25.8-WU-TOX	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	17.1	3.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	20.1
25.9-SRU	0.0	0.0	0.0	10.5	0.0	8.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	18.5
26-NIPH	1.2	2.0	1.0	30.2	60.0	19.9	2.0	0.0	1.9	118.2
26.1-IMR	0.0	1.0	0.0	0.0	4.2	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	5.2
26.2-STAMI	0.0	0.7	4.3	7.2	9.0	17.0	0.0	0.0	5.1	43.2
26.3-NILU	0.0	0.0	0.0	9.0	1.0	2.5	0.0	0.0	0.0	12.5
26.4-NIVA	0.2	0.1	0.0	0.0	12.3	16.5	3.9	1.0	0.0	34.0
26.5-NMBU	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	11.1	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	11.1
26.6-NVI	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	12.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	12.0
26.7-UNN	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.3	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	1.1	1.4
27-NIOM	1.3	1.5	1.0	1.9	0.0	19.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	24.7
27.1-IEP-NRI	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	14.3	25.2	0.0	0.0	0.0	39.5
27.2-UG-PL	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	23.2	15.0	12.6	0.0	0.0	50.7
27.3-WULS-SGGW	0.0	0.0	0.0	12.3	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	12.3
28-FMUL	0.0	0.0	4.6	0.0	0.0	4.6	0.0	0.0	4.5	13.7
28.1-PL	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0
28.2-UM	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0
29-INSA	9.4	14.0	36.6	30.7	32.5	12.0	0.0	0.0	16.5	151.7
29.1-APA	1.0	0.0	3.5	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	4.5
29.2-DGS	0.0	1.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	1.0	0.0	2.0
29.3-ENSP	0.0	4.0	3.0	0.5	0.5	6.1	0.0	0.0	3.0	17.1
29.4-UC	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	5.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	5.0
29.5-UAVR	0.0	1.0	2.6	0.0	16.1	7.0	0.0	0.0	2.8	29.5
30-SZU-SK	3.1	1.0	1.0	6.5	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	1.3	12.9
30.1-UK	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	1.2	1.2

31-JSI	0.5	0.7	1.5	54.3	7.0	1.4	25.6	0.0	3.3	94.3
31.1-GeoZS	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	7.5	0.0	0.0	0.0	7.5
31.2-NIB	0.0	0.0	3.0	0.0	41.5	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	44.5
31.3-NIC	0.0	0.0	1.5	0.0	23.0	0.0	0.0	7.0	0.0	31.5
31.4-ULFFA	0.0	0.0	0.0	2.3	2.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	1.0	5.3
31.5-MFUM	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.3	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.3
32-NIJZ	4.5	2.0	5.5	10.4	0.0	15.8	6.0	0.0	2.5	46.7
32.1-OI	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	6.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	6.0
32.2-NLZOH	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.2	0.0	0.2	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.4
32.3-ARSO	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0
32.4-UKCMB	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0
33- CSIC	0.4	0.0	0.0	40.9	54.8	27.0	0.0	0.0	17.8	140.9
33.1-ULPGC	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.4	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.4
33.2-UNAV	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	24.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	24.0
33.3-UGR	0.0	0.0	0.0	19.0	0.0	5.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	24.0
33.4-UPO	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	6.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	6.0
34-ISCIII	5.2	0.5	2.0	37.8	34.8	30.0	0.0	0.0	31.4	141.7
34.1-EASP	0.0	0.0	0.0	5.3	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	5.3
34.2-FISABIO	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.7	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	2.0	2.7
34.3-FINBA	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	25.3	0.0	0.0	0.0	25.3
34.4-FNS	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	3.2	3.2
34.5-IISPV	0.3	1.0	0.0	2.2	17.0	19.5	24.0	0.0	0.0	64.0
34.6-INSST	0.0	0.0	0.0	1.3	0.0	0.0	0.0	2.0	0.0	3.3
34.7-UCLM	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	12.5	0.0	0.0	0.0	12.5
34.8-UPV/EHU	0.0	0.0	0.0	7.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	7.0
35-SEPA	1.1	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	1.1

35.1-UGOT	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0
35.2-KI	0.0	0.0	0.0	3.5	1.0	8.3	0.5	0.0	2.0	15.3
35.3-ULUND	0.0	0.0	0.0	13.8	0.0	0.6	0.0	0.0	0.0	14.4
35.4-ORU	0.0	0.0	0.0	9.7	0.0	3.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	12.7
35.5-RISE	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	8.7	0.0	0.0	0.0	8.7
35.6-SU	0.3	0.0	0.0	8.5	6.5	61.5	0.0	0.0	0.0	76.8
35.7-KEMI	3.2	1.0	1.0	0.0	0.0	17.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	22.2
35.8-IVL	0.0	0.0	0.0	19.2	0.0	10.2	0.0	9.0	0.0	38.4
35.9-SLV	1.0	0.0	1.0	1.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	3.0
35.10-SLU	0.0	1.0	0.0	11.0	12.0	10.5	0.0	0.0	0.0	34.5
35.11-UMU	0.0	0.0	0.0	2.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	15.2	0.0	17.2
35.12-UU	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	25.5	0.0	8.2	0.0	0.0	33.7
36-AUTH	5.6	36.0	10.0	31.9	25.0	14.5	4.0	73.0	3.2	203.1
36.1-EFET	0.0	0.0	5.5	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	5.5
36.2-GCSL	3.0	5.0	19.0	1.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	3.1	31.1
36.3-NKUA	0.0	1.0	10.5	10.5	0.0	0.0	0.0	7.5	0.0	29.5
36.4-UOC	0.0	0.0	3.9	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	3.9
37-BPI	0.3	0.0	2.5	16.8	51.2	40.7	0.0	0.0	3.7	115.1
38-FOPH	0.0	0.0	1.0	1.0	0.0	0.5	0.0	0.0	0.0	2.5
39-AGROSCOPE	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0
40-UNISANTE	0.0	0.0	0.0	5.0	0.0	14.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	19.0
41-EAWAG	0.0	0.0	0.0	20.9	0.0	2.3	0.0	0.0	0.0	23.2
42-ETHZ	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0
43-EMPA	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0
44-FOEN	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	6.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	6.0
45-USI	0.0	0.0	0.0	6.2	0.0	2.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	8.2
46-UNIBAS	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	3.0	6.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	9.0
47-SECO	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.8	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.8

48-ECHA	0.0	24.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	24.0
49-EFSA	0.0	5.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	4.0	2.0	0.0	0.0	11.0
50-UKHSA	2.0	1.0	2.0	3.0	1.5	0.0	0.0	0.0	1.0	10.5
51-BUL	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0
52-Cefas-Defra	0.0	1.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.7	0.0	1.7
53-UKCEH	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	17.2	0.0	0.0	0.0	17.2
54-EA	0.0	0.0	0.0	1.0	0.5	0.6	0.0	0.0	0.0	2.1
55-HSE	0.0	0.0	0.0	6.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	6.0
56-IOM	0.0	0.0	0.0	1.1	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	1.1
57-UBAH	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0
58-UNIABDN	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0
59-UOB	3.0	1.0	1.0	0.0	0.0	4.3	5.0	0.0	0.0	14.3
60-UCL	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0
61-EPA	1.2	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	1.2
62-DCU	0.0	0.0	0.0	13.2	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	13.2
63-UCD	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0
64-IPHMNE	1.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	1.0
Total PMs	239.0	190.5	189.9	1461.7	1769.0	1241.3	310.4	194.0	229.0	5824.8

Table 2.3.b: Other major cost items (travel, equipment, infrastructure, goods and services)

1.2 - INRAE	Cost (€)	Justification
Other Goods, Works & Services	100 000	Laboratory consumables including labeled molecules as part of project P5.1.1.b_Y1
Remaining purchase costs (<15% of pers. Costs)	86 700	
Total	186 700	
1.6 - INRS	Cost (€)	Justification
Other Goods, Works & Services	20 500	Laboratory consumables including for HMRS analysis and other goods as part of projects P4.3.1.b_Y1 (4 000€), P4.3.1.d_Y1 (2 000€), P4.3.2.b_Y2 (8 000€), P4.3.2.c_Y3 (3 000€), P5.1.1.b_Y1 (500€) and P6.2.1.b_Y1 (3 000€)

Equipment	15 000	Depreciation cost for an LC-HRMS equipment as part of project P4.3.2.b_Y2
Remaining purchase costs (<15% of pers. Costs)	28 340	
Total	63 840	
1.7 - ONIRIS	Cost (€)	Justification
Other Goods, Works & Services	11 500	Consumables and publication costs as part of projects P4.1.1.3.a_Y4 (7 500€) and P4.3.3.b_Y2 (4 000€)
Remaining purchase costs (<15% of pers. Costs)	12 440	
Total	23 940	
3 - EAA	Cost (€)	Justification
Travel and subsistence	13 280	Travel and subsistence for the Stakeholder Forum members to participate in the Stakeholder Forum meetings (12 450€) Travel and subsistence for 1 person to attend the SYNET Forum (830€)
Remaining purchase costs (<15% of pers. Costs)	24 510	
Total	37 790	
3.4 - MUI	Cost (€)	Justification
Other Goods, Works & Services	29 500	Consumables as part of projects P4.3.2.b_Y2 (19 500€) and P4.3.2.c_Y3 (10 000€)
Remaining purchase costs (<15% of pers. Costs)	38 686	
Total	68 186	
4.7 - UAntwerpen	Cost (€)	Justification
Other Goods, Works & Services	4 000	Consumables including LC-MS consumables for project P4.3.2.c_Y3
Remaining purchase costs (<15% of pers. Costs)	72 810	
Total	76 810	
5.2 - EV-ILVO	Cost (€)	Justification
Other Goods, Works & Services	875	Consumables and reagents for project P4.3.4.a_Y2
Remaining purchase costs (<15% of pers. Costs)	2 620	
Total	3 495	
5.3 - VUB	Cost (€)	Justification
Other Goods, Works & Services	25 000	Running costs for sample preparations and analysis, and consumables related to experiments in project P5.2.1.c_Y1

Remaining purchase costs (<15% of pers. Costs)	45 920	
Total	70 920	
6 - CIPH	Cost (€)	Justification
Travel and subsistence	830	Travel and subsistence for 1 person to attend NHCP meetings
Remaining purchase costs (<15% of pers. Costs)	1 660	
Total	2 490	
6.1 - IMROH	Cost (€)	Justification
Travel and subsistence	5 950	Travel and subsistence for: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - 1 person to attend 1 meeting in WP4 - 2 persons to attend 2 meetings in WP6 - 2 persons to attend 1 meeting in WP7 - 1 person to attend 2 meetings in WP9
Remaining purchase costs (<15% of pers. Costs)	830	
Total	6 780	
7 - MOH-CY / SGL	Cost (€)	Justification
Other Goods, Works & Services	45 500	Consumables as part of project P4.2.c_Y3 (30 000€) and P6.2.3.a_Y1 (5 500€), and costs for analysis for HBM surveys as part of P4.1.1.2.a_Y1 (10 000€)
Remaining purchase costs (<15% of pers. Costs)	20 190	
Total	65 690	
7.1 - SHSO	Cost (€)	Justification
Other Goods, Works & Services	3 000	Consumables for HBM surves as part of task 4.1
Travel and subsistence	1 060	Travel for 1 person to attend 1 meeting in WP4
Remaining purchase costs (<15% of pers. Costs)	0	
Total	4 060	
8.2 - VSCHT	Cost (€)	Justification
Other Goods, Works & Services	49 000	Consumables and chemicals, including consumables for LC-MS and GC-MS as part of task 4.2 (40 000€), projects P4.2.c_Y3 (5 000€), and P4.2.a_Y1 (4 000€)
Remaining purchase costs (<15% of pers. Costs)	7 490	
Total	56 490	
8.3 - OU	Cost (€)	Justification

Travel and subsistence	830	Travel for 1 person to attend 1 meeting in WP4
Remaining purchase costs (<15% of pers. Costs)	0	
Total	830	
8.4 - JU	Cost (€)	Justification
Other Goods, Works & Services	1 200	Consumables for analysis as part of projects P4.3.3.a_Y1 and P4.3.3.b_Y2
Travel and subsistence	830	Travel and subsistence for 1 person to attend 1 meeting for task 4.1
Remaining purchase costs (<15% of pers. Costs)	0	
Total	2 030	
9 - UZIS	Cost (€)	Justification
Travel and subsistence	1 422	Travel and subsistence for 2 persons to attend 1 consortium meeting in WP7
Remaining purchase costs (<15% of pers. Costs)	0	
Total	1 422	
10.4 - UCPH	Cost (€)	Justification
Other Goods, Works & Services	32 000	Consumables and materials such as skin cell model with human keratinocytes and human fibroblasts, and MSD as part of project P6.4.1.c_Y3
Remaining purchase costs (<15% of pers. Costs)	10 000	
Total	42 000	
10.5 - SDU	Cost (€)	Justification
Travel and subsistence	1 060	Travel and subsistence for 1 person to attend to 1 meeting in WP5
Remaining purchase costs (<15% of pers. Costs)	30 107	
Total	31 167	
11 - HB	Cost (€)	Justification
Travel and subsistence	830	Travel and subsistence for 1 person to attend to 1 meeting in WP1
Remaining purchase costs (<15% of pers. Costs)	830	
Total	1 660	
11.1 - SOM	Cost (€)	Justification
Travel and subsistence	2 950	Travel and subsistence for 1 person to attend Governing Board meeting in WP1 (830€) and for 1 person to attend 2 meetings in WP2 (2 120€)

Remaining purchase costs (<15% of pers. Costs)	0	
Total	2 950	
13 - THL	Cost (€)	Justification
Travel and subsistence	1 060	Travel and subsistence for 1 person to attend 1 meeting in WP1
Remaining purchase costs (<15% of pers. Costs)	-	
Total	1 060	
14.2 - Tukes	Cost (€)	Justification
Travel and subsistence	2 000	Travel and subsistence for 1 person to attend 2 meeting as part of project P6.4.3.b_Y3
Remaining purchase costs (<15% of pers. Costs)	0	
Total	2 000	
14.4 - UEF	Cost (€)	Justification
Other Goods, Works & Services	4 000	Consumables for UHPLC-MS analysis as part of project P4.3.2.b_Y2
Remaining purchase costs (<15% of pers. Costs)	830	
Total	4 830	
15.6 - KUM	Cost (€)	Justification
Other Goods, Works & Services	2 500	Lab chemicals, tips, tubes, microsampling devices (VAMS, DBS), Instrument consumables (argon, sample cups), etc. related to project P4.3.2.a_Y1
Remaining purchase costs (<15% of pers. Costs)	4 320	
Total	6 820	
16.1 - Fraunhofer	Cost (€)	Justification
Other Goods, Works & Services	20 000	Consumables for analyses including material for hiPSC culture, antibodies, assay kits, chemicals as part of projects P5.3.4.b_Y4
Remaining purchase costs (<15% of pers. Costs)	18 980	
Total	38 980	
16.3 - IUF	Cost (€)	Justification
Other Goods, Works & Services	40 000	Consumables for project P5.2.1.e_Y1
Remaining purchase costs (<15% of pers. Costs)	1 060	
Total	41 060	
16.5 - MLU	Cost (€)	Justification

Travel and subsistence	830	Travel and subsistence for 1 person to attend to 1 meeting in WP1
Remaining purchase costs (<15% of pers. Costs)	0	
Total	830	
16.8 - UKON	Cost (€)	Justification
Other Goods, Works & Services	23 645	Consumables for project P5.2.1.e_Y1: reagents for toxicological test and reagents for cell culture (hPSC)
Travel and subsistence	1 890	Travel and subsistence for 1 person to attend 1 meeting in WP1 and 1 meeting in WP5
Remaining purchase costs (<15% of pers. Costs)	0	
Total	25 535	
16.9 - TiHo	Cost (€)	Justification
Other Goods, Works & Services	20 000	Consumables for project P5.2.1.e_Y1: Cell culture medium for stem cell culture, Cell culture plastic ware, cell culture medium additives, antibodies, chemicals
Remaining purchase costs (<15% of pers. Costs)	830	
Total	20 830	
17 - NCPHP	Cost (€)	Justification
Other Goods, Works & Services	64 971	Reagents, consumables, kits, cell culture as part of projects P5.2.1.d_Y1 (22 607€) and P5.2.1.g_Y4 (42 364€)
Remaining purchase costs (<15% of pers. Costs)	21 760	
Total	86 731	
19 - MOH	Cost (€)	Justification
Other Goods, Works & Services	10 706	Consumables and costs for analysis as part of HBM survey in project P4.1.1.2.a_Y1
Remaining purchase costs (<15% of pers. Costs)	1 060	
Total	11 766	
20 - ISS	Cost (€)	Justification
Other Goods, Works & Services	78 000	Consumables for project P4.2.a_Y1
Remaining purchase costs (<15% of pers. Costs)	48 430	
Total	126 430	
20.5 - UMIL	Cost (€)	Justification
Other Goods, Works & Services	30 000	Consumables for project P5.1.1.b_Y1: Chemicals, antibodies, ELISA kits, cell culture medium and supplements, buffy coats, etc

Remaining purchase costs (<15% of pers. Costs)	25 053	
Total	55 053	
20.6 - UNINA	Cost (€)	Justification
Other Goods, Works & Services	5 357	Publications costs as WP8 co-leader
Travel and subsistence	1 890	Travel and subsistence costs for 1 person to attend 2 meetings in WP3 and 1 meeting in WP4
Remaining purchase costs (<15% of pers. Costs)	4 380	
Total	11 627	
20.7 - UNIPD	Cost (€)	Justification
Travel and subsistence	3 000	Travel and subsistence for 2 persons to attend 2 meetings in WP6
Remaining purchase costs (<15% of pers. Costs)	1 277	
Total	4 277	
21 - RSU	Cost (€)	Justification
Other Goods, Works & Services	29 837	Consumables and costs for analysis as part of HealthCare survey in project P4.1.1.4.c_Y1 (15 000€) and HBM survey in project P4.1.1.2.a_Y1 (14 837€)
Remaining purchase costs (<15% of pers. Costs)	20 660	
Total	50 497	
21.1 - UL	Cost (€)	Justification
Other Goods, Works & Services	3 000	Consumables (reagents, tubes, micropipette tips, microfilters) as P4.2.c_Y3
Remaining purchase costs (<15% of pers. Costs)	2 060	
Total	5 060	
22 - NPHSL	Cost (€)	Justification
Travel and subsistence	6 730	Travel and subsistence for 1 person to attend 7 meetings in WP9 (5 670€) and for 1 person to attend 1 meeting in WP1 (1 060€)
Remaining purchase costs (<15% of pers. Costs)	2 490	
Total	9 220	
23 - LSMU	Cost (€)	Justification
Other Goods, Works & Services	16 940	Consumables and costs for analysis as part HBM survey in project P4.1.1.2.a_Y1
Travel and subsistence	4 800	Travel and subsistence for 1 person to attend 6 meetings in WP6

Remaining purchase costs (<15% of pers. Costs)	5 970	
Total	27 710	
25.4 - UL-LACDR	Cost (€)	Justification
Other Goods, Works & Services	153 125	Costs for Cell culture, molecular biology, microscopy, transcriptomics, chemicals, disposables, plastics for projects P5.2.1.a_Y1 (47 000€), P5.3.1.a_Y1 (40 000€), P5.3.1.b_Y4 (55 000€) and P6.1.1.c_Y1 (11 625€)
Remaining purchase costs (<15% of pers. Costs)	72 755	
Total	225 880	
25.7 - WR	Cost (€)	Justification
Other Goods, Works & Services	65 070	Consumables for projects P4.3.2.a_Y1 (25 190€), P4.3.1.d_Y1 (8 940€) and P4.3.4.a_Y2 (30 940€)
Remaining purchase costs (<15% of pers. Costs)	25 600	
Total	90 670	
26.2 - STAMI	Cost (€)	Justification
Other Goods, Works & Services	24 000	Lab consumables as part of project P6.4.1.c_Y3 including 3D skin cell model and skin tissue model
Remaining purchase costs (<15% of pers. Costs)	49 520	
Total	73 520	
26.5 - NMBU	Cost (€)	Justification
Other Goods, Works & Services	11 981	Costs for analyses as part of project P5.2.1.e_Y1
Remaining purchase costs (<15% of pers. Costs)	5 777	
Total	17 758	
27.1 - IEP-NRI	Cost (€)	Justification
Other Goods, Works & Services	18 940	Costs for laboratory materials, reagents and services as part of project P5.1.2.b_Y1
Remaining purchase costs (<15% of pers. Costs)	18 536	
Total	37 476	
27.3 - WULS-SGGW	Cost (€)	Justification
Other Goods, Works & Services	30 872	Consumables and standards, solvents, reagents, services for projects P4.1.1.2.a_Y1 (3 532€), P4.3.2.b_Y2 (20 000€), P4.3.2.c_Y3 (3 000€), and P4.3.4.a_Y2 (4 340€)
Remaining purchase costs (<15% of pers. Costs)	5 260	
Total	36 132	

28 - FMUL	Cost (€)	Justification
Travel and subsistence	2 120	Travel and subsistence for 1 person to attend 2 meetings in WP2
Remaining purchase costs (<15% of pers. Costs)	3780	
Total	5 900	
29 - INSA	Cost (€)	Justification
Other Goods, Works & Services	80 736	Consumables and costs for analysis as part of HBM survey in project P4.1.1.2.a_Y1 (22 717€), P5.1.1.c_Y3 (15 000€), P5.1.1.d_Y4 (5 900€) Organisation of meetings and training sessions as part of task 9.4 (22 120€) Organisation of SYNnet forum meetings as part of task 3.3 (15 000€)
Remaining purchase costs (<15% of pers. Costs)	121 716	
Total	202 452	
29.2 - DGS	Cost (€)	Justification
Travel and subsistence	3 020	Travel and subsistence for: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - 1 person to attend 2 meetings in WP2 (2 120€) - 1 person to attend 1 meeting in WP8 (900€)
Remaining purchase costs (<15% of pers. Costs)	0	
Total	3 020	
29.3 - ENSP	Cost (€)	Justification
Travel and subsistence	8 395	Travel and subsistence for: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - 1 person to attend 2 meetings in WP2 (2 120€) - 1 person to attend 5 meetings in WP6 (4 200€) - 1 person to attend 3 meeting in WP9 (2 905€)
Remaining purchase costs (<15% of pers. Costs)	8 955	
Total	18 180	
29.4 - UAVR	Cost (€)	Justification
Travel and subsistence	830	Travel and subsistence for 1 person to attend 1 meeting in WP3
Remaining purchase costs (<15% of pers. Costs)	15 990	
Total	16 820	
30 - SZU-SK	Cost (€)	Justification
Travel and subsistence	7 330	Travel and subsistence for: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - 1 person to attend 2 meetings in WP4 (3 780€) - 1 person to attend 4 meetings in WP9 (3 550€)

Remaining purchase costs (<15% of pers. Costs)	4 830	
Total	11 710	
30.1 - UK	Cost (€)	Justification
Travel and subsistence	1 890	Travel and subsistence for: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - 1 person to attend 1 meeting in WP4 (830€) - 1 person to attend 1 meeting in WP9 (1 060€)
Remaining purchase costs (<15% of pers. Costs)	0	
Total	1 890	
31 - JSI	Cost (€)	Justification
Other Goods, Works & Services	59 732	Chemicals and consumables for projects P4.3.4.a_Y2 (21 670€), P4.3.2.c_Y3 (33 000€) and P4.1.1.2.a_Y1 (5 062€)
Remaining purchase costs (<15% of pers. Costs)	70 430	
Total	130 162	
31.2 - NIB	Cost (€)	Justification
Other Goods, Works & Services	74 200	Consumables such as plastic ware, chemicals, media for growth of bacteria and cell cultures, maintenance of fish, food for fish, S9 mix, specific antibodies, preamplification kits, assays for qPCR, etc. as part of projects P5.2.1.a_Y1 (24 000€), P5.1.2.b_Y1 (26 150€) and P5.1.1.a_Y1 (24 050€)
Remaining purchase costs (<15% of pers. Costs)	4 890	
Total	79 090	
31.3 - NIC	Cost (€)	Justification
Other Goods, Works & Services	1 400	Consumables for project P5.1.2.b_Y1
Remaining purchase costs (<15% of pers. Costs)	16 740	
Total	18 140	
31.4 - UL FFA	Cost (€)	Justification
Other Goods, Works & Services	3 670	Consumables for projects P4.3.4.a_Y2 (1670€) and P5.1.1b_Y1 (2000€)
Remaining purchase costs (<15% of pers. Costs)	2 830	
Total	6 500	
32.2 - NLZOH	Cost (€)	Justification
Travel and subsistence	9 600	Travel and subsistence for 1 person to attend 4 meetings in WP6
Remaining purchase costs (<15% of pers. Costs)	0	

Total	9 600	
33 - CSIC	Cost (€)	Justification
Other Goods, Works & Services	58 000	Costs for consumables as part of projects P4.3.4_Y2 (10 000€), P5.1.2.b_Y1 (23 000€) and P6.2.3.a_Y1(25 000€): solvents, reagents, standards, glassware and supplies of mass spectrometry and chromatography
Remaining purchase costs (<15% of pers. Costs)	81 956	
Total	139 956	
33.1 - ULPGC	Cost (€)	Justification
Travel and subsistence	830	Travel and subsistence for 1 person to attend 2 meetings in WP4
Remaining purchase costs (<15% of pers. Costs)	0	
Total	830	
33.2 - UNAV	Cost (€)	Justification
Other Goods, Works & Services	19 000	Consumables and natural toxins for assays as part of projects P5.2.1.a_Y1
Remaining purchase costs (<15% of pers. Costs)	2 830	
Total	21 830	
33.3 - UGR	Cost (€)	Justification
Other Goods, Works & Services	17 500	Consumables as part of projects P4.3.2.a_Y1 (10 000€) and P4.3.2.b_Y2 (7 500€)
Remaining purchase costs (<15% of pers. Costs)	17 960	
Total	35 460	
34 - ISCIII	Cost (€)	Justification
Other Goods, Works & Services	75 740	Buffer for training organization (2 trainings per year including organisation and trainer costs) in T9.4, temporarily allocated to WPL ISCIII (70 740€) Consumables as part of project P4.2.c_Y3 (5 000€)
Remaining purchase costs (<15% of pers. Costs)	88 192	
Total	163 932	
34.2 - FISABIO	Cost (€)	Justification
Travel and subsistence	3 830	Travel and subsistence for: - 1 person to attend 3 meetings in WP4 - 1 person to attend 1 meeting in WP9
Remaining purchase costs (<15% of pers. Costs)	1 060	
Total	1 890	
34.4 - FNS	Cost (€)	Justification

Travel and subsistence	830	Travel and subsistence for 1 person to attend 1 meeting in WP9
Remaining purchase costs (<15% of pers. Costs)	2100	
Total	2 930	
34.6 - INSST	Cost (€)	Justification
Travel and subsistence	6 360	Travel and subsistence for: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - 2 persons to attend 1 meeting for project P4.1.1.4.c_Y1 (2 120€) - 1 person to attend 4 meetings in WP8 (4 240€)
Remaining purchase costs (<15% of pers. Costs)	0	
Total	6 360	
35.3 - ULUND	Cost (€)	Justification
Other Goods, Works & Services	17 030	Consumables for analysis and sampling as part of activities of biomonitoring in Task 4.1
Remaining purchase costs (<15% of pers. Costs)	10 260	
Total	27 290	
35.7- KEMI	Cost (€)	Justification
Other Goods, Works & Services	2 678	Publication costs in task 6.4
Remaining purchase costs (<15% of pers. Costs)	26 383	
Total	29 061	
35.10 - SLU	Cost (€)	Justification
Other Goods, Works & Services	45 420	Consumables for analysis and sampling as part of projects P4.3.4.a_Y2 (25 420€) and P6.4.4.c_Y1 (20 000€)
Remaining purchase costs (<15% of pers. Costs)	21 530	
Total	66 950	
35.12 - UU	Cost (€)	Justification
Other Goods, Works & Services	50 000	Consumables as part of project P5.2.1.e_Y1
Remaining purchase costs (<15% of pers. Costs)	9 933	
Total	59 933	
36.2 - GCSL	Cost (€)	Justification
Other Goods, Works & Services	16 650	Costs for the organisation of Stakeholder Forum meetings, International Board meetings and of SYNnet Forum meetings in WP3
Travel and subsistence	14 130	Travel and subsistence for: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - 1 person to attend 1 meeting in WP1 (2 600€)

		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - 1 person to attend 2 meetings in WP2 (2 120€) - 1 person to attend 4 meetings in WP3 (9 410€)
Remaining purchase costs (<15% of pers. Costs)	18 480	
Total	49 260	
37 - BPI	Cost (€)	Justification
Other Goods, Works & Services	154 400	Consumables including for in vitro testing, molecular biology, lab materials, chemicals etc. for projects P5.1.1.a_Y1 (38 400€), P5.1.2.b_Y1 (71 000€), and P5.1.1.d_Y4 (45 000€)
Remaining purchase costs (<15% of pers. Costs)	41 040	
Total	195 440	
61 - EPA	Cost (€)	Justification
Travel and subsistence	830	Travel and subsistence for 1 person to attend 1 meeting in WP1
Remaining purchase costs (<15% of pers. Costs)	830	
Total	1 660	
62 - UCD	Cost (€)	Justification
Other Goods, Works & Services	5 200	Publication costs for scientific articles in project P4.1.1.2.a_Y1
Remaining purchase costs (<15% of pers. Costs)	10 326	
Total	15 526	

Table 2.3.c: Overview of planned budget per project and per Work Package

Task/Project ID	Budget allocated for Y4	% Budget allocated for Y4 / total WP budget allocated for Y4	Total Budget allocated	Total WP budget at proposal stage	% Project Total Budget allocated / Total WP budget at proposal
Projects	52 406.33	3.53%	83 500.58		0.41%
P2.1.a_Y3	52 406.33	3.53%	83 500.58		0.38%
Transversal activities	1 380 929.67	92.95%	9 282 578.48		45.46%
Task 2.1	356 467.05	23.99%	2 672 486.01		12.21%
Task 2.2	771 272.39	51.91%	4 943 190.34		22.58%

Task 2.3	253 190.23	17.04%	1 666 902.12		7.61%
TOTAL WP2	1 485 742.33	96.47%	9 449 579.63	20 419 420.00	42.79%

Task/Project ID	Budget allocated for Y4	% Budget allocated for Y4 / total WP budget allocated for Y4	Total Budget allocated	Total WP budget at proposal stage	% Project Total Budget allocated / Total WP budget at proposal
Projects	11 826 084.45	47.66%	54 634 808.27		46.25%
P4.1.1.2.a_Y1	2 721 595.60	10.97%	11 798 991.02		9.99%
P4.1.1.3.a_Y4	196 388.55	0.79%	922 406.84		0.78%
P4.1.1.3.b_Y4	144 836.69	0.58%	403 089.32		0.34%
P4.1.1.3.c_Y4	240 840.58	0.97%	736 341.23		0.62%
P4.1.1.4.a_Y1	0.00	0.00%	82 588.89		0.07%
P4.1.1.4.b_Y1	3 700.00	0.01%	241 029.88		0.20%
P4.1.1.4.c_Y1	436 202.95	1.76%	1 355 244.25		1.15%
P4.1.1.4.d_Y1	516 518.70	2.08%	1 736 854.74		1.47%
P4.1.3.1.a_Y1	279 987.08	1.13%	1 938 670.52		1.64%
P4.1.3.1.b_Y4	241 309.16	0.97%	991 359.51		0.84%
P4.1.3.3.a_Y1	466 376.89	1.88%	2 245 648.74		1.90%
P4.1.4.2.a_Y1	240 670.24	0.97%	1 469 608.19		1.24%
P4.1.5.a_Y1	111 308.29	0.45%	605 653.09		0.51%
P4.2.a_Y1	1 459 567.19	5.88%	8 619 904.32		7.30%
P4.2.b_Y2	0.00	0.00%	2 251 025.15		1.91%
P4.2.c_Y3	1 193 258.05	4.81%	3 773 460.45		3.19%
P4.2.d_Y4	225 279.03	0.91%	488 222.20		0.41%
P4.3.1.a_Y1	0.00	0.00%	259 035.98		0.22%
P4.3.1.b_Y1	168 778.28	0.68%	703 979.98		0.60%
P4.3.1.c_Y1	99 837.73	0.40%	427 395.24		0.36%
P4.3.1.d_Y1	333 042.28	1.34%	1 435 447.18		1.22%
P4.3.2.a_Y1	993 810.84	4.01%	3 379 126.47		2.86%
P4.3.2.b_Y2	268 213.87	1.08%	1 090 722.04		0.92%
P4.3.2.c_Y3	591 148.37	2.38%	2 231 794.91		1.89%
P4.3.3.a_Y1	45 862.50	0.18%	2 605 435.16		2.21%
P4.3.3.b_Y2	335 250.35	1.35%	1 262 748.10		1.07%
P4.3.4.a_Y2	512 301.27	2.06%	1 579 024.90		1.34%
Transversal activities	12 986 225.95	52.34%	12 986 225.95		10.99%
Task 4.1	11 127 428.95	44.85%	11 127 428.95		9.42%
Task 4.2	1 374 951.19	5.54%	1 374 951.19		1.16%
Task 4.3	483 845.81	1.95%	483 845.81		0.41%
TOTAL WP4	24 812 310.40	100.00%	67 621 034.22	118 124 452.00	57.25%

Task/Project ID	Budget allocated for Y4	% Budget allocated for Y4 / total WP budget allocated for Y4	Total Budget allocated	Total WP budget at proposal stage	% Project Total Budget allocated / Total WP budget at proposal
Projects	14 916 045.36	91.66%	65 193 572.04		67.49%
P5.1.1.a_Y1	840 877.01	5.29%	4 956 017.67		5.13%
P5.1.1.b_Y1	1 033 596.46	6.50%	3 642 717.88		3.77%
P5.1.1.c_Y3	591 046.94	3.72%	1 827 129.41		1.89%
P5.1.1.d_Y4	676 270.95	4.25%	3 424 753.25		3.55%
P5.1.2.a_Y1	0.00	0.00%	501 413.84		0.52%
P5.1.2.b_Y1	2 136 062.13	13.43%	8 686 291.25		8.99%
P5.1.2.c_Y4	294 992.25	1.86%	606 536.25		0.63%
P5.2.a_Y4	279 955.00	1.76%	792 945.00		0.82%
P5.2.1.a_Y1	1 178 426.13	7.41%	6 221 326.19		6.44%
P5.2.1.b_Y1	382 349.49	2.40%	3 160 972.34		3.27%
P5.2.1.c_Y1	782 798.70	4.92%	3 349 608.36		3.47%
P5.2.1.d_Y1	995 769.05	6.26%	4 595 580.94		4.76%
P5.2.1.e_Y1	1 249 412.02	7.86%	4 917 706.36		5.09%
P5.2.1.f_Y4	657 115.49	4.13%	2 722 831.47		2.82%
P5.2.1.g_Y4	672 339.52	4.23%	2 448 127.37		2.53%
P5.2.1.h_Y4	258 600.19	1.63%	530 450.39		0.55%
P5.3.1.a_Y1	915 533.30	5.76%	3 368 241.90		3.49%
P5.3.1.b_Y4	732 698.51	4.61%	2 794 945.55		2.89%
P5.3.2.a_Y1	654 951.87	4.12%	3 461 759.85		3.58%
P5.3.4.a_Y1	242 719.95	1.53%	3 184 216.80		3.30%
P5.3.4.b_Y4	340 530.41	2.14%	1 532 374.29		1.59%
Transversal activities	1 326 812.20	8.34%	6 210 263.15		6.43%
Task 5.1	500 394.25	3.15%	2 096 195.02		2.17%
Task 5.2	540 775.17	3.40%	2 228 267.87		2.31%
Task 5.3	285 642.77	1.80%	1 885 800.26		1.95%
TOTAL WP5	15 902 327.15	100.00%	71 403 835.20	96 602 616.00	73.92%

Task/Project ID	Budget allocated for Y4	% Budget allocated for Y4 / total WP budget allocated for Y4	Total Budget allocated	Total WP budget at proposal stage	% Project Total Budget allocated / Total WP budget at proposal
Projects	10 031 388.22	92.99%	53 566 145.76		73.00%
P6.1.1.a_Y1	0.00	0.00%	1 184 329.66		1.61%

Task/Project ID	Budget allocated for Y4	% Budget allocated for Y4 / total WP budget allocated for Y4	Total Budget allocated	Total WP budget at proposal stage	% Project Total Budget allocated / Total WP budget at proposal
P6.1.1.b_Y1	0.00	0.00%	2 241 553.63		3.05%
P6.1.1.c_Y1	473 679.19	4.39%	2 386 295.86		3.25%
P6.1.1.d_Y1	150 616.25	1.40%	1 459 754.39		1.99%
P6.1.1.e_Y4	325 331.48	3.02%	1 395 232.15		1.90%
P6.1.1.f_Y4	266 494.15	2.47%	1 092 349.10		1.49%
P6.2.1.a_Y1	214 339.18	1.99%	1 350 896.09		1.84%
P6.2.1.b_Y1	918 330.53	8.51%	3 783 666.14		5.16%
P6.2.2.a_Y1	152 970.25	1.42%	2 742 328.72		3.74%
P6.2.3.a_Y1	1 759 788.92	16.31%	7 100 422.78		9.68%
P6.2.4.a_Y1	336 025.24	3.11%	1 873 018.05		2.55%
P6.2.4.b_Y1	502 041.06	4.65%	2 817 809.17		3.84%
P6.2.4.c_Y1	258 397.65	2.40%	861 107.64		1.17%
P6.2.4.d_Y1	154 160.06	1.43%	569 124.90		0.78%
P6.3.1.a_Y1	209 429.38	1.94%	860 122.63		1.17%
P6.3.1.b_Y1	517 623.46	4.80%	1 896 005.26		2.58%
P6.3.2.a_Y1	328 208.51	3.04%	1 853 618.96		2.53%
P6.4.1.a_Y1	124 121.70	1.15%	1 185 533.84		1.62%
P6.4.1.b_Y1	70 838.73	0.66%	730 950.28		1.00%
P6.4.1.c_Y3	300 523.75	2.79%	940 625.00		1.28%
P6.4.1.d_Y4	617 436.64	5.72%	1 755 563.89		2.39%
P6.4.2.a_Y1	0.00	0.00%	204 304.08		0.28%
P6.4.2.b_Y1	149 293.70	1.38%	1 009 693.55		1.38%
P6.4.2.c_Y1	0.00	0.00%	385 203.69		0.52%
P6.4.2.d_Y4	310 974.49	2.88%	1 464 141.08		2.00%
P6.4.2.e_Y4	113 428.75	1.05%	449 490.00		0.61%
P6.4.3.a_Y1	0.00	0.00%	575 769.38		0.78%
P6.4.3.b_Y3	368 357.00	3.41%	1 029 618.63		1.40%
P6.4.4.a_Y1	162 179.21	1.50%	1 135 962.14		1.55%
P6.4.4.b_Y1	513 374.75	4.76%	2 559 591.75		3.49%
P6.4.4.c_Y1	309 052.65	2.86%	1 744 711.04		2.38%
P6.4.4.d_Y1	145 197.78	1.35%	1 083 916.51		1.48%
P6.4.4.e_Y1	279 173.77	2.59%	1 843 435.75		2.51%
Transversal activities	756 266.35	7.01%	4 106 125.28		5.60%
Task 6.1	112 672.50	1.04%	930 077.50		1.27%
Task 6.2	202 345.72	1.88%	1 052 043.72		1.43%
Task 6.3	111 756.84	1.04%	753 792.55		1.03%
Task 6.4	329 491.29	3.05%	1 370 211.51		1.87%
TOTAL WP6	10 787 654.57	100.00%	57 672 271.04	73 379 540.00	78.59%

Task/Project ID	Budget allocated for Y4	% Budget allocated for Y4 / total WP budget allocated for Y4	Total Budget allocated	Total WP budget at proposal stage	% Project Total Budget allocated / Total WP budget at proposal
Projects	1 022 293.62	37.30%	4 617 350.99		21.09%
P7.2.2.a_Y1	294 855.73	10.76%	1 897 303.98		8.67%
P7.2.2.b_Y1	475 038.18	17.33%	1 513 169.10		6.91%
P7.3.3.a_Y1	252 399.71	9.21%	1 206 877.91		5.51%
Transversal activities	1 718 218.77	62.70%	12 238 726.12		55.91%
Task 7.1	236 652.65	8.64%	1 717 359.56		7.85%
Task 7.2	691 210.75	25.22%	5 272 779.09		24.09%
Task 7.3	790 355.37	28.84%	5 248 587.47		23.98%
TOTAL WP7	2 740 512.39	100.00%	16 856 077.12	21 889 938.00	77.00%

Annex I AWP Y4

PARC PROJECT PORTFOLIO

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List of abbreviations

3PFF: Three-Point FAIRification Framework	CEACs: Chemicals of Emerging Arctic Concern
3Rs: Replacement, Reduction and Refinement	CEC: Chemicals of Emerging Concern
ADME: Absorption, Distribution, Metabolism and Excretion	CESNET: Czech Education and Scientific NETWORK
ADME4NGRA: Implementing the EFSA NAMs roadmap through advancing toxicokinetic knowledge in chemical risk assessment	CG: Core Group
AEP: Aggregated Exposure Pathways	CHIASMA: Accessible Innovative Methods for the Safety & Sustainability Assessment of Chemicals & Materials
AI: Artificial Intelligence	CHMS: Canadian Health Measures Survey
ALTERNATIVE: environmentAL Toxicity chEmical mixtuRes through aN innovative platform based on aged cardiac tissue model	CLH: harmonised classification and labelling
AMAP: Arctic Monitoring and Assessment Programme	CLP: Classification, Labelling and Packaging
AO/ AON/ AOP: Adverse Outcome/ AO Network/ Pathway	CMD: Carcinogens and Mutagens Directive
ASPA: ASPIS-initiated alternative Safety Profiling Algorithm	CMRD: carcinogens, mutagens and reproductive toxic substances directive
ASPIS: Animal-free Safety assessment of chemicals: Project cluster for Implementation of novel Strategies projects	CoMPAIT: Collaborative Modeling Project for Acute Inhalation Toxicity
ASR/ AWP: Annual Summary Report/Work Plans	CONTAM: Contaminants in the Food Chain Panel
ATHENA: Assays for the identification of Thyroid Hormone axis - disrupting chemicals: Elaborating Novel Assessment strategies	COST: Cooperation in Science and Technology
ATHLETE: The Exposome from Evidence to Translation	CPDC: Common Platform for Data on Chemicals
BBB: Blood Brain Barrier	CPR: Cosmetic Products Regulation
BCF: bioconcentration factor	CRA: Chemical Risk Assessment
BMD: Benchmark dose	CSS: Chemicals Strategy for Sustainability
BoD: Burden of Disease	CVMS: cyclic volatile methylsiloxanes
BPA: Bisphenol A	CYP: cytochrome P450
BPR: Biocides Products Regulation	DALYs: Disability-Adjusted Life Years
CAAT: Center for Alternatives to Animal Testing	DART: developmental and reproductive toxicity
CAD: Chemical Agents Directive	DBS: Dried Blood Spots
CAGs: Cumulative Assessment Groups	DEP: Diethyl phthalate
CDC: the Centers for Disease Control and Prevention	DHNB: Diethylamino Hydroxybenzoyl Hexyl Benzoate
CE: circular economy	DIT: Developmental Immunotoxicity
	DMP: Data Management Plan
	DMP: Dimethyl phthalate
	DNEL: derived no-effect level
	DnHexP: Di-n-hexyl phthalate
	DNT/ANT: Developmental and Acute Neurotoxicity
	DoA: Description of Action
	DoHAD: Developmental origins of health and disease

EAGMST: Extended Advisory Group on Molecular Screening and Toxicogenomics

EAGMST: Extended Advisory Group on Molecular Screening and Toxicogenomics

EATS: Estrogen, Androgen, Steroidogenesis, and Thyroid

EBD: Environmental Burden of Disease

EBTC: Evidence-Based Toxicology Collaboration

EC: European Commission

ECEH: European Centre for Environment and Health

ECHA: European Chemicals Agency

ED/ EDCs: Endocrine Disruptors / endocrine disrupting compounds

EDA: Effect-Directed Analysis

EDoNIS: Endocrine disruptors: investigation of the effects on the immune and nervous systems

EEA: European Environment Agency

EFSA: European Food Safety Authority

EHEN: European Human Exposome Network

EIRENE: Environmental Exposure Assessment Research Infrastructure

EMA: European Medicines Agency

EMEP: European Monitoring and Evaluation Programme

EMT: epithelial-mesenchymal transition

ENDOMIX: Understanding how endocrine disruptors and chemical mixtures of concern target the immune system to trigger or perpetuate disease

ENKORE: evolving KnOwledge REsource

EOGRT: Extended One Generation Reproductive Toxicity

EOSC: European Open Science Cloud

EPHOR: Exposome project for health and occupational research

E-PRTR: European Pollutant Release and Transfer Register

ERA: Environmental Risk Assessment

ERGO: EndocRine Guideline Optimisation

ESCA: Emerging Science in Chemicals Assessment

ESFRI: European Strategic Forum for Research Infrastructure

EU-NETVAL: European Union Network of Laboratories for the Validation of Alternative Methods

EURION: European Cluster to Improve Identification of Endocrine Disruptors

EURL ECVAM: EU Reference Laboratory for alternatives to animal testing

EWS: Early Warning System

Eximious: Mapping Exposure-Induced Immune Effects: Connecting the Exposome and the Immunome

EXPANSE: EXposome Powered tools for healthy living in urbAN Setting”

EXPOSIM: Environmental stressors as causal determinants for immune-mediated diseases

FAIR: Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable

FCM: Food contact materials

FELS: fish early-life stage

FIP: FAIR Implementation Profiles

FOCUS: FORum for the Co-ordination of pesticide fate models and their Use

FTOHs: fluorotelomer alcohols

GB: Governing Board

GDPR: General Data Protection Regulation

GENASIS: Global ENvironmental ASsessment Information System

GEOSS: Global Earth Observation System of Systems

GERDA: GEobased Runoff, Erosion, and Drainage risk Assessment for Germany

GFF: Go Fair Foundation

GIVIMP: Good In Vitro Methods Practices

GLP: Good Laboratory Practice

GOLIATH: Generation Of NoveL, Integrated and Internationally Harmonised Approaches for Testing Metabolism Disrupting Compounds

GTTC: Genetic Toxicology Technical Committee

GWD: Groundwater Directive

HA: Hazard Assessment

HBGV: Health-based guidance value

HBM: Human BioMonitoring	KEs: Key Events
HBM4EU: The European Human Biomonitoring Initiative	LCA: Life-cycle assessment
HBM-GV: Human BioMonitoring Guidance Value	LCI: lowest concentration of interest
Hedimed: Human Exposomic Determinants of Immune Mediated diseases	LEP: Leptin
HES: health examination surveys	LIFESAVER: Living Impact on Fetal Evolution: Shelter-Analyze-Validate-Empower Regulations
HESI: Health and Environmental Sciences Institute	LLM: large language model
HIA: Health Impact Assessment	LMVS: linear volatile methylsiloxanes
HILIC: Hydrophilic interaction chromatography	LOD: limit of detection
hiPSC: human induced pluripotent stem cell	LUCAS: Land Use and Coverage Area frame Survey
HMPs: Hazardous medicinal products	MAF: Mixture Assessment (or Allocation) Factor
HRMS: High Resolution Mass Spectrometry	MDC: Metabolic (or Metabolism) Disrupting chemicals
HTPP: high-throughput phenotypic profiling	MEC: Measured Environmental Concentrations
HTTr: high-throughput transcriptomics	MELODI: Multidisciplinary European Low Dose Initiative
HYBIT: Hyalella Azteca bioconcentration test	MERLON: Merging scientific Evidence with Regulatory practices and Leveraging identification Of endocrine disruptors using New approach methodologies
IA: Indoor Air	MIE: Molecular Initiating Event
IA-GV: Indoor Air – Guidance Values	MIHCSMEL: Minimum Information for High Content Screening Microscopy Experiments
IAQ: Indoor Air Quality	ML: Machine Learning
IARC: International Agency for Research on Cancer	MnHexP: mono-n-hexyl phthalate
IATA: Integrative Approaches for testing and Assessment	MoA: Mode of Action
IDEAL: Indoor air quality health cluster	MOMENTUM: Microplastics and Human Health Consortium
INDRA: Integrated Network and Dynamical Reasoning Assembler	MRA: Mixture Risk Assessment
INQUIRE: Improving indoor air quality for a healthier home and Europe	MRI: Mixture Risk Indicators
IPCHEM: Information Platform for Chemical Monitoring	MRM: Mixture Risk Mitigation
iPSC: Induced pluripotent stem cells	mSC: multipotent stem cells
ISES: International Society of Exposure Science	MSFD: Marine Strategy Framework Directive
ITS: Integrated Testing Strategies	NAMs: New Approach Methodologies
IVB: in vitro test battery	NAMS4NANO: Integration of NAMs results in CRA: case studies addressing nanoscale considerations
IVIVE: in vitro - in vivo extrapolation	NEMESIS: Novel Educational Model Enabling Social Innovation Skills development
JRC: Joint Research Centre	NER: Named Entity Recognition
KARC: Key Areas of Regulatory Challenge	NGO: Non-governmental organization
KERs: Key Event Relationships	

NGRA: Next Generation Risk Assessment	<i>OO7: Develop/ implement annual R&I work programmes to respond to identified needs in chemical RA</i>
NGTxC: Non-Genotoxic Carcinogens	
NHANES: National Health and Nutrition Examination Survey	<i>OO8: Develop monitoring capacity by extending the HBM platform created in HBM4EU and supporting the provision of environmental and multisource data for regulatory purposes</i>
NHCs: National Hub Coordinators	
NHCPs: National Hub Contact Points	<i>OO9: Develop tools to facilitate the acceptance and use of PARC's results in regulatory RA processes and support (existing) standardisation and validation processes for innovative approaches to RA.</i>
NHs: National Hubs	
NICEATM: NTP Interagency Centre for the Evaluation of Alternative Toxicological Methods	<i>OO10: Implement FAIR data practices and enhance innovation in complex data analysis for RA</i>
NLP: Natural language processing	
NORMAN: Network of reference laboratories, research centres and related organisations for monitoring of emerging environmental substances	<i>OO11: Consolidate existing and develop new networks of laboratories and research centres</i>
NR: Nuclear Receptors	<i>OO12: Develop models and innovative concepts for RA and deliver toolboxes to promote their acceptability and uptake</i>
NTS: Non-Targeted Screening	<i>OO13: Build capacities by developing and carrying out training and exchange programmes in chemical RA</i>
NUTS: Nomenclature of Territorial Units for Statistics	
ODC: Other direct costs (travel, goods and services, equipment, chemicals and consumables)	OORF: OECD Omics Reporting Framework
OECD: Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development	OPRF: OECD-equivalent Phenotypic Reporting Framework
OELs: occupational exposure limits	OSH: Occupational safety and health
OHDSI: Observational Health Data Sciences and Informatics	OSOA: One Substance One Assessment
Ontox: Ontology-driven and artificial intelligence-based repeated dose toxicity testing of chemicals for next generation risk assessment	PAHs: polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons
OO: Operational Objectives:	PANORAMIX: Providing risk assessments of complex real-life mixtures for the protection of Europe's citizens and the environment
<i>OO1: Set-up and operate a high-level group to strategically steer PARC</i>	PBK: Physiologically Based Kinetic
<i>OO2: Expand long-term sustainable network of National Hubs (NH)</i>	PBPK: Physiologically Based Pharmacokinetic
<i>OO3: Define common R&I strategies with transparent criteria and a prioritisation strategy</i>	PBT: persistent, bioaccumulative and toxic
<i>OO4: Actively foster regulatory uptake of PARC knowledge</i>	PBTK: Physiologically Based Toxicokinetic
<i>OO5: Promote cooperation with other R&I initiatives</i>	PCB: Polychlorinated biphenyls
<i>OO6: Communicate & disseminate PARC knowledge to increase citizen's understanding/awareness of chemical RA</i>	PEC: Predicted Environmental Concentrations
	PEH: Personal Exposure and Health
	PEH: Personal Exposure and Health
	PERA: Partnership for next generation, systems-based Environmental Risk Assessment
	PFAS: per- and polyfluoroalkyl substances
	PFCAs: perfluorocarboxylic acids

PFDP: PARC FAIR Data Policy	SAM: Stress Addition Model
PHIRI: Population Health Information Research Infrastructure	(S)CBA: (social) cost benefit analyses
PM: Person-month	SCAR: Scientific Committee of Antarctic Research
PMT: Persistent, mobile and toxic	SCCS: Scientific Committee on Consumer Safety
PoC: Proof of Concept	SCENARIOS: Strategies for health protection, pollution Control and Elimination of Next generation RefractIve Organic chemicals from the Soil, vadose zone and water
POD: Point of Departure	SCORE: Supporting Consumer Co-Ownership in Renewable Energies
POLYRISK: Understanding human exposure and health hazard of micro- and nanoplastic contaminants in our environment	SCREENED: Screening for Endocrine Disruptors
POP: Persistent Organic Pollutant	SE: Single exposure
PPPR: Plant Protection Products Regulation	SF: Stakeholder Forum
PROMISCES: Preventing Recalcitrant Organic Mobile Industrial chemicals for Circular Economy in the Soil-sediment-water system	SO: Specific Objectives
PTR-MS: Proton Transfer Reaction Mass Spectrometry	SOP: Standard Operating Procedures
PVC: polyvinyl chloride	SPRINT: Sustainable Plant Protection Transition
QA/QC: Quality Assurance / Quality Control	SRIA: Strategic Research and Innovation Agenda
qAOP: Quantitative Adverse Outcome Pathway	SS: suspect screening
QIVIVE: Quantitative in vitro / in vivo Extrapolation	SSbD: Safe-and-Sustainable-by-Design
QSAR: Quantitative Structure Activity Relationship	STOP: Source to Outcome Pathways
QSPR: Quantitative Structure-Property Relationships	STOT: Specific target organ toxicity
R&I: Research and Innovation	SUD: Sustainable Use Directive
RA/RM: Risk Assessment / Risk Management	SVHC: Substances of Very High Concern
RAx: read-across	SWB: Silicone Wristbands
RDA: Research Data alliance	TDAR: T-cell dependent antibody response
RE: Repeated exposure	TDI: tolerable daily intake
REACH: registration, evaluation, authorisation and restriction of chemicals	TEHDAS: Towards the European Health Data Space
REEG: REACH Exposure Expert Group	tFET: THSD Fish Embryo Acute Toxicity
RISKHUNT3R: RISK assessment of chemicals integrating HUMAN centric Next generation Testing strategies promoting the 3Rs	TG: test guideline
RMOA: Risk Management Option Analysis	THSD: Thyroid Hormone System Disruptors
RNN: Recurrent Neural Networks	THSDCs: thyroid hormone system disrupting chemicals
RRM: Rapid Response Mechanism	UN: United Nations
SAICM: Strategic Approach to International Chemicals Management	UNEP: United Nations Environment Programme
	US-EPA: US Environmental Protection Agency
	US-NIEHS/NTP: US National Institute of Environmental Health Sciences/National Toxicology Program
	UV: ultraviolet

VHP4Safety: Virtual Human Platform for Safety Assessment

VOCs: Volatile organic compounds

vPvB: very persistent and very bioaccumulative

vPvM: very persistent and very mobile

W4M: Workflow for Metabolomics

WBE: wastewater-based epidemiology

WFD: Water Framework Directive

WHO: World Health Organization

WoE: Weight-of-Evidence

WPHA/WPEA: Working Party for Hazard and Exposure Assessments

WWTP: Wastewater treatment plants

XETA: Xenopus embryonic thyroid signalling assay

XMEs: xenobiotic metabolizing enzymes

ZEROPM: Zero pollution of Persistent, Mobile substances

ZFe: Zebrafish embryo

WP2 A common science and policy Agenda – 1 project

The main goal of WP2 is to establish a dialogue and priority-setting process bringing together regulatory entities and Risk Assessment (RA) agencies in Europe (European and national entities or agencies) to develop a strategic research and innovation agenda (SRIA) for chemicals RA in collaboration with the scientific and regulatory community, to promote the uptake of innovative Next Generation Risk Assessment (NGRA) methodology into policy and regulatory practice and to ensure the sustainability of the partnership.

T2.1 Priority setting – 1 project

Task 2.1 aims to coordinate the prioritisation of research activities by risk assessors and risk managers in collaboration with scientists. It develops research activities explicitly addressing regulatory challenges, ensuring that results are relevant and applicable in the regulatory context.

In this framework, a Rapid Response Mechanism (RRM), drawing on the European Human Biomonitoring Initiative (HBM4EU)’s experience has been implemented ([Rapid Response Mechanism | Parc](#)). The aim of the mechanism is to allow the inclusion of new and urgent needs for information on chemicals in the EU policy community and at national level, outside of the formal timeframes for project nomination. Task 2.1 coordinates the eligibility and feasibility checking of the requests. In this framework, Task T2.1 followed the progress of the new project on the evaluation of the extent of exposure to mono-n-hexyl phthalate (MnHexP), at European level and to understand the potential sources of this phthalate metabolite, whose occurrence in human urine is unwanted.

P2.1.a_Y3_MnHexP-RRM_UBA

Project Title	Mono-n-hexyl phthalate, extent of exposure and potential sources		
Project Acronym	MnHexP-RRM		
Project Manager	Till Weber Till.Weber@uba.de	UBA	Germany
Deputy Project manager	Magnus Lofstedt Magnus.Lofstedt@eea.europa.eu	EEA	Europe
Expected starting date	M29	Expected duration (months)	48
PARC (Month number)		PARC	1
PARC Workpackage number	WP2	Task/Activity/Sub-activity:	
Project Id	P2.1.a_Y3_MnHexP-RRM_UBA		

Status: Implementation

Summary of the project

This project focuses on the need formulated by the European Environmental Agency (EEA) and the European Chemicals Agency (ECHA), in February 2024, prompting the RRM of PARC, on the topic of the recent human biomonitoring (HBM) data showing increased MnHexP exposure in Germany and Denmark and thus responds to a new and urgent need for information on chemicals in the EU policy community and at national level.

While different parent compounds (e.g., mixed chain phthalates) could be responsible for this exposure the newest data suggest the exposure source to be batches of the UV-filter Diethylamino Hydroxybenzoyl Hexyl Benzoate (DHHB) contaminated with Di-n-hexyl phthalate (DnHexP).

In a tiered approach, available data on human exposure and potential exposure sources will be gathered to possibly be integrated in the harmonised classification and labelling (CLH) dossier for C4-C6 phthalates currently prepared by France and potentially in a restriction dossier by ECHA on polyvinyl chloride (PVC) and its additives. Depending on the resources available, additionally samples from the indoor environment will be analysed to identify potential ways of exposure. The last tier, if feasible, will consist of new HBM, environmental and product measurements in PARC, to evaluate the extent of MnHexP exposure in Europe.

Main expected outputs of the project

Data gaps on human MnHexP exposure in Europe should be filled by a better understanding of the exposure source as well as a better understanding of levels of human and environmental exposure. The data will be made available to the EEA and ECHA in a timely manner.

Outcomes and impacts expected on end-users and stakeholders

Di-n-hexyl phthalate (DnHexP), the potential parent compound of MnHexP, is listed in “registration, evaluation, authorisation and restriction of chemicals” (REACH) Annex XIV thus wide exposure should not be expected. Results of this project will help understand potential shortcomings of the chemical regulation and provide an explanation of the source of exposure to end-users and stakeholders.

Outcomes and impacts expected to be incorporated into a specific regulatory framework

The data will potentially be integrated in the CLH dossier for C4-C6 phthalates currently prepared by France and potentially in a restriction dossier by ECHA on PVC and its additives.

Key words: Rapid Response Mechanism, MnHexP, DnHexP, Phthalates, HBM, Exposure, UV filters

Link to the PARC Description of Action (DoA):

The project is the result of the activation of the RRM. The project responds to the PARC objectives OO4 with the direct connection to regulatory action. It also responds to objective OO6 since the data will be made available publicly and thus help the citizens to understand how this exposure could have happened. It will also respond to OO8 focussing on an up to now not prioritized phthalate metabolite in the PARC Aligned Studies.

Links within PARC (WPs/Tasks/Activities/Projects)

The related WPs are best equipped to find or produce new monitoring data and evaluate potential sources. Data collection is dependent e.g. on the ongoing work in the PARC Aligned Studies.

Interactions with T4.1 Human biomonitoring, T4.2 Environmental and Multisource Monitoring, T6.2 Integrative exposure and RA, T6.4 Transposing results to regulatory RA methodologies and with the projects: P4.2.c_Y3_HumanExposure_INERIS_AU, P6.2.1_Y1_SourceToDose_VITO and P6.2.1.b_Y1_Aggregate_Anse, P6.4.3.a_Y1_SuProM_MU and P6.4.3.b_Y3_ENFORCE_KemI.

Links outside PARC

The data on use /source will potentially be integrated in the CLH dossier for C4-C6 phthalates currently prepared by France.

The data will potentially be integrated in a restriction dossier by ECHA on PVC and its additives.

The exposure data gathered great interest of regulatory, media and public representatives in Germany, thus European data is highly anticipated.

The Scientific Committee on Consumer Safety (SCCS) has also been mandated by the Commission to identify the maximum safe level of DnHexP as a contaminant in DHHB preparations used as a UV-filter in cosmetic products ([41bf1624-c922-499f-b9de-17c6385990cc en](https://ec.europa.eu/sccs/en/41bf1624-c922-499f-b9de-17c6385990cc)).

Key PARC Deliverables (or Additional Deliverables) and Milestones to which the project contributes
AD2.2. RRM DnHEXP (M76)

Partners List: UBA (Germany), ANSES (France), CSTB (France), EEA (Europe), VITO (Belgium), KEMI (Sweden), ISCIII (Spain), AU (Denmark), MU (Czech Republic), LNS (Luxembourg),

Schedule:

Starting date: 30/09/2024 (M29)

Expected ending date: 31/08/2028 (M76)

Costs¹

Expected PM: 5 PM

Expected ODC (Other direct costs: travel, goods and services, equipment, chemicals and consumables):
10 000 €

¹ For P2.1.a_Y3_MnHexP-RRM_UBA, preliminary work started Y3 and so the reported costs related to the project corresponds to the Y3 + Y4 of PARC

WP4 Monitoring and exposure – 23 PROJECTS

Guided by regulatory needs, WP4 aims to develop and improve the chemical monitoring and exposure assessment capacities in Europe as depicted in figure 1. The overall goal is a better understanding of the environmental and human exposure to chemicals from multiple sources, including pathways of exposure between the environment and humans. In support of a “one substance, one assessment approach” (OSOA) new monitoring approaches will be applied to complement existing monitoring schemes. Robust, reliable and fit-for-purpose innovative tools and methods will be developed, primarily to support and facilitate exposure assessment for vulnerable sub-populations and the early warning detection of chemicals of emerging concern (CEC). The work under WP4 is divided into three tasks that address the objectives of developing a) the HBM platform initiated in HBM4EU, b) environmental and multisource monitoring, and c) innovative methods and tools for monitoring.

Chemical monitoring guided by regulatory challenges

Fig 1: WP4 General approach and vision

T4.1 Human Biomonitoring – 11 PROJECTS

A HBM survey targeting the general population will constitute the basis of a well aligned HBM surveillance programme for chemical exposure of European citizens and will generate internal exposure data (see Fig.2). Statistically derived internal exposure reference values will allow for the evaluation of spatial and temporal trends in chemical exposure and monitoring of the impact of regulations and the EU’s Chemicals Strategy for Sustainability (CSS). In addition, targeted HBM surveys will address specific research and policy questions related to vulnerable groups (young children, pregnant women), highly exposed groups (workers, hotspot residents) or time trends. Priorities will be identified in cooperation with WP2 (‘A common science-policy agenda’). Further to the work achieved in HBM4EU and in coordination with WP9 (‘Building infrastructural and human capacities’), activities are being designed and implemented to ensure the quality and comparability of the HBM results. Harmonisation and improvement of analytical methods across laboratories will be implemented, defining reference analytical methods when possible. Special efforts will also be devoted into developing useful tools for the improvement of the HBM laboratory network. Task 4.1 will further develop the HBM4EU strategy to derive Health-Based Guidance Values (HBGVs) for the general and/or the occupational population. Effect biomarkers will complement exposure biomarkers to evaluate associations between chemical exposure and adverse health effects. Issues related to the linkage of HBM, health examination, occupational and dietary surveys will be identified and solved with support of WP7 (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable (FAIR) Data’). In collaboration with WP2 co-leaders and partners, the ultimate goal of this task is to prepare a long-term sustainable HBM and surveillance system for exposure to chemicals in Europe.

PARC Aligned Studies

Fig 2: PARC Aligned Studies

A4.1.1 Design, alignment and fieldwork of HBM studies – 6 PROJECTS

S4.1.1.1 Development of supporting materials for harmonized EU HBM conduct

No project submitted at present.

S4.1.1.2 General population survey – 1 PROJECT

P4.1.1.2.a_Y1_GenHBMSurvey_VITO

Project Title	General population human biomonitoring survey		
Project Acronym (15 letters max)	GenHBMSurvey		
Project Manager	Liese Gilles liese.gilles@vito.be	VITO	Belgium
Deputy Project manager	Susana Pedraza Diaz ISCIII PARC <PARC@isciii.es>	ISCIII	Spain
Expected starting date PARC (Month number)	1	Expected duration	81
PARC Workpackage number	4	PARC Task/Activity/Sub-activity:	4.1.1.2
Project Id	P4.1.1.2.a_Y1_GenHBMSurvey_VITO		

Status: Implementation

Summary of the project

This project is of relevance for all regulatory frameworks governing chemical production, use, environmental release, and exposure in various contexts, including those aimed at safeguarding environmental and human health.

Demonstrating the effectiveness of existing policies is vital for public trust and increasing transparency towards industry and stakeholders.

In this project biomarkers of chemical pollutants will be assessed in human biological samples (urine,

blood, hair) of the general EU population. This European-wide HBM, conducted through harmonized approaches and quality assured analytical methods, provides coherent data on priority substances in different European regions. HBM results from HBM4EU and PARC provide a baseline and time trends against which to track the efficacy of the European Green Deal's Zero Pollution Action Plan and the CSS (PARC HBM data will for instance feed into Zero Pollution Action and CSS indicators).

Comparing HBM data from across Europe can highlight regional differences linked to variations in environmental quality, climate, diet, consumer behavior and lifestyle (see expected outputs). This project will also be identifying exposure to CEC, including substitutes for banned substances, in the population can serve as a warning of undetected risk. Measuring effect biomarkers and studying associations with health outcome data will provide insight into the extent to which chemicals and substitutes have an impact on health and support chemical grouping approaches and avoidance of regrettable substitution.

Main expected outputs of the project

Data gaps filled by this project are expected to include:

- New internal aggregate and mixture exposure data and reference values for prioritized chemicals for all four geographical regions of Europe.
- Spatial and temporal trends in chemical exposure.
- Increased understanding of the sources and pathways of human exposure.
- Associations of exposures with (early) adverse effects and health impact.
- Identification of emerging chemicals of concern.
- An understanding of population exposure and the exposure of vulnerable groups against health-based human biomonitoring guidance values(HBM-GV)
- Advance methodologies for assessing health effects due to exposure to chemical mixtures through real-life co-exposure assessment.

Outcomes and impacts expected for end-users and stakeholders

The project will support the discoverability, accessibility and availability of high quality, reliable and coherent datasets on human exposure to chemicals at European level, supporting the sharing and reusing of HBM data across legislative silos. The HBM data can support time trend development and evaluation of policy efficacy (e.g., effect of REACH restrictions on exposure levels). Baseline human exposure data also allow comparison with international chemical monitoring programs such as NHANES and the Centers for Disease Control and Prevention (CDC). In addition, data on internal exposure generated by HBM provide a complete picture of human exposure and can be used to enhance chemical RA by providing information on actual human exposure via multiple exposure pathways likely to be regulated under separate policy silos. An understanding of the contribution that different exposure routes make to the overall exposure (taking into account differences in exposure modifiers, such as age and gender, as well as profession) provides the starting point for deciding on risk management (RM) measures under legislative silos. As such, this project contributes to the OSOA approach included in the CSS. In addition, identifying upstream exposure routes in various material flows - including in consumer products, via diet and in the occupational setting - can inform targeted efforts to minimize exposure by eliminating chemicals from material flows. Over the long term, the availability of information on exposure to chemicals in specific material flows, including products, will stimulate the production of safer chemicals, products and materials.

The results of the general population survey can be used by different stakeholders:

- ✓ PARC project partners, Governing Board (GB) members (responsible for RA at EU/national/regional level), EU agencies, and the scientific community: input for exposure science, modelling, RA, health impact assessment (HIA); monitor the impact of implementation of the EU's CSS
- ✓ Policy makers/regulators/Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development (OECD), World Health Organization (WHO), United Nations (UN): deriving policy recommendations for reduction of exposure, use of articles, chemicals production and release; evaluating the efficiency of regulation or the need for further action.

- ✓ Citizens: better understanding and awareness of exposure and risk; recommendations for lifestyle and prevention.
- ✓ Industrial hygienists, occupational physicians, workers, trade unions: release to the environment via production processes; worker exposure and protection.

Key words: Human biomonitoring (HBM), internal exposure levels, determinants of exposure, exposure-effect associations

Link to the PARC DoA:

The project responds to the PARC operational objective OO8.

The project contributes to the aim of T4.1 to perform an HBM survey targeting the general population which will form the basis of a well aligned HBM surveillance programme for chemical exposure of European citizens and will generate baseline internal exposure data. This project will deliver the statistically derived internal exposure reference values that will allow for evaluation of spatial and temporal trends in chemical exposure and monitoring of the impact of regulations and the EU’s CSS. As part of this project biomarkers of chemical exposure will be analysed in human samples from the General population (children 6-11 (N = ±3300-3500), teenagers 12-17 (N = ±2650-2750) and adults 18-39 (N = ± 4600-4750)). By collecting and generating HBM data for PARC priority chemicals and exposure scenarios across Europe, the project will contribute to specific objective (SO) 2 “European and national RA entities and their scientific networks carry out a joint research and innovation (R&I) program to respond to the agreed priorities in chemicals RA”. The project will support the understanding of the contribution of chemicals as upstream determinants of diseases, to the reduction of environmental and human health impact of exposure to hazardous chemicals, and as such to the improvement of the protection of environmental and citizen’s health, and awareness of citizens and professionals about risks of chemical exposures.

This project will deliver new HBM data with EU wide coverage for the period 2023-2026, building on existing capacity. The partners responsible for HBM conduct in their country/region are supported by this project and HBM practices are harmonized.

Links within PARC (WPs/Tasks/Activities/Projects)

- Other T4.1 projects:
 - ✓ P4.1.4.2.a_Y1_DataAnalysisHBM4EU_VITO
 - ✓ P4.1.3.1.a_Y1_DerivationofHBM-GVs_UBA
 - ✓ P4.1.3.3.a_Y1_RoadmapLinkingHBMhealth_SpF_VITO
 - ✓ Link HBM studies to health examination and dietary surveys
 - ✓ P4.1.1.4b_Y1_SentinelSystem_KULeuven
 - ✓ Targeted surveys
 - ✓ P4.1.1.4.c_Y1_HealthCareSurvey_TTL_SRU
 - ✓ P4.1.1.4.d_Y1_OccupWaste_ENSP_TTL
 - ✓ P4.1.1.4.a_Y1_OccupFeasability_TTL
 - ✓ P4.1.5.a_Y1_SustainHBMSystem_VITO
- T4.2: analyse associations between sources, external exposure data and internal exposure
- T4.3: development and proof of concept (PoC) of innovative tools and methods
- WP1: indicators to monitor progress and impact
- WP2: priority setting and uptake into policy
- WP3: communication and dissemination of results
- WP5: identification of effect biomarkers relevant for specific chemicals, age groups and health outcomes
- T6.2 projects: internal exposure data can be used to feed into aggregate and internal-external exposure modelling, mixture risk assessment (MRA), and HIA/Burden of Disease (BoD)
 - ✓ Strategy for aggregate exposure from general life and occupational exposures
 - ✓ Developing, performing and validation of source to dose modelling including selected case studies
 - ✓ Refinement and development of Physiologically Based Pharmacokinetic (PBPK) models for RA

- ✓ Real-life mixtures assessment
- ✓ Improvement of HIA methodologies
- ✓ Inventory of HIA data for PARC priority chemicals
- ✓ Case studies on HIA
- ✓ Development of a set of risk and health impact indicators
- WP7: FAIR and sustainable storage of HBM data; innovative data analysis
- WP8: Early Warning System (EWS)
- WP9:
 - ✓ inventory of HBM/HES studies (T9.2) that will support the identification of the opportunities in the HBM survey
 - ✓ laboratory networks (T9.1) as an essential key in the quality assurance and quality control (QA/QC) programme organization (T9.3) and implementation as well as in the analysis of the samples
 - ✓ training activities (T9.4) that can cover issues related to all the study phases (sampling, chemical analysis, statistical analysis, etc.).

Links outside PARC

- HBM4EU legacy: the project will build further on experiences, results, materials, and networks developed within HBM4EU
- European Human Exposome Network (EHEN) projects
- National/regional studies participating in the general survey
- Exposure levels observed in the survey can be compared with levels from other international HBM surveys such as Canadian Health Measures Survey (CHMS, Canada), National Health and Nutrition Examination Survey (NHANES, US)

Key PARC Deliverables and Milestones to which the project contributes

D4.3; D4.8; D4.12: Progress report on the general survey (M36; 48; 60)

D4.13: Concluding report summarizing the outcome of all studies for a future monitoring approach (M81)

Partners List:

Core partners: VITO (BE), ISCIII (ES), SPF (FR), UBA (DE), LNS (LU), RegionH (DK), INSA (PT).

Partners involved in statistical analysis of the data: ANSES (FR), AU (DK), AUTH (EL), BPI (EL), EASP (ES), INRAE (FR), INRS (FR), INSA (PT), INSERM (FR), IPA (DE), ISCIII (ES), ISSeP (BE), JSI (SI), LNS (LU), LSMU (LT), MU (CZ), NIJZ (SI), NIPH (NO), PIH (BE), Sciensano (BE), SLU, SPF (FR), SZU-SK (SK), UBA (DE), UGR (ES), UH (BE), UNIVIE (AT), UU-IRAS (NL), VITO (BE).

Partners involved in study conduct: AUTH (EL), EAA(AT), EASP (ES), INSA (PT), ISCIII (ES), ISS (IT), ISSeP (BE), JSI (SI), LNS (LU), LSMU (LT), MOH-CY/SGL (CY), MOH-IL (IL), NIOM (PL), NIPH (NO), NCPHP (HU), NIJZ (SI), PIH (BE), RegionH (DK), RIVM (NL), RSU (LV), SPF (FR), SZU-CZ (CZ), UI (IS), UKHSA (UK), University Tartu/ Health Board (EE), UPV/EHU (ES), VITO (BE), WULS (PL)

Schedule:

Starting date: 01/05/2022 (M1)

Expected ending date: 31/01/2029 (M81)

Costs

Expected PM for the fourth year of the project: 297 PM

Expected ODC for the fourth year of the project: 262 192 €

S4.1.1.3 Targeted surveys – 3 PROJECTS

P4.1.1.3.a Y4_PFAS Mother milk_BPI_LNS

Project Title	PFAS in Mother Milk: pregnancy and postnatal health		
Project Acronym (15 letters max)	PFASMotherMilk		
Project Manager	Radu Duca radu.duca@lns.etat.lu Konstantinos Kasiotis k.kasiotis@bpi.gr	LNS BPI	Luxembourg Greece
Deputy Project manager	Maria Torres Toda Maria.TorresToda@lns.etat.lu Machera Kyriaki k.machera@bpi.gr	LNS BPI	Luxembourg Greece
Expected starting date PARC (Month number)	M37	Expected duration (months)	45
PARC Workpackage number	WP4	PARC Task/Activity/Sub-activity:	4.1.1.3
Project Id	P4.1.1.3.a_Y4_PFAS Mother milk_BPI_LNS		

Status: Initiation

Summary of the project

The project aims to implement a longitudinal HBM survey, comprising three follow-ups, to address the most vulnerable population group: pregnant women and new-borns. It will investigate their exposure to relevant per- and polyfluoroalkyl substances (PFAS) across various biological samples, including identification of emerging PFAS, with particular emphasis on breast milk samples. This project addresses the specific research needs for PFAS in T4.1, T4.3, and T6.2, as outlined in the PARC initial prioritisation as well as some newly identified future activities.

The general population is exposed to PFAS via multiple sources and pathways, and it has been concluded that the unborn and newborn child is the most susceptible individual as regards to PFAS adverse health effects. The maternal transfer of PFAS to offspring occurs both prenatally and postnatally via breastfeeding. Relatively little is known on PFAS levels in maternal milk nowadays and across Europe.

Only very few individual PFAS molecules have been restricted and managed by now under the EU Persistent Organic Pollutant (POP) Regulation and REACH (<https://echa.europa.eu/hot-topics/perfluoroalkyl-chemicals-pfas>). The recent REACH group restriction proposal targets around 10,000 persistent PFAS. However, pending its full evaluation and effective EU-wide implementation, furthermore anticipated sector-specific derogations, it is evident that PFAS will continue to be emitted in the coming years and will remain in our (personal) environment for a very long time. The European Food Safety Authority (EFSA) extensively reviewed the epidemiological evidence for associations between PFAS exposure and adverse health effects (EFSA, 2018; EFSA, 2020)² concluding that more longitudinal epidemiological studies are needed on human endpoints, different populations, as well as more studies on adverse outcomes (AO) (e.g. immune AO). It is therefore important to better understand and characterise PFAS exposure of pregnant women and the newborn via breastfeeding, and how their exposure evolves over time, to effectively mitigate potential risks and health

² EFSA, 2018. Risk to human health related to the presence of perfluorooctane sulfonic acid and perfluorooctanoic acid in food. EFSA Journal, doi: 10.2903/j.efsa.2018.5194

EFSA, 2020. Risk to human health related to the presence of perfluoroalkyl substances in food. EFSA Journal, doi: 10.2903/j.efsa.2020.6223.

concerns. The results will cover a specific series of countries: Luxembourg, Greece, Czechia, The Netherlands, Austria, Slovenia, Spain, Cyprus and potentially Latvia.

Main expected outputs of the project

Filling data gaps for human health RA:

- PFAS exposure levels in pregnant women and children in various biological samples, particularly through the analysis of breast milk samples, which are underrepresented in current research. The implementation of such a longitudinal survey, comprising three follow-ups, will provide data on a highly vulnerable population group.
- PFASMotherMilk will generate data on longer-chain persistent PFAS previously prioritized within the PARC Aligned Studies, but also other, short-chained, PFAS with excretion kinetics via breast milk.
- PFASMotherMilk will include an assessment of effect biomarkers, such as leptin (LEP) methylation, LEP, oxidative stress, immunotoxicity markers, and thyroid hormones.

Innovative methods and approaches:

- HBM and Analytics: Development and validation of innovative biomonitoring and analytical methods for PFAS detection, furthermore, suspect screening (SS) approaches to identify potential emerging PFAS compounds.
- Estimating BoD : PFAS are chemicals of concern for population health in Europe and previous studies have estimated Disability-Adjusted Life Years (DALYs) attributable to risk factor specific exposure including PFAS in European countries based on HBM4EU data (Feasibility study by Plass et al., 2023³). PFASMotherMilk will select and assess relevant health impact biomarkers in support of BoD estimation associated with PFAS exposure of newborn, eventually informing HIA (in particular insights into the mediation effects of oxidative stress and LEP in obesity, enhancing the understanding of PFAS-related health effects).

Outcomes and impacts expected on end-users and stakeholders

- The proposed survey will provide crucial data on PFAS exposure and its health impacts, which are currently limited, particularly for vulnerable groups like pregnant women and children. End-users, including parents, healthcare providers, and caregivers will benefit from sensible and enhanced public dissemination about the results of the study on PFAS in breast milk, which will also serve to inform and support public health measures.
- Public health officials and policymakers will benefit from evidence-based insights in PFAS exposure in the vulnerable population group pregnant women and newborns via breast milk helping to inform current and future restriction needs.
- PFAS are used in a wide range of applications, governed by different regulatory frameworks, including industrial, consumer and medical applications. Furthermore, PFAS are ubiquitously present in the environment – accordingly, the results are relevant for several authorities governing the respective legislation, i.e. at EU level EFSA, EEA, ECHA, European Medicines Agency (EMA). The results will be also of relevance for national health authorities governing public health.

Outcomes and impacts expected to be incorporated into a specific regulatory framework

The EC CSS stresses that special attention should be given to the protection of vulnerable population groups such as children and pregnant women from exposure to groups of chemicals with known hazardous properties. Specifically, PFAS do require action, considering their wide use and the large number of cases of contamination of soil and water - including drinking water - in the EU (2020, CSS).

³ Plass, D., Kienzler, S., Bessems, J., Buekers, J., Cops, J., Purece, A., Beloconi, A., Vounatsou, P., Widmer, K. (2023). Estimating the burden of disease due to lead, PFAS, phthalates, cadmium, pyrethroids and bisphenol A using HBM4EU data – test of feasibility and first results for selected countries. (Eionet Report – ETC HE 2023/13). European Topic Centre on Human Health and the Environment.

Key words: Emerging PFAS; PFAS; health impacts; pregnancy; breast milk; breastfeeding; human biomonitoring; exposure biomarkers; effect biomarkers; burden of diseases.

Link to the PARC DoA

The project responds to the PARC operational objectives (OOs): OO4, OO5, OO6, OO7, OO8, OO10, OO12, OO9, OO11 and OO13

OO4-13: PFASMotherMilk aspires to formulate a basis for the exposure of pregnant women and newborns in early life through breast milk and systematically permit the monitoring of PFAS trends for the most vulnerable individuals in the future. It will also allow a review of the effectiveness of regulatory restrictions and RM provisions regarding human exposure and potential health impacts. Robust chemical analytical workflows, the generation of recent data on European pregnant and breastfeeding women expanding the list of PFAS exposure biomarkers, toxicokinetic information, and biomarkers of effect, will be communicated and integrated to R&I initiatives in PARC, characteristically operating in WP4 and WP6 (and not only), while PFAS data will feed health RA approaches. Attention will be given to the dissemination and communication of results and related substantive ethical implications on how to communicate HBM results for breast milk, considering limited guidance is available on how to report on breast milk chemical contamination, without jeopardizing the promotion of breastfeeding as a key nutrition pillar. In this direction, a case specific communication plan will be developed, demonstrating-separating the pivotal role of human breast milk and its potential “contamination”.

Links within PARC (WPs/Tasks/Activities/Projects)

WP3: Enhance communication and awareness about the results among stakeholders within PARC and beyond. This support will be particularly crucial in addressing the sensitive topic of breastfeeding benefits.

WP4: Alignment with PARC Aligned Studies (P4.1.1.2); P4.1.1.3.b_Y4_PFASChildren_SpF and Short PFAS in human samples project (T4.1.2.4). Common workshops / meetings will be further explored, especially with the P4.1.1.3.b_Y4_PFASChildren_SpF. HBM-GV for PFAS in serum (P4.1.3.1); RoadmapLinkingHBMhealth (P4.1.3.3) projects for the selection of relevant exposure and effect biomarkers. Collaboration with other activities within WP4 such as innovative methods (task 4.3, e.g. 4.3.2.1_H01_Perinatal Exposure).

WP6: PARC Real Life Mixtures project (WP6.2.3) to assess PFAS mixture risk based on HBM data and the relative potencies of selected PFAS for specific effects and respective AOs as part of T6.2.4 HIA and the related P6.2.4 projects (activities on BoD, etc).

WP7: Developing and implementing a robust data management plan (DMP) tailored to the specific study needs (P7.2.2.b). More details are given in data management part.

WP9: Establish laboratory networks for sample analysis and training for personnel involved in data collection and analysis. Sampling protocols reviewed and developed in PARC’s WP9 (9.1 and 9.3) to ensure consistency and avoid duplications in sampling procedures.

Links outside PARC

- The survey will exploit the synergies with the WHO/ United Nations Environment Programme (UNEP) study of POP in human milk and evaluation of the effectiveness and impact assessment of the Stockholm Convention. The survey aims to assess a variety of PFAS with a longitudinal dimension assessing maternal exposure during pregnancy and children exposure during early childhood. The selection of PFAS goes beyond those currently under the POP Regulation but is of paramount importance to consider co-exposure to Polychlorinated biphenyls (PCBs) and Dioxins regulated under the Stockholm Convention due to their known health impacts.
- National surveys on pregnant women and newborn: The broad study design allows PARC partners the flexibility to join with a mother-child pregnancy cohort or existing biological fluids and mother milk samples subject for further analysis.

Key PARC Deliverables and Milestones to which the project contributes

D4.6. 1st Progress report on targeted surveys (M48)

D4.15. 2nd Progress report on targeted surveys (M81)

Partners List:

LNS (Luxembourg), BPI (Greece), JSI (Slovenia), MU (Czechia), RIVM (The Netherlands), MUW (Austria), UGR (Spain), ONIRIS (France), SGL/MoH-CY (Cyprus), *RSU (Latvia) in a later stage.*

Schedule:

Starting date: 01/05/2025 (M37)

Expected ending date: 30/01/2029 (M81)

Costs

Expected PM for the first year of the project: 17 PM

Expected ODC for the first year of the project: 32 925 €

P4.1.1.3.b_Y4_PFASChildren_SpF

Project Title	Description of PFAS Exposure in early life in European countries: study on young children (6-11y)		
Project Acronym (15 letters max)	PFASChildren		
Project Manager	Loïc RAMBAUD loic.rambaud@santepubliquefrance.fr	SpFrance	France
Deputy Project manager	Rima SOUKI rima.souki@santepubliquefrance.fr	SpFrance	France
Expected starting date PARC (Month number)	M37	Expected duration (months)	45
PARC Workpackage number	WP4	PARC Task/Activity/Sub-activity:	4.1.1.3
Project Id	P4.1.1.3.b_Y4_PFASChildren_SpF		

Status: Initiation

Summary of the project

PFAS are widespread chemicals used in various industrial and commercial applications. They are very stable synthetic chemicals that dissolve in both water and lipids and are easily distributed in the environment. Moreover, they are bioaccumulating in living organisms and can be detected in almost every human. Several studies show that PFAS exposure can lead to specific adverse health effects in adults, teenagers but also children. There is growing awareness that exposure to environmental chemicals during critical developmental stages can potentially change a child's future health risks permanently, even when the doses are not impactful in adults. Furthermore, some studies have shown that children have higher body burden of PFAS exposure than adults, making the ubiquitous exposure even more alarming. In Europe, little is known about the exposure of children to PFAS. According to EFSA, diet is the major source of PFAS exposure for most of the population, but determinants might slightly differ for children as behaviour and metabolic rates are different compared to adults. EFSA also shows that PFAS intake for toddlers and children are approximately twofold higher than older age groups, which makes this subpopulation group of specific interest for PFAS exposure evaluation. Therefore, it is crucial to investigate the exposure to PFAS of this vulnerable population. This project focuses on the specific research requirements for PFAS identified

in T4.1, T4.3, and T6.2, as outlined in the initial prioritization of PARC and in a fact sheet detailing newly identified future activities.

The European CSS targets PFAS as a chemical group of interest for which European countries have to phase out their use. In PARC, PFAS have been prioritized among the PARC project as chemical substances of interest for which more data are needed in adults, teenagers and children. However, the General HBM Survey project P4.1.1.2 (PARC Aligned studies) will collect new data on PFAS exposure only for adults and teenagers due to difficulty to generalize the collection of blood samples from children for all participating studies. In the HBM4EU project, data on PFAS were collected only for teenagers.

In this project, we aim to build on existing national HBM capacities foreseeing to collect serum samples (among European children on a period between May 2024 and December 2026 and to harmonize them to the maximum extent possible. This project extends the work of P4.1.1.2 (PARC Aligned Studies) to PFAS among children. The resources and methodologies developed under the Aligned Studies Project will be used to obtain comparable data across EU countries. All phases of participating studies will be upfront harmonized in the framework of the PARC Aligned Studies project (P4.1.2.2), including harmonized materials and questionnaires, sampling timeframe, target population. These materials enable the exploration of determinants of exposure, such as sociodemographic factors, dietary habits, lifestyle, residential environments, and home exposures. Please refer to the following deliverables for more information: https://www.eu-parc.eu/sites/default/files/2023-09/PARC_AD4.1.pdf.

8 out of 16 Studies of the aligned studies for children are participating in this project. Gathered data will be used to 1) characterize PFAS levels of exposure for European Children population, 2) derive an internal exposure reference level for children and 3) investigate determinants of exposure. If available from P4.1.3.1a, a HBGV will be used to compare with observed levels of exposure. This will allow to estimate the proportion of children for which levels of exposure might lead to health adverse effects.

The opportunity will be evaluated to connect with available environmental data collected within T4.2 projects or other studies (outside PARC) to investigate exposure sources. This project will bring new individual data that are of relevance for regulatory framework restricting the production and use of PFAS in Europe to protect human and environmental health.

Main expected outputs of the project:

This project will collect more than 1,000 children (6-11 years) blood samples from 7 countries distributed in 3 European geographical areas (north, south and west) and will generate new and comparable HBM data for PFAS exposure. Targeted PFAS will be selected in coherence with PFAS compounds selected for teenagers and adults within the P4.1.1.2.a. GenHBMSurvey project as well as additional PFAS that we will define later in the project. The selection will be based on the analytical capacities of laboratories. This aims to describe levels of exposure to PFAS for children within Europe and compare levels between each country and covered geographical area.

By collecting data from questionnaires addressed to the participants for each involved study, the project will allow an analysis of determinant of exposure. This will increase the understanding of the sources and pathways of exposure for the children sub-population which is considered as more vulnerable. The comparison with a HMGV (if produced by P4.1.3.1.a) is expected to contribute to an evaluation of the health impact of PFAS exposure among children in Europe by providing meaningful information on the percentage of a part of European children having a higher health risk linked to PFAS exposure.

Moreover, as an ad-on and in complement to the targeted analysis, this project will contribute to the development and evaluation of an experimental new analytical method for non-targeted screening (NTS) on serum samples (T4.3). On a sub-sample of blood samples, this method could lead to the detection of potential PFAS biomarkers that were not included in the targeted list and provide data on the discovery scope set. The different partners have not committed to sending samples for NTS analysis yet, as this will depend on the success of method development and sample volume availability.

Outcomes and impacts expected on end-users and stakeholders:

HBM data are lacking within Europe to characterize PFAS exposure for Children. This project takes the opportunity to use the framework developed for the PARC Aligned HBM surveys (P4.1.1.2.a. GenHBMSurvey project) to produce harmonised and FAIR HBM data that will address this lack.

Levels of exposure that will be determined by this project could be used **as a future zero time point** for further time trend assessment of PFAS exposure within Children and serve as a reference for the evaluation of future European policies efficacy. The produced data could also be used for international comparisons with other HBM programs outside Europe.

HIA that will be done using available HBM-GVs will allow policy makers to have a better overview of the effects of PFAS exposure for Children within Europe and help to prioritize policies development to reduce harmful exposures. The determinants of exposure analysis will provide information of the routes of exposure to PFAS among Children and facilitate the elaboration of management measures. As such, this project contributes to the OSOA approach included in the European CSS.

The results of this project can be used by several stakeholders:

- PARC project partners, GB members, EU agencies and the scientific community for exposure science, RA, modelling, etc.
- Policy makers/regulators/OECD/WHO/UN for deriving policy recommendations for the reduction of PFAS exposure.
- Citizens for a better understanding and awareness of exposure levels and associated risks, recommendations for lifestyle and prevention.
- Indirectly, the chemical industry will also benefit, of the results by receiving clear indication on PFAS that can be problematic for children exposure and encouraging them to shift in PFAS production practices or the substitution of PFAS with alternative substance groups altogether

Outcomes and impacts expected to be incorporated into a specific regulatory framework:

Further European regulations are needed to prevent PFAS exposure and particularly for some specific vulnerable sub-population groups such as young children. The data generated by this project will provide a European-scale baseline of children's exposure to PFAS and identify key determinants of exposure that could be used as a reference for setting an objective of reduction within new regulations. This information can directly support various regulatory frameworks such as the PFAS restriction (REACH), the POPs Regulation, the European CSS, and the universal PFAS ban to evaluate the impact of those regulations or proposed restrictions/bans.

Key words: Human biomonitoring, Exposure, Determinants of exposure, PFAS, Perfluorinated Compounds, emerging PFAS, Children, Early life, NTS, Indicators.

Link to the PARC DoA:

The project responds to the PARC OOs: OO5, OO6, OO7, OO8, OO10.

The project extends the HBM capacities by collecting and harmonizing PFAS exposure data from European children, addressing gaps in the existing HBM4EU platform. It supports regulatory efforts, including the European CSS, by providing crucial data on exposure levels and health risks. The project increases public awareness of chemical RA through effective dissemination of findings. By implementing FAIR data practices, it ensures that data is accessible and reusable for future research and policy-making.

Links within PARC (WPs/Tasks/Activities/Projects):

- WP4 projects or activities:
 - PARC Aligned HBM studies (P4.1.1.2a)
 - Derivation of health based HBM-GVs (P4.1.3.1a)
 - Targeted surveys
 - Statistical analyses, statistical analysis plan T4.1

- Analyse associations between sources, external exposure data and internal exposure
- Link with P4.1.1.3.a_Y4_PFAS_mother_milk_LNS_BPI: explore possible links to this project (workshops together) and aligning certain aspects
- Potential link to environmental monitoring (T4.2)
- Development and PoC of innovative tools and methods (T4.3)
- WP3: communication and dissemination of results
- WP7: DMP, FAIR and sustainable storage of HBM data, innovative data analysis
- WP8: Contribution to EWS
- WP9: Laboratory network for QA/QC programme organization and implementation of samples analysis, Training for issues related to the study phases (sampling, chemical analysis, statistical analysis, etc.)

Links outside PARC

This project is built on national capacities among some European countries and rely on the population surveys run by participant countries. Each survey is already contributing to the PARC Aligned studies project but still remains national independent projects run for national objectives. The interaction with this project consists in providing serum samples collected at national (or regional) scale.

Key PARC Deliverables and Milestones to which the project contributes

- D4.6. 1st Progress report on targeted surveys (M48)
- D4.15. 2nd Progress report on targeted surveys (M81)

Partners List:

SpF (FR), RegionH (DK), University Tartu (EE), Health Board (EE), AUTH (EL), JSI (SI), NIJZ (SI), UBA (DE), LNS (LU), ONIRIS (FR), VITO (BE)

Schedule:

Starting date: 01/05/2025 (M37)
 Expected ending date: 31/01/2029 (M81)

Costs

Expected PM for the first year of the project: 20 PM
 Expected ODC for the first year of the project: 6 500 €

P4.1.1.3.c_Y4_TimePatternEU_VITO

Project Title	Time patterns of internal human exposure to environmental pollutants in Europe		
Project Acronym (15 letters max)	TimePatternEU		
Project Manager	Hamid Hassen hamid.hassen@vito.be	VITO	Belgium
Deputy Project manager	Jiří Kalina kalina@mail.muni.cz	MU	Czech Republic
Expected starting date PARC (Month number)	M37	Expected duration (months)	36
PARC Work package number	WP4	PARC Task/Activity/Sub-activity:	4.1.1.3
Project Id	P4.1.1.3.c_Y4_TimePatternEU_VITO		

Status: Initiation

Summary of the project

In the HBM4EU and PARC project, several HBM data has and will be generated in children, teenagers, and adults. Although significant insights have been obtained so far, efforts dedicated to investigating the time patterns of internal exposure levels of environmental pollutants in the EU were limited. Determining the trend of population level exposure concentrations across time is crucial to monitor the impact of policies, regulations, and interventions. The findings from this study would trigger EU and country level regulatory measures. Foremost, regulatory agencies of respective country and region could use the findings to evaluate the impact of previous policies and update future policies aimed at reducing human exposure to environmental pollutants. Furthermore, determining the trend would push regulatory enforcement of existing policies to monitor and control pollutant sources. It would also guide the design and implementation of targeted public health interventions aiming at raising awareness about the risks associated with environmental pollutants and promoting healthier lifestyle choices to decrease personal exposure. In general, this study would play a crucial role in protecting society from environmental pollutants through informing policy development, regulatory enforcement, and public health interventions.

This project will involve analysing data on internal exposure levels of selected environmental pollutants over time using HBM data. A study group is established involving partners with existing HBM studies with consecutive cycles or longitudinal cohorts and additional partners specialized in the methodological approaches to statistically analyse time pattern data. Each of the study data owners harmonizes their HBM data to the PARC basic codebook, checks their data using the data validation tool, and analyses their own data using the same statistical methods as elaborated in the PARC statistical analysis plan using the common script that will be developed during the project. Moreover, after checking the feasibility, for studies with overlapping time periods and exposure biomarkers, pooled analysis will be performed.

Based on availability of consecutive cycles and regulatory need, we prioritized the following group of substances: Phthalates and substitutes, PFAS, PCBs, Metals, Bisphenols, Pesticides, flame retardants (FRs), Polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons (PAHs), Volatile organic compounds (VOCs), Acrylamide, ultraviolet (UV) filters. To fill in the data gap for some of the studies, chemical analysis might be needed on biobank samples.

Main expected outputs of the project

The main outputs from this project will be the time patterns for the internal exposure levels of selected pollutants for each country and region. These time patterns will be compared descriptively between studies. Furthermore, pooled results of patterns and trends will be identified if feasible depending on the similarity of time periods, number of cycles, measurement techniques, and target populations, allowing comparisons between different countries and regions in the EU. Numerical parameters summarizing the rate of observed changes and variability across time periods and subgroups will be estimated. Based on the observed patterns, forecasts or projections of future trends will be generated. The underlying factors driving the observed trends and their implications, through comparisons with policy changes, external factors or interventions will be discussed. The results of the analysis will be presented graphically, such as through time series plots or other visualizations, to aid interpretation and communication of findings. Summary statistics, analysis results and figures will be integrated into the Information Platform for Chemical Monitoring (IPCHEM) and the European HBM dashboard. IPCHEM will be phased out, and the EC will support another chemical platform. Results from this project will feed into that platform.

Outcomes and impacts expected on end-users and stakeholders

The outputs of this project aid stakeholders in understanding the evolution of internal exposures of environmental pollutants over time, enabling informed decision making, and the formulation of strategies for intervention or further research. The results derived from this project are applicable to various stakeholders, including:

1. Policy makers/regulators – local and regional

Policy makers can make more informed decisions based on the insights gained from understanding patterns of internal exposure across time. This can include decisions related to policy formulation, resource allocation, investment strategies, program planning, and support evaluation of the efficiency of regulation or the need for further action.

2. EC, EU agencies, member states

Identifying the time pattern can help identify emerging risks or changes in risk levels over time, allowing EC, EU agencies and member states to implement proactive measures to mitigate or manage these risks effectively. It contributes to the monitoring of the impact of implementation of the EU's CSS and zero pollution action plan. Moreover, the time trend analysis provides a basis for monitoring the performance of programs, policies, or interventions over time. Stakeholders can assess whether objectives are being met, identify areas for improvement, and make necessary adjustments.

3. Advocacy groups

Showing the time pattern can serve as a valuable tool for advocacy efforts by providing empirical evidence to support positions or arguments. This can be particularly useful for advocating for policy changes or increased investment in specific areas.

4. Citizens

Findings can be used to raise public awareness about important issues, trends, or challenges facing society. This can contribute to increased understanding, engagement, and support for relevant initiatives. Furthermore, understanding trends in behaviour or consumption patterns over time can inform efforts to promote behavioural change, such as encouraging healthier lifestyles, reducing environmental impact, or promoting sustainable practices.

Outcomes and impacts expected to be incorporated into a specific regulatory framework

The project's outcomes, particularly the harmonized data and identified patterns in human internal exposure to environmental pollutants, will contribute to regulatory frameworks like the REACH and the European CSS. By providing robust evidence on long-term exposure patterns, the findings will support RA and chemical regulation processes. Furthermore, country-level exposure patterns and future forecasting will aid in updating safety limits and policy measures of respective country or region.

Key words: Time pattern; internal exposure; Human Biomonitoring; EU

Link to the PARC DoA

The results of this project will contribute to the overall goal of WP4, monitoring and tracing chemicals in humans and the environment. This project is part of Task 4.1 which seamlessly aligns with the overarching objectives of the PARC. By exploring the time patterns of internal human exposure, this project contributes significantly to one of the aims of Task 4.1 mainly evaluating the temporal trends in chemical exposure, thereby enhancing our ability to monitor the effectiveness of regulations, the EU's CSS and interventions. The project responds to the PARC OOs: OO4, OO6, OO8, OO10 and OO13.

Assessing temporal trends in chemical exposure is crucial for monitoring the effectiveness of regulations and the EU's sustainability strategy, as highlighted in the PARC objectives (OO4). To achieve this, data from individual studies will be harmonized to align with the proposed analysis method, facilitating communication with regulators at both country and regional levels (OO8, OO10). The statistical analysis method developed within this project will be utilized by partners and contribute to updating the statistical analysis plan for Task 4.1 (OO10). Data owners will receive training on statistical methods for time pattern and trend analysis to apply to their own data (OO13). Furthermore, the project findings will be disseminated to the general public (OO6), the PARC consortium, and policymakers to inform regulatory decisions (OO4).

Links within PARC (WPs/Tasks/Activities/Projects)

The project has significant interactions with work packages, tasks, activities, and projects within PARC, ensuring alignment and maximizing synergies.

WP2: Priority setting and uptake into policy: The findings of this project will be crucial for informing policy decisions. The project will provide insights that should feed into WP2's efforts to prioritize issues and facilitate policy uptake. This interaction will occur during the final phases of the project when results become available and are ready for integration.

WP3: Synergies, communication, and awareness: The results need to be effectively communicated to ensure that stakeholders are aware of key results and their implications. WP3 will support the dissemination of relevant findings, particularly concerning specific research questions addressed by the project.

WP7: Data management plan, innovative data analysis: This project will closely coordinate with WP7 to ensure that data management practices are aligned with PARC's standards, and to leverage innovative data analysis techniques developed within WP7. This includes contributing to and benefiting from the FAIR HBM datasets project (P7.2.2.b). The interaction will be ongoing, particularly during the early phases of data harmonization and method development, ensuring that data management and analytical approaches are robust and standardized.

WP4: Identifying trends in internal exposure levels: The identified trends in internal exposure levels, will provide valuable input for other projects within WP4, such as T4.1 (analysis of trends using HBM data) and T4.2 (environmental samples). This will enhance the understanding of exposure dynamics across different population groups and regions. Whenever studies have consecutive cycles of environmental samples from T4.2, we will consider comparing the patterns of internal exposure (our findings) with environmental exposure (T4.2). This comparison will be conducted during interpretation, rather than through direct data integration, to explore correlations and contrasts between internal and environmental exposure trends.

Links outside PARC

This project builds further on existing regional/national HBM studies. This study will enhance our understanding of how human exposure to environmental chemicals has changed over time across different countries and regions in the EU. This will contribute to the European Green Deal towards zero pollution. Furthermore, the internal exposure trend from this study can be compared with other international trends such as CHMS (Canada), NHANES (US), etc.

Key PARC Deliverables (or Additional Deliverables) and Milestones to which the project contributes

D4.6: 1st progress report on targeted surveys (M48)

D4.15: 2nd progress report on targeted surveys (M81)

Although not official deliverable, it will also contribute to the Statistical Analysis Plan (SAP) for T4.1 projects

Partners List: VITO (Belgium), MU (Czech Republic), KI (Sweden), MU (Czech Republic), NIPH (Norway), RegionH-RH (Denmark), SFA (Sweden), SpF (France), SZU-CZ (Czech Republic), UBA (Germany), UH (Belgium), UI (Iceland), ULUND (Sweden), ISS (Italy), VITO (Belgium)

Schedule:

Starting date: 01/05/2025 (M37)

Expected ending date: 30/04/2028 (M72)

Costs

Expected PM for the first year of the project: 25 PM

Expected ODC for the first year of the project: NA

S4.1.1.4 Occupational surveys – 2 PROJECTS

P4.1.1.4.a_Y1_OccupFeasability_TTL (closed M29)

Project Title	Feasibility study to evaluate occupational exposure in general surveys		
Project Acronym (15 letters max)	OccupFeasability		
Project Manager	Tiina Santonen tiina.santonen@ttl.fi	Finnish Institute of Occupational Health	Finland
Deputy Project manager	-	-	-
Expected starting date PARC (Month number)	1	Expected duration	29*
PARC Workpackage number	4	PARC Task/Activity/Sub-activity:	4.1.1
Project Id	P4.1.1.4.a_Y1_OccupFeasability_TTL		

*The project closed M29, the related AD4.8 is planned to be submitted M34

P4.1.1.4.b_Y1_SentinelSystem_KULeuven (closed M36)

Project Title	Assessment of exposure to substances of high concern in the working population through a sentinel surveillance system: Mapping and preparation of proof-of-concept		
Project Acronym (15 letters max)	SentinelSystem		
Project Manager	Lode Godderis Lode.godderis@kuleuven.be	KULeuven	Belgium
Deputy Project manager	Emine Aktas Bajalan emine.aktasbajalan@kuleuven.be Aziza Menouni aziza.menouni@kuleuven.be	-	-
Expected starting date PARC (Month number)	1	Expected duration	36
PARC Workpackage number	4	PARC Task/Activity/Sub-activity:	4.1.1.4
Project Id	P4.1.1.4.b_Y1_SentinelSystem_KULeuven		

*The project will be closed M36, a final project report will be submitted M39

P4.1.1.4.c_Y1_HealthCareSurvey_TTL_SRU

Project Title	Occupational survey in the healthcare sector		
Project Acronym (15 letters max)	HealthcareSurvey		
Project Manager	Tiina Santonen tiina.santonen@ttl.fi	Finnish Institute of Occupational Health	Finland
Deputy Project manager	Paul Scheepers paul.scheepers@ru.nl	Stichting Radboud University	Netherlands
Expected starting date PARC (Month)	1	Expected duration	48

number)			
PARC Workpackage number	4	PARC Task/Activity/Sub-activity:	4.1.1
Project Id	P4.1.1.4.c_Y1_HealthcareSurvey_TTL_SRU		

Status: Implementation

Summary of the project

In this project we will perform a cross sectional study in the hospital-based healthcare to assess the exposure and risks to priority chemicals of concern by using exposure and effect biomonitoring. This will contribute to further improvement of healthy and safe working conditions. The project will target the following chemicals:

- Hazardous medicinal products (including cytotoxic drugs)
- Inhalation anaesthetics
- Disinfectant and cleaning products (including biocides)

The project aims are to introduce HBM as an approach to study both exposure and effects related to the use of chemicals in hospital-based healthcare. This will lead to more awareness and better understanding of how work practices contribute to internal exposure to chemicals and how these practices can be further improved to reduce uptake of these chemicals. We aim for 20-24 hospitals in 10-12 EU member states.

More specifically the project aims to:

1. Identify chemical exposures of concern and relevant exposure scenarios in the hospital-based healthcare;
2. Study how HBM can inform chemical RA of hazardous medicinal products, inhalation anaesthetics, disinfection products and cleaning products (biocides);
3. Contribute to the further improvement of healthy and safe working conditions
4. Study contributions from different sources of exposure, also outside work, in assessment of aggregated exposure;
5. Develop HBM-based approaches for the assessment and management of chemical exposures in hospital-based healthcare.

The regulatory processes

In 2019 it was agreed that hazardous drugs, including cytotoxic drugs, should adhere to minimum requirements for the protection of health and safety of workers, in particular those provided for in the Council Directive 98/24/EC and in the Carcinogens and Mutagens Directive 2004/37/EC (CMD). Development of a new guidance to support the implementation of safe use of hazardous medicinal products at work is currently ongoing based on a previous evaluation (European Commission, 2021). In December 2021, the European Parliament proposed to bring reprotoxic chemicals under the remit of the CMD. This will require further development of protocols for measurement of chemical exposures on the workplace, especially for periods of higher susceptibility such as during pregnancy.

Main expected outputs of the project

- A dataset describing the current exposure to selected chemicals in approximately 20-24 hospitals in approximately 10-12 EU Member States
- An improved understanding of how current work practices in the hospital-based healthcare translate to internal exposure to selected chemicals
- Recommendations for policy changes in line with current and new health and safety procedures and sustainability programmes on national and EU level

Outcomes and impacts expected for end-users and stakeholders

- For workers, employers, occupational hygienists and occupational physicians: better understanding and increased awareness of the potential health risk of chemical exposures;
- Recommendations for RM leading to improved work practices

- The scientific community and primarily other partners in PARC: potential added value of HBM approach as input for RA and HIA
- For policymakers, EU and national regulators, EU Agencies (EU OSHA): evaluating the efficiency of current regulations and further development of these existing regulations and implementation of the new harmonised guidance on safe use of Hazardous medicinal products (HMPs) including cytotoxic drugs.

Key words: occupational exposure, hospital, risk management measures, hazardous medicinal products, cytotoxic drugs, inhalation anaesthetics, disinfection, cleaning, biocides

Link to the PARC DoA

T4.1 on HBM aims at measuring total exposure to priority compounds in humans considering different sources, chemical fates & exposure pathways. The current project uses HBM data and tries to understand how much occupational exposure contributes to general, adult population total exposure to different compounds and whether it is possible to identify possibly new occupational exposure sources from general population survey datasets.

The healthcare survey is an occupational study that contributes to increased understanding/ awareness of the chemicals used in the hospital-based healthcare setting (OO6). It has been designed to support the recent policy actions under EU CMRD (carcinogens, mutagens and reproductive toxic substances directive), with the recent inclusion of hazardous medicinal products. Based on the prior experience on occupational studies performed in HBM4EU we will introduce established and innovative biomarkers of exposure and effect related to selected priority chemicals (hazardous medicinal products, inhalation anaesthetics and disinfection/cleaning products). For this we will develop a network of laboratories and research centers in 10 countries (OO11). We expect that our results will support health and safety policy, including the development of biological guidance values (OO8).

Links within PARC (WPs/Tasks/Activities/Projects)

The project is linked to other activities within WP4, specifically aligned studies planned under WP4. It can provide recommendations to be considered in PARC aligned HBM studies. Thus, PARC WP4 projects it is closely linked to include:

- Project: P4.1.1.2.a General population HBM survey
- Project: P4.1.1.4.b Assessment of exposure through a sentinel surveillance system
- Project: P4.1.1.4.d Occupational survey in waste management
- Project: P4.3.2.b Proof-of-concept of innovative sampling and High Resolution Mass Spectrometry (HRMS) based screening methods for exploring occupational exposure to chemicals of emerging concern.
- Project: P4.1.3.3.a Roadmap from exposure to health

In addition, close collaboration is made with following activities/projects within T4.1:

- T4.1.1.1 activity related to development of supporting materials for fieldwork
- T4.1.2 on QA and analytics related to selection of laboratories
- T4.1.4 related to statistical data analyses

This also links to WP6 and especially to activities related to aggregate exposure from multiple sources and routes of exposure for the general population and workers (task 6.2.1) and mixture RA (task 6.2.3). Since the exposure of health care personnel typically consists of mixed exposure to several compounds, the data collected can be used as a case study in 6.2.3.

Links outside PARC

- Previous HBM4EU occupational studies on chromates, e-waste and diisocyanates
- EU-OSHA funded project aiming to provide a practical guidance on preventing and reducing occupational exposure to HMPs, including cytotoxic drugs
- Inhalation anaesthetics study funded by the social fund of the Netherlands Federation of Academic Hospitals (Project number F2491)

- Ethanol exposure assessment study funded by the social fund of the Netherlands Federation of Academic Hospitals (Project number F2492)
- Masarykova Univerzita (MU). National network of monitoring of drugs in the hospitals and pharmacies in Czech Republic and Slovakia (see: <https://www.cytostatika.cz/>)

Key PARC Deliverables and Milestones to which the project contributes

D4.7 Progress report on occupational surveys (M48).

Partners List:

TTL (FI), SRU (NL), MU (CZ), AU (DK), UGR (ES), INRS (FR), ISS (IT), UMIL (IT), UNINA (IT), UNIPD (IT), RSU (LV), LNS (LU), SGGW (PL), ENSP (PT), HSE (UK), IOM (UK), UGR (ES), INSST (ES)

Schedule:

Starting date: 01/05/2022 (M1)

Expected ending date: 30/04/2026 (M48)

Costs

Expected PM for the fourth year of the project: 17 PM

Expected ODC for the fourth year of the project: 8 326 €

P4.1.1.4.d_Y1_OccupWaste_ENSP_TTL

Project Title	Occupational survey in the waste management sector		
Project Acronym (15 letters max)	Occup_Waste		
Project Manager	Tiina Santonen tiina.santonen@ttl.fi	Finnish Institute of Occupational Health	Finland
Deputy Project manager	Susana Viegas Susana.viegas@ensp.unl.pt	ENSP-UNL NOVA National School of Public Health	Portugal
Expected starting date PARC (Month number)	1	Expected duration	48
PARC Workpackage number	4	PARC Task/Activity/Sub-activity:	4.1
Project Id	P4.1.1.4.d_Y1_OccupWaste_ENSP-TTL		

Status: Implementation

Summary of the project

The EC adopted a new Circular Economy Action Plan - one of the main building blocks of the European Green Deal, Europe's new agenda for sustainable growth. With measures along the entire life cycle of products, the new Action Plan aims to make EU economy fit for a green future, strengthen competitiveness while protecting the environment and provide new rights to consumers (EC, 2020). As Europe moves towards a more circular economy, the product of today will become the raw material of tomorrow. The waste management sector is expected to play a pivotal role in this development.

Based on this, an increase is expected of the number of workers involved in processes and tasks related with waste streams where the potential for circularity is high. Some of these waste streams are for instance electronics, batteries and vehicles, plastics, textiles, general household, and construction and buildings materials. The reuse and recycling of these materials could result in an increase of exposure (e.g., metals, flame retardants, phthalates) of workers involved in different steps of the waste processing chain such as collection, sorting, dismantling, shredding and further pre-processing and purification of waste components to allow their use as raw materials in different processes and industries (e.g., textile, plastics - and also PVC, furniture, construction). Additionally, the increase in waste volumes and complexity may reduce the

capability of the sector to process waste safely.

In the scope of HBM4EU project an exploratory study in occupational exposures in electrical and electronic waste (E-waste) processing was developed and a study protocol using a cross sectional survey design to study worker's exposures and compare these to the exposure of non-exposed individuals preferably was implemented (Scheepers et al., 2021). This study protocol can be adapted to future European-wide occupational studies developed in the scope of PARC such as the one described here.

Overall, the project aims to understand waste management workers exposure to chemicals since new materials in the waste stream may pose additional risks to waste sector workers. The waste streams that will be the focus of this study are the e-waste and plastics (household and industry).

The regulatory processes the project can support are mainly REACH and Occupational safety and health (OSH) processes. When general population HBM data is used for the exposure assessment it is important to understand the main sources of exposure. On the other hand, the data may contribute to the occupational exposure assessment under REACH or OSH processes.

Main expected outputs of the project

The main outputs and impacts expected from the project are:

- Provide EU relevant data on chemical exposures in the e-waste and plastics (household and industrial) waste streams to be used as scientific evidence to support several actions at different levels, namely: companies and workers level, country level and, also, EU policy level for adaptation and/or create new policies if considered needed.
- Evaluate the usefulness of biomonitoring as a tool to assess complex exposures such as the ones that can happen in these occupational settings.
- Identify the project outputs value as a contribution for identifying exposure scenarios at the general population level.

Outcomes and impacts expected for end-users and stakeholders

The results of the survey can be used by different stakeholders:

- PARC project partners and the scientific community: input for exposure science, modelling, RA, HIA; monitoring of the impact of implementation of the EU OSH directives
- Policy makers, EU and national regulators, EU Agencies (EU OSHA): deriving further regulation and guidance, evaluating the efficiency of current regulations.
- Workers and trade unions, industrial hygienists, occupational physicians: better understanding and awareness of exposure and risk; recommendations for RM.

Key words: occupational exposure, HBM, waste management, circular economy

Link to the PARC DoA

The project responds to the PARC OOs OO4, OO7, OO8, OO9, OO11 and OO13.

The project will foster regulatory uptake of PARC knowledge since it will provide EU relevant data on chemical exposures and RA in the e-waste and plastics (household and industrial) waste streams to be used as scientific evidence to support several actions at different levels, namely : companies and workers level, country level and, also, EU policy level for adaptation and/or create new policies if considered needed in different regulatory frameworks (e.g. OSHA, Environment, REACH). The project will also boost the existing networks of laboratories and research centres and develop new ones and it will contribute to build capacities by developing and carrying out training and exchange programmes in chemical RA.

Links within PARC (WPs/Tasks/Activities/Projects)

Considering the data that will be produced by the project it can be linked to WP2 and with WP3 . Also, WP5 , particularly with the tasks developed in the scope of characterizing Adverse Outcome Pathways (AOPs) and relevant effect biomarkers since the project will also integrate the AOPs approach to allow a better understanding of the mechanism of action of the chemicals and mixtures and to select the most suitable biomarkers of effect to be used. Within WP4, the project is linked to all other WP4.1 activities and projects, especially to Occupational survey on health care workers (sharing e.g. some standard operating

procedures (SOPs)), on the development of survey materials (4.1.1.1), project P4.1.3.3.a_Y1_RoadmapLinkingHBMhealth_SpF_VITO on roadmap from exposure to health (4.1.3.3), QA and analytical activities (4.1.2), statistical data analysis activities (4.1.4). In addition, the project is linked to task WP4.3: Innovative sampling methods and metabolomic studies since these new methods are planned to be tested within the project.

Additionally, this project will have several linkages with WP6 where the exposure to several substances will trigger multiple collaborations such as development and use of integrative models to determine and quantify the internal exposure to chemicals from different routes and sources of exposure and to combine several routes and sources of exposure and/or exposures obtained from different methodologies. The data generated within this project can be used for the assessment of risks of mixed exposure to multiple hazardous substances within waste management sector. Along the same lines, links with WP9 will probably emerge when planning the study and also in a later stage, when the data will start to become available and used for training and capacity building purposes.

Links outside PARC

The EU-OSHA's is developing a third foresight cycle that looks at changes in work that may result from the EU's transition to a circular economy (CE) and the potential impact on OSH (<https://osha.europa.eu/en/emerging-risks/circular-economy>). Our project, developed in the scope of PARC, will provide useful information to streamline this objective. Additionally, our project will continue the work developed in the scope of HBM4EU Project, particularly in what concerns to the E-Waste study since it intends to use the samples (biomonitoring and industrial hygiene samples) already collected and look for other substances that were not targeted in the E-Waste study (Scheepers et al., 2021). These are for instance cobalt and antimony due to their possible presence in this type of waste and the need of exposure data already recognize in the International Agency for Research on Cancer (IARC) evaluation developed recently (Karagas et al., 2022). Additionally, for those results of E-waste study that were not possible to be analysed in detail during HBM4EU, an extensive statistical analysis will be performed for the further refinement of waste management study design to be developed in PARC.

Key PARC Deliverables and Milestones to which the project contributes

D4.7: First Progress report on occupational surveys (M48).

Partners List:

ENSP (Portugal); AU(Denmark); ISS (Italy); UNIPD (Italy); UMIL (Italy); UNINA (Italy); WULS (Poland); ULUND (Sweden); STAMI (Norway); AUTH (Greece); INSA (Portugal); TTL (Finland); LNS (Luxembourg); MOH-CY (Cyprus); NIOM (Poland); IOM (UK); HSE (UK); UGranada (ES).

Schedule:

Starting date: 01/05/2022 (M1)

Expected ending date: 30/04/2026 (M48)

Costs

Expected PM for the fourth year of the project: 22 PM

Expected ODC for the fourth year of the project: 34 155 €

S4.1.1.5 Implementation of innovative methods

No project submitted at present.

A4.1.2 Laboratory analysis and quality assurance

No project submitted at present.

A4.1.3 Link exposure and health related information – 3 PROJECTS

S4.1.3.1 Propose health-based HBM guidance values – 2 PROJECTS

P4.1.3.1.a_Y1_DerivationofHBM-GVs_UBA

Project Title	Propose health-based HBM guidance values (HBM-GVs)		
Project Acronym (15 letters max)	P4.1.3.1.a_Y1_DerivationofHBM-GVs_UBA		
Project Manager	Petra Apel Petra.apel@uba.de	UBA	Germany
Deputy Project manager	NA	NA	NA
Expected starting date PARC (Month number)	1	Expected duration	81*
PARC Workpackage number	4	PARC Task/Activity/Sub-activity:	4.1.3.1
Project Id	P4.1.3.1.a_Y1_DerivationofHBM-GVs_UBA		

*The project has been extended from M36 to M81.

Status: Implementation

Summary of the project

Task 4.1 includes HBM to support EU chemicals policy. As a prerequisite for a health-related interpretation of HBM results, guideline values are needed that have been derived epidemiologically or toxicologically and relate directly to measured human exposure. The purpose of the present project is therefore to derive and agree on further such values for priority substances identified within PARC for which specific exposure biomarkers are defined in sub-task 4.1.2. Consensus on these values should be reached within the PARC project to achieve broad scientific acceptance for these values and to ensure a harmonized assessment of HBM results. It is envisaged that the values will be agreed in stages, first at the 4.1.3.1.a project level and then via National Hub Coordinators (NHCs) and National Hub Contact Points (NHCPs) within a wider circle of experts involved in PARC. HBM-GVs for the general population and/or workers are generally intended to be derived according to the agreed strategy for deriving HBM-GVs (Apel et al., 2020), but continuous development of the strategy is planned and will be taken into account when deriving the values. In individual cases, PBPK/TK modelling may be necessary and corresponding results would then have to be made available within PARC. Cooperation with sub-task 5.3.4 should be sought in this regard. A level of confidence should be attributed to the derived HBM-GVs.

Main expected outputs of the project

Over the course of the seven-year PARC project, a set of HBM-GVs will be successively established. These assessment tools can then be used for health-related RA of survey results in the general population and in the workplace.

Outcomes and impacts expected for end-users and stakeholders

Comparison of PARC HBM data with HBM-GVs allow statements on whether citizens or subpopulations in European regions are at risk of health effects and whether measures for risk mitigation have to be recommended or adapted. With the help of further information e.g. on marketing and findings from HBM accompanying questionnaires on individual product use, the use of HBM-GVs as an assessment tool can have an improving effect on regulations for food, cosmetics, etc. HBM-GVs can also be used to assess local event-related HBM investigations.

Furthermore, HBM-GVs can also be used to develop impact indicators that illustrate physical exposure and possible health risks in a simple and easily accessible way, helping to inform a wider audience (e.g. citizens). HBM-GVs can also be used as a basis for RA of mixtures, e.g. by applying the hazard index approach or mixture assessment/ allocation factors.

Key words: health-based human biomonitoring guidance values, human biomonitoring guidance values, HBM-GVs, risk assessment

Link to the PARC DoA

The project responds to the PARC OOs OO4, OO5, OO6, OO7, OO8, OO10, OO12 and OO9. Based on survey data, HBM-GVs make it possible to check whether the RAs and risk reduction measures carried out in the context of substance and product regulation or in the workplace are appropriate or need to be corrected (OO4, OO8, OO9, OO10, OO12). In line with the DoA, the HBM-GVs as project results could also contribute to potential PARC responses to new and urgent needs for information at EU and national level (OO6). Cooperation with other international R&I initiatives in the field of biomonitoring and chemical RA will also be promoted (OO5).

Links within PARC (WPs/Tasks/Activities/Projects)

- A4.1.4 data management and analysis
- A5.1.1 Closing data gaps of concern for human health
- A5.3.2 AOP development based on integration
- A5.3.4 PBTK models and quantitative systems toxicology
- A6.2.3 Mixture exposure and RA
- A6.2.4 Human health impact assessment and risk indicators
- A6.3.1 Substance and effect specific reviews
- WP7: FAIR data

Links outside PARC

1. National activities on HBM assessment values: e.g. German HBM Commission (HBM values); Health Canada (biomonitoring equivalents); ANSES, TTL i.a. (OELs)
2. OECD activities on deriving occupational biomonitoring levels
3. i-HBM activities on collecting and comparing HBM assessment values
4. EFSA/ECHA activities

Key PARC Deliverables and Milestones to which the project contributes

- AD4.3 Derivation of HBM-GVs - first set (M36)
- AD4.15 Derivation of HBM-GVs/ HBM-EECRs – second set of toxicological assessment values (will include all reports with submission date until M60) (M60)
- AD4.17 Derivation of HBM-GVs/ HBM-EECRs – third set of toxicological assessment values (will include all reports with submission date until M81) (M81)

Partners List:

ANSES (FR), AUTH (GR), MOH-IL (IL), NIJZ (SI), NIPH (NO), TTL (FI), SRU (NL), UBA (DE), Unisante (CH), Uni Oulo (FI)

Schedule:

Starting date: 01/05/2022 (M1)
 Expected ending date: 31/01/2029 (M81)

Costs

Expected PM for the fourth year of the project: 28 PM
 Expected ODC for the fourth year of the project: 19 038 €

P4.1.3.1.b Y4_Health-based-IA-GV_LNS_NCPHP

Project Title	Derivation of Health-based Indoor Air Guideline Values		
Project Acronym (15 letters max)	Health-based-IA-GV		
Project Manager	Ruth Moeller	LNS	Luxembourg
	ruth.moeller@lns.etat.lu		

Deputy Project manager	Tamás Szigeti szigeti.tamas@nngyk.gov.hu	NCPHP	Hungary
Expected starting date PARC (Month number)	M37	Expected duration (months)	45
PARC Workpackage number	WP4	PARC Task/Activity/Sub-activity:	4.1.3.1
Project Id	P4.1.3.1.b Y4_Health-based-IA-GV_LNS_NCPHP		

Status: Initiation

Summary of the project

PARC prioritizes the assessment of human exposure to support EU chemicals policy through task 4.1 HBM and task 4.2 human indoor environmental exposure monitoring. Indoor air (IA) pollutants comprise a large and diverse number of chemicals, such as aldehydes, aliphatic-, aromatic- and chlorinated hydrocarbons, glycol ethers, terpenes and ozone reaction products. In addition, several of the substance groups prioritized in PARC may be found as IA pollutants, e.g. lower molecular weight and more volatile phthalates diethyl phthalate (DEP) and dimethyl phthalate (DMP), and neutral and volatile PFAS (Morales-McDevitt et al. 2021) (in addition, partitioning of less volatiles and particle bound substances, e.g. phthalates, biocides, flame retardants, into air may result in long-term low exposure through an inhabitants` direct indoor environment). While HBM data aggregate the total systemic exposure burden from all exposure pathways, IA measurement data aggregate inhalation exposure for substances released by several sources and potentially provoking adverse systemic or local (site of contact) health effects.

The CSS has flagged attention to consumer protection and chemicals of concern affecting the immune, neurological, or respiratory systems and specific target organs. These adverse health effects are of particular relevance for indoor pollutants.

As a prerequisite, however, for a health-related interpretation of human IA exposures and for effective RM, guideline values are needed that have been derived epidemiologically or toxicologically and relate directly to the measured IA concentrations. What is essentially lacking is methodological harmonization and sufficient coverage of relevant substances with indoor air guideline value (IA-GV) to allow systematic and health-based evaluation of IA pollution by national risk assessors, public health institutes or European regulatory bodies. Such methodology will be suitable to derive inhalation values for all chemical substances that may be inhaled, including VOC and semiVOC.

The latter is reflected in the EC Staff Working document on supporting Indoor Air Quality (IAQ) (SWD 2024. 147 final), stipulating further needs for policies, regulatory instruments to improve comparability of reporting and monitoring, and databases and technical instruments.

The project will establish a suitable methodology which will be used to derive health-based IA-GV (derived by consensus of project partners) with a primary focus on substances prioritized in the PARC human exposure monitoring surveys (mainly P4.1.1.2.a_Y1_GenHBMSurvey and P.4.2.c_Y3_HumanExposure) aiming to achieve broad scientific acceptance for these values and to support a harmonized health-related interpretation of monitoring data collected under PARC.

The Commission has proposed a OSOA chemicals assessment reform for faster, simplified and transparent processes, this includes a legislative proposal Establish a Common Data Platform and introduce a ‘one-stop shop’ access to data on chemicals held by the EU agencies and the Commission, compiled under EU legislation (COM(2023) 779 final). In the spirit of this OSOA initiative, IA-GV derived based on harmonized methodology, if integrated in the future common data platform which will expand the scope to

almost all EU chemicals legislation, may contribute to coherent and transparent safety assessments of chemicals used in various products, articles and processes across different regulatory frameworks.

Main expected outputs of the project:

- **Methodology:** A suitable methodology of how to derive IA-GVs based on toxicological and/or epidemiological data will be proposed in alignment with regulatory methods and guidelines (e.g. ECHA Guidance R8 used under REACH).
- **Health-based guideline values:** The project will provide an inventory of relevant available (inter)national IA-GVs for substances prioritized for targeted monitoring under PARC (4.1/4.2), review and consolidate these values, furthermore, derive de novo health-based IA-GVs, where lacking, building upon national efforts and initiatives (see initiatives in the *table on links outside PARC*).
- **Prioritization criteria:** Criteria will be defined on how to prioritize substances for de novo derivation of health-based guideline values.

Outcomes and impacts expected on end-users and stakeholders:

The general population is widely exposed to chemicals present in the indoor environment, originating from various products, articles and processes. Humans spend 60-90% of their life indoors, in their home, in private and public indoor environments. The exposure is regular and long-term, and all age groups including vulnerable sub-populations are concerned. IA pollution is societally relevant. Health problems, if systematically present in a society, can weigh heavily on the economy (productivity, burden on health care system). Possible health effects from IA pollutants can include unspecific symptoms like headaches, fatigue, acute and local effects including skin and mucous membrane irritation or sensory irritation, as well as long-term effects such as allergies and diseases of the lung, the cardiovascular system and systemic effects on various organs and the reproductive system.

In absence of a dedicated IAQ policy, the evaluation of IAQ by or for the various concerned actors, including monitoring and measurement laboratories, public (national, regional) health institutions, or other stakeholders such as private and public building owners, is essentially hampered. Uncertainties and misconceptions about the applicability of different kind of values, such as statistical values derived from monitoring data (not health-based), health-based guideline values, precautionary or intervention values, emission limits, etc. persist and influence trust and risk perception of the public.

PARC will generate comparable and EU-wide human and indoor exposure measurement data (PARC project 4.2_HumanExposure). A comparison of the IA exposure data with health-based indoor guideline values will allow statements on whether citizens or subpopulations in European regions are at potential risk of health effects and whether measures for risk mitigation have to be recommended or adapted for IA. It will allow the identification of IA pollutants for which negative health impacts cannot be excluded.

More overarching, guideline values will be available for various actors to support coherent, transparent, and cross-silo assessment of chemical concentrations and IAQ. The project will support public health actors and risk managers striving towards improving IAQ and regulating substances of concern with potential negative health impacts for the general population. This may ultimately improve health protection, contribute to reducing BoD and strengthen citizen trust in public health actors and risk managers. Additionally, enhanced knowledge of health-based values may also mitigate concerns related to IA and adverse health effects if actual concentrations fall below the guidance values to be derived.

Outcomes and impacts expected to be incorporated into a specific regulatory framework:

IA-GVs derived will serve risk assessors evaluating indoor pollution under the various national and European frameworks and policies and furthermore will assist the various stakeholders and risk managers in prioritizing and taking risk mitigation and intervention decisions.

IA-GVs (conceptually comparable to the general population derived no-effect levels (DNELs) (inhalation) under REACH, following the ECHA R8 guidance) derived will be available for RA/RM under the REACH Regulation, i.e. REACH Registration and REACH Restriction processes, in some cases it may also support REACH substance evaluation to clarify a concern.

Based on an evaluation of PARC monitoring data that will be collected in residential homes in several countries (PARC project 4.2_HumanExposure), and by comparison with the IA-GVs, substance can be prioritized for RM under different regulatory frameworks, including REACH Restriction, Construction Products Regulation, and other product specific frameworks (such as cosmetics regulation, biocides etc.). One possible opportunity is the assessment of regulatory needs and the identification of IA pollutants that should be further investigated in a regulatory Risk Management Option Analysis (RMOA) under REACH and CLP.

EU- lowest concentration of interest (LCI) values are health-based reference concentrations of chemical substances for inhalation exposure used to assess emissions after 28 days from a single construction product during a laboratory test chamber procedure as defined in the EN 16516. In contrast, IA-GVs are used to evaluate IA pollution including exposure of vulnerable populations (e.g. children, elderly people). Nevertheless, commonalities in the derivation can be identified and synergies can be exploited.

It may also happen that the same substances are of concern for the general population and for workplace safety and health-based IA-GVs, when adapted to the workplace context (by applying the appropriate assessment factors for worker population and exposure scenario), may be considered also for worker RA under the Chemical Agents Directive (CAD) and CMRD, or at national level. In addition, when evaluating IA pollution in workplaces such as offices, schools, kindergartens (i.e. non-industrial-type workplaces), or public buildings, health-based IA-GVs could often be more relevant starting point than occupational exposure limits (OELs).

Key words: health, indoor air guideline values, indoor air quality, human exposure, inhalation, risk assessment, consumer safety, substances of concern, indoor air pollutants

Link to the PARC DoA:

The project responds to the PARC OOs OO4, OO5, OO6, OO7, OO8, OO10 , OO12, OO9, OO13.

OO4: Guideline values derived in accordance with regulatory standards will be disseminated and should be included in the common data platform to be considered by regulators for RA (i.e. by ECHA and EEA or national actors). OO5: the project will connect to other initiative (e.g. IDEAL cluster) and explore synergies. OO6: Dissemination of the project and its outcome to citizen may contribute to building trust and mitigating IAQ complaints (possible collaboration with WP3). OO7: this project will complement existing PARC initiatives, i.e. 4.1 and 4.2 exposure monitoring projects and HBM-GV project, and the output will actively be used inside and outside PARC for evaluation of human exposure to air pollutants. OO8: Availability of guideline values will enable linking of exposure monitoring data with health effects and risks. OO10: The project will derive guideline values based on existing data and will make available these values according to FAIR principles. OO12: The project will propose a harmonized methodology based on existing national regulatory initiatives and in accordance with established European regulatory guidance to promote regulatory uptake and acceptability of methodology and derived guideline values by stakeholders. OO9: the methodology may serve as initiation of technical guidance for future initiatives on IAQ assessment and derivation of HBGVs. OO13: depending on availability of resources, training on the use of the methodology and guideline values for IAQ assessment may be developed (possible collaboration with WP9).

Links within PARC (WPs/Tasks/Activities/Projects):

This project mentioned links with the projects P4.1.1.2.a_Y1_GenHBMSurvey, Substances prioritized for monitoring will be considered for prioritization of IA-GV derivation, P4.1.3.1.a_Y1_HBM-GV, Synergies

with the sister project on derivation of HBM-GV - will be explored, P.4.2.c_Y3_HumanExposure Substances prioritized for monitoring will be considered for prioritization of IA-GV derivation, P6.2.3.a_Y1_RealLifeMixtures, MRA for indoor contaminants, P6.4.3b_Y3_ENFORCE, the project may provide a list of priority substances in consumer products indoor environment useful for substance prioritization for IA-GV derivation.

This project also mentioned links with WP7 FAIR data: guideline values should be FAIR. If needed, collaboration with WP9 may be considered (T9.4. Depending on partners` resources, additional training activities may be developed) and with WP3 Synergies, collaboration and awareness. Collaboration with WP3 may be considered (T3.2 Communication, dissemination on project output to increase stakeholder awareness on IAQ and IA-GVs).

Links outside PARC:

This project mentioned links with:

- Initiative deriving IA-GVs (German Committee on Indoor Guide Values, ANSES deriving Valeurs guides de qualité d'air intérieur, RIVM and VITO experts deriving Health based guideline values for the indoor environment, Arbeitskreis Innenraumluft at the Austrian Federal Ministry for Climate Action, Environment, Energy, Mobility, Innovation and Technology deriving “wirkungsbezogenen Innenraumrichtwerte”)
- [EC EU-LCI subgroup](#) to derive and recommend EU-wide harmonised health-based reference values for the assessment of product emissions, based on the so-called ‘lowest concentration of interest’ (LCI) concept
- “Indoor air quality health” (IDEAL) cluster WG4-Guidelines. IDEAL is a Horizon Europe cluster comprising seven EU funded projects targeting IAQ Health (including “Improving indoor air quality for a healthier home and Europe”, INQUIRE). Synergies are expected specifically with WG 4 activities of the IDEAL cluster, which revolve around standardization.
- [INQUIRE](#): EU-funded project on IAQ providing knowledge, tools, and measures to significantly enhance IAQ. Synergies in the area of substance prioritization, toxicity assessment, risk communication.
- WHO European Centre for Environment and Health (ECEH): WHO ECEH recently developed the IAQRiskCalculator tool that estimates the health risks for children from combined exposure to multiple hazardous chemicals in IA by using different reference values. The potential areas of collaboration include the inclusion of the recommended HBGVs and new chemicals in the tool, and the promotion of the [IAQRiskCalculator](#).

Key PARC Deliverables and Milestones to which the project contributes

AD4.18. Derivation of IA-GV (M81)

Partners List: LNS (LU), NCPHP (HU), VITO (BE), TTL (FI), EEA (AT), MU (CZ), IMM-KI (SE)

Schedule:

Starting date: 01/05/2025 (M37)

Expected ending date: 31/01/2029 (M81)

Costs

Expected PM for the first year of the project: 19 PM

Expected ODC for the first year of the project: 17 513 €

S4.1.3.2 Identify effect biomarkers for prioritized chemicals, populations and health outcomes

No project submitted at present.

S4.1.3.3 Link HBM studies to health examination and dietary studies – 1 PROJECT

P4.1.3.3.a_Y1_RoadmapLinkingHBMhealth_SpF_VITO

Project Title	Roadmap to explore the links between prioritized chemical substances exposure and health concerns		
Project Acronym (15 letters max)	RoadmapLinkingHBMhealth		
Project Manager	Lea Lefebvre lea.lefebvre@santepubliquefrance.fr	SpF	France
	Sylvie Remy Sylvie.remy@vito.be	VITO	Belgium
Deputy Project manager	For effect biomarkers : Andrea Rodríguez Carrillo (andrea.rodriguezcarriilo@vito.be)	VITO	Belgium
Expected starting date	1	Expected duration	52
PARC (Month number)			
PARC Workpackage number	4	PARC Task/Activity/ Sub-activity:	4.1.3.2 and 4.1.3.3
Project Id	P4.1.3.3.a_Y1_RoadmapLinkingHBMhealth_SpF_VITO		

Status: Implementation

Summary of the project

Building on HBM4EU recommendations for further implementation of traditional and novel effect biomarkers in HBM studies and the linkage of HBM and health examination surveys (HES), this project aims to develop a roadmap that identifies concrete actions to undertake to foster investigations on the link between chemical exposures and health outcomes through biomarkers of effect. The project will be conducted in a two-step approach; I. first, the integration of standardized effect biomarker and health measurements and questionnaires in HBM surveys conducted under T4.1.1 – HBM surveys design; II. Second, a feasibility study to explore the possibility to assess past exposures to prioritized chemicals and determine effect biomarkers levels from biobanked samples collected earlier in cohorts and evaluate the prospective associations with health outcomes that will be collected under PARC. A case study will be applied to a specific PARC priority substance through retrospective analysis. This project will establish a core strategy for linking past exposures to current health effects and create a baseline assessment that will guide future surveys combining biomonitoring and health examinations. In that capacity, the project will deliver tools and information for measuring exposure and health-effect biomarkers that could be used alongside the classical toxicological, regulatory framework-driven RA.

Main expected outputs of the project

- Roadmap for exploration of the links between HBM data and existing health outcome
- Supporting materials for PARC surveys:
 - Scoping document of a list of health measurements to be included in the HBM/HES surveys including standardized procedures and materials for collecting health, dietary and occupational data
 - Effect biomarker implementation plan for PARC surveys
 - Investigation of the links between exposure and adverse health outcomes, from analyses of biobanked samples within Health examination cohorts

Outcomes and impacts expected for end-users and stakeholders

The results and data of this project are of interest to:

- PARC project partners

- GB members
- EU commission and agencies
- EU national bodies
- Broader scientific community
- Policy makers and regulators

The generated information materials will provide tools for a more comprehensive and integrative biomonitoring of chemical exposure in Europe and ascertain to study relationships among risk factors, health promotion and protection behaviors, and health status.

Key words: Human biomonitoring, biomarkers of effect, health outcome assessment, Molecular epidemiology

Link to the PARC DoA

The project responds to the PARC OOs OO7, OO8, OO12, OO9.

T4.1: Effect biomarkers will complement exposure biomarkers to evaluate associations between chemical exposure and adverse effects (LNS, SpF, UGR, VITO). Issues related to the linkage of HBM, health examination, occupational and dietary surveys will be identified and solved with support of WP7 (RSU, SpF).

Through the activities on exposure monitoring and toxicology, the Partnership will foster a better understanding of the health impacts of exposures and, thereby, indirectly contribute with evidence for health cost estimations.

This project will contribute to SO2 “European and national RA entities and their scientific networks carry out a joint R&I programme to respond to the agreed priorities in chemicals RA”. The project will support the understanding of the contribution of chemicals as upstream determinants of diseases, to the reduction of environmental and human health impact of exposure to hazardous chemicals, and as such to the improvement of the protection of environmental and citizen’s health, and awareness of citizens and professionals about risks of chemical exposures.

Links within PARC (WPs/Tasks/Activities/Projects)

This project is mainly linked to T4.1 activities:

- General Survey
- Targeted surveys
- Occupational surveys
- Definition of standardised materials (questionnaires, protocols, etc.)
- Preparation of a sustainable monitoring and surveillance system for Europe
- Data management and analysis

WP2: Prioritization of substances and uptake into policy

WP7: FAIR data management and technical issues related to the linkage of HBM and HES

WP9: Inventory of HBM/HES studies that will support the identification of the opportunities in the HBM survey

Links outside PARC

- HBM4EU legacy: the project will build further on experiences, results and materials developed within HBM4EU
- European Human Exposome Network (EHEN)
- OECD interdisciplinary activity ‘Addressing combined exposures and effects by using Adverse Outcome Pathway (AOP) knowledge in combination with relevant effect-biomarkers’
- OECD expert group related to Working Parties on Hazard and Exposure Assessments (WPHA/WPEA)

Key PARC Deliverables and Milestones to which the project contributes

There is no specific PARC deliverable for this project. The results will feed into T4.1 deliverables

- MS10 Finalisation of study design for the HBM surveys (delivered)

- AD4.1 Periodic report on available supporting materials for HBM studies (delivered)
- AD4.2 Periodic report on analytical methods and measurements for exposure and effect biomarkers (M36) has been cancelled
- D4.3 1st Progress report on the general survey (M36)
- D4.8 2nd Progress report on the general survey (M48)
- D4.12 3rd Progress report on the general survey (M60)
- D2.22 2nd PARC sustainability report (M81) contribution with the final strategy for a sustainable and centrally coordinated HBM programme for Europe

Partners List:

SpF (France), VITO (Belgium), AU (Denmark), AUTH (Greece), BPI (Greece), CEA (France), CSIC (Spain), EAA (Austria), EHESP (France), Fraunhofer (Germany), KI/IMM KI (Sweden), INRS (France), INSA (Portugal), INSERM (France), INSST (Spain), ISCIII (Spain), ISS (Italy), JSI (Slovenia), KULeuven (Belgium), LNS (Luxembourg), LSMU (Lithuania), MU (Czech Republic), NIJZ (Slovenia), NIOM (Poland), NLZOH (Slovenia), UKHSA (England), SRU (Netherlands), RSU (Latvia), Sciensano (Belgium), SECO (Switzerland), STAMI (Norway), TTL (Finland), UBA (Germany), Ugent (Belgium), UGR (Spain), ULPGC (Spain), UNINA (Italy), UNIPD (Italy), UOC (Greece), UOULU (Finland) , USI (Switzerland), UU-IRAS (Netherlands), WULS-SGGW (Poland)

Schedule:

Starting date: 01/05/2022 (M1)
 Expected ending date: 31/08/2026 (M52)

Costs

Expected PM for the fourth year of the project: 66 PM
 Expected ODC for the fourth year of the project: 18 694 €

A4.1.4 Data Management and analysis – 1 PROJECT

S4.1.4.1 Data management

No project submitted at present.

S4.1.4.2 Data analysis – 1 PROJECT

P4.1.4.2.a_Y1_DataAnalysisHBM4EU_VITO

Project Title	Further analysis of the data generated within HBM4EU		
Project Acronym (15 letters max)	DataAnalysisHBM4EU		
Project Manager	Eva Govarts Eva.govarts@vito.be	VITO	Belgium
Deputy Project manager	-	-	-
Expected starting date PARC (Month number)	1	Expected duration	48*
PARC Workpackage number	4	PARC Task/Activity/Su b-activity:	4.1.4.2
Project Id	P4.1.4.2.a_Y1_DataAnalysisHBM4EU_VITO		

*The project has been extended from M36 to M48

Status: Implementation

Summary of the project

Within the context of the HBM4EU project, a large range of HBM data has been generated via the

HBM4EU Aligned Studies in adults, teenagers and children, occupational studies (chromium VI, diisocyanates and e-waste), the MOM-study (mercury exposure during pregnancy) and the SPECIMEn study (pesticide hotspots). Much useful information has already been obtained during HBM4EU and more publications are expected to be out soon. It is nevertheless foreseen that research questions will remain or will emerge from the data analysis, and not all the generated data are analysed. In order to make optimal use of the available HBM4EU data and use the results to feed into the design of HBM studies planned under PARC, further statistical analyses will be performed on HBM4EU data. More information can be generated on exposure sources and routes, exposure-effects and pathway analyses.

The project is of relevance for all regulatory frameworks restricting the production, use, environmental release, and environmental/dietary/consumer product exposure of chemicals, as well as frameworks targeted to environmental, human and worker health protection. Europe's zero-pollution agenda should depart from an understanding of how the bodies of European citizens are polluted with synthetic chemicals, and make reducing the chemical body burden and associated health impacts a key priority. Measuring exposure and effect biomarkers in HBM studies will provide insight into the extent to which chemicals and substitutes have an impact on health and support chemical grouping approaches and avoidance of regrettable substitution.

Main expected outputs of the project

Output will be generated with regard to exposure sources and routes and exposure-effect and pathway analyses. More information will be obtained on exposure sources and routes by linking HBM data with external exposure (e.g. products/articles, environmental monitoring, lifestyle, food consumption patterns) data (measured, estimated or modelled), both on individual level (as gathered by the HBM studies) as well as obtained on an aggregated level within the time frame of the HBM sampling. Results on exposure-effect associations and exposure-effect pathways will be obtained from the further analyses of data generated within the HBM4EU Aligned Studies. The results coming out of this project will be published in scientific peer-reviewed publications, and communicated and disseminated to the general public, the PARC consortium and policy makers for regulatory uptake.

Outcomes and impacts expected for end-users and stakeholders

The results of the data analyses planned in this project can be used by different stakeholders:

- Policy makers/regulators/OECD, WHO, UN
 Feed into policies for reduction of exposure, use of products/articles, chemicals production and release; support RA and mitigation for known and emerging chemicals; support evaluation of the efficiency of regulation or the need for further action.
- EC, EU agencies, member states, and the scientific community
 Input for exposure and hazard evaluation, modelling, RA, HIA; feed into monitoring of the impact of implementation of the EU's CSS and zero pollution action plan.
- Industrial hygienists, occupational physicians, workers, trade unions
 Release to the environment via production processes, worker exposure and protection.
- Citizens
 Better understanding and awareness of exposure and risk; recommendations for lifestyle and prevention.

Key words: Human Biomonitoring, HBM4EU, exposure routes, exposure-effect analyses, health effects, effect biomarkers, pathways.

Link to the PARC DoA

The project responds to the PARC OOs OO4, OO5, OO6, OO8, OO10, OO11 and OO13.

The results of the project link to the overall goal of WP4 in observing different sources, chemical fates and exposure pathways.

For the analyses of exposure sources and routes, geospatial information should be derived based on the geolocation of the participants or an aggregated level as Nomenclature of Territorial Units for Statistics (NUTS). For this, the project will get support from partners involved in the R&I funded EHEN. Training

will be organised for the study data owners to derive these geospatial variables for their participants. The data for this project will be shared via the Personal Exposure and Health (PEH) Data Platform initiated within HBM4EU. The newly generated data (geospatial information as environmental data) will be added to this PEH Data Platform as well. A network of research centres will be built to explore the exposure sources/routes and exposure-effect analyses. The results coming out of this project will be communicated and disseminated to the general public, the PARC consortium and policy makers for regulatory uptake.

Links within PARC (WPs/Tasks/Activities/Projects)

Links to other Work package/Tasks/Activities:

- WP2: priority setting and uptake into policy
- WP3: communication on results data analyses with regard to specific research questions
- T4.1: design of general, targeted and occupational HBM surveys
- T4.2: external exposure data
- T6.2: exposure routes (modelling) and exposure-effect associations (risk and HIA)
- WP7: linking of data sources and routes, DMP, case study HBM data, innovative data analysis
- WP9: maybe training is needed on data analysis

Links to other projects:

- P4.1.1.2.a_Y1_GenHBMSurvey_VITO
- P4.1.1.4.a_Y1_OccupFeasability_TTL
- P4.1.1.4.c_Y1_Occuphealthcare_TTL_SRU
- P4.1.1.4.d_Y1_OccupWaste_ENSP_TTL
- P4.1.3.3.a_Y1_RoadmapLinkingHBMHES_SpF_VITO
- P6.2.3.a_Y1_RealLifeMixtures_RIVM
- P7.2.2.b_Y1_HBMdatasets_VITO

Links outside PARC

- HBM4EU legacy: the project will perform further analyses on data generated and collected within HBM4EU
- European Human Exposome Network (EHEN) projects

Key PARC Deliverables and Milestones to which the project contributes

Deliverable D7.1 Data management plan (delivered)

Milestone MS7 Establishment of working groups (delivered) by establishing a statistical working group with experts on HBM data analysis

AD4.11. Progress report statistical analyses (new delivery date M48)

Partners List:

Project manager: VITO (Belgium)

Project team: AU (Denmark), AUTH (Greece), BPI (Greece), EASP (Spain), INRAE (France), INRS (France), INSA (Portugal), INSERM (France), ISCIII (Spain), ISSeP (Belgium), JSI (Slovenia), LNS (Luxembourg), LSMU (Lithuania), MU (Czech Republic), NIJZ (Slovenia), NIPH (Norway), Sciensano (Belgium), SPF (France), SZU-SK (Slovakia), TTL (Finland), UBA (Germany), UGR (Spain), UNIVIE (Austria), UU-IRAS (Netherlands), VITO (Belgium)

Schedule:

Starting date: 01/05:2022 (M1)

Expected ending date: 30/04/2026 (M48)

Costs

Expected PM for the fourth year of the project: 23 PM

Expected ODC for the fourth year of the project: 6 400 €

A4.1.5 Preparation of a sustainable monitoring and surveillance system for Europe – 1 PROJECT

P4.1.5.a_Y1_SustainHBMSystem_VITO

Project Title	Preparation of a sustainable monitoring and surveillance system for Europe		
Project Acronym (15 letters max)	SustainHBMSystem		
Project Manager	Liese Gilles liese.gilles@vito.be	VITO	Belgium
Deputy Project manager	Loic Rambaud loic.rambaud@santepubliquefrance.fr	SpF	France
Expected starting date PARC (Month number)	1	Expected duration	66*
PARC Workpackage number	4	PARC Task/Activity/Sub-activity:	4.1.5
Project Id	P4.1.5.a_Y1_SustainHBMSystem_VITO		

* The project has been broken down at M66 (that corresponds to the Final strategy for a sustainable and centrally coordinated HBM program for Europe report). As the implementation of the EU HBM survey will not depend on PARC but on decision taken at that time about the follow up of PARC. A new projet could follow for the period M67-M81 after having reviewed what has been achieved and if the evaluation is positive.

Status: Implementation

Summary of the project

The general population HBM survey under T4.1 (P4.1.1.2.a_Y1_GenHBMSurvey_VITO), running from 2022-2028, will form the basis for chemical exposure assessment of European citizens within PARC. While the aim is to advance the concept of the HBM4EU Aligned Studies in the PARC general population survey, further steps towards implementation of a long-term sustainable HBM framework for exposure to chemicals within Europe will in parallel be taken in this project.

A long-term sustainable and inclusive HBM surveillance system for exposure to chemicals within Europe to succeed the PARC general population survey will be prepared. This system will build further on scenarios explored and recommendations developed under HBM4EU and take lessons learned from the HBM4EU Aligned Studies and PARC general survey and innovative approaches developed under various PARC Tasks into account. In addition, experts in charge of HBM surveys conducted in Europe, the USA, Canada, Japan, South Korea and Australia will be consulted. By 2028, a final concept should be ready for implementation to guide and support the HBM survey that succeeds the general survey under PARC.

The sustainable HBM system should allow to obtain truly representative and maximally harmonized exposure data for Europe to provide useful results for policy makers and to answer the information needs of citizens. The relevance of HBM results will be increased by optimisation of the number of countries and subjects to be included and samples to be collected and analysed, for instance via reduction of costs and increased efficiency of fieldwork. Harmonization will be maximized via upfront alignment of studies and application of guidelines/protocols/SOPs/supporting materials.

The project is of relevance for all regulatory frameworks restricting the production, use, environmental release, and environmental/dietary/consumer product exposure of chemicals, as well as frameworks targeted to environmental and human health protection. The exact regulatory processes and frameworks for which future EU wide HBM campaigns will provide input will depend on the regulatory strategies and questions that are most prominent at that specific point of time.

Main expected outputs of the project

The project will deliver a blueprint for a sustainable long-term HBM program in Europe for implementation after PARC.

Outcomes and impacts expected for end-users and stakeholders

The results of a European HBM surveillance system with regular frequency can be used by different stakeholders:

- Policy makers/regulators/OECD, WHO, UN
 Feed into policies for reduction of exposure, use of products/articles, chemicals production and release; support RA and mitigation for known and emerging chemicals; support evaluation of the efficiency of regulation or the need for further action.
- EC, EU agencies, member states, and the scientific community
 Input for exposure and hazard evaluation, modelling, RA, HIA; feed into monitoring of the impact of implementation of the EU's CSS.
- Citizens
 Better understanding and awareness of exposure and risk; recommendations for lifestyle and prevention.

Baseline human exposure data will be suited for comparison with international chemical monitoring programs such as NHANES and CDC.

Key words: sustainable HBM programme, Europe, Harmonized, chemical RA toolbox.

Link to the PARC DoA

The project responds to the PARC operational objective OO8

The project will prepare the development of a sustainable HBM surveillance programme for chemical exposure of European citizens.

Links within PARC (WPs/Tasks/Activities/Projects)

Links to other Work package/Tasks/Activities:

WP4:

T4.1: general population HBM survey

T4.2 & T6.2: associations between sources, external exposure to (mixtures of) chemicals and internal exposure

T4.3: development and PoC of innovative tools and methods

WP2: prioritization, sustainability and exit strategy

WP3: synergies

WP5: effect biomarkers

WP7: FAIR data

WP8: EWS

WP9: capacities and infrastructure

National Hubs (NHs): implementation of the framework

Links to other projects:

P4.1.1.2.a_Y1_GenHBMSurvey_VITO

P4.1.4.2.a_Y1_DataAnalysisHBM4EU_VITO

P4.1.3.3.a_Y1_RoadmapLinkingHBMHES_SpF_VITO

P7.2.2.b_Y1_HBMdatasets_VITO

Links outside PARC

- HBM4EU legacy: the project will build further on experiences, results, materials, and networks developed within HBM4EU
- National/regional studies participating in the general survey
- International key players in HBM research such as CDC (NHANES), Health Canada (CHMS), Japan, South Korea, Australia
- ISES HBM working groups

Key PARC Deliverables and Milestones to which the project contributes

D2.22: 2nd PARC sustainability report (M81).

Partners List: UBA (Germany), LNS (Luxembourg), ISCIII (Spain), VITO (Belgium), SPF (France), INSA (Portugal), LSMU (Latvia), FOPH (Switzerland), NIPH (Norway), SZU-CZ (Czech Republic), MOH-CY (Cyprus)

Schedule for the first part of the project:

Starting date: 01/05/2022 (M1)

Expected ending date: 31/10/2027 (M66)

Costs

Expected PM for the fourth year of the project: 10 PM

Expected ODC for the fourth year of the project: 5 300 €

T4.2 Environmental and Multisource Monitoring – 3 PROJECTS

Monitoring studies will be performed in EU-wide collaborative initiatives to generate environmental data according to regulatory needs and to fill in gaps in exposure data for an integrated assessment of pollution affecting environmental and human health. The steps in the T4.2 monitoring projects are outlined in Fig. 3 and will be established and tested in a Pilot Project on PFAS and EDCs (Fig. 4). Based on a review of existing knowledge, activities and infrastructure of chemical analysis in the environment, Task 4.2 will design and conduct monitoring activities with the aim to track the source and route of chemical exposure, which will also support the development of an EWS in WP8 (‘Concepts and Toolboxes’). This includes defining a sampling strategy, also considering existing samples and sampling programmes, and selecting analytes and methods (see Fig 3).

Fig 3: PARC environmental monitoring strategy

Particular attention will be paid to a QA/QC concept (in collaboration with the T9.3). Data analysis will develop and apply state-of-the-art methods. The exploitation of the data could include spatial analysis of exposure levels, input data for exposure factors, evaluation of time trends, and comparison with benchmark values for environmental and human health protection, mixture toxicity assessment, and integration of chemical data and bioanalytical responses. In collaboration with Task 2.1, a feedback mechanism will be established to analyse whether or not the regulatory needs were met and whether new issues of scientific and/or regulatory significance emerge which should feed into new monitoring activities. Task 4.2 also works on the development and implementation of a prioritisation process to define chemicals/matrices/endpoints for future monitoring studies (see Fig 4). A project on the human exposure to organic contaminants from non-food environmental sources is started in Year 3, connecting environmental monitoring with HBM in T4.1.

Fig 4: Summary of the three projects started in T4.2

P4.2.a_Y1_ENVMonitoringPilotSurvey_INERIS_AU

Project Title	Establishment of the overall process of environmental and multisource monitoring with the help of a pilot study addressing PFAS and endocrine disruptors		
Project Acronym (15 letters max)	EDC and PFAS pilot		
Project Manager	Katrin Vorkamp kvo@envs.au.dk	Aarhus University	Denmark
	Valeria Dulio Valeria.dulio@ineris.fr	INERIS	France
Expected starting date	1	Expected duration	42*
PARC (Month number)		PARC	4.2.1
PARC Workpackage number	4	Task/Activity/Sub-activity:	
Project Id	P4.2.a_Y1_ENVMonitoringPilotSurvey_INERIS_AU		

*The project has been extended from M36 to M42

Status: Implementation

Summary of the project

Establishing a process for environmental and multisource monitoring is a key component in PARC. It has the purpose of supporting the EU chemical RA in relation to policy needs identified in the field of i) environmental ecosystems and ii) human exposure, with a strong link to HBM. Together with the prerequisite of building on existing structures and knowledge, these objectives make environmental and multisource monitoring a complex task in PARC, which needs highly optimized processes to be fully beneficial.

PFAS and endocrine disrupting compounds (EDCs) are two compound groups of regulatory interest due to concerns about persistence, mobility and toxicity (PFAS) and toxicity (EDCs), potentially in combination with other undesired properties and effects. There is a need for long-term monitoring of these compounds in different matrices to characterise their sources and current exposure levels and evaluate the effect of risk-reducing measures in support of the EU's Zero Pollution ambition.

A pilot phase focussing on PFAS and EDCs was started in Year 1 with the purpose of establishing and validating environmental monitoring structures, including a review of state-of-the-art methods as well as

the design of a monitoring study for the long-term work in T4.2. This project will continue in Year 2 with a focus on the actual monitoring study to be performed and will proceed into Year 3 and 4 for data analysis and transfer until the formulation of lessons learnt as part of a feedback mechanism.

Main expected outputs of the project

The main outputs of the project will include:

1. Review of existing knowledge for the list of candidate EDCs and PFAS (Y1):
 - Characterisation of compound classes, exploration of possibilities of grouping
 - Review of analytical methods
 - Survey for inventory of available data and on-going monitoring studies
2. A study design (Y1 and Y2), followed by a more detailed monitoring plan targeting i) PFAS in the freshwater environment and ii) EDCs in a multicompartment approach, including:
 - target compounds
 - analytical approaches also involving SS/NTS, sum parameters (for PFAS) and effect-based methods (for EDCs)
 - the QA/QC concept
 - criteria for selection of laboratories with documented expertise in the field of the project
3. Monitoring data in Y2
4. Data analysis and transfer and Establishment of a feedback mechanism in Y3 and Y4 that also addresses lessons learnt, with a view to adjustments in the task structure and workflows for future monitoring projects in PARC.

Outcomes and impacts expected for end-users and stakeholders

End-users: DG ENV, national environment agencies, ECHA, EEA.

Expected impact:

- Combination of existing and new monitoring data for the establishment of a baseline for two prioritised compound groups (PFAS and EDCs) that pose a risk to European environmental ecosystems in support of:
 - o EU water legislation, in particular for improvement of lists of priority pollutants, e.g. List of Priority Substances under the Water Framework Directive (WFD), Groundwater Directive (GWD), Marine Strategy Framework Directive (MSFD), etc.)
 - o EU Soil Strategy
 - o assessment of the effectiveness of chemical management measures (e.g. ECHA PFAS restriction proposal).
- comprehensive assessment of environmental contamination by EDCs in terms of effect-based assessment for a broad spectrum of species-specific endocrine activities, representative of different modes of action, thereby identifying the links between observed ED activities and sources of emission of biologically active EDCs (REACH, Classification, Labelling and Packaging (CLP)).
- Implementation of new monitoring schemes for PFAS as a whole family, including non-target and aspecific methods (Total Organofluorines (TOF) and Total Oxidizable Precursor (TOP) assays) (to support RA under Drinking Water Directive approach and the ECHA PFAS restriction proposal).

Key words: Pilot study, EDCs, PFAS, environmental monitoring, knowledge gaps, freshwater, multicompartment

Link to the PARC DoA

The project responds to the PARC OOs OO5, OO6, OO7, OO8 and OO11.

This project is tightly intertwined with the PARC overall aim to strengthen the EU's capacity for RA to protect human health and the environment, as well as closely linked to projects developing innovative models and concepts for RA. The project will *develop, test and validate a workflow* for the design and operation of further monitoring campaigns in PARC, thereby ensuring that the future environmental and multisource monitoring will be designed based on complete and up-to-date information, answering the

identified regulatory needs (e.g. lack of consideration of mixture effects, lack of consideration of PFAS precursors for RA and regulatory monitoring). Among other activities, the project will test effect-based methods for EDCs and method combinations of PFAS target analysis, screening and sum parameters. While this project is based on regulatory needs identified prior to the start of the project, future projects will include a prioritisation step, in close collaboration with T2.1.

The project will promote cooperation with other R&I initiatives by applying *innovative methods*. The *analytical monitoring work* will contribute to consolidate existing and develop new *networks of laboratories and research centres*. The project will also include a *feedback mechanism*, with a review function for prioritisation, which will foster *regulatory uptake of PARC knowledge*. The above-mentioned steps will be tested on the two case studies (PFAS and EDCs) of this pilot project, thereby supporting the provision of environmental and multisource data for regulatory purposes already identified under HBM4EU.

Links within PARC (WPs/Tasks/Activities/Projects)

- Collaboration with T2.3, T4.1, T4.3, WP7 and T9.2 in the review of existing knowledge and infrastructure, which has the purpose to avoid duplication by re-using existing data, samples and other experiences.
- Collaboration with T4.1, T4.3 and WP9 to support the definition of the QA/QC concept, application of innovative methods, criteria for selection of laboratories.
- Contacts to T4.1, T6.2 and WP7 regarding data analysis and data management and transfer.

Links outside PARC

PFAS have been amongst the prioritized substances in HBM4EU and were addressed as a priority group of chemicals under the recent Horizon 2020 European Green Deal Call (January 2021). Three research projects have been funded under this call: “Preventing Recalcitrant Organic Mobile Industrial chemicals for Circular Economy in the Soil-sediment-water system” (PROMISCES), “Zero pollution of Persistent, Mobile substances” (ZEROPM) and “Strategies for health protection, pollution Control and Elimination of Next generation Refractive Organic chemicals from the Soil, vadose zone and water” (SCENARIOS).

The same considerations apply to EDCs, which are an obvious example of mixture exposure, as addressed under Area 8.2: “Fostering regulatory science to address combined exposures to industrial chemicals and pharmaceuticals: from science to evidence-based policies”. Three research projects have been approved for funding under this call: “environmentAL Toxicity chemical mixtures through an innovative platform based on aged cardiac tissue model” (ALTERNATIVE), “Living Impact on Fetal Evolution: Shelter-Analyze-Validate-Empower Regulations” (LIFESAVER) and “Providing risk assessments of complex real-life mixtures for the protection of Europe’s citizens and the environment” (PANORAMIX), which can provide relevant inputs to this PARC pilot project.

Relevant collaboration opportunities are also identified with the outcomes of the LIFE APEX project, in particular as regards the procedures for sample exchange, protocols for sample preparation and storage, etc. The “Network of reference laboratories, research centres and related organisations for monitoring of emerging environmental substances” (NORMAN) network will be invited to contribute, whenever relevant, in the activities of the PARC project. Links will also be established to national/regional monitoring activities, according to the prerequisite of building on existing knowledge and infrastructure, e.g. reusing samples or linking activities to existing sample stations.

Key PARC Deliverables and Milestones to which the project contributes

AD4.4 Procedures for agreement on transparent use of existing data, access to samples and involvement of external laboratories has been cancelled

AD4.5. Technical specifications of the study (project design, hypothesis and research question as well as analytical procedures including QA/QC and data flows) (delivered)

D4.4. 1st Progress report on on-going monitoring projects (new delivery date M42)

Partners List:

INERIS (FR), AU (DK), INRAE (FR), MU (CZ), SYKE (FI), UBA (DE), CNR-IRSA (IT), IVL (SE),

NKUA (GR), ANSES (FR), BRGM (FR), CSTB (FR), SpF (FR), OVAM (BE), ISSeP (BE), Uantwerpen (BE), LNS (LU), VUA (NE), NILU (NO), JSI (SL), UL FFA (SL), ARSO (SL), ISCIII (ES), FISABIO (ES), UCLM (ES), EA (UK), UKCEH (UK), EFET (GR), BPI (GR), Sciensano (BE), BfG (DE), UFZ (DE), SLU (SE), Eawag (CH), CEH (UK), CNRS (FR), CSTB (FR), EV-ILVO (BE), Fraunhofer-IME (DE), ISS (IT), INSERM (FR), NIJZ (SI), NMBU (NO), ONIRIS (FR), OFB (FR), UniLu (LU), VITO (BE), VSCHT (CZ).

Schedule:

Starting date: 01/05/2022 (M1)

Expected ending date: 31/10/2025 (M42)

Costs

Expected PM for the fourth year of the project: 158 PM

Expected ODC for the fourth year of the project: 167 250 €

P4.2.b_Y2_ENVMonitoringframe_AU_INERIS (closed M36)

Project Title	Applications of a framework for priority setting in environmental and multi-source monitoring		
Project Acronym (15 letters max)	Monitoringframe		
Project Managers	Katrin Vorkamp kvo@envs.au.dk	Aarhus University	Denmark
	Valeria Dulio Valeria.dulio@ineris.fr	INERIS	France
Expected starting date PARC (Month number)	13	Expected duration	24*
PARC Workpackage number	4	PARC Task/Activity/Sub-activity:	4.2.1
Project Id	P4.2.b_Y2_Monitoringframe_AU_INERIS		

*The project has been extended from M30 to M36 and therefore will be closed M36, a final project report will be submitted M39

P4.2.c_Y3_Human exposure_INERIS_AU

Project Title	Human exposure to organic contaminants from non-food environmental sources		
Project Acronym (15 letters max)	Human exposure		
Project Managers	Matteo Creta and Ruth Moeller Matteo.Creta@lns.etat.lu , Ruth.Moeller@lns.etat.lu , Maria-José Rueda-Lopez, Maria-Jose.Rueda-Lopez@cstb.fr , Pernilla Bohlin-Nizzetto and Maja Nipen : pbn@nilu.no , Mni@nilu.no , Katrin Vorkamp kvo@envs.au.dk , Valeria Dulio Valeria.Dulio@ineris.fr	LNS; CSTB; NILU AU; INERIS;	Luxembourg; France; Denmark; Norway
Expected starting date PARC (Month number)	M25	Expected duration (months)	48
PARC Workpackage number	WP4	PARC Task/Activity/Sub-activity:	T4.2
Project Id	P4.2.c_Y3_Human exposure_INERIS_AU		

Status: Implementation

Summary of the project

Humans are exposed to organic contaminants from a variety of sources. While food is recognized as an important exposure source and subject to systematic RA regarding chemical exposure of the general population, other sources are generally studied to a lesser degree, although some of them are known to be significant. For example, dust was identified as the “missing link” in the human exposure to brominated flame retardants after original focus on exposure through food (Jones-Otazo et al., 2005).

In general, dust accumulates many semi-volatile contaminants emitted in the indoor environment including less persistent compounds, such as phthalates, that do not typically accumulate in food chains (Zhu et al., 2023). The inhalation of IA might lead to an exposure to more volatile compounds, such as fluorotelomer alcohols (FTOHs), which can be transformed to perfluorocarboxylic acids (PFCAs) after uptake (Schlummer et al., 2013). Dermal uptake can occur from direct contact with consumer products and indoor surfaces (Frederiksen et al., 2018). Other relevant exposure sources include drinking water, especially for water-soluble compounds (Domingo and Nadal, 2019). For children, ingestion of soil has repeatedly been reported (van Wijnen et al., 1990), although it will likely not be a permanent exposure situation. Although non-food sources have been recognized as potentially significant for human exposure to a variety of chemicals, and guidelines for exposure determination through these pathways exist (ECHA, 2016), they are not monitored or assessed in the same comprehensive and systematic way as food-related exposure sources.

The proposed project is intended to support the T4.1 General HBM Survey (also called the “PARC aligned studies”) within the T4.1 project on the General Population Survey (P4.1.1.2.a_Y1_GenHBMSurvey_VITO) with exposure data from environmental samples. The project is a PoC, testing the hypothesis that some internal exposure biomarkers can be linked to external exposure data other than food, leading to improved interpretability of the internal exposure data. Food as an exposure source is widely recognized and can be included in this study on the basis of existing data, e.g. from national and/or European monitoring efforts. However, the use of chemicals in consumer products presents a more complex situation where non-food pathways may play a greater role than anticipated so far. For brominated flame retardants, for example, correlations between dust and human plasma were shown (Frederiksen et al., 2010). Recent studies on contributions from different exposure pathways to PFAS in human serum confirmed food as the major exposure source but also identified dust and IA as significant contributors, as well as a large individual variation (Poonthong et al., 2020). This variation is specifically addressed in the study approach linking human and environmental samples for the same individuals.

The selected chemicals will be related to the prioritised chemicals in T4.1 (i.e. phthalates, bisphenols, PFAS, pesticides), but also include additional compounds known to be important pollutants in the respective matrices, e.g. flame retardants, non-phthalate plasticizers or chlorinated paraffins in the indoor environment, as well as the identification of compounds in SS/NTS approaches. The overall study outline is visualized in Figure 5, consisting of a substantial cross-section with T4.1 as well as task-specific activities. In order to reduce dependency on sampling possibilities in T4.1, the study will also use existing samples (of dust and soil) and complementary sampling to study the exposure from non-food sources. This is a relevant research and monitoring topic in itself, even if the samples do not directly reflect exposure of the specific study participants in the T4.1 General Survey. Given the large variability that has been documented for chemicals in dust (Vorkamp et al., 2011; Zhu et al., 2023), a broader approach including existing samples will improve the possibilities of establishing mean levels for e.g. spatial comparisons, and of setting the individual’s exposure into a broader perspective.

Although some national regulatory frameworks exist for e.g. IAQ in public buildings and labelling of construction materials, the indoor environment is not addressed in a dedicated European framework or covered by an EU-wide systematic monitoring programme. As such, the project does not address a specific regulatory topic or body but will provide data for a better assessment of a not previously systematized field, which can be combined with food-based data in an integrative exposure assessment approach. Several typical indoor contaminants are regulated under e.g. REACH, including the list of Substances of Very High

Concern (SVHC) and the Biocidal Product Regulation (BPR). PFAS are subject of the recent restriction proposal submitted to the ECHA and also an important parameter in the EU Drinking Water Directive (EU/2020/2184), alongside many other problematic chemicals, such as pesticides, PAHs and chlorinated solvents. Pesticides are regulated under the Regulation for Plant Protection Products (1107/2009). Chemicals in cosmetics are addressed under the Regulation for Cosmetic Products. Exposure to chemicals from soil is relevant for the recently proposed Directive on Soil Monitoring and Resilience. Thus, the project will contribute to improvements of cross-regulatory assessments of relevance to several regulatory bodies, thus stimulating important steps towards OSOA approaches. The connection with T4.1 General HBM Survey explores possibilities of more holistic RAs in a One Health approach. Identification of exposure to CEC, including substitutes for banned substances, can serve as a warning of risks that may have been overlooked. As the project has a direct supporting function for the General HBM Survey under T4.1, it also supports the policies and regulatory initiatives in the focus of the General Survey.

Fig. 5: Conceptual study outline in support of the General HBM Survey in T4.1. The extent of the cross-section will be decided in preparatory meetings with T4.1 and depend on the obtainability of exposure samples linked to the T4.1 General HBM Survey.

Main expected outputs of the project:

The project aims to generate exposure data on relevant non-food exposure pathways for chemicals prioritised in T4.1 and for the individuals involved in the T4.1 General HBM Survey, to the extent that the collection of environmental samples is feasible within this project. These samples will include indoor dust, IA, drinking water and soil (from participants' gardens). Thus, the project will test the concept of linking internal exposure biomarkers to external exposure data from exposure media other than food. If successful, this link will support the interpretation of the internal exposure data obtained in the General HBM Survey. It will be a strength of this project that these data will be obtained in a harmonized and standardized manner. Beyond the connection with T4.1, the project also aims to

- Generate data on chemicals of importance for specific exposure pathways, for example flame retardants in IA and dust, plastic additives in consumer products etc. The extent of these supplementary analyses depends on budgets, sample availability and analytical expertise in the project group and will be further defined in the preparatory phase of the project. These analyses refer to the project part that does not overlap with T4.1 (Fig. 5) but could also link to national studies potentially including more biomarkers than those prioritised in T4.1. The task-specific project part will be developed as a potential standalone project, should the strong interlinkage with T4.1 present difficulties (e.g. in terms of timelines, additional sample collections etc.).
- Obtain supplementary information from existing samples from other locations, since project partners in T4.2 have access to environmental specimen banks including dust and soil samples. These will be catalogued and addressed with regard to potential use in the project, e.g. for spatial comparisons. Likewise, complementary sampling of non-stored matrices (drinking water, IA) can be considered. Geographical differences have been shown for chemicals in IA and dust in Europe (e.g. Esplugas et al., 2022). However, given the large variability that has been documented for semi-volatile organic chemicals in IA and dust (Vorkamp et al., 2011), a relatively large number of samples is necessary to establish robust mean values and their variation between locations. In order to improve representativeness, the project will also include existing samples and/or additionally collected samples, to the extent feasible in the overall project plan and budget. This will also allow better assessment of the individual's exposure situation in the cross-sectional part of the study with T4.1.

- Identify other compounds in SS/NTS approaches, with connections to EWSs in PARC (T8.2) and potential indications of new relevant biomarkers in T4.1. This part offers further collaboration possibilities with T4.3.
- Work towards reference values (primarily dust and air), based on the statistical distributions of measured chemical concentrations in a matrix (AGÖF, 2013). These are statistically derived and not toxicity-based reference values.

As mentioned above, it is important to plan this part of the study carefully to reduce dependency on sampling campaigns in relation to T4.1 which may carry currently unknown obstacles (e.g. non-compatible timelines, limitations for additional sampling due to ethical approval etc.).

Outcomes and impacts expected on end-users and stakeholders:

If successful in linking internal and external exposure measurements, this project will allow to study associations between internal and external exposure for a variety of chemicals, age groups and European countries, and thus identify relevant non-food exposure pathways. Information on exposure of food can be included on the basis of existing data. However, food monitoring is relatively well-established and coordinated with EFSA as the central European authority, whereas some non-food exposure pathways, in particular the indoor environment, have only been subject to specifically dedicated research projects. As previous studies have shown associations between chemicals in e.g. dust and human blood (Frederiksen et al., 2010) or otherwise identified IA and dust as a non-negligible exposure source (Fridén et al., 2011), a complete assessment of human exposure needs more focus on non-food exposure sources and pathways. The process will contribute to the intended integration of human and environmental monitoring in WP4 and the One Health approach envisioned in PARC, improving the understanding of human exposure and providing data for more holistic RA approaches. This will be of particular interest for policy makers in chemicals management and for the scientific community within and beyond PARC.

Furthermore, the draft reference values for air and dust which will be derived using statistical approaches as well as the identifications of new compounds in specific exposure media will be particularly relevant for regulatory bodies. The envisaged reference values are purely statistical values (P50, P90 etc.) indicating whether an indoor dust or air concentration is within the typical range measured in a building. This has been applied to VOCs in IA (AGÖF, 2013) and is useful where no HBGVs exist. The WHO has published guidelines for IAQ, but they remain limited to a very small number of substances. Given the large variability of indoor concentrations of semi-volatile organic compounds, statistical approaches need a certain number of samples to result in reliable draft reference values.

The chemicals covered by this study are currently addressed in a variety of directives and policy frameworks, with examples given above. This study will contribute to overcoming silo-approaches and will work towards OSOA solutions. It is important to note that the project will not target a specific regulatory topic or body but provide data for an integrative assessment of human exposure which has been systematized for food, but not for other exposure sources of potentially similar or even higher importance. Finally, the project will liaise with WP6 with regard to consumer products as a potential direct and indirect exposure source, i.e. via direct contact and emissions to the environment. Chemical analyses might be included, to the extent methodologies are available, and literature data will be collected. Therefore, we also expect an interest from the manufacturing industry and trade organizations in relevant fields.

Even if the intended close link to T4.1 has to be reduced because of potential practical limitations, the study will deliver these important outcomes of the task-specific standalone part, i.e. draft reference values, identification of new compounds, knowledge of chemicals in consumer products, and related inputs towards OSOA approaches.

Key words: Articles, BPA (analogues), emerging chemicals, environmental monitoring, exposure routes, human exposure, multi-source exposure

Link to the PARC DoA:

The project responds to the PARC OOs: OO5, OO7, OO8, OO10, OO12 and OO11.

The project will contribute to each of the specific objectives in PARC, due to the cross-cutting nature of

the project. Under SO1 (cross-disciplinary network to set priorities for R&I in chemical RA), we expect contributions to OO5, for example via the interface with the Horizon Europe cluster IDEAL, as further described below. We expect the project to contribute to all OOs under SO2 (carry out a joint R&I programme to respond to the agreed priorities in chemical RA). The project relates to OO7 as it will contribute to a work programme that includes needs of integration of human and environmental monitoring approaches in chemical RA. It directly responds to OO8 extending the HBM platform (to external exposure data) and supporting the provision of environmental and multisource data for regulatory purposes. As in all projects in T4.2, FAIR data practices will be implemented and complex data will be analysed, with possibilities of testing and applying innovative concepts (OO10). The project will be linked to the EWS via the close connection established between T4.2 and T8.2 in ongoing projects. Specifically, the use of SS/NTS approaches intended for this project links directly with the strategies for an EWS in T8.2. Thus, information on newly identified compounds can be provided in a one-off initiative, for example for one of the case studies in T8.2. Furthermore, the monitoring strategy to be developed in this project can be incorporated in an EWS for future studies on non-food human exposure sources. The project will provide information for use in integrative RA, both explicitly mentioned under OO12, by integrating human and environmental monitoring data and approaches across compounds and matrices. We also see a contribution to SO3 (access to R&I capacities required to implement innovative chemical RA), in particular OO11. In close collaboration with WP9, the project will consolidate and extend existing networks and contacts between laboratories in the field of environmental analyses. Several partners in T4.2 have expertise in the analysis of environmental contaminants in the indoor environment and/or drinking water and soil.

Links within PARC (WPs/Tasks/Activities/Projects)

Besides its focus on environmental monitoring, the project will establish a substantial cross-section with T4.1 to test the concept that internal exposure data generated in the General HBM Survey can be linked to external exposure data from non-food sources (Fig. 5). Statistically derived external exposure reference values (dust, air) will complement internal exposure reference values and allow the evaluation of spatial and temporal trends in chemical exposure, also with a view to effectiveness evaluations of regulatory efforts. Emerging substances can be identified for future selection of HBM exposure biomarkers and regulatory RM needs.

The generated dataset will be of interest also to exposure models developed in WP6 to predict the correlation between environmental and internal concentrations. Specifically, the PFAS data obtained in this project will support the aggregate PFAS exposure model developed in T6.2. Currently, there is a significant lack of data regarding the sources and indoor concentrations of PFAS, to run and validate this model.

An obvious link exists with T4.3 since the project will also apply innovative techniques such as SS/NTS. Further fields of collaboration will be elucidated over the course of the project. Collaborations with WP7 and T9.3 are foreseen in the fields of data analysis and transfer and the project's QA/QC concept, respectively. Furthermore, T4.2 has a close collaboration with T8.2 where mutual information exchange is ongoing and should also be continued in this project. Given the obvious link to the IDEAL cluster which also includes involvement of several T4.2 partners, potential information exchange and collaborations will involve T3.2.

Links outside PARC:

The importance of IAQ in the context of human exposure and health has been internationally recognised. The cluster IDEAL includes several Horizon Europe projects that address this topic. It will provide data, exposure assessment strategies and policy advice at the interface of the current project. Several T4.2 partners are involved in the IDEAL cluster and can make relevant connections.

The NORMAN network has a working group on ambient and IA, also working on dust as a relevant exposure matrix, where emerging substances and techniques are addressed, which will also be of interest to this project. NORMAN also has extensive experience with water monitoring, which will be beneficial for the drinking water part of this study. Projects in the EHEN would be relevant to connect with this study. Furthermore, the project will be linked to the national and regional studies participating in the T4.1 General HBM Survey.

Given the importance and knowledge gaps in the field of PFAS occurrence and exposure, several European countries have established dedicated PFAS expert groups and developed PFAS action plans, for example aiming at efficient production of scientific knowledge and easier access to information for citizens. The project will also support these initiatives.

Key PARC Deliverables (or Additional Deliverables) and Milestones to which the project contributes

AD4.10: Description of the study concept, including i) collaborative component with T4.1; ii) complementary work to complete the external exposure study; iii) selected compounds and iv) summary of sampling techniques and analytical methods (M36). The integration of HBM and external exposure monitoring is considered relevant for RA and regulatory work in more holistic approaches, including a One Health concept has been cancelled (AD4.10 will be merged with D4.4)

D4.4. 1st Progress report on on-going monitoring projects (new delivery date M42)

AD4.14. The overall project report will provide relevant data aiming at links between internal and external exposure for the same individual, concentrations of prioritized chemicals in non-food exposure media and new knowledge and experiences in integrative approaches. Since only few studies exist that link human and environmental monitoring, the project will provide relevant new information for risk assessors and policy makers, also at the methodological and conceptual level (M72).

Partners List:

Project co-leading group: AU (Denmark), INERIS (France), LNS (Luxembourg), CSBT (France), NILU (Norway)

Key contributors: VITO (Belgium), MU (Czech Republic), UBA (Germany), IVL (Sweden), AUTH (Greece), NKUA (Greece), key contributors involved in collecting the environmental samples in the General HBM Survey

Extended group: BRGM (France), ISCIII (Spain), IDAEA-CSIC (Spain), ISSeP (Belgium), JSI (Slovenia), OVAM (Belgium), UAntwerp (Belgium), UL (Latvia), UniLU (Luxembourg), VSCHT (Czech Republic), UPV/EHU (Spain), ISS (Italy), MO-CY/SBL (Cyprus), RSU (Latvia)

Schedule:

Starting date: 01/05/2024 (M25)

Expected ending date: 30/04/2028 (M72)

Costs

Expected PM for the second year of the project: 117 PM

Expected ODC for the second year of the project: 194 125 €

P4.2.d_Y4_Siloxanes_AU_INERIS

Project Title	Volatile siloxanes in the European environment – towards robust data in support of regulatory actions		
Project Acronym (15 letters max)	Siloxanes		
Project Manager	Katrin Vorkamp kvo@envs.au.dk	Aarhus University (AU)	Denmark
	Valeria Dulio Valeria.Dulio@ineris.fr	INERIS	France
Deputy Project manager	NA	NA	NA
Expected starting date	M37	Expected duration	24
PARC (Month number)		(months)	
PARC Workpackage number	WP4	PARC Task/Activity/Sub-activity:	T4.2
Project Id	P4.2.d_Y4_Siloxanes_AU_INERIS		

Status: Initiation

Summary of the project

The project addresses the group of siloxanes, in particular the cyclic volatile methylsiloxanes (CVMS) octamethylcyclotetrasiloxane (D4), decamethylcyclopentasiloxane (D5) and dodecamethylcyclohexasiloxane (D6) and some linear volatile methylsiloxanes (LMVS). Siloxanes are high production volume chemicals used in a variety of industries, such as construction, transport, oil and gas, the medical sector etc. as well as personal care products. D4, D5 and D6 are considered for review under the United Nations Stockholm Convention on POPs, i.e. with regard to their persistence, bioaccumulation, toxicity and ability to be transported over long distances (ECHA, 2023). In addition, the EC adopted an EU-wide restriction of D4, D5 and D6 in May 2024, which will be applied from June 2026 (EC, 2024). Norway intends to submit a proposal to list the LVMS L2, L3, L4 and L5 as SVHC⁴.

Related to these regulatory activities, there is a need for more environmental data to support i) the proposal to the Stockholm Convention, ii) allow a future effectiveness evaluation of CVMS at the European and/or global level and iii) provide information for assessments of LMVS. However, siloxane measurements are highly challenging due to e.g. risks of contamination and limited stability in some sampling media, for example on certain sorbent materials used for air sampling (Warner et al., 2020). It will therefore be a first important step to ensure accurate, precise and robust measurements.

CVMS were identified as Chemicals of Emerging Arctic Concern (CEACs) by the Arctic Monitoring and Assessment Programme (AMAP, 2017), based on data in e.g. Arctic air and aquatic environments. The occurrence in the aquatic environment was mainly related to wastewater discharges. While siloxanes reached relatively high concentrations in air, their deposition from the air was questioned (AMAP, 2017). Air and wastewater will be primary matrices of interest, linked to sources and transport pathways in the environment. Furthermore, wet and dry deposition are open research questions. Environmental levels should also be established for receiving waters, including sediment and biota, in order to allow a better characterisation of the environmental fate of CVMS and LVMS, also considering human exposure via environmental pathways.

A case study on LVMS and CVMS has been requested by ECHA in their report on Key Areas of Regulatory Challenge (KARC) (ECHA, 2023), which has subsequently been included in the PARC “Future Activities”. In the internal PARC document, the case study was suggested as part of a broader initiative on persistent mobile and toxic (PMT) compounds. However, given the main PBT-related concerns and the fact that D4 and D5 have been characterized as very bioaccumulative substances (EC, 2024) a PMT-focussed study might not be an ideal design to address this group of compounds. The KARC suggestion focusses on deposition processes as a missing link between the atmospheric and terrestrial/aquatic environments, which hampers the evaluation of the long-range transport potential siloxanes.

Siloxanes have also been of interest for HBM but only been included in few studies (e.g. Fromme et al., 2025) because of challenges with the analytical methods. Compared with the environmental analyses, HBM is particularly challenging because of lower levels and biomarkers that might be different from parent compounds. While this project can provide important new ideas for approaches to HBM of siloxanes, it will focus on environmental samples and the related regulatory context. This focus is ambitious in itself and its success cannot be guaranteed.

For this reason, we propose a two-phase approach, the first phase concentrating on the technical feasibility of generating environmental data in support of regulatory actions. This phase will consist of a collection and evaluation of analytical methods for environmental monitoring, combined with dedicated tests where data and experience are missing. Relevant performance indicators will be defined in this first phase that will be used to assess the achievable analytical quality, for example detection limits and measurement uncertainty. If it is concluded at the end of this phase that no siloxane measurements of relevance for regulatory action are possible with the required analytical quality, as assessed by the performance

indicators, the project will be discontinued. The second phase will consist of a monitoring campaign, subject to the outcomes of the first phase.

Main expected outputs of the project:

We expect the project to deliver an assessment of the possibility to generate environmental monitoring data in support of regulatory actions, for example for air, precipitation, wastewater, sediment and biota from selected locations across Europe, based on relevant performance indicators. Ideally, the project will create a network of laboratories (in collaboration with WP9) capable of conducting state-of-the-art environmental analyses of CVMS and LVMS addressing the existing data and knowledge gaps for siloxanes. These data have been requested by regulators (e.g. in connection with REACH and the Stockholm Convention). In addition, we expect the project to outline possibilities for future environmental monitoring of siloxanes, including clear descriptions of potential caveats in the current sampling and determination methods. An assessment, tests and consolidation of the analytical methods will be a step towards more routine-based analyses of siloxanes in Europe, which can be considered a prerequisite in a regulatory context.

Outcomes and impacts expected on end-users and stakeholders:

Siloxanes, in particular the CVMS D4, D5 and D6, are considered a concern for ecosystems and human health, which has led to regulatory actions at EU level, including an expected proposal of global regulation via the Stockholm Convention. Screening criteria of the Stockholm Convention include persistence, bioaccumulation, toxicity and long-range environmental transport, and an assessment of these criteria can be based on monitoring data. Steps towards regulation of the LVMS L2, L3, L4 and L5 are being considered. The regulations already in place or proposed create a need for effectiveness evaluation, i.e. consecutive measurements to establish if the regulations have the desired effect. New regulatory actions require reliable data for assessments. However, the current analysis of volatile siloxanes in environmental samples includes several challenges, resulting in only few laboratories with this analytical capacity for specific matrices. Consequently, there is a lack of data for RAs as well as a lack of robust methods for future analysis, for example for effectiveness evaluations. It is the main aim of this project to address these gaps.

Siloxanes were also previously defined as relevant compounds for HBM, as documented in correspondence among German HBM experts that has been provided by UBA. Due to challenges with the analytical methods and questions about suitable biomarkers, attempts to include siloxanes in HBM initiatives were paused. Experiences with HBM will be considered in the feasibility discussions, as they might also be relevant for environmental monitoring. If successful with environmental analyses, the project might also provide new ideas and suggestions for the HBM community, which could be pursued and tested subsequently, outside this project. The exchange with HBM experts will further contribute to the bridges between environmental monitoring and HBM that are being built in PARC.

Outcomes and impacts expected to be incorporated into a specific regulatory framework:

The outcomes of this project can be incorporated into REACH, for example providing data in support of the planned proposal of LMVS to the list of SVHC and methods for follow-up measurements assessing the effectiveness of the CMVS EU-wide restriction. Furthermore, both data and methods will be of use for the POP Review Committee under the Stockholm Convention for assessments of screening criteria and, potentially, establishment of risk profiles for D4, D5 and D6.

Key words: Atmosphere; bioaccumulation; deposition; long-range environmental transport; persistence; persistent organic pollutants (POPs); REACH; Stockholm Convention; toxicity; wastewater

Link to the PARC DoA:

The project will contribute to OO3, OO4 under SO1. It is directly linked to ECHA's priorities summarized in KARC and the identification of relevant PARC "Future Activities", which has been a transparent and

open process revealing scientific data and knowledge gaps of importance for regulators. Siloxanes are a chemical group for which great regulatory interest exists. The project group will seek close contacts to both regulatory authorities and other R&I initiatives, for example the Co-operative programme for monitoring and evaluation of long-range transmission of air pollutants in Europe (European Monitoring and Evaluation Programme, EMEP), which will enhance the scientific quality of the project and possibilities of efficient regulatory uptake.

The project will also contribute to OO7 and OO10 under SO2. As mentioned above, the project proposal responds to identified needs in chemical RA, as summarized in KARC and transferred to the PARC “Future Activities”. If approved, the project will be implemented in the annual work programmes for PARC Years 4 and 5, using FAIR data practices and state-of-the-art methods in data analysis for RA. In accordance with the PARC principles of building on existing knowledge, the project will a) bring together expertise in the chemical analysis of siloxanes (in workshops and meetings) to identify possibilities and limitations with current methodology, define performance indicators for the analytical quality, design and run corresponding tests and conclude on the analytical feasibility of an environmental monitoring campaign and b) apply strategies and techniques that have been developed in the pilot project in T4.2 (P4.2.a_Y1_ENVMonitoringPilotSurvey_INERIS_AU). Given the interest in human exposure to siloxanes and methods for HBM, the project can also provide new ideas for HBM and facilitate the exchange of experience and potential solution models between experts focusing on chemical analyses of environmental and human samples, respectively.

The project will also contribute to OO9 and O11 under SO3. The focus of parts of the project on the feasibility of precise, accurate and robust analyses will improve the level of harmonization and validation of these methods which are currently challenged by e.g. blank contamination and instability of the analytes. Connected with OO4 above, the regulatory uptake of these results will be an important aspect of the project. Based on the experience that already exists in WP9 regarding laboratory networks, a subgroup of laboratories will be established for siloxanes that can lead specialized discussions on the state-of-the-art and related challenges of the chemical analyses and define relevant performance indicators for the assessment of analytical quality. While the project focusses on environmental data, experts interested in the chemical analyses of siloxanes (and/or related biomarkers) in human matrices will be welcome to join the network to contribute with their experience and to further strengthen the collaboration between environmental and HBM in PARC. HBM experts might gain new ideas for the analyses of siloxanes in human matrices, which are generally even more challenging than environmental studies because of lower concentration levels and the potential metabolization processes.

Links within PARC (WPs/Tasks/Activities/Projects)

Collaboration with WP9 will be important for this project in several respects. T9.1 focusses on laboratory networks and should be associated with this project. While the expert laboratory network in this project will be a highly specialized one with the focus on a specific compound group, its establishment and work should still be aligned with general laboratory network structures in PARC. It could also be of interest to T9.1 to see if existing network structures allow the ad hoc formation of subgroups that are dedicated to specific chemical compounds under the overall T9.1 umbrella. T9.3 focusses on QA/QC and should also be associated with this project. Since the chemical analysis of CVMS and LVMS is challenging, QA/QC measures are particularly important and will be a central aspect of the project. T9.3 can advise based on their scientific expertise and ensure alignment with overall QA/QC concepts in PARC, analogously to the work of T9.1 in the field of laboratory networks.

Collaboration with T4.1 will be of particular interest in the first phase of the project where experience with the chemical analyses of siloxanes will be exchanged and the feasibility of an environmental monitoring campaign will be assessed. Based on information provided by UBA, previous attempts to include siloxanes in HBM initiatives met challenges that were similar to those described for the environmental analyses,

including blank issues. It might be of mutual benefit to include expertise from the HBM and the environmental field. HBM-based expertise could strengthen the knowledge base for this project, while the environmental expertise might provide new inputs to HBM-oriented method development. Thus, a close contact on analytical methods will further enhance the collaboration between T4.1 and T4.2.

Links outside PARC

The EMEP programme is connected to the Convention on Transboundary Air Pollution under the United Nations Economic Commission for Europe. Given their documented presence in outdoor air, siloxanes are included in some air monitoring activities under this programme. Their importance and the analytical challenges connected with their measurements were discussed at a recent workshop organised by NILU, which also included recommendations for future work (NILU, 2024). The outcomes of that workshop will be included in this project and provide important inputs to the work in the first phase of this project, regarding evaluations of analytical methods and specific tests to e.g. check the practicability of methods and their performance. Specifically, the workshop included a number of recommendations for the future air monitoring of siloxanes, which could also inspire discussions about other matrices and the design of dedicated tests. For example, the potential of online measurements with Proton Transfer Reaction Mass Spectrometry (PTR-MS) was discussed for air, as it would avoid sorption and extraction steps and thus reduce the risk of contamination.

AMAP is a Working Group under the Arctic Council consisting of the eight Arctic States and Permanent Participants. AMAP coordinates Arctic monitoring of contaminants and assessed the knowledge of siloxanes and other CEACs in a dedicated report (AMAP, 2017), which has also been presented to the Stockholm Convention and other policymaking bodies. An update of this report is planned, but not yet initiated. Following the AMAP model, AMAP was endorsed in 2023 as a UN Ocean Decade project under the Scientific Committee of Antarctic Research (SCAR). Work on siloxanes has also previously been performed in the Antarctic, and relevant experiences might be hosted for this project.

NORMAN is a network of laboratories and organisations with a focus on emerging contaminants. Its members might include laboratories with expertise in siloxane analyses that are not partners in PARC and that might be able to contribute to this project via the collaboration agreement that is currently being prepared between NORMAN and PARC. If the project is approved, the T4.2 co-leads will contact the NORMAN network and develop a survey to assess the potential expertise of NORMAN laboratory members in this field and their interest in contributing to this project. If relevant NORMAN members are identified who are not yet involved in PARC, a collaboration will be established under the PARC-NORMAN collaboration agreement. The details of this collaboration will be described in an annex to the collaboration agreement, including procedures for publications of the results generated in this project. No additional costs are anticipated for this potential project collaboration.

Key PARC Deliverables and Milestones to which the project contributes

AD4.16. Project report (M60)

Partners List: AU (Denmark), INERIS (France), IVL (Sweden), NILU (Norway), IDAEA-CSIC (Spain), UBA (Germany), UAntwerpen (Belgium), MU (Czech Republic), ISCIII (Spain), WUR (Netherlands), potentially others

Schedule:

Starting date: 01/05/2025 (M37)

Expected ending date: 30/04/2027 (M60)

The project will proceed in two phases, with the first one focussing on the analytical feasibility of environmental analyses of siloxanes. The first phase will last one year. Thus, if the conclusion of the first phase is that environmental analyses will not be feasible, the project will end on 30/04/2026 (M48)

Costs

Expected PM for the first year of the project: 22 PM
Expected ODC for the first year of the project: 21 250 €

T4.3 Innovative methods and tools for monitoring and surveys – 9 PROJECTS

Innovative (self-)sampling approaches will be evaluated for applicability in large scale monitoring programmes and specific surveys addressing population groups such as the occupational population. Innovative high-throughput *in vitro* and/or *in vivo* bioassays for effect-based environmental and human exposure monitoring will be improved. SS approaches will be harmonised across the environment-food-HBM communities in terms of definitions, objectives supporting policy context, and technical implementation. NTS approaches will be promoted and harmonised to complement multiple exposure assessment across the environmental, food safety and HBM fields and to comply with regulatory needs. These innovative approaches will be evaluated through complementary proof-of-concepts each dealing with a given particular new sampling and measurement approach applied to a given exposure/sample type and sub-population.

Fig 6: Projects structuration under Task 4.3

A4.3.1 Transversal actions –3 PROJECTS

P4.3.1.b_Y1_T02-QAQC_WR

Project Title	QA/QC requirements for HRMS and EDA-based screening approaches in environmental, food and human matrices		
Project Acronym (15 letters max)	QA/QC for HRMS and EDA		
Project Manager	Rosalie Nijssen rosalie.nijssen@wur.nl	WR (WFSR)	NL
Deputy Project manager	Karsten Beekmann Karsten.beekmann@wur.nl	WR (WFSR)	NL
Expected starting date PARC (Month number)	1	Expected duration	60*
PARC Workpackage number	4	PARC Task/Activity/Sub-activity:	4.3.1
Project Id	P4.3.1.b_Y1_T02_QAQC_WR		

*The project has been extended from M36 to M60

Status: Implementation

Summary of the project

SS/NTS is a key component in PARC to find chemicals beyond the currently known and prioritised ones. The chemical and biological effect-based approaches for SS/NTS are relatively new and QA/QC is not yet well established and harmonised. This project will consist of developing a transversal action aiming at defining minimal common QA/QC requirements to be used specifically for chemical SS/NTS based on chromatography coupled to HRMS and biological effect-directed assays (EDA). This project will inventory the existing QA/QC procedures, guidelines, proposals (and interpretations thereof) in the food, environmental and HBM domains, identify inconsistencies and gaps, and aims to align and establish procedures and criteria across the application domains.

Main expected outputs of the project

- 1) More consistent and comparable data from SS/NTS methods generated by multiple laboratories (within application domains)
- 2) Implementation of harmonised approaches across application domains (environment, HBM, food)

Outcomes and impacts expected for end-users and stakeholders

The proposed project appears as a necessary follow-up of the work achieved under HBM4EU, where a number of QA/QC provisions, guidance SOP, and supporting template for QA/QC data analysis were produced in the particular context of the Specimen Study (pesticide screening in 2000 human urine samples from 5 countries by 5 different laboratories). From that basis, the goal of the present project is to deliver to end-users interested to implement those innovative screening approaches an extended and consolidated QA/QC framework to be applied more globally for a wide range of different applications within the environmental-food-HBM communities. This medium-term perspective should benefit a number of end-users and stakeholders through improvement of data quality / comparability.

Key words:

Quality Control, Quality Assurance, suspect screening, non-target screening, identification, effect-directed assays

Link to the PARC DoA:

The project responds to the PARC OOs OO5, OO9 and OO11.

This project will deal with necessary QA/QC provisions specifically dedicated to the innovative approaches developed under task 4.3. Indeed, the analytical chemistry community has developed for many years appropriate QA/QC provisions for assessing the performance of conventional targeted methods applied to environmental, food or human matrices. The situation is less mature for emerging and innovative approaches where the objectives differ from the previous ones. A main need for qualitative (or semi-quantitative) suspect and non-targeted approaches relies on the precise and transparent documentation of the method application range, i.e., the contour of the accessible markers of exposure, in order to possibly compare and well interpret the results obtained by different methods. This workline was explicitly included in the task 4.3 DoA.

Links within PARC (WPs/Tasks/Activities/Projects)

The project is very closely linked to WP9/task 9.3, and WP4, specifically to the QA/QC activities therein (T4.1.2, T4.2.4). Several experts/key contributors from these tasks are also involved in the present project 4.3_T02 that will permit to establish this necessary articulation. While in T9.3 overarching frameworks are set, this activity focusses specifically on HRMS and EDA based screening methods, and for that the generation of experimental- and experience-based QA/QC criteria and requirements and establishing QA/QC programs of SS/NTS and EDA. Prioritised substance groups in activities in T4.1 and T4.2 are taken into account with respect to type of chemicals addressed (e.g., PFAS and EDs, EDCs), and possible integration of QA/QC programs (e.g. proficiency testing using the same control materials in both target and screening methods).

Links outside PARC:

Within the below mentioned projects and already existing regulations/guidance documents, QA/QC for screening methods has been (partially) addressed to various levels of detail. This project will link with and build forth on these projects:

HBM4EU

NORMAN (<https://www.norman-network.com/?q=Home>)

MetroFood (<https://www.metrofood.eu/>)

Joint Research Centre (JRC) (<https://crm.jrc.ec.europa.eu/>)

EU-TOXRISK/”RISK assessment of chemicals integrating HUMAN centric Next generation Testing strategies promoting the 3Rs” (RISKHUNT3R) (<https://www.eu-toxrisk.eu/> , <https://www.risk-hunt3r.eu/>)

Food screening regulations, e.g., dioxins Calux Commission Regulation (EU) 2017/644

Key PARC Deliverables and Milestones to which the project contributes

AD4.5: Technical specifications of the study (project design, hypothesis and research question as well as analytical procedures including QA/QC and data flows) (delivered)

AD4.12: General guideline for QA/QC in non-target screening (M60)

MS7: Establishment of working groups (delivered)

Partners List:

Lead: WR (NL). Partners: INRAE (FR), ANSES (FR), AU (DK), BfG (DE), BRGM (FR), EAWAG (CH), EHESP (FR), INRS (FR), JSI (SI), KWR (NL), LNS (LU), MU (CZ), MUI (AU), ORU-MTM (SE), SLU (SE), UAntwerpen (UA), UBA (DE), UCPH (DK), UFZ (DE), AUTH (GR), EV-ILVO (BE), CSIC (ES), LNE (FR) NILU (NO), WULS (PL)

Schedule:

Starting date: 01/05/2022 (M1)

Expected ending date: 30/04/2027 (M60)

Costs

Expected PM for the fourth year of the project: 15 PM

Expected ODC for the fourth year of the project: 19 125 €

P4.3.1.c_Y1_T03_EWStools_SLU

Project Title	Illustrating the usefulness of innovative (self-)sampling combined with integrated suspect/NTS/EDA approaches as a contribution to early warning system and harmonized framework from environment-food-human		
Project Acronym (15 letters max)	Early Warning System Tools		
Project Manager	Lutz Ahrens Lutz.ahrens@slu.se	SLU	Sweden
Deputy Project manager	Georgios Niarchos georgios.niarchos@slu.se	SLU	Sweden
Expected starting date PARC (Month number)	1	Expected duration	60
PARC Workpackage number	4.3	PARC Task/Activity/Sub-activity:	4.3.1.c
Project Id	P4.3.1.c_Y1_T03_EWStools_SLU		

Status: Implementation

Summary of the project

Establishment of an EWS for identification of new and existing potentially hazardous substances is a key component in PARC and current EU regulatory actions. For prioritization of new chemicals, several tools

have been developed that can be used in combination or independently, among which SS/NTS coupled to effect directed analyses approaches. This project will support the development of EWS under WP8 (task 8.2) by ensuring that data generated through those innovative methods can be used to identify and prioritize hazardous substances in human, food and environmental matrices that may be associated with a potential risk. The project will illustrate the usefulness of early warning monitoring tools both for environmental samples (e.g. soil, sediment, sludge, dust), human samples (e.g. blood), food (incl. drinking water) and products (incl. waste streams, recycled products). The project will identify in particular chemical properties, toxicological endpoints and HRMS features relevant for the EWS, initially with the purpose to gather all necessary ones, and then identify criteria to assign relative weights to each parameter and endpoint.

Main expected outputs of the project

Review already existing information related to innovative (self-)sampling combined with integrated SS/NTS/EDA approaches as early warning monitoring tools

Contribute/formulate criteria for categorizing annotated data to be integrated in the EWS format.

Elaborate a proof-of-concept illustrating (self-)sampling combined with integrated SS/NTS/EDA approaches as a contribution to EWS.

Outcomes and impacts expected for end-users and stakeholders

This project will generate proofs-of-concepts and tools of relevance to risk assessors and policy makers at national and EU level. Innovative (self-)sampling combined with integrated SS/NTS/EDA approaches are of utmost importance for identification of new and existing potentially hazardous substances at an early stage. Cutting edge tools will be conceptualized and illustrated for establishment of an EWS. End-users include ECHA, EFSA, EEA, national environmental and chemical agencies, national food safety authorities, NORMAN, researchers, industry, Non-governmental organizations (NGOs), national consumer protection organizations and the general public.

Key words:

Early warning system (EWS); early warning monitoring tools; Effect-Directed Analysis (EDA); suspect and non-targeted screening (NTS); high resolution mass spectrometry (HRMS); innovative sampling

Link to the PARC DoA:

The project responds to the PARC OOs OO3, OO5, OO7, OO8, OO10, OO12, OO9, OO11 and OO13.

The project will establish a proof-of-concept illustration of innovative (self-)sampling combined with integrated SS/NTS/EDA approaches as a contribution to EWSs and harmonized framework from environment-food-human. This will ensure that the generated data can be used to support the development of EWSs under WP8 to communicate risks, facilitate awareness of risks and disseminate warnings to inform risk assessors and risk managers at an early stage of future challenges or emerging risks, linked to other activities and future projects in PARC.

For the development of a proof-of-concept EWS, criteria for a prioritization strategy for hazardous chemicals will be defined in cooperation with other R&I initiatives. The concept of EWS tools and towards an EWS will be shared within the joint R&I programme. The results coming out of this project will be communicated and disseminated to the general public, the PARC consortium and policy makers for regulatory uptake.

Links within PARC (WPs/Tasks/Activities/Projects)

WP4:

4.3/4.3.1/P4.3.1.a_Y1_T01_Concept Paper_MU: Alignment of objectives / purposes of SS/NTS/EDA

4.3/4.3.1/P4.3.1.b_Y1_T02_QA/QC Issues_WR: Ensure quality of the generated data

4.3/4.3.1/P4.3.1.d_Y1_T04_Data Processing Workflow_EHESP: Support annotation of generated data

4.3/4.3.2/P4.3.2.a_Y1_H01-Perinatal exposure_INRAE: Ensure useful output for EWS

4.3/4.3.2/P4.3.2.b_Y2_H02_Occupational exposure_INRS: Ensure useful output for EWS

4.3/4.3.2/P4.3.2.c_Y3_H03_Other complementary studies_JSI: Ensure useful output for EWS

4.3/4.3.3/P4.3.3.a_Y1_E01-WBE_UFZ-UBATH: Ensure useful output for EWS

4.3/4.3.3/P4.3.3.b_Y2_E02-Sentinel animals_ONIRIS: Ensure useful output for EWS

WP5: Effect-directed tools based on bioassays using new approach methodologies (NAMs).
 WP7: Definition of specific requirements for SS/NTS/EDA data management (retrospective use, repository...). FAIR Data libraries.
 WP8: Conceptualization of an EWS from sampling/NTS/EDA methods in humans, environment, food and products combining exposure and hazard data. Computational methods for text mining, data curation and hazard scoring.
 WP9: Contribution to harmonised QA/QC and training for SS/NTS/EDA approaches.

Links outside PARC:

[HBM4EU](#) (data, models), [HEALS](#), [CROME-Life](#), UBA [NTS Portal with BfG](#) (Water, suspended matter), [NORMAN Network](#) activities, DG ENV EWS project

Key PARC Deliverables and Milestones to which the project contributes

D.4.10. 3rd Proof-of-concept assessing the usefulness of innovative (self-) sampling combined with integrated suspect/NTS/EDA approaches (M60)

Partners List:

SLU (SE), INRAE (FR), VUA (NL), ANSES (FR), BRGM (FR), EAWAG (CH), JSI (SI), MUI (AT), ORU-MTM (SE), UAntwerpen (BE), UBA (DE), UCPH (DK), UFZ (DE), UniLU (LU), AUTH (GR), ISS (IT), NILU (NO)

Schedule:

Starting date: 01/05/2022 (M1)
 Expected ending date: 30/04/2027 (M60)

Costs

Expected PM for the fourth year of the project: 12 PM
 Expected ODC for the fourth year of the project: 7 245 €

P4.3.1.d_Y1_T04-Data Processing Workflow_EHESP

Project Title	Establishment of necessary advanced data processing methodologies and bioinformatic tools for NTS. Identify gaps / necessary methodological improvements for retrospective use of NTS HRMS data (digital sample freezing platform) and EU capacity in terms of centralized data repository		
Project Acronym (15 letters max)	Data processing workflow		
Project Manager	Arthur David Arthur.david@ehesp.fr	EHESP	FR
Deputy Project manager	Jade Chaker jade.chaker@ehesp.fr	EHESP	FR
Expected starting date PARC (Month number)	1	Expected duration	60
PARC Workpackage number	4	PARC Task/Activity/Sub-activity:	4.3.1
Project Id	P4.3.1.d_Y1_T04-Data processing workflow_EHESP		

Status: Implementation

Summary of the project:

Considering the vast amount of chemicals present on the market, there is currently a substantial lack of data on human and environmental exposure to these chemicals, preventing the implementation of efficient regulatory approaches by policy makers with regard to the RA of such complex real-life mixtures. Hence, SS and non-targeted analyses based on high-resolution offer great promises to identify emerging and chemical mixtures without a priori. The lack of comprehensive and user-friendly automated pipeline for SS and NTS data processing however appears as a crucial issue and current major bottleneck for efficient

implementation of these approaches. Indeed, a wide range of software tools are today available to perform one or several components of such data processing and extraction of the useful information from the raw data, including peak picking, peak alignment, and annotation. But still no consensual guidelines were proposed regarding both a preferable selection from this panel of existing tool or their fine appropriate parameterization in the context of NTS. Overall, an integrated, sustainable, and open access solution permitting to perform all these necessary steps with sufficient QA/QC consolidation for support to policy application and sufficient high throughput capacity for application to large scale cohorts, is still lacking and is urgently needed.

Main expected outputs of the project

- Build a strong and dynamic consortium within the environment-food safety-HBM scientific communities to harmonize and mutualize the current and future resources
- Updated CECScreen database with the aim to improve the annotation quality
- Pursued development of an extended, unified, sustainable and open access European member state reference library through the collaborative generation of mass spectrometry and tandem mass spectrometry reference spectra
 - Developed comprehensive and user-friendly automated pipeline for SS and NTS
 - Defined appropriate quality strategies to ensure retrospective analyses/EWS
 - Developed / improved appropriate data processing workflow dedicated to bioassay data

Outcomes and impacts expected for end-users and stakeholders

This project appears as a pre-requisite methodological development related activity, expected to provide at medium term (4 years) new consolidated ground to implement SS/NTS approaches at larger scale and provide new data on human and environmental exposure for policy makers. This medium-term perspective should benefit a number of end-users including laboratories aiming to implement those new analytical approaches (capacity building within the EU), as well as actors aiming to build and use EWSs for which the expected new exposure data generation capabilities will represent a significant input, including sanitary agencies, risk assessors, and public health authorities.

Key words:

Suspect screening; non-targeted screening; data processing, annotation, user-friendly workflow; CECScreen database; reference library; marker identification; automation

Link to the PARC DoA:

The project responds to the PARC OOs OO5, OO7, OO8, OO10, OO12 and OO11.

The development of this comprehensive and user-friendly automated pipeline for SS and NTS is a necessary step for all the projects that will use these strategies in WP4 and other related WPs. Following the work done in HBM4EU, the development of an extended, unified, sustainable and open access European MS reference library as a key stone of the annotation workflow underlying to these HRMS-based SS approaches applied across the environment-food-human continuum is clearly part of the defined DoA for task 4.3, as well as the establishment of necessary advanced data processing methodologies and bioinformatic tools for better efficiency and deployment of NTS (e.g. inspired from the Workflow for Metabolomics (W4M)/Galaxy user friendly environment).

Links within PARC (WPs/Tasks/Activities/Projects)

WP4:

4.3/4.3.1/P4.3.1.a_Y1_T01_Concept Paper_MU: Alignment of objectives / purposes of SS/NTS/EDA

4.3/4.3.1/P4.3.1.b_Y1_T02_QA/QC Issues_WR: Ensure quality of the generated data

4.3/4.3.2/P4.3.2.a_Y1_H01-Perinatal exposure_INRAE: Mutualized resources / harmonization

4.3/4.3.2/P4.3.2.b_Y2_H02_Occupational exposure_INRS: Mutualized resources / harmonization

4.3/4.3.2/P4.3.2.c_Y3_H03_Other complementary studies_JSI: Mutualized resources / harmonization

4.3/4.3.3/P4.3.3.a_Y1_E01-WBE_UFZ-UBATH: Mutualized resources / harmonization

4.3/4.3.3/P4.3.3.b_Y2_E02-Sentinel animals_ONIRIS: Mutualized resources / harmonization

WP7: Definition of specific requirements for SS/NTS/EDA data management (retrospective use,

repository...)

WP9: Contribution to harmonised QA/QC and training for SS/NTS/EDA approaches

Links outside PARC

Continuity with regard to HBM4EU WP16 related activities that has developed basis of harmonisation and development for SS and NTS but without considering the related innovative sampling approaches considered in the present project.

NORMAN (<https://www.norman-network.com/?q=Home>), JRC (<https://crm.jrc.ec.europa.eu/>) France-Exposome, Institut Français de Bioinformatique (IFB, ELIXIR-FR, <https://www.france-bioinformatique.fr/elixir-fr/>), “European Life-science Infrastructure for Biological Information” (ELIXIR) and “Environmental Exposure Assessment Research Infrastructure“ (EIRENE) infrastructures.

Key PARC Deliverables and Milestones to which the project contributes

D.4.9 Workflow for data processing and annotation of HRMS based chemical profiles generated from SS/NTS approaches (M54).

Partners List:

EHESP (FR), INRAE (FR), VUA (NL), ANSES (FR), INRS (FR), JSI (SI), KWR (DE), MU (CE), MUI (AT), Oniris (FR), UBA (DE), UCPH (DK), UFZ (DE), UniLU (LU), WR (NL)

Schedule:

Starting date: 01/05/2022 (M1)

Expected ending date: 30/04/2027 (M60)

Costs

Expected PM for the fourth year of the project: 45 PM

Expected ODC for the fourth year of the project: 33 090 €

A4.3.2 Human samples based proof-of-concepts – 3 PROJECTS

P4.3.2.a_Y1_H01-Perinatal exposure_INRAE

Project Title	Proof-of-concept of innovative sampling and HRMS based / EDA screening methods for exploring human perinatal exposure to chemicals of emerging concern		
Project Acronym (15 letters max)	Perinatal exposure		
Project Manager	Jean-Philippe Antignac jean-philippe.antignac@inrae.fr	INRAE	FR
Deputy Project manager	Tarek Moufawad Tarek.moufawad@oniris-nantes.fr	INRAE	FR
Expected starting date PARC (Month number)	1	Expected duration	48
PARC Workpackage number	4	PARC Task/Activity/Sub-activity:	4.3.2
Project Id	P4.3.2.a_Y1_H01-Perinatal exposure_INRAE		

Status: Implementation

Summary of the project

Capturing the complex real human chemical exposure requires new conceptual frameworks and innovative methodological approaches. These ones, from sampling to exposure data generation and analysis, are however requiring a better consolidated development and a better documented performance assessment before large scale implementation in human cohorts. As formulated by several agencies (e.g., EFSA), early stage human exposure appears in particular as a high concern not yet well addressed, both in terms of RA

and link to health impact at latest stages (Developmental origins of health and disease (DoHAD) concept). New sampling methods (e.g., silicone wristbands (SWBs) and/or dried blood spots (DBS)), compatible with the non-invasiveness and restricted sample requirements typically expected for those sub-populations represent potentially relevant options to be considered in that context. SS/NTS based on HRMS coupled to EDA are another new trend in analytical laboratories with high potential. The aim of this project is to develop and conduct a proof-of-concept permitting to assess the performances, and illustrate the usefulness, of those innovative methods, as complementary to conventional and targeted approaches, with a focus on human samples collected from mother-newborn/child individuals. By definition screening approaches should permit to capture simultaneously various substances from different classes, relying on the global prioritization strategy from WP2, including both non persistent and persistent organic CEC.

Main expected outputs of the project

- Characterization of advantages/limitations of innovative approaches compared to conventional ones
- Scientifically supported prioritisation of some of them for short term implementation
- Paved way for further developments/improvements needed for long term implementation
- Identification of relevant markers/matrices combinations for perinatal exposure assessment
- Documenting real life mixtures associated to perinatal chemical exposure
- Prioritization of further targeted developments focused on particular exposure markers evidenced
- Contribution to feed EWS through an established link between tasks 4.3 and 8.2

Outcomes and impacts expected for end-users and stakeholders

The proposed project appears as a pre-required methodological development activity, expected to provide at medium term (4 years) consolidated bases for implementing a set of innovative sampling and exposure measurement approaches for HBM. This medium-term perspective should benefit a number of end-users including laboratories aiming to implement those new analytical approaches (capacity building), as well as actors aiming to build and use EWSs for which the expected new exposure data generation capabilities will represent a significant input, including sanitary agencies, risk assessors, and public health authorities.

Key words:

Biomonitoring, perinatal exposure, innovative methods, dry blood spots, silicone wristbands, suspect screening, non-targeted screening, effect-directed analysis, real-life mixtures, emerging chemicals

Link to the PARC DoA

The project responds to the PARC OOs OO3, OO5, OO6, OO7, OO8, OO12 and OO11. Conventional sampling and targeted quantitative analytical methods are already available to support environmental, food and human monitoring, RA/RM decisions. However, these approaches sometimes suffer from a lack of sensitivity to characterize lowest exposed populations, face some limitations for large scale implementation, and only capture a limited number of a priori known and selected markers of exposure. From this global picture, a specific concern formulated by several agencies (e.g., EFSA) is related to a need for a better characterization of exposure for particularly vulnerable sub-populations, notably newborns and young children. Human foetal exposure also appears as a not yet well addressed high concern in the context of linking this early exposure to human health impact at latest stages (DoHAD concept). This project will contribute to address those issues related to the PARC objectives and DoA.

Links within PARC (WPs/Tasks/Activities/Projects)

WP4:

4.3/4.3.1/P4.3.1.a_Y1_T01_Concept Paper_MU: Alignment of objectives / purposes of SS/NTS/EDA

4.3/4.3.1/P4.3.1.b_Y1_T02_QA/QC Issues_WR: Ensure quality of the generated data

4.3/4.3.1/P4.3.1.c_Y1_T03_Early Warning System_SLU: Ensure useful output for EWS

4.3/4.3.1/P4.3.1.d_Y1_T04_Data Processing Workflow_EHESP: Support annotation of generated data

4.3/4.3.2/P4.3.2.b_Y2_H02_Occupational exposure_INRS: Mutualized resources / harmonization

4.3/4.3.2/P4.3.2.c_Y3_H03_Other complementary studies_JSI: Mutualized resources / harmonization

4.1/4.1.1: Pro/con expert review and analysis, QAQC consolidation and implementation of DBS/SWB

WP6: Potential use of some of the generated new exposure data from SS/NTS/EDA for mixture modelling

WP7: Definition of specific requirements for SS/NTS/EDA data management (retrospective use, repository...)

WP8: Potential use of some of the generated new exposure data from SS/NTS/EDA for EWS

WP9: Contribution to harmonised QA/QC and training for SS/NTS/EDA approaches

Links outside PARC

Continuity with regard to HBM4EU WP16 related activities that has developed bases of harmonisation and development for SS and NTS but without considering the related innovative sampling approaches considered in the present project.

Key PARC Deliverables and Milestones to which the project contributes

D.4.5: 2nd Proof-of-concept illustrating the usefulness of innovative (self-)sampling combined with integrated suspect/NTS/EDA approaches as a contribution to EWS and risk assessment for human monitoring (M48).

Partners List:

INRAE (FR), EHESP (FR), CEA (FR), VUA (NL), KUM (DE), UNIVIE (AT), UFZ (DE), WR (NL), JSI (SI), MUI (AT), UAntwerpen (BE), UGR (SP), AU (DK), UniLU (LU), LNS (LU), UNIADBN (UK), MU (CZ), ISPV (SP), VSCHT (CZ), BPI (GR), VITO (BE), CSIC (SP), ISCII (SP), ISS (SP), SU (SE), AUTH (GR)

Schedule:

Starting date: 01/05/2022 (M1)

Expected ending date: 30/04/2026 (M48)

Costs

Expected PM for the fourth year of the project: 104 PM

Expected ODC for the fourth year of the project: 193 488 €

P4.3.2.b_Y2_H02-Occupational exposure_INRS

Project Title	Proof-of-concept of innovative sampling and HRMS based / EDA screening methods for exploring occupational exposure to chemicals of emerging concern.		
Project Acronym (15 letters max)	Occupational exposure		
Project Manager	Sophie Ndaw, sophie.ndaw@inrs.fr	INRS	FR
	Radu Duca, radu.duca@lns.etat.lu	LNS	Lux
Deputy Project manager	Baninia Habchi, baninia.habchi@inrs.fr	INRS	FR
	Ogier Hanser, ogier.hanser@inrs.fr		
	Emilie Hardy, emilie.hardy@lns.etat.lu	LNS	Lux
Expected starting date	13	Expected duration	48
PARC (Month number)			
PARC Workpackage number	4	PARC Task/Activity /Sub-activity:	4.3.2
Project Id	P4.3.2.b_Y2_H02-Occupational exposure_INRS		

Status: Implementation

Summary of the project:

In the workplace, most workers are co-exposed to various chemicals at the same time and same place. More, the EC adopted a new Circular Economy Action Plan where Europe moves towards a more circular economy. The reuse and recycling of materials could result in an increase of exposure of workers involved in different steps of the waste processing chain. Innovative approaches are needed for better characterizing the nature and effects of those multiple exposure on workers' health since the conventional targeted analysis

are limited to *a priori* known biomarkers. SS/NTS enabling the detection of biomarkers of exposures and effects and coupled to new sampling methods such as DBS and SWB represent promising new options and solutions in this context. However, these approaches are not yet widely applied in the field of human exposure assessment and biomonitoring. Both improvement and harmonization are needed before implementing these novel approaches in EU to support policy and prevention actors. The aim of this project is to develop and conduct a proof-of-concept permitting to assess the performances, and illustrate the usefulness, of those innovative methods, as complementary to conventional and targeted approaches, for particular assessment of occupational exposure.

Main expected outputs of the project:

- Characterization of advantages/limitations of innovative approaches compared to conventional ones
- Validation of innovative approaches by using selected case studies
- Scientifically and regulatory supported prioritisation of some of them for short term implementation
- Roadmap for further developments/improvements needed for long-term implementation
- Identification of relevant markers/matrices combinations for occupational exposure assessment
- Contributing to document real life mixtures associated to occupational chemical exposure, for waste management and health care sectors
- Prioritization of further targeted developments focused on particular exposure markers evidenced
- Contribution to feed the developed EWSs through an established link between tasks 4.3 and 8.2.

Outcomes and impacts expected on end-users and stakeholders:

The results of the survey should benefit to different stakeholders:

- consolidated bases for implementing a set of innovative sampling and exposure measurement approaches, which will benefit to a number of end-users including laboratories (capacity building), as well as actors aiming to build and use EWSs for which the expected new exposure data generation capabilities will represent a significant input;
- For workers, employers, occupational hygienists and occupational physicians: better understanding and increased awareness of the potential health risk of emerging chemicals exposures, further recommendations for RM.
- The scientific community and primarily other partners in PARC: potential added value of HBM approach as input for further RA and HIA related mainly to emerging chemicals of concerned or unknown potential process related occurring chemicals.
- On a longer term, policy makers, EU and national regulators, EU Agencies (EU OSHA): deriving further regulation and guidance, evaluating the efficiency of current regulations.

Key words: Biomonitoring, occupational exposure, innovative methods, dried blood spots (DBS), silicone wristbands (SWB), suspect screening, non-targeted screening, exposures and effect biomarkers, real-life mixtures, emerging chemicals

Link to the PARC DoA:

The project responds to the PARC OOs OO2, OO3, OO5, OO6, OO7, OO8, OO11 and OO13.

The main objectives of this project consist of developing a proof-of-concept for illustrating the suitability of innovative methodological approaches such as SS/NTS and innovative sampling methods for occupational exposure assessment in Europe. Furthermore, this project contributes and improves the chemical RA by studying the samples collected under Occupational survey projects (T4.1.1.4): P4.1.1.4.d_Y1_OccupWaste_ENSP-TTL and P4.1.1.4.c_Y1_HealthcareSurvey_TTL_SRU including regulated compounds, banned compounds and new/emerging compounds, potentially formed along the production process. In addition, a new network of laboratories and research centers will be developed and coordinated by the 15 European institutions participating in this project and each partner will be involved in the respective NHs.

Links within PARC (WPs/Tasks/Activities/Projects):

WP4: 4.1.1/T4.1.1.5 occupational surveys:

- Identification of the partners involved in the sample collection

- Identification of suitable case studies to test and validate the innovative sampling methods from T4.3_H02
- Identification of cohorts required for the proposed project (type, volume, number, collection method, etc.)
- Organisation and management of the sampling collection in collaboration with task 4.3.
- QA/QC consolidation between tasks 4.3 and 4.1 through the establishment of a specific working group in charge of evaluating advantages / limitations, necessary caution before use and implementation etc...
- Preliminary test / possible improvement before applying to real samples.
- Contribution to the evaluation of innovative sampling methods and SS/NTS approaches based on the comparison with exposure markers obtained with conventional targeted methods

4.3.1. Transversal:

- 4.3/4.3.1/P4.3.1.a_Y1_T01_Concept Paper_MU: Alignment of objectives / purposes of innovative sampling approaches
- 4.3/4.3.1/P4.3.1.b_Y1_T02_QA/QC Issues_WR: Ensure quality of the generated data
- 4.3/4.3.1/P4.3.1.d_Y1_T04_Data Processing Workflow_EHESP: Support annotation of generated data
- 4.3.2. Human based proof-of-concept
- 4.3/4.3.2/P4.3.2.a_Y1_H01_Perinatal exposure_INRAE: Mutualized resources / harmonization
- 4.3/4.3.2/P4.3.2.c_Y3_H03_Other complementary studies_JSI: Mutualized resources / harmonization

WP6: Potential use of the generated new exposure data from innovative sampling approaches coupled to SS/NTS for exposure assessment in regulatory RA

WP7: Definition of specific requirements for innovative sampling approaches coupled to SS/NTS/EDA data management (retrospective use, repository...)

WP8: Potential use of the generated new exposure data from innovative sampling approaches coupled to SS/NTS for EWSs

WP9: Contribution to harmonised QA/QC and training for innovative sampling approaches coupled to SS/NTS approaches

Links outside PARC:

- HBM4EU legacy: WP8 of the HBM4EU project conducted studies on occupational exposure among chromate workers, e-waste workers and diisocyanate-involved workers. In those studies, multiple occupational exposures have been shown, which highlighted the need of novel methods to assess poly-exposures. The present project is aiming to capitalize on those HBM4EU results to expand its scope. Various exposome research projects (amongst which “Exposome project for health and occupational research” (EPHOR)) develop innovative sampling approaches for occupational exposure assessment that are very relevant for this task.

- EU-OSHA funded project aiming to provide a practical guidance on preventing and reducing occupational exposure to HMPs, including cytotoxic drugs

Key PARC Deliverables (or Additional Deliverables) and Milestones to which the project contributes

D.4.10. 3rd Proof-of-concept assessing the usefulness of innovative (self-) sampling combined with integrated suspect/NTS/EDA approaches (M60)

Partners list: INRS (FR), LNS (LU), WULS-SGGW (PL), INRAE (FR), MUI (AT), UGR (SP), STAMI (NO), TNO (NL), UAntwerpen (BE), TTL (FI), MU (CZ), JSI (SI), WR (NL), BPI (GR), AUTH (GR)

Schedule:

Starting date: 01/05/2023 (M13)

Expected ending date: 30/04/2027 (M60)

Costs

Expected PM for the third year of the project: 19 PM

Expected ODC for the third year of the project: 123 025 €

P4.3.2.c_Y3_H03-Complementary developments_JSI-UAntwerpen

Project Title	Complementary developments regarding the application of HRMS based / EDA screening methods on human samples		
Project Acronym (15 letters max)	H03_Complementary developments		
Project Manager	Tina Kosjek tina.kosjek@ijs.si	JSI	SI
Deputy Project manager	Alexander van Nuijs alexander.vannuijs@uantwerpen.be	UAntwerpen	BE
Expected starting date PARC (Month number)	M25	Expected duration (months)	48
PARC Workpackage number	WP4	PARC Task/Activity/Sub-activity:	4.3.2
Project Id	P4.3.2.c_Y3_H03-Complementary developments_JSI		

Status: Implementation

Summary of the project

Accurately capturing the intricacies of real-life human chemical exposure demands the introduction of novel conceptual frameworks (e.g. Exposome concept) and innovative methodological approaches (e.g. alternatives matrices, new instrumental techniques, SS, NTS, EDA). However, before a widescale implementation of these novel approaches within human cohorts, they still require a consolidated development and harmonization process, as well as a thorough performance assessment including the design of sampling, sample treatment, and subsequent generation and analysis of exposure data. A number of issues related to the challenges and application of those innovative methods to human samples are covered by already running Task 4.3 H01 and H02 projects, respectively focused on perinatal and occupational exposure. However, the extent of methodological aspects to be investigated and not yet considered in the previous projects, as well as a wish of direct connection between this task 4.3 component of the PARC project and the aligned studies developed within task 4.1, motivated the elaboration of the present additional project.

Policy-driven demand for more effective preventive measures calls for monitoring exposure trends and expanding our understanding of the chemical exposome, including broadening compound coverage and relating biomarkers to matrices. The justification for this expanded effort lies in the inherent limitations of current regulatory frameworks to keep pace with the dynamic landscape of the chemical space. The ever-growing pool of emerging contaminants introduces potential hazards that may go unnoticed within the confines of traditional monitoring approaches. By proactively contributing to the recognition of early warning signals, this project plays an important role in identifying chemical hazards that may otherwise escape detection. This not only supplements existing frameworks but also contributes to the continual evolution of regulatory practices. The project's broader compound coverage and correlation of biomarkers to matrices provide nuanced insights beyond what current sources offer. In the long term, our efforts aim to foster a more adaptable and responsive regulatory environment, ultimately advancing the overarching goal of ensuring the safe use of chemicals in a dynamically changing landscape. In this context, alternative matrices suited for non-invasive sampling and covering different detection windows offer the potential. Additionally, SS/NTS approaches represent a cutting-edge trend that promises simultaneous capturing of substances from different classes, including persistent and nonpersistent organic CEC. Globally, the support to policy rationale of the present project relies to the need for accelerating and improving the practical implementation of SS/NTS/EDA as a contribution to substance prioritization and EWS. The SS/NTS/EDA methodologies are complementary screening techniques that can be employed in various combinations,

either simultaneously or sequentially, based on the capabilities and resources of individual laboratories. They collectively represent Tier 1 in exposure assessment that informs subsequent targeted analyses, aiding in RA and management strategies.

In this view, the primary project objective is to evaluate the effectiveness of complementary methodological strategies not yet covered in the previous task 4.3 projects, including orthogonal liquid chromatography separation systems (e.g. Hydrophilic interaction chromatography (HILIC) adapted to several highly polar compounds/metabolites (Nuclear magnetic resonance (NMR) is not suited due to insufficient limit of detection (LOD)), alternative sample preparation protocols directly impacting the analytical results (e.g. deconjugation, phospholipid removal), and the use of alternative non-invasive matrices (e.g. hair or saliva), finally leading to potential additional SOPs of interest. Another goal is to build on the key findings and lessons learned from PARC T4.3 cross-cutting projects, especially those related to quality assurance, quality control (QA/QC) and data processing challenges. We aim to use these insights as a practical way to demonstrate their value by applying them to new sets of samples. To that end, a direct link will be established to PARC task 4.1 aligned studies to source a set of supporting samples already planned to be analysed through conventional targeted methods. This proposed add-on aims at improving the range of detected compounds in the same samples (blood, urine) through HRMS-based profiling methods.

Main expected outputs of the project:

- Comprehensive synthesis of existing knowledge regarding innovative methodological approaches, including sampling (hair and saliva), sample preparation (deconjugation, phospholipid removal), and instrumental analysis (HILIC). By highlighting the known advantages and limitations of these innovative approaches, we aim to demonstrate their potential in supplementing the traditional chemical monitoring methods. This synthesis is particularly geared toward informing policy targets and aiding in the identification of substances that demand specific attention from regulatory authorities, aligning with PARC's overarching science-to-policy objectives.
- Specific methodological developments and assessment activities to address the gaps in knowledge.
- Provide recommendations that confirm their use in relevant application areas and promote the harmonized implementation of these techniques.
- Development of a decision-ready proposal focusing on samples from T4.1 aligned studies to be used as a proof-of-concept and corresponding budget refinement
- Proof-of-concept illustrating the usefulness of these complementary approaches by using selected case studies supported by human samples originated from T4.1 aligned studies.
- Identification of relevant markers and matrices for more comprehensive exposure assessment
- Scientifically and regulatory supported prioritisation of selected complementary approaches for short-term implementation. The prioritization will be achieved through compiling the synthesis of existing knowledge and the results from the “Initial investigations” activity assessing alternative matrices, complementary sample preparations, and HILIC separation. Then, the most suitable complementary approach or matrix will be selected based on the criteria such as number, complementarity of chemical space or detection window, and the potential hazard of additional biomarkers of exposure to be identified. Documented SOPs built on the achieved methodological work, aiming at facilitating the implementation of those selected and harmonized protocols for SS/NTS/EDA applied to human samples in European laboratories
- Contribution to feed the EWSs under development through an established link between tasks 4.3 and 8.2

Outcomes and impacts expected on end-users and stakeholders:

- The project acts towards supporting method harmonization, enhancing networking, interlinking and interdisciplinarity, particularly between partners of PARC and towards capacity building in the scientific community.
- Expected new and complementary exposure data will present an input to EWSs.

- Improved understanding and increased awareness of the potential health risk deriving from the exposure to the CEC and further recommendations for RM.
- Enhanced possibility for large-scale HBM using non-invasive sampling methods as well as for monitoring of particularly vulnerable subpopulations such as neonates, toddlers and elderly.
- Potential added value of HBM approach as input for further RA and HIA.
- Policy makers, EU and national regulators, EU agencies will be able to derive further regulation and guidance, evaluating the efficiency of current regulations.
- Broadened compound coverage and improved ability to monitor trends in exposure will lead to a better understanding of chemical exposome and leverage the definition of more efficient prevention measures.

Key words: Biological samples, biomarkers, human biomonitoring (HBM), suspect screening (SS), non-targeted screening (NTS), effect-directed analysis (EDA), real-life mixtures, emerging chemicals, high resolution mass spectrometry, human exposure, aligned studies, harmonisation, human relevance, regulatory relevance, innovative methods, Quality Assurance / Quality Control (QA/QC)

Link to the PARC DoA:

The project respond to the PARC OOs OO8, OO9 and OO11.

The project addresses the need for improved chemical safety and RA by overcoming limitations in conventional methods. Leveraging innovative tools, it identifies substances requiring attention from regulatory authorities, aiming for harmonized implementation in large-scale HBM contributing to OO8. Additionally, it showcases practical applications from PARC T4.3 projects, emphasizing QA/QC and data processing, thereby contributing to standardization and validation processes for innovative RA approaches (OO9). With 23 partners, the project strengthens existing collaborations and forges new ones, collectively advancing chemical safety, enriching RA methodologies, and supporting regulatory decision-making for public health (OO11).

Links within PARC (WPs/Tasks/Activities/Projects):

WP4:

4.1: Pro/con expert review and analysis, Collaboration established and ongoing from the beginning, i.e. from the initial project co-building phase, Capitalizing on biobanked samples of hair or saliva from 4.1 aligned studies, QAQC consolidation.

4.3/4.3.1/P4.3.1.a_Y1_T01_Concept Paper_MU: Alignment of objectives / purposes of SS/NTS/EDA

4.3/4.3.1/P4.3.1.b_Y1_T02_QA/QC Issues_WR: Ensure quality of the generated data

4.3/4.3.1/P4.3.1.c_Y1_T03_Early Warning System_SLU: Ensure useful output for EWS

4.3/4.3.1/P4.3.1.d_Y1_T04_Data Processing Workflow_EHESP: Support annotation of generated data

4.3/4.3.2/P4.3.2.a_Y1_H01_Perinatal exposure_INRAE: Lessons learned / harmonization of QAQC, reporting, annotation workflow / complementarity of approaches

4.3/4.3.2/P4.3.2.b_Y2_H02_Occupational exposure_INRS: Lessons learned / harmonization of QAQC, reporting, annotation workflow / complementarity of approaches

WP6: Potential use of some of the generated new exposure data from SS/NTS/EDA for mixture modelling

WP7: Definition of specific requirements for SS/NTS/EDA data management (retrospective use, repository...)

WP8: Potential use of some of the generated new exposure data from SS/NTS/EDA for EWS

WP9: Contribution to harmonised QA/QC and training for SS/NTS/EDA approaches

Links outside PARC:

Continuity with regard to HBM4EU WP16 related activities that has provided a basis of harmonization and development for SS/NTS but without considering the complementary developments of the present project.

Key PARC Deliverables (or Additional Deliverables) and Milestones to which the project contributes

AD4.13: Proof-of-concept on the application of the complementary approaches/matrices to real samples from HBM surveys (M70)

Partners List:

Leads: JSI (SI), UAntwerpen (BE), Participants: AUTH (GR), BPI (GR), CEA (FR), IISPV (ES), ISCIII (ES), ISS (IT), LNS (LU), MU (CZ), MUI (AT), SU (SE), UFZ (DE), VITO (BE), VSCHT (CZ), VUA (NL), WR (NL), WULS (PL), INRAE (FR), CNRS (FR), CSIC (ES), INRS (FR), AU (DK)

Schedule:

Starting date: 01/05/2024 (M25)
 Expected ending date: 30/04/2028 (M72)

Costs

Expected PM for the second year of the project: 51 PM
 Expected ODC for the second year of the project : 148 054 €

A4.3.3 Environment samples based proof-of-concepts – 2 PROJECTS

P4.3.3.a_Y1_EO1-Wastewater based epidemiology_UFZ-UBATH

Project Title	Mining chemical information from wastewater treatment plants for I. human community (<i>wastewater fingerprinting for community wide human exposure assessment</i>) and II. environmental exposure assessment (<i>screening of wastewater treatment plant effluents to assess the release of Chemicals of Emerging Concern into the water cycle</i>).		
Project Acronym (15 letters max)	Wastewater based epidemiology		
Project Manager	Werner Brack werner.brack@ufz.de	UFZ	DE
Deputy Project manager	Barbara Kasprzyk-Hordern bkh20@bath.ac.uk	UBATH	UK
Expected starting date PARC (Month number)	1	Expected duration	48*
PARC Workpackage number	4	PARC Task/Activity/S ub-activity:	4.3.3
Project Id	P4.3.3.a_Y1_EO1-Wastewater-based epidemiology_UFZ-UBATH		

*The project has been extended from M36 to M48

Status: Implementation

Summary of the project

Wastewater can serve as a source of information with respect to human exposure, by measuring specific human metabolites in raw sewage (wastewater-based epidemiology – WBE). WWTPs are a main source for complex mixtures of chemicals in surface water, impacting the environment and human health (e.g., via drinking water). This project addresses both human and environmental exposure, focusing on (i) wastewater fingerprinting for community wide human exposure assessment and (ii) on screening of WWTP effluents to assess the release of CECs into the water cycle. The development of WBE as well as the screening of effluents using SS/NTS approaches and EDA will deliver innovative methods for community wide human exposure assessment, environmental exposure assessment and the identification of CECs of (eco-)toxicological concern. The European-scale monitoring data generated by these methods as well as a re-evaluation of existing data will greatly improve our knowledge on CECs in wastewater and their primary sources as a basis for the revision of the Urban Waste Water Treatment Directive with regard to reducing CEC emissions, providing candidate compounds and information on their sources for priority/river-basin-specific chemicals in the context of the WFD, and providing information on chemical mixtures for the revision of REACH with regard to environmental mixture concerns.

Main expected outputs of the project

- Innovative screening / targeted methods for community-wide chemical exposure assessment by WBE
- Innovative screening methods and workflows for environmental exposure assessment of wastewater
- Europe-wide human community exposure patterns via targeted and non-targeted WBE
- Wastewater and source patterns representing typical emission scenarios in Europe
- Prioritisation of compounds of concern emitted with wastewater for further assessment

Outcomes and impacts expected for end-users and stakeholders

We will develop innovative analytical approaches that will define future approaches to exposure studies, both in the context of environmental and public health. This project is potentially transformative for several stakeholder groups including, regulatory sectors (e.g. water quality/control authorities) and public health agencies.

Key words

wastewater, wastewater-based epidemiology, suspect and nontarget screening, compound prioritization, community exposure assessment, mixture risk drivers, effect-directed analysis

Link to the PARC DoA

The project responds to the PARC OOs OO5, OO8, OO10, OO12, OO9 and OO11.

The project provides human exposure (via WBE), environmental and multisource monitoring data for regulatory purposes from the mining of existing HRMS-based datasets and Pan-European monitoring studies (OO8, OO10). The project enhances the collaboration between the partners conducting WBE and wastewater monitoring through consolidated and harmonised analytical and data processing workflows (OO11). Developing a proof-of-concept for illustrating the capacities of SS/NTS/EDA approaches in the particular case of environmental monitoring as an innovative approach feeding into regulatory RA (OO12, OO9).

Links within PARC (WPs/Tasks/Activities/Projects)

The proposed project will be closely linked to Tasks 4.1 (Human exposure assessment) and 4.2 (Environmental and multisource monitoring) especially P4.2.c_Y3_(Human exposure_INERIS_AU Project Title, Human exposure to organic contaminants from non-food environmental sources) providing innovative methods and tools for monitoring and surveys supporting these tasks. This project will inform on toxicity data gaps of concern based on realistic human and environmental exposure (Task 5.1) and will closely collaborate with Task 5.2 on innovative tools for toxicity testing, filtering Task 5.2 tools for methods useful for EDA. The project will provide valuable measured human and environmental exposure information as input to Task 6.2. The project will also feed in directly into Task 8.2 aiming at the establishment of an EWS.

Links outside PARC

Within the EU Horizon 2020 Cooperation in Science and Technology (COST) action “Supporting Consumer Co-Ownership in Renewable Energies” (SCORE) (www.score-cost.eu), activities in the field of WBE are initiated and coordinated. While the main focus was on illicit drugs, the focus is shifting towards current, in-use compounds to investigate patterns of factors related to lifestyle, disease and environment. Hydra-EWS: Marie Curie initiative led by University of Bath (UBAH), in which connection with task 4.3 is already made, possibly providing synergy. European Pollutant Release and Transfer Register (E-PRTR) programme (<https://industry.eea.europa.eu/#/home>) VANDALF: National Danish project aiming to develop and implement a RA platform based on NTS and effect-based methods to identify CECs in wastewater, will be closely linked through the involvement of the coordinator UPCH. NORMAN network: Strong collaboration and exchange, use of and exchange with NORMAN database system.

Key PARC Deliverables and Milestones to which the project contributes

D4.2 1st Proof-of-concept assessing the usefulness of innovative (self-)sampling combined with integrated suspect/NTS/EDA approaches (new delivery date M48)

Partners List: UFZ (DE), UBATH (UK), MUI (AT), UCPH (DK), EAWAG (CH), IRFM (IT), ORU-

MTM (SE), SLU (SE), UAntwerpen (BE), JSI (SI), KWR (NL), UniLU (LU), VUA (NL), ISS (SP), INERIS (FR), BfG (DE), UL-FFA (SI), BRGM (FR), WULS-SGGW (PL), JU (CZ), MU (CZ), INRAE (FR), OFB (FR), UL (PL), VITO (BE)

Schedule:

Starting date: 01/05/2022 (M1)

Expected ending date: 30/04/2026 (M48)

Costs

Expected PM for the fourth year of the project: 9 PM

Expected ODC for the fourth year of the project: 1 625 €

P4.3.3.b_Y2_EO2-Sentinel animals_ONIRIS

Project Title	Proof-of-concept of innovative sampling and HRMS based / EDA screening methods for exploring chemicals of emerging concern in sentinel animal species		
Project Acronym (15 letters max)	Sentinel animals		
Project Manager	Ronan CARIOU ronan.cariou@oniris-nantes.fr	ONIRIS	FR
Deputy Project manager	Gaud DERVILLY gaud.dervilly@oniris-nantes.fr	ONIRIS	FR
Expected starting date PARC (Month number)	13	Expected duration	48
PARC Workpackage number	P4	PARC Task/Activity/Sub-activity:	4.3.3
Project Id	P4.3.3.b_Y2_EO2-Sentinel animals_ONIRIS		

Status: Implementation

Summary of the project:

Capturing the complex real chemical exposure of human and/or in the environment requires new conceptual frameworks and innovative methodological approaches: SS/NTS based on HRMS coupled to EDA are a promising trend developed within PARC T4.3 in that purpose. Within the One Health concept, animal sentinel species can serve as a source of useful information with respect to both human exposure to chemical hazards through the food chain and ecotoxicological considerations related to the environment. Species with bioaccumulation capacities especially appears of interest for SS/NTS screening of chemicals based on higher concentration levels than those observed in human biological matrices. Selected species will cover marine and terrestrial environments. Candidate species are marine mammals, molluscs, gulls, pigeons, raptors and bees. The sample sourcing of such sentinel species also stands as less laborious compared to human matrices, especially if already available in a specimen bank. The aim of this project is to develop and conduct a proof-of-concept permitting to assess then relevance of animal sentinel species upon applying those innovative methods, as complementary to conventional and targeted approaches. It will feed the EWS on CEC, the end-users being the food and environment policy makers.

Main expected outputs of the project:

- Documented advantages/limitations of innovative approaches compared to conventional ones
- Scientifically supported prioritisation of some animal species for short term implementation
- Paved way for further developments/improvements needed for long term implementation
- Documentation of real-life mixtures associated to environmental health and human food chain

- Prioritization of further targeted developments focused on particular exposure markers evidenced
- Contribution to feed EWS through an established link between tasks 4.3 and 8.2
- General food law and environment policy makers aware of the main findings

Outcomes and impacts expected on end-users and stakeholders:

The proposed project appears as a pre-required methodological development activity, expected to provide eventually a list of exposure markers pinpointing potential CEC. This perspective should benefit a number of end-users including laboratories aiming to implement those new analytical approaches (capacity building), as well as actors aiming to build and use EWSs for which the expected new exposure data generation capabilities will represent a significant input.

Policies related to the human food chain are a first target. It includes the general food law (Reg 178/2002), as well as the recently revised official control regulation (Reg 2017/625) and other regulations for business operators (Reg183/2005 Reg 852/2004, Reg 853/2004). For example, EFSA recently noted in its opinion on PFASs (doi: 10.2903/j.efsa.2020.6223) that a representative set of occurrence data are still lacking for many foods and, therefore, recommended to gather such data for a wide range PFASs in a broad range of widely consumed foods. Consequently, it is advised in the Commission Recommendation 2022/1431 that Member States should also consider testing for the presence in food of emerging PFASs, in addition to the 4+18 cited.

Policies related to the environmental aspects are another target. It includes the Marine Strategy Framework Directive (Dir 2008/56/EC) in which Qualitative descriptors for determining good environmental status n°8 and n°9 deal with contaminants giving rise to pollution or concern for human consumption. Such approach is also about to be extended to terrestrial environments according to a current proposal for a Nature Restoration Law.

Key words:

Sentinel species, human food chain, environmental health, innovative methods, suspect screening, non-targeted screening, effect-directed analysis, real-life mixtures, emerging chemicals

Link to the PARC DoA:

The project responds to the PARC OOs OO3, OO5, OO7, OO8 and OO12.

Conventional sampling and targeted quantitative analytical methods are already available to support environmental, food and human monitoring, RA/RM decisions. However, these approaches sometimes suffer from a lack of sensitivity to characterize lowest exposed populations, face some limitations for large-scale implementation, and only capture a limited number of *a priori* known and selected markers of exposure. Developing a proof-of-concept for illustrating the capacities of SS/NTS/EDA approaches in the particular case of sentinel animal species is directly connected to task 4.3 DoA, in particular with regard to fostering collaboration of environmental, food safety and HBM communities.

Links within PARC (WPs/Tasks/Activities/Projects) (between 2-8 lines):

WP4:

4.1: Check Human internal exposure to highlighted exposure markers

4.2/4.2.2/P4.2.a_Y1_ENVMonitoringPilotSurvey_INERIS_AU: Mutualized resources

4.3/4.3.1/P4.3.1.a_Y1_T01_Concept Paper_MU: Alignment of objectives / purposes of SS/NTS/EDA

4.3/4.3.1/P4.3.1.b_Y1_T02_QA/QC Issues_WR: Ensure quality of the generated data

4.3/4.3.1/P4.3.1.c_Y1_T03_Early Warning System_SLU: Ensure useful output for EWS

4.3/4.3.1/P4.3.1.d_Y1_T04_Data Processing Workflow_EHESP: Support annotation of generated data

WP6: Potential use of some of the generated new exposure data from SS/NTS/EDA for mixture modelling

WP7: Definition of specific requirements for SS/NTS/EDA data management (retrospective use, repository...)

WP8: Potential use of some of the generated new exposure data from SS/NTS/EDA for EWS

Links outside PARC:

Tight connexions with the NORMAN network and LIFE APEX consortium for taking advantage of existing

tools developed for monitoring the environment and top food chain biota, respectively. It includes sample handling, QA/QC procedures and highly visible data repositories. There will be discussion with biodiversa + on possible collaboration.

Key PARC Deliverables (or Additional Deliverables) and Milestones to which the project contributes
 D4.14. Final report on the application of new exposure assessment approaches (*i.e.* from sampling to data interpretation) to support regulatory needs (*i.e.* lessons learnt and conclusions/perspective for sustainable follow-up) (M81).

Partners list: ONIRIS (FR), ANSES (FR), AU (DK), BfR (DE), EAWAG (CH), CSIC (SP), INRAE (FR), JSI (SI), JU (CZ), OFB (FR), ORU-MTM (SE), SU (SE), UFZ (DE), UG-AT (AT), VUA (NL).

Schedule:

Starting date: 01/05/2023 (M13)

Expected ending date: 30/04/2027 (M60)

Costs

Expected PM for the third year of the project : 36 PM

Expected ODC for the third year of the project : 74 479 €

A4.3.4 Food samples based proof-of-concepts – 1 PROJECT

P4.3.4.a_Y2_F02- Food items exposure _ANSES

Project Title	Complementary developments regarding the application of HRMS based/EDA screening methods on food samples		
Project Acronym (15 letters max)	F02-Food items exposure		
Project Manager	Julien Parinet julien.parinet@anses.fr	ANSES	France
Deputy Project manager	Sophie Mompelat sophie.mompelat@anses.fr	ANSES	France
Expected starting date PARC (Month number)	13	Expected duration	36
PARC Workpackage number	4	PARC Task/Activity/Sub-activity:	4.3.4
Project Id	P4.3.4.a_Y2_F02- Food items exposure _ANSES		

Status: Implementation

Summary of the project:

Innovative approaches such as SS/NTS based on HRMS, and EDA combined with HRMS, represent a revolution in the field of monitoring chemicals present or potentially present in food, allowing to cover a much larger chemical range than the approaches used until now (low resolution) in the regulatory field. However, the application of these innovative approaches in food is still limited. In addition, the performances of SS/NTS/EDA approaches need to be better assessed in order to be adapted to a regulatory context and harmonisation. This project aims to develop and to qualitatively and quantitatively compare various analytical strategies and workflows (from food sample preparation to data acquisition and data processing) in order to identify their complementarities or overlap in terms of captured exposure markers (known, emerging and unknown chemicals) in food. A preliminary step will consist in the selection of specific food items related to particular risk situations for both general and particularly vulnerable populations (*e.g.* infant food), as highlighted by EFSA as a major issue for RA. The aim of this project is to develop and conduct a proof-of-concept permitting to assess the relevance of the implementation of such

developed screening methods as part of the monitoring and control plans. This would allow to identify original contaminant mixtures from field data. The longitudinal follow-up of the data generated by these means would also allow highlighting both emergences (unregulated substances) and misuses (regulated substances). It will feed and help to structure the EWS on CEC, the end-users being the food policy makers.

Main expected outputs of the project:

- Characterization of advantages/limitations of innovative approaches compared to conventional ones through the evaluation of the chemical coverage potential of different SS/NTS/EDA methods
- Qualitative and quantitative assessment of the performances of the developed SS/NTS/EDA methods in order to implement one or more methods that will cover the largest possible chemical range and thus limit the failure to detect hazardous substances potentially present in a sample
- Definition of the needs for further developments/improvements for long-term implementation
- Generation of FAIR data to support the monitoring of real-life mixtures, and especially to support the exposure assessment of vulnerable population groups (*e.g.* children)
- Contribution to feed EWS through an established link between tasks 4.3 and 8.2
- Awareness of general food law policy makers regarding key findings of the project and the data generated

Outcomes and impacts expected on end-users and stakeholders:

By providing a clearer picture of the complementarity and performances of the methods compared in this project, the project should open the door to the integration of new innovative methods and tools needed for a more exhaustive monitoring for end-users, including the laboratories in charge of implementing control methods. Actors from the EWSs will also benefit from the innovative methods capabilities to generate external exposure data. The production of field data through the application of these new tools will allow risk assessors and risk managers to have a broader view of the real-life chemical mixtures to which consumers are exposed. This will provide scientific data for guiding further toxicological studies and hence support the paradigm shift in RA of these chemical mixtures.

Policies related to the human food chain are a first target. It includes the general food law (Reg 178/2002), and official control regulation (Reg 2017/625) as well as specific food laws such as Regulation (EC) No 1881/2006, Regulation (EC) No 396/2005, Regulation (EC) No 1935/2004.

Key words:

Monitoring, food, innovative methods, suspect screening, non-targeted screening, effect-directed analysis, real-life mixtures, emerging chemicals

Link to the PARC DoA:

The project responds to the PARC OOs OO1, OO2, OO3, OO4, OO6, OO8, OO10, OO11 and OO13. Food monitoring is supported by the use of targeted analytical methods focusing on a selection of a relatively limited number of chemicals, compared to the number and diversity of chemicals constantly appearing on the market. The development of new and innovative analytical approaches is needed to support and renew the monitoring of the actual complex chemical mixtures in food to which consumers are exposed. The improvement and provision of new methods and tools is therefore a prerequisite to meet the need, formulated by European agencies (including EFSA) and in the EC Roadmap for the CSS, for a paradigm shift in exposure/RA and the establishment of an EWS. This project aims to contribute to the fulfilment of these needs as expressed in the PARC's objectives and DoA.

Links within PARC (WPs/Tasks/Activities/Projects):

WP4:

- 4.3/4.3.1/P4.3.1.a_Y1_T01_Concept Paper_MU: Alignment of objectives / purposes of SS/NTS/EDA
- 4.3/4.3.1/P4.3.1.b_Y1_T02_QA/QC Issues_WR: Ensure quality of the generated data
- 4.3/4.3.1/P4.3.1.c_Y1_T03_Early Warning System_SLU: Ensure useful output for EWS
- 4.3/4.3.1/P4.3.1.d_Y1_T04_Data Processing Workflow_EHESP: Support annotation of generated data
- 4.3/4.3.1/P4.3.2.b_Y2_E02_Sentinel animals_ONIRIS: Mutualized resources / harmonization

WP6: Potential use of some of the generated new exposure data from SS/NTS/EDA for mixture modelling

WP7: Definition of specific requirements for SS/NTS/EDA data management (retrospective use, repository...)

WP8: Potential use of some of the generated new exposure data from SS/NTS/EDA for EWS

WP9: Contribution to harmonised QA/QC and training for SS/NTS/EDA approaches

Links outside PARC:

In order to carry out the project, it would be preferable to capitalize on the projects already initiated by the partners in the margin of PARC. As such, there will be links between this task and French TDS3, ANR AlimOmic, PhD Emergexpo, PhDs and other projects conducted by the contributing partners.

Key PARC Deliverables (or Additional Deliverables) and Milestones to which the project contributes

D4.10. 3rd Proof-of-concept assessing the usefulness of innovative (self-) sampling combined with integrated suspect/NTS/EDA approaches (M60)

Partners list: ANSES (FR), INRAE (FR), VUA (NL), BfG (DE), CEA (FR), CNRS (FR), EAWAG (CH), CSIC (SP), ISS (IT), JSI (SI), MUI (AT), Oniris (FR), SLU (SE), UAntwerpen (BE), UL-FFA (SL), VSCHT (CZ), WR (NL), WULS (PL), EV-ILVO (BEL), GCSL (GR).

Schedule:

Starting date: 01/05/2023 (M13)

Expected ending date: 30/04/2026 (M48)

Costs

Expected PM for the third year of the project : 44 PM

Expected ODC for the third year of the project : 262 119 €

WP5 Hazard Assessment - 20 PROJECTS

The overall goal of WP5 is to overcome the major challenges in hazard assessment (HA) for human and environmental health. The specific objectives are:

- a) to close data gaps identified by key stakeholders;
- b) to improve the current hazard characterisation paradigm by establishing comprehensive testing strategies, thereby promoting the availability and applicability of NAMs in RA;
- c) to contribute to the improvement of mechanistic understanding of toxicity by analysing all available data and applying systems toxicology approaches and taking into account AOPs and to improve modelling approaches such as PBPK modelling. The work envisaged is divided into three tasks: T5.1, T5.2 and T5.3

Fig 7: WP5 contribution: Hazard assessment

T5.1 Toxicity testing addressing data gaps of concern 6 PROJECTS

This task aims to investigate and close existing data gaps through toxicity testing. The following groups of substances have been selected for the first round of testing: natural toxins, in particular the mycotoxins enniatins and those derived from *Alternaria* -their presence in food products is of concern-, as well as alternatives to Bisphenol A (BPA). Activities on toxins will address existing data gaps left open by regulatory data requirements, such as toxicokinetics data or comprehensive studies like the Extended One-Generation Reproductive Toxicity study (OECD 2018a). The latter study is also envisaged for other groups of substances of concern, which may include synthetic contaminants such as BPA alternatives/analogues not assessed by industry for authorisation or PFAS (per- and polyfluoroalkyl substances).

A5.1.1 Closing data gaps of concern for human health – 4 PROJECTS

P5.1.1.a_Y1_Toxins_BfR_UNIVIE

Project Title	Hazard identification and hazard characterisation of the mycotoxins enniatins and <i>Alternaria</i> toxins in order to close data gaps and improve risk assessment for human health		
Project Acronym (15 letters max)	Toxins		
Project Manager	Doris Marko doris.marko@univie.ac.at	UNIVIE	Austria
Project manager	Anne-Cathrin Behr	BfR	Germany

Anne-Cathrin.Behr@bfr.bund.de			
Expected starting date	1	Expected duration	48*
PARC (Month number)		PARC Task/Activity/Su b-activity:	5.1.1
PARC Workpackage number	5		
Project Id	P5.1.1.a_Y1_Toxins_BfR_UNIVIE		

*The project has been extended from M36 to M48

Status: Implementation

Summary of the project

Natural toxins have no manufacturer or supplier that is responsible for providing hazard data. Due to climate changes, the human exposure to natural toxins will likely increase and regulatory agencies have asked for more hazard data to improve the RA. This will ultimately result in recommendations on which natural toxins should be closely monitored in food feed and food products (Regulation (EC) No 1881/2006) in order to prevent adverse human health effects and setting maximum levels in food and feed based on knowledge.

For example, EFSA’s Contaminants in the Food Chain (CONTAM) Panel stated that there might be a health concern regarding chronic exposure to the natural toxin enniatins however there is insufficient data to assess the risk on chronic exposure⁴. Also, in the case of another natural toxins *Alternaria*, the scientific Panel was not able to conduct a systematic RA due to the lack of data. Additionally, for both enniatins and *Alternaria* toxins major data gaps were identified in toxicity data in a recent report from the Norwegian Scientific Committee for Food and the Environment (VKM et al., 2019)⁵.

All the above-mentioned underlines that further research, in terms of hazard identification and characterization, is required for both toxins: enniatins and *Alternaria*. This project initially focuses on these two emerging mycotoxins, with pressing regulatory need for more specific hazard data: i.e., enniatins and *Alternaria* toxins. Preferably, the studies will be performed according to OECD test guidelines (TGs), but in some cases no guidelines are available to address the specific endpoints and NAMs will be employed.

Main expected outputs of the project

The study will provide urgently needed *in vitro* data and identify critical toxicological effects of enniatins and *Alternaria* toxins. The data is necessary for subsequent *in vivo* studies which are required to establish HBGVs and to perform an appropriate RA and provide an efficient consumer protection.

Outcomes and impacts expected for end-users and stakeholders

This project will generate toxicological data (mainly focusing on hazard identification and characterization), aiming at incorporating it in RA performed in EU Agencies to set HBGVs that could therefore trigger the establishment of maximal levels in food in the context of Regulation (EC) No 1881/2006.

Key words: Natural toxins, *Alternaria* toxins, enniatins, mycotoxins, genotoxicity, endocrine effects, immunotoxicology, *in vitro*, *in silico*

Link to the PARC DoA

The project responds to the PARC OOs OO3, OO4, OO5, OO6, OO7, OO10 and OO11.

⁴ EFSA CONTAM, *Scientific Opinion on the risks to human and animal health related to the presence of beauvericin and enniatins in food and feed*, EFSA Journal, 2014, 12(8): 3802

⁵ VKM, Inger-Lise Steffensen, Christiane Kruse Fæste, Trine Husøy, Helle Katrine Knutsen, Gro Haarklou Mathisen, Robin Ørnstrud, Angelika Agdestein, Johanna Bodin, Edel Elvevoll, Dag O. Hessen, Merete Hofshagen, Åshild Krogdahl, Asbjørn Magne Nilsen, Trond Rafoss, Taran Skjerdal, Gaute Velle, Yngvild Wasteson, Gro-Ingunn Hemre, Vigdis Vandvik, Jan Alexander (2019). Ranking of substances for monitoring in foods, drinks and dietary supplements

- based on risk and knowledge gaps. Scientific Opinion of the Scientific Steering Committee of the Norwegian Scientific Committee for Food and Environment. VKM report 2019:13, ISBN: 978-82-8259-329-8, ISSN: 2535-4019. Available at <https://vkm.no/>

The project was designed in order to fill data gaps regarding the main representatives of emerging mycotoxins groups of enniatins and Alternaria toxins as defined by EFSA. The results are needed to identify critical toxicological effects for subsequent in vivo studies which are needed to establish HBGVs and to perform an appropriate RA and provide an efficient consumer protection. A working group was formed in which specialists on Alternaria and enniatins were combined with specialists in genotoxic, endocrine effects and immunotoxicological endpoints in order to design and deliver a program of studies. Review papers are in progress to summarise the existing data. Frequent meetings were held in order to share as much relevant information as possible. The long-term objective is to establish a European network of scientists interested and having experience in studying natural toxins.

Links within PARC (WPs/Tasks/Activities/Projects)

- WP4: Human exposure to the mycotoxins will be monitored in WP4. Analytical support in measuring the test items in test media is needed in order to support PBPK and in vitro - in vivo extrapolation (IVIVE) modelling.
- WP5: T5.2 and T5.3: The test items will also be studied in selected NAMs in T5.2 (Cf. project on immunotoxicology P5.2.1.d). Data that will be generated on kinetics and toxicity will be used in task 5.3 in order to improve and expand existing models (AOP and Physiologically Based Kinetic (PBK)).
- WP6: Hazard data generated will be used in WP6 to build Integrative Approaches for testing and Assessments (IATAs). Since most mycotoxins will be present in food and feed as mixtures, selected mixtures will also be tested. Relative Potency Factors could therefore be derived where possible and will provide important support for the assessments of risks of mixtures.
- WP7: T7.3: data and text mining, data provision, DMP

Links outside PARC

- HBM4EU
- EFSA- link to the Scientific Committee and Emerging Risks Unit European Food Safety Authority, Parma, Italy
- OECD project Using AOP to address combined exposures to chemicals with relevant effect-biomarkers. 2022-2025

Key PARC Deliverables and Milestones to which the project contributes

D5.1: 1st NAMs Report (delivered)

D5.3: 1st new AOPs Report (delivered)

D5.4: 1st Closing data Gaps Report (M36)

D5.11. 2nd closing data gaps report (M54)

Partners List:

BfR (Germany), UNIVIE (Austria), BPI (Greece), IBMT (Germany), IMR (Norway), INRS (France), ANSES (France), INSA (Portugal), NIB (Slovenia), NIPH (Norway), Sciensano (Belgium), STAMI (Norway), UNAV (Spain), NVI (Norway), WU-TOX (Netherlands), ISS (Italy), NVI (Norway)

Schedule:

Starting date: 01/05/2022 (M1)

Expected ending date: 30/04/2026 (M48)

Costs

Expected PM for the fourth year of the project: 87 PM

Expected ODC for the fourth year of the project: 170 401 €

P5.1.1.b_Y1_BPA_HumTox_BfR

Project Title	Hazard assessment of bisphenol A alternatives to close data gaps of concern for human health and improve their risk assessment		
Project Acronym (15 letters max)	BPA_HumTox		
Project Manager	Kiara Aiello Kiara.Aiello-Holden@BfR.Bund.de	BfR	Germany
Deputy Project manager	1. Endocrine Disruptors: Sabrina Tait and Catherine Viguié 2. Developmental Neurotoxicity: Sakina Mhaouty-Kodja 3. Immunotoxicity: Emanuela Corsini 4. Carcinogenicity: Maria Jaoa Silva 5. Metabolism: Daniel Zalko and Emma Di Consiglio	1. ISS INRAE 2. CNRS 3. UMIL 4. INSA 5. INRAE, ISS	Italy France France Italy Portugal France, Italy
Expected starting date PARC (Month number)	1	Expected duration	54*
PARC Workpackage number	5	PARC Task/Activity/Sub-activity:	5.1.1
Project Id	P5.1.1.b_Y1_HumanTox_BfR		

*The project has been extended from M36 to M54

Status: Implementation

Summary of the project

Due to the restrictions on the use of BPA in consumer products, which is the most widely used and studied bisphenol, a number of BPA substitutes have emerged. For most BPA alternatives, information on potential effects on relevant endpoints for human health is either missing or too limited for a sound HA/characterization. BPA alternatives are already being found in humans and the environment and have raised concerns in a regulatory context. With the upcoming restrictions on BPA, BPA's alternatives' tonnages and frequencies of use are expected to severely increase in the coming years.

Therefore, this project aims to fill the identified data gaps, and providing a complete data set for at least four relevant BPA alternatives. The selected alternatives were identified in an ad hoc Workshop together with ECHA and EFSA, following a tiered approach (Details on the prioritization basis can be found at AD5.1, [Deliverables page | Parc \(eu-parc.eu\)](#)). We will fill the knowledge gaps on human health on the following five toxicological endpoints:

1. EDs;
2. Developmental Neurotoxicity (DNT);
3. Immunotoxicity;
4. Non-genotoxic Carcinogenicity;
5. Metabolism (biotransformation, potential bioactivation pathways, toxicokinetics).

This project will also contribute to the identification of molecular biomarkers to develop a method to rapidly predict the possible effects of BPA alternatives. The identification of molecular biomarkers enables the determination of the mechanism(s) through which BPA alternatives act; identifying the key steps of their modes of action will be a key driver in the synergy between Work Package 5 and 6 regarding the improvement/production of AOP.

Main expected outputs of the project

Fill the identified data gaps on human health and provide a complete data set for at least four relevant BPA alternatives on the five toxicological endpoints stated previously.

The data obtained will provide modelers with input for PBPK and QIVIVE models and/or AOP development as well as a trigger for further higher-tier investigations.

Furthermore, the results to be obtained in this project will provide risk assessors with screening-level information that feeds mainly into the HA component of RA. Our project's data will help to decide if specific BPA alternatives are potential regrettable substitution if e.g., their ED potential is higher than that of BPA. In that sense, the data will be supporting information for regulatory processes. This will contribute significantly to the enhanced protection of public health and requirements for safe food, consumer products and drinking water.

Outcomes and impacts expected for end-users and stakeholders

The Project will provide *in vitro* data on a set of toxicological endpoints for BPA alternatives that have not been assessed by the industry, to support assessors in conducting an adequate RA and implementing CLP classifications.

With this project we will address the concern of the general population regarding this kind of substances, contributing to the production of safe products, such as plastic bottles, food cans and cash receipts, therefore minimizing the risk of adverse effects for end users.

Key words:

BPA analogues, risk assessment, endocrine disruptors, developmental neurotoxicity, immunotoxicity, metabolism, kinetics, *in vitro* methods, cognitive impairment, carcinogenicity

Link to the PARC DoA

The project responds to the PARC OOs OO3, OO4, OO5, OO6, OO7, OO10 and OO11.

A significant contribution to the PARC project will be made, providing useful data regarding BPA alternatives for both general awareness as well as for the needs of regulatory bodies. The data will provide also input for modellers working in PARC to build an experimental strategy relying only on NAMs.

A working group was formed in which specialists on BPA alternatives were combined with specialists in genotoxic and non-genotoxic carcinogenesis, endocrine disruption, developmental neurotoxicology, and immunotoxicological endpoints in order to deliver a program of studies. Frequent meetings were held in order to share as much relevant information as possible. A Workshop between WP/T leaders, project partners, EFSA and ECHA was organized to build a list of priority BPA alternatives for study (AD5.1), considering the regulatory gaps and needs.

Links within PARC (WPs/Tasks/Activities/Projects)

- WP4: Elucidation of the structure of yet unknown metabolites of BPA alternatives that may be used as potential biomarkers of exposure and related effect biomarkers
- WP5; Task 5.1, Task 5.2 and Task 5.3:
 - Task 5.2 Human Tox: we are working together with P5.2.1.e to fill up BPA alt data gaps using the established developmental neurotoxicity *in vitro* test battery (DNT IVB). Other WP5 project working with BPA alternatives in Task 5.1 and 5.2 Environment is P5.1.2.b joint project with A5.2.2.
 - We will share with projects in WP5 working with BPA Alt. the information regarding the production of major BPA alternatives metabolites for toxicological screening, notably as regards their potential to activate Nuclear Receptors (NR); Characterization of bioactivation pathways mechanistically involved in the onset of endpoints such as immune-toxicity and genotoxicity.
 - Mechanistic data generated will be used in the development of AOPs (e.g., DNT endpoint in A5.2.3.2)
 - We are also working closely with PBPK modelers in A5.3.4 to share the data produced (Km, Vmax, hepatic clearance)
- WP6: Hazard data is expected to feed into IATA building. Potency factors will be derived for the assessment of mixture effects.
- WP7: Task 7.3: data and text mining, data provision, DMP

Links outside PARC

- HBM4EU
- “European Cluster to Improve Identification of Endocrine Disruptors” (EURION) as regards the endpoint 5. Metabolism, on the metabolic fate of BPA analogues, the proposed project relies on the use of the human HepaRG cell line, a relevant human hepatic model displaying a broad panel of xenobiotic metabolizing enzymes (XMEs), also currently used in H2020 EURION by INRAE in the context of the “Generation Of NoveL, Integrated and Internationally Harmonised Approaches for Testing Metabolism Disrupting Compounds” (GOLIATH) project (Augmentation of the applicability domain of the cytochrome P450 (CYP) induction test method: OECD draft TG, TM2009-14, for EDCs/MDCs). Such studies will enhance the possibility to interpret results obtained in PARC in the most accurate manner, while no overlap in activities is foreseen.
- National Italian project: PRIN2017 ‘Endocrine disruptors: investigation of the effects on the immune and nervous systems (EDoNIS)’ Ref N. 2017MLC3NF
- Interaction and use of data in the forthcoming “Cluster 1 – Health “Topics WP 2023-2024 (2. Developmental neurotoxicity and 2.03 on Endocrine Disruptors)
- RIVM, Health Canada: Activities are coordinated with BPA alternatives projects initiated at RIVM and meetings to build synergies started recently with Health Canada (July 2023)

Key PARC Deliverables and Milestones to which the project contributes

- AD5.1: List of Prioritized BPA alternatives for WP5 HA activities. Workshop report (delivered)
- D5.1: 1st NAMs Report (delivered)
- D5.3: 1st new AOPs Report (delivered)
- D5.4: 1st Closing data Gaps Report (M36)
- D5.11: 2nd closing data gaps report (M54)

Partners List:

BfR (Germany), INRAE (France), IBMT Fraunhofer (Germany), ISS (Italy), INRS (France), UMIL (Italy), ULFFA (Slovenia), ISCIII (Spain), CNRS (France), TTL (Finland), MUI (Austria), LIH (Luxembourg), INSA (Portugal), NILU (Norway)

Schedule:

Starting date: 01/05/2022 (M1)
 Expected ending date: 31/10/2026 (M54)

Costs

Expected PM for the fourth year of the project: 105 PM
 Expected ODC for the fourth year of the project: 207 833 €

P5.1.1.c_Y3_TG+ EnnB1_ANSES

Project Title	TG+ Enniatin B1		
Project Acronym (15 letters max)	TG+ EnnB1		
Project Manager	Gilles Rivière Gilles.RIVIERE@anses.fr	Anses	France
Deputy Project manager	NA	NA	France
Expected starting date PARC (Month number)	M25	Expected duration (months)	36
PARC Workpackage number	WP5	PARC Task/Activity/Sub-activity:	5.1.1
Project Id	P5.1.1.c_Y3_TG+ EnnB1_ANSES		

Status: Implementation

Summary of the project

Enniatins are mycotoxins produced by *Fusarium* species, and are common contaminants of food and feed, mainly cereal grains and cereal by-products.

In 2014, in its “Scientific Opinion on the risks to human and animal health related to the presence of beauvericin and enniatins in food and feed,” EFSA stated that “Given the lack of relevant toxicity data, a RA was not possible,” and that “To perform a human RA, in vivo toxicity data on beauvericin and enniatins are needed. A study investigating possible health effects likely to arise from repeated exposure (i.e. 90-day study), (...), is required.” (EFSA, 2014). Among the “emerging” mycotoxins, enniatin B1 is one of the most prevalent compounds found in food.

To fill this data gap identified by EFSA, we are planning to conduct a TG+ study as a PoC, which consists in performing an OECD TG-conform animal study (TG 408: “Repeated Dose 90-Day Oral Toxicity Study in Rodents,” in feed, in rats), and in addition to the endpoints required by the TG, additional parameters will be investigated, such as toxicogenomics, without the necessity to include additional animals. TG+ studies, or ‘omics-enhanced in vivo studies’ have been described by ECHA as “necessary for further development of NAM for hazard/RA” (ECHA, 2023).

In parallel with the TG+ study, as a PoC, an omics-enhanced 5-day study will also be conducted (5-day, repeat oral dosing, transcriptomics rodent assay).

Additionally, in both studies, as many materials as possible will be collected that can be used for NAMs development and improvement in order to compare the results from NAMs-based assays and current methods, and ultimately help facilitate the regulatory acceptance of NAMs.

Main expected outputs of the project:

- In vivo data gaps to be filled on enniatins B1
- Development of NAMs and demonstration of robustness of alternative methods (TG+ study, NAMs, 5-day + omics study...).

Outcomes and impacts expected on end-users and stakeholders:

An in vivo data gap concerning enniatin B1 has been identified by EFSA to make a RA decision. This project would fill this data gap, while increasing confidence in the TG+ concept, that has been mentioned by ECHA as “necessary for further development of NAM for hazard/RA” (ECHA, 2023).

Additionally, as many materials as possible will be collected from this TG+ study so that WP5 partners can develop/optimize NAMs.

A number of in vitro and NAM-based tests are currently being performed to study the hazards of enniatin B1 project 5.1.1a and 5.2.1.d. The results of those tests will be compared to the results of the TG study to demonstrate the robustness of such methods.

This project will also build confidence in the 5d + omics approach, which is increasingly being used by the US Environmental Protection Agency (US-EPA).

Key words: NAMs, data gaps, human health, hazard assessment, toxicological endpoints, in vivo, 90-d

Link to the PARC DoA:

The project responds to the following PARC OOs:

OO4 – this project will fill up a data gap identified by EFSA (Efsa, 2014). There is an ongoing dialogue with EFSA regarding this knowledge gap.

OO6 – scientific publications

OO7- development of assessment methodologies for new mechanistic data streams and application of omics data for RA will contribute to innovation in complex data analysis for RA.

OO10 – production, storage and use of data following FAIR principles

OO12 – NAMs will be developed/optimized as part of this project, and confidence in NAMs and innovative concepts such as the 5d and TG+ studies will be increased.

OO9. - including innovative methods alongside a traditional TG study to fill up a data gap identified by a

European agency will facilitate the acceptance and use of PARC’s results in regulatory RA processes.

Links within PARC (WPs/Tasks/Activities/Projects)

WP5 T5.1, 5.2, 5.3 - work on enniatin B1 is already being performed in those tasks and will complement the work done in this project

WP6 - NAMs, AOPs

Links outside PARC:

EFSA – data gap was identified by EFSA (EFSA, 2014)

ECHA – TG+ study concept promoted by ECHA

US-EPA – 5d study + omics is a concept that has been developed and is being increasingly used by US-EPA

Key PARC Deliverables (or Additional Deliverables) and Milestones to which the project contributes

AD5.8: Study report (M41)

D5.4: 1st Closing data gaps report (M36)

D5.5: 2nd New approach methodologies report (new delivery date M48)

D5.8: 3rd New approach methodologies report (M60)

D5.11: 2nd Closing data gaps report (M54)

Partners List: ANSES (France), ANSES Fougères (France), BfR (Germany), NIPH (Norway), INSA (Portugal), NGere-INSERM (France), TUB (Germany)

Schedule:

Starting date: 01/05/2024 (M25)

Expected ending date: 30/04/2027 (M60)

Costs

Expected PM for the second year of the project : 23 PM

Expected ODC for the second year of the project : 78 234 €

Planned subcontracting 100% funded using the EU contribution for the second year of the project: 320 000 €

P5.1.1.d_Y4_PlasticLeach_NIPH

Project Title	Hazard characterization of leachable chemicals present in plastics	
Project Acronym (15 letters max)	PlasticLeach	
Project Manager	Hubert Dirven hubert.dirven@fhi.no	Norwegian Institute of Public Health Norway
Deputy Project manager	Dorte Herzke dorte.herzke@fhi.no Igor Snapkov igor.snapkov@fhi.no	Norwegian Institute of Public Health Norway
Expected starting date PARC (Month number)	M37	Expected duration (months) 45
PARC Workpackage number	WP5	PARC Task/Activity/Sub-activity: 5.1.1
Project Id	P5.1.1.d_Y4_PlasticLeach_NIPH	

Status: Initiation

Summary of the project

A recent report from the PlastChem project, initiated by the Norwegian Environment Agency/Norwegian Research Council), identified that over 16,000 chemicals have been found in plastics. Of these, only 6% are regulated globally, while 4200 chemicals are of concern because of known hazards. Strikingly, there is a complete lack of hazard information for 10,000 chemicals (<https://zenodo.org/records/10701706>). These numbers are in the same range as described in a [report](#) from the UN issued in 2023.

The Norwegian government, in two strategic documents, has emphasized the need for more knowledge on hazardous substances in plastics ([Norwegian Plastics Strategy](#) and [Norwegian Action Plan for a Toxic-Free Everyday Life](#)). The government has indicated a strong willingness to initiate actions to regulate the use of hazardous chemicals in plastics, both in Europe and globally. Similar initiatives are either in place or are being developed in multiple countries around the world.

The widespread human exposure to chemicals leaching from plastics, such as phthalates and bisphenols, has been well-documented in biomonitoring studies across Europe, for example, in the Aligned studies conducted under the HBM4EU.

The main goal of the project is to identify the most hazardous chemicals leaching from selected plastics for both the environment and human health. The proposed project also aligns with the UN plastic treaty currently under discussion..

The hazards of chemicals present in plastics will be studied with a primary focus on plastic additives and non-intentionally added chemical residues. Real-life leachates from plastic products will be studied as mixtures and hazard will be predicted and tested using selected NAMs focusing on CLP endpoints (including general cytotoxicity, carcinogenic, mutagenic or reprotoxic potential, Specific target organ toxicity - repeated exposure (STOT RE), endocrine disruption and genotoxicity, immunotoxicity, DNT, fertility outcomes, and effects on the barrier function of epithelial cells, using both human and environmental test models.) A tiered testing approach will be employed using NAMs. Since a number of these NAMs are still in development in PARC we will rank the NAMs proposed for technical readiness at the start of the project.

The final list of plastics for the project will be developed during the planning phase, taking into account factors such as their use and prevalence, areas of application, regulatory requirements, and the availability of commercial standards. Plastic products that will be considered are textiles, tobacco filters, balloons, wet wipes, food containers, cups, bottles etc. as indicated in the [UN report](#) as plastics with data gaps.

Leachate samples will be ranked according to toxicity based on both predicted effect (hazard) thresholds and laboratory-derived effect values. Identification of the chemicals present in the most hazardous leachates will be performed. Following the identification of additives or non-intentionally added chemical residues, commercially available standards of these chemicals will be used to assess their hazard potency/potency factors in the NAM-based tests. In the selection of test chemicals we will take into account the [results of the PLASI project](#) of ECHA in which 400 chemicals were identified that are added to plastics in amounts of more than 100 ton/year.

Main expected outputs of the project:

The proposed project aims to close existing data gaps by enhancing the hazard characterization of chemicals and their mixtures that can leach from plastics. This will be achieved by testing plastic leachates across various test models to assess effects on multiple endpoints relevant to human health and the environment. A range of NAMs being developed and tested in other tasks within PARC—including those for genotoxicity DNT, immunotoxicity, etc. will be utilized. Identification of hazardous chemicals will be attempted on available hazard prediction models and experimental results, and depending on the results, the Norwegian government is prepared to propose regulatory actions within REACH, in close cooperation with other member states.

Outcomes and impacts expected on end-users and stakeholders:

The [UN's recent report](#) highlights the urgent need for more data on the chemical content of plastics including exposure assessment, toxicity, and methods to evaluate toxicity. Policymakers, regulatory authorities and industries widely recognize the importance of this knowledge. The proposed project aims to address these critical aspects.

Outcomes and impacts expected to be incorporated into a specific regulatory framework:

The Norwegian government is committed to initiate regulatory action, if needed, within REACH on the most hazardous chemicals in plastics.

Data from the project will be used in the UN plastic treaty that is currently being negotiated. The results can also support the Science-Policy Panel in an ongoing UN Environment Programme initiative on the sound management of chemicals and waste and pollution prevention.

Key words: leachates, plastic, hazard, NAM-based testing, human, environment, regulatory actions, UN plastic treaty, REACH

Link to the PARC DoA:

The project responds to the PARC OOs OO3, OO4, OO5, OO6, OO7, OO8, OO10, OO12, OO9, OO11. The output of this project will identify some of the most hazardous chemicals that can leach from plastics, resulting in human and environmental exposure. The most hazardous compounds identified may become subject to regulatory action (OO3, OO4, OO7, OO9). Regulation will result in reduced exposure to these chemicals for both humans and the environment, a trend likely to be visible in biomonitoring studies (OO8). Computational and experimental NAMs will be used to test for mixture effects and data will be collected in compliance with FAIR initiatives (OO10).

Links within PARC (WPs/Tasks/Activities/Projects):

The proposed project has synergies with the bisphenol A alternatives projects in WP 5 (T5.1.1/ T5.1.2) and is expected to create synergies with NAMs development in T5.2 (Technical readiness of NAMs), also with T5.3.1 projects on omics. Synergies are expected with the PFAS projects within WP6 (T6.3 Case study on plastic additives). Collaboration with project P4.1.1.4.d_Y1_OccupWaste_ENSP_TTL – exposure to chemicals from plastics in the industry is planned. Collaboration with WP4.3 on the non-target screening of chemicals leaching from the plastics is key to success. Data templates will be developed in conjunction with WP7 (T7.2 FAIRification of exposure and hazard data) to ensure that the data is generated in a standardized and FAIR format. Given that plastics and associated chemicals are a global concern, interaction with stakeholders, the establishment of synergies with other related projects and communication of plans and results will be performed together with WP3. The knowledge generated can contribute to the safe-by-design concepts and integrative models developed by WP8.

Links outside PARC

- REACH
- Toy Safety Directive
- Food contact materials (FCM regulations (EC 10/2011 and 2022/1516)
- Drinking Water Directive
- General Product Safety Directive
- UNEA Resolution 5/14 “End plastic pollution: Towards an international legally binding instrument”
- Norwegian Plastics Strategy and Norwegian Action Plan for a Toxic-Free Everyday Life
- Interactions with the CUSP cluster
- Various national environmental- and biomonitoring initiatives

- Research projects on plastics under the Horizon Europe programme

This project will provide data to inform existing and emerging regulations on plastics and chemicals in plastics. Bio- and environmental monitoring studies from various countries will be used to identify the most widespread plastic-related chemicals. Additionally, findings and analytical methods from other research projects will be evaluated and, where relevant, incorporated into the project's framework, including the case study on plastic additives in task 6.3

Key PARC Deliverables and Milestones to which the project contributes

D5.11: 2nd closing data gaps report (M54)

D5.15: 3rd closing data gaps report (M81)

Partners List:

NIPH (NO), INSA (PT), KIST Europe (DE) (modalities of collaboration are still under discussion), ANSES (FR), UU (NL), IEP – NRI (PT), UAVR (PT), NIB (SI), INRS (FR), NIVA (NO), WU (NL), BPI (EL).

Advisors: UFZ (DE), NTNU (NO)

Schedule:

Starting date: 1 May 2025 (M36)

Expected ending date: 31/01/2029 (M81)

Costs

Expected PM for the first year of the project: 78 PM

Expected ODC for the first year of the project: 136 988 €

A5.1.2 Toxicity assessment addressing data gaps of concern (Environment) – 2 PROJECTS

P5.1.2.a_Y1_NaturalToxinsAqua_UGent (closed M36)

Project Title	Toxicity assessment of naturally occurring toxins on aquatic organisms		
Project Acronym (15 letters max)	AquaToxins		
Project Manager	Jana Asselman Jana.asselman@ugent.be	Ghent University	Belgium
Deputy Project manager	Stefan Örn stefan.orn@slu.se	SLU	Sweden
Expected starting date	1	Expected duration	36
PARC (Month number)			
PARC Workpackage number	5	PARC Task/Activity/Sub-activity:	5.1.2
Project Id	P5.1.2.a_Y1_NaturalToxinsAqua_UGent		

*The project will be closed M36, the related D5.4 is planned to be submitted M36

P5.1.2.b_Y1_BPAalternatives_BPI_MU

Project Title	BPA alternatives and associated mixtures (data gaps and NAM development)		
Project Acronym (15 letters max)	Bisphenols_ENV		
Project Manager	Ludek Blaha (ludek.blaha@recetox.muni.cz)	Masarykova univerzita (MU)	Czech Republic

Deputy Project manager	Ondřej Adamovský (ondrej.adamovsky@recetox.muni.cz) Katerina Kyriakopoulou (k.kyriakopoulou@bpi.gr)	Benaki Phytopathological Institute (BPI)	Greece
Expected starting date PARC (Month number)	1	Expected duration	48*
PARC Workpackage number	5	PARC Task/Activity/Sub-activity:	5.1.2 5.2.2
Project Id	P5.1.2.b_Y1_BPAalternatives_BPI_MU		

*The project has been extended from M42 to M48

Status: Implementation

Summary of the project

The concerns regarding the potential adverse effects of BPA and tight restrictions of BPA in many countries has led to the development of alternative chemicals (*e.g.*, bisphenol Z (BPZ), bisphenol E (BPE), bisphenol P (BPP), bisphenol AP (BPAP), bisphenol B (BPB), bisphenol C (BPC), bisphenol S (BPS), bisphenol F (BPF), bisphenol AF (BPAF)) resulting in emerging environmental contaminants found worldwide in various environmental components including water, sediment, sludge, soil, indoor dust and air. In addition, the use of BPA alternatives will be increased in the following years, since the use of BPA should be significantly reduced based on the upcoming EFSA scientific opinion in which EFSA has re-evaluated the risks from BPA in food and propose a lower tolerable daily intake (TDI) than the one previously set. Regarding their properties most bisphenols are characterized as toxic (or very toxic) to aquatic organisms, have been shown to exhibit adverse effects on the endocrine, reproduction, metabolism and immune system in different species and some of them are persistent, mobile or bioaccumulative and are characterized as persistent, bioaccumulative and toxic (PBT)/very persistent and very bioaccumulative (vPvB) or Persistent, mobile and toxic (PMT)/very persistent and very mobile (vPvM). In parallel, BPA alternatives are molecules regulated under REACH and their chemical safety assessment is carried out at different levels of comprehensiveness according to the specific data requirements based on the tonnage levels in which the substance is produced. These data are not always adequate to assess the potential adverse effects of BPA alternatives not only on human health but also on non-mammalian species, also considering the widespread use of many bisphenols and the possibility of exposure in the environment.

Finally, the current regulatory RA focuses on single chemicals, widely disregarding potential adverse effects of mixtures of BPA alternatives on different organisms, especially after long-term exposure to environmentally realistic concentrations. Consequently, the assessment of combined effects of BPA alternatives and chemicals in general is recognized as one of the major needs in chemical RA and this need has been highlighted in the CSS, in the European Green Deal and in PARC / HBM4EU prioritization survey. Therefore, this project aims to fill the data gaps concerning the BPA alternatives (activities i and ii) and will serve as a platform for development of NAMs (activities iii-v).

Main expected outputs of the project

The specific aims and the relevant expected outputs of this project are the following:

- Investigation of the potential adverse effects (*e.g.*, apical endpoints such as mortality, effects related to the anticipated mode of action (MoA) or molecular initiation events (MIE), effects on reproduction, effects on endocrine system) of certain individual substances and “real-life” mixtures of BPA alternatives on non-mammalian organisms belonging to different taxa (*activity i and ii*)
- Development of *in silico* and modelling tools for HA of BPA alternatives to ultimately support grouping of substances and read-across (RAx) approaches based on NAMs (*activity iii*).

- Development / advancing invertebrates' models as NAMs for the HA of BPA alternatives and/or other prioritized chemicals (*activity iv*)
- Development / advancing alternative 3R-compatible vertebrate aquatic models for environmental HA of BPA alternatives and other prioritized chemicals (*activity v*)

Outcomes and impacts expected for end-users and stakeholders

This project will provide *in vivo* and *in vitro* toxicological data for BPA alternatives relevant for different endpoints (e.g. endocrine disruption, reproduction, etc) and several species, that have not been assessed by the industry since they are not included in the specific data requirements under REACH. The project will also bring new data regarding the toxicity of BPA alternatives, as this topic is largely unexplored. Moreover, the project will contribute to the development of NAMs. Therefore, the project aims to assist risk assessors, Member State Regulatory Authorities, EU agencies and other relevant stakeholders in conducting hazard/RA.

Key words: data gaps, NAMs, BPA alternatives, *in silico*, *in vivo*, *in vitro*

Link to the PARC DoA

The project will contribute to the investigation and closing of data gaps regarding the HA of priority chemicals - bisphenols (single compounds and chemicals) with focus on the environment (Activity 5.1.2). In addition, this project will contribute to the development of innovative methodologies (NAMs) that will directly contribute to hazard identification and RA not only for BPA alternatives but also for other chemicals (Activity 5.2.2). The project will mainly contribute to the PARC OOs OO4, OO7 and OO9 by developing and implementing R&I work programs based on priorities set and generating results and knowledge to support the use of new approaches and methods, fill data gaps in BPA alternatives HA, and by development of tools and methods to facilitate the acceptance and use of PARC results in regulatory RA processes.

The project will also contribute to the PARC OOs by providing input to priority-setting (OO3), promote cooperation with other relevant R&I initiatives (OO5), develop new networks of laboratories (OO11), contribute to communication and dissemination of the results (OO6) and implement FAIR data practices to enable open science (OO10).

Links within PARC (WPs/Tasks/Activities/Projects)

- WP4: T4.2.1 and T4.2.2 - incorporation of environmental monitoring data into BPA selection process.
- WP5: All tasks T5.1, 5.2, 5.3 - data derived in 5.1 and 5.2 will be valuable for AOP development / modeling in 5.3.
- WP6: T6.1, 6.2 and others - discussion regarding building NAM confidence for regulatory purposes.
- WP7: Data management – bilateral discussion regarding proper data storage and management.
- WP3 and WP9: will be contacted for identification of synergies.

Links outside PARC

- HBM4EU: Information on exposure and real-life mixtures will be taken from information provided by HBM4EU.
- POLYSAFE: French national program on assessment of plastic alternatives for food containers (Coordinated by CNRS)
- Precision Tox: A link to Precision Tox will be established to benefit from the 5-species 250 substances toxicogenomic approach, to create synergies and to avoid duplication of work.
- PRORISK: The activity will be synergized by sharing predicted and experimentally derived environmental hazard data to a novel integrative RA platform developed in PRORISK (<https://prorisk-itn.eu/>) that links chemical-biological interactions, through AOPs, effects on organisms and populations up to predictions of risks for ecosystem services and the socio-economic costs of environmental damage.

Key PARC Deliverables and Milestones to which the project contributes

- AD5.1: List of Prioritized BPA alternatives for WP5 HA activities. Workshop report (delivered)
- AD5.3: List of first assays to be developed for prioritised endpoints (delivered)

- D5.1: 1st NAMs Report (delivered)
- D5.4: 1st Closing data Gaps Report (M36)
- D5.5.: 2nd New approach methodologies report (M48)
- D5.11: 2nd closing data gaps report (M54)

Partners List:

BPI (Greece), SLU (Sweden), IISPV (Spain), SDU (Denmark), INERIS (France), NIB (Slovenia), IEP-NRI (Poland), UU (Sweden), UG-PL (Poland), UAVR (Portugal), EAWAG (Switzerland), NIVA (Norway), MU (Czechia), NIC (Slovenia), UFZ (Germany), BFG (Germany), UPO (Spain), UAntwerpen (Belgium), CNRS (France), MUI (Austria), SU (Sweden), INRAE (France), Cefas-Defra (UK).

Schedule:

Starting date: 01/05/2022 (M1)
 Expected ending date: 30/04/2026 (M48)

Costs

Expected PM for the fourth year of the project: 293 PM
 Expected ODC for the fourth year of the project: 350 904 €

P5.1.2.c_Y4_TG+MP_ANSES

Project Title	TG + Microplastic bioaccumulation data gaps and applicability of in vitro bioaccumulation assessment methods (environment)		
Project Acronym (15 letters max)	TG+MP		
Project Manager	Gilles Rivière Gilles.RIVIERE@anses.fr	ANSES	France
Deputy Project manager	NA	NA	France
Expected starting date PARC (Month number)	M37	Expected duration (months)	24
PARC Workpackage number	WP5	PARC Task/Activity/Sub-activity:	5.1.2
Project Id	P5.1.2.c_Y4_TG+MP_ANSES		

Status: Initiation

Summary of the project

Information on bioaccumulation is used within several regulations such as REACH and BPR for PBT assessment, hazard classification or chemical safety assessment.

There are two alternative methods that are especially promising for bioaccumulation assessment: the freshwater amphipod *Hyalella Azteca* bioconcentration test (HYBIT), and OECD TG 319 A and B. HYBIT provides an aquatic bioconcentration factor (BCF) value, and OECD TG 319 A/B provide an estimate of intrinsic hepatic clearance based on in vitro assays, which can be extrapolated to a BCF using IVIVE methods. There are, however, uncertainties regarding their applicability domain (ECHA, 2024). Indeed, for some substances, such as organometals, surfactants, ionisable substances, the log Kow alone isn't sufficient to conclude on a bioaccumulation potential, and oftentimes, in such cases, in vivo fish testing is used. REACH Annex IX section 9.3.2 states that it is not possible to waive the bioaccumulation test in aquatic species based on low Log Kow if the substance is ionisable or surface active at environmental pH. There is also a research need regarding suitable NAM approaches covering regulatory relevant endpoints, including bioaccumulation potential in the environment, for micro materials (ECHA, 2023).

This project would be divided into two workstreams, one on the bioaccumulation of microplastic particles, and one on the bioaccumulation of plastic additives. The objectives are twofold: filling datagaps on the bioaccumulation in fish of those contaminants and assessing the applicability domain of in vitro bioaccumulation assessment methods. Additionally, using tissues from the TG studies performed under Good Laboratory Practice (GLP), non-targeted metabolomics and/or proteomics analyses will be performed to define biomarkers of exposure and to characterize possible biological pathways triggered or suppressed after the bioaccumulation of the tested plastic additives. Non-targeted metabolomics and proteomics studies have been implemented for several years in the environmental field to investigate toxicity mechanisms/pathways for hazard identification. This can lead to the identification of new potential markers of exposure of toxicological concern. This project is meant to be the second TG+ study of WP5.

Main expected outputs of the project

The output of this project is twofold:

- Filling data gaps on the bioaccumulation in fish of microplastic particles and selected additives
- Demonstrating the robustness and the applicability domain of in vitro bioaccumulation assessment methods
- Discovery of biomarkers of exposure and highlighting toxicity mechanisms/pathways associated with microplastics/chemicals released from plastics.

Outcomes and impacts expected on end-users and stakeholders

- Demonstrating the robustness and applicability domain of in vitro bioaccumulation assessment methods is key to increasing their use, and reduce the need for vertebrate testing on fish, and allow improved assessment of some substances that cannot be assessed by conventional methods, due to their properties.
- Generation of TG-based bioaccumulation data on plastic additives and microplastic particles that can be used to manage more appropriately the environmental impacts of such substances on aquatic ecosystems.
- Inclusion of analytical methodologies to the bioaccumulation assessment protocols for the detection of biomarkers of exposure and/or triggered toxicity pathways.

This project is based on research needs expressed in the KARC document (ECHA, 2023) and on the priorities established in PARC.

Outcomes and impacts expected to be incorporated into a specific regulatory framework

According to REACH, it is not possible to waive the bioaccumulation test in aquatic species based on low Log Kow if the substance is ionisable or surface active at environmental pH, meaning that for these substances, in vivo fish testing is needed. Demonstrating the robustness and applicability domain of in vitro bioaccumulation assessment methods is key to increasing their use, and reduce the need for vertebrate testing on fish, and allow improved assessment of some substances that cannot be assessed by conventional methods, due to their properties.

Key words

Microplastics, additives, NAMs, omics, fish, bioaccumulation

Link to the PARC DoA

The project responds to the PARC OOs OO4, OO5, OO7, OO10, OO12

This project is based on a research need identified by ECHA and aims at testing and promoting innovative concepts for RA. A dialogue has been initiated with institutions in Europe working on a similar topic. FAIR data practices will be implemented to the best of our abilities.

Links within PARC (WPs/Tasks/Activities/Projects)

This project complements the work done in Task 5.2.2 (NAMs for environmental toxicology) and will benefit from the input from the project Leachables in Plastics (T5.1). This also complements the work of WP7 to implement FAIR data practices

Links outside PARC

This project mentioned links with:

- UBA-led project – new strategies for regulatory bioaccumulation assessment

Both projects aim at advancing alternative methods and integrating them into regulatory bioaccumulation assessment. The interaction will consist in sharing experiences and expertise.

Key PARC Deliverables and Milestones to which the project contributes

D5.5: 2nd New Approach Methodologies report (M48)

D5.8: 3rd New Approach Methodologies report (M60)

D 5.11: Report on data gaps (M54)

Partners List:

ANSES (FR), BPI (EL), INRAE (FR)

Schedule:

Starting date: 01/06/2025 (M38)

Expected ending date: 30/04/2027 (M60)

Costs

Expected PM for the first year of the project: 7 PM

Expected ODC for the first year of the project: 5 000 €

T5.2 Innovative methods and tools for toxicity testing and modelling - 9 PROJECTS

The focus of this task is on the improvement of the current hazard characterisation paradigm by establishing comprehensive testing strategies that logically combine novel methods with well-established approaches, preferably in a tiered manner. In brief, this task will evaluate the relevance and readiness of new technologies, e.g., genomic, transcriptomic, proteomic, high-content analysis microscopy, HRMS, and human inducible pluripotent stem cell technology, for the assessment of (eco)toxicological endpoints such as non-genotoxic carcinogenicity, immunotoxicity, endocrine disruption and DNT, thereby leveraging OECD’s and PARC’s AOP frameworks. Also, test methods, tools and methodologies will be developed to identify drivers of toxicity in mixtures and to support the grouping of chemicals, including the application of RAX. Furthermore, this task aims for the development and application of predictive *in vitro* and *in silico* tools to identify and characterise specific hazards. Through close collaboration with HBM communities in- and outside PARC, methods and computational approaches will be developed to study the metabolism of chemical substances in different biological (test) systems or matrices (e.g., cells, organoids, organs, blood) for comparison between species.

P5.2.a_Y4_RegNAMs _ANSES

Project Title	Regulatory readiness of NAMs		
Project Acronym (15 letters max)	RegNAMs		
Project Manager	Gilles Rivière gilles.riviere@anses.fr	ANSES	France
Deputy Project manager	Philip Marx-Stoelting Philip.Marx-Stoelting@bfr.bund.de	BfR	Germany

Expected starting date PARC (Month number)	M37	Expected duration (months)	45
PARC Workpackage number	WP5	PARC Task/Activity/Sub-activity:	Task 5.2
Project Id	P5.2.a_Y4_RegNAMs _ANSES		

Status: Initiation

Summary of the project

As of today, regulatory requirements for chemicals, mostly rely on OECD TGs assays. The validations of these assays are based on guideline 34 currently under revision. An important ambition of PARC is to facilitate and accelerate the transition of NAMs for toxicological hazard and chemical safety assessment from a research phase into regulatory practice contributing to the Replacement, Reduction and Refinement (3Rs) approach. Ultimately, one important measure of the success of PARC will consist of the tangible positive impact PARC will have made on regulatory processes and decision-making contexts. In WP5 ('Hazard Assessment') and WP6 ('Innovation in regulatory risk assessment') of PARC, there is a substantial number of projects underway aimed at tackling different challenges and priorities with regard to NAMs and integrated approaches, each with its own specific objectives and strategies but all aimed at making new approaches fit to use in regulatory practice.

There are five endpoints for which specific NAMs are developed in PARC: non-genotoxic carcinogenicity, metabolic disruption, thyroid disruption, immunotoxicity and DNT.

All of these endpoints are complex and cannot be covered by a single NAM; instead, batteries of relevant NAMs are needed. For some of the abovementioned endpoints, NAMs have already been under development and promising NAMs have been identified within and outside PARC, which need further work to improve regulatory readiness.

The primary objective of this project is to support validation activities that improve the regulatory readiness of NAMs. A selection of the most promising NAMs (in terms of regulatory impact, not necessarily the most developed assays) to undergo validation activities will be made in collaboration with the partners. The methodology to select these NAMs will be discussed and agreed with the partners at the beginning of the project. These activities will be coordinated with other projects and initiatives (e.g. EU-NETVAL) to create synergies as well as WP6 and the methodology leader on validation in PARC.

Within WP5, the developers of NAMs could self-assess their ongoing assay(s) using the ReadEDTest tool providing some degrees of readiness for several aspects (availability of SOP, data interpretation procedures, data management system, chemical tested etc.). As of today, the ReadEDTest is specifically dedicated to assessing in vitro and fish embryo assays triggering endocrine disruption (<https://readedtest.u-paris-sciences.fr/>). In parallel, one objective of this project is to expand ReadEDTest to assess test methods under development for other endpoints, to organize the independent peer-review of the readiness of NAMs developed in WP5.

Main expected outputs of the project:

In Y3, this transversal project focusing on regulatory readiness of NAMs will be initiated. This project aims to facilitate the uptake of the NAMs being developed in WP5 by assessing their readiness, supporting NAMs developers with, for instance, SOPs development (Good In Vitro Methods Practices (GIVIMP) workshops), and working on the alignment with AOPs / IATAs being developed in PARC. The objectives of this project can be broken down as follows:

- Selection of NAMs addressing regulatory needs;
- Expand ReadEDTest to assess methods for some endpoints prioritized within WP5 (e.g. non-genotoxic carcinogenicity, immunotoxicity, DNT/ANT);

- Organize independent peer-review of readiness of NAM developed in WP5 (SOPs, results of ReadEDtest)
- Support validation activities of these selected NAMs for willing partners
- As an optional objective, writing a manuscript based on the position paper, further guidance and respective deliverables.

This project will be coordinated by ANSES and main contributors will be INSERM, BfR, JRC, methodology leader on validation and RIVM (more partners will be involved as the project moves forward).

Outcomes and impacts expected on end-users and stakeholders:

Expansion of ReadEDTest to new endpoints for NAM developers

Selection of NAMs of regulatory interest in collaboration with stakeholders

Support validation activities: standardisation, SOP development and/or transferability and inter-laboratory reproducibility of regulatory-relevant NAMs

Potential outputs include involvement of PARC and possibly European Union Network of Laboratories for the Validation of Alternative Methods (EU-NETVAL) partners to test interlaboratory reproducibility, and involvement of the JRC and methodology leader to perform an independent peer review of the methods being developed in PARC. Measures for achievement of project objectives include number of methods peer-reviewed, and number of methods improved through this process, also evidenced by their ReadEDTest scores.

Outcomes and impacts expected to be incorporated into a specific regulatory framework:

Outcomes: Selected regulatory relevant NAMs will gain in regulatory readiness

Regulatory frameworks: NAMs could ultimately be incorporated in the following regulatory frameworks (non-exhaustive):

- Regulation (EC) No 1107/2009.
- Regulation (EU) No 10/2011.
- Regulation (EU) No 528/2012.
- Regulation (EC) No 1272/2008.
- Regulation (EC) No 1333/2008.

Key words: NAMs, pre-validation, IATAs, regulatory readiness

Link to the PARC DoA:

The project responds to the PARC OOs OO3, OO4, OO5, OO7, OO9, OO11, OO13

This project aims to contribute to the regulatory uptake of NAMs demonstrating their regulatory readiness. This will be achieved by the validation related activities supported by this project in collaboration with stakeholders (assay developers, EU-Netval, Pepper).

Links within PARC (WPs/Tasks/Activities/Projects):

- WP5 - T5.2
 NAMs development: This project will contribute mainly to the following Guiding principles listed in the NGRA roadmap (PARC WP2): #4: Science, #5: Evidence Integration, #6: Regulatory Workflows, #7: Biology.
- WP6 - T6.1 IATAs, New project foreseen to be submitted by WP6 on regulatory readiness of assays
- WP9 - Training (ReadEDTest), laboratory network (contributing to the mapping of European scientific and infrastructure resources, T9.2)

Links outside PARC:

- EU JRC, ECHA, EFSA - NAMS4NANO consortium

- Pepper <https://ed-pepper.eu/>
- OECD

A close link with OECD will be established as to avoid duplication of work and to ensure sustainability of the validation-related activities performed within PARC.

Key PARC Deliverables and Milestones to which the project contributes

D5.5: 2nd New approach methodologies report (M48)

D5.8: 3rd New approach methodologies report (M60)

D5.12: 4th New approach methodologies report (M81)

Partners List:

INSERM (FR), ANSES (FR), BfR (DE), JRC (EU), RIVM (NL)

Schedule:

Starting date: 01/05/2025 (M37)

Expected ending date: 31/01/2029 (M81)

Costs

Expected PM for the first year of the project: 28 PM

Expected ODC for the first year of the project: 9 000 €

A5.2.1 Innovative methods and tools for toxicity testing and modelling – 8 PROJECTS

P5.2.1.a_Y1_NGTXCs_INRAE

Project Title	Non-genotoxic carcinogens		
Project Acronym (15 letters max)	NGTXCs		
Project Manager 1	Marc Audebert marc.audebert@inrae.fr	INRAE	France
Project Manager 2	Michael Oelgeschläger Michael.Oelgeschlaeger@bfr.bund.de	BfR	Germany
Expected starting date PARC (Month number)	1	Expected duration	60
PARC Workpackage number	5	PARC Task/Activity/Sub-activity:	5.2.1
Project Id	P5.2.1.a_Y1_NGTXCs_INRAE		

Status: Implementation

Summary of the project:

A range of organ and cellular model systems (including liver, breast, colon, adipocytes) will be investigated with innovative human-relevant NAMs, including state of the art transcriptomic approaches, high-content analysis, cell painting, epigenetics and high-throughput-compatible reporter systems addressing well established and relevant mechanisms of carcinogenesis, such as (oxidative) stress, epithelial-mesenchymal transition (EMT), inflammation, changes in metabolism, epigenetic marks or nuclear receptors signaling as well as proliferation. In addition, experimental approaches will be complemented by the optimization of *in silico* tools for the identification of Non-Genotoxic Carcinogens (NGTxCs) to address the assay needs for the development of an NGTXCs IATA in cooperation with WP6.1 and ongoing activities at EU (e.g. RISK-HUNT3R) and OECD level. The project will improve our knowledge of the relationships between a range of different substances specific for distinct AOP that ultimately lead to cancer. In addition, methods with increasing complexity, from 2D cell culture up to 3D spheroids and zebrafish embryo (ZFe)'s as a simple

vertebrate model system are used in the project. Zebrafish will be used in order to have a whole organism included that also provides some metabolic activity. The use of NAMs with increasing levels of complexity will facilitate the integration of the physiological and toxicological relevant information with respect to adversity in order to inform about potential carcinogens and to improve chemical assessment and regulation. Here, the comparative analysis of the various assays in this project will also facilitate the characterisation of the applicability domain and limitation of each method. The project will align with AOPs and IATA work under Task 5.3 as well as T6.1 and takes into account the ongoing work of the OECD expert group on NGTXCs as well as current EU initiatives (e.g. RISK-HUNT3R. Further details of this project can be found here <https://www.frontiersin.org/articles/10.3389/ftox.2023.1220998/full>

Main expected outputs of the project

To develop internationally acceptable *in vitro* testing batteries (NAMs) and IATAs, the test methods (including *in silico* prediction tools) will be subject to testing of a sufficiently large set of reference compounds, including prioritized PARC compounds, to allow the evaluation of reliability and relevance taking into account sensitivity and specificity of the various systems as well as their complementarity detecting different MoAs involved on non-genotoxic carcinogenicity. The more complex systems will be further developed and optimized to allow a more physiological evaluation of activity for a subset of the reference compounds.

Outcomes and impacts expected for end-users and stakeholders

The project will be particularly helpful from a risk assessor's as well as applicants from industry because the innovative, rapid, reliable and cost-efficient methods developed therein will allow an efficient and relevant mechanistic NGTXCs hazard analysis of a high number of substances and mixtures thus contributing to detection of hazardous substances well as product optimization following the zero pollution ambition of the green deal and the CSS.

Key words: Carcinogenesis, 3D cell models, OMICs, MoA, risk assessment

Link to the PARC DoA

The project responds to the PARC OOs OO3, OO4, OO5, OO6, OO7, OO10, OO12, OO9 and OO11. The composition of the consortium ensures efficient communication with other PARC Work Packages, NHs, research initiatives (Horizon projects), and the OECD. The consortium has already connected various labs from different European countries and is in contact with additional laboratories. (SO1, OO4, and OO5; SO2, OO7; SO3, OO11).

Concerning SO2, OO10 This project will cooperate with WP 9 to ensure FAIR data practices.

The main aim is to develop new approaches and innovative concepts to detect and evaluate potential NGTxC /carcinogens considering current practices of standardization and aims at the validation of some methods in cooperation with external activities. (SO2, OO12; SO3, OO9).

Links within PARC (WPs/Tasks/Activities/Projects)

- WP2 and WP3: The priorities regarding the various regulatory frameworks to be addressed will be confirmed in close collaboration with WP2 “A common science-policy agenda” and WP3 “Synergies, collaboration and awareness”.
- WP5 and WP6: We will closely collaborate with WP5 “Hazard assessment” and with WP6 “Innovation in regulatory risk assessment” on topics related to NGTXCs and IATA development. These topics include:
 - a) mapping of existing AOPs and associated NAMs for non-genotoxic carcinogenicity;
 - b) interaction with the other A5.2.1 subjects related to endocrine disruption and immunotoxicity end-points;
 - c) development of (quantitative) AOP networks using, among others, data generated in WP5;
 - d) evaluation of NGTXCs IATA through case studies in WP6.
- WP7: The data generated in the project itself as well as the case studies also provide a link to WP7 “FAIR data”, in which analysis of the uncertainties associated with the IATA will be one of the use cases.
- WP9: this work relates to WP9 “Capacities”, since valuable learnings will be taken up in relevant training courses.

Links outside PARC

- H2020 Projects: This project is closely linked to ongoing H2020 projects, in particular the ASPIS and the EURION clusters,
- OECD activities, including the work of the OECD Advisory Group on Emerging Science in Chemicals Assessment (ESCA), the OECD WPHA as well as and the OECD NGTXCs expert group.

Key PARC Deliverables and Milestones to which the project contributes

AD5.2: (delivered)- Report of the description of the Extended One Generation Reproductive Toxicity (EOGRT) study to be conducted. Associated Task: T5.1 Leader of the deliverable: ANSES, BfR. Associated Task co-leaders: BPI/NIPH/INSA. It was planned that the project managers would contribute to this deliverable, but in the end it was not necessary.

AD5.3: (delivered)- List of first assays to be developed for prioritised endpoints. Associated Task T5.2. Leader of the deliverable: DTU, VUB. Associated Task co-leaders: DTU/VUB/MU.

D5.1: (delivered) - 1st NAMs Report. Associated Task: T5.2. Leader of the deliverable: BfR. Associated Task co-leaders: DTU/VUB/MU.

D5.3: (delivered) - 1st new AOPs Report. Associated Task: T5.3. Leader of the deliverable: INSERM. Associated Task co-leaders: UL-LACDR/SCIENSANO/Fraunhofer.

D5.5: M48 (April 2026) - 2nd New approach methodologies report. Associated Task: T5.2. Leader of the deliverable: BfR. Associated Task co-leaders: DTU/VUB/MU.

D5.8: M60 (April 2027) - 3rd New approach methodologies report. Associated Task: T5.2. Leader of the deliverable: BfR. Associated Task co-leaders: DTU/VUB/MU.

Partners List:

INRAE (FR); BfR (DE); ANSES (FR); INSERM (FR); NIB (SI); UL-LACDR (NL); UNAV (ES); IRFM (IT); RIVM (NL); RPTU (DE); NILU (NO); MU (CZ)

Schedule:

Starting date: 01/05/2022 (M1)

Expected ending date: 30/04/2027 (M60)

Costs

Expected PM for the fourth year of the project: 150 PM

Expected ODC for the fourth year of the project: 258 519 €

P5.2.1.b_Y1_MD-EDC_BfR

Project Title	Metabolic Endocrine Disruption		
Project Acronym (15 letters max)	MD-EDC		
Project Manager	Denise Bloch denise.bloch@bfr.bund.de	BfR	Germany
Deputy Project manager	Daniel Zalko daniel.zalko@inrae.fr	INRAE	France
Expected starting date PARC (Month number)	1	Expected duration	48*
PARC Workpackage number	5	PARC Task/Activity/Su b-activity:	5.2.1
Project Id	P5.2.1.b_Y1_MD-EDC_BfR		

*The project has been extended from M36 to M48

Status: Implementation

Summary of the project

Over the past decade, progress in EDC research has demonstrated that one specific adverse effect of a number of EDC is their capability to induce a lasting disruption of endogenous metabolism. These substances, referred as "metabolism disrupting chemicals" (MDC) are largely suspected to contribute to the incidence of obesity and related metabolic disorders such as type II diabetes and non-alcoholic fatty liver disease, in association with genetic factors, nutrition and lifestyle. Nowadays, more than 50 million people in Europe suffer from metabolic disorders with the role of environmental stressors (either man-made or natural chemicals) being increasingly recognized. Despite MDC being suspected to play a major role in the worldwide epidemics of metabolic disorders, there are currently no specific regulatory *in vivo* or *in vitro* tests allowing to identify their adverse effects. The WHO/IPSC (2002) presents specific criteria that should be fulfilled for a substance to be considered as an EDC, but no criteria are established for MDC yet. The WHO/IPSC (2002) EDC criteria could be considered to apply to MDC too. From a regulatory perspective (e.g., with respect to the fields of pesticides or chemicals regulation), it is thus of paramount importance to validate methodologies allowing to identify and assess MDC-associated risks. Therefore, this project will focus on the development of NAMs facilitating regulators to identify and assess MDC-associated risks. Further details of this project can be found here <https://www.frontiersin.org/articles/10.3389/ftox.2023.1212509/full>

Main expected outputs of the project

A comprehensive exploration of NR-driven effects will be carried out using stably transfected cell lines, expanding the on-going prevalidation of transient cell lines in EURION. An extended spectrum of substances will be assessed for priority families, including major metabolites and breakdown molecules, allowing further MoA exploration, as well as AOP and RAX development. We will develop NAMs encompassing hepatic and non-hepatic *in vitro* systems including multi-tissue cross-talk, opening the road for a refined assessment of the obesogenic effects of MDC. This will involve a deep mechanistic exploration of key cellular pathways using human *in vitro* models, as well as parallel additional 3R-compliant models and novel methods, including imagery. New developments enabling the proposal of accurate NAMs based on human as well as non-human models will enable to close major data gaps in the field of metabolic disruption, in close connection with other PARC topics, tasks and WPs. The developed and (pre-)validated *in vitro* test systems will allow for the identification of endocrine MDC and thus direct impact on regulatory decisions related to endocrine activities of compounds. Moreover, the work carried out with specific compound classes (e.g., bisphenol derivatives) will impact on the RA of these classes of compounds.

Outcomes and impacts expected for end-users and stakeholders

Currently, there is no regulatory TGs, approaches or testing strategies for MDCs. The sheer need for tests development in the field of metabolic disorders has been highlighted in recent work commissioned by DG Environment. In this project section, new methods will be developed for identifying MDC, with outcomes expected to be of great use for risk assessors. Work will be focused on projects aiming at a comprehensive exploration of NR-driven effects using stably transfected cell lines, expanding the on-going pre-validation of transient cell lines. An extended spectrum of substances will be assessed for priority families, including major metabolites and breakdown molecules, allowing further MoA exploration, AOP and RAX development. We will develop NAMs encompassing hepatic and non-hepatic *in vitro* systems including multi-tissue cross-talk, to open the road for a refined assessment of the obesogenic effects of MDC. This will involve a deep mechanistic exploration of key cellular pathways using human *in vitro* models, but also additional 3R-compliant models and novel methods, including imagery. The goal is to produce new developments enabling the proposal of accurate NAMs based on human as well as non-human models, so to close major data gaps in the field of MDC, in close connection with other PARC topics, tasks and WPs.

Key words:

Endocrine Disrupting Chemicals, EDC, Metabolism Disrupting Chemicals, MDC, metabolic disruption, obesity, energy metabolism, fatty acid metabolism, metabolic disorders, metabolism, cellular signalling, NAM

Link to the PARC DoA

The project responds to the PARC OOs OO5, OO7, OO10, OO12, OO9 and OO11 and OO13.

The project is directly related to the PARC DoA, as it is directed towards the development of new approach

methods to allow for animal-free testing of compounds. The tests to be developed to detect metabolic disruption will close a gap for which until now no specific test systems or guidelines are in place. Thereby the project will directly contribute to improved RA and an elevated level of consumer protection in the EU.

Links within PARC (WPs/Tasks/Activities/Projects)

- WP2, Task 2.1: complementarity with guideline tests
- WP5, P5.1.1.b: link with the assessment of the fate of model EDs/MDCs and availability of major metabolites for testing.
- Task 5.2.2: link with environmental package whenever EDs are involved (e.g. data from fish can be used to inform on potential risks for human health; this is done in collaboration with Task 5.3 and Task 6.1).
- The EDC/MDC section of Task 5.2, Activity 5.2.1 Human Health, will enhance synergies and avoid overlaps with ongoing projects such as EURION, by building on knowledge and experimental systems already established or in development, but with a focus on experimental systems not yet primarily addressed in these projects, as well as by extending the spectrum of MDC and focusing on priority-listed families of substances.
- Task 5.3: use of NAMs for AOP development and effect marker validation
- WP6, Task 6.1: use of NAMs for toxicity testing
- Task 6.3: several case studies concerning with EDs

Links outside PARC

- H2020 projects HBM4EU & EDCmixrisk: compound selection.
- H2020 project cluster EURION (esp. projects GOLIATH, OBERON and EDCmet): compound selection, complementary test systems (duplication of work is avoided by focusing on other target organs and tissues), synergies in AOP and IATA development.

Key PARC Deliverables and Milestones to which the project contributes

AD5.3: (delivered)- List of first assays to be developed for prioritised endpoints. Associated Task T5.2. Leader of the deliverable: DTU, VUB. Associated Task co-leaders: DTU/VUB/MU.

D5.1: (delivered) - 1st NAMs Report. Associated Task: T5.2. Leader of the deliverable: BfR. Associated Task co-leaders: DTU/VUB/MU.

D5.4: M36 - 1st Closing data Gaps Report. Associated Task: T5.1. Leader of the deliverable: ANSES, BfR. Associated Task co-leaders: BPI/NIPH/INSA.

D5.5: M48 - 2nd New approach methodologies report. Associated Task: T5.2. Leader of the deliverable: BfR. Associated Task co-leaders: DTU/VUB/MU.

Partners List:

BfR (DE); INSERM (FR); UU IRAS (NL); U Antwerpen (BE); UU (SE); UIBK (AT); UFZ (DE); IfADo (DE); INRAE (FR)

Schedule:

Starting date: 01/05/2022 (M1)

Expected ending date: 30/04/2026 (M48)

Costs

Expected PM for the fourth year of the project: 36 PM

Expected ODC for the fourth year of the project: 19 321 €

P5.2.1.c_Y1_EDThDisruption_DTU

Project Title	T5.2a_Endocrine disruptors – Thyroid hormone system disruption		
Project Acronym (15 letters max)	ED-Thyro		
Project Manager	Louise Ramhøj louram@food.dtu.dk	DTU	Denmark
Deputy Project manager	Tamara Vanhaecke Tamara.Vanhaecke@vub.be	VUB	Denmark
	Terje Svingen tesv@food.dtu.dk	DTU	
Expected starting date PARC (Month number)	1	Expected duration	48
PARC Workpackage number	5	PARC Task/Activity/Sub-activity:	5.2.1
Project Id	P5.2.1.c_Y1_EDThDisruption_DTU		

Status: Implementation

Summary of the project

ECHA has adopted the revised OECD Guidance Document 150 (OECD 2018) in its regulatory guidance for evaluating biocides and pesticides for ED activity. Despite these relatively recent advances, current test strategies and regulations are inadequate with regard to specifically identifying thyroid hormone system disruptors (THSDs). Some *in vitro* assays (non-OECD TGs) for certain MIEs relevant for THSD are available and are currently in the process of regulatory validation (<https://ec.europa.eu/jrc/en/science-update/vitro-methods-detection-thyroid-disruptors>). However, there is still a pressing need to develop more extensive test batteries of NAMs that cover a broader range of Key Events (KEs) i.e. from MIE to AO. The goal of this project is to help fill this gap by gaining more mechanistic knowledge on THSD for targeted NAM development. In addition, this project will also help to understand key species differences in THSD, as well as IVIVE by performing targeted *in vivo* rodent studies, *in silico* assays, human relevant stem cell-derived *in vitro* systems, and utilizing zebrafish as a unique non-mammalian whole organism model fit for THSD identification. The use of *in vivo* studies (e.g. rodents) is still required to elucidate the KEs responsible for THSD-mediated AOs in order to facilitate the development of NAMs predictive of human health effects, as this causal knowledge is still unknown. In particular, rodent studies are performed to delineate toxicogenomic effects across target organs in a complex developing organism, with this information envisioned to help target biomarkers of mechanisms of action that can be exploited for further NAMs development relying on e.g. human-derived cell-based assays. Further details of this project can be found here: <https://www.frontiersin.org/articles/10.3389/ftox.2023.1189303/full>

Main expected outputs of the project

Studies will be conducted that are aimed specifically at characterizing new mechanistic knowledge to enable the development of relevant NAMs. Especially the identification of upstream MIEs or KEs for downstream AOs relevant for THSD effect outcomes, Once identified, specific KEs can be targeted for NAMs development to increase the predictive power of non-animal test data for hazard identification and/or RA purposes. The project thus focusses on points of vulnerability along the TH signalling pathway to chemical perturbation. For NAMs development, the project will examine direct versus indirect perturbation of the TH axis by exogenous agents; build a novel developmental stem cell-based assay with human relevance; characterize further the evolutionary conservation of the THS axis in order to make better use of non-human NAMs (e.g. fish, invertebrates) to inform on human health risks. New knowledge and NAMs will better enable development of a robust IATA specific for THSD.

Outcomes and impacts expected for end-users and stakeholders

The project will deliver valuable contributions to chemical safety assessors and regulators by providing evidence-based mechanistic knowledge for THSD that will enable better use of non-vertebrate animal test data for decision making. This will contribute greatly to the detection of hazardous chemical substances with focus on EDs and THSDs, thus adhering to the zero-pollution ambition of the Green Deal, as well as the Chemicals Strategy set out by the EC. Other end-users such as the chemical and cosmetic industry will benefit from gathered knowledge and developed test methods and strategies, as they may themselves adopt new and improved alternative test methods for a more rapid, reliable and cost-efficient internal testing regimen. The long-term benefit for stakeholders will be a sizeable reduction in animals used for safety testing of chemical and cosmetic substances. Stakeholders will also benefit by minimizing exposure to unwanted THSDs, possibly leading to improved public health.

Key words: Thyroid hormone system disruptors; T3; T4; endocrine; brain; liver; risk assessment

Link to the PARC DoA

The project responds to the PARC OOs OO3, OO4, OO5, OO6, OO7, OO10, OO12, OO9 and OO11. The project supports innovation by providing novel mechanistic knowledge that will be exploited for developing novel NAMs for THSD testing. The project will close much needed regulatory test-method and scientific gaps related to the thyroid hormone system and as such contribute towards improved regulation and consumer protection for THSD compounds. Cooperation with other R&I initiatives is assured through collaboration with other PARC activities related to NAMs (activity 5.2.2), systems biology (task 5.3) and IATA development and RA (tasks 6.1 and 6.3). FAIR data practice is ensured through WP9 cooperation. Communication of the project results to the research community will be done via publication in peer-reviewed journals and participation in congresses.

Links within PARC (WPs/Tasks/Activities/Projects)

- WP2 Task 2.1: complementarity with guideline tests
- WP3: Synergies, Communication and awareness
- WP5: A5.2.2: link with environmental package whenever EDs and THDs are involved (e.g. data from fish can be used to inform on potential risks for human health; this is done in collaboration with A5.2.2, 5.3 and 6.1).
- Task 5.3: use of NAMs for AOP development and effect marker validation
- WP6 Task 6.1: use of NAMs for toxicity testing. Task 6.3: several case studies of which some concerned with EDs and THSDs (e.g., case study 10)
- WP7: DMP
- WP9: Training, laboratory network

Links outside PARC

- H2020 projects – EURION cluster: “Assays for the identification of Thyroid Hormone axis - disrupting chemicals: Elaborating Novel Assessment strategies” (ATHENA) project, “Screening for Endocrine Disruptors” (SCREENED) project and “Endocrine Guideline Optimisation” (ERGO) project
- Green Deal projects: PANORAMIX project

Key PARC Deliverables and Milestones to which the project contributes

AD5.2: (delivered)- Report of the description of the EOGRT study to be conducted. Associated Task: T5.1
 Leader of the deliverable: ANSES, BfR. Associated Task co-leaders: BPI/NIPH/INSA. It was planned that the project managers would contribute to this deliverable, but in the end it was not necessary.

AD5.3: (delivered)- List of first assays to be developed for prioritised endpoints. Associated Task T5.2.
 Leader of the deliverable: DTU, VUB. Associated Task co-leaders: DTU/VUB/MU

D5.1: (delivered) - 1st NAMs Report. Associated Task: T5.2. Leader of the deliverable: BfR. Associated Task co-leaders: DTU/VUB/MU.

D5.3: (delivered) - 1st new AOPs Report. Associated Task: T5.3. Leader of the deliverable: INSERM.
 Associated Task co-leaders: UL-LACDR/SCIENSANO/Fraunhofer.

D5.5: M48 - 2nd New approach methodologies report. Associated Task: T5.2. Leader of the deliverable: BfR. Associated Task co-leaders: DTU/VUB/MU.

Partners List:

DTU (Denmark); VUB (Belgium), BfR (Germany); SDU (Denmark); UAntwerpen (Belgium); VUA (Netherlands); ISCIII (Spain); INSERM (France)

Schedule:

Starting date: 01/05/2022 (M1)

Expected ending date: 30/04/2026 (M48)

Costs

Expected PM for the fourth year of the project: 89 PM

Expected ODC for the fourth year of the project: 55 040 €

P5.2.1.d_Y1_Immunotox_Inserm

Project Title	Immunotoxicity		
Project Acronym (15 letters max)	Immunotox		
Project Manager	Etienne Blanc etienne.blanc@u-paris.fr	Inserm	France
Deputy Project manager	Saadia Kerdine saadia.kerdine-romer@u-psud.fr	Université Paris Sud	France
Expected starting date PARC (Month number)	1	Expected duration	48*
PARC Workpackage number	5	PARC Task/Activity/Sub-activity:	5.2.1
Project Id	P5.2.1.d_Y1_Immunotox_Inserm		

*The project has been extended from M36 to M48

Status: Implementation

Summary of the project

During the first three years of PARC and in line with regulatory needs we will develop research aiming at characterizing new NAMs addressing three major endpoints in immunotoxicity: organ-related immunotoxicity with a focus on respiratory toxicity and sensitization; immunosuppression, in particular through response to vaccination; characterizing new models for cellular immunotoxicity assessing KEs. The major outcome will be the development of NAMs in these immunotoxicity areas. For this, reference chemicals will be used and once the NAMs are developed, PARC priority substances will be tested when relevant. These new NAMs will be used for the development of AOP (T5.3) and the development of IATA (T6.1).

Regulatory relevance:

- REACH: several immune related outcomes are relevant for REACH: skin sensitization, respiratory sensitization, immunosuppression. Currently under REACH, the immunotoxicity investigations are triggered based on repeated dose toxicity studies (28- or 90-day) in case there are some indications of immunotoxicity. If indications of immunosuppression are seen, one can include e.g. Cohort 3 into the study design of EOGRTS (developmental immunotoxicity) or request to have an immunotoxicity investigation included in a standard repeated dose toxicity study (adult immunotoxicity).
- CLP (Reg EC 1272/2008): While respiratory sensitization is mentioned as a hazard in the CLP regulation, it is acknowledged, that there is no respective method to detect respiratory sensitizers.

Hence, a need to develop methods to detect respiratory sensitizers is recognized. On top of that the CLP regulation foresees that non-animal testing is conducted wherever possible, implying support for the development of NAMs.

- PPPR (Reg EC 1107/2009) and biocides (Reg EC 528/2012): Sensitization is analysed as part of the data requirements for PPP and biocides. The need to develop methods for respiratory sensitization as well as alternative testing strategies is recognized.
- Cosmetic products: skin sensitization
- FCM (Regulation (EC) No 1935/2004): allergenicity
- Food contaminants (Regulation (EC) No 1881/2006) and enzymes (Regulation (EC) No 1332/2008): allergenicity
- Chemicals strategy: Immunotoxicity is listed as one of the top priority hazard classes in the chemicals strategy (COM(2020) 667 final, 2020).

Main expected outputs of the project

This project will deliver a set of *in vitro* systems that allow the assay of KEs in the immune system function or dysfunction. New parameters will be developed to better explore the immune system cellular content and activity, cytokine and antibody production and release, as well as the effect of signaling. Different primary cell systems and cell lines as well as epithelial and immune cell co-cultures will be characterized. Depending on the advancement of the work on the characterization of the NAMs, interlaboratory validation can be considered. A specific discussion on this topic will be held in fall. Before that, in June/July, a list of reference compounds will be decided within labs working on the same topics and/or same models, which could be used for the interlaboratory testing process. In fact, first we thought to perform this pre-validation within the project (5.2.1d and perhaps other labs within WP5 working on immunotox (mycotoxin group and Bisphenol Alternative group)). This will push ourselves to produce SOP and will challenge the NAM before going to a more official and formal process (through for example EU-NETVAL network). This subject will also probably be part of the new immunotox project for Y4/7.

The global aim is to provide task 5.3 and WP6 with assays and data that will support the build-up of AOPs and IATAs through a better characterization of KEs in NAMs. For example, if we show that chemicals that activate a receptor, also induce the expression of cytokine genes in an immune cell, this will support the relationship between receptor activation (MIE) and cytokine production (KE) and therefore the build up of an AOP.

Outcomes and impacts expected for end-users and stakeholders

The project will be helpful from a risk assessor's perspective because the innovative methods developed therein will allow rapid mechanistic hazard analysis of a high number of substances thus contributing to detection of hazardous substances, to the Zero Pollution Ambition of the Green Deal and to The Chemicals Strategy. Additionally, the methods will be able to screen mixtures thus contributing to the aforementioned EU strategies. In addition, the project will be helpful to other end-users like applicants from industry as *in vitro* methods they will be rapid, reliable and cost efficient. Stakeholders will see benefits in the reduction of animal testing, the identification and regulation of hazardous substances and ultimately in the benefits for public health ultimately resulting from the regulatory implementation of the assays.

Key words: immunotoxicity, sensitization, immunosuppression, vaccination, inflammation, NAMs, tests, AOPs

Link to the PARC DoA

The project responds to the PARC OOs OO3, OO4, OO5, OO6, OO7, OO10, OO12, OO9 and OO11. The aim of PARC is to develop new toxicity tests in compliance with the 3R concept, particularly in outcomes that have been prioritized in the chemical strategy for sustainability. Immunotoxicity is one of these outcomes and this project directly addresses this objective. By developing new NAMs that are biologically and regulatorily relevant, this project addresses the PARC objective of developing new models and innovative concepts for regulatory RA. A working group was set up around four major themes:

respiratory immunotoxicity and sensitization, immunosuppression including response to vaccination, immunostimulation, and barrier immunity.

Links within PARC (WPs/Tasks/Activities/Projects)

- WP2, Task 2.1: complementarity with guidelines tests
- WP4, Task 4.1: immunotoxicity studies in human (the COVID-19 vaccination study)
- WP5, Task 5.2: complementarity with environmental immunotoxicity, Task 5.3: use of NAMs for AOP development and effect marker validation
- WP6, Task 6.1: use of NAM for IATA/DA validation for regulatory purposes: NAM will be developed that feed into these IATAs.

Links outside PARC

H2020 project on persistent and mobile chemicals (PFAS), EHEN projects on immune effects of the exposome: “Human Exposomic Determinants of Immune Mediated diseases” (Hedimed) and “Mapping Exposure-Induced Immune Effects: Connecting the Exposome and the Immunome” (Eximious), EURION projects, including Oberon, Goliath, EDCmet, “Animal-free Safety assessment of chemicals: Project cluster for Implementation of novel Strategies” (ASPIS) projects including “Ontology-driven and artificial intelligence-based repeated dose toxicity testing of chemicals for next generation risk assessment” (Ontox), RISKHUNT3R, PrecisionTox, “Understanding human exposure and health hazard of micro- and nanoplastic contaminants in our environment” (POLYRISK), Aurora, “Virtual Human Platform for Safety Assessment” (VHP4Safety), MOMENTUM, EFSA (sensitization), new ENKORE cluster.

Key PARC Deliverables and Milestones to which the project contributes

- AD5.2: (delivered)- Report of the description of the EOGRT study to be conducted. Associated Task: T5.1
 Leader of the deliverable: ANSES, BfR. Associated Task co-leaders: BPI/NIPH/INSA. It was planned that the project managers would contribute to this deliverable, but in the end it was not necessary.
- AD5.3: (delivered)- List of first assays to be developed for prioritised endpoints. Associated Task T5.2.
 Leader of the deliverable: DTU, VUB. Associated Task co-leaders: DTU/VUB/MU
- D5.1: (delivered) - 1st NAMs Report. Associated Task: T5.2. Leader of the deliverable: BfR. Associated Task co-leaders: DTU/VUB/MU.
- D5.5: M48 - 2nd New approach methodologies report. Associated Task: T5.2. Leader of the deliverable: BfR. Associated Task co-leaders: DTU/VUB/MU.

Partners List:

INSERM (France), NIPH (Norway), MUI (Austria), NCPHP (Hungary), RIVM (Netherlands), IRAS (Netherlands), UL-FFA (Slovenia), INSA (Portugal), UFZ (Germany), WR (Netherlands), LIH (Luxemburg), LIST (Luxemburg)

Schedule:

Starting date: 01/05/2022 (M1)
 Expected ending date: 30/04/2026 (M48)

Costs

Expected PM for the fourth year of the project: 121 PM
 Expected ODC for the fourth year of the project: 55 834 €

P5.2.1.e_Y1_DNT-ANT_UFZ_IUF_NIPH

Project Title	Neurotoxicity		
Project Acronym (15 letters max)	DNT / NT		
Project Manager	Tamara Tal tamara.tal@ufz.de	UFZ	Germany

Deputy Project manager	Oddvar Myhre Oddvar.Myhre@fhi.no	NIPH (from Q2 2023)	Norway
	Ellen Fritsche //Joëlle Rüegg	IUF/UU (until Q2 2023)	Germany/Sweden
Expected starting date PARC (Month number)	1	Expected duration	48*
PARC Workpackage number	5	PARC Task/Activity/Sub-activity:	5.2.1
Project Id	P5.2.1.e_Y1_DNT-ANT_UFZ_IUF_UU (until Q2 2023) P5.2.1.e_Y1_DNT-ANT_UFZ_NIPH (from Q2 2023)		

*The project has been extended from M36 to M48

Status: Implementation

Summary of the project

DNT and acute neurotoxicity (ANT) are currently assessed via different OECD guideline studies and with different REACH standard information requirements. DNT/ANT guideline studies are extraordinarily resource-intensive and therefore not suited for studying adverse effects of large numbers of chemicals. Therefore, there is international consensus, strongly supported by EFSA and the OECD (1), that DNT testing must be faster and more human-relevant by implementing an alternative DNT testing battery for regulatory purposes. The current state-of-the-art is the use of an DNT IVB comprised of several human- and rat-based *in vitro* test methods covering key neurodevelopmental processes, e.g., neural progenitor cell proliferation, differentiation of neurons and oligodendrocytes, and apoptosis. While this represents a step forward towards establishing an alternative DNT testing regime, there are gaps in the DNT IVB including human synaptogenesis, human neural network formation, myelination, and behavioral correlates for the rodent *in vivo* studies including behavior, sensory function, learning and memory endpoints.

The main goal of 5.2.1e is to build second generation NAMs that fill these gaps. To demonstrate the potential added value of the NAMs, the same set of chemicals will be tested across the DNT IVB and 5.2.1e NAMs. Based on these comparative data of hazard classification and potency determinations, we will ultimately make recommendations about the potential inclusion of second generation NAMs in a second generation of the DNT IVB. An additional goal of 5.2.1e is to generate a test battery for acute/adult neurotoxicity.

Main expected outputs of the project

- New NAMs that fill the current DNT IVB gaps. Here, test methods will be set up from existing test systems (human stem cell-based systems, zebrafish).
- New NAMs for ANT. Current test systems will be used for test method set-up (human stem cell-based systems, zebrafish).

Outcomes and impacts expected for end-users and stakeholders

- Additional IVB NAMs developed for DNT/ANT will provide risk assessors with rapid mechanistic hazard analysis supporting the green deal and the chemicals strategy.
- Mixture screening in these NAMs contributing to the aforementioned EU strategies.
- Industry will be strongly supported by developed NAMs as they will serve as valid tools for pre-screening and in-house prioritization based on rapid, reliable and cost-efficient methods.
- NGOs and consumers will see benefits in the reduction of animal testing, identification and regulation of hazardous substances and ultimately, in the benefits for public health upon regulatory implementation of the assays.

Keywords: Developmental neurotoxicity (DNT), Acute neurotoxicity (ANT), Alternative DNT testing battery, *in vitro* testing battery (IVB), New Approach methodologies (NAMs)

Link to the PARC DoA

In the EU Green Deal strategy, the CSS specifically mentions neurotoxicity (DNT/ANT) as well as ED-DNT as critical outcomes. Moreover, mental and behavioral health are part of the children's health protection policy. Due to large data gaps, DNT has been recognized as a serious public health concern by many countries and regulatory agencies world-wide. The OECD provides the umbrella for current regulatory DNT efforts including the production of a guidance document for regulatory use of the DNT IVB. Within PARC, gaps within the DNT IVB will be closed and an ANT IVB will be established.

5.2.1.e will generate transparent criteria for inclusion of NAMs in a testing battery for DNT/ANT hazard identification and chemical prioritisation. Via interaction with WP6 partners, we will actively foster regulatory uptake of PARC knowledge. 5.2.1.e members are part of multiple other tasks and projects and will work to promote cooperation with other R&I initiatives. (OO3, OO4, OO9, OO11, OO12). Project members are engaged in EU-level projects with public dissemination mechanisms. Members will additionally interact with the public via social media and press releases describing our work. (OO5, OO6). All members will release underlying data upon publication, in line with FAIR data practices (OO10). We will develop ANT/DNT NAM-based testing strategies to revolutionize RA for neurotoxic chemicals and work with RA's to proactively address concerns and promote implementation.

Links within PARC (WPs/Tasks/Activities/Projects)

- WP4: Make use of results from HBM studies for prioritizing HA.
- WP5, T5.1. Toxicity testing to address chemicals of concern. T5.3: Quantitative systems toxicology and development of new AOPs that are relevant for DNT/ANT.
- WP6, T6.1: Delivering IATAs ready for regulatory application. WP 5.2 will provide data, tools and concepts to improve RA in general. DNT (ANT is to be clarified) is a priority area for developing qAOP but not in the first round (ED, non-genotoxic carcinogenesis and liver are first).
- WP7: DMP. We will link with WP7 to make our data available, as soon as possible, for regulators, external researchers, and public. We need access to a database where we can store data, with immediate access for regulators and embargo dates for public use.

Links outside PARC

ENDpoiNTs and other projects within the EURION cluster. In ENDpoiNTs, a battery of assays (in silico, in vitro and in vivo) are developed that detect ED-induced DNT.

- ONTOX, Precisiontox and RiskHunter of the ASPIS cluster.
- H2020 Panoramix (panoramix-h2020.eu)
- US-EPA for common data analysis and DNT IVB assembly.
- “The Exposome from Evidence to Translation” (ATHLETE) project of the EHEN cluster (athleteproject.eu).
- VHP4Safety
- HBM Platform Austria
- EFSA Brain Health Consortium

Key PARC Deliverables (and Milestones to which the project contributes)

AD5.2: (delivered)- Report of the description of the EOGRT study to be conducted. Associated Task: T5.1
 Leader of the deliverable: ANSES, BfR. Associated Task co-leaders: BPI/NIPH/INSA. It was planned that the project managers would contribute to this deliverable, but in the end it was not necessary.

AD5.3: (delivered)- List of first assays to be developed for prioritised endpoints. Associated Task T5.2.
 Leader of the deliverable: DTU, VUB. Associated Task co-leaders: DTU/VUB/MU.

D5.1: (delivered) - 1st NAMs Report. Associated Task: T5.2. Leader of the deliverable: BfR. Associated Task co-leaders: DTU/VUB/MU.

D5.5: M48 - 2nd New approach methodologies report. Associated Task: T5.2. Leader of the deliverable: BfR. Associated Task co-leaders: DTU/VUB/MU.

Partners List:

INSERM-UBX (FR); UU (SE); NIPH (NO); IUF (DE); UKON (DE); RIVM (NL); UFZ (DE); ISCIII (ES); TiHo (DE); AIT (AT); NMBU (NO); UG-PL (PL); BfR (DE); UOB (UK)

Schedule:

Starting date: 01/05/2022 (M1)

Expected ending date: 30/04/2026 (M48)

Costs

Expected PM for the fourth year of the project: 133 PM

Expected ODC for the fourth year of the project: 178 101 €

P5.2.1.f_Y4_DART-ED_DTU

Project Title	Developmental and Reproductive Toxicity - Endocrine Disruption		
Project Acronym (15 letters max)	DART-ED		
Project Manager	Terje Svingen tesv@food.dtu.dk	DTU Food	Denmark
Deputy Project manager	Dries Knapen Dries.knapen@uantwerpen.be	UAntwerpen	Belgium
Expected starting date PARC (Month number)	M37	Expected duration (months)	45
PARC Workpackage number	WP5	PARC Task/Activity/Sub-activity:	T5.2.2
Project Id	P5.2.1.f_Y4_DART-ED_DTU		

Status: Initiation

Summary of the project

This project will address current gaps in ED identification related to developmental and reproductive toxicity (DART) outcomes. The studies will focus on characterizing new mechanistic knowledge to support the development of relevant NAMs and the refinement of AOPs under other PARC activities. This work aligns with current regulatory needs by addressing key aspects of DART, including Estrogen, Androgen, Thyroid, and Steroidogenesis (EATS) regulation, as well as non-EATS modalities and chemical perturbation vulnerabilities, particularly in sensitive life stages. The project will also focus on developing NAMs capable of testing multiple modalities within a single assay, incorporating crosstalk between EAS and T signaling axes.

Project outcomes will align with regulatory processes/frameworks, including the CSS Towards a Toxic-free Environment by supporting challenges posed by hazardous chemicals such as EDs, the REACH by providing new tools and knowledge for investigating EDs when triggered, the CLP, by providing support for development and use of NAMs for ED identification, the Plant Protection and Biocidal Products regulation by developing more sensitive methods for EATS as well as animal-free alternative testing strategies, and the Cosmetics Regulation (EC) N° 1223/2009, again by providing new NAMs and added support for existing NAMs.

Main expected outputs of the project:

The project will provide valuable contributions to chemical safety assessors and regulators by delivering evidence-based mechanistic knowledge for DART-ED, facilitating the increased adoption of non-animal test data for ED identification and decision-making. This work will significantly enhance the availability

of methods for detecting EDs, supporting the zero-pollution ambition of the Green Deal and the EC's Chemicals Strategy. Specifically, the project will:

- Deliver ED endpoints for addition to fish TG both for non-protected (TG 236) and protected life stages (e.g., TG210 which is required under Annex IX of REACH).
- Deliver ED endpoints for placenta toxicity, relevant for both reproduction and development
- Advance in vitro models for male steroidogenesis and testis function.

Outcomes and impacts expected on end-users and stakeholders:

Methods for the combined evaluation of DART-ED in non-mammalian models for environmental health are currently lacking. This project will expand on T modality method development and broaden coverage for ED, addressing needs in the evolving regulatory landscape. Additionally, no validated NAMs currently assess ED effects on placental angiogenesis. This project will develop a new method to replicate the angiogenic and endocrine properties of the human placenta, enabling the identification of EDs that disrupt its proper development. The adequacy of the only validated in vitro assay for male steroidogenesis (H295R steroidogenesis assay, OECD TG 456) is questionable, as it relies on a female adrenal cell line. This project will contribute to the development of more physiologically relevant in vitro models, enhancing NAM batteries for male reproductive assessment. Finally, hiPSC-derived spermatogenesis protocols to scrutinize epigenetic re-programming in response ED exposure will be further developed.

Outcomes and impacts expected to be incorporated into a specific regulatory framework:

There are currently no REACH standard data requirements for ED identification in the environment. This project will focus on broadening DART-ED coverage in fish, building on and complementing the ongoing validation of THSD-sensitive endpoints for inclusion in existing OECD Fish TG. Integration into REACH requirements (e.g., TG 210 under Annex IX) will facilitate their use in REACH/CLP. Additionally, fish ED assays developed through this work will be valuable for PPP, BP, and cosmetics regulation. The availability of a placenta assay will further support CLP for reproductive toxicants. Re-assessment of regulatory TG augmentation possibilities for effects on spermatogenesis will be evaluated.

Key words: endocrine disruptors, EDC, NAM, reproduction, developmental toxicity

Link to the PARC DoA:

The project responds to the PARC OOs OO4, OO6, OO10, OO12, OO9, OO11, OO13.

The project addresses a pressing need for new methods for ED evaluation in the continuously evolving regulatory landscape (e.g., ED criteria under CLP). Project partners are actively involved in stakeholder groups (e.g. OECD, ECHA, EFSA) ensuring direct alignment with regulatory needs and rapid uptake.

Links within PARC (WPs/Tasks/Activities/Projects):

- WP2
 - T2.1 Complementarity with guideline tests
- WP5
 - T5.3 Use of NAMs for AOP development and effect marker validation
 - P5.1.2.b: BPA alternative ENV. closing data gaps and developing NAMs. Activity i-ii: Investigation of the potential adverse effects (e.g. apical endpoints such as mortality, effects related to the anticipated MoA or MIE, effects on reproduction, effects on endocrine system) of certain individual substances and “real-life” mixtures of BPA alternatives on non-mammalian organisms belonging to different taxa Activity v: Development / advancing alternative 3R-compatible vertebrate aquatic models for environmental HA of BPA alternatives and other prioritized chemicals.
 - T5.3.2 Development of AOPs for ED (SG2)
- WP6

- T6.1 Use of NAMs for IATA development and IATA case studies
- T6.3 Case studies involving EDs

Links outside PARC:

- ENKORE Cluster: “Merging scientific Evidence with Regulatory practices and Leveraging identification Of endocrine disruptors using New approach methodologies” (MERLON) project
- MSCA Doctoral Network (NeXED)
- Denmark-EPA Pesticide Programme (PeT)

Key PARC Deliverables (or Additional Deliverables) and Milestones to which the project contributes

D5.5: 2nd New approach methodologies report (M48)

D5.8: 3rd New approach methodologies report (M60)

D5.12: 4th New approach methodologies report (M81)

Partners List:

DTU (DK), UAntwerpen (BE), VUB (BE), ISS (IT), MU (CZ), NMBU (NO), SDU (DK), UKHSA (UK)

Schedule:

Starting date: 01/05/2025 (M37)

Expected ending date: 31/01/2029 (M81)

Costs

Expected PM for the first year of the project: 62 PM

Expected ODC for the first year of the project: 106 008 €

P5.2.1.g_Y4_DIT-NAM_INSERM

Project Title	Developmental Immunotoxicity - NAM development		
Project Acronym (15 letters max)	DIT-NAM		
Project Manager	Saadia Kerdine-Römer saadia.kerdine-romer@universite-paris-saclay.fr	Universite Paris Saclay	France
Deputy Project manager	Birgitte Lindeman Nicola M. Smith Birgitte.lindeman@fhi.no Nicolamargareta.smith@fhi.no	Norwegian Institute of Public Health	Norway
Expected starting date PARC (Month number)	M37	Expected duration (months)	45
PARC Workpackage number	WP5	PARC Task/Activity/Sub-activity:	5.2.1
Project Id	P5.2.1.g_Y4_DIT-NAM_INSERM		

Status: Initiation

Summary of the project

In EU chemical regulations, the current approaches are considered to lack sensitivity for identification of immunotoxicants. This is mainly due to the limited assessment of changes in immune system function included in the current tests. Currently, the T-cell dependent antibody response (TDAR) assay included in

the extended EOGRT study is the only functional immunotoxicity endpoint included in the test requirements. Furthermore, the Developmental Immunotoxicity (DIT) cohort is only included in the EOGRT study if triggered, and there is a general lack of accepted sensitive triggers. Hence, very few chemicals are tested for their potential to cause DIT. These limitations are highlighted by ECHA in their KARC document in which they identify DIT as a regulatory need and a proposed area for further research within PARC. The short-term aims highlighted by ECHA involve identifying critical windows in immune system development, evaluating existing NAM methodologies, and considering the need for further NAM development. In the long term, research efforts should focus shifts to developing and validating a NAM testing battery for DIT assessment and exploring its use in regulatory contexts, including screening and hazard identification.

This project will be divided into two different subprojects:

- 1) Non-lab: Identification of critical developmental windows and processes to support NAM development through physiological mapping, collaboration with Center for Alternatives to Animal Testing (CAAT) DIT alternatives, and alignment with AOP development
- 2) Lab-based: NAM development and their use in regulatory testing (Stem cell models, zebrafish studies, modifying existing immunotox assays for DIT)

Main expected outputs of the project:

The project will deliver updated information on immune system development and sensitive windows during development. The information will be made available to the community in the form of a “living” physiological map. The project will in the short-term perspective adapt existing assays and NAMs developed in WP5.2.1 for DIT screening, prioritisation and RAx purposes. In the longer term, and guided by the updated information presented in physiological maps, the project will develop novel NAMs to evaluate the impact of chemicals on the developing immune system to reduce and replace animal testing.

Outcomes and impacts expected on end-users and stakeholders:

Subproject 1 (non-laboratory activities):

There is limited human data available on the development of the immune system, but recent studies and ongoing projects are providing valuable new information. The physiological map will serve as a new method to support the proposed paradigm shift away from the exclusive use of animal testing to the application of human-relevant approaches by modelling critical developmental steps *in vitro*. It will synthesise the spatial and temporal dynamics of human immune system development, serving as a tool to identify critical processes for assay development and knowledge gaps for targeted research.

Subproject 2: (lab-based):

Adaptation of existing methods and development of novel NAMs will ultimately contribute to fill data gaps, reducing reliance on animal testing and support development of efficient RA tools. By generating human-relevant data, the project will enhance DIT evaluation, reduce reliance on animal testing, and improve regulatory decision-making, ultimately benefiting public health and safety.

Outcomes and impacts expected to be incorporated into a specific regulatory framework:

See above or detailed objective and how these can be incorporated into a specific regulatory framework. Additionally, the physiological maps and the adapted and novel NAMs will contribute to the knowledge base and test battery needed if a new hazard class for immunotoxic substances will eventually be included in the CLP classification.

Key words: developing human immune system, immunotoxicity, NAMs, physiological maps, network modelling

Link to the PARC DoA:

The project responds to the PARC OOs OO3, OO4, OO5, OO6, OO10, OO12, OO9, and OO11.

004: The project will align closely with ECHA's KARC report, which outlines the regulatory challenges related to DIT. Additionally, the project will actively seek input from the ECHA PARC team and from other regulatory or scientific agencies including EFSA, to ensure the efficient use of resources from an early stage, addressing urgent needs such as NAMs/ *in vitro* test battery covering DIT endpoints and closing knowledge gaps, including identifying sensitive timepoints for immune system development. This proactive approach will foster the regulatory uptake of PARC knowledge, enhancing regulatory decision-making processes.

005: Subproject 1, which focuses on physiological mapping, is also a key component of the ONTOX project. To ensure a harmonized approach, we will maintain ongoing interaction and coordination with the ONTOX project. Similarly, the CAAT DIT Alternatives project shares the goal of advancing non-animal methods for detecting DIT. We will ensure close collaboration with regular information exchange to align efforts and maximize synergies between these parallel initiatives.

009: The project will focus on developing *in vitro* models, avoiding animal use, to capture early disruptions that chemicals may cause to the sensitive developing immune system. Expanding knowledge in this field will enhance the acceptability of these models by regulatory bodies. The project will also include procedure standardizations to support future acceptance in RA processes (e.g assessing test readiness), working closely on related AOPs/physiological maps to ensure alignment with regulatory use.

0010: In the context of PARC, WP7 is developing template(s) to collect FAIR data. WP5 leaders and Task leaders are currently discussing the way to implement FAIR data practices.

0012: The new NAMs developed in this project are based on novel concepts, advanced analytical methods, and cutting-edge scientific knowledge. There is a focus on ensuring they are able to be applied in Integrated Testing Strategies (ITS) or IATA, with a focus on high-throughput screening of molecules to support RA processes. From the initiation of the work there will be regular contact with regulators to ensure their need will be met.

Links within PARC (WPs/Tasks/Activities/Projects):

- WP5
 - T5.3.2: Use of NAMs for AOP development and effect marker identification
 - T5.1.1.b: Human tox BPA *In vitro* assays for immunotoxicity
 - T5.2.1d: NAM development for the mature immune system
 - WP6
 - T6.1: IATA development activities, possibility to explore an IATA case study for a DIT endpoint
- Within WP5, the AOP development work (Specialist Group 1: Immunotoxicity) in 5.3.2 and NAM development (in the extension of the immunotoxicity NAM development project 5.2.1d) will closely collaborate. There is overlap in the leadership of these tasks and other partners. The three projects all aim to advance the tools available to capture modulating effects of chemical contaminants on the immune system and to make the data usable for the RA process (and minimising the use of animals).

Links outside PARC:

- CAAT DIT alternatives initiative – Working groups members
- Establishment of human induced pluripotent stem cell (hiPSC)-based assays for testing for DIT *in vitro* (Germany – IUF).
- “Understanding how endocrine disruptors and chemical mixtures of concern target the immune system to trigger or perpetuate disease” ([endomix](#)) (EU-funded project)
- “Environmental stressors as causal determinants for immune-mediated diseases” (EXPOSIM) (EU-funded project)

Key PARC Deliverables (or Additional Deliverables) and Milestones to which the project contributes

D5.5: 2nd New approach methodologies report (M48)
 D5.8: 3rd New approach methodologies report (M60)
 D5.12: 4th New approach methodologies report (M81)

Partners List:

INSERM (FR), NIPH (NO), IUF (DE), Wageningen Food Safety Research (NL), LIH (LU), MUI (AT), UFZ (DE), RIVM (NL), NCPHP (HU), NMBU (NO), UMIL (IT)

Schedule:

Starting date: 01/05/2025 (M37)
 Expected ending date: 31/01/2029 (M81)

Costs

Expected PM for the first year of the project: 93 PM
 Expected ODC for the first year of the project: 151 896 €

P5.2.1.h_Y4_SDHEPATOX_ANSES

Project Title	Sexual dimorphism associated to susceptibility to hepatotoxicity of environmental contaminants		
Project Acronym (15 letters max)	SDHEPATOX		
Project Manager	Ludovic Le Hegarat ludovic.lehegarat@anses.fr	ANSES	France
Deputy Project manager	Tamara Vanhaecke Tamara.Vanhaecke@vub.be	VUB	Belgium
Expected starting date PARC (Month number)	M37	Expected duration (months)	24
PARC Workpackage number	WP5	PARC Task/Activity/Sub-activity:	5.2.1
Project Id	P5.2.1.h_Y4_SDHEPATOX_ANSES		

Status: Initiation

Summary of the project

The liver is one of the most sexually dimorphic organs, and the hepatic metabolic pathways subject to sexual dimorphism include the metabolism of xenobiotics, amino acids and lipids. Thus, sex-related biological and physiological differences will influence individual sensitivity and the impact of exposure to chemicals on human health. For example, women are more likely than men to suffer acute liver failure, and 70% of all cases of acute liver failure occur in women. Animal studies can take sexual dimorphism into account by selecting the most sensitive sex for *in vivo* studies. However, *in vitro* models and methods used to characterise the toxicity of contaminants do not yet make it possible to predict individual susceptibility linked to sexual dimorphism.

It is therefore important and urgent to take into account hepatic sexual dimorphism in the assessment of the toxicological effects of environmental contaminants in *in vitro* studies and to integrate this knowledge into the development of NAMs from a regulatory point of view.

The aim of this project is to contribute to the improvement of current *in vitro* methods for assessing chemical-induced hepatotoxicity by integrating sexual dimorphism parameters in different hepatic cell models (primary human hepatocytes, HepaRG, hepatic cells derived from multipotent stem cells (mSC) and induced pluripotent stem cells (iPSC)). This will increase our understanding of the underlying

mechanisms of sex-specific hepatic adverse responses.

The project will align with work under Task 5.2.1 and T5.3 as well as WP6 and takes into account the ongoing work of the OECD expert group on NGTxCs and ED. In fact, an OECD expert group is working on the development of an IATA for NGTxCs and is attempting to identify mechanistic assays that could be implemented as part of this strategy. Consequently, the SDHepatox project could provide future in vitro methods for identifying and characterising NGTX.

Outputs of the project:

The expected outcome of this project is to improve the acceptability at international level of IVB using NAMs, by taking into account sexual dimorphism during chemical safety assessment strategies for human health. IVB may include assays for hepatotoxicity, endocrine disruption, and metabolic disruption. Specific examples of test batteries will be selected based on their relevance to the chemicals under study and their role in existing or emerging regulatory frameworks.

By combining multiple human hepatic models with integrated sexual dimorphism characteristics during HA we will gain insights in the underlying sex-dependent mechanisms of adversity. In addition, an integrated analysis of measured responses in the models of each partner will be conducted for the evaluation of (sex-specific) hepatotoxicity.

Outcomes and impacts expected on end-users and stakeholders:

Currently, sexual dimorphism is not taken into account in the assessment of the toxicity of environmental contaminants, particularly in the context of the development of NAMs. Therefore, the project will be particularly helpful from a risk assessor’s perspective because the innovative methodology developed therein will allow for the first time the integration of sexual dimorphism and sex-specific response in hazard analysis of chemicals, and ultimately, resulting from the regulatory implementation of the assays, the protection of public health and the environment.

Outcomes and impacts expected to be incorporated into a specific regulatory framework:

This proposal must be considered a PoC approach to assess the biological relevance of sexual dimorphism in an in vitro context; including assessments of chemical-specific responses (e.g. EDCs).

This approach will improve our mechanistic understanding which is a requirement to develop new and/or refine already existing in vitro test systems/NAMs for a specific context of use. If the PoC data show robust biological differences, all NAMs currently (or planned) part of a regulatory framework can be impacted. Before this becomes concrete, further qualification and validation of these in vitro assays is needed. However, even without full validation, NAMs may contribute to Weight-of-Evidence (WoE) evaluations in combination with other data sources, such as animal studies, in silico models, or historical data.

Key words: HepaRG, mPSC-Hep, iPS, Hepatotoxicity, sexual dimorphism, male, female, High-content screening, metabolomics, MoA

Link to the PARC DoA:

The project responds to the PARC OOs OO3, OO4, OO5, OO6, OO7, OO10, OO12, OO9, OO11.

The project is directly related to the PARC DoA, as it is focused on improving NAMs aimed at enabling animal-free testing of compounds. This advancement will incorporate considerations of sexual dimorphism, closing a significant gap that has previously not been integrated and for which no specific test systems or regulatory guidelines are in place. Consequently, the project will directly contribute to improved RA processes and elevated the level of consumer protection standards within the EU.

The OECD, and other international regulatory authorities, have already recognized the urgent need for improvements in in vitro toxicity testing.

Links within PARC (WPs/Tasks/Activities/Projects):

- WP5
 - T5.2: Link to T5.2.1.a_ NGTXCs, this NGTXCs project aims at filling this data gap by improving and implementing various test systems that address different aspects of carcinogenic mechanisms, therefore the models developed in the SDhepatox project could be also used to improve the capacities of in vitro to detect potential carcinogens. The consortium of SDHepatox are also implicated in WP5.2.a.1 that will facilitate the dissemination between the 2 projects
 - T5.2: Link to T5.2.1.b SDHepatox will propose innovative model to take account gender specificity in the characterisation of compounds that induce metabolic disorders. Progress of the SDHepatox project will be shared with the 5.2.1.b during the annual meeting.
- WP6
 - T6.1: Use of NAMs for IATA development and IATA case studies

Links outside PARC:

- ASPIS Cluster
- EFSA – ADME4NGRA
- OECD

Key PARC Deliverables and Milestones to which the project contributes

D5.5: 2nd New approach methodologies report (M48)

D5.8: 3rd New approach methodologies report (M60)

Partners List:

ANSES (FR), BfR (DE), VUB (BE)

Schedule:

Starting date: 01/05/2025 (M37)

Expected ending date: 30/04/2027 (M60)

Costs

Expected PM for the first year of the project: 24 PM

Expected ODC for the first year of the project: 59 625 €

A5.2.2 Innovative methods and tools for toxicity testing and modelling for Environmental Toxicology / Ecotoxicology

No project submitted at present.

T5.3 Quantitative systems toxicology and development of new AOPs - 5 PROJECTS

This task will contribute to the development of AOPs and provide data for the improvement of Physiologically Based Toxicokinetic (PBTK) models. It further aims to integrate relevant human disease models and develop concepts facilitating IVIVE. For this, systems biology methodology will be applied to *in silico*, *in vivo* and *in vitro* data (biochemical data, omics, endpoints). New data generated in tasks 5.1 and 5.2 as well as relevant data from databases will be mapped to existing (networks of) AOPs, with the aim to hypothesise AOs. Available literature will be automatically explored to fill gaps in AOPs and to link priority chemicals to events in AOPs using text mining and network analysis tools. This will support the identification and biological characterisation of effect markers that can, later on, be used in WP4. Using bioinformatic tools, this will allow informing human disease mechanisms based on omics and other information. Gaps in pathophysiological knowledge will then be filled by using datasets from existing human biobanks.

Regarding PBK models and quantitative systems toxicology, task 5.3 aim to develop IVIVE-PBK models, to characterise the impact and predictivity of *in vitro* Absorption, Distribution, Metabolism and Excretion (ADME) parameters, to quantify the uncertainty by comparing to *in vivo* studies and to collaborate with WP6 on a wide range of case studies. Toxicokinetic parameters will be generated for all WP5 test compounds using the appropriate *in vitro* test systems, *in silico* predictions and analytical measurements. PBK modelling will be used to estimate internal exposure and to compare this to POD derived from *in vitro* mechanistic NAM assays for priority chemicals and pathways. Integration of toxicokinetic and toxicodynamic models in quantitative systems toxicology models will improve AO prediction.

A5.3.1 Prioritized NAM-based mechanistic hazard characterization – 2 PROJECTS

P5.3.1.a_Y1_SystemsToxicology_UL-LACDR

Project Title	Systems toxicology approaches for mechanism-based chemical safety assessment.		
Project Acronym (15 letters max)	SysTox		
Project Manager	Bob van de Water water_b@lacdr.leidenuniv.nl	UL-LACDR	NL
Deputy Project manager	Olivier Taboureau olivier.taboureau@u-paris.fr	INSERM	FR
Expected starting date PARC (Month number)	1	Expected duration	48*
PARC Work package number	5	PARC Task/Activity/Sub-activity:	5.3.1 and 5.3.3
Project Id	P5.3.1.a_Y1_SystemsToxicology_UL-LACDR		

*The project has been extended from M36 to M48

Status: Implementation

Summary of the project

The SysTox project is part of WP5 and reflect the activities of T5.3.1 and T5.3.3. The objective is to support the chemical RA in the AOP framework, with the evaluation of mechanistic data for a quantitative hazard characterization through NAMs. Mapping and quantifying MIE activity and KE activation is essential for the ultimate application of the AOP framework in chemical safety assessment. Systems toxicology involves the holistic quantitative assessment of perturbations of biological systems by chemicals and typically involves omics approaches, including transcriptomics and metabolomics. To derive confidence in the application of NAM-based omics data, there is a necessity to determine the relevance of *in vitro omics* data with the *in vivo* situation. Various bioinformatics approaches are available to uncover hazard. There is a need to understand the validity of each method with respect to the qualitative and quantitative characterization of hazards. In this project we will validate innovative *in silico* and bioinformatics approaches for quantitative chemical HA and will be evaluated in this project. We will also address the human *in vivo* relevance of *in vitro* findings. The ultimate aim is that a quantitative assessment of hazard will contribute to classification of chemicals for specific health effects related to EDC, immunosuppression, DNT, NonGenotoxic carcinogenesis, areas that are of critical relevance for PARC.

Main expected outputs of the project

We will establish innovative approaches for mechanism-based HA based on *in silico* prediction and omics approaches. This will involve both Quantitative Structure Activity Relationship (QSAR)-based prediction of critical MIE activation as well as quantitative assessment of KE activation based on omics data. In

addition, we will provide confidence in the relevance of *in vitro* transcriptomics responses with respect to responses occurring in the human *in vivo* situation. Results of this project should help to prioritize accurate and robust omics-bases prediction for critical toxicological endpoints in chemical RA.

Outcomes and impacts expected for end-users and stakeholders

The outcome of the project will be interactive online systems toxicology tools that will allow rapid mechanistic understanding of novel omics data. The tools will be helpful to end-users like applicants from industry and regulatory agencies, since it will allow a cross-sector application of systems toxicology in a structured manner using similar bioinformatics tools. This will allow commonalities in the understanding of omics technologies in a quantitative manner for determination of point-of-departure for RA. Stakeholders will also see benefits in the reduction of animal testing. Finally, the results of our project will allow for the regulatory implementation of omics strategies and, thereby, for the efficient mechanism-based identification and regulation of hazardous substances that will benefit public health from.

Key words:

Omics, transcriptomics, systems toxicology, gene network, key events, human translation

Link to the PARC DoA

The project responds to the PARC OOs OO3, OO4, OO5, OO6, OO7, OO10, OO12 and OO9

The SysTox project directly links to the DoA of WP5 T5.3: Quantitative systems toxicology and development of new AOPs. This project will ultimately lead to the development of NGRA tools that integrate human-relevant test methods, using *in vitro* and *in silico* approaches to provide quantitative mechanistic information on modes of action, and that allow the rapid mechanistic understanding of novel omics data. As such, it will establish an initial framework for the application of omics data in a regulatory setting. Collaboration is taking place within and outside of Workpackage 5. A workshop on systems toxicology aiming to identify relevant datasets to be used in case studies was organized in January 2022, and benefitted from the regulatory insight of EFSA and the BfR. Three reports will be produced to disseminate the results of this project.

Links within PARC (WPs/Tasks/Activities/Projects)

The SysTox project is linked to the following tasks:

- WP4, Task 4.1: human studies and effect markers: translate candidate biomarkers from SysTox studies to HBM effect markers.
- WP5, Task 5.1, 5.2: complementarity with gap filling studies (5.1) and experimental studies and NAM development (5.2): data from T5.1 and T5.2 will be used in case study.
 Activity 5.3.2: use of NAM data for AOP development and effect marker validation: findings from SysTox project can be used in Project 5.3.2.
- WP6, Task 6.1: development of qAOPs and IATA validation: information from SysTox can be used for data gap filling for qAOP development.
 Task 6.2: mixture effects: mixture effects can be quantitatively addressed through SysTox tools
- WP7, Task 7.3: data and text mining: data provision
- WP8: SysTox bioinformatics tools can be integrated in toolbox
- WP9: training of bioinformatics tools for regulators

Links outside PARC

The project will liaise with the below projects, clusters and initiatives to identify datasets that will be of importance for the SysTox project. Focus will be on omics datasets. This includes interactions with:

- EURION cluster
- EHEN projects on immune/neuro effects of the exposome: Hedimed and Eximious
- EU-ToxRisk project
- ASPIS cluster projects on application of NAM for chemical safety assessment: RISK-HUNT3R, ONTOX, PrecisionTOX.

- H2020 green deal project on persistent and mobile chemicals (PFAS)
- OECD - Extended Advisory Group on Molecular Screening and Toxicogenomics (EAGMST) and the OECD WPHA
- US-EPA and US National Institute of Environmental Health Sciences/National Toxicology Program (US-NIEHS/NTP)

Key PARC Deliverables and Milestones to which the project contributes

AD5.4: Inventory of omics data, biochemical data, other relevant readouts in public domain repositories for all PARC selected AOs and mapping of the available information sources and datasets related to human pathophysiology focusing on the prioritised endpoints (delivered)

AD5.7: Draft strategy for the development of bioinformatics tools that are needed to link omics data and other mechanistic information to human relevant disease mechanisms (delivered).

D5.3: 1st new AOPs Report (delivered) is no longer linked to this project

D5.4: 1st Closing data Gaps Report (M36) is no longer linked to this project

D5.7. Systems toxicology (and AOPs) report (M48)

Partners List

UL-LACDR (NL), INSERM (FR), Ugent (BE), MUI (AT), ISCIII (ES), ISS (IT), BPI (GR), KIT (DE), NCPHP (NO), WR (NL), Sciensano (BE), NIPH (HU), UNIABDN (UK), UFZ (DE), UG-PL (PL), IRFM (IT), UIBK (AT), UMIL (IT), AUTH (GR), IISPV (ES), UOB (UK).

Schedule

Starting date: 01/05/2022 (M1)

Expected ending date: 30/04/2026 (M48)

Costs

Expected PM for the fourth year of the project: 98 PM

Expected ODC for the fourth year of the project: 91 306 €

P5.3.1.b_Y4_grOMICS_UL-LACDR

Project Title	Fostering the use of omics for grouping and read-across in risk assessment		
Project Acronym (15 letters max)	grOMICS		
Project Manager	Giulia Callegaro g.callegaro@lacdr.leidenuniv.nl	Leiden University	NL
Deputy Project manager	Bob van de Water water_b@lacdr.leidenuniv.nl	Leiden University	NL
Expected starting date PARC (Month number)	M37	Expected duration (months)	45
PARC Workpackage number	WP5	PARC Task/Activity/Sub-activity:	5.3.1
Project Id	P5.3.1.b_Y4_grOMICS_UL-LACDR		

Status: Initiation

Summary of the project

There is a clear need for developing test methods and approaches that allow to rapidly and confidently screen large volumes of compounds for their safety (PARC Activity 5.3.1). Omics data, including high-throughput transcriptomics (HTTr) and high-throughput phenotypic profiling (HTPP), and systems toxicology models applied to *in vitro* test systems could address this need. Different regulatory agencies

are embracing this opportunity both in strategic documents as by supporting initiatives to foster development of these technologies and methods. ECHA recently identified omics as potential NAMs to refine grouping and RAX in their KARC (ECHA, 2023), a topic investigated by the scientific community in the last few years as well (Gruszczynska et al., 2024; Vrijenhoek, 2022; Yan et al., 2023). Transparency and reproducibility in data processing, analysis, reporting and interpretation are also areas of interest. The OECD ESCA is currently refining the OORF for transcriptomic and metabolomics (Harrill, Viant, et al., 2021)) amongst others, working on dedicated elements of reporting for grouping of chemicals and enrichment analysis (OECD, 2024). In addition, classification and labelling as well as derivation of reference values require – in addition to the reporting frameworks and sampling documents already developed by OECD and / or ECHA – frameworks for the handling and interpretation of the enormous amounts of data created by HTTr amongst others, working on dedicated elements of reporting for grouping of chemicals and enrichment analysis (OECD, 2024). In addition, classification and labelling as well as derivation of reference values require – in addition to the reporting frameworks and sampling documents already developed by OECD and / or ECHA – frameworks for the handling and interpretation of the enormous amounts of data created by HTTr.

Here, we propose to foster the use of systems toxicology data for grouping and RAX applications, by targeting the following objectives:

- 1) to develop a database system and interface of the proposed OORF,
- 2) to develop a standardized, interoperable and toxicologically-oriented pathways and gene set ontology, to be applied to test systems specific co-expression models and bridge to the AOP framework;
- 3) to propose guidelines on how to integrate structural and physiochemical similarity measurements and MoA features such as derived from omics and phenotypic profiling. We will focus on publicly available datasets obtained on two cell lines (MCF7 and U2OS) with more than ~1500 compounds of human and environmental concern (Bundy et al., 2024; Harrill et al., 2024). Among them, PFAS, BPAs, pesticides are included, therefore impacting on PARC research need PFAS, BPA, pesticides. MCF7, a human breast cancer cell line is highly relevant for several PARC endpoint priorities (endocrine and metabolic disruption, non-genotoxic carcinogenicity) including the recently highlighted reproductive toxicity. The U2OS cell line, a human osteosarcoma cell line, provides an excellent comparison to assess the dependency of findings related to the cell line used. In addition, these datasets will allow to have a broader impact on a large chemical space. CF7, a human breast cancer cell line is highly relevant for several PARC endpoint priorities (endocrine and metabolic disruption, non-genotoxic carcinogenicity) including the recently highlighted reproductive toxicity. The U2OS cell line, a human osteosarcoma cell line, provides an excellent comparison to assess the dependency of findings related to the cell line used. In addition, these datasets will allow to have a broader impact on a large chemical space.

This project will generally impact PARC areas “NAMS to replace animal testing for hazard endpoints” and “Read across and NAMs: Development of case studies” and all their research needs. Ultimately, this project will have an impact within the REACH Regulation, in particular within the recommended guidelines to perform RAX detailed in section 3.7 of ECHA-13-R-02-EN.

Main expected outputs of the project:

Following the above-described aims, we anticipate to deliver the following outputs:

1. a database system to collect and query the OORF This system will allow to seamlessly fill in the reporting information, browse and query study characteristics and potentially integrate with existing regulatory study frameworks (e.g. OHT 201 (Carnesecchi et al., 2023));
2. an OECD-equivalent Phenotypic Reporting Framework (OPRF), based on the adaptation of the OORF, for cellular morphology data (HTPP) and integration of the recently adapted REMBI template so-called MIHCSME (Minimum Information for High Content Screening Microscopy Experiments) (Sarkans et al., 2021);
3. co-expression models for HTTr for test systems for screening, e.g. MCF7 and U2OS. The models are wrapped in a web-interface (TXG-MAPr, (Callegaro et al., 2021)) that allows users of any background to evaluate the effect on MoA of compound exposure;
4. phenotypic network models for HTPP for test systems for screening, e.g. MCF7 and U2OS. Pattern matching and in silico models based on machine learning (ML) approaches will be developed using Cell Painting data for chemical RA on some toxicological endpoints (Lejal et al., 2023);
5. a standardized ontology that translates between existing biological entities (gene sets and pathways databases e.g. GO, KEGG, Wikipathways), gene co-expression modules) and relates these to the terms / concepts in the AOPWiki;
6. a database of chemical and physiochemical properties, HTTr, HTPP, ADME data, in vivo endpoints for the US-EPA chemical library;
7. Evaluation of grouping overlap between and within different MoA similarity measures, and different structural and physiochemical-based similarity measures for the 3 case studies selected;
8. Development of AOP-based grouping, where structural and physiochemical properties are used to group for the MIE, and MoA data are preferred to group early KEs.

Outcomes and impacts expected on end-users and stakeholders:

Using omics data that reflects compounds MoA to determine and justify grouping and RAX strategies is a recommendation in various guidance documents in the chemical, food and cosmetics fields. Currently, it is however:

- 1) Laborious to report data generation and analysis processes. In addition, the current system (the OORF) is not embedded in an interfaced database tool, nor it includes phenotypic profiling data (HTPP);
- 2) Difficult to obtain a clear and unambiguous interpretation of omics data. Pathway and gene set knowledge is redundant, non-interoperable and not directly connected to accepted toxicological framework (e.g. AOP);
- 3) Unclear how to merge or differentially consider biological mode-of-action and physiochemical properties to define groups in grouping and RAX approaches.

This project will:

- 1) Provide the first tool to report, query and store information about generation and analysis of HTTr and HTPP data for toxicological applications. This will streamline this task, increasing the feasibility of including HTTr and HTPP in RAX and grouping studies and increase confidence in the usage of such data to support regulatory decision making. The tool will be developed in concert with the dedicated OECD expert group (ESCA, Advisory Group on Emerging Science in Chemicals Assessment) and imaging expert groups (“Health and Environmental Sciences Institute” (HESI), and the JRC working group which met in March 2024 on the theme ‘Facilitating the uptake of imaging-based in vitro methods in regulatory toxicology’);
- 2) Define test systems-specific network models for HTTr and HTPP for frequently used screening test systems, equipped with a clear MoA ontology that will reduce the complexity and redundancy of omics data interpretation, and connect to AOP, whenever possible. This will increase confidence in the use of omics-based analysis for regulatory decision making as the comparison between different

outputs will be eased, and will lower the barrier to understand the output of these analyses to a general toxicologically oriented audience;

- 3) Provide guidelines on how to integrate structural and physiochemical similarity measurements and MoA. This will be co-developed in concert with ECHA, EFSA and OECD to be considered for inclusion in relevant recommendations.

Outcomes and impacts expected to be incorporated into a specific regulatory framework:

In particular, impact 1 and 3 delineated above should resonate in specific regulatory frameworks:

- 1) This project has the ambition to propel the standardization of reporting of the use of omics data for RA. The description document of the developed reporting system will be taken up by the dedicated expert group of the OECD, refined, to ultimately be included in a future guidance document about reporting omics data.
- 3) The developed guidelines should, upon revision from ECHA, be considered as case studies for the application of omics for RAX.

Key words:

Systems toxicology, omics, read across, standardization, reporting, ontology, phenotypic screening, OORF, HTTr, HTPP

Link to the PARC DoA:

The project responds to the PARC OOs OO3, OO4, OO5, OO6, OO7, OO9, OO10 and OO12. This project is, firstly, constructing a network of PARC associated partners that have experience or are interested in using omics data for the purpose of risk assessment, in particular grouping and read-across. Partly, this represents the continuation of the previous 5.3.1.a (Systems Toxicology) project's community, running from Y1 to Y4, enriched by explicit collaboration with the FAIR data management community in WP7. This project will produce the first tool to report, query and store information about generation and analysis of HTTr and HTPP data for toxicological applications. In addition, specific guidelines on the usage of mechanistic data in this context will be produced, related to a standardise interpretation framework for HTTr and HTPP output, and their application in the context of read-across.

Links within PARC (WPs/Tasks/Activities/Projects):

The SysTox project is linked to the following workpackages and tasks:

WP5:

- Action 2 of this project is connected with P5.3.2.a (AOP development based on integration)
- We will connect with P5.3.4.a activities to include ADME components in the grouping and RAX approaches

WP6:

- T6.1, the application of HTTr in qAOP- and NAM-based NGRA and IATA development.

WP7: this project is strongly connected with WP7 in terms of ontology development and database development, and must be fully aligned with the PARC Data Hub. The outcomes from this project would benefit from a more extensive WP7 involvement and indeed should be co-developed with WP7, as we briefly outline below. The T7.2 Toxicology cluster has expressed interest in such extensive involvement, potentially converting this project to a joint WP5-WP7 project.

- Action 1 of this project is directly connected with T7.2 Toxicology Cluster (FAIRification of Toxicology/OMICS/AOP data). This project will, as a minimal output, consolidate the core of a database and interface for reporting of omics data and phenotypic data. In the optimal scenario, based on the interest raised in the toxicology cluster, more extensive WP7 involvement will support a more ambitious database system in terms of data FAIRness and interoperability (e.g., with the PARC FAIR Data Hub), that is fully aligned with best practice in ontology-linked data schemas for example.

- Action 2 of this project is directly connected with A7.3.3 (lead partner IISPV). This project will directly benefit from actions underway in A7.3.3 led by UL, where efforts are directed to developing an AI-assisted ontology to bridge between biological entities. In this project, we will test directly the WP7 output, and feedback to refine it. Also here, more extensive involvement from T7.2 (e.g., ontology experts Karin Slater and George Gkoutos from BHAM) will help in the quality and FAIRness of the to-be-developed ontology.
- Action 3 of this project on data collection will require support from WP7 in terms of the metadata and data collection templates and their integration into PARC FAIR Data Hub, which will be provided by BHAM (Iseult Lynch) with support from IISPV/BfR.

WP8 is made up of three sectors: T8.1 (safe-and-sustainable-by-design, SSbD), T8.2 (EWSs), and T8.3 (model inventory).

- T8.1: The development of standardized and toxicologically-oriented pathways could integrate sustainability metrics, ensuring that the efficacy, safety, and sustainability of compounds are taken into account during the design process. The project could guide the selection of pathways that prioritize chemicals with minimal environmental persistence and reduced bioaccumulation potential.
- T8.2: The findings from this project could directly benefit the work done in EWS as the pathways and biologically relevant outcomes would have important implications for EWSs and strategies. The generation of standardised pathway and ontology sets could also facilitate better EWSs.
- T8.3: the model inventory aims to incorporate all the models, databases, and analysis methods and algorithms that will be developed or used within the work packages of PARC. This project can contribute to this standardised and centralized inventory. Both sectors could also benefit from lessons learned through the generation of databases for interoperability

WP9:

- training of bioinformatics tools for regulators

Links outside PARC:

This project will liaise with the following initiatives:

- US-EPA and US-NIEHS/NTP: the main datasets will be made available by US-EPA. We therefore will have regular interactions to assure we analyze the data synergistically
- OECD ESCA and OECD: this project will significantly contribute to the reporting endeavor of the OECD ESCA, therefore we will have regular conversations. In addition, several partners are member of ESCA, facilitating the conversation. Representatives of OECD declared their intention to follow this project, if it is approved.
- ECHA: this project will have significant impact on how RAx is applied under REACH regulations. We will therefore have regular contact with ECHA officers, continuing the interactions from the SysTox project, CS1. Representatives of ECHA declared their intention to follow this project, if it is approved.
- EFSA, in particular the Working Group on RAx (EFSA, 2024). The purpose of the WG is to define a Guidance document on the use of RAx within EFSA's remit. One of the project partner is a member (Emilio Benfenati). Representatives of ECHA declared their intention to follow this project, if it is approved.
- ASPIS and children projects RISK-HUNT3R, ONTOX and PRECISIONTOX. We aim to support WP3 findings by applying the developed framework to ASPIS data.
- EFSA TXG-MAP project: the project lead (NL) is leading an-EFSA funded project that aims to generate multiple test-systems specific HTTr co-expression models (TXG-MAPr). Many synergies are therefore expected that could have direct regulatory implications.

- HESI consortium OASIS. The group is experimenting on the utility of phenotypic profiling (with or without transcriptomic data) can be predictive of existing rat liver data. We will coordinate with them in WP1 and WP3.
- eSTAR (Emerging Systems Toxicology for the Assessment of Risk) WG on Use of Transcriptomic POD for Chemical RAs.

Key PARC Deliverables and Milestones to which the project contributes

D5.7: Systems toxicology (and AOPs) report (M48)

D5.10: Systems toxicology and AOPs report (M60)

D5.14: Systems toxicology and AOPs report (M81)

Partners List:

UL-LACDR (NL), INSERM (FR), UFZ (DE), IRFM (IT), UGent (BE), KIT (DE), AUTH (EL), Sciensano (BE), BfR (DE), UHC (DE), BHAM (UK), IISPV (ES)

Schedule:

Starting date: 01/05/2025 (M37)

Expected ending date: 31/01/2029 (M81)

Costs

Expected PM for the first year of the project: 103 PM

Expected ODC for the first year of the project: 83 219 €

A5.3.2 AOP development based on integration – 1 PROJECT

P5.3.2.a_Y1_AOPDevelopment_Inserm

Project Title	AOP Development		
Project Acronym (15 letters max)	AOP		
Project Manager	Karine Audouze karine.audouze@u-paris.fr	Inserm	France
Deputy Project manager	Birgit Mertens birgit.mertens@sciensano.be	Sciensano	Belgique
Expected starting date PARC (Month number)	1	Expected duration	48*
PARC Workpackage number	5	PARC Task/Activity/Sub-activity:	5.3.2
Project Id	P5.3.2.a_Y1_AOPDevelopment_Inserm		

*The project has been extended from M36 to M48

Status: Implementation

Summary of the project

NAMs provide a large diversity and amount of data that are very challenging, if not impossible to implement in regulatory applications or mechanistic toxicology unless they are integrated and represented in a useful and widely accepted framework. AOPs fulfill all requirements for providing such a framework. AOPs describe the causal relationships between MIEs, subsequent KEs at different biological levels and ultimately AOs. They are developed by integrating and connecting data from various sources i.e. databases and scientific literature, in a logical sequence of causally-linked events.

However, at present, AOPs for important regulatory endpoints are lacking or insufficiently developed.

Therefore, in this project, we aim to tackle this regulatory challenge by developing comprehensive AOPs that cover mechanisms underlying regulatory relevant AOs such as immunotoxicology, neurotoxicology, non-genotoxic carcinogenesis, endocrine disruption and metabolic disruption. Different groups will first identify available AOPs (if any), gaps in knowledge, and will develop AOPs related to these outcomes using transparent and consistent methodologies, and following the FAIR data principles. One group will focus on methodologies and tools for AOP development, and another group will identify putative effect markers based on available AOPs. By providing a framework for the use of NAMs and/or development of IATA for high-priority endpoints, the project will have an impact on legislations for chemicals (REACH and CLP), plant protection products and biocides, cosmetic products and food (food additives, food contaminants and food contact materials).

The work in this project will also address the EFSA Roadmap for Action on NAMs in RA by refining the existing AOP inventory and developing additional AOPs, advanced cell culture models and facilitating data integration. The development and characterisation of advanced *in vitro* NAMs including integration of AOPs will entail a major step towards NGRA. These will also prepare solid ground for further development of quantitative AOPs by pointing out where the data is missing and needs to be generated.

Main expected outputs of the project

The project will be helpful from a risk assessor's perspective because the AOPs will support the further development and implementation of innovative methods to rapidly analyze the mechanistic hazard of a high number of substances thus contributing to detection of hazardous substances and to the zero-pollution ambition of the green deal and the CSS. Additionally, AOPs developed in this project will be used to define assessment groups and to group chemicals (sharing the same MoA/AOP or not) in a step-wise approach, facilitating the assessment of mixtures thus also contributing to the aforementioned EU strategies. AOPs are currently already used by different agencies to support hazard identification. They are the basis for IATA development and for the identification of relevant effect markers. Ultimately, the project will help to increase confidence in the AOPs, NAMs and IATAs and facilitate their use to inform the various steps in the RA process.

Outcomes and impacts expected for end-users and stakeholders

The developed AOPs will be helpful to end-users like applicants from industry because they provide a framework to structure regulatory relevant mechanistic information and facilitate targeted testing with NAMs in a rapid, reliable and cost-efficient way. Stakeholders will see benefits in the reduction of animal testing, the identification and regulation of hazardous substances and ultimately in the benefits for public health resulting from the regulatory implementation of the assays. Other possible outcomes:

- Develop protocols and tools to optimize and harmonize data collection, appraisal, synthesis and visualization based on artificial intelligence (AI) supporting AOP development;
- Acquire available and most recent information on toxicity pathways leading to immune and hormonal dysregulation, neurotoxicity and non-genotoxic carcinogenesis, including chemicals able to interfere with all the identified pathways;
- Identify missing data, inconsistencies and scientific gaps that might affect extrapolation in a regulatory setting;
- Link to the AOP-Wiki database contributing to the AOP- Knowledge Base project launched by OECD
- Provide a framework for the identification of biomarkers of effect, the targeted development/improvement of NAMs and the design of AOP-based IATAs (cfr. PARC T6.1).

Key words:

AOP, method, immunotoxicology, neurotoxicology, non-genotoxic carcinogenesis, endocrine disruption, metabolic disruption, development, artificial intelligence (AI)

Link to the PARC DoA

The project responds to the PARC OOs OO3, OO4, OO5, OO6, OO10, OO12, OO9 and OO11. Regulatory uptake will be fostered through the identification of missing data, inconsistencies and scientific gaps that might affect extrapolation in a regulatory setting. Innovation in complex data analysis for RA will take place through, namely, the development of protocols aiming to optimize data collection, appraisal, synthesis and visualization based on AI. Cooperation with other R&I initiatives is a core element of this project, as there will be a sustained collaboration with PARC activities related to NAMs (task 5.2), systems biology (activities 5.3.1, 5.3.3), and IATA development and RA (task 6.1). <mailto:parc@anses.fr>

Links within PARC (WPs/Tasks/Activities/Projects)

WP2, Task 2.1: complementarity with guidelines tests
 WP3: Synergies, Communication and awareness
 WP4, Task 4.1: Human studies and effect markers
 WP5, Task 5.2, 5.1: complementarity with experimental studies and NAM development. Task 5.3: use of NAMs for AOP development and effect marker validation
 WP6, Task 6.1: development of qAOPs and IATA validation, Task 6.2: mixture effects, Task 6.3: text mining
 WP7, Task 7.3: data and text mining. DMP (AOP data FAIRness)
 WP8, Task 8.2: emerging chemicals
 WP9: Training

Links outside PARC

- H2020 Green Deal Projects: ALTERNATIVE, PROMISCES, LIFESAVER, SCENARIOS, PANORAMIX, ZeroPM
- EURION: European Cluster to improve identification of Endocrine Disruptors
- EHEN projects on immune/neuro effects of the exposome: Hedimed and Eximious
- EU-ToxRisk project
- ASPIS cluster projects on application of NAM for chemical safety assessment: RISK-HUNT3R, ONTOX, PrecisionTOX.
- OECD: OECD Working Group of National Co-ordinators of the TGs programme (WNT), OECD ESCA; previous EAGMST, OECD WPHA and different OECD Working Groups
- US-EPA and US NIEHS/NTP
- EFSA, ECHA, SCCS, EEA
- PEPPER

Key PARC Deliverables and Milestones to which the project contributes

AD5.4: Inventory of omics data, biochemical data, other relevant readouts in public domain repositories for all PARC selected AOs and mapping of the available information sources and datasets related to human pathophysiology focusing on the prioritised endpoints (delivered) is no longer linked to this project

AD5.5: Inventory of the available (networks of) AOPs, prioritisation and establishment of the framework for further development in PARC (delivered)

D5.3: 1st new AOPs Report (delivered)

D5.7. Systems toxicology (and AOPs) report (M48)

Partners List:

ACES or SU (SE); AU (DK); AUTH (GR); BfG (DE); BPI (GR); DTU (DK); IISPV (ES); Inserm (FR); IRSN (FR); ISS (IT); KI (SE); KIT (DE); KU-Leuven (BE); LIST (LU), MUI (AT); NILU (NO); NIPH (NO); NCPHP (HU); UG-PL (PL); SDU (DK); Sciensano (BE); UAntwerpen (BE); UGent (BE); UKK/UoC (DE); UIBK (AT); UL-LACDR (NL); UMIL (IT); UNIVIE (AT); WR (NL), Cefas-Defra (UK)

Schedule:

Starting date: 01/05/2022 (M1)

Expected ending date: 30/04/2026 (M48)

Costs

Expected PM for the fourth year of the project: 74 PM
 Expected ODC for the fourth year of the project: 20 275 €

A5.3.3 Translation to human pathophysiology

No project submitted at present.

A5.3.4 PBTK models and quantitative systems toxicology – 2 PROJECTS

P5.3.4.a_Y1_PBK_Kinetics_Fraunhofer

Project Title	PBK models and quantitative systems toxicology		
Project Acronym (15 letters max)	PBK_Kinetics		
Project Manager	Sylvia Escher sylvia.escher@item.fraunhofer.de	ITEM	DE
Deputy Project manager	Georg Aichinger georg.aichinger@hest.ethz.ch	ETHZ	Swiss
Expected starting date PARC (Month number)	1	Expected duration	48*
PARC Workpackage number	5	PARC Task/Activity/Sub-activity:	5.3.4
Project Id	P5.3.4.a_Y1_PBK_Kinetics_Fraunhofer		

*The project has been extended from M36 to M48

Status: Implementation

Summary of the project

The aim of this project is to fill data and knowledge gaps in the area of kinetic modelling. To achieve this, project P5.3.4 will develop PBK models, which are informed by mainly NAM data. In addition, we will integrate PBK models with AOPs as a basis for quantitative system toxicology. Several conceptual and data gaps will be addressed, such as i) individual human variability in bioavailable concentrations; ii) the impact of the human microbiome on the metabolism of xenobiotics iii) transport across the blood brain barrier (BBB); and iv) uptake of inhalable compounds via the respiratory tract. This project will refine and establish in a bottom-up approach generic models that describe ADME of chemicals in the human organism on the basis of compartments defined by physiological parameters. The developed models will facilitate QIVIVE in a reliable way to produce data of direct value for chemical RA. Compound-specific input data will be derived by the validation and use of *in silico* and *in vitro* ADME approaches. For the initial phase, 9 case studies were defined, focusing on the expansion or refinement of PBK models using data-rich model compounds or the generation of predictive PBK models for PARC priority compounds. We aim to establish an initial framework for the application of Quantitative IVIVE-PBK (QIVIVE-PBK) models in a regulatory setting, so that a quantitative assessment of hazard will be possible starting from the *in vitro* hazard identification in e.g. AP.3.1 and AP.3.3. This work will therefore contribute to characterise the hazard of chemicals for specific health effects e.g. in the area of EDC, immunosuppression, DNT and non genotoxic carcinogenesis.

Main expected outputs of the project

We will have established innovative approaches to characterize the ADME processes of priority compounds

by integrating *in silico* prediction and *in vitro* ADME data into PBK models for oral and inhalation exposures, accounting for uncertainty linked to relevant biological processes.

Outcomes and impacts expected for end-users and stakeholders

By establishing innovative IVIVE-PBK models, this project will have an important impact on the integration of NAM-based approaches into regulatory RA. IVIVE-PBK models are needed for the extrapolation from the *in vitro* benchmark concentration to a human equivalent concentration or dose. This will enable users to determine a POD from NAM based RA. Thereby the project links directly to the project P5.3.1 and P5.3.2 in T5.3 and the IATAs developed in WP6. In addition, the project will show the applicability and by this will promote use of *in vitro* and *in silico* ADME data in PBK models for predicting human plasma and tissue concentrations. In addition, the project will be helpful to other end-users like applicants from industry since it will allow a cross-sector application of kinetic modelling in a structured manner using similar PBK models. Models will be made available by publications and other suitable platforms as e.g. provided by WP7.

Key words:

in vitro ADME models, *in silico* ADME models, physiologically based kinetic modelling, oral, inhalation, human equivalent concentration/dose, microbiome metabolism, transport processes

Link to the PARC DoA

The project responds to the PARC OOs OO3, OO4, OO5, OO6, OO7, OO10, OO12, OO9 and OO11. The PBK_kinetic project directly links to the DoA of WP5 T5.3: Quantitative systems toxicology and development of new AOPs. NGRA relies on NAM based hazard identification and characterization. PBK modelling is a central key element of NGRA, as it will be used for QIVIVE, deriving equivalent plasma and tissue concentrations which serve as a NAM based point of departure for RA. Project 5.3.4 will close data and knowledge gaps in PBK modeling by using case studies. These case studies will be used to i) discuss the workflow for implementing PBK models and QIVIVE into regulatory decision making, ii) outline remaining uncertainties but also advantages compared to the current HA paradigm iii) to close data gaps for PARC priority compounds. P5.3.4 core team will connect to other European projects, like e.g. ASPIS and in particular RiskHunt3R to promote the development of a harmonized internal exposure framework. Data and modelling work are dedicated to FAIR data principles.

Links within PARC (WPs/Tasks/Activities/Projects)

The PBK_kinetic project is linked to the following tasks:

- WP5, Task 5.1, 5.2: complementarity with gap filling studies (5.1) and experimental *in vitro* ADME studies (5.2): data from T5.1 and T5.2 will be used in case studies to develop and validate IVIVE-PBK approaches.
- WP6, Task 6.1: development of qAOPs and PBK models to be integrated into IATAs. Information from PBK_Kinetics can be used for QIVIVE and for qAOP development.
- WP7, Task 7.3: Data and text mining: data provision
- WP8: PBK_Kinetics bioinformatics tools can be integrated in toolbox
- WP9: training of PBK models for regulators

Links outside PARC

The project will liaise with the below projects, clusters and initiatives to identify datasets that will be of importance for the PBK_kinetic project. Focus will be on *in vitro*, *in silico* ADME model data, PBK modelling approaches as well as concepts for tiered testing strategies, starting from simple to more complex testing. This includes interactions with:

- EURION cluster
- EHEN projects on immune/neuro effects of the exposome: Hedimed and Eximious
- EU-ToxRisk project
- ASPIS cluster projects on application of NAM for chemical safety assessment: RISK-HUNT3R, ONTOX, PrecisionTOX.

- H2020 green deal project on persistent and mobile chemicals (PFAS) like ZeroPM
- OECD – IATA case studies
- EFSA ADME4NGRA
- US-EPA and US NIEHS/NTP

Key PARC Deliverables and Milestones to which the project contributes

D5.2: 1st new PBK models report (M36)
 D5.6: 2nd new PBK models report (M48)

Partners List: ANSES (FR); ETHZ (CHE); IISPV (ES); INERIS (FR); Inserm (FR); ISCIII (ES); ISS (IT); ITEM-Fraunhofer (DE); NVI (NO); UKK/UoC (DE); UIBK (AT); UNIVIE (AT); WR (NL); WU-Tox (NL); EA (UK), AUTH (EL), UFZ (DE), Cefas-Defra (UK), NIPH (NO), Unisanté (CH), STAMI (NO)

Schedule:

Starting date: 01/05/2022 (M1)
 Expected ending date: 30/04/2026 (M48)

Costs

Expected PM for the fourth year of the project: 38 PM
 Expected ODC for the fourth year of the project: 9 988 €

P5.3.4.b_Y4_RESUPT_RIVM

Project Title	<i>In vitro</i> methods to assess RESpiratory Uptake & Toxicity		
Project Acronym (15 letters max)	RESUPT		
Project Manager	Yvonne Staal Yvonne.Staal@RIVM.nl	RIVM	The Netherlands
Deputy Project manager	Tanja Hansen tanja.hansen@item.fraunhofer.de	Fraunhofer	Germany
Deputy Project manager	Pierre-Andre Billat Pierre-andre.BILLAT@ineris.fr	Ineris	France
Expected starting date PARC (Month number)	M37	Expected duration (months)	45
PARC Workpackage number	WP5	PARC Task/Activity/Sub-activity:	T5.3.4
Project Id	P5.3.4.b_Y4_RESUPT_RIVM		

Status: Initiation

Summary of the project

To effectively use *in vitro* models of the respiratory system in a regulatory context, three key aspects must be considered: (1) ensuring well-characterized and human-relevant exposure conditions, (2) applicability of the cell model, and (3) measuring relevant read-outs at appropriate time points. While the primary focus has been on local toxicological assessments, these *in vitro* models hold significant promise for evaluating respiratory uptake to determine systemic availability. This information is crucial for PBPK modelling and subsequent assessment of systemic toxicological effects using other *in vitro* models. However, the use of *in vitro* respiratory models for uptake assessment is still in its infancy. Although relevant receptors for transport of substances have been identified ([Dong et al, 2024](#)), the practical applicability of respiratory epithelial models depends on experimental data and their correlation with human respiratory uptake. The

aim of this project is to fill this data gap. The focus of this project will be on inhaled pesticides (like pyrethroids or others) and inhaled PFAS, but for validation a comparison with human *in vivo* data, other substances may be relevant. It involves the collection and generation of kinetic data to establish PBK models suitable for IVIVE for different routes of exposure. Quantitative Structure-Property Relationships (QSPR) models, along with other *in silico* tools (i.e. RAX to predict kinetic for target chemicals based on similar source compounds), will be used for PBK model parameterisation. IVIVE is one key aspect in hazard characterization, as this process derives a human equivalent concentration in plasma or tissue, which can be used as point of departure for RA.

The assessment of uptake upon inhalation is relevant for occupational settings, where workers are often exposed to airborne substances at relatively high concentrations. Information on respiratory uptake provides information on systemic availability and possibility for systemic toxicity. Standardization and development of *in vitro* models for respiratory uptake will allow evaluation of the importance of the inhalation route of exposure for systemic effects, as this is often neglected (like for many pesticides and PFAS). Further development of *in vitro* models to assess respiratory uptake is essential for the use of NAMs for RA of airborne substances under various legislations, such as REACH and OSH and to facilitate the adherence to the 3Rs strategy. Applicability in the regulatory context will be ensured by close collaboration and feedback from ECHA and EFSA. The results of this project will provide guidance on the use of *in vitro* models, alone or in combination with *in silico* tools, of the respiratory tract to assess respiratory uptake.

This work will therefore contribute to the PARC activities: PFAS, PFAS related chemical, NAMs to replace animal testing for hazard endpoints, ED mixtures, Validation of a systematic *in vitro/in silico* battery to steer generation of chronic toxicity data for vertebrates and RAX and NAMs: development of case studies.

Main expected outputs of the project:

This project aims to enhance our understanding of how *in vitro* respiratory models can be applied to study respiratory uptake, which is crucial for evaluating the systemic toxic effects of inhaled substances. Specifically:

- Define criteria for *in vitro* respiratory models to evaluate their usefulness in assessing respiratory uptake. Two aspects will be considered i) the *in vitro* to *in vivo* comparisons of transporters, enzymes, ii) the knowledge and methods used to account for loss of compounds based on the *in vitro* set up (like adsorption to plastics, evaporation etc).
- Generate experimental data of the respiratory uptake of a limited set of substances that can be used for e.g. the ITEM PBK model. Expand the dataset gathered in the lung case study of project P5.3.4.a.
- Generate experimental data on the *in vitro* biokinetics of the very same set of substances to define which *in silico* models and experimental approaches are needed to assess the loss of substances due to the *in vitro* experimental design.
- Develop *in silico* tools to be applied for predicting missing input data for parametrizing PBK models, including interaction with proteins that affect bioavailability and distribution.
- Develop guidance /a tiered assessment strategy for assessing the translocation of inhaled substances. Where possible, provide insights in physico chemical properties that are indicative for local and systemic effects.

Outcomes and impacts expected on end-users and stakeholders:

This project will provide guidance for assessment of respiratory uptake of airborne substances. Respiratory uptake can be an important route for systemic availability and toxicity. The use of *in vitro* models, in combination with PBK models, will allow assessment of the importance of this exposure route. In addition, the diversity of substances requires guidance to the use of optimal exposure methods for airborne substances. This project will provide guidance for a selected group of substances, with the opportunity to

build this further for other groups of substances. Finally, the project will enable the regulatory implementation of NAM-based approaches, thus facilitating the efficient mechanism-based identification and regulation of hazardous substances for the benefit of public health.

Outcomes and impacts expected to be incorporated into a specific regulatory framework:

The project will have an important impact on the integration of NAM-based approaches into regulatory RA, as the characterization of *in vitro* models, exploration of appropriate dosimetry and the collection and use of kinetics data for PBK modelling will allow better determination of respiratory uptake. In addition, this guidance is not only useful for uptake, but also applies to the assessment of local toxicological effect in the respiratory tract.

Key words:

In vitro, respiratory uptake, air-liquid-interface, inhalation, translocation, ADME models, physiologically based kinetic modelling, biokinetics, *in vitro in vivo* extrapolation, QSAR

Link to the PARC DoA:

The project responds to the PARC OOs OO3: Define common R&I strategies with transparent criteria and a prioritisation strategy, OO4, OO5, OO10, OO12, OO9, OO11.

This work will fill a gap in the literature on NAMs for the assessment of inhalation toxicity after exposure. This will be carried out by several partners already involved in either inhalation NAMs or PBK assessment. This data will be disseminated to stakeholders, authorities and other experts.

Links within PARC (WPs/Tasks/Activities/Projects):

- WP6 - T6.2.2 Modelling exposure through life (IRFM)

Links outside PARC:

- VHP4safety (NL)
- Riskhunt3r – ASPIS Cluster
- French ministerial action plan on PFAs
- CoMPAIT (Collaborative Modeling Project for Acute Inhalation Toxicity)

Key PARC Deliverables and Milestones to which the project contributes

D5.6: 2nd new PBK models report (M48)

D5.9: 3rd new PBK models report (M60)

D5.13: 4th new PBK models report (M81)

Partners List:

RIVM (NL), ITEM (DE), INERIS (FR), VITO (BE), ENSP-NOVA (PT), LIST (LU), Fraunhofer IBMT (DE), IRFM (IT), STAMI (NO), UG-PL/QSARLab (PL), AUTH (EL), WU (to be confirmed) (NL)

Possibly to add analytical partner

Possibly to add partner having cells with transfected transporters

Schedule:

Starting date: 01/05/2025 (M37)

Expected ending date: 31/01/2029 (M81)

Costs

Expected PM for the first year of the project: 37 PM

Expected ODC for the first year of the project: 54 438 €

WP6 Innovation in regulatory risk assessment – 28 PROJECTS

The overall goal of WP6 is to drive innovation in regulatory RA by strengthening its scientific basis, with implementation of NGRA as ultimate goal.

The specific objectives are:

- To deliver IATAs for a selected set of human health effects, developed in close collaboration with relevant stakeholders and proven to be applicable through dedicated case studies
- To perform integrative RA based on internal and external exposure of humans exposed to chemicals and mixtures thereof *via* different routes of exposure, including the workplace
- To evaluate and map current methodologies employed in regulatory RA across sectors
- To identify gaps and needs in methodological knowledge
- To develop and foster the uptake of innovative, effective and protective regulatory RA approaches and methodologies
- To develop a framework to assess exposure of and facilitate enforcement of chemicals in articles and materials on the EU-market.

The work in WP6 is divided into four tasks:

T6.1 Integrated Approaches to Testing and Assessment of Chemicals 4 PROJECTS

The goal of this task is to establish IATAs, to be used for different European regulations on chemical safety for different industry sectors as well as for the CLP Regulation. The IATAs will be developed for a selected set of health effects (e.g. liver toxicity, genotoxicity, endocrine disruption). To provide a strong mechanistic basis for IATA development, existing and newly developed AOPs for selected health effects will be combined into AOP networks. Wherever possible and relevant, Key Event Relationships (KERs) will be quantitated by applying computational methodologies. IATAs will be developed in close collaboration with stakeholders including OECD and through various cycles of optimisation. In addition, systematic quantitative determination of the uncertainty of application of a combined set of NAMs in an IATA will provide insight in the overall confidence for the application of a selected test battery for respective IATAs.

Fig 8: WP5.3_WP6.1 interactions on AOPs: IATA Development

A6.1.1 Development of IATAs for regulatory purposes – 4 PROJECTS

P6.1.1.a_Y1_HumanRelevance_RIVM (closed M36)

Project Title	Workflow for Human Relevance Assessment of AOPs and Associated New Approach Methodologies		
Project Acronym (15 letters max)	Human Relevance		
Project Manager	Mirjam Luijten Mirjam.luijten@rivm.nl	RIVM	NL
Deputy Project manager	Elisavet Renieri elisavet_renieri@hotmail.com	AUTH	GR
Expected starting date PARC (Month number)	1	Expected duration	36*
PARC Workpackage number	6	PARC Task/Activity/Sub-activity:	6.1.1
Project Id	P6.1.1.a_Y1_HumanRelevance_RIVM		

*The project will be closed M36, a final project report will be submitted M39

P6.1.1.b_Y1_IATA-ED_Uantwerpen (closed M36)

Project Title	Integrated Approaches to Testing and Assessment (IATA) for Endocrine Disruption		
Project Acronym (15 letters max)	IATA-ED		
Project Manager	Dries Knapen Dries.knapen@uantwerpen.be	UAntwerpen	BE
Deputy Project manager	Miriam Jacobs Miriam.Jacobs@ukhsa.gov.uk	UKHSA	UK
Expected starting date PARC (Month number)	1	Expected duration	36*
PARC Workpackage number	6	PARC Task/Activity/Sub-activity:	6.1.1
Project Id	P6.1.1.b_Y1_IATA-ED_UAntwerpen		

*The project will be closed M36, a final project report will be submitted M39

P6.1.1.c_Y1_IATA_GENTOX_Sciensano

Project Title	Integrated Approaches to Testing and Assessment (IATA) for Genotoxicity		
Project Acronym (15 letters max)	IATA-GENTOX		
Project Manager 1	Birgit Mertens birgit.mertens@sciensano.be	Sciensano	BE

Project manager 2	Marc Audebert marc.audebert@inra.fr	INRAE	FR
Expected starting date PARC (Month number)	1	Expected duration	48*
PARC Workpackage number	6	PARC Task/Activity/Sub-activity:	6.1.1
Project Id	P6.1.1.c_Y1_IATA_GENTOX_Sciensano		

*The project has been extended from M36 to M48

Status: Implementation

Summary of the project

The goal of Task 6.1 (T6.1) in PARC is to deliver IATA for a selected set of health effects. The majority of the IATAs will focus on human health; however, environmental health will also be addressed in some projects. To ensure that the IATA will address regulatory needs, they will be developed in close collaboration with relevant stakeholders and evaluated through dedicated case studies. This project is focused on IATA development for genotoxicity, one of the health effects that has been prioritized in the EU CSS. Moreover, genotoxicity is considered a low-hanging fruit for IATA development based on existing data and available test systems. The test strategies for genotoxicity that are in place under the current regulations for the different regulatory frameworks are somewhat similar but often rely on animal testing, and do not integrate NAMs such as 3D comet and micronucleus assays, ToxTracker®, the yH2Ax/pH3 method or transcriptomic-based gene expression biomarkers (e.g. TGx-DDI and GENOMARK). By delivering an IATA, the project aims to move towards the assessment of genotoxicity without the use of animals.

Main expected outputs of the project

The main expected output of the project is an AOP-based IATA for genotoxicity. This will include an overview of the test methods and assays that can be applied and a (partially) quantitative AOP framework for this endpoint. Information on ADME will also be integrated through collaboration with T5.3. The applicability of the IATA will be demonstrated by means of case studies. A first set of case studies will involve known (non-)genotoxicants to evaluate the overall structure and performance of the IATA. More complex compounds will be selected in close collaboration with regulatory agencies such as ECHA and EFSA for the second set of case studies. Overall, this project will provide a conceptual framework for the application of an AOP-based IATA for the assessment of genotoxicity that can be included for future assessment.

Outcomes and impacts expected for end-users and stakeholders

The project impact on stakeholders and end-users will involve a defined IATA for genotoxicity that can be applied for safety testing. It will allow insight in a defined testing approach including the test methods to assess this endpoint without the use of animals. The IATA framework could benefit all EU agencies dealing with genotoxicity assessment (e.g. EFSA, ECHA and EMA), as well as a plethora of regulations addressing this hazard class (REACH, CLP, PPP, etc.), thus contributing to the harmonization of data requirements among EU agencies. Case study compounds will be carefully selected in collaboration with the regulatory agencies to ensure that, wherever necessary, regulation-specific issues are addressed. Regarding REACH, the outcome of this project might have an impact on the revision of the testing requirements, although this will depend on the timeline of the REACH revision and the project. Furthermore, the utility and applicability of a shift towards a more quantitative approach for assessment of genetic toxicity hazard will be explored (e.g. by analysis of genotoxicity data with the benchmark dose modelling (BMD) approach).

Key words

Integrated Approaches for Testing and Assessment (IATA), genotoxicity, DNA damage, gene mutations,

chromosome damage, (quantitative) Adverse Outcome Pathway (AOP), key events

Link to the PARC DoA

This project responds to SO3, and more specifically to OO9.

Links within PARC (WPs/Tasks/Activities/Projects)

For T6.1 the project is linked to the three other T6.1 projects in PARC:

1. P6.1.1.a_Y1_HumanRelevance_RIVM
2. P6.1.1.b_Y1_IATA_ED_UAntwerpen
3. P6.1.1.d_Y1_IATA_STOT_UL-LACDR

To maximize synergy across the T6.1 projects, core teams addressing common elements will be established. These core teams include “AOP networks”, “Quantitative AOPs”, and “IATA development/evaluation”. The project team involved in the project on human relevance will closely collaborate with the other three projects, in particular with the core teams on AOP networks and quantitative AOPs.

The work described in this project is connected to other WPs in PARC, in multiple ways.

Firstly, the proposed priorities regarding regulatory frameworks to be addressed will be confirmed with stakeholders in close collaboration with WP2 “A common science-policy agenda” and WP3 “Synergies, collaboration and awareness”. Secondly, we will closely collaborate with WP5 “Hazard assessment” on various topics related to IATA development. These topics include: a) mapping of existing AOPs and associated NAMs for genotoxicity; b) development of (quantitative) AOP networks using, among others, data generated in WP5 (e.g. data generated with toxins); c) linkage to QIVIVE and PBK modeling (T5.3) and evaluation of IATA through case studies. Within WP6, the case study *T6.3_CS11: Analysis and evaluation of genotoxicity and carcinogenicity assessment across legislations, with a special focus on (Q)SAR based approaches* will be particularly relevant for the mapping of existing AOPs but also for the evaluation of IATA through case studies, we will closely collaborate with T6.2, T6.3 and T6.4. The case studies also provide a link to WP7 “FAIR data”, in which analysis of the uncertainties associated with the IATA will be one of the use cases. Integrative models developed in T8.3 of WP8 will be considered as well. Lastly, this work relates to WP9 “Capacities”, since valuable learnings will be taken up in relevant training courses.

Links outside PARC

The project is closely linked to work done by the HESI Genetic Toxicology Technical Committee (GTTC), on AOP development and NGRA. It is also linked to work ongoing at OECD, in relation to NAMs for genotoxicity (e.g. 3D comet and micronucleus assays, ToxTracker®, the yH2Ax/pH3 method and miniaturized versions of the bacterial reverse gene mutation test), AOP development (OECD AOP programme) and IATA case studies. As such, regular interactions with the OECD EAGMST and the OECD WPHA are foreseen. The link with the work on AOP development for radiation effects done within the context of the “Multidisciplinary European Low Dose Initiative” (MELODI) project will also be investigated. Finally, wherever applicable and relevant, a link to ongoing activities on IATAs for non-genotoxic carcinogenicity will be made as well.

Key PARC Deliverables and Milestones to which the project contributes

The output from this project will substantially contribute to the following key deliverables of WP6:

- D6.5; D6.12: Reports on IATAs and associated case studies (M42; M81; Sciensano)
- D6.11: Harmonized workflow for human relevance assessment of AOPs and associated NAMs (M72, RIVM)
- AD5.5 Inventory of the available (networks of) AOPs, prioritisation and establishment of the framework for further development in PARC (delivered; INSERM)
- Merged AD6.1-AD6.9: Report on draft IATAs for selected endpoints (ED, genotoxicity and STOT) and recommendations/strategies for future IATA development for more complex endpoints. (new delivery date M36; Sciensano/UL-LACDR)

Partners List

Sciensano (BE), INRAE (FR), VUB (BE), UL-LACDR (NL), WU-TOX (NL), ISS (IT), IBMT (DE),

UG-PL (PL), STAMI (NO), LIST (LU), BPI (GR), IRSN (FR), RIVM (NL), KWR (NL), NILU (NO), IRFM (IT), MUI (AT), NIPH (NO), WR (NL).

Schedule

Starting date: 01/05/2022 (M1)

Expected ending date: 30/04/2026 (M48)

Cost:

Expected PM for the fourth year of the project: 51 PM

Expected ODC for the fourth year of the project: 92 267 €

P6.1.1.d_Y1_IATA_STOT_UL-LACDR

Project Title	Integrated Approaches to Testing and Assessment (IATA) for Systemic Target Organ Toxicity		
Project Acronym (15 letters max)	IATA-STOT		
Project Manager	Bob van de Water water_b@lacdr.leidenuniv.nl	UL-LACDR	NL
Deputy Project manager	Joost Beltman j.b.beltman@lacdr.leidenuniv.nl	UL-LACDR	NL
Expected starting date PARC (Month number)	1	Expected duration	48*
PARC Workpackage number	6	PARC Task/Activity/Sub-activity:	6.1.1
Project Id	P6.1.1.d_Y1_IATA_STOT_UL-LACDR		

*The project has been extended from M36 to M48

Status: Implementation

Summary of the project

The goal of Task 6.1 (T6.1) in PARC is to deliver Integrated Approaches to Testing and Assessment (IATA) for a selected set of health effects. The majority of the IATAs will focus on human health; however, environmental health will also be addressed in some projects. To ensure that the IATA will address regulatory needs, they will be developed in close collaboration with relevant stakeholders and evaluated through dedicated case studies. This project is focused on IATA development for STOT. The project will initially focus on liver toxicity, and at a later stage, but in parallel, other types of target organ toxicity will be started such as respiratory toxicity. Liver toxicity is the most often observed toxic effect in 90-day studies and also considered low-hanging fruit for IATA development based on existing data and liver test systems. Yet, liver toxicity is complex and involves different end-points that typically have different mechanisms as well as time course for development. An initial focus will be on liver fibrosis as a critical endpoint. In contrast, for respiratory toxicity there is a need for IATA development and implementation/application of scientifically developed in vitro methods. Lung fibrosis is an important human health end-point and we will consider how an IATA for liver fibrosis could be generalized to other target organs, including lung fibrosis. Note that liver fibrosis is typically a late event following chemical exposure, in part because multiple cell types are involved, and we intend to develop and include appropriate culture systems to properly deal with this issue. Such a system should in principle allow for both single exposure (SE) and repeated exposure (RE) testing, and while the project is running, we will decide on which of these aspects to focus, depending on the challenges related to SE and RE.

Main expected outputs of the project

The main expected output of the project is an IATA for liver toxicity with an initial focus on liver fibrosis that is based on an AOP framework. This will include an overview of the test methods and assays that can be applied and a quantification AOP framework for this endpoint. This project will provide a conceptual framework for the application of an AOP-based IATA for the assessment of STOT that can be included for future assessment of systemic toxicity. The case study of the project will demonstrate the applicability of the established IATA.

Outcomes and impacts expected for end-users and stakeholders

There is currently no IATA for liver toxicity. The project impact on stakeholders and end-users will involve a defined IATA for liver fibrosis that can be applied for safety testing. It will allow insight in a defined testing approach including the test methods to assess this end-point without the use of animals. An IATA for liver fibrosis represents only an initial step in the development of a comprehensive IATA approach that would meet the standard information requirements under REACH (acute, sub-acute and sub-chronic repeated dose toxicity), as these requirements go beyond studying liver effects. Nevertheless, such an IATA will partially inform the information requirements needed for STOT-SE and STOT-RE classification as defined under REACH. These include respectively 8.5.1 (acute toxicity - annex VII), 8.5.2 or 8.5.3 (acute toxicity - annex VIII), and 8.6.1 (short-term repeated dose toxicity study, 28 days - annex VIII), 8.6.2. sub-chronic toxicity study (90-day) (annex IX). Note that in this project we intend to produce a quantitative assessment of the involved assays in relation to the AO, which is an important aspect for STOT SE and STOT-RE classification.

Key words

Integrated Approaches for Testing and Assessment (IATA), systemic toxicity, liver, fibrosis, (quantitative) Adverse Outcome Pathway (AOP), key events

Link to the PARC DoA

This project responds to SO3, and more specifically to OO9.

Links within PARC (WPs/Tasks/Activities/Projects)

The project is linked within the following PARC activities:

For T6.1 the project is linked to three other projects in T6.1:

1. P6.1.1.a_Y1_HumanRelevance_RIVM
2. P6.1.1.b_Y1_IATA_ED_UAntwerpen
3. P6.1.1.c_Y1_IATA_GENTOX_Sciensano

To maximize synergy across the T6.1 projects, core teams addressing common elements will be established. These core teams include “AOP networks”, “Quantitative AOPs”, and “IATA development/evaluation”. The project team involved in the project on human relevance will closely collaborate with the other three projects, in particular with the core teams on AOP networks and quantitative AOPs.

The work described in this project is connected to other WPs in PARC, in multiple ways.

Firstly, the proposed priorities regarding regulatory frameworks to be addressed will be confirmed with stakeholders in close collaboration with WP2 “A common science-policy agenda” and WP3 “Synergies, collaboration and awareness”. Secondly, we will closely collaborate with WP5 “Hazard assessment” on various topics related to IATA development. These topics include: a) mapping of existing AOPs and associated NAMs for endocrine disruption; b) development of (quantitative) AOP networks using, among others, data generated in WP5; c) linkage to QIVIVE and PBK modeling (T5.3); and c) evaluation of IATA through case studies. For the latter, we will also closely collaborate with T6.2 – T6.4. The case studies also provide a link to WP7 “FAIR data”, in which analysis of the uncertainties associated with the IATA will be one of the use cases. Lastly, this work relates to WP9 “Capacities”, since valuable learnings will be taken up in relevant training courses.

Links outside PARC

Furthermore, the project is closely linked to the Horizon2020 projects EU-ToxRisk, RISK-HUNT3R, ONTOX and PrecisionTox, and to work ongoing at OECD in relation to AOP development (OECD AOP

programme) and IATA case studies. As such, regular interactions with the OECD EAGMST and the OECD WPHA are foreseen.

Key PARC Deliverables and Milestones to which the project contributes

The output from this project will substantially contribute to the following key deliverables of WP6:

- D6.5; D6.12: Reports on IATAs and associated case studies (M42; M81; Sciensano)
- D6.11: Harmonized workflow for human relevance assessment of AOPs and associated NAMs (M72, RIVM)
- AD5.5 Inventory of the available (networks of) AOPs, prioritisation and establishment of the framework for further development in PARC (delivered; INSERM)
- Merged AD6.1-AD6.9: Report on draft IATAs for selected endpoints (ED, genotoxicity and STOT) and recommendations/strategies for future IATA development for more complex endpoints. (new delivery date M36; Sciensano/UL-LACDR)

Partners List

UL-LACDR (NL), WU-TOX (L), INSERM (FR), Ugent (BE), AUTH (GR), MU (CZ), IISPV (ES), STAMI (NO), ISS (IT), IRFM (IT), WFSR (NL).

Schedule

Starting date: 01/05/2022 (M1)

Expected ending date: 30/04/2026 (M48)

Cost:

Expected PM for the fourth year of the project: 13 PM

Expected ODC for the fourth year of the project: 9 000 €

P6.1.1.e_Y4_FISH-THSD_UAntwerpen

Project Title	An AOP network-based approach for assessing thyroid hormone system disruptors in fish		
Project Acronym (15 letters max)	FISH-THSD		
Project Manager	Dries Knapen dries.knapen@uantwerpen.be	UAntwerpen	BE
Deputy Project manager	Miriam Jacobs Miriam.Jacobs@ukhsa.gov.uk	UKHSA	UK
Expected starting date PARC	M37	Expected duration (months)	45
PARC Workpackage number	WP6	PARC Task/Activity/Sub-activity:	T6.1.1
Project Id	P6.1.1.e_Y4_FISH-THSD_UAntwerpen		

Status: Initiation

Summary of the project

This project aims to develop and test an AOP network-based approach for the identification of thyroid hormone system disrupting chemicals (THSDCs) in fish. This work addresses important gaps in the currently available tools for the identification of THSDCs by integrating in silico, in vitro and in vivo fish test data for the T modality in a tiered testing approach that is aligned with the ECHA-EFSA Guidance for the identification of EDs. The project addresses different KARC: in the context of ED the project will increase the use of NAMs to allow the identification and regulation of THSDCs, while reducing the need for animal testing.

A series of specific case studies will be developed and executed in collaboration with ECHA, EFSA and other stakeholders, generating new data and re-using existing data for chemicals that are relevant in the

context of specific legislations. Some of the most advanced (not yet fully validated) methods for THSD evaluation will be tested in a regulatory context. The project will run in parallel with the ongoing in vitro and fish in vivo validation efforts (OECD, PEPPER), independent in terms of timing, and will give timely feedback on strengths and weaknesses of methods under validation and on which additional methods may be needed. This will speed up the future implementation of new methods in regulatory frameworks. The project will propose approaches for using in silico, in vitro and fish (protected and non-protected life stages) test data for THSDC identification, in relation to amphibian tests, in the specific contexts of the REACH and CLP legislations as well as the PPPR and the BPR.

Key benefits of the project:

Proactively develops application strategies of fish endpoints under OECD validation: Proactively investigate how assays that are under validation may be applied in a regulatory context. While being independent in terms of timing, mutual feedback between this project and validation efforts will speed up regulatory implementation.

Case study for using fish embryos to assess adversity: Inclusion of a combination of endpoints, together indicative of T-mediated adversity, in the tFET test using non-protected life stages will be tested on compounds with regulatory relevance.

Gain experience with using in vitro tools to predict in vivo outcomes: The relation between (human) in vitro and (fish, amphibian) in vivo data will inform on the extent to which available in vitro assays can predict outcomes in fish and amphibians.

Provides evidence and guidance for using fish vs amphibian data, incl THSD Fish Embryo Acute Toxicity /Xenopus embryonic thyroid signalling assay (tFET/XETA): Fish and amphibian sensitivity will be compared using available amphibian data. Implementation scenarios using fish and/or amphibian tests will be developed.

Directly applicable in the context of PPPR/BPR, REACH/CLP: Development of specific flow charts that facilitate short-term implementation of new assays into existing regulatory approaches.

Fits in the roadmap to phasing out animal testing: Provide an outlook on how these types of assays can be used in the future, with increased reliance on NAMs (in silico, in vitro, FET including adversity, XETA) and reduced reliance on animal testing.

Main expected outputs of the project

The project will provide data on chemicals of regulatory interest and will propose integrated approaches for the identification of THSDCs for aquatic hazard assessment that are supported by OECD-endorsed AOPs and executed using assays that are currently under validation. The project will focus on integrating (1) the measurement of thyroid hormone levels, thyroid histopathology, eye development, swim bladder inflation and behaviour in ZFe and zebrafish larvae as additions to existing OECD TG (TG 236 and TG 210), (2) the in vitro measurement of a selection of relevant THSD mechanisms, (3) and the use of in silico tools. Implementation scenarios will be developed for specific current and future regulatory contexts and will be designed in a tiered fashion that allows the implementation of a decision tree logic with emphasis on the relation to amphibian testing and reducing the overall need for animal testing for environmental ED hazard assessment.

Outcomes and impacts expected on end-users and stakeholders

For environmental THSDC assessment, mostly amphibian tests are being used (e.g., OECD GD 150, ECHA-EFSA ED Guidance). Both in vitro assays and augmented OECD fish TGs (using protected and non-protected life stages) for the identification of THSDCs have been developed and are currently under validation. This project will propose strategies for using these new assays in a tiered ED testing approach for current regulatory contexts and provide a perspective on increased reliance on NAMs and reduced animal testing in line with the EC Roadmap to phase out animal testing for chemical safety assessment. A

gradual approach based on evolving legislation and increasing experience with - and confidence in - the NAMs is envisioned. While our project does not necessarily aim to replace amphibian testing with fish testing, this *can* be a valid approach in some scenarios as for example where a substance is identified as an ED based on T-endpoints in a fish test that is already a part of standard information requirements.

Outcomes and impacts expected to be incorporated into a specific regulatory framework

REACH/CLP: There are at present no standard information requirements for ED identification in the environment. While only amphibian assays are currently available for specifically addressing the T modality, amphibian tests are not included in the standard information requirements. A number of fish tests however, including TG 210, are required, dependent on the tonnage of the chemical. Since the current endpoints in TG 210 are sensitive to, but not diagnostic of, the thyroid modality, inclusion of a diagnostic battery of endpoints for the identification of THSDs in these tests could therefore have immediate regulatory impact. Further, this project will promote the uptake of using THSD in vitro and fish test data for Substance Evaluation by EU member states. In the context of the PPPR and BPR, T modality assessment for non-mammalian non-target organisms will no longer need to be only based on amphibian data. This project will provide a framework for using in silico, in vitro, FET (TG 236) and fish early-life stage (FELS) (TG 210) THSD data providing detailed mechanistic information including hormone measurements and adverse endpoints while reducing the need for animal testing.

Key words: endocrine disruptors, thyroid hormone system disrupting chemicals, fish testing, NAMs

Link to the PARC Description of Action (DoA)

The projects respond to the OOs: OO4, OO5, OO9, OO10, OO11 and OO12.

Briefly describe how the project responds to the PARC objectives indicated above.

The project contributes to fostering regulatory uptake of internationally developed methods in the continuously evolving regulatory landscape (e.g., ED criteria under CLP). Project partners are actively involved in relevant stakeholder groups (e.g., OECD Thyroid Methods Expert Group, OECD VMG-Eco, ECHA ED Expert Group, EFSA ED Working Group) ensuring direct alignment with regulatory needs and rapid uptake.

Links within PARC (WPs/Tasks/Activities/Projects):

The project is linked to the PARC projects P5.3.2.a_Y1_AOPDevelopment_Inserm (the present project is based on the THSD AOP network and data will feed into P5.3.2.a to support further AOP development), P5.2.1.c_Y1_EDThDisruption_DTU (method development in P5.2.1.c is taken up in the present project), new project submitted: P5.2.1.f_DART-ED (development of methods for developmental toxicity with relevance to THSD planned in T5.2.2_DART may be taken up in the present project), new project submitted P5.2.a_Y3_RegNAMs_ANSES on regulatory readiness of NAMs, P6.1.1.a_Y1_HumanRelevance_RIVM (THSD is a common topic of interest), P6.3.2.h_Y1_CS18_ED-classes_BPI: Common interest in use of new test methods for new hazard classes in CLP.

Links outside PARC:

International:

OECD Thyroid Disruption Methods Expert Group (TDM EG) (multiple project partners are experts in this group)

Validation of THSD endpoints in TGs 236 and 210 (OECD project 2.64 on the TG Programme) (The leads of the validation are project partners)

EU:

JRC's EU Reference Laboratory for alternatives to animal testing (EURL ECVAM) "EU-NETVAL validation study to identify potential thyroid disruptors" (JRC is collaborating partner in this project)

MSCA Doctoral Network/Network for Cross-disciplinary assessment of Endocrine Disrupting compounds: training the next generation of toxicologists (NeXED) (the coordinator as well as several partners of NeXED are part of this project)

Key PARC Deliverables and Milestones to which the project contributes

D6.12. 2nd Report on IATAs and associated case studies (M81, SCIENSANO)

Partners List: UAntwerpen (Belgium), UKHSA (United Kingdom), SDU (Denmark), MU (Czechia), CEFAS-DEFRA (United Kingdom), RIVM (Netherlands), UG-PL (Poland), IRFM (Italy), VU (Netherlands)

Collaborating organisation: JRC (EU)*

* *The JRC is supporting the project by providing ad-hoc input e.g. in relation to the status of development of in vitro methods, status of validation, by providing training upon request and by reviewing some of the documentation.*

Schedule:

Starting date: 01/05/2025 (M37)

Expected ending date: 31/01/2029 (M81)

Costs

Expected PM for the first year of the project: 34 PM

Expected ODC for the first year of the project: 49 644 €

P6.1.1.f_Y4_HumanRelevance_RIVM

Project Title	Workflow for Human Relevance Assessment of AOPs and Associated New Approach Methodologies		
Project Acronym (15 letters max)	Human relevance		
Project Manager	Mirjam Luijten Mirjam.luijten@rivm.nl	RIVM	Netherlands
Deputy Project manager	Elisavet Renieri elisavet_renieri@hotmail.com	AUTH	Greece
Expected starting date PARC (Month number)	37	Expected duration (months)	45
PARC Workpackage number	WP6	PARC Task/Activity/Sub-activity:	6.1.1
Project Id	P6.1.1.f_Y4_HumanRelevance_RIVM		

Status: Initiation

Summary of the project

In the context of PARC task 6.1 (T6.1), which aims to develop IATA for selected health effects, this specific project focuses on establishing a harmonized workflow for assessing the human relevance of AOPs and of NAMs that are related to KEs and KERs.

The project addresses the need for a standardized workflow to assess the human relevance of AOPs and their associated NAMs, focusing on KEs and KERs. Currently, no harmonized approach exists to perform these assessments. This project will fill that gap by optimizing a workflow, initially developed in the P6.1.1.a_Y1_HumanRelevance_RIVM project (PARC Y1-Y3). It will improve both qualitative and quantitative aspects of human relevance assessments, including cross-species comparisons and *in vitro* versus *in vivo* data.

Case studies will be a core element to ensure the applicability of the workflow, selected in collaboration with ECHA and EFSA. The goal is to provide a harmonized, transparent workflow for assessing human relevance in RAs, ensuring regulatory applicability across EU frameworks and supporting decision-making in processes like REACH and the CSS.

The project aligns with PARC’s Future Needs: “NAMs to replace animal testing for hazard endpoints” by focusing on replacing animal testing with validated NAMs and ensuring their regulatory acceptance. Additionally, it addresses PARC Need “Read across and NAMs: Development of case studies” by refining case studies that demonstrate the practical application and regulatory relevance of NAMs.

Main expected outputs of the project:

The main output of the project is a pragmatic, harmonized workflow for the assessment of human relevance of both AOPs and associated NAMs. This will not include a workflow as such, but also comprehensive templates for applying and reporting the workflow. Furthermore, it will entail a structured and transparent process for WoE evaluation of all information and data considered in the assessment. The workflow will be accompanied by a set of case studies demonstrating how the workflow can be applied in regulatory practice.

Outcomes and impacts expected on end-users and stakeholders:

The project builds upon the work done in a previous PARC project (P6.1.1.a_Y1_HumanRelevance_RIVM; Y1-Y3), which in turn was building on the WHO IPCS Framework for Mode of Action and Human Relevance. The expected outcome is a pragmatic, harmonized workflow for the assessment of human relevance of AOPs and associated NAMs that are used to measure MIEs and KEs. Firstly, such a workflow will inform on which networks of AOPs should be covered by an IATA or Defined Approach for a given health effect for human health RA. Next, the workflow allows for assessment of the human relevance of NAMs related to the KEs of the pathways under study, thereby providing insight into which NAMs are better suited for detecting perturbation of KE(s). Together, this type of information is highly valuable for end-users, i.e. regulators and industry, and other stakeholders.

Outcomes and impacts expected to be incorporated into a specific regulatory framework:

Information on the human relevance of AOPs (or networks thereof) and on associated NAMs that can be used to measure KEs of such AOPs is highly relevant for all regulatory frameworks that apply to human health. Hence, the expected outcomes and impacts are the same as those mentioned in the previous paragraph.

Key words: human relevance, Adverse Outcome Pathways (AOPs), toxicological mechanisms, Mode of Action, New Approach Methodologies (NAMs), weight of evidence, test methods

Link to the PARC DoA:

This project responds to SO1 and SO3 and to the PARC OOs OO4, OO5, OO7, OO12 and OO9. The envisioned workflow will greatly facilitate the establishment of an overview of the AOPs that should be considered for human health RA. Additionally, it will also help to gain insight which NAMs (provided they are sufficiently robust and meeting criteria for regulatory use) may be better suited to measure perturbation of these AOPs. Finally, we strive for a harmonized workflow to be used across different regulatory jurisdictions. Together, this will be of considerable added value for putting next-generation RA into practice, and thus provide a significant contribution to OO4, OO7 and OO9. The project will also contribute to the PARC OOs by cooperating with other relevant R&I initiatives (OO5), and by providing input to innovative concepts for RA (OO12).

Links within PARC (WPs/Tasks/Activities/Projects)

The project is linked to the projects P6.1.1.b_Y1_IATA_ED_UAntwerpen, P6.1.1.c_Y1_IATA_GENTOX_Sciensano, P6.1.1.d_Y1_IATA_STOT_UL-LACDR and also to the tasks 6.3 (Review of risk assessment methodologies) and 6.4 (Transposing results to regulatory risk assessment methodologies).

WP2, A common science-policy agenda: Achievement of regulatory readiness of the workflow for human relevance assessment will require dedicated discussions with various international regulatory bodies, to ensure that regulatory needs are being addressed.

WP3, Synergies, Communication and awareness: The development of a workflow that is ready for regulatory implementation will strongly benefit from raising awareness, proper communication of the (draft) workflow and collecting feedback from stakeholders. This will be done in close collaboration with WP3.

WP5, Hazard assessment: The workflow is of relevance for T5.2 (development of NAMs for human health risk assessment) and for T5.3 (AOP development). It also relates to the new WP5 project on regulatory readiness.

WP7, DMP, P7.3.3.a_Y3_ ALT-IST_IISPV.

Links outside PARC

Commissioned by the Dutch Ministry of Health, Welfare and Sports, RIVM initiated the development of a workflow for human relevance assessment in 2020. Currently, RIVM is working on refining the workflow on various aspects. The work done is complementary to the work done in PARC, for example by conducting another set of case studies. RIVM provides updates to the PARC project team on the progress made in the national project on a regular basis, to maximize synergies between the projects.

Key PARC Deliverables and Milestones to which the project contributes

D6.11. Report on harmonized workflow for human relevance assessment of AOPs and associated NAMs (M72, RIVM)

D6.12. 2nd Report on IATAs plus associated case studies (M81, SCIENSANO/UL-LACDR)

Partners List: AUTH (GR); RIVM (NL); ENSP (PT); BPI (GR); WU-TOX (NL); NIPH (NO); STAMI (NO); ISS (IT); IISPV (ES); LIST (LU); IRSN (FR)

Schedule:

Starting date: 01/05/2024 (M37)

Expected ending date: 31/01/2029 (M81)

Costs

Expected PM for the first year of the project: 24 PM

Expected ODC for the first year of the project: 16 075 €

A6.1.2 Evaluation of IATAs through case studies

This activity is incorporated in the projects listed under A6.1.1.

A6.1.3 Stakeholder engagement

This activity is incorporated in the projects listed under A6.1.1.

T6.2 Integrative exposure and risk assessment - 8 PROJECTS

The aim of this task is to develop innovative and practical approaches for human health risk and impact assessment of single, aggregated and combined exposure to chemicals *via* multiple sources across regulatory silos and routes during lifetime. Relative contributions of sources and routes will be determined. Living and working environment as well as chemical transfer from soil to water, food, and air and migration from consumer products, articles and materials will be integrated. For estimating and reconstructing chemical exposure through life, accounting for varying exposure scenarios and physiological and biochemical characteristics over time, PBK models will be developed. Simulations of concentrations in target tissues will be linked to AOPs and IATAs. Finally, data availability and methodologies to perform health impact and cost-benefit assessment for prioritised chemicals, exposure routes, windows of exposure, subpopulations, geographical locations, and health outcomes will be improved.

Innovative methods, tools and concepts to perform integrative risk and health impact assessments : combining data and methods from different approaches and disciplines

Fig 9: W6.2: Risk and health Impact Assessment

A6.2.1 Aggregate exposure from multiple sources and routes for general population and workers – 2 PROJECTS

P6.2.1.a_Y1_SourcetoDose_VITO

Project Title	Developing, performing and validation of source to dose modelling including selected case studies		
Project Acronym (15 letters max)	SourcetoDose		
Project Manager	Katleen De Brouwere katleen.debrouwere@vito.be	VITO	BE
Deputy Project manager	Radu Duca radu.duca@lns.etat.lu	LNS	LU
Expected starting date PARC (Month number)	1	Expected duration	42*
PARC Workpackage number	6	PARC Task/Activity/Sub-activity:	6.2.1
Project Id	P6.2.1.a_Y1_SourcetoDose_VITO		

*The project has been extended from M36 to M42

Status: Implementation

Summary of the project

This project aims to model from sources to doses, the human exposure of general population to chemicals, potentially arising from a variety of sources and routes. Sources include different types: environmental sources including 1) emissions from industrial facilities, traffic and households, etc. 2) diffuse environmental sources (e.g., historical soil contamination, water etc), and 3) consumer sources present in our everyday life, (e.g., construction products, household products, etc.) potentially releasing chemicals that may enter our bodies.

It is anticipated that for some source and route of exposure, models do exist, but are (overly) conservative in nature because of their intended uses for screening purposes. However, when it comes to combination of exposures from different sources into an aggregated exposure (and comparison with HBM values) and HIA, realistic external exposure models are crucial, and needed for policy makers (e.g., in view of comparing impact of different policy or RM options).

This project is connected to the project on aggregate exposure modelling. The scope of this project will be routes and sources for which realistic exposure models are currently lacking. Where models are lacking, they will be developed. Where possible, we will rely on existing models and improve them in order to shift from screening models to higher tier models generating realistic exposure estimates.

This project focus is on modelling as a complementary tool to HBM, for the general population (occupational exposure is out of scope). Case studies will be tailored toward chemical classes in line with PARC projects (e.g., case studies on PFAS, flame retardants, metals, pesticides).

The ultimate goal is to come up with robust, mechanistic model(s) and tools which are, at the same time relatively simple in use for risk assessors.

Main expected outputs of the project

- Improvement of existing models for generating realistic exposure assessment for selected consumer articles or products, and environmental sources
- Development of new model(s) for routes and sources for which there is currently a lack of models (for selected sources)
- Transcription of the conceptual model(s) to T8.3

Outcomes and impacts expected for end-users and stakeholders

The role of modelling in aggregate exposure assessment is that modelling offers a complementary tool to HBM to perform chemical RA.

This project will make it possible to end-users to perform RA for chemicals (environment and consumer exposure) covered in this project. It will offer end-users the opportunity 1) to expand the assessment to other groups not included in HBM studies ((e.g. specific age groups, vulnerable groups), 2) to assess the relative contribution of different sources and exposure routes (given that that the models will generate realistic exposure estimates for each source and route), and 3) to calculate the impact of RM options (e.g. predicting impact of restrictions, mitigations). The latter can inform policy makers about the most efficient RM strategies thus allowing for better informed decision making.

Key words: human exposure, modelling, consumer exposure, exposure *via* the environment, realistic exposure modelling, migration, articles

Link to the PARC DoA

OO5: The project will identify data required for source to dose modelling for priority chemicals and exposure scenarios across Europe. The project will use data and knowledge generated and published by other past and ongoing R&I projects and initiatives.

OO7: Based on data gaps that appear from the data and models inventories, studies to fill these gaps may be initiated.

OO8: The project will support the provision of environmental and multisource data for regulatory purposes, since environmental and multisource data are key elements for parameterization and/or verification of source to dose models.

OO10: As the project will use data that are generated outside PARC and by other PARC projects, and will

generate data that can be used by other activities in and outside of PARC, implementation of FAIR data practices is a prerequisite.

OO13: The project will be developing and carrying out training and exchange programmes regarding source to dose models.

Links within PARC (WPs/Tasks/Activities/Projects)

- Connection with T4.1 (HBM data from T.4.1 will be used to validate the model outcome)
- Connection with A6.2.1 Interoperability of models for aggregate exposures:
 - gaps identified will steer the priorities in 6.2.1
 - model outcomes generated in this project can be included in aggregate exposure modelling in 6.2.1.
- Connection with T8.3: outcome (model) will be taken up in T8.3
- Project “Strategy for aggregate exposure from general life and occupational exposures” (project P6.2.1.b_Y1_Aggregate_ANSES)
- Projects from T8.3

Links outside PARC

This project will start from the work of previous initiatives such as the ones from International Society of Exposure Science (ISES) Europe and the REACH Exposure Expert Group (REEG), HBM4EU (WP 12), and 7th FP projects (e.g., 4-FUN)

Key PARC Deliverables and Milestones to which the project contributes

- AD6.3. Roadmap on aggregated exposure strategy through different living environments sources and routes (delivered)
- D6.1. 1st Report on aggregate exposure for general population and workers, and source to dose models applied to case studies (M36)

Partners List:

VITO (BE); RIVM (NL); ANSES (FR); LNS (LU); IVV (DE); CSTB (FR); KWR (NL); IVL (SW); NIJZ (SI); FOPH (CH); GeoZS (SI); FMUL (PT), UoB (UK), IISPV (ES)

Schedule

Starting date: 01/05/2022 (M1)

Expected ending date: 31/10/2025 (M42)

Cost:

Expected PM for the fourth year of the project: 17 PM

Expected ODC for the fourth year of the project: 12 200 €

P6.2.1.b_Y1_Aggregate_Anse

Project Title	Strategy for aggregate exposure from general life and occupational exposures		
Project Acronym (15 letters max)	Aggregate		
Project Manager	Crépet Amélie amelie.crepet@anses.fr	ANSES	France
Deputy Project manager	David Vernez david.vernez@unisante.ch	UNISANTE	Switzerland
Expected starting date PARC (Month number)	1	Expected duration	48
PARC Workpackage number	6	PARC Task/Activity/Sub-activity:	6.2.1
Project Id	P6.2.1.b_Y1_Aggregate_ANSES		

Status: Implementation

Summary of the project

In the context of a compartmentalized view of RA, this project aims to advance knowledge on the combination of various exposure environments including occupational and general life exposures. It will help to propose a more integrative RA and management crossing regulatory silos. This project will draw up the strategy to aggregate exposures from multiple sources and routes in considering both general life and occupational exposures. It is divided into three parts. The first one aims to review available models, tools and data and draw a functional design for model connection. The second part is to work on methods and criteria to perform aggregate exposure and the last part is to organize and start the relevant case studies selected from the defined criteria and PARC priorities. Building from current knowledge, this project is an important step to propose advanced aggregate exposures assessment from multiple sources and routes. It will provide a better understanding of the main sources and routes of exposure during occupational and general life to support effective RM measures.

Main expected outputs of the project

The outputs for model interoperability and data inventory part are: selection of models for further analysis, models and tools description with their structural analysis, functional design for model connection for T8.3, data inventory for T7.1 and data gaps to be feed by T4.1 and T4.2. The outputs for methods for aggregate exposure part are: strategy and roadmap for aggregate RA, innovative methods to perform aggregate RA, criteria for prioritisation of case studies and advance knowledge on the combination of various exposure environments including occupational and general life exposures. The outputs for case studies for aggregate exposure part are: selection of relevant case studies of aggregate exposure including general life and occupational exposures, aggregated exposure results and prioritization of main sources and routes of exposure from general life and occupational environments.

Outcomes and impacts expected for end-users and stakeholders

Provide tools to facilitate comparisons between entry routes and exposure situations and, ultimately, prioritize areas for action and prevention. This project will also make it possible to end-users to perform RA from several sources and routes of exposure. It will make possible to account for both general life and work activities in RA. Concrete case studies will be conducted for prioritized chemicals.

Key words: Aggregate exposure, multiple sources, multiple routes, risk mitigations, occupational exposures, general life exposures, consumer exposure, environmental exposure.

Link to the PARC DoA

This project responds to the PARC OOs OO4, OO6, OO12, OO9 and OO13. This project will develop methods, toolboxes, and organize relevant data to combine exposure from various environments including occupational and general life exposures. In identifying main sources and routes of exposure during occupational and general life, the output of the project will help to prioritize RM measures. Training to the new methods and tools will be proposed with T8.3 to the different stakeholders.

Links within PARC (WPs/Tasks/Activities/Projects)

This project is also strongly connected to other projects from T6.2. As example aggregate exposures can be used as input in mixture (P6.2.3) and health impact projects (P6.2.4). The output of the sources to dose (P6.2.1.a) and PBPk projects (P6.2.2.a) can be used as input of this project.

This project will be strongly connected to the T8.3 on integrative models in involving the task leader WR-BIOM. The objective is to deliver the functional design to task T8.3 for its implementation.

The data inventory will be conducted in connection with the T4.1 and T4.2 and the results of the data gap analysis will be discussed with the leaders to see how they can be handled.

A connection with T7.3 on methods to combine data to account for uncertainty will be also done as aggregate exposure can be a good case study.

It can also propose input for training in WP9.

Links outside PARC

This project will start from the work of previous initiatives such as the ones from ISES Europe and the REEG. It is also linked to the SCCS.

Key PARC Deliverables and Milestones to which the project contributes

AD6.3. Roadmap on aggregated exposure strategy through different living environments sources and routes (including inventory of databases, models and tools (delivered)

D6.1. 1st Report on aggregate exposure for general population and workers, and source to dose models applied to case studies (M36)

AD6.21. Report describing the results of the aggregate strategy and its application (M48) has been cancelled.

Partners List: ANSES (FR), UNISANTE (CH), RIVM (NL), VITO (BE), UU (SE), NIOM (PL), INSA (PT), TNO (NL), NIJZ (SI), AU (DK), TTL (FI), SRU (NL), GeoZS (SI), LNS (LU), ISSeP (BE), CSTB (FR), EFSA (EU), MU (CZ), WR-BIOM (NL), CSIC (ES), INRS (FR), NIPH (NO), KWR (NL), IVL (SE), ISCII (ES), FOPH (CH), STAMI (NO), FMUL (PT), ENSP-UNL (PT), UOB (UK), BPI (EL), AUTH (EL).

Schedule

Starting date: 01/05/2022 (M1)

Expected ending date: 30/04/2026 (M48)

Cost:

Expected PM for the fourth year of the project: 112 PM

Expected ODC for the fourth year of the project: 87 650 €

A6.2.2 Modelling exposure through life – 1 PROJECT

P6.2.2.a Y1 PBPK INERIS AUTH

Project Title	Refinement and development of PBPK models for human risk assessment		
Project Acronym (15 letters max)	PBPK		
Project Manager	Aude RATIER aude.ratier@ineris.fr	INERIS	France
Deputy Project manager	Spyros KARAKITSIOS spyros.karakitsios@gmail.com	AUTH	Greece
Expected starting date PARC (Month number)	1	Expected duration	48
PARC Workpackage number	6	PARC Task/Activity/Sub-activity:	6.2.2
Project Id	P6.2.2.a_Y1_PBPK_INERIS_AUTH		

Status: Implementation

Summary of the project

PBPK models are essential tools in toxicokinetic modelling and RA as they describe the ADME processes in the human body. PBPK models are able to focus on the effective dose at the target site, providing a better characterization of the relationship between exposure dose and adverse effects (Andersen, 1995; Verner et al., 2010). Given the growing interest in using PBPK models in the RA process, guidelines for appropriate extrapolations of species, doses, and exposure scenarios have been proposed. The mechanistic basis of PBPK models is well adapted to toxicological RA (US-EPA, 2006; IPCS, 2010; OECD, 2021), in particular for dealing with extrapolations inherent to these domains (in vitro to in vivo, laboratory animals to humans, various exposure or dosing schemes, etc.). The HBM4EU project reviewed available PBPK models for

several compounds, highlighting a lack of toxicokinetic data for many prioritized compounds and a lack of models for sensitive populations such as pregnant women and their fetuses, newborns, young children, or the elderly. In this PARC project, PBPK models will be refined or developed to address population sub-group sensitivities, integrating multiple exposure routes and sources, and interpreting HBM data. Different sources of data will be used (either from literature or from synergies with WP5) for refining or developing PBPK models necessary for the use of internal dose metrics for RA.

Main expected outputs of the project

PBPK models will be refined or developed to address population sub-group sensitivities, integrating multiple exposure routes (oral ingestion, inhalation, and dermal contact) and sources (occupational, consumer, and environmental), and new matrices of exposure predictive of specific exposure (e.g., hair or meconium for newborns). These models will be applied to biomonitoring data for one chemical or mixtures and will help to interpret them. The experimental needs with WP5 will be identified, and QSAR models will be used to obtain parameters related to kinetics and partitioning. The models developed in this task will be interoperable (in collaboration with WP7 and WP8) with open platform used for RA.

Outcomes and impacts expected for end-users and stakeholders

As PBPK models are tools used to support risk assessors and managers, it is essential to provide models that are adapted to their requirements and that follow the most up-to-date guidance, e.g., the OECD document on the characterisation, validation and reporting of PBK models for regulatory purposes (Series on Testing and Assessment No. 331, ENV/CBC/MONO(2021)1). This project within PARC will focus on the refinement or development of PBPK models for prioritized compounds and mixtures, e.g., with limited information, sensitive populations, and the aggregation of the various exposures. The models that will be proposed will be made interoperable (in collaboration with WP7 and WP8) with other modules in integrative open platforms used for RA.

Key words: PBK models; multi-route exposures; lifelong exposure; sensitive human sub-groups; metabolic interactions; barrier models.

Link to the PARC DoA

The project responds to the PARC objectives OO5: the project will identify models for priority chemicals and sub-groups of population for which refine RA is needed across Europe. The project will use data and knowledge generated and published by other past and ongoing R&I projects and initiatives, OO7: Based on data gaps that appear from the PBK models inventory, studies to fill these gaps may be initiated, OO10: Implementation of FAIR data practices is a prerequisite. PBK models will be developed or implemented under the FAIR principles and OO12: PBK models will be developed to answer or to suggest innovative concepts for RA, and will be available on toolboxes to promote their acceptability.

Links within PARC (WPs/Tasks/Activities/Projects)

Activities undertaken in WP5 (Tasks 5.1, 5.2, 5.3) for the generation of toxicokinetic data and the development of AOP, WP8 (Task 8.3) for the model integration in an open platform, WP4 for the availability of HBM data.

WP6: Other T6.2 projects that aim to link internal and external exposures from multiple sources (6.2.1) and for mixtures (6.2.3):

- Strategy for aggregate exposure in order to confirm external exposure assessment with HBM data.
- New RA and exposome methodologies to reduce exposure and risk of real-life mixtures

Links outside PARC

Bisphenols, PFAS, pesticides, metals and mycotoxins have been priority compounds among the HBM4EU project and modelling efforts, as well as review of existing models and identification of gaps has been carried out.

Some compounds are also EDCs that are studied in the EURION cluster, specifically in the OBERON project.

Links to the exposome projects, such as ATHLETE.

The work in this area that is ongoing outside Europe is also considered (*e.g.*, US-EPA).

Key PARC Deliverables and Milestones to which the project contributes

AD6.4: Inventory of PBK models for assessing the internal exposure through life and for in-vitro-to-in-vivo extrapolation (delivered)

D6.2: 1st Report on innovative methods based on PBK models (M36)

AD6.22: Case studies of the application of refined/developed PBPK models in the risk assessment process (M48) has been cancelled.

Partners List: INERIS (France), AUTH (Greece), IISPV (Spain), ANSES (France), RIVM (Netherlands), SLU (Sweden), NIPH (Norway), VITO (Belgium), WR-BIOM (Netherlands), WR-WFSR (Netherlands), IRFM (Italy), IVL (Sweden), TNO (Netherlands)

Schedule

Starting date: 01/05/2022 (M1)

Expected ending date: 30/04/2026 (M48)

Cost:

Expected PM for the fourth year of the project: 12 PM

Expected ODC for the fourth year of the project: 10 163 €

A6.2.3 Mixture exposure and risk assessment – 1 PROJECT

P6.2.3.a_Y1_RealLifeMixtures_RIVM

Project Title	New risk assessment and exposome methodologies to reduce exposure and risk of real-life mixtures		
Project Acronym (15 letters max)	RealLifeMixtures		
Project Manager	Jacob Van Klaveren jacob.van.klaveren@rivm.nl	RIVM	Netherlands
Deputy Project manager	Amélie Crépet Amelie.crepet@anses.fr	Anses	France
Expected starting date PARC (Month number)	1	Expected duration	48
PARC Workpackage number	6	PARC Task/Activity/Sub-activity:	6.2.3
Project Id	P6.2.3.a_Y1_RealLifeMixtures_RIVM		

Status: Implementation

Summary of the project

The mixture concerns are reflected in the prioritisation process and were ranked as a high priority for many stakeholders and Member States. Furthermore, there is a need to regulate chemicals in such a manner that potential mixture effects are already considered in the registration or authorisation process (prospective RA of mixtures).

The project will build on scientific progress made on MRA, by international organisations (such as EFSA, EEA and ECHA, EC-JRC, OECD), regarding hazard-based grouping of chemical and statistical approaches developed in previous project such as Euromix, HBM4EU and the EHEN exposome projects. The project combines RA and epidemiological approaches to support scientific needs from Member States, DG SANTE and DG Environment. It will integrate the needs identified in the Chemical Strategy and the linked EC

Policy Document SWD 250 final STAFF WORKING DOCUMENT Progress report on the assessment and management of combined exposures to multiple chemicals (chemical mixtures) and associated risks.

The main objectives of the projects are to:

- Build a common strategy to perform human RA to chemical mixtures
- Integrate exposome and RA approaches
- Prioritize real-life mixtures from HBM data
- Develop hazard and kinetic information on prioritized mixtures
- Study the link between mixture biomarkers of exposures and effects
- Perform MRA for prioritized mixtures

Main expected outputs of the project

- Prioritisation methods and/or grouping approaches to select the components to be considered;
- Options to use (eco)toxicity and exposure data on the single components to predict mixture hazard and/or risks, through component-based approaches based on dose additivity;
- Tiered approaches bringing together advances made for mixtures in regulatory RA and in the field of exposome to refine the assessment depending on the availability and quality of exposure and hazard data

Outcomes and impacts expected for end-users and stakeholders

- EFSA, ECHA and EEA in future scientific opinions on RA of mixtures
- EU Member States in communication towards stakeholders and the general public
- Industry addressing the risk of mixtures when assessing the risk of new chemicals before entering the market

The project includes training activities for end-users that will be organised by WP3 and WP9.

Key words: Mixture, HBM, co-exposure, health effects, AOP, RPF, PBPK, risk assessment

Link to the PARC DoA

This project responds to the PARC OOs OO4, OO5, OO6, OO12, OO9 and OO13.

Real-life mixture project will fill-in basic science gaps to explore how human bio-monitoring can be used in practice for MRA. The project is developing a strategy to perform MRA in three main steps: 1) Prioritisation of mixtures considering regulatory priorities 2) Collection and organisation of HBM and hazard data, and 3) MRA for prioritised mixtures and effects. The collected data and the developed approaches will be integrated in the MCRA toolbox which is a web-based computational environment addressing chemical mixtures and their hazard, exposure and RA for health effects. Finally, the project will deliver methods, tools and practical results on prioritized chemical families and effects that will serve regulators to move forward on mixture questions

Links within PARC (WPs/Tasks/Activities/Projects)

This project has strong connection with:

- WP1 : management and indicators
- WP2: priority setting and uptake into policy
- WP3: communication and dissemination of results
- WP4: Derivation of health-based HBM-GVs and link HBM studies to health examination and dietary surveys
- WP5: further hazard characterisation for mycotoxins, PFAS and heavy metals
- WP7: link with external data sources (e.g., IPCHEM, Tox data or EFSA data)
- WP8 : task 8.3 integrative models

This project is strongly connected to other projects from T6.2. For, example aggregate exposures (T6.2.1) can be used as input in this project and development from PBPK projects (T6.2.2) will be directly applied in the context of mixture. This project is cooperating with T4.1 (generation of HBM data), WP7 (data formatting and data organisation) and T8.3 (integrative model development).

Links outside PARC

- HBM4EU legacy: the project will build further on experiences, results, materials, and networks developed within HBM4EU
- EuroMix legacy and EuroMix follow-up: make use of the MCRA software developed in the EuroMix project
- Green Deal projects addressing PFAS and mixtures (e.g., awarded projects as PANORAMIX for mixtures) and “Sustainable Plant Protection Transition” (SPRINT) (pesticides).
- EFSA RACEMIC Roadmap for the Risk Assessment of Combined Exposure to Multiple Chemicals.
- DG SANTE and EFSA-RIVM partnership on Regulatory implementation of dietary RA of pesticide mixtures.
- OECD activity effect biomarkers/AOPs

Key PARC Deliverables and Milestones to which the project contributes

D6.3. 1st Report on innovative approaches for real-life mixture RA (M36)

AD6.5. Report describing co-occurrence probabilities of chemicals forming real life mixtures of the selected HBM studies across Europe and overview of the kinetic and grouping aspects of prioritised mixtures (delivered)

AD6.23 Report describing the results of the mixture RA strategy and its application (M48) was deleted from the Project Description Document and has been cancelled.

Partners List:

ANSES (FR), RIVM (NL), AU-PH (DK), AUTH (EL), BPI (EL), IDAEA-CSIC (ES), IISPV (ES), UGR (ES), DTU (DK), EASP (ES), EFSA (EU), EHESP (FR), FINBA (ES), ICPS (IT), JSI (SI), INERIS (FR), INSERM (FR), ISCH (ES), IVL (SE), LNS (LU), MOHCY/SGL (CY), MU Recetox (CZ), NIJZ (SI), NIPH (NO), SRU (NL), SLU (SE), STAMI (NO), Swiss SECO (CH), TTL (FI), UBA (DE), UGPL (PL), UNIPD (IT), UU-IRAS (NL), VITO (BE), WR (NL), INRAE (FR), KWR (NL), FMUL (PT), GeoZS (SI), UNIVIE (AT), IRFM (IT), IPA (DE)

Schedule

Starting date: 01/05/2022 (M1)

Expected ending date: 30/04/2026 (M48)

Cost:

Expected PM for the fourth year of the project: 197 PM

Expected ODC for the fourth year of the project: 147 863 €

A6.2.4 Human health impact assessment and risk indicators – 4 PROJECTS

P6.2.4.a_Y1_HIADDataAvailability_VITO

Project Title	Collection and generation of data for HIA of PARC priority chemicals		
Project	HIADDataAvailability		
Acronym (15 letters max)			
Project Manager	Jurgen Buekers	VITO	BE
	jurgen.buekers@vito.be		
Deputy Project manager	Jelle Vlaanderen	UU-IRAS	NL
	J.J.Vlaanderen@uu.nl		
Expected starting date PARC (Month number)	1	Expected duration	66*
PARC Workpackage number	WP6	PARC Task/Activity/Sub-activity:	6.2.4
Project Id	P6.2.4.a_Y1_HIADDataAvailability_VITO		

* The project has been broken at M66 (that corresponds to the last landmark of the project) to assess what has been achieved and if the review is positive then then this project could go on until M81.

Status: Implementation

Summary of the project

Availability of data on external or internal exposure (including variation per geographical location and socioeconomic status), health outcomes (based on MoA and dose-response data from toxicological as well as epidemiological studies), relative risk, disease incidence or prevalence, and demographic data are a prerequisite to perform HIA for chemical exposures prioritized in PARC. However, data required to perform environmental burden of disease (EBD) or HIA are often incomplete. This project will evaluate and increase the availability of data for EBD or HIA for PARC priority substances for specific or aggregated exposure routes, windows of exposure, vulnerable populations, occupational settings, geographical locations, age groups, health outcomes etc. Increased availability of suitable data for EBD or HIA calculations for specific exposure scenarios will facilitate HIAs to be used by regulators for evaluation and prioritization exercises. This task supports the 1st and 3rd flagship of the Zero Pollution Action being reducing health inequalities as pollution has no equal impact across society and better monitor the impact of chemicals on our health and progress towards pollution relevant targets set under the Zero Pollution Action and CSS.

This project is part of four interrelated projects on HIA. Together with results of the project on ‘Improvement of HIA methodologies’, the results will serve as input for the projects ‘Case studies on HIA’ and ‘Development of a set of risk and health impact indicators’. The project case studies (6.2.4.c) forms the central starting point to which other projects (6.2.4.a data availability, 6.2.4.b methodologies, 6.2.4.d indicators) are linked (see Fig 10).

Fig 10. Interrelationship between different 6.2.4 projects

Main expected outputs of the project

The inventory and collection or generation of data required for HIA of chemicals and exposure scenarios (specific or aggregated exposure routes, windows of exposure, vulnerable populations, occupational settings, geographical locations, age groups etc.) prioritized in PARC will be linked to the case studies which is a recurring activity every year.

Outcomes and impacts expected for end-users and stakeholders

RA, BoD calculations, HIA, and (social) cost benefit analyses ((S)CBA) inform stakeholders and policymakers to help protect and eventually improve human health. The EU Green Deal, in particular the Zero Pollution Ambition policy, in which the CSS is a cornerstone, aims at reducing the planetary health impact from chemical exposures. HIA and SCBA allow to objectify the impact of current chemical exposure on health in EU populations, prioritize preventive or mitigatory actions to be taken, and estimate the environmental BoD and costs avoided as a result of EU policies and regulations.

Key words: Health impact assessment (HIA), data gaps

Link to the PARC DoA

OO5: The project will identify data required for EBD or HIA calculations for priority chemicals and

exposure scenarios across Europe that are generated and published by other past and ongoing projects and initiatives.

OO6. The project will disseminate results case studies through scientific publication taking into account the FAIR data principle.

OO7: Based on data gaps that appear from the data inventory, exposure or hazard data generation and derivation of population-specific exposures may be initiated.

OO10: As the project will use data that are generated outside PARC and by other PARC projects, and will generate data that can be used by other activities in and outside of PARC, implementation of FAIR data practices is a prerequisite.

Links within PARC (WPs/Tasks/Activities/Projects)

- Measured or modelled internal and external exposure data will be collected in cooperation with WP3, WP4, WP8 and other T6.2 activities and with support from WP7
- Exposure-effect data may be generated by WP4 (epidemiological studies) and in WP5 (toxicity studies)
- T4.1.3 and WP9 will be consulted for information on health data registers
- Projects inside PARC :
 - P6.2.4.b Improvement of health impact assessment methodologies
 - P6.2.4.c Case studies on health impact assessment
 - P6.2.4.d Development of a set of risk and health impact indicators

Links outside PARC

- HBM4EU and NHANES for internal exposure data (*link via VITO, UU-IRAS, ANSES*)
- ATHLETE, EXPANSE, HEALS for exposure data (*link via ANSES*)
- EHEN for exposome data (*link via UU-IRAS*)
- COST Action CA18218 European Burden of Disease Network (*link via Sciensano*)
- EU health information projects (e.g., Population Health Information Research Infrastructure (PHIRI), Towards the European Health Data Space (TEHDAS))

Key PARC Deliverables and Milestones to which the project contributes

- AD6.6. Inventory of existing HIA, exposure and exposure-effect data for chemicals prioritised in PARC (delivered)
- D6.4. 1st Report on health impact indicators and their policy implications (M36)

Partners List:

ANSES (FR); AUTH (EL); DTU (DK); ENSP (PT); FMUL (PT); IISPV (ES); INSA (PT); ISSeP (BE); IVL (SE); KI (SE); MU (CZ); NIJZ (SI); NIPH (NO); NLZOH (SI); OI (SI); SRU (NL); Sciensano (BE); STAMI (NO); USI (CH); UU-IRAS (NL); VITO (BE)

Schedule for the first part of the project:

Starting date: 01/05/2022 (M1)

Expected ending date: 31/10/2027 (M66)

Costs:

Expected PM for the fourth year of the project: 43 PM

Expected ODC for the fourth year of the project: 18 200 €

P6.2.4.b_Y1_HIAMethod_UU-IRAS

Project Title	Improvement of health impact assessment methodologies		
Project	HIAMethod		
Acronym (15 letters max)			
Project	Jelle Vlaanderen	UU-IRAS	NL

Manager	J.J.Vlaanderen@uu.nl		
Deputy	Jurgen Buekers	VITO	BE
Project manager	jurgen.buekers@vito.be		
Expected starting date PARC (Month number)	1	Expected duration	66*
PARC Workpackage number	WP6	PARC Task/Activity/Sub-activity:	6.2.4
Project Id	P6.2.4.b_Y1_HIAMethod_UU-IRAS		

* The project has been broken at M66 (that corresponds to the last landmark of the project) to assess what has been achieved and if the review is positive then then this project could go on until M81.

Status: Implementation

Summary of the project

Data on exposure, exposure-effect relations, health outcomes, relative risk, and demographics can be used for EBD calculations, analytical HIA, cost analysis (direct, indirect and intangible) and cost-benefit analysis for chemical exposures. Several aspects of EBD and HIA methodologies can be improved to reduce uncertainties in EBD estimates and HIA calculations. The methodological improvements of EBD & HIA calculations to be realized via this project will reduce the uncertainties in HIA and allow the use of a broader range of data as input for EBD and HIA calculations. This will improve the usability of EBD and HIA calculations by policy makers for evaluation and prioritization exercises. Specifically for REACH, under the restriction process, authorities should demonstrate the proportionality of the restrictive measure and should justify that the societal gain from improved environmental and human health outweighs any foreseen economic losses. Improvement of the EBD and HIA calculations may support justification of regulatory RM of substances that are of (very) high concern to society. Similarly, e.g. improved EBD and HIA may allow for a better assessment of consequences of not taking action, which may support the Commission in deciding on regulatory action on groups of substances. This is especially useful in the context of the EU Green Deal, particularly the Zero Pollution Ambition Plan in which the CSS is a cornerstone, which aims at reducing the planetary health impact from chemical exposure.

This project is part of four interrelated projects on HIA. Together with results of the project on ‘Collection and generation of data for HIA of PARC priority chemicals’, the results will serve as input for the projects ‘Case studies on HIA’ and ‘Development of a set of risk and health impact indicators’. The project case studies (6.2.4.c) forms the central starting point to which other projects (6.2.4.a data availability, 6.2.4.b methodologies, 6.2.4.d indicators) are linked (see Fig 10).

Main expected outputs of the project

Facilitation of EBD calculations, analytical HIA, cost analysis (direct, indirect and intangible) and cost-benefit analysis and improved confidence in results due to further development and improvement of methods to assess e.g. exposure-effect associations, dynamics in exposure and mixture risks.

Outcomes and impacts expected for end-users and stakeholders

RA, EBD calculations, HIA, and (S)CBA inform stakeholders and policymakers to help protect and eventually improve human health. The EU Green Deal, in particular the Zero Pollution Ambition Plan in which the CSS is a cornerstone, aims at reducing the planetary health impact from chemical exposures. EBD, HIA and SCBA allow to objectify the impact of current chemical exposure on health in EU populations, prioritize preventive or mitigatory actions to be taken, and estimate the EBD and costs avoided as a result of EU policies and regulations.

Key words: Environmental Burden of Disease (EBD), Health impact assessment (HIA), methodologies, uncertainty

Link to the PARC DoA

OO3: Methodological improvements developed in this project may be incorporated in harmonized approaches for EBD and HIA calculations.

OO4: Reduction of uncertainty in EBD and HIA calculations will improve the usability of results by policy makers for evaluation and prioritization exercises.

OO5: Information exchange and collaborations with other networks and initiatives in the area of EBD and HIA will be established.

OO7: Based on methodological issues and uncertainties that are identified via this project, methodological improvements will be developed and implemented during the course of PARC.

OO10: As the project will use data that are generated outside PARC and by other PARC projects, and will generate data that can be used by other activities in and outside of PARC, implementation of FAIR data practices is a prerequisite.

OO13: Methods developed in this project may be disseminated inside and outside of PARC via training and exchange initiatives.

Links within PARC (WPs/Tasks/Activities/Projects)

- P6.2.4.c: Case studies on health impact assessment
- P6.2.4.d: Development of a set of risk and health impact indicators
- T6.2.4: Exposure through life
- T6.4.4 Risk assessment to support and promote efficient overall protection of biodiversity
- T4.1: General population survey, Targeted surveys, Occupational surveys
- T5.3: projects identifying effect biomarkers

Links outside PARC

- HERA project: Guidelines for HIA of environmental factors
- COST Action CA18218 European Burden of Disease Network
- EPHOR: methodology for exposure dynamics (falling risk curves) and for appropriately adding effects estimates of correlated exposures
- HEALS, ICARUS, EXPANSE: ABM models for estimating the expected effect of environmental interventions

Key PARC Deliverables and Milestones to which the project contributes

AD6.6. Inventory of existing HIA, exposure and exposure-effect data for chemicals prioritised in PARC (delivered)

D6.4. 1st Report on health impact indicators and their policy implications (M36)

Partners List:

ANSES (FR); AUTH (EL); DTU (DK); ENSP (PT); FMUL (PT); IISPV (ES); INSA (PT); IVL (SE); KI (SE); MU (CZ); NIPH (NO); OI (SI); RIVM (NL); Sciensano (BE); UBA (DE); USI (CH); UU-IRAS (NL); VITO (BE); WR-BIOM (NL)

Schedule for the first part of the project:

Starting date: 01/05/2022 (M1)

Expected ending date: 31/10/2027 (M66)

Costs:

Expected PM for the fourth year of the project: 53 PM

Expected ODC for the fourth year of the project: 17 575 €

P6.2.4.c_Y1_HIACaseStudies_UU-IRAS

Project Title	Case studies on health impact assessment		
Project Acronym (15 letters max)	HIACaseStudies		
Project Manager	Jelle Vlaanderen	UU-IRAS	NL
	J.J.Vlaanderen@uu.nl		

Deputy Project manager	Jurgen Buekers jurgen.buekers@vito.be	VITO	BE
Expected starting date	1	Expected duration	42*
PARC (Month number)			
PARC Workpackage number	WP6	PARC Task/Activity/Sub-activity:	6.2.4
Project Id	P6.2.4.c_Y1_HIACaseStudies_UU-IRAS		

*The project has been broken at mid-term (M42) to assess what has been achieved at the mid-term and if the review is positive then for the second part of PARC (Y5-Y7), the 6.2.4 projects will be merged into one new project.

Status: Implementation

Summary of the project

EBD analyses are quantitative assessments of the BoD (including morbidity, mortality and financial costs) in a specific population that is attributable to environmental factors such as chemicals. HIA is a tool to estimate the health impact of a policy or program on population health. EBD and HIA analyses for current chemical exposure of EU populations can be used to compare the BoD attributable to different environmental exposures and to prioritize preventive or mitigatory actions to be taken. Case studies will be performed for PARC priority substances.

Based on results of the T6.2.4 projects on data availability and methodological improvements, a selection of case studies will be performed to calculate the health impact and risk/benefit or cost/benefit scenarios for chemical substances, classes or mixtures, adverse health effects and exposed populations prioritized in PARC, using existing data and/or data generated in PARC. The results of the case studies will also feed into the T6.2.4 project ‘Development of a set of risk and health impact indicators’. The case studies (6.2.4.c) form the central starting point to which other projects (6.2.4.a data availability, 6.2.4.b methodologies, 6.2.4.d indicators) are linked (see Fig 10).

Main expected outputs of the project

In year 1, criteria for selection of case studies to be implemented will be defined (e.g., availability of required data, part of the population exposed above HBGVs, possibility for EU-wide assessment) and the case studies to be initiated in year 2 will be selected and designed. In order to define the chemicals and exposure scenarios addressed in the case studies, a risk ranking exercise may be conducted based on evidence-based semi-quantitative methodologies. Prioritization of case studies will take the preferences of key stakeholders into account, across priority societal domains, quantified through multi-criteria decision analysis, and will be done in consultation with WP2 and PARC boards. The selection, design, and performance of case studies will be recurring activities during the course of PARC.

Outcomes and impacts expected for end-users and stakeholders

RA, EBD calculations, HIA, and (social) cost benefit analyses (S)CBA inform stakeholders and policymakers to help protect and eventually improve human health. The EU Green Deal, in particular the Zero Pollution Ambition plan, in which the CSS is a cornerstone, aims at reducing the planetary health impact from chemical exposures. EBD, HIA and SCBA allow to objectify the impact of current chemical exposure on health in EU populations, prioritize preventive or mitigatory actions to be taken, and estimate the EBD and costs avoided as a result of EU policies and regulations.

Key words: Environmental Burden of Disease (EBD), health impact assessment (HIA), case studies

Link to the PARC DoA

OO3: A prioritization framework is developed as part of this project for selection of case studies related to EBD and HIA calculations to be implemented during the course of PARC.

OO4: The project will increase the understanding of the contribution of chemicals as upstream determinants

of diseases. This will support policy makers in the reduction of environmental and human health impact of exposure to hazardous chemicals and as such in the improvement of the protection of environmental and citizen's health.

OO6: Increased understanding of the contribution of chemicals as upstream determinants of diseases will support communication to citizens and increase their awareness about risks of chemical exposures.

OO7: Prioritization and selection of case studies will be a recurring activity to develop annual work plans (AWPs) during the course of PARC.

OO10: As the project will use data that are generated outside PARC and by other PARC projects, and will generate data that can be used by other activities in and outside of PARC, implementation of FAIR data practices is a prerequisite.

Links within PARC (WPs/Tasks/Activities/Projects)

- WP2 for prioritization
- WP3 for stakeholder consultation and communication
- Use of existing data in cooperation with WP3 and data generated in WP4, WP5 and other T6.2 activities
- Data sharing options and integrative model tools provided by WP7 and WP8
- Projects inside PARC:
 - P6.2.4.a: Collection and generation of data for HIA of PARC priority chemicals
 - P6.2.4.b: Improvement of health impact assessment methodologies
 - P6.2.4.d: Development of a set of risk and health impact indicators
 - *Projects from other WPs/Tasks to be identified*

Links outside PARC

Projects generating quantitative chemical exposures and effects data e.g. ATHLETE, “EXposome Powered tools for healthy living in urbAN Setting” (EXPANSE), NHANES, HEALS, NEUROSOME

Key PARC Deliverables and Milestones to which the project contributes

AD6.6. Inventory of existing HIA, exposure and exposure-effect data for chemicals prioritised in PARC (delivered)

D6.4. 1st Report on health impact indicators and their policy implications (M36)

Partners List:

ANSES (FR); AUTH (EL); BPI (EL); DTU (DK); ENSP (PT); FMUL (PT); IISPV (ES); INSA (PT); KI (SE); NIPH (NO); OI (SI); SRU (NL); Sciensano (BE); STAMI (NO); UU-IRAS (NL); VITO (BE)

Schedule for the first part of the project:

Starting date: 01/05/2022 (M1)

Expected ending date: 31/10/2025 (M42)

Costs:

Expected PM for the fourth year of the project: 31 PM

Expected ODC for the fourth year of the project: 2 000 €

P6.2.4.d_Y1_HIAIndicators_VITO

Project Title	Development of a set of risk and health impact indicators		
Project	HIAIndicators		
Acronym (15 letters max)			
Project Manager	Jurgen Buekers	VITO	BE
Deputy Project manager	Jelle Vlaanderen	UU-IRAS	NL
	J.J.Vlaanderen@uu.nl		

Expected starting date	1	Expected duration	42*
PARC (Month number)			
PARC Workpackage number	6	PARC Task/Activity/Sub-activity:	6.2.4
Project Id	P6.2.4.d_Y1_HIAIndicators_VITO		

*The project has been broken at mid-term (M42) to assess what has been achieved at the mid-term and if the review is positive then for the second part of PARC (Y5-Y7), the 6.2.4 projects will be merged into one new project.

Status: Implementation

Summary of the project

Indicators related to exposure, risk and health impact of chemical exposure support national and European policy makers and can complement and support monitoring frameworks for e.g., the CSS, the Zero Pollution Action Plan, and the 8th Environment Action Programme .

The suitability of one indicator over another depends on the policy questions that need to be answered, the availability and quality of data, the uncertainties of each indicator, and on the availability of resources and expertise. Indicators applying generally to detrimental effects of chemicals range from attributable cases to DALYs/QALYs and external costs. When insufficient data for health impact analysis are available, exceedance of HBGVs (RCR, MOE, ..) can be used to indicate which part of the population is exposed to levels above such guidance values as a measure of potential health impact.

This project is part of four interrelated projects on HIA and will interact with the three other projects: ‘Collection and generation of data for HIA of PARC priority chemicals’, ‘Improvement of HIA methodologies’, and ‘Case studies on HIA’. The case studies (6.2.4.c) form the central starting point to which other projects (6.2.4.a data availability, 6.2.4.b methodologies, 6.2.4.d indicators) are linked (see Fig 10).

Main expected outputs of the project

An inventory of different types of existing exposure, risk and health impact indicators for exposure to chemical (single, combined, aggregated, ..) will be made, followed by a proposal for development of (complementary) indicators based on PARC data and results (including outcomes of the T6.2 projects on data availability and methodological improvements). A selection of indicators integrating dynamic exposure and hazard data and accounting for variability in the population and for uncertainties will be developed in subsequent years, to assess the health impact of specific exposure scenarios (including between- and within-person variance estimates, and dynamics of population exposure and health risk via combining monitoring data with exposure trends as a function of specific socio-economic parameters that condition the level of population exposure per route and pathway). A link will be made with current policies to support policymakers.

Outcomes and impacts expected for end-users and stakeholders

RA, EBD calculations, HIA, and (S)CBA inform stakeholders and policymakers to help protect and eventually improve human health. The EU Green Deal, in particular the Zero Pollution Ambition policy, in which the CSS is a cornerstone, aims at reducing the planetary health impact from chemical exposures. EBD, HIA and SCBA allow to objectify the impact of current chemical exposure on health in EU populations, prioritize preventive or mitigatory actions to be taken, and estimate the EBD and costs avoided as a result of EU policies and regulations. Indicators related to health impact of PARC priority substances can be developed to support policymakers. Similar kind of indicators were developed for HBM4EU focusing on RA <https://www.mdpi.com/1660-4601/15/10/2085> , <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S1438463923000020?via%3Dihub> and <https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/36434900/>.

Key words: Environmental Burden of Disease (EBD), health impact assessment (HIA), indicators

Link to the PARC DoA

OO3: Prioritization and selection of indicators to be developed during the course of PARC is part of this project.

OO4: Development of exposure, risk, health impact and cost indicators will increase the understanding of the contribution of chemicals as upstream determinants of diseases and support policy makers in the reduction of environmental and human health impact of exposure to hazardous chemicals and as such in the improvement of the protection of environmental and citizen's health.

OO5: Information exchange and collaborations with other networks and initiatives in the area of EBD and HIA will be established.

OO6: Development of indicators will support communication to citizens and increase their awareness about risks of chemical exposures.

OO7: Prioritization and selection of case studies will be a recurring activity to develop AWP's during the course of PARC.

OO9: Calculation and visualization tools for risk and health impact assessment may be developed in a later stage in this project.

OO10: As the project will use data that are generated outside PARC and by other PARC projects, and will generate data that can be used by other activities in and outside of PARC, implementation of FAIR data practices is a prerequisite.

OO13: Indicator development applied in this project may be disseminated inside and outside of PARC via training and exchange initiatives.

Links within PARC (WPs/Tasks/Activities/Projects)

- Cooperation with T1.3 for the Partnership monitoring framework, WP2 for prioritization and policy uptake, and WP3 for communication
- Exchange of data and computation and visualization tools in collaboration with WP7 and Task 8.3.
- Projects inside PARC:
 - P6.2.4.a: Collection and generation of data for HIA of PARC priority chemicals
 - P6.2.4.b: Improvement of health impact assessment methodologies
 - P6.2.4.c: Case studies on health impact assessment

Links outside PARC:

Exchanges with stakeholders such as JRC and EEA are ongoing to align the PARC activities with development of an indicator framework for the EC CSS, among others.

Key PARC Deliverables and Milestones to which the project contributes

D6.4. 1st Report on health impact indicators and their policy implications (M36)

Partners List:

ANSES (FR); AUTH (EL); ENSP (PT); FMUL (PT); INSA (PT); IVL (SE); MU (CZ); NIJZ (SI); OI (SI); Sciensano (BE); UU-IRAS (NL); VITO (BE); WR-BIOM (NL)

Schedule for the first part of the project:

Starting date: 01/05/2022 (M1)

Expected ending date: 31/10/2025 (M42)

Costs:

Expected PM for the fourth year of the project: 19 PM

Expected ODC for the fourth year of the project: 938 €

T6.3 Review of risk assessment methodologies - 3 PROJECTS

Review of current regulatory RA methodologies within and across relevant chemical sectors will be performed through a series of case studies. Effectiveness of the methodologies will be reviewed. The case studies will provide science-based support for method development, identify R&I needs as well as suggest

improvements and harmonisation opportunities. For the first years, the case studies will focus on two areas: substance and effect specific reviews and use of tools, criteria, and methods. Thereafter the focus areas will be evaluated, and either be further analysed through additional case studies or, if relevant, replaced with new focus areas. Final conclusions and recommendations based on the case studies performed will be generated, also considering the EU-wide relevance.

A6.3.1 Substance and effect specific reviewers – 2 PROJECTS

P6.3.1.a_Y1_SubstanceRA_SU

Project Title	Review of substance-specific risk assessment		
Project Acronym (15 letters max)	SubstanceRA		
Project Manager	Olwenn Martin olwenn.martin@ucl.ac.uk	University College London	United Kingdom
Deputy Project manager	NA	NA	NA
Expected starting date PARC (Month number)	1	Expected duration	48
PARC Workpackage number	6	PARC Task/Activity/Sub-activity:	6.3.1
Project Id	P6.3.1.a_Y1_SubstanceRA_SU		

Status: Implementation

Summary of the project

There is a significant number of EU legislations in force that deal with chemicals directly or indirectly. These rules have been developed at different points in time and for different purposes. Attempts have been made to harmonize and streamline different parts of the regulatory system. Nevertheless, the regulatory system for RA is still scattered across different laws and agencies, and between EU and national levels. This has led to a situation where there are inconsistencies between the different regulatory frameworks. Meeting the concerns about inconsistencies and inefficiency requires a move towards a more holistic approach. This is in line with the foreseen development towards a OSOA approach. The [CSS](#) sets the objective to move towards OSOA approach by improving efficiency, effectiveness, coherence and transparency of the delivery of safety assessments of chemicals across all relevant legislation.

Case studies will be performed to review substance-specific assessments to understand the differences and similarities based on intended use, and subsequent implications, across legislations. The case studies will evaluate opportunities for improving particular aspects of the RA of chemicals. This will include aspects such as data availability and/or data sharing mechanisms, methodologies for hazard and exposure assessment, and assessment of the effectiveness of potential mitigation measures considering the impact on the environment and safety of the consumer.

The project currently contains case studies on coordination needs towards a OSOA approach looking at specific substances (case study CS12_MethodOSOA_SU has been extended from M36 to M42), plastic additives (case study CS13_PlasticizersRA_UCL has been extended from M24 to M36), and substances with biocidal properties (case study CS14_BiocidesRA_SU, closed M24).

Main expected outputs of the project

An analysis of how to contribute to the harmonization or consolidation of requirements, guidance, and practices, and move towards a OSOA approach in the EU.

Mapping of relevant legislation linking to functions of additives in specific polymers for various intended use, including a report describing current regulatory processes in relevant legislation, analysing

commonalities and differences and justification thereof, as well as barriers and opportunities for harmonisation, and recommendations for policymakers.

Outcomes and impacts expected for end-users and stakeholders

The outcomes of this project may serve as a ground for adjustments of the relevant regulations. The identification of dissimilarities in testing requirements and HAs of substances depending on specific uses will offer valuable information for the implementation and potential impacts of the OSOA approach on regulations targeting specific uses of chemicals. Further, the potential barriers and opportunities, and available methods, for harmonisation in a systematic way will be presented. The analysis of the justification for RM measures will reveal implicit or explicit value judgment that may inform the development and refinement of the essential use criteria.

Keywords: One Substance One Assessment, harmonisation, biocides, plastic, polymer, additives, essential use, circularity

Link to the PARC DoA:

The project will mainly contribute to the PARC OOs OO4, OO7, and OO9 by generating knowledge on substance-specific RAs performed across regulatory frameworks and thus informing and supporting the development and use of new RA approaches and methods, regulatory processes, and policy developments (OO4, OO7). The project will be performed in close collaboration with authorities and agencies to promote and facilitate the uptake of the results in RA and regulatory contexts and will provide input to the design and implementation of projects in other Tasks and WPs related to the regulations and aspects reviewed (OO4, OO9).

The project will also contribute to the PARC OOs by providing input to priority-setting (OO3), cooperate with other relevant R&I initiatives (OO5), communicate and disseminate results (OO6), implement FAIR data practices to enable open science (OO10), provide input to innovative concepts for RA (OO12), and share the results and experiences through training (OO13).

Links within PARC (WPs/Tasks/Activities/Projects):

WP2: Prioritizations of chemical substances.

WP3: Synergies, Communication and awareness: Various initiatives related to the issue of additives in polymers may be underway in European institutions such as the Commission, EFSA or JRC. Being alert to such developments, particularly if they are not widely advertised by responsible institutions could avoid the duplication of efforts or identification of synergies.

WP6: Potential interactions identified within WP6 that need to be explored further; Project 6.2.1.a Source-to-dose models, Activity 6.4.3 Comprehensive review and application of databases in materials.

WP7: DMP

WP8: Can inform case use studies for SSbD criteria (task 8.1).

Links outside PARC:

Work currently undertaken under the auspices of the Food Packaging Forum may potentially be of interest, specifically the FCCMigex database (<https://www.foodpackagingforum.org/fccmigex>) or other tools available from <https://www.plastiverse.org/tools>. The project will also take note of the Plastic additives initiative by ECHA 2016-2018 (Plastic additives initiative - ECHA (europa.eu)).

Linked to activities within the OECD WPHA project *Tools and good practices to improve the use of academic data in regulatory assessments*, led by JRC and DG Environment within the working group OSOA.

Key PARC Deliverables (or Additional Deliverables) and Milestones to which the project contributes:

D6.6 '1st Report on conclusions from case studies reviewing RA methodologies' due M42.

D6.17 '2nd Report on conclusions from case studies reviewing RA methodologies' due M81.

MS13 'Mid-term review of the PARC activities, performance and budget' due M42.

Partners List:

SU (SE), UCL (UK), Sciensano (BE), IRFM (IT), KI (SE)

Schedule:

Starting date: 01/05/2022 (M1)

Expected ending date: 30/04/2026 (M48)

Cost:

Expected PM for the fourth year of the project: 26 PM

Expected ODC for the fourth year of the project: 1 314 €

P6.3.1.b_Y1_EffectRA_BPI

Project Title	Review of effect-specific risk assessment		
Project Acronym (15 letters max)	EffectRA		
Project Manager	Dimitra Nikolopoulou d.nikolopoulou@bpi.gr	BPI	Greece
Deputy Project manager	Emma Westerholm Emma.Westerholm@kemi.se	KEMI	SE
Expected starting date PARC (Month number)	1	Expected duration	48
PARC Workpackage number	6	PARC Task/Activity/Sub-activity:	6.3.1
Project Id	P.6.3.1.b_Y1_EffectRA_BPI		

Status: Implementation

Summary of the project

Chemical RAs are currently performed under various regulatory frameworks and at different points in time by responsible EU agencies, scientific committees, expert groups, or Commission departments. The European Green Deal and Commission CSS (COM(2020) 667 final, Brussels, 14.10.2020) highlight the need for innovation in regulatory RA to rapidly and effectively identify chemicals with hazardous properties for human health and the environment through a simpler “OSOA” process. The project will be implemented through case studies reviewing RA methodology concerning specific endpoints that are highlighted as priority in the EC Chemicals Strategy. Currently, this includes endocrine disruption (case studies CS10_ED-cosmetics_VUB has been extended from M32 to M42, CS17_ED-in vitro_BPI and CS18_ED-classes_BPI have been extended from M36 to M48), skin sensitisation (case study CS9_SKINSENSIRISK_REGIONH), genotoxicity and carcinogenicity (case study CS11_GenotoxCarc_ISS), and DNT (case study CS15_DNT_SU has been extended from M36 to M48). The case studies will review current regulatory practices across regulatory areas in EU. The goal is to evaluate and suggest opportunities for improving and harmonising particular aspects of RA methodology, including bridging legislative inconsistencies.

Over the past few years, chemicals with endocrine disrupting (ED) properties have been identified under different regulatory frameworks, including Regulation (EC) 1107/2009 (PPPR), Regulation (EU) 528/2012 (Biocides Products Regulation, BPR), Regulation (EC) No 1907/2006 (REACH) and Regulation (EC) No 1223/2009 (Cosmetic Products Regulation, CPR). Whilst all of these pieces of legislation endorse the WHO/IPCS (2002) definition for an ED, different methodology and approaches are followed for ED assessments of chemicals. The EFSA/ECHA Guidance for the identification of EDs in the context of Regulations (EU) No 528/2012 and (EC) No 1107/2009 has been endorsed to provide harmonised scientific criteria for the identification of pesticides with ED properties but not for chemicals regulated under REACH or the CPR. Moreover, the use of experimental animals for safety assessment is fully prohibited under CPR.

since March 2013. The new hazard classes on ED properties are expected to substantially contribute to harmonization in the identification of ED chemicals across EU.

Skin sensitization is a systemic repeat dose toxicity caused by chemicals leading to permanent changes in the immune system and potentially chronic skin disease in case exposure continues. At least 25% of the European adult population are sensitized to one or more chemicals from consumer products and/or exposures in the work environment. Skin sensitization may lead to permanent skin disease, affect quality of life, and impair work ability. The economic expenses on a European level is considerable, alone skin sensitization due to fragrance ingredients is estimated to cost 11-16 billion Euro/year.

Genotoxicity and carcinogenicity are essential components of human health safety assessment. Although various EU and international regulations are open to the use of approaches different from standard toxicology tests on animals, such as *in vitro* short-term tests and structure-activity based methodologies, today's alternative strategies generally rely on paradigms that fail to detect the full spectrum of genotoxic and carcinogenic chemicals.

An additional case will evaluate conclusions drawn in guideline-compliant DNT studies considered under different legislative frameworks for regulation of plant protection products, biocides, food contact materials and chemicals under REACH, depending on data availability.

Main expected outputs of the project

- Development of specific criteria for evaluation of non-validated *in vitro* methods to facilitate ED assessments across regulatory frameworks ; identification of methodological differences in the assessment of substances with ED activity among legislative frameworks on cosmetics and on other chemicals; development of guidance on the added value of NAMs in classification of chemicals for endocrine disrupting properties under the new CLP criteria and for shifting away from animal testing through a WoE approach.
- Evaluation of the performance and efficacy of current legislation on skin sensitisation assessment, including practices for mixtures of skin sensitizers; identification of knowledge gaps and suggestions for improvements in RA.
- Development of protocols and recommendations summarising the main directions for increasing the regulatory acceptance of QSAR-related methodologies in genotoxicity and carcinogenicity RA.
- Advance the understanding of overall compliance in guideline DNT studies.

Outcomes and impacts expected for end-users and stakeholders

This project aims to assist Member State Regulatory Authorities, EU agencies, Scientific Committees, Expert Groups, relevant Commission Departments and the Industry in adopting harmonised RA methodologies on selected human health effects:

- Contribute to a harmonized way of using existing and emerging NAMs for RA of compounds with potential ED concerns.
- Remove current bottlenecks regarding acceptance of non-validated *in vitro* ED test methods; provide confidence in risk assessors and consistency in the assessment of data from non-validated ED test methods for use in WoE assessment.
- Contribute to the harmonized implementation of the new CLP criteria on hazard classes for endocrine disruption taking into consideration all available methods and tools.
- Contribute to the development of harmonised RA methodology on skin sensitisation.
- Identify the most relevant gaps and inconsistencies in current legislation for genotoxicity and carcinogenicity RA, highlighting potential of improvement and harmonization.
- Support the integration of information from different sources (e.g., NAMs, AOPs) identifying their best placement into genotoxicity and carcinogenicity RA detailing and addressing the underlying uncertainties.
- Identify areas where further development of legislation or regulatory practice is needed regarding the performance of DNT studies highlighting potential of improvement and harmonization to ensure a high level of protection for human health.

Key words: risk assessment; endocrine; *in vitro*; skin sensitization; (Q)SAR; genotoxicity, carcinogenicity, DNT, reliability, relevance, NAMs

Link to the PARC DoA:

The project will mainly contribute to the PARC OOs OO4, OO7, and OO9 by reviewing current methodology for chemical RA across different regulatory frameworks with focus on specific priority endpoints, i.e., endocrine disruption, skin sensitisation, genotoxicity and carcinogenicity and skin sensitisation. The project aims to identify knowledge gaps and areas where harmonisation is mostly needed and provide recommendations for increasing regulatory acceptance of NAMs in chemicals RA (OO4, OO7). This outcome is expected to provide input to related projects on the use of NAMs and IATA development towards the transition to NGRA (OO7, OO9). Identification of potential limitations in the use of NAMs is expected to inspire the design of new projects and case studies under different WPs within PARC (OO4, OO9). Collaboration with regulatory agencies and authorities is expected to promote and facilitate the uptake of results in the regulatory context (OO4, OO9).

The project will also contribute to the PARC OOs by providing input to priority-setting (OO3), cooperate with other relevant R&I initiatives (OO5), communicate and disseminate results (OO6), implement FAIR data practices to enable open science (OO10), provide input to innovative concepts for RA (OO12), and share the results and experiences through training (OO13).

Links within PARC (WPs/Tasks/Activities/Projects):

The following links of this project to other PARC activities are identified:

- WP2: Contribute to priorities as defined in WP2 to meet the EC’s CSS Towards a Toxic-Free Environment; contribute to the link between research and regulatory science.
- WP3: Foster synergies and collaborations with other projects at national, EU and international level.
- WP5: Provide feedback on assessment criteria of *in vitro* studies available in the open literature that could be used to assist identification of regulatory gaps for priority compound testing; DNT activities.
- WP5/Task 5.3: Assist the development of new AOP(s) for non-genotoxic carcinogenesis.
- WP6/Task 6.1: Provide feedback for the evaluation of *in vitro* studies for use in IATAs development on EDs and assist the development of quantitative networks of AOPs and IATA for genotoxicity.
- WP6/Task 6.4/Project P6.4.1.c_Y3_Skinsenmix_RegionH: Provide feedback on the additive or synergistic effects of mixtures of skin sensitizers.
- WP6/Task 6.4/Project P6.4.2.d_Y4_RegulatoryNAMs_ISS: Developing and fostering the uptake of innovative, effective and protective regulatory approaches.
- WP7: Align with data management plan
- WP9: Scheduled training activities

Links outside PARC:

- Endocrine Disruption: Links with the EURION cluster, the work performed by the OECD Performance Based TGs, the OECD IATA Case Study Project, the ABU Project, Better use of academic data (CSS), the activities of the CARACAL Subgroup on EDs (CASG ED), one-substance one-assessment.
- Skin sensitisation: Collaboration with University of Copenhagen on immune reactions to skin sensitizers, ongoing activities in France, Germany and Ireland on the potential need for regulatory action on skin sensitizers in consumer mixtures, workshop in Brussels on Application of the EU Cosmetics Regulation and relevant OSH Directives for the safe use of cosmetic products (25/10/2022), workshop in Basel on model development for quantitative RA for skin sensitising pesticides (August 2022) by the State Secretariat for Economic Affairs (SECO) - Chemicals and Occupational Health, and the Swiss Centre for Applied Human Toxicology together with an international scientific organising committee.
- Genotoxicity and carcinogenicity: Links with OECD (Chemicals and Biotechnology Committee (OECD / EHS Prog.), QSAR Assessment Framework project, IATA case studies project, QSAR Toolbox Management Group, EAGMST (AOP Programme), WG on revision of Genotoxicity TGs); ECHA (Member State Committee (MSC), Committee for Risk Assessment (RAC), Risk Management and Evaluation (RiME+) platform, Competent Authorities for REACH and CLP (CARACAL)); and EFSA

(Expert Panel on Food Additives and Flavouring (FAF), Working Group on Genotoxicity of the Scientific Committee, Working Group on Technological Additives of the Expert Panel on Feed Additives and Products (FEEDAP), and working groups on genotoxicity and toxicology).

- Developmental neurotoxicity: Links with EFSA, ECHA, EU Commission.

Linked to activities within the OECD WPHA project *Tools and good practices to improve the use of academic data in regulatory assessments*, led by JRC and DG Environment within the working group OSOA.

Key PARC Deliverables (or Additional Deliverables) and Milestones to which the project contributes

Findings of the project will feed into the following PARC deliverables and milestones:

- D6.6 ‘1st Report on conclusions from case studies reviewing RA methodologies’ due M42
- D6.17 ‘2nd Report on conclusions from case studies reviewing RA methodologies’ due M81
- MS13 ‘Mid-term review of the PARC activities, performance and budget’ due M42

Partners List:

REGIONH (DK), STAMI (NO), SU (SE), IRFMN (IT), UNIBAS (CH), VUB (BE), BPI (EL), KI (SE), INSERM (FR), INERIS (FR), EAA (AT), ISS (IT), NILU (NO), INSA (PT), UBA (DE), INRAE (FR)

Schedule:

Starting date: 01/05/2022 (M1)

Expected ending date: 30/04/2026 (M48)

Cost:

Expected PM for the fourth year of the project: 56 PM

Expected ODC for the fourth year of the project: 25 500 €

A6.3.2 Use of tools, criteria, and methods – 1 PROJECT

P6.3.2.a_Y1_ToolsRA_SU

Project Title	Review of tools, criteria, and methods used in risk assessment		
Project Acronym (15 letters max)	ToolsRA		
Project Manager	Jussi Reinikainen jussi.reinikainen@syke.fi	Finnish Environment Institute, SYKE	Finland
Deputy Project manager	NA	NA	NA
Expected starting date PARC (Month number)	1	Expected duration	48
PARC Workpackage number	6	PARC Task/Activity/Sub-activity:	6.3.2
Project Id	P6.3.2.a_Y1_ToolsRA_SU		

Status: Implementation

Summary of the project:

The European Green Deal and the Initiative on the CSS set as a priority for the next generation chemical safety assessments the development and implementation of the OSOA process. This project aims at reviewing current RA practices, including tools, criteria and methods currently used within and across regulatory frameworks, assessing the level of protection to human health and the environment and making suggestions from improvements in the broader context of ‘OSOA’.

This project will review the processes as well as the use of tools, criteria and methods, both within and across legislations, in order to promote more transparent and consistent evaluation of scientific information

and data. The case studies will cover issues such as RA methodologies, test requirements, effectiveness towards risk reduction, sources of uncertainty as well as methodological challenges in implementing uncertainty analysis and bridging of data gaps in RA. Case studies related to the specific areas of environmental and occupational RA have also been developed. Other specific areas in regulatory RA may additionally be identified during the course of PARC.

The project currently contains case studies on comparative analysis of risk-based decision benchmarks (CS1_CARB_SYKE has been extended from M36 to M48), identification and review of methods for evaluating the effectiveness of RA for reducing risk (CS2_RiskReduction_SU will be closed M36), practical challenges in using quantitative expressions of uncertainty in assessment (CS16_UncertaintyRA_ULUND has been extended from M36 to M48), the status of chemical data gap filling approaches (CS19_DataGapFilling_KEMI-DTU, new case study added year 2 closed M30) and understanding the implementation and use of NAMs in pesticide dossiers in both the HH and the environment CS20_PESTNAM_ISS (new case study added year 3).

With regard to ERA, two case studies are currently included on protecting the same ecosystem under different regulations (case study CS7_REGPREP_EAWAG: first project phase on surface water and sediment and a second one on soil and air that Soil and air would be during the last 4 year) and secondary poisoning and protection of wildlife (case study CS4_SecPoisoning_INERIS has been extended from M38 to M48).

With regard to occupational RA, two case studies are currently included on occupational exposures to reproductive and developmental toxicants (case study CS8_OccupReproDev_KI has been extended from M36 to M48) and workplace chemical RA (case study CS3_WorkplaceRA_TTL will be closed M36).

Main expected outputs of the project:

- Identify inconsistencies, loopholes and gaps in the current chemical RA frameworks.
- Contribute to an increased understanding of how to measure the effectiveness of RA aimed at reducing risk.
- An overview of options beyond AOP, NAM and IATA development for a sustainable regulation of chemicals.
- A general introduction to uncertainty analysis for RA in a PARC context.
- A systematic overview of currently used and state-of-the-art chemical data gap-filling approaches applied across EU legislations
- A review on the current PPP ERAs under different regulations.
- Practices for properly assessing the risk of secondary poisoning under different regulatory schemes.
- Comparison of coverage of known reproductive toxicants by OELs and DNELs.
- Evaluation of how regulatory information provided under different regulatory processes is utilized in workplace chemical RA and risk mitigation in practice.

Outcomes and impacts expected for end-users and stakeholders:

The project will guide the future design of legislation on chemical RA, focusing on sustainable management of chemical risks, as well as the implementation of the “OSOA” approach. The project will provide regulators, legislators and other stakeholders an in-depth understanding of the commonly used decision benchmarks and the significance of their appropriate foundation and application. The project will provide options for sustainable chemical control beyond NAM, AOP, and IATA development, including possible approaches for the assessment of non-chemical alternatives to chemical biocides and pesticides. The project will provide new knowledge about the practical challenges in using quantitative expressions of uncertainty in assessment, as well as pedagogical examples on how to implement quantitative expressions of uncertainty and the benefit of these in assessment and communication. The project will provide recommendations for harmonizing data gap-filling approaches in relevant EU legislations, which will have an impact on the practices of filling data gaps during compliance reporting, monitoring and assessment by companies, scientists, and policymakers alike.

Keywords: data gaps, uncertainty, sustainable chemical control, effectiveness, comparative analysis, reference value, environmental risk assessment, OSOA, secondary poisoning, occupational exposure.

Link to the PARC DoA:

This project will contribute towards the WP6.3 objective to “map and evaluate current methodologies employed in regulatory RA to identify gaps and needs in methodological knowledge”.

The project will contribute to PARC objective OO4. Based on the priorities, PARC will deliver results relevant to support the use of new approaches and methods, fill data gaps and reduce uncertainty in RA.’

The project will contribute to the PARC main objective ‘Drive innovation in regulatory RA by strengthening its scientific basis, with the implementation of NGRA as the ultimate goal’ by strengthening the implementation of uncertainty analysis in NGRA.

The project will moreover contribute to PARC objective OO9 by proposing recommendations that are harmonized across EU policies.

Links within PARC (WPs/Tasks/Activities/Projects)

The project has potential synergies with several other WPs, tasks, activities or projects that address holistic approaches to RA. Plans for concrete cooperation will be specified during the study regarding other projects in WP6 as well as potential interactions at the task level e.g., with WP2, WP7 and WP3.

- WP2: This work will support the objective of 6.3 to contribute to priorities as defined in WP2 to meet the EC’s CSS Towards a Toxic-Free Environment.
- WP3: Interaction with WP3 foreseen to clarify how to best communicate on recommendations for regulatory action and for aspects related to risk communication.
- WP4/Task 4.2: “Case study on Endocrine Disrupting Chemicals (EDCs)”. One of the aims of the project are to promote efficient overall protection of biodiversity by ensuring that the environmental and multisource monitoring is designed based on complete and up-to-date information, answering the identified regulatory needs. EDCs will include a variety of different classes of chemicals, among which pesticides. Besides, it will allow for the comparison of chemical approaches, such as in prospective assessment, with effects actually found in the field using effect-based tools. Exchange will be ensured through a common research partner (INERIS, EAWAG).
- WP4: This work will be linked to WP4 for the collection of monitoring data in wildlife and their possible use in secondary poisoning assessment.
- WP5: This project could provide feedback on the need of input data for ecotoxicity studies and models to be used for SP assessment.
- WP6/Task 6.2: The project will provide feedback for the need of models for a better understanding of exposure kinetics.
- WP6/Task 6.4: uptake of the outcome of the project in Regulatory frameworks
- WP7: the project will feed into the work of WP7, specifically task 7.3 which targets the development and implementation of innovative data analytical approaches from the computational, statistical, and mathematical fields, including quantification of the uncertainties and propagation of these uncertainties when combining different sets of data. This case study is a retrospective analysis of practitioners’ experience, which make the findings valuable for the work under task 7.3 which approaches the issue of uncertainty analysis from a more normative and methodological perspective. Data related to data gap-filling methods across relevant EU legislations will be collected and generated in the present project, which will be included in the DMP of PARC under WP7.
- WP8: The project will connect to and explore synergies with 8.1 SSbD. Toolbox requirements of the PARC model network developed under WP8 will be explored to clarify how the harmonization of data gap-filling approaches across modelling, monitoring and assessment tools can consistently contribute to a strong and reliable PARC toolbox.

Links outside PARC

The project may contribute to other EU regulations and policy frameworks (i.e., those not currently or directly embedded in our project plan), such as the EU’s Soil Strategy, Circular Economy and Zero Pollution Action Plans, and the EFSA-funded projects RACEMiC and PERA (Partnership for next generation, systems-based Environmental Risk Assessment).

The Austrian Green Chemicals Platform (<https://www.grünechemieösterreich.at/>).

The project will harvest synergies with UNEP SAICM and with Mistra SafeChem.

- Protecting the same ecosystem under different regulations: Implemented by risk assessors with a broad network regarding EU ERA, the following list is a non-exhaustive list of their fields of collaborations and involvements: WG chemicals under the WFD. PPR panel under 1107/2009 EFSA project PERA. Premier project on improving pharmaceutical RA, Norman Network (ecotoxicology database), EEA project on soil RA.
- Secondary poisoning and protection of wildlife: This project will be complementary to EU and national activities regarding monitoring in biota, as a regular task under WFD, but also for the interpretation of biota level in wildlife. The project will also be linked to the Horizon project PROMISCES, in the interpretation of the risks due to the promotion of the circularity of natural resources (water, soil) during life cycle of chemicals. The project will also grounds on the EU LIFE VERMEER (Life Vermeer – Integrating VEGA, toxRead, MERLIN-Expo and ERICA in A Platform for Risk Assessment and Substitution of Risky Substance (life-vermeer.eu) for the use of the SPHERA Tools and models.
- Occupational exposures to reproductive and developmental toxicants: Partners closely connected to various OSH-stakeholders, expert group members and active researchers.

Linked to activities within the OECD WPHA project *Tools and good practices to improve the use of academic data in regulatory assessments*, led by JRC and DG Environment within the working group OSOA.

Key PARC Deliverables (or Additional Deliverables) and Milestones to which the project contributes

- D6.6 ‘1st Report on conclusions from case studies reviewing RA methodologies’ due M42
- D6.17 ‘2nd Report on conclusions from case studies reviewing RA methodologies’ due M81
- MS13 ‘Mid-term review of the PARC activities, performance and budget’ due M42

Partners List:

SYKE (FI); ISSeP (BE); SU (SE); UBA (DE); STAMI (NO); UCL (UK); JSI (SI); MUI (AT); KEMI (SE); ULUND (SE); KI (SE); BPI (EL); DTU (DK); UCPH (DK); Eawag (CH); FOEN (CH); INERIS (FR); TTL (FI), LSMU (LT); RSU (LV), ISS (IT), UMIL(IT), UNIPD (IT).

Schedule:

Starting date: 01/05/2022 (M1)

Expected ending date: 30/04/2026 (M48)

Cost:

Expected PM for the fourth year of the project: 28 PM

Expected ODC for the fourth year of the project: 20 250 €

T6.4 Transposing results to regulatory risk assessment methodologies 13 PROJECTS

This task will support regulatory processes for reducing risks to humans and the environment by undertaking scenario-based case-studies resulting in guidance documents and/or recommendations. First, in coordination with ongoing EC activities, a European framework for the regulatory assessment of mixtures encompassing all relevant chemical classes, exposure scenarios and protection goals will be developed. It will evaluate the availability and quality of data for regulatory assessment, analyse the additional risk caused by mixtures and its implications. The second activity aims to promote and facilitate the regulatory acceptance and practical use of NAMs in RA across different chemical sectors. Focus will be put on real-life situations and application contexts encountered by risk assessors. Long-term objectives include the definition of harmonised scientific criteria for acceptance of NAMs across regulations and of an evidence-based framework to ensure systematic, transparent, and reproducible application of NAMs in RA. Next, we will develop and apply tools and databases that enable a systematic identification of priority substances in products and materials. In doing so, the activity will promote a more effective and harmonised enforcement of legislation, support informed substitution of problematic chemicals in products and materials and inform how sustainability assessments can be achieved with respect to chemicals.

T 6.4 Transposing results to risk assessment methodologies

Develop and foster the uptake of innovative, efficient and protective regulatory risk assessment and management approaches and methodologies.

Fig 11: W6.3: RA methodologies

A6.4.1 Develop regulatory relevant approaches and methods for chemical mixtures – 4 PROJECTS

P6.4.1.a_Y1_OPREMIXCS1_BRUNEL_RWTH

Project Title	Optimizing regulatory risk assessment and management of chemical mixtures in Europe		
Project Acronym (15 letters max)	OPREMIX		
Project Manager	Thomas Backhaus thomas.backhaus@rwth-aachen.de	Aachen University	DE
Deputy Project manager	Andreas Kortenkamp andreas.kortenkamp@brunel.ac.uk	Brunel University London	UK
Expected starting date	1	Expected duration	40*
PARC (Month number)		PARC	6.4.1.
PARC Workpackage number	6	Task/Activity/Sub-activity:	
Project Id	P6.4.1.a_Y1_OPREMIXCS1_BRUNEL_RWTH		

*The project has been extended from M36 to M40

Status: Implementation

Summary of the project

This project has its focus on the current approaches related to the management of mixtures across regulatory areas as e.g., REACH, CLP, Pesticides and Biocides, cosmetics, food contact material, pharmaceuticals. Further regulation on food and drinking water as well as on environmental media and emission will be considered. It will also explore the use of the Mixture Assessment Factor (MAF) approach for the assessment and management of mixtures across regulatory areas and uses (beyond REACH) and compare it to other mixture approaches. This project will address the question if and under which circumstances a MAF is applicable or not and how different are the conclusion drawn by different mixture approaches when

challenged with real word data sets and if there are differences to what extend would the MAF approach might provide biased results. Case studies will be used from the human and ecotoxicological arenas to attempt data-driven sizings of MAFs.

This project is highly relevant for supporting the improvement of the regulatory management of mixtures across chemicals legislation and areas of use, regarding human health and the environment. It will address the overall objectives of activity 6.4.1 “*Develop regulatory and legally accepted risk assessment and management approaches and methods for chemical mixtures*”, while specifically focusing on and comparing the methods and tools currently used for the regulatory assessment and management and providing guidance for further development.

Main expected outputs of the project

A systematic comparative evaluation of current mixture tools (and those that are currently under development or might be developed within PARC). The mixture tools will be compared regarding their practicability, effectiveness and efficiency, level of protection, feasibility, applications domain and data demands. Particular focus will be on developing case studies for the comparative evaluation of the MAF. As far as feasible, the project will provide direct input and feedback to ongoing regulatory action, such as the revision of REACH or the WFD.

Outcomes and impacts expected for end-users and stakeholders

This project will provide the input to develop a “European cookbook” of mixture tools that describes the application domain for each tool, its data demands, protectiveness, feasibility and reliability, in the view of the different demands from regulators, industries and civil society.

Key words: mixtures, MAF, Mixture tools, European cookbook of mixtures.

Link to the PARC DoA

This project respond to the PARC OOs OO4, OO5, OO10, OO12 and OO9.

Chemical mixtures were one of the highest scored topics in the first round of prioritisation within PARC, and this project will support in particular Objectives 9 and 12. The practical experiences with handling heterogeneous datasets of complex mixtures will also feed into Objective 10. The project focuses on comparing existing methods of MRA with the MAF, which is to be implemented for industrial chemicals (REACH), as requested by the CSS.

Links within PARC (WPs/Tasks/Activities/Projects)

WP3: Synergies, Communication and awareness: a cooperation for the foreseen survey would be of value, especially in distributing it to risk assessor

WP7: DMP

WP9: Training, laboratory network

Other WPs: The project will primarily link to and exchange findings and input with project P6.4.1.b_Y1_CS2_UFZ (Dealing with unknown mixtures in regulatory risk assessment through the use of monitoring data and NAMs). Findings from WP 4 and WP5 regarding monitoring data and toxicity data will be considered in this Project. Further, there will probably be links to and exchange with 6.2.3 on issues related to human real-life exposure and modelling of exposure. In WP6.2 mixtures will be approached from a research science perspective with the focus on modelling, human health and dietary exposure. Relevant findings of Task 6.2 will be considered in this project for sizing one or more MAFs.

Links outside PARC

There are several currently ongoing research and policy development activities on mixtures in the EU. Under Horizon 2020, the so-called Green Deal Call includes a call dedicated to mixture toxicity, with a certain focus on aquatic environment and the occurrence of pharmaceutical residues in unintentional mixtures. There are also ongoing and planned mixture related activities related to the remits of EFSA (e.g., food safety and pesticides), e.g., regarding the further development of the Cumulative Assessment Groups (CAGs), primarily for the assessment of mixtures of pesticide residues in food. Further, the EC will conduct an impact assessment of the introduction of a MAF or MAFs under REACH.

Key PARC Deliverables and Milestones to which the project contributes

AD6.17: Optimizing regulatory risk assessment and management of chemical mixtures in Europe (M40)

D6.18: Final report on risk assessment and management methods for chemical mixtures across legislations (M81)

Partners List: RWTH (DE), BUL (UK), AGES (AT), UBA (DE), BPI (EL), UI (IS), NIVA (NO), ENSP (PT), EAWAG (CH), KEMI (SE), UK Env. Agency (UK), STAMI (NO), NIOM (PL), UAVR (PT), NLZOH (SI), UK-CEH (UK), LSMU (LT).

Schedule:

Starting date: 01/05/2022 (M1)

Expected ending date: 31/08/2025 (M40)

Costs

Expected PM for the fourth year of the project: 15 PM

Expected ODC for the fourth year of the project: 13 674 €

P6.4.1.b_Y1_MONAMMIXCS2_UFZ

Project Title	Dealing with unknown mixtures in regulatory risk assessments through the use of monitoring data and NAMs		
Project Acronym (15 letters max)	MONAMMIX		
Project Manager	Wibke Busch wibke.busch@ufz.de	Helmholtz Environmental Research center (UFZ)	Germany
Deputy Project manager	Enken Hassold Enken.Hassold@uba.de	German Environment Agency (UBA)	Germany
Expected starting date PARC (Month number)	1	Expected duration	40*
PARC Workpackage number	6	PARC Task/Activity/Sub-activity:	6.4.1
Project Id	P6.4.1.b_Y1_MONAMMIX CS2_UFZ		

*The project has been extended from M36 to M40

Status: Implementation

Summary of the project

The project is highly relevant for supporting the improvement of the regulatory management of mixtures across chemicals legislation and areas of use, regarding human health and the environment by bridging data gaps. It will address the overall objectives of activity 6.4.1 “Develop regulatory and legally accepted risk assessment and management approaches and methods for chemical mixtures” and strives to link prospective mixture assessment methods with monitoring and AOP knowledge. In particular, it is focusing on case studies on environmental monitoring under EU directives such as WFD, (Directive 2000/60/EC), Sustainable Use of PPPs Directive 2009/128/EC) and HBM initiatives such as HBM4EU or the cohort studies within the European Exposome Network. In this project the use of NAMs i.e. bioanalytical methods for untargeted exposure detection and hazard identification in conjunction with chemical screening data, to deal with unknown mixtures will be compared with MRA methods relying on component-based standard toxicity information.

In this project we will address the following research question:

- How can data from NAMs be used to provide more comprehensive pictures of the chemical exposure that needs to be addressed in chemical RA?
- How could available bioanalytical methodology and information from environmental monitoring contribute to MRA?
- Are AOP networks a way to overcome data gaps and account for compounds mixture contributions?

- Can priority mixtures be defined with the application of non-target methods?
- Can NAMs complement component-based MRA?

Main expected outputs of the project

The availability of empirically based support data from established monitoring efforts on human health and environmental quality, as well as AOP knowledge compiled under OECD efforts, will be important for developing the assessment and management of mixtures in several ways. It will for example be crucial to argue the size of a MAF as currently proposed under REACH, to define common assessment groups as currently under development at EFSA, or to aggregate exposures of single substances and combined exposures of mixtures in the respective regulations as well as across regulatory silos. Identified priority mixtures containing chemicals recently assessed or regulated by different regulatory authorities will be provided to provide support in these respects, while providing additional options for tiered mixture assessment strategies, e.g. in the frame of the European WFD (2000/60/EC) for environmental mixture exposures, or the European Drinking Water Directive (2020/2184) for mixtures humans are exposed to.

Outcomes and impacts expected for end-users and stakeholders

To advance the regulatory assessment and management of unintentional mixtures additional approaches are needed which are practicable in a regulatory context and capable of dealing with data constraints. It can be foreseen that monitoring information based on non-target chemical and bioanalytical methods will be utilized to define unknown mixture exposures and address data gaps. Furthermore, a curated database on modes of chemical action will provide mechanistic information from *in vitro* bioanalytical NAMs and can be employed for establishing AOP networks to bridge data gaps in mixture assessment. Chemical producers, risk assessors, and respective regulators might e.g. be using NAMs and NAM-generated data in particular for chemicals with few information and to e.g., consider the expectable additional effect of product formulation compounds to the toxicity of an individually assessed active ingredient. A guidance document for the development and RA of context-related reference mixtures based on monitoring and NAM data will be provided and a reference mixture developed for European wastewater treatment plant effluents.

Key words: chemical mixtures, new approach methods, environment, human health, regulatory acceptance

Link to the PARC DoA

In this project, the use of data of NAMs (i.e. bioanalytical methods for untargeted exposure detection and hazard identification in conjunction with chemical screening data) to deal with mixtures will be compared with MRA methods relying on component-based standard toxicity information. During the project data integration will be performed in collaboration with WP7 and according to the FAIR principles. Reuse of data and workflows will be enabled. Chemical mixtures are an integral part in the CSS. Further, chemical mixtures were one of the highest scored topics in the first round of prioritisation within PARC. However, this project will highly support the OO4, OO5, OO10 and OO12.

Links within PARC (WPs/Tasks/Activities/Projects)

WP3: Synergies, Communication and awareness: we will do a survey in cooperation with Task 6.4.2, for that we will need some support in distributing the survey to risk assessor.

WP7: DMP

WP9: Training, laboratory network: for now, we see no need for support from WP9, but if we identify needs, we will contact WP9

Other WPs: The project will primarily link to and exchange findings and input with project P6.4.1.a_Y1_CS1_BRUNEL_RWTH (Optimising regulatory RA and management of chemical mixtures in Europe) and with Task 6.4.2. Further, there will be links to and exchange with 6.2.3 on issues related to human real-life exposure and modelling of exposure. In a later stage, if available, the newly generated monitoring data from WP 4 and the outcome of WP 5 regarding toxicity testing and AOPs will be considered in our case studies.

Links outside PARC:

There are several currently ongoing research and policy development activities on mixtures in the EU. Under Horizon 2020, the so-called Green Deal Call includes a call dedicated to mixture toxicity, with a certain focus on aquatic environment and the occurrence of pharmaceutical residues in unintentional mixtures. There are also ongoing and planned mixture related activities related to the remits of EFSA (e.g. food safety and pesticides), e.g. regarding the further development of the CAGs, primarily for the assessment of mixtures of pesticide residues in food. Further, the EC will conduct an impact assessment of the introduction of a MAF or MAFs under REACH, which will be supported by a consultant study.

Key PARC Deliverables and Milestones to which the project contributes

AD6.17: Optimizing regulatory risk assessment and management of chemical mixtures in Europe (M40)
 AD6.18: Dealing with mixtures in regulatory risk assessment through the use of monitoring data and NAMs (M40) has been cancelled (merged with AD6.17)
 D6.18: Final report on risk assessment and management methods for chemical mixtures across legislations (M81)

Partners List: UFZ (DE), UBA (DE), NIVA (NO), BPI (EL), UI (IS), AGES (AT), STAMI (NO), UKCEH (UK), EA (UK), NLZOH (SI)

Schedule:

Starting date: 01/05/2022 (M1)
 Expected ending date: 31/08/2025 (M40)

Costs

Expected PM for the fourth year of the project: 11 PM
 Expected ODC for the fourth year of the project: 3 000 €

P6.4.1.c_Y3_Skinsenmix_RegionH

Project Title	Skin sensitization – effect of mixtures, current practices and gaps		
Project Acronym (15 letters max)	Skinsenmix		
Project Manager	Jeanne Duus Johansen Jeanne.Duus.Johansen@regionh.dk	RegionH	Denmark
Deputy Project manager	Jose Hernán Alfonso jose.alfonso@stami.no	STAMI	Norway
Expected starting date PARC (Month number)	M25	Expected duration	48
PARC Workpackage number	WP6	PARC Task/Activity/Sub-activity:	6.4.1
Project Id	P6.4.1.c_Y3_Skinsenmix_RegionH		

Status: Implementation

Summary of the project

A skin sensitizer is a chemical substance that will lead to an allergic response following repeated skin contact as defined by the UN Globally Harmonized System of Classification and labelling of Chemicals. At least 25% of the European adult population are sensitized to one or more chemicals from consumer products and/or exposures in the work environment. However, no generally accepted RA model exists in the EU to be used in regulations. Most consumer and occupational products contain several sensitizing chemicals which is known to influence the immune system. Furthermore, many products also contain irritants such as detergents, which may additionally impact the response, however this needs further study.

The lack of a common RA model means that many skin sensitizers remain uncontrolled and that ad hoc

decisions are taken when epidemics of skin sensitization occur with major consequences for those becoming sensitized. There is a paucity of knowledge concerning the impact of mixtures (allergens and irritants) on risk of skin sensitization leading to an urgent need to develop predictive models and test systems. NAMs, both in chemico and in vitro methods, have been validated and are now accepted for classification and potency grading (OECD 497) in some areas, however, they have not yet been assessed regarding their suitability for testing mixtures. In a recent questionnaire study among regulators and dermatologists/scientists in EU performed under PARC (6.3.1), most respondents found that, regulations concerning skin sensitizers could be improved, that NAMs needed further development, and that more insight into mechanisms, especially concerning effect of mixtures were required (unpublished). To our knowledge, from a regulatory point of view, no alternative method to animal testing for skin sensitisation potential assessment of mixtures exposed has yet been proposed. Therefore, this project aims to assess the performance of several NAMs in the assessment of defined mixtures and to gain more insight into effects of mixtures by using 3 D skin models, as these more closely reflect real-life, than the currently approved NAMs.

Main expected outputs of the project:

- 1) To assess the applicability and suitability of NAMs and a 3D skin model to evaluate the skin sensitization hazard of mixture exposures (several skin sensitisers together and skin sensitisers + irritant).
- 2) To integrate data from the NAMs and a 3D skin model to define a general mixture factor (MAF-SEN) that can be used in RA models, which are being considered in 6.3.
- 3) To assess mixture effects on elicitation in humans to be considered in regulations of ongoing epidemics.

Outcomes and impacts expected on end-users and stakeholders:

At least 25% of the European population are sensitized to one or more chemicals from consumer products and/or by occupational exposures. This project will develop new tools for RA and management of mixtures of skin sensitizers/irritants. Prevention of skin sensitization is a health priority of several national authorities. In a recent questionnaire study (PARC 6.3.1), many regulators from EU countries pointed to the need of more knowledge and data concerning NAMs and effect of mixtures. Thresholds derived from elicitation studies in humans have traditionally been used for ad hoc regulations of allergens in ongoing epidemics, however a mixture effect has not been considered. The project will therefore address considerable knowledge gap to improve regulations e.g., REACH; Cosmetics; Biocides.

Key words: skin sensitizer, mixtures, allergens, irritant, detergents, NAMs, 3D skin cell model.

Link to the PARC DoA:

The management of mixtures was one of the highest scoring topics in the “PARC survey”. Furthermore, mixtures are an integral part in the CSS.

Links within PARC (WPs/Tasks/Activities/Projects):

WP6.3. The current regulatory practices for skin sensitization will be reviewed under 6.3 as a case story but is also of major relevance to the aims and objectives under 6.4, where it is suggested to focus especially on mixtures, both current practices and fill known gaps.

Links outside PARC:

The investigations are closely linked to projects being performed by our group in RegionH and in collaboration with University of Copenhagen already on immune reactions to skin sensitizers but will especially focus on effects of mixtures and regulatory practises. Furthermore, it is envisaged to establish an advisory group of experts, e.g., from OECD, the NTP Interagency Centre for the Evaluation of Alternative Toxicological Methods (NICEATM), EURL ECVAM and, if possible, from relevant industries.

Key PARC Deliverables (or Additional Deliverables) and Milestones to which the project contributes
 D6.18: Final report on risk assessment and management methods for chemical mixtures across legislations (M81)

Partners List:

National Allergy Research Centre, Denmark (REGIONH), STAMI, Norway, UCPH (DK), Dept of Immunology and Microbiology, AGES (AT), Department of Risk assessment.

Schedule:

Starting date: 01/05/2024 (M25)

Expected ending date: 30/04/2028 (M72)

Costs

Expected PM for the second year of the project: 23 PM

Expected ODC for the second year of the project: 87 000 €

P6.4.1.d_Y4_RE-MIX_UBA_Eawag

Project Title	Options to assess and REgulate MIXtures		
Project Acronym (15 letters max)	RE-MIX		
Project Manager	Enken Hassold enken.hassold@uba.de	UBA	Germany
Deputy Project manager	Marion Junghans Marion.junghans@oekotoxzentrum.ch	EAWAG	Switzerland
Expected starting date PARC (Month number)	M37	Expected duration (months)	45
PARC Workpackage number	WP6	PARC Task/Activity/Su b-activity:	6.4.1
Project Id	P6.4.1.d_Y4_RE-MIX_UBA_Eawag		

Status: Initiation

Summary of the project

RE-MIX will build upon the outcomes and partially continue the work that has been done under the previous 6.4.1 projects OPREMIX and MONAMMIX ([link](#)) which will end in August 2025. The project relies on the expertise and contributions of the already existing partners. The expected outcome of OPREMIX will be an analysis of the usefulness and comparative assessment of current mixture assessment tools, systematic data-driven assessments of the MAF-approach in comparison to other established mixture assessment methods and a draft European mixture framework. MONNAMMIX have provided a number of case studies analysing mixture risks, a review on the needs for monitoring as well as a guidance on new approach methods for specific regulatory options. Overall, the project mainly addresses the specified needs with respect to need 28 “co-exposure to multiple chemicals” (T6.2 and T 6.4) according to the identified PARC future activities, namely the objective to “develop a strategy for MRA applied to prioritised chemicals and effects”. The existing and envisaged case studies will address needs in the current developments of EU regulations, e.g. WFD CIS work programme 2025-27, REACH revision, revision of EFSA guidance document for soil RA. Further needs with regards to MRA will be identified in collaboration with relevant EU authorities (e.g. EFSA, ECHA, EEA). In addition, also other PARC specific needs are being addressed, such as need to assess the connection between “chemicals and biodiversity” or need to explore the theme of “ED mixtures” more in depth.

Thematic areas for the case studies and conceptual analyses that will be addressed in the project.

The thematic areas for the case studies and conceptual analyses are roughly visualized in the following figure.

In the first phase of the project core regulatory areas of the project will be defined and specific project goals will be set. Based on the results of OPREMIX and MONAMMIX as well as on a landscaping exercise on current regulatory gaps and needs the core regulatory group will seek to set up case studies to provide regulatory options tailored to EU regulations, tools and methods for regulators and evidence for mixtures risks under different regulatory areas. The following research questions are currently in focus for the landscaping exercise:

Regulatory challenges & options for MRAs and measures

- Evaluation of the applicability of different regulatory options available, such as e.g. a MAF, Mixture Risk Indicators (MRI), or case-by case MRA and Mixture Risk Mitigation Options (MRM). These might be applicable for certain legislative frameworks only.
- Analysis of options, challenges and gaps across different legislations (substance-, media-, product- or emission-oriented) is important to improve and align mixture assessment and legal requirements on mixture risks across different areas. The revisions of REACH or the water framework directive could be a starting point, where the research activities will aim at supporting the implementation processes regarding mixtures.
- In order to identify and justify the need for a regulatory measure, the characterization and identification of “typical” mixture compositions and/or prioritisation of mixture risk drivers are important as basis for assessments for specific substance groups or mixtures of regulatory relevance. Here data analyses providing evidence will feed in.
- If possible, also analyses estimating the possible impact of regulatory measures on emissions and co-exposures of chemicals to the environment or humans (e.g. restrictions, non-authorizations, MAF) would be beneficial. Here, the indicators developed by EEA could be a starting point for further analyses.

Tools & methods for a NGMRA

- A number of currently available methods, tools and approaches for MRAs are to be compiled by OPREMIX, already used in the ongoing case studies and will further be evaluated for applicability under different regulations in future case studies.
- These and potentially further Methods developed under RE-MIX are important to improve the analyses of mixture effects, exposure and RAs in a structured way, covering e.g. the probability of co-occurrences, identification mixture risk drivers, and the use of mixture risk indicators. Uncertainty analyses would be important.
- A current gap is the lack of data for (eco-)toxicity and exposure data. This situation might be improved via AI approaches and/or new approach methods that were initiated by MONAMMIX and could be continued under REMIX.
- The documentation in accessible data-bases is important to enable mixture risk analyses in the areas of human health and the environment. Here, an exchange with the EU agencies is needed, regarding the OSOA ambitions.
- In these areas, also an exchange with the PARC activity 6.2.3 might be beneficial.

Scientific evidence for mixture risks

- Analyses of datasets for evidences of the occurrence, frequency and magnitude for mixture risks is the expected core work of the partners. Analyses are conducted on the basis of e.g. monitoring or modelled data on chemical co-occurrences/exposures together with available (eco)toxicity data from prospective assessments. Modelling approaches to estimate and/or visualize the magnitude of mixture risks on EU level on the basis of retrospective and/or prospective RAs may be included.
- Different scenarios may be covered. For the environment, case studies might focus on e.g. agricultural/urban areas, soil, marine, hospitals, groundwater. For human health, case studies may focus on exposures via food, non-dietary exposures, workplace exposures or exposure of humans via the environment.
- Case studies may also address the “missing link” between laboratory data and “real life” evidences for impacts and mixture effects in the field, on ecosystems or human populations (including e.g. impacts on communities, biodiversity).

Main expected outputs of the project:

RE-MIX will provide the EU institutions and agencies with input to regulatory considerations regarding different pieces of relevant EU legislation, will provide tools and methods to be used in the implementation of the legislation and will give evidence on mixtures risks associated with different regulatory areas. The regulatory core group (CG) together with the advisory group will ensure that case studies and conceptual analyses will tackle existing regulatory gaps with respect to available data, assessment tools and risk mitigation options that enable MRAs as well as proposing options for risk mitigation and management measures across the different regulations. In general, RE-MIX will enhance scientific evidence, improve assessment tools and come up with analyses of different options. The details of the expected outputs will depend on the case studies and conceptual analyses that will be initiated. The selection of new case studies will be based on the needs of PARC future activities.

Results are to be published as reports, peer-review open-access journals, summaries for decision makers and/or policy briefs by the project partners. Summaries of the achievements will be reported in the Annual Summary Reports (ASRs).

The envisaged **Forum for Exchange** will be the central part and output of the project as it fosters an open exchange and discussion of results and further needs between experts from different perspectives (e.g. environment and human health, academia, regulatory agencies, EU) and enables a better cooperation between academic research and regulatory practise but also between different PARC projects dealing with

co-exposures. In addition, a Workshop will be organised to discuss the outcomes and possibilities for use and/or implementation in regulatory practise.

Outcomes and impacts expected on end-users and stakeholders:

We will provide evidences, proposals and analyses to improve the assessment on chemical mixtures on a regulatory desk level and will also contribute with closing some data gaps.

Outcomes and impacts expected to be incorporated into a specific regulatory framework:

We will provide scientific evidence for mixture risks as well as proposals for options to address combined exposures and effects in current regulations and guidances (e.g. REACH, EFSA GD PPP, WFD, Soil Restoration and Monitoring Law) supporting the demands of the different actors (e.g. companies, applicants, regulatory bodies).

Key words: mixture, environment, human health, MAF, regulatory options, monitoring, prospective, retrospective, risk mitigation

Link to the PARC objectives and DoA:

The project responds to the PARC OOs OO4, OO5, OO10, OO12, OO9, OO11.

The assessment and management of unintentional mixtures was one of the highest scoring topics in the “PARC survey”. Mixtures are an integral part in the CSS with a proposal for introducing a MAF in REACH and check the applicability in further regulations. The work under PARC will (a) provide scientific evidence for possible mixture risks across all relevant chemical classes, exposure scenarios and protection goals, will (b) focus on supporting European regulation by analysing feasible options to address unintentional chemical mixtures, c) enhance the cooperation between experts from different regulatory areas and the different protection goals (i.e. human health and environment).

Links within PARC (WPs/Tasks/Activities/Projects):

During the initiation phase, the project will start with a Kick-of workshop in May 2025, where focus areas will be defined with the partners. This will be prepared in advance.

WP3: The exchange forum will be the central instrument to present results and exchange knowledge and ideas.

In addition, a stakeholder Workshop is planned, where we would like to connect with the PARC Stakeholder Forum (SF) in order to organise this event.

A link with WP4 will be established for the use of monitoring data. As a first step we will discuss with WP 4 which data are available and how we can share data sets that are available from partners in RE-MIX.

Within WP6, we will elaborate on collaboration and links with 6.2.3 real life mixtures and with 6.4.4 regarding biodiversity and pesticides in the environment. Regular meetings with 6.2.3 are foreseen to strengthen synergies between the two tasks but also to avoid overlaps as both address mixtures with respect to human health. Break-Out groups and follow-up meetings between the mixture-related activities in 6.4.1 and 6.2.3 are planned back-to back in the context of WP6 Workshops.

WP7: Since it is mandatory in PARC to work according to the FAIR principal, we will here have a discussion with the designated Data Champion and Data Liaison Manager.

Links outside PARC:

During the initiation phase, meetings with representatives from EEA, EFSA, ECHA and JRC would be beneficial in order to streamline the project.

RE-MIX will interact with further EU projects and activities outside PARC. This will comprise regular exchange on results and/or approaches via involved partners.

There are several currently ongoing research and policy development activities on mixtures in the EU, such as e.g. the EU projects TerraChem and “Novel Educational Model Enabling Social Innovation Skills

development” (NEMESIS). Currently it is under discussion to collaborate with the two projects on a case study level (e.g. data exchange or advisory role).

Also, cooperation with database developments, such as the “Land Use and Coverage Area frame Survey” (LUCAS) Soil database, the NORMAN Network or IPCHEM will be explored.

During the implementation phase we will further explore the possibility to collaborate with ongoing mixture related activities in the remits of EEA (mixture indicators/signals), EFSA (CAGs and guidance developments), ECHA (grouping approaches), JRC (mixture analyses, IPCHEM), or OECD (combined exposure database). Here, RE-MIX could support with scientific data and results, provide proposals for addressing mixtures in guidances and/or take up the needs highlighted by the regulatory agencies/international bodies. Activities of national and international authorities as well as NGOs (e.g. Chemtrust) with respect to mixtures will be followed.

Key PARC Deliverables and Milestones to which the project contributes

D6.18: Final report on risk assessment and management methods for chemical mixtures across legislations (M81)

Partners List: UBA (DE), EAWAG (CH), AGES (AT), BPI (EL), UKCEH (UK), ENSP (PT), KEMI (SE), LMSU (LT), NILZOH (SL), NIOM (PL), NIVA (NO), UFZ (DE), UI (IS), RWTH (DE), UOB (UK), ULUND(SE), UAVR (PT)

Schedule:

Starting date: 01/05/2025 (M37)

Expected ending date: 31/01/2029 (M81)

Costs

Expected PM for the first year of the project: 63 PM

Expected ODC for the first year of the project: 28 319 €

A6.4.2 Facilitate the regulatory acceptance and use of new methods – 3 PROJECTS

P6.4.2.a_Y1_LandscapingSurv_UNIBAS (closed M36)

Project Title	Status of integration and use of New Approach Methodologies in the EU regulatory risk assessment landscape		
Project Acronym (15 letters max)	P6.4.2.a_Y1_LandscapingSurv_UNIBAS		
Project Manager	Ellen Fritsche ellen.fritsche@unibas.ch	University of Basel (UNIBAS)	Switzerland
Deputy Project manager	Andrea bearth andrea.bearth@unibas.ch	University of Basel (UNIBAS)	Switzerland
Expected starting date PARC (Month number)	1	Expected duration	36*
PARC Workpackage number	6	PARC Task/Activity/Sub-activity:	6.4.2
Project Id	P6.4.2.a_Y1_LandscapingSurv_UNIBAS		

*The project will be closed M36, the related AD6.16 is planned to be submitted M36

P6.4.2.b_Y1_NGRApractice_VKM_NIPH

Project Title	Next generation risk assessment applied in practice		
Project Acronym (15 letters max)	NGRApractice		
Project Manager	Gro Haarklou Mathisen Gro.haarklou.mathisen@vkm.no	National Institute of Public Health (NIPH), represented by the Norwegian Scientific Committee for Food and Environment (VKM)	Norway
Deputy Project manager	Camilla Svendsen Camilla.svendsen@fhi.no		Norway
Expected starting date PARC (Month number)	1	Expected duration	81*
PARC Workpackage number	6	PARC Task/Activity/Sub-activity	6.4.2
Project Id	P6.4.2.b_Y1_NGRApractice_VKM_NIPH		

*The project has been extended from M36 to M81.

Status: Implementation

Summary of the project

Application of systematic review principles in chemical RA is increasing. In 2021, a framework for the use of systematic review in chemical RA was published by WHO. Evaluation of validity of studies is one important step in the systematic review process, however, tools to evaluate validity of in vitro studies (including in vitro NAMs), are currently not available. Such tools are needed to incorporate in vitro data in systematic reviews (which is a part of a chemical RA), to identify data of sufficient validity to inform decision making by risk managers and to have ensure strong confidence in the conclusions. The VKM project “NGRA applied in practice” aim to create evidence-based tools and guidance’s for RA based on NAMs, which will be included in an overall evidence-based NGRA framework usable for the evaluation of human health risk/safety across sectors (e.g. food and cosmetic). The framework will enable risk assessors to use other studies than human and animal studies, and also academic studies that are not OECD guideline studies, as evidence. This will contribute to fill knowledge gaps, and the outcome will be more robust RAs with reduced uncertainty, being a better knowledge base for the regulators/risk managers.

Main expected outputs of the project

- Generic, sector-independent tools for evidence-based HA of chemicals using NAMs addressing potential adverse human health effects.
- Generic, sector-independent guidance documents on identification of a POD from NAMs and on the evaluation of uncertainty in NAMs.
- Generic, sector-independent checklists (reporting standards) for different NAMs, to ensure adequate design and reporting for the research outcome of NAMs to be usable as evidence in RA.

Outcomes and impacts expected for end-users and stakeholders

We are starting with the creation of tools for evaluation of internal and external validity of NAMs, enabling risk assessors to use NAMs in evidence-based RA. The tools are needed to ensure that only evidence of sufficient quality is included based on the WoE principle, that the effects addressed are relevant for human adverse health effects, and that the HA process and product is objective, robust, transparent, and reproducible. The internal validity tools will make it possible to evaluate whether a reported effect is caused by the exposure or if it may be due to systematic errors (bias) introduced by the study design, conduct, reporting or analysis. The external validity tool will make it possible to evaluate if the data generated by the study can be translated to human health effects.

Key words:

Chemical risk assessment, evidence-based, guidance, NAMs, NGRA, systematic review, tool.

Link to the PARC DoA

OO4, OO9 and OO12: Although NAMs are developed to be used for RAs, risk assessors must evaluate the internal validity of the study (the risk of bias; whether the reported results may be caused by other issues than the exposure) and the external validity (the generalisability/if the results can be translated to human health effects). This validity evaluation is critical for inclusion as evidence in RAs, and for grading the certainty in the evidence, for transparency, and for the description of uncertainty. Using structured approaches for these evaluations makes these evaluations more transparent and objective.

OO5: Knowing how to use the tools, and which information that needs to be reported to be able to apply the tools to evaluate a study, is important knowledge for researchers and to improve study reporting. In addition, our projects are highly relevant for projects focusing on readiness of in vitro studies, and vice versa, and collaborations are therefore important. We are already in contact with a RiskHunt3R project focusing of readiness evaluation, and they participate as experts in our studies to create these tools.

OO13: We aim to develop training materials for the users to make them able to self-train. If possible, we will also prepare online training sessions (depends on funding).

Links within PARC (WPs/Tasks/Activities/Projects)

A scientific advisory group has been established for this project.

It is important to ensure dissemination, communication, and awareness of the outcomes of this project. We would like to arrange a workshop and/or a symposium (year 2023/2024) to which the main stakeholders will be invited. An in-person workshop could e.g., include training people in use of the tools (presentation of the tools and the development methods, followed by hands-on training). Training could also be developed as online prerecorded material with on-demand Q&As to help users. A symposium could e.g., focus on making NAMs usable for risk managers (from science to evidence in chemical RAs to scientific basis for risk managers).

- WP7: This information is included in the section Data Management
- WP9: This project does not involve laboratory work. Hands-on training courses on the use of the tools, for assessors coming from different regulatory sectors including e.g., food safety, pesticides, cosmetics, consumer products, industrial chemicals, could be organised. Courses could be foreseen also for researchers and in Industries to make them aware of the tools.
- Other WPs: A scientific advisory group has been established for this project.

This project is related to the two other Activity 6.4.2-projects:

- Status of integration & use of NAMs in the EU regulatory RA landscape
- Landscape and readiness of advanced ML & AI approaches for NGRA

Links outside PARC

Several projects outside PARC addressing similar topics are ongoing. A scientific advisory group has been established, consisting of experts in the topic of interest with the goal to ensure a broad, multidisciplinary representation of members from academia, regulatory authorities, and scientific organizations that will give advice related to the planned work on development of tools and share information about ongoing work addressing similar question.

The purpose of the Advisory Group is to give strategic guidance and content-related support to the project group related to aspects considered important for the development of the tools, and to share information about ongoing work addressing similar questions to ensure that the outcome of the project complements the work of others, thereby creating synergies and avoiding duplication of efforts.

The members of the scientific advisory group are linked to the following institutions/projects outside PARC: CAAT, EBTC (Evidence-Based Toxicology Collaboration), ECHA, Johns Hopkins University, JRC, Karolinska Institutet, US-NTP, OECD, ONTOX, Radboud University, US-EPA, EFSA, University of California San Francisco.

Key PARC Deliverables and Milestones to which the project contributes

AD6.16. Status of integration and use of NAMs in the EU chemical regulatory risk assessment landscape – a mapping exercise and gaps & needs analysis (M36)

D6.19: Report on regulatory acceptance and use of new methods (NAMs). This deliverable will give guidance for translation of the case studies results into scientific criteria to be used in regulatory actions (M81).

Partners List:

NIPH, represented by VKM (Norway); UNIBAS (Switzerland); UT (Estonia); BPI (Greece); ISS (Italy); NIVA (Norway); UAVR (Portugal).

Schedule:

Starting date: 01/05/2022 (M1)

Expected ending date: 31/01/2029 (M81)

Costs:

Expected PM for the fourth year of the project: 14 PM

Expected ODC for the fourth year of the project: 21 000 €

P6.4.2.c_Y1_NAMAM_UT (closed M36)

Project Title	Landscape and readiness of computational New Approach Methods based on advanced AI and ML approaches for chemicals' next generation risk assessment		
Project Acronym (15 letters max)	NAMAM		
Project Manager	Uko Maran uko.maran@ut.ee	University of Tartu	Estonia
Deputy Project manager	Sulev Sild sulev.sild@ut.ee	University of Tartu	Estonia
Expected starting date PARC (Month number)	1	Expected duration	36*
PARC Workpackage number	6	PARC Task/Activity/Sub-activity:	T6.4.2
Project Id	P6.4.2.c_Y1_NAMAM_UT		

*The project will be closed M36, the related AD6.16 is planned to be submitted M36

P6.4.2.d_Y4_RegulatoryNAMs_ISS

Project Title	Demonstrating the applicability of NAMs for specific regulatory processes through a series of case studies		
Project Acronym (15 letters max)	Regulatory use of NAMs		
Project Manager	Emma Di Consiglio emma.diconsiglio@iss.it	ISS	Italy
Deputy Project manager	Mirjam Luijten Mirjam.luijten@rivm.nl	RIVM	Netherlands
Expected starting date PARC (Month number)	37	Expected duration (months)	45
PARC Workpackage number	WP6	PARC Task/Activity/Sub-activity:	6.4.2
Project Id	P6.4.2.d_Y4_RegulatoryNAMs_ISS		

Status: Initiation

Summary of the project

The aim of the project is to test and demonstrate how a NAM-based approach for regulatory hazard and RA of chemical substances may work and could be implemented in several regulatory frameworks and for different regulatory purposes. For this, the project will address different and horizontal aspects that are highly important for the implementation of NAMs for regulatory purposes, such as biological coverage, predictability, chemical applicability domain, handling data gaps, and uncertainties. The planned work will be performed in close collaboration with related PARC projects, but also in close collaboration with initiatives outside PARC. In order to ensure that important aspects of NAM-based approaches for regulatory RA are identified, discussed and addressed in a realistic way, the work will be performed in different phases and through a set of case studies (see Appendix). The envisioned case studies will focus on specific health effects or endpoints, and on specific regulatory processes. This exercise will allow us to identify both the opportunities and the challenges when moving from animal-based towards NAM-based regulatory decision-making. Equally important, it will build confidence in the integration of NAMs as ‘stand-alone’ evidence in hazard and RAs (dependent on the problem formulations of the case studies performed).

The project will contribute to the PARC future needs: “NAMs to replace animal testing for hazard endpoints (including acute fish toxicity)” and “Validation of a systematic in vitro/silico battery to steer generation of chronic toxicity data for vertebrate species”. It may also, dependent on the case study selection, contribute to future need “DART”, “Carcinogenicity”, and “RAX and NAMs: Development of case studies”. The project will contribute to the priority area of implementation of NAMs as standalone information targeting priority endpoints such as neurotoxicity, endocrine disruption, and carcinogenicity.

Main expected outputs of the project:

The project will provide new insights into which regulatory areas and for which endpoints further implementation of NAMs is feasible and what refinements are needed. As expected outputs we envision that results may demonstrate the applicability of a NAM-based approach, thereby pushing regulatory acceptance. Further, results will provide insight where finetuning of existing NAMs and/or development of additional NAMs is needed. Finally, results may also suggest new grounds on which regulatory requests for different purposes (e.g. hazard identification) should be identified.

Outcomes and impacts expected on end-users and stakeholders:

This project aims to provide knowledge and insights that contribute to the activities of the EC foreseen under the “Roadmap for phasing out animal testing in chemical safety assessments” in the EU. The outcome of the project will provide useful information for risk assessors and decision makers (yielding highly valuable lessons learned on the possible implementation of NAMs), for applicants (what may submission of a NAM-based dossier for regulatory purposes involve), and for regulators (having real-life cases to underpin requests for changing the regulatory core data requests, thereby substantially limiting animal testing).

In particular, we want to evaluate where NAMs can be applied on the short(er) term for regulatory purposes, i.e. replacing (or reducing) animal testing under the current regulatory system. In addition, we would like to gain better insight into the challenges that require longer-term solutions or approaches and thus should be further developed. As such, this project will contribute to putting NGRA into practice.

Outcomes and impacts expected to be incorporated into a specific regulatory framework:

The outcomes of the project are in principle applicable to regulatory RA in general. NAM-based approaches for chemical hazard or RA have been explored for a long time, but their implementation in regulatory processes is seriously lagging behind. This is partly due to [socio-technical barriers](#), and partly due to lack or insufficient insight into aspects of NAMs that are considered important for gaining trust. In this project

we focus on the latter. We do not foresee that NAM-based approaches for a specific regulatory question will be sufficiently mature to be ready for implementation during the lifespan of PARC. Nevertheless, the case studies conducted will provide a significant step forward and provide valuable insights into the remaining gaps.

Key words: next-generation risk assessment, New Approach Methodologies (NAMs), Adverse Outcome Pathways (AOPs), risk of bias, weight of evidence, data integration, implementation

Link to the PARC DoA:

This project responds to the three Specific objectives defined for PARC. The project will contribute to the PARC OOs OO4, OO7, and OO9 by testing in practice and analysing opportunities and challenges when moving from animal-based to NAM-based regulatory decision making under different regulatory frameworks with focus on specific priority endpoints. The project aims to identify knowledge gaps and needs for improvements for NAM-based RA and provide recommendations for increasing regulatory acceptance of NAMs in chemicals RA (OO4, OO7). This outcome is expected to provide input to related projects on the use of NAMs and IATA development towards the transition to NGRA (OO4, OO7, OO9). Collaboration with regulatory agencies and authorities is expected to promote and facilitate the uptake of results in the regulatory context (OO4, OO9).

The project will also contribute to the PARC OOs by providing input to priority-setting (OO3), cooperate with other relevant R&I initiatives (OO5), communicate and disseminate results (OO6), implement FAIR data practices to enable open science (OO10), provide input to innovative concepts for RA (OO12), and share the results and experiences through training (OO13).

Links within PARC (WPs/Tasks/Activities/Projects):

- WP2: Regulatory applicability of NAMs; NGRARoute.
 In close collaboration with WP2, we will establish a '**regulatory forum**', with European and national regulatory agencies (incl. ECHA, EFSA, JRC) as members, with the aim to have frequent exchanges on priority setting, progress made, and challenges encountered.
 - T2.2
- WP5: NAM development; Evaluation of regulatory readiness (new project).
 - T5.2.1a
 - T5.3.2 AOP development
 - T5.3.4 PBTK models and quantitative systems toxicology
- WP6
 - T6.1: projects on IATA for various endpoints; project on workflow for human relevance assessment; THSD case study
 - T6.3: Project reviewing effect-specific RA, Project reviewing tools, criteria, and methods used in regulatory RA
 - T6.4: project on extrinsic and intrinsic validity
- WP7: FAIR Data; Uncertainty assessment.
 - T7.3

Links outside PARC:

- RISK-HUNT3R, ASPIS cluster
- CHANGE
- MERLON
- ADME4NGRA
- TGX-MAP

Within the context of RISK-HUNT3R and the ASPIS cluster, a workflow aimed at the operationalization

of NGRA is being developed. This workflow, entitled ‘ASPIS-initiated alternative Safety Profiling Algorithm’ (ASPA), provides a framework for testing and evaluating the different aspects that need to be met by NAMs in order to be considered for regulatory use. Proper linkage between the projects will be established through participation of e.g. RIVM in both projects. Regular meetings between the PARC project team and key representatives of RISK-HUNT3R / ASPIS are foreseen, to safeguard that both projects benefit from the lessons learned and to seize the opportunity to discuss challenges with a wider group of experts, where needed.

MERLON is a five-year project funded under the Horizon Europe R&I programme and included in the ENKORE cluster. The project includes development of NAMs as well as NAM-based assessment and identification of EDs anchored in AOP methodology. It also includes identifying current scientific and regulatory practices for ED identification, as well as needs and possibilities for advancements in these practices.

ADME4NGRA is a four-year project funded by EFSA. In order to provide EFSA concrete guidance for using in vitro ADME tools for parameterising PBK, the Project has the aims to compare ADME processes between humans and rats using advanced in vitro systems; to develop and apply advanced in silico models and databases to depict ADME processes; to integrate QIVIVE and PBK models in human RA.

TGX-MAP is a four-year project funded by EFSA, which aims to deliver an easy to use, integrated toolbox for toxicogenomics data analysis and pathway-based interpretation for safety assessors. The key impact of TGX-MAP will be obtaining confidence in the fit-for-purpose of human NAM in vitro test systems for application in toxicogenomics mechanism-based chemical safety assessment.

Key PARC Deliverables and Milestones to which the project contributes

D6.11: Report on harmonized workflow for human relevance assessment of AOPs and associated NAMs (M72)

D6.12: 2nd Report on IATAs plus associated case studies (M81)

D6.17: 2nd Report on conclusions from case studies reviewing RA methodologies (M81)

D6.19: Report on regulatory acceptance and use of new methods (NAMs) (M81)

Partners List: KEMI (SE); RIVM (NL); ISS (IT); BPI (EL); UNIBAS (CH); MU (CZ); KI (SE); SCIENSANO (BE); STAMI (NO), IISPV (ES), IRFM (IT), KWR (NL), UL-LACDR (NL), SU (SE), TTL (FI)

Schedule:

Starting date: 01/05/2025 (M37)

Expected ending date: 31/01/2029 (M81)

Costs

Expected PM for the first year of the project: 35 PM

Expected ODC for the first year of the project: 23 450 €

P6.4.2.e_Y4_READYAI_UNIBAS

Project Title	Establishment of Readiness Criteria for AI-based tools for risk assessment		
Project Acronym (15 letters max)	READYAI		
Project Manager	Ellen Fritsche ellen.fritsche@unibas.ch	UNIBAS	Switzerland
Deputy Project manager	Tomasz Puzyn t.puzyn@qsarlab.com	Gdansk	Poland
Expected starting date	M37	Expected duration (months)	45

PARC (Month number)

PARC Workpackage number WP6 **PARC Task/Activity/Sub-activity:** 6.4.2.e

Project Id P6.4.2.e_Y4_READYAI_UNIBAS

Status: Initiation

Summary of the project

This project addresses the challenges of using in silico tools based on ML/AI for regulatory purposes, focusing on RA and various applications like evidence management, toxicity prediction, and exposure assessment. AI/ML tools are advancing rapidly, but there's uncertainty about their reliability in chemical regulation. To address this, the project aims to establish readiness criteria and a scoring system for in silico tools based on ML/AI, similar to those developed for in vitro methods, to help regulatory scientists gauge their reliability. Collaborating with key stakeholders and developers, the project will create a readiness check questionnaire for AI/ML tools, supporting regulations across sectors and nations. The outcomes of the project will establish criteria for reliability for in silico tools based on ML/AI. This will facilitate their application in the RA process. The tools, and methods are horizontally applicable across the RA process. However, a few examples on their uses in the policy processes are:

Tools for the systematic review process (like e.g. SysRev) to facilitate and support data collection and extraction for performing IATAs commonly used by e.g. EFSA in the RA process.

Tools aiding in the generation of AOPs like the AOP-helpFinder 2.0 that supports the establishment of event-event relationships and the WoE approach. AOPs can be the basis of IATAs when a certain mode-of-action is well established.

QSAR Models for predicting hazard based on chemical structures. QSAR tools, like the OECD toolbox, are used for RA process under several frameworks, e.g fulfilling data requirement under REACH and development of AI based QSARs are ongoing.

There will be impacts on the shorter and on the longer scale. When the first readiness criteria are established starting with the first two tools, these can immediately be applied for assessing readiness of AI/ML based methods. We envision the tools aiding in the systematic review process and QSAR tools to be the low hanging fruit. For extending the criteria to additional tools (e.g. the AOP-helpFinder, tools dealing with omics data, image recognition tools, ADME/PBK modelling tools, exposure assessment modelling tools) will take until the end of the funding period. Thereby, it has to be assessed which readiness criteria of AI/ML-based tools are universal and which are specific to the area of application.

Main expected outputs of the project:

The outputs will be catalogues of questions that are firstly to be used by AI/ML tool developers to rate the developed tools. For reaching this output, within this project criteria for evaluation of readiness will be defined and in case examples it will be investigated to what extent these criteria are fulfilled. These analyses can be applied across different sectors and tasks. In a second step the project and in particular the core steering group (including ECHA and EFSA) will further investigate how it can be assured that the framework is applied consistently by developer so that it can be used to more independently to assess the regulatory applicability of AI/ML based tools.

Outcomes and impacts expected on end-users and stakeholders:

There is a high uncertainty concerning the use of AI/ML-based methods for regulatory applications in the regulatory community. With the establishment of readiness criteria and scores for respective tools this uncertainty can be reduced and the appropriate usage of tools promoted. As AI/ML-based tools exceed the speed of expert judgement tremendously, the impact will be high. This project aims to provide tools for RA facilitating the replacement of animal studies by AI/ML based in silico NAMs. Hence the project will

contribute to the activities of the EC towards a “Roadmap for phasing out animal testing in chemical safety assessments” in the EU.

Outcomes and impacts expected to be incorporated into a specific regulatory framework:

The outcome is applicable framework-overarching. However, examples on utilization of tools were given in the previous section.

Key words: AI/ML, artificial intelligence, machine learning, readiness criteria, trust

Link to the PARC DoA:

Due to the over-arching nature of the envisioned readiness criteria this project responds to all SO1-3, and here the operative objectives OO4, OO5, OO7, OO9 - OO13.

Links within PARC (WPs/Tasks/Activities/Projects):

- WP2: This work will contribute to priorities as defined in WP2 to meet the EC’s CSS Towards a Toxic-Free Environment by speeding up chemical assessment by implementing AI/ML into the RA process (T2.2)
- WP5: Link to AI/ML tool developer.
 - T5.2.
 - T5.3: AOP development; T5.3.2, T 5.3.4 PBTK models and quantitative systems toxicology
- WP7: Link to FAIR criteria and AI/ML tool users (T7.3)

Links outside PARC:

ONTOX will deliver a generic strategy to create innovative NAMs in order to predict systemic repeated dose toxicity effects (liver, kidney, developing brain) that, upon combination with tailored exposure assessment, will enable human RA. Thereby, it strongly implements AI/ML-based tools. Interaction with ONTOX enables access to a plethora of these tools and their users or developers.

“Accessible Innovative Methods for the Safety & Sustainability Assessment of Chemicals & Materials” CHIASMA will generate machine readable versions of the ToxTemps, which are essential for the regulatory uptake of NAMs.

The Swiss Federal Office for Public Health (FOPH) project also supports the study of the use of AI/ML-based tools for the RA process.

Key PARC Deliverables and Milestones to which the project contributes

D6.19. Report on regulatory acceptance and use of new methods (NAMs) (M81)

Partners List: UNIBAS (CH), UT (EE), UG-PL (PL), UoB (UK), IRFM (IT), possibly KEMI (SE), possibly AGES (AT), Anses (FR)

Schedule:

Starting date: 01/05/2024 (M37)

Expected ending date: 31/01/2029 (M81)

Costs

Expected PM for the first year of the project: 17 PM

Expected ODC for the first year of the project: 9 375 €

A6.4.3 Developing information transfer structures and enforcement methodology for chemicals in articles to support the transition to a circular economy – 1 PROJECT

P6.4.3.a_Y1_SuProM_MU (closed M36)

Project Title	A comprehensive review and application of databases and testing methods for SUBstances in PROducts and Materials		
Project Acronym (15 letters max)	SuProM		
Project Manager	Lisa Melymuk lisa.melymuk@recetox.muni.cz	MU (RECETOX)	Czechia
Deputy Project manager	Robin Vestergren robin.vestergren@kemi.se	KemI	Sweden
Expected starting date PARC (Month number)	1	Expected duration	36
PARC Workpackage number	6	PARC Task/Activity/Sub-activity:	6.4.3
Project Id	P6.4.3.a_Y1_SuProM_MU		

*The project will be closed M36, the related AD6.15 is planned to be submitted M39

P6.4.3.b_Y3_ENFORCE_KemI

Project Title	New methods to support the ENFORCEment of chemicals in consumer articles		
Project Acronym (15 letters max)	ENFORCE		
Project Manager	Robin Vestergren Robin.vestergren@kemi.se	Swedish chemicals agency (KemI)	Sweden
Deputy Project manager	Lisa Melymuk lisa.melymuk@recetox.muni.cz	MU (RECETOX)	Czechia
Expected starting date PARC (Month number)	25	Expected duration (months)	48
PARC Workpackage number	WP6	PARC Task/Activity/Sub-activity:	6.4.3b
Project Id	P6.4.3.b_Y3_ENFORCE_KemI		

Status: Implementation

Summary of the project

Enforcement of EU chemicals safety legislation has a central role in implementing the European Green Deal agenda and the CSS. Effective enforcement will ensure that EU citizens are not exposed to regulated substances and ensure a level playing field for producers and importers of consumer articles.

The recent development in analytical techniques and use of chemical information systems have opened opportunities for characterizing the universe of chemicals in different matrices facilitating the identification of CECs. Yet, the full potential of these novel methods is not exploited for regulatory purposes.

The project will evaluate the applicability of methods of chemical identification for use in the enforcement of chemical safety legislation, to fulfil crucial needs raised in project 6.4.3a. For effective enforcement rapid screening methods that cover a wide range of restricted/SVHC substances that can be applied to a variety of sample matrices are typically needed. The methods developed and tested in this project will

facilitate a systematic identification of priority substances, products, and materials and provide efficient analytical methods for enforcement actions. This will support national enforcement authorities of chemicals legislation (REACH and CLP) as well as product-specific legislations (for example, the Restriction of Hazardous Substances Directive, EC Toys directive, POPs-regulation, regulations on food contact materials, etc.).

Main expected outputs of the project:

The project will evaluate methods of chemical screening and quantification according for their applicability to enforcement of chemical safety legislation. In evaluating methods, this project will further test to what extent databases reviewed in P6.4.3a capture the chemical composition of articles. By developing and applying rapid analytical techniques for screening and validation the project will provide a proof-of-concept methodology that could be used in enforcement of chemicals legislation. The project will focus on (i) additives in high volume plastics and (ii) per- and polyfluoralkyl substances in articles identified as major use categories. Although the project will specifically focus on restricted substances and SVHCs a broader range of chemicals will be included in in the methodology testing. The methods developed in this project will be presented at several stages to ECHA enforcement forum to assess the possibilities and needs for further standardisation.

Outcomes and impacts expected on end-users and stakeholders:

The primary stakeholders for this project are national and EU agencies responsible for the enforcement of chemical and product legislation. It is envisaged that the results from this project will provide strategies and tools that could be implemented by enforcement agencies, that need better opportunities to prioritise enforcement and today lack fast, reliable and harmonised screening methods for analysing organic substances. The project will also foster a collaboration between scientists and regulators at national agencies and national inspectors through ECHA forum that could serve as a model for addressing future regulatory needs. Thus, the project will contribute to more systematic and effective enforcement of chemicals also beyond the completion of PARC.

Key words: Enforcement, consumer articles, PFAS, plastics, data bases.

Link to the PARC DoA:

The project responds to the PARC OOs: OO4 , OO5, OO6, OO7, OO10, OO12 and OO9. In response to identified needs in Chemical RA (OO7) this project will build on existing methodologies and ongoing research projects (OO5) to develop testing methods that can be used in enforcement of chemicals legislation (OO4, OO5), and in increase knowledge and awareness on chemical exposures and risks (OO6). The project will include assessment of the FAIR and open aspects of existing databases, and recommendations for improved data structures that meet FAIR and open data criteria and are useable tools for further RA related to substances in articles and materials (OO10, OO12)

Links within PARC (WPs/Tasks/Activities/Projects):

WP3: Synergies, Communication and awareness: Support the communication with national agencies and ECHA forum regarding their need for methods.

WP4: Considering the focus on new analytical methods the work carried out in 6.4.3a will be closely linked to Task 4.3 (Analytical method development). Two of the partners in 6.4.3 (VUA and ÖRU) have ongoing/planned projects with PMs under task 4.3. which will contribute to the objectives of this project.

WP9: Training, laboratory network: Evaluation of chemical laboratories/methods involved in enforcement activities related to substances in products and materials; capacity-building related to enforcement activities.

Other WPs: WP6 (Task 6.2 Exposure via consumer articles); WP8 (Task 8.1 SSbD).

Links outside PARC:

The work under 6.4.3a has identified numerous research initiatives on PFAS in consumer articles and additives in plastics which may be relevant to communicate and collaborate with. The research on new testing methods for products and materials will be carried out in close collaboration with national agencies

responsible for enforcing chemical and product legislations and ECHA forum. In particular, the competent authorities responsible for the proposal of a broad PFAS restriction (Norway, Sweden, Denmark, Germany and the Netherlands) will be consulted during the development of methods to support the upcoming restriction.

Key PARC Deliverables (or Additional Deliverables) and Milestones to which the project contributes

D6.20 Framework & case studies for articles & recycled materials for systematic identification of priority substances, materials, & articles from market data (M81).

AD6.26. New methods to support a systematic and effective enforcement of chemicals M72 (MU/KemI).

Partners List: MU (Czechia), KemI (Sweden), Rise (Sweden), TUKES (Finland), VUA (Netherlands), Stockholm University (Sweden), Örebro University (Sweden)

Schedule:

Starting date: 01/05/2024 (M25)

Expected ending date: 30/04/2028 (M72)

Costs

Expected PM for the second year of the project: 50 PM

Expected ODC for the second year of the project: 40 700 €

A6.4.4 Risk assessment to support and promote efficient overall protection of biodiversity – 5 PROJECTS

P6.4.4.a Y1_CRNCS1_KEMI

Project Title	Clarify regulatory needs – Transform EU strategies into regulatory useable research projects		
Project Acronym (15 letters max)	CRNCS1		
Project Manager	Johan Axelman Johan.axelman@kemi.se	Swedish Chemicals Agency	Sweden
Deputy Project manager	Sabine Duquesne Sabine.Duquesne@uba.de	Umweltsbundesamt (UBA)	Germany
Expected starting date PARC (Month number)	1	Expected duration	81*
PARC Workpackage number	6	PARC Task/Activity/Sub-activity:	6.4.4
Project Id	P6.4.4.a_Y1_CRNCS1_KEMI		

* The project has been extended from M42 to M81

Status: Implementation

Summary of the project

The activity is tailored toward supporting strategic transition initiatives such as the roadmap to systems-based ERA (by EFSA PERA) and European co-funded partnership on biodiversity (Biodiversa+). The project is directly applicable to the ERA for the authorisation of PPP and aims to better link the goal of the EU environmental and agricultural strategies to the EU regulation 1107/2009.

The activity aims at better assessing effects on overall biodiversity and the possibility to simplify (i.e. less resource demanding) the methods used for the ERA of PPP without compromising the level of protection to be ensured by the assessment. That will be achieved by benchmarking existing and new methods (such as NAMs) against each other and against independent environmental monitoring data. Approaches, research

questions and methodologies for these benchmarking activities are described in project plans for 6.4.4.b_Y1_PPPEXPCS2_SLU, 6.4.4.c_PPPEFF_CS3_UFZ and 6.4.4.d_PPPBENCHCS4_UDE. Furthermore, we will explore new holistic approaches to ERA to overcome the shortcomings of the current substance-by-substance paradigm and consider the environmental context more realistically. Approaches, research questions and methodologies for these benchmarking activities are described in project plans for 6.4.4.d_PPPBENCHCS4_UDE and P6.4.4.e_Y1_PPPOSCS5_ISCIII. Both existing and new models for prospective RA will be reviewed and amended using monitoring data. The activity will also help to explore new frameworks for risk characterisation that support system-based approaches to RA by expanding the current approach.

Main expected outputs of the project

The project will ensure that the outcome of the other projects within 6.4.4 address the common goal of an improved ERA-scheme better aligning with EU strategies and assessing biodiversity. Considering regulatory needs and ensuring regulatory acceptance are key components of this project. It will be identified how the input from other stakeholders (risk managers, farmers, etc) can be integrated in the ERA development.

Outcomes and impacts expected for end-users and stakeholders

The current ERA scheme is well established, but has fallen out of step with environmental reality and technological possibilities. The project will provide a more realistic and resource-efficient ERA-scheme. However, the development needs to be supported by EFSA to be taken up by the risk assessors in the member states. The close collaboration with EFSA in this project, ensures a targeted and operational development of a new ERA-scheme and facilitates the application by end-users and stakeholders, e.g., risk assessors and applicants.

Key words:

Environmental risk assessment, Systems-based approach, Regulatory needs, Stakeholder engagement

Link to the PARC DoA

The PARC objective is the regulatory applicability of the research, and this project will assure regulatory applicability of the activity 6.4.4 through the direct involvement of regulatory risk assessors and EFSA.

OO3– This project’s key objective is to translate regulatory and policy needs into ERA research issues for the projects involved in 6.4.4 as well as other collaboration projects (see OO5 below). The translation process will be guided by an iterative and knowledge building dialogue with regulators, policymakers and other stakeholders. The dialogue involves mutual knowledge exchange between researchers in all projects of 6.4.4.

OO4– See comment for OO3 (iterative knowledge-building dialogue).

OO5– As a representative of all projects in Activity 6.4.4 this project is approached by and actively seeks out to establish collaboration with relevant other projects (Horizon Europe and other). A knowledge exchange platform with monthly meetings for all partners in 6.4.4 has been established.

OO8, OO9

OO12– This project is designed to support a step-wise transition towards systems-based assessments, a process that includes a wide range of stakeholders. A scientific reframing of (E)RA driven by integration of knowledge from many different science disciplines requires an iterative knowledge building processes involves regulatory stakeholders.

Links within PARC (WPs/Tasks/Activities/Projects)

All five projects in Activity 6.4.4 are tightly linked and addresses different aspects of a step-wise transition to next generation systems-based ERAs. The role of this project (P6.4.4.a_Y1_CRNCS1) *Clarifying regulatory needs* is to coordinate the research questions and deliverables of the other four projects in 6.4.4. The role of this project is also to organise stakeholder interactions and engagement in order to ensure regulatory relevance of all projects in 6.4.4. Other planned linked are:

- WP2 and 3 to ensure a coordinated dialogue with regulators and policy makers.

- T6.3 Project within *Review of risk assessment methodologies*: Specificities and similarities of prospective and retrospective RA for pesticides.
- Activity 6.4.1 ERA of chemical mixtures to ensure alignment and avoid overlaps in system approaches.
- Activity 6.4.2 Project on NAMs in ERAs
- T4.2 Environmental monitoring.
- WP7 Data policy (management, harmonisation, interoperability, exchange). A standardised and comparable methodology would facilitate sharing and downstream use of the ERA-data.

Links outside PARC

Strategic partnerships at the EU-level, such as EFSA PERA and Biodiversa+, as well as projects such as SPRINT.

Key PARC Deliverables and Milestones to which the project contributes

AD6.7: Technical report outlining the regulatory needs for ERA development areas (M36)

D6.21 Recommendations for new ERA guidance documents (M81)

Partners List:

KEMI (SE); UBA(DE); FOEN (CH); ANSES (FR); EFSA (EU); ULUND (SE); NIVA (NO); UOS (DE)

Schedule for the first part of the project:

Starting date: 01/05/2022 (M1)

Expected ending date: 31/01/2029 (M81)

Costs

Expected PM for the fourth year of the project: 18 PM

Expected ODC for the fourth year of the project: 7 825 €

P6.4.4.b_Y1_PPPEXPCS2_RPTU

Project Title	Reduce complexity of models for predicted environmental concentrations of plant protection products while ensuring their predictive capacity		
Project Acronym (15 letters max)	PPPEXPCS2		
Project Manager	Mikaela Gönczi Mikaela.Gonczi@slu.se	SLU (M1-M24)	SE
	Ralf Schulz r.schulz@rptu.de	RPTU (M25-M81)	DE
Deputy Project manager	Gusatf Boström Gusatf.bostrom@slu.se	SLU (M1-M24)	SE
	Larissa Herrmann l.herrmann@rptu.de	RPTU (M25-M81)	DE
Expected starting date PARC (Month number)	1	Expected duration	81*
PARC Workpackage number	6	PARC Task/Activity/Sub-activity:	6.4.4
Project Id	P6.4.4.b_Y1_PPPEXPCS2_SLU (M1-M24) P6.4.4.b_Y1_PPPEXPCS2_RPTU (M25-M81)		

* The project has been extended from M36 to M81

Status: Implementation

Summary of the project

This project aims at investigating if the predictions in the exposure part of the ERA carried out in the context of authorization of PPPs under the Regulation (EC) No 1107/2009 can be simplified, improved in predictive

potential and validated by maintaining the level of protection required. In 2019 the SLU Centre for Pesticides in the Environment (CKB) at the Swedish University of Agricultural Sciences developed a new method for calculating predicted concentrations in surface water (called PEC CKB) (Boström et al., 2019). This approach successfully extends the type of methods which predict environmental concentrations (PECs) of PPPs in water bodies with fewer input parameters, but on the basis of established knowledge of environmental processes (e.g. Kattwinkel et al. 2011). The proposed calculation method is very simple and requires minimal input data. Further work would aim at achieving even closer conformity between PEC and measured (MEC) concentrations by focusing improvements on the most important factors of the calculations. This proposed project aims at exploring further ways of simplifying the PEC calculations within the ERA. This can be pursued through testing and further development of the PEC CKB or similar concepts like the German models Exposit and GEobased Runoff, Erosion, and Drainage risk Assessment for Germany (GERDA), and through comparing the predictability of these simpler models to MEC from different EU member states. The new models will be validated against currently existing models and monitoring data additional to those used to derive the models.

Main expected outputs of the project

The comparison of several models for exposure, including different parameters, with the same dataset will give us information on differences and similarities of the models' predictive capacity and protection level. By various analyses we will be able to evaluate which factor are most important to explain the concentrations in the environment and how the predictive capacity can be improved. We will also assess the transferability of the models between data from different member states and identify factors that play an important role such as geography, climate or soil properties.

Outcomes and impacts expected for end-users and stakeholders

The end-users of the research are mainly risk assessors in the context of authorization of plant protection products at member state and EU level. In addition, the project aims to contribute to a transition to a systems-based ERA by facilitating reusability of data generated within the ERA. In order to efficiently allocate resources, we need to examine if the ERA used for plant protection products can be simplified.

Key words:

Environmental risk assessment, exposure assessment, systems-based approach, plant protection products, monitoring

Link to the PARC DoA

The project aims to contribute to the development of existing and new models for estimating the risks of exposure to chemicals.

The project mainly responds to OO9 - developing models and innovative concepts for RA, and to deliver toolboxes to promote their acceptability and uptake, initially focusing on models for predicting surface water concentrations of pesticides.

Links within PARC (WPs/Tasks/Activities/Projects)

- PARC WPs interlinking within Activity 6.4.4.
- WP2 and 3 to ensure a coordinated dialogue with regulators and policy makers.
- T6.3 Project within *Review of risk assessment methodologies*: Specificities and similarities of prospective and retrospective RA for pesticides.
- Activity 6.4.1 ERA of chemical mixtures to ensure alignment and avoid overlaps in system approaches.
- Activity 6.4.2 Project on NAMs in ERAs
- Task 4.2 Environmental monitoring.
- WP7 Data policy (management, harmonisation, interoperability, exchange). A standardised and comparable methodology would facilitate sharing and downstream use of the ERA-data.

Links outside PARC

A member of the former FOCUS (FORum for the Co-ordination of pesticide fate models and their USE) surface water workgroup is participating in the project. Since their work is the basis of the exposure

component of the existing ERA this will improve the possibility that the results of the project will be implemented in a regulatory context. Other groups working with exposure models, such as GERDA will also be contacted.

Key PARC Deliverables and Milestones to which the project contributes

AD6.20. Technical report on factors and processes needed to be included in robust aquatic exposure predictions for regulatory use, including an assessment of geographic representativeness (M36) has been cancelled (merged with AD6.7)

D6.21 Recommendations for new ERA guidance documents (M81)

Partners List:

SLU (SE), RPTU (DE), Fraunhofer IME (DE), University of Osnabrück UOS (DE), EAWAG (CH), NIVA (NO), ULUND (SE), IEP-NRI (PL), UoB (UK). Regulatory CG: KEMI (SE), UBA (DE), FOEN (CH), ANSES (FR), EFSA (EU).

Schedule for the first part of the project:

Starting date: 01/05/2022 (M1)

Expected ending date: 31/01/2029 (M81)

Costs

Expected PM for the fourth year of the project: 65 PM

Expected ODC for the fourth year of the project: 35 871 €

P6.4.4.c_Y1_PPPEFFCS3_UFZ

Project Title	Reduce complexity of models for predictions of environmental effects of plant protection products while ensuring their predictive capacity		
Project Acronym (15 letters max)	PPPEFF CS3		
Project Manager	Matthias Liess matthias.liess@ufz.de	UFZ	DE
Deputy Project manager	Paulo Sousa jps@zoo.uc.pt	UC	PT
Expected starting date PARC (Month number)	1	Expected duration	81*
PARC Workpackage number	6	PARC Task/Activity/Sub-activity:	6.4.4
Project Id	P6.4.4.c_Y1_PPPEFF CS3_UFZ		

* The project has been extended from M36 to M81

Status: Implementation

Summary of the project

The RA process of PPPs has developed into a highly sophisticated, time consuming and complex process. Despite this elaborated procedure, the occurrence of PPP has been linked to adverse ecological effects on non-target organisms in several field investigations. This does not comply with the Regulation (EU) 546/2011 that “Member States shall ensure that use of plant protection products does not have any long-term repercussions for the abundance and diversity of non-target species” (EU Commission, 2011). The aim of this project is moving towards a protective ERA with reduced complexity and resources required while keeping it as information-rich as necessary. This will be achieved by including only the information and processes that have been proven by ecosystem monitoring and effect modelling to be relevant. This

improves the extrapolation of effect information from lower tier laboratory investigations to field effects. The ecosystem effects will be modelled with the stress addition model (SAM) (Liess et al. 2016) and compared with the effects monitored at the ecosystem level. This approach enables to identify the most parsimonious description of ecosystem processes related to the effects of PPP. A differentiation related to the MoA of PPPs and in relation to the respective groups of species will be performed. This project will contribute to the development of a more resource-efficient and realistic ERA as described in 6.4.4.1. The framework will be made accessible by a software package to enable a practicable and reproducible ERA.

Main expected outputs of the project

Field monitoring data related to exposure and effects of PPP in a great variety of member states will be collated. Currently high-quality data have been identified for Germany, Sweden, Switzerland. Data from a variety of member states in different regions of the EU need to be included to reflect the European diversity. A feedback loop between existing RA thresholds and retrospective ecosystem monitoring results will be formalized to constantly improve the level of realism and validation of ERA. By this the project will enable regulators to identify ecological process to be included into the RA.

Outcomes and impacts expected for end-users and stakeholders

The end-users will be provided with the identification of the relevant factors needed to link laboratory lower-tier tests and effects at the ecosystem level to make better use of lower-tier test information. Additionally, effect information obtained from the ecosystem level will enable to better use higher-tier test information within the RA framework

The implementation of the most relevant environmental factors into the RA process so that the sensitive field populations can be identified and protected and that ERA at the same time strives an improved balance between reduced complexity and increased ecological realism.

Increase regulatory usability by documenting a transparent and easy to follow framework on how effect models can be replicated and adapted to ensure transferability between member states.

Key words:

Environmental risk assessment, effect assessment, systems-based approach, plant protection products, monitoring

Link to the PARC DoA

The project responds to the PARC OO7, OO8, OO10, OO12, OO9.

Under this project, we aim to collate monitoring data from different member countries to improve current RA of chemicals. This involves validation of models such as SAM covering all relevant chemical and non-chemical stressors occurring in the field. using field monitoring data and hence contribute to RA.

Links within PARC (WPs/Tasks/Activities/Projects)

- All the projects within 6.4.4 are closely linked, aiming at RA to support and promote efficient overall protection of biodiversity. The project 6.4.4.a will ensure and translate the regulatory needs into research projects on ERA. The exposure data from 6.4.4.b project will be used with available effect data to better link exposure and effects (6.4.4.c) in the field. Based on field effects, the additional environmental factors relevant for ERA (6.4.4.d) will be identified and approaches will be benchmarked (6.4.4.e) with exposure and effects datasets.
- Interlink within Activity 6.4.4.
- WP2 and 3 to ensure a coordinated dialogue with regulators and policy makers.
- T 6.3 Project within *Review of risk assessment methodologies*: Specificities and similarities of prospective and retrospective RA for pesticides.
- Activity 6.4.1 ERA of chemical mixtures to ensure alignment and avoid overlaps in system approaches.
- Activity 6.4.2 Project on NAMs in ERAs
- T4.2 Environmental monitoring.

- WP 7 Data policy (management, harmonisation, interoperability, exchange). A standardised and comparable methodology would facilitate sharing and downstream use of the ERA-data.

Links outside PARC

Strategic partnerships at the EU-level, such as EFSA PERA and Biodiversa+, as well as projects such as SPRINT.

Key PARC Deliverables and Milestones to which the project contributes

AD6.19 Technical report informing on factors and processes needed to be included in the ERA to obtain an improved balance between reduced complexity and increased ecological realism (M36) has been cancelled (merged with AD6.7)

D6.21 Recommendations for new ERA guidance documents (M81)

Partners List:

UFZ (DE), UC (PT), EAWAG (CH), SLU (SE), UDE (DE), ULUND (SE), NIVA (NO), UCLM (ES), UOS (DE), ISCIII (ES)

Regulatory core team: KEMI (SE), UBA (DE), FOEN (CH), EFSA (EU), ANSES (FR), UKCEH (UK)

Schedule for the first part of the project:

Starting date: 01/05/2022 (M1)

Expected ending date: 31/01/2029 (M81)

Costs:

Expected PM for the fourth year of the project: 33 PM

Expected ODC for the fourth year of the project: 29 663 €

P6.4.4.d_Y1_PPPBENCHCS4_UDE

Project Title	Benchmark ERA to support the transition towards a holistic paradigm		
Project Acronym (15 letters max)	PPPBENCH		
Project Manager	Ralf Schäfer ralf.schaefer@uni-due.de	UDE	DE
Deputy Project manager	NA	NA	NA
Expected starting date PARC (Month number)	1	Expected duration	81*
PARC Workpackage number	6	PARC Task/Activity/Sub-activity:	6.4.4
Project Id	P6.4.4.d_Y1_PPPBENCHCS4_UDE		

* The project has been extended from M42 to M81

Status: Implementation

Summary of the project

This project aims to ensure that results of any independently performed ERA of a PPP can be used as a benchmark for ERAs of other PPPs, i.e., comparing and ranking risk profiles of PPPs among substances and in different areas (e.g., for selected organism groups) of the ERA when assessed on the basis of similar level of refinement. This project aims to develop concepts and methodologies to improve the ERA so that results from the individual RAs become inter-comparable in terms of risk profiles considering each area of the ERA. This helps in delivering consistent ERA results and once compared to monitoring results, it will eventually improve its reliability regarding the estimation of environmental risks. The overall aim of the project is to contribute to a more holistic ERA that manages the overall risk in an efficient manner.

Based on available data sets and case studies on rejected products, the internal and external risk benchmarking will be conducted. Depending on the results, gaps will be identified in current ERA paradigm

and short-term remedies proposed. Over the project period, a compatibility methodology will be suggested based on the future ERA paradigm that the partners develop in PARC. The project will thus have a direct impact on the development of an improved ERA under EU regulation 1107/2009.

Main expected outputs of the project

Expected output is an ERA concept and defined methodology to be used as a basis to develop a new guidance for ERA within the authorisation process. The resulting ERA should have an improved performance in terms of capturing the relative risk of different PPPs in a relevant spatial and temporal scale when assessed on the basis of similar data/ level of refinement. The improved ERA should also support systems-based RAs and facilitate use down the line, such as improved advisory services and systems-based RM.

Outcomes and impacts expected for end-users and stakeholders

One fundamental property of the ERA to improve would be the comparability of the methodology used to assess the environmental risks (not to be confused with comparative assessment performed as part of substitution process in the current assessment). If used in connection with specific decision rules, this methodology in turn could ensure that newly authorised PPPs have a lower, or if other reasons apply (e.g. resistance management) similar, risk level than those previously authorised.

The outcome of this project will aid the aims defined under 6.4.4.1 to align EU regulations and improve the ERA-scheme by identifying how a RA methodology should be designed to allow for benchmarking of PPPs against each other capturing their relative risk. Furthermore, the complexity of the current ERA will be reduced by identifying key descriptors of PPP-substances (physico-chemical properties, toxicological profiles) and use (exposure related parameters) that have the most weight in the description of the risk. Finally, the consistency of the RAs from different tiers regarding individual substances will be evaluated.

Key words:

Environmental risk assessment, effect assessment, systems-based approach, plant protection products, monitoring, benchmarking, comparative risk assessment

Link to the PARC DoA

The project responds to the following PARC OO4, OO5, OO10, OO12, OO9, and OO13. The expected output will promote the use of developed concepts with the possibility of their use in the approval process and also foster the uptake of PARC knowledge to increase stakeholders' awareness. It will also provide some collaboration with other partners thus enabling.

Links within PARC (WPs/Tasks/Activities/Projects)

- PARC WPs interlinking within Activity 6.4.4
- WP2 and 3 to ensure a coordinated dialogue with regulators and policy makers.
- Task 6.3 Project within *Review of risk assessment methodologies*: Specificities and similarities of prospective and retrospective RA for pesticides.
- Activity 6.4.1 ERA of chemical mixtures to ensure alignment and avoid overlaps in system approaches.
- Activity 6.4.2 Project on NAMs in ERAs
- Task 4.2 Environmental monitoring.
- WP7 Data policy (management, harmonisation, interoperability, exchange). A standardised and comparable methodology would facilitate sharing and downstream use of the ERA-data.

Links outside PARC

Strategic partnerships at the EU-level, such as EFSA PERA and Biodiversa+, as well as projects such as SPRINT.

Key PARC Deliverables and Milestones to which the project contributes

D6.21 Recommendations for new ERA guidance documents (M81)

Partners List:

UDE (DE), UFZ (DE), ISCIII (ES), EAWAG (CH), NIVA (NO), ULUND (SE).
 Regulatory core team: KEMI (SE), UBA (DE), FOEN (CH), ANSES (FR), EFSA (EU)

Schedule for the first part of the project:

Starting date: 01/05/2022 (M1)
 Expected ending date: 31/01/2029 (M81)

Costs:

Expected PM for the fourth year of the project: 19 PM
 Expected ODC for the fourth year of the project: 6 403 €

P6.4.4.e_Y1_PPPOSCS5_ISCIII

Project Title	Quantify effects of PPP and other stressors through landscape risk assessment informing on environmental impacts		
Project Acronym (15 letters max)	PPPOS		
Project Manager	José Tarazona jtarazona@isciii.es	ISCIII	ES
Deputy Project manager	Matthias Liess matthias.liess@ufz.de	UFZ	DE
Expected starting date PARC (Month number)	1	Expected duration	81*
PARC Workpackage number	6	PARC Task/Activity/Sub-activity:	6.4.4
Project Id	P6.4.4.e_Y1_PPPOSCS5_ISCIII		

* The project has been extended from M42 to M81

Status: Implementation

Summary of the project

Despite elaborate regulation of agricultural pesticides, their occurrence has been linked to adverse ecological effects on non-target organisms in several field investigations. This situation does not comply with the Regulation (EU) 546/2011 that states “Member States shall ensure that use of PPP does not have any long-term repercussions for the abundance and diversity of non-target species.” (EU Commission, 2011). This project investigates how multiple PPP and additional stressors can be integrated in ERA on a landscape level considering agricultural intensification and vulnerability of populations. The aim is moving the ERA paradigm from single chemical-crop combination to landscape-based ERA integrating landscape structures and aggregated (several crops) and combined (several pesticides) exposures into the current RA methods. Due to the complexity of environmental landscape-scale assessments, the identification of the key “drivers” for exposure and effects and the benchmarking proposed in the other three projects constitute a prerequisite. This project will build landscape models considering the results from the three previous projects, which will be used for the identification of the key modelling blocks under different landscape conditions. In addition, the EFSA proposals for setting protection goals based on ecosystem services and biodiversity in ERA will be implemented to develop risk characterisation tools that could be used as information source for environmental impact assessments; this will help to overcome the currently too fragmented ERA approaches.

Main expected outputs of the project

The project has direct connections and will benefit from the outcomes of the projects aiming to compare

predictions with monitoring data, using the agricultural landscape characteristics for strengthening the feedback loop from environmental monitoring and vigilance and ensure focus on factors that trigger the risk and overall impact on biodiversity in terrestrial agro-biosystems and aquatic ecosystems. In addition to supporting regulatory decisions, including the design and implementation of National Plans under the Sustainable Use Directive (SUD), a complementary long-term goal is to deliver management tools to advise and support practitioners to make informed decision (e.g. considering in selection of a PPP versus another PPP the local and regional levels/ ecotype) in the design and implementation of Integrated Pest Management and optimizing use and effects of ecosystem restorations with multiple purposes (i.e. improving biodiversity, reducing PPP pollution etc. through e.g. Nature Based Solutions).

Outcomes and impacts expected for end-users and stakeholders

This project aims to deliver methodologies and tools to promote a transition to a system- based ERA. End-users will be actors responsible for a systems-based RA, such as authorisation, enforcement and agricultural advisors. Comprehensible data on environmental impact and tools will enable these actors to take informed decisions.

The project will provide direct support to the implementation of measures under the SUD and reduction of pesticide impacts under the EU Green Deal and specifically the Farm to Fork Strategy.

The integration of farm management with agricultural landscape characteristics will provide support to decisions on sustainability at local, regional and national level, supporting the integration of sustainability concepts in food production and the CAP.

These new approach for ERA would support other policies, including WFD and the Habitats Directive. Optimizing the overlap of concepts and terminologies between central compartments in environmental management is essential for a (cost)efficient collaboration between different public management bodies. The outcomes will successfully pinpointing key stressors at regional level that impair biodiversity, ecological quality, and ecosystem services.

Key words:

Environmental risk assessment, systems-based approach, plant protection products, landscape assessment, multiple stressors, holistic risk assessment

Link to the PARC DoA

The project will develop new conceptual approaches, methodologies and tools for improving the ERA of pesticides (OO7). The project outputs will provide additional value to regulatory RAs, facilitating the interpretation of the risk characterisation outcome as environmental impacts, supporting not only the regulatory process for PPPs, but also associated regulatory needs connected to biodiversity protection and sustainable agriculture (OO12, OO9). Direct links with EU projects, and EU Agencies activities have been already identified OO4 , OO5). A key element for the project is to address the combined effects of pesticides on the environment, offering realistic alternatives to the current substance-by-substance regulatory approach (OO7).

Links within PARC (WPs/Tasks/Activities/Projects)

- PARC WPs interlinking within Activity 6.4.4
- WP2 and 3 to ensure a coordinated dialogue with regulators and policy makers.
- Task 6.2 and 6.3. The landscape approach for ERA will be used as the basis for case studies on aggregated human pesticide exposure from the environment, including the integrative prospective assessments (case study under 6.2) and a retrospective assessment (case study under 6.3) using HBM data.
- Task 6.3 Project within *Review of risk assessment methodologies*: Specificities and similarities of prospective and retrospective RA for pesticides.
- Activity 6.4.1 ERA of chemical mixtures to ensure alignment and avoid overlaps in system approaches.
- Activity 6.4.2 Project on NAMs in ERAs
- Task 4.2 Environmental monitoring.

- WP7 Data policy (management, harmonisation, interoperability, exchange). A standardised and comparable methodology would facilitate sharing and downstream use of the ERA-data.

Links outside PARC

Strategic partnerships at the EU-level, such as EFSA PERA and BiodivERsA.

The proposed work will be interlinked with several national and international projects including the Norwegian Agriculture monitoring program for pesticides and supporting cumulative RAs (<https://www.nibio.no/en/subjects/environment/the-norwegian-agricultural-environmental-monitoring-programme-jova>), the project « Cumulative hazard and risk assessment of complex mixtures and multiple stressors (MixRisk) » (www.niva.no/mixrisk), and several activities of NIVAs Computational Toxicology Program, NCTP (www.niva.no/nctp).

Key PARC Deliverables and Milestones to which the project contributes

D6.21 Recommendations for new ERA guidance documents (M81)

AD6.24. Applicability of landscape ERA approaches for refining the risk and assessing the impacts of PPPs (M81), summary of the case study results and analysis (detailed case study results will be disseminated as scientific publications)

AD6.25. Opportunities and challenges for addressing spatial and temporal variability in the regulatory context through landscape-based approaches (M83), final project deliverable

Partners List:

ISCHII (ES), UFZ (DE), UDE (DE), UC (PT), NIVA (NO), IEP-NRI (PL), OFB (FR), INERIS (FR), UCLM (ES), ULUND (SE), Uni Osnabrück (DE), UAVR (PT), SLU (SE), UoB (UK), UKCEH (UK), EAWAG (CH). Regulatory core team: KEMI (SE), UBA (DE), FOEN (CH), ANSES (FR), EFSA (EU)

Schedule for the first part of the project:

Starting date: 01/05/2022 (M1)

Expected ending date: 31/01/2029 (M81)

Costs:

Expected PM for the fourth year of the project: 53 PM

Expected ODC for the fourth year of the project: 11 131 €

WP7 FAIR data – 3 PROJECTS

In the context of the EU's Open Science Policy (https://research-and-innovation.ec.europa.eu/strategy/strategy-2020-2024/our-digital-future/open-science_en), PARC will promote harmonisation of data and exchange between different actors (scientific community, health agencies, regulators, policy-makers etc.) and disciplines (exposure science, toxicology...) to promote transparency, support RA, and allow for reuse. It will ensure data and associated information is FAIR, and addresses the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR; Regulation (EU) 2016/679) related challenges for data exchange.

T7.1 PARC FAIR Data Policy (PFDP) and DMP - No project submitted at present

Data “FAIRification” will be a key activity of PARC to facilitate data reuse. Implementing FAIR data practices is among the main OOs of PARC and will be measured by the proportion of datasets developed in PARC that will be FAIR, and the number of deliverables reusing existing data. A common DMP will be established and shared.

The PFDP will define the principles and conditions that govern provision, management, access, use and re-use of data, in line with the FAIR principles, while taking into account legal aspects (i.e. GDPR), security, transparency, sustainability and quality of the data. WP7 will provide the framework (guiding principles, data policy, framework DMP), set up specific methods and tools and guidance to FAIRify data and facilitate data reuse in the R&I WPs and in regulatory agencies. Through training, FAIR implementation will be broadly embedded in PARC. PARC will establish collaboration with specialised FAIR initiatives and projects (e.g. European Open Science Cloud (EOSC)-Life, ENVRIFAIR, WorldFAIR), and collaborate with experts from the Go FAIR Foundation (GFF) to kick start the FAIRification process in the first two years.

T7.2 Data libraries – 2 PROJECTS

Data will be made FAIR at the source whenever possible, described by FAIR metadata, and associated with a persistent identifier. PARC will use established FAIRification approaches such as the Three Point FAIRification framework (3PFF), elaboration of FAIR Implementation Profiles (FIPs) defining concrete implementation choices for each of the 15 FAIR principles (Schultes et al.¹, 2020; Wilkinson et al.², 2016), and established software solutions to manage FAIR data sources. Specific use cases will enable the multi-faceted FAIRification process to be developed gradually and pragmatically. Compatibility assessment, efforts for harmonisation and maximum interoperability will start from these FIPs. Standardised templates will be created, as necessary, based on domain specific standards, formats and vocabularies whenever available. PARC will perform landscape exercises and FAIRness assessments to identify potential partners to functionally integrate and exchange different types of data from different domains, and different national and transnational levels. It will build further upon DG ENV's Common Data Platform for Chemicals (CDPC), which will be the default option for data that are within scope for the DG ENV domain of interest (read: data relevant to regulatory RA). Because the CDPC is, at the current moment, still under development, a joint exercise will be set up to align PARC activities with the DG ENV roadmap. For data that is out of scope for the CDPC (read: not commonly used in regulatory RA), the content and accessibility of specialised data centres (e.g. ESFRI (European Strategic Forum for Research Infrastructure) research infrastructures (i.e., EIRENE -for human exposome data-, ELIXIR -life sciences collaboration-), member state Open Data initiatives -lab analysis results processing-, domain-specific repositories, institutional repositories, and open generic repositories such as Zenodo) will be explored, integrating efforts and achievements from recently ended projects such as EuroMix (<https://www.euromixproject.eu/> -chemical mixtures-), NORMAN (<https://www.norman-network.net/> -data on emerging environmental substances-) and HBM4EU (HBM data), ongoing project clusters such as the EHEN cluster or the EURION, and

community databases such as the aforementioned NORMAN. Integration with IPCHEM – the EC’s IPCHEM - and the OECD eChemPortal will be implemented also, through semantic mapping of the underpinning data schema. A dedicated FAIR data hub hosting core functionalities (such as querying of data, use of searchable catalogues and metadata services) complementary to existing platforms, will be implemented. Establishment of new FAIR Data Points (Thompson et al.³, 2020) or dedicated repositories will be considered in cases where existing solutions do not satisfy the needs of the PFDP.

A7.2.1 Mapping the PARC Data Landscape

No project submitted at present.

A7.2.2 PARC FAIR data hub – 2 PROJECTS

P7.2.2.a_Y1_chemicals-in-environment_MU_VITO

Project Title	Chemicals in the Environment data reuse		
Project Acronym (15 letters max)	ENV DATA (RE)USE		
Project Manager	Richard Hůlek richard.hulek@recetox.muni.cz	Masaryk University (MU, RECETOX)	CZ
Deputy Project manager	Jana Klánová jana.klanova@recetox.muni.cz	Masaryk University (MU, RECETOX)	CZ
Expected starting date PARC (Month number)	1	Expected duration	42*
PARC Workpackage number	7	PARC Task/Activity/Sub-activity:	7.2.2
Project Id	P7.2.2.a_Y1_chemicals-in-environment_MU		

*The project has been extended from M36 to M42

Status: Implementation

Summary of the project

The project’s main goal is to support the reuse of existing data in relation to environmental exposure and the management of newly generated data in accordance with FAIR principles and in view of the concepts of Open Data and One substance, one assessment.

The monitoring component of PARC (WP4, WP6, WP9), including HBM, environmental monitoring, and innovative methods, explores the presence of (priority) chemicals in a multicompartment environment and the resulting exposure of humans. These chemical substances originate from multiple sources and move along different pathways. Aggregated, combined, and cumulative exposures will be assessed through surveys of the co-occurrence of chemical substances, their metabolites, and degradation products in different matrices, including humans. These monitoring initiatives from source to humans foster a “one health” chemical RA strategy.

Members in R&I work packages in PARC (e.g. WP4, WP6, WP8) ask for solutions to access/connect to existing data resources in monitoring programs, databases, and libraries to help them with mapping and accessing the information available in the various data resources. This includes a need to extract and combine information on (priority) chemicals in the environment that will then guide further work on improvements of human and environmental/ecological RA. The structures that facilitate the review and extraction of existing information should reflect the requirements of regulatory processes and strategies to which the work of R&I work packages is linked (e.g. EU WFD, Soil strategy, ECHA PFAS restriction proposal, REACH).

Over the years various tools and database platforms were created to provide for storage, analysis, and visualization of occurrence data and trends in chemical exposure in the environment at global, EU, and national levels (for example, EMEP⁶, EBAS⁷, Global ENvironmental ASsessment Information System (GENASIS)⁸, Global Monitoring Plan (GMP) data warehouse⁹, NORMAN¹⁰, IPCHEM¹¹). Nevertheless, each of the tools or knowledge hubs was developed for different communities and comprises different services and scopes. Available datasets are often organized by environmental matrix, contain different scopes and contents, and are at various stages of development (harmonization principles, ontology, tools). The project aims for an effective exchange of reliable, relevant, curated, and FAIR data on chemicals (specifically environmental exposure data) between different stakeholders and policy domains (in line with the European Strategy for Data). Via mapping the existing data landscape and developing tailored solutions for data re(usage) and the implementation of FAIR principles, the chemical RA community in PARC and beyond will increasingly reuse both scientific and regulatory data for application and innovation in RA, thus empowering the European Green Deal Data Space.

Additionally, the R&I work packages in PARC (e.g. WP4, WP6, WP9) generate new datasets, and there is a need to create solutions and provide tools to manage newly generated data in line with the FAIR principles and to provide structures for newly generated data that would further be used by risk assessors on European and national levels.

Main expected outputs of the project

The project is structured around three main activities: i) mapping the existing data resources relevant to environmental exposure to chemicals and assessing the current landscape (mainly on European and national levels), and assessment of FAIRness level of the priority resources; ii) developing solutions for accessing and re(usage) existing/newly developed data resources, iii) cooperate and support other PARC WPs (WP4, WP6, WP8) in producing and managing environmental data in line with FAIR principles and in accordance with the Open Data approach, which should ultimately support the concept of “One substance, once assessment”.

The main project outputs are:

- Inventory of the priority and most relevant resources for assessing environmental exposure to chemicals with the information on the level of their FAIRness
- Online metadata catalogues of existing (priority) data resources on (priority) chemicals for reuse in RA in PARC (and in particular in research and monitoring activities in WPs 4, 6, 8), but also for national users, regulatory agencies, and the research community
- PARC-generated data are in line with the FAIR principles and stored in a FAIR online platform

Outcomes and impacts expected for end-users and stakeholders

⁶ « The co-operative programme for monitoring and evaluation of the long-range transmission of air pollutants in Europe (informally 'European Monitoring and Evaluation Programme' = EMEP) is a scientifically based and policy driven programme under the Convention on Long-range Transboundary Air Pollution (CLRTAP) for international co-operation to solve transboundary air pollution problems. » <https://www.emep.int/>

⁷ « EBAS is a database with atmospheric measurement data. EBAS objective is to handle, store and disseminate atmospheric composition data generated by international and national frameworks like long-term monitoring programmes and research projects. » <https://ebas.nilu.no/>

⁸ « GENASIS (Global ENvironmental ASsessment Information System) provides a comprehensive information on contamination of the environment by chemicals, namely persistent organic pollutants (POPs). » <https://www.genasis.cz/index-en.php>

⁹ « Global Monitoring Plan (GMP) for Persistent Organic Pollutants (POPs) under the Stockholm Convention Data Warehouse (GMP DWH) is an online tool developed for handling persistent organic pollutants (POPs) monitoring data generated in the frame of the Global Monitoring Plan (GMP) under the Stockholm Convention on POPs. » <http://visualization.pops-gmp.org/2014/>

¹⁰ NORMAN organises the development and maintenance of various web-based databases for the collection & evaluation of data / information on emerging substances in the environment

¹¹ « IPCHEM - the Information Platform for Chemical Monitoring is the European Commission's reference access point for searching, accessing and retrieving chemical occurrence data collected and managed in Europe. » <https://ipchem.jrc.ec.europa.eu/>

This project contributes to REACH - supports human and environmental/ecological RA, and allows for the reuse of data and knowledge - regulatory agencies to have direct access to environmental data, and indirectly that data will be available for reuse in models and toolboxes or for addressing research questions. The project has an important function within PARC as many other projects include a step of reviewing existing data, in order to build on them and avoid duplication. By facilitating this review and providing structures for easy access to existing data, this project will support many other activities in PARC in their address of specific regulatory needs.

Key words: (meta)data, data resources, libraries, FAIR, harmonization, (open) access, open data, environmental exposure

Link to the PARC DoA

OO5: The project aims to connect to existing databases.

OO7: The project responds to the needs of PARC projects and WPs regarding the access and reuse of existing data relevant to chemical RA.

OO8: The project will support the provision of environmental and multiscore data for regulatory purposes.

OO10: The project aims to assess the FAIRness of existing priority data resources, and provides solutions towards FAIR management of newly generated (environmental) data in PARC.

OO9 : The project will support in two ways: i) supporting R&I PARC WPs directly linked to regulatory processes and strategies in reusing existing data and creating solutions for newly generated data in line with FAIR principles; and ii) creating systems and solutions for newly generated data in PARC to be further used by risk assessors.

OO13: Through training on FAIR principles.

Links within PARC (WPs/Tasks/Activities/Projects)

WP3: Synergies, Communication and awareness: The project in 7.2 would need to establish synergies with existing projects and monitoring networks such as ERA Planet (H2020), e-shape (H2020 project EuroGEOSS Showcases: Showcasing and promoting users' uptake of Global Earth Observation System of Systems (GEOSS)), Solutions, IPCHEM, NORMAN, European - EMEP, global - Stockholm Convention and Minamata Convention monitoring plans and also shared infrastructures (i.e., Elixir, CESNET, EOSC, EnvriFAIR-ESFRI) to foster the environmental data management and solutions in line with FAIR principles.

WP7: Data management plan: The DMP of the project is elaborated in close collaboration with the WP7 in line with the WP7 recommendations. Data management issues observed during the project that might be relevant to the whole PARC project will be communicated to the WP7.

WP9: Training, laboratory network: The inventory of existing resources relevant for the assessment of environmental exposure is carried out in close collaboration with WP9. WP9 carried out the inventory of monitoring networks and laboratories. This project will focus on other relevant resources potentially not included in the WP9 scope, and assess the priority and FAIRness of those resources (mapped by both WP9 and WP7). The project will cooperate with tasks 9.1 and 9.2 in the development of the best-fit architecture for WP9 catalogues on laboratory and exposure monitoring networks.

Other WPs:

For this particular project, close collaboration is expected with task 4.2 Environmental monitoring and multisource exposure. The current project in T4.2 ("ENVMonitoringPilotSurvey") includes an activity on "Review of existing knowledge", which is also foreseen for future projects in T4.2. It is therefore expected that data from various data resources would need to be brought together, assessed against the FAIR principles, and combined to allow for use in T4.2. This project will cooperate and support T4.2 project partners in finding and applying the best solutions for accessing all the relevant data, their connection, re(use) and management in accordance with FAIR principles and if needed, making them available and accessible via a FAIR platform/repository.

This project also aims to screen and select specific use cases in other PARC WPs/project (WP4, WP6, WP8) that would respond to the need of those projects for support in generating new environmental data in line with the FAIR principles. Similarly, close cooperation is foreseen in regard to WP6 and WP8, whenever

data generated outside or within PARC are to be used in models.

Further links with PARC projects, tasks and WPs will be regularly investigated and fostered via regular communication and (if needed) workshops with the involved PARC partners.

Links outside PARC

This project serves experts/data holders and data users in tasks 4.2, 4.3, 6.2., 6.4., and WP8 but would need to establish synergies with existing projects and infrastructures, such as ERA Planet (H2020), e-shape (H2020 project EuroGEOSS Showcases: Showcasing and promoting users' uptake of GEOSS), Solutions, IPCHEM, NORMAN, European - EMEP, global - Stockholm Convention and Minamata Convention monitoring plans, and shared infrastructures (i.e., Elixir, CESNET, EOSC, EnvriFAIR-ESFRI).

Key PARC Deliverables and Milestones to which the project contributes

The project will partly contribute to the following deliverables of WP7 (task 7.1):

D7.1. Data Management Plan (DMP) (delivered)

D7.2. PARC FAIR data policy (PFDP) (delivered)

D7.3. 1st report on Data infrastructure, tools and services for FAIRification and reuse of chemical RA data (M36)

D7.5. 1st review of the Data Management Plan (DMP) (M42)

D7.6. 2nd review of the Data Management Plan (DMP) (M72)

MS11. Network of trained FAIR data stewards (delivered)

MS12. Architecture of PARC FAIR data hub & its integration with the COPCSD (delivered)

Partners List: MU (CZ), VITO (BE), UFZ (DE), BRGM (FR), UNILU (LU), ISSEP (BE), JSI (SI), ANSES (FR), NIVA (NO), UBA (DE), AUTH (GR)

Schedule

Starting date: 01/05/2022 (M1)

Expected ending date: 31/10/2025 (M42)

Cost:

Expected PM for the fourth year of the project: 43 PM

Expected ODC for the fourth year of the project: 1 500 €

P7.2.2.b_Y1_HBMdatasets_VITO

Project Title	FAIR and sustainable storage of human biomonitoring (HBM) datasets		
Project Acronym (15 letters max)	HBMdatasets		
Project Manager	Eva Govarts eva.govarts@vito.be	VITO	Belgium
Deputy Project manager	Dirk Devriendt Dirk.devriendt.ext@vito.be	VITO	Belgium
Expected starting date PARC (Month number)	1	Expected duration	48*
PARC Workpackage number	7	PARC Task/Activity/Sub-activity:	7.2.2
Project Id	P7.2.2.b_Y1_HBMdatasets_VITO		

*The project has been extended from M42 to M48

Status: Implementation

Summary of the project

This project deals with availability and (re)use of existing HBM datasets (including datasets from HBM4EU, but also datasets produced in other projects), as well as with new datasets generated in PARC

(i.e., in Task 4.1). HBM dataset will be made available as FAIR datasets for potential reuse by the broad RA community. HBM datasets are challenging for reuse as they contain personal, sensitive data, which poses specific challenges for storage and reuse, related to ethical and legal issues. The full strength of the data for scientific and regulatory purposes will only be attained if analyses can be carried out on the individual data, if the coherence of the dataset is maintained, and if the data can be linked to different domains (e.g., health, biomolecular, spatial-environmental data, food, consumption, occupational). Finally, HBM datasets contain analyses of chemical metabolites for which no standardized identifications exist.

HBM datasets will be made available to allow reuse by different user groups: scientific users who may want to reuse the entire datasets (for research questions on exposure determinants, geographical comparisons, time trends, exposure-effect analyses, link with environmental sources, ..., comparing modelled exposure with observed exposure), regulatory users who may be interested in the core occurrence data (for assessment and follow-up, integration of HBM data in models and toolboxes), and the general public. As such this project indirectly supports multiple regulatory processes and frameworks through support for improved human RA, and for reuse of data and knowledge.

The broader relevance of the project lies in the development and implementation of scalable solutions for reuse of personal sensitive data while safeguarding legal and ethical constraints, including cross-domain linking of data, semantic and technical interoperability, and development and implementation of cross-domain ontologies, vocabularies and metadata schemes.

The project will be strongly aligned with Task 4.1, and more specifically with Task 4.1.5 as part of a sustainable HBM system.

Methodologically the project will investigate the feasibility to make use new developments in federated data infrastructures and federated data analysis. These methods are still in an early phase.

Main expected outputs of the project

- Short-term operational data infrastructure for exchange of HBM data between PARC partners
- Hybrid federated data infrastructure allowing
 - Reuse of HBM datasets by *new parties* while respecting privacy and consent
 - New data collected in PARC
 - New PARC partners working with the data
 - Integration with *external HBM datasets* from other projects (e.g. EHEN projects)
 - Federated data analysis
- Metadata, schema mappings and search engines to increase *findability and interoperability* across disciplines (health, biomolecular, lifestyle, ...) for cross-domain linking
- Identification scheme for metabolites linking metabolites and parent chemicals

Outcomes and impacts expected for end-users and stakeholders

Facilitated access and reuse of both (individual) HBM datasets and core HBM (occurrence) data by researchers and risks assessors

Regulatory agencies improve human RA

Decision makers evaluate effectiveness of adopted regulatory measures (Chemicals policy)

Researchers make new generation RA tools and models available

Key words: human biomonitoring, FAIR data, personal sensitive data, federated data analysis, metadata schemas, ontologies

Link to the PARC DoA

The project supports the achievement and is closely aligned with PARC OO10 It aims for an effective exchange of reliable, relevant, curated, and FAIR HBM data between different stakeholders and policy domains (in line with the European Strategy for Data). FAIR data solutions for sensitive data will support the development of monitoring capacity (OO8). Via mapping the existing data landscape and developing tailored solutions for data re(use) and the implementation of FAIR principles, the chemical RA community in PARC and beyond will increasingly reuse HBM data for application and innovation in RA (OO9). OO13

will be supported through training on FAIR data principles, practices and data stewardship for participants.

Links within PARC (WPs/Tasks/Activities/Projects)

The project is obviously strongly related with Task 4.1 and more specifically 4.1.4 and 4.1.5, with Task 6.2 for linking predicted exposure to observed exposure, with Task 8.3 for integrating HBM data in the modelling toolbox, and with Task 2.2 (data layer of PARCopedia).

WP3: a strategy will be developed on communication and awareness on FAIR data, both in general and in specific communities. This project will benefit from organisation of synergy networks and networking events. Collaboration on these aspects will be discussed with WP3.

Internally in WP7 the project will exchange with Task 7.1 on data policies, and on training and awareness on FAIR data, and with Task 7.3 for exploration of novel approaches towards enhanced privacy preservation for personal sensitive data (e.g., federated data analysis).

WP9 will be involved for the inventory of HBM projects and datasets, and for collaboration on training and awareness on FAIR data.

Links outside PARC

The project will start from the achievements of HBM4EU. It will link with other initiatives that are working on similar data, such as the EHEN, EOSC-Life, EIRENE RI, and on generic metadata schemas and ontologies, such as HL7, Bioschemas, Research Data alliance (RDA), Observational Health Data Sciences and Informatics (OHDSI). It will align with the EC's roadmap and activities towards a Common Open Platform on Chemicals data, and i.e., with IPCHEM's activities on HBM data.

Key PARC Deliverables and Milestones to which the project contributes

D7.2. PARC FAIR data policy (PFDP) (delivered). This project contributed to the FAIR methodology as well as the privacy related aspects of the PFDP.

D7.3. 1st report on Data infrastructure, tools and services for FAIRification and reuse of chemical RA data (M36)

D7.5. 1st review of the Data Management Plan (DMP) (M42)

MS11. Network of trained FAIR data stewards (delivered)

MS12. Architecture of PARC FAIR data hub & its integration with the COPCSD (delivered)

Partners List:

VITO (BE); MU (CZ); UU (SW); UBA (DE); ISSEP (BE); JSI (Slovenia), WR (NL)

Schedule:

Starting date: 01/05/2022 (M1)

Expected ending date: 30/04/2026 (M48)

Cost:

Expected PM for the fourth year of the project: 39 PM

Expected ODC for the fourth year of the project: 3 975 €

A7.2.3 Solutions for FAIR data: development and implementation

No project submitted at present.

A7.2.4 Standards and harmonisation

No project submitted at present.

T7.3 Innovative analyses – 1 PROJECT

Innovative analytical approaches to maximise use and insights from increasing amounts of open and FAIR data for RA will be introduced. Promising approaches will be applied to use cases, selected together with WPs 4-8, to evaluate and showcase their usefulness. A range of advanced approaches will be developed

and documented, including pooling and meta-analysis of heterogeneous datasets, uncertainty analysis, and knowledge and text mining via on-the-fly ontological mapping, Bayesian networks, ML and other approaches. Analytical tools will be made available as FAIR algorithms and supplied to WPs 4-8 for use and integration into toolboxes. Good practice guidelines describing the approaches and their applications for regulatory RA will be published.

A7.3.1 Innovative methods for combined analyses of FAIR (heterogeneous) data

No project submitted at present.

A7.3.2 Methods for uncertainty characterisation, propagation and quantification as a basis for harmonisation in RA

No project submitted at present.

A7.3.3 Novel computational methods for integrating and extracting knowledge from non-structured data – 1 PROJECT

P7.3.3.a_Y1_ALT-IST_IISPV

Project Title	AI, text mining and ontology-assisted hazard identification and risk assessment (OnTextTox)		
Project Acronym (15 letters max)	ALT-IST		
Project Manager	Vikas Kumar Vikas.kumar@iispv.cat	IISPV	ES
Deputy Project manager	Karin Slater k.slater@bham.ac.uk	UoB	UK
Expected starting date PARC (Month number)	1	Expected duration	60
PARC Workpackage number	7	PARC Task/Activity/Sub-activity:	7.3.3
Project Id	P7.3.3.a_Y1_ALT-IST_IISPV		

Status: Implementation

Summary of the project

The ALT-IST project is a part of T7.3. It involves the development of an ontology-based text-mining and data integration scheme for the classification and storage of information about chemical hazards and RA. Followed up by the development of tools using the database of RA. Several regulatory agencies such as OECD, EFSA and ECHA have adopted evidence-based methodologies for RA i.e. AOP. The utmost requirement for developing this mechanistic pathway is data. The well-curated, connected, structured and unambiguous database will ease the accessibility of information and also compliments AOP development by filling experimental data gaps. Ontology-based data integration will further help toward the broader application of Advance data science including network biology and ML to predict the chemical adverse effect on the human system. The developed tools and methodologies will be validated by real case studies selected in collaboration with other WPs (WP4, WP5, WP6). Project will explore different text mining tools (e.g. Integrated Network and Dynamical Reasoning Assembler (INDRA), TRIPS or other tools) during scoping study to understand its usability and set the agenda for future research needs. Aside the application in developing (quantitative) AOPs and supporting network biology approaches to identify and describe hazards in relation to disease development (i.e. AOP), other applications of AI, network approaches, text mining and ontology assisted hazard identification are foreseen as well. These, to accommodate the need for the faster detection of potential emerging risks from imported goods/chemicals into the EU, as well as

the identification of data gaps within heterogeneous hazard data sources to help the further prioritization of testing.

Main expected outputs of the project

This project will deliver an ontology-based text-mining and data integration scheme for the classification and storage of information about chemical hazards and RA. Linked case studies with WP5 and WP6 will establish NAM for RA using new data discovery and integration of other available data and the data developed in different work packages. This will involve ontology-based data curation and its automated maintenance using NLP (Natural language processing). In addition, developed ontology will assist the further development of qAOP in collaboration with different partners.

Outcomes and impacts expected for end-users and stakeholders

This project is designed according to the perspective of a computational toxicologist, epidemiologists and risk assessor because it introduces a novel *in-silico* approach toward defining associations between human health outcomes and exposure to chemicals through the integrated use of advanced analytical and predictive tools for hazard and RA and chemical screening for regulatory purposes. It will employ natural language processing, cheminformatics and bioinformatics techniques directly to the data mining of the integrated data set which will lead to the advancement of *in-silico* methodologies for OECD's IATA and support the 3R strategy of chemical testing.

Key words:

Ontology, Text mining, Artificial intelligence, Natural Language Processing, System toxicology

Link to the PARC DoA

The project will mainly contribute to the PARC OO9, OO10, and OO12 by developing and implementing R&I work programmes for new *in silico* tools and generating results and knowledge (data discovery from text mining) to support the use of new approaches and methods (AI assisted text mining), develop models and innovative concept for RA (predictive AI models) to facilitate the acceptance and use of PARC results in regulatory RA processes. The project will also contribute to the PARC OOs by providing input to priority-setting (OO3), facilitate PARC wide collaboration with different case studies and promoting cooperation with other R&I initiatives (OO5), communicate and disseminate results (OO6) and implement FAIR data practices to enable open science (OO10).

Links within PARC (WPs/Tasks/Activities/Projects)

Task 5.3.2: AOP developed in 5.3.2 can be used as case study and data generated in this project can help in developing AOPs

Task 6.1: data generated in this project can help in the development of qAOPs and IATA.

Task 6.2: mixture effects can be quantitatively addressed through targeted data mining and network modelling

WP8: SysTox bioinformatics tools can be integrated in the toolbox

WP9: training of informatics tools for regulators

Links outside PARC

Relevant text mining AI data initiatives (ELIXIR, Bio.Tools). Furthermore, the project is closely linked to other EU project in similar domain like EU-ToxRisk, RISK-HUNT3R, ONTOX and PrecisionTox, and to work ongoing at OECD in relation to AOP development (OECD AOP programme) and IATA case studies. As such, regular interactions with the OECD EAGMST and the OECD WPHA are foreseen.

Key PARC Deliverables (or Additional Deliverables) and Milestones to which the project contributes

D7.4: 1st Evaluation of innovative analytical approaches and uncertainty approaches for introduction in chemical RA (M36)

Partners List:

IISPV (ES), UoB (UK), ANSES (FR), INSERM (FR), JSI (SI), AUTH (GR), MU (CH), UL-LACDR (NL), KI (SE), NIVA (NO), WR (NL)

Schedule:

Starting date: 01/05/2022 (M1)

Expected ending date: 30/04/2027 (M60)

Cost:

Expected PM for the fourth year of the project: 30 PM

Expected ODC for the fourth year of the project: 15 137 €

A7.3.4 Identify additional needs in PARC for innovative analyses and promising evolutions in the data science landscape, and translate them in use cases for evaluation

No project submitted at present.

List of Project Reports, Project Key Landmarks and Deliverables, Additional deliverables, Milestones to which the projects contribute

Only Deliverables and Additional Deliverables are official documents to be submitted to HaDEA. Project reports and key landmarks correspond to intermediate or significant stage in the development of the scientific results of the projects that will be part of the annual **Additional Deliverables** or **Deliverables**. Additional Deliverables and Deliverables that have been approved by HaDEA are available on the PARC website: [Deliverables](#) | [Parc](#)

Glossary:

D = Deliverable

AD = Additional deliverable

M = Milestone

R = Project Report

L = Project Key Landmark

In grey, D/AD/M/R/L achieved

In pink, Projects starting Y1 (M1)

In yellow, Projects starting Y2 (M13)

In blue, Projects starting Y3 (M25)

In green, Projects starting Y4 (M37)

WP2

Project ID	Project end	D_AD_M-R_L number	Title	Partner Responsible	Expected delivery date	Achievement date
P2.1.a	76	R1_MnHexP-RRM	First data for regulatory agencies	UBA	M35	
P2.1.a	76	R2_MnHexP-RRM	Interim report	UBA	M48	
P2.1.a	76	R3_MnHexP-RRM	End of project combination of data sets (final project report)	UBA	M76	
P2.1.a	76	AD2.2	AD2.2. RRM DnHExP	UBA	M76	

WP4

Project ID	Project end	D_AD_M-R_L number	Title	Partner Responsible	Expected delivery date	Achievement date
P4.1.1.2.a	81	R1_GenHBMSurvey	First interim progress report (postponed from M18 to M23)	VITO	M23	M24
P4.1.1.2.a	81	R2_GenHBMSurvey	Second interim progress report	VITO	M42	
P4.1.1.2.a	81	R3_GenHBMSurvey	Third interim progress report	VITO	M66	
P4.1.1.2.a	81	R4_GenHBMSurvey	Final report	VITO	M81	

P4.1.1.2.a	81	D4.3	D4.3. 1st Progress report on the general survey	VITO	M36	
P4.1.1.2.a	81	D4.8	D4.8. 2nd Progress report on the general survey	VITO	M48	
P4.1.1.2.a	81	D4.12	D4.12. 3rd Progress report on the general survey	UBA	M60	
P4.1.1.2.a	81	D4.13	D4.13. Concluding report summarizing the outcome of all studies for a future monitoring approach	INERIS	M81	
P4.1.1.3.a	81	R1_PFAS_mother_milk	Study implementation plan	BPI	M48	
P4.1.1.3.a	81	R2_PFAS_mother_milk	Statistical analysis and data management plan	LNS, BPI	M60	
P4.1.1.3.a	81	R3_PFAS_mother_milk	Project progress report	BPI, LNS	M70	
P4.1.1.3.a	81	D4.6	D4.6. 1st Progress report on targeted surveys	VITO	M48	
P4.1.1.3.a	81	D4.15	D4.15. 2nd Progress report on targeted surveys	VITO	M81	
P4.1.1.3.b	81	R1_PFASChildren	Peer reviewed scientific article for PFAS levels of exposure description among European Children and determinants of exposure	SpF	M81	
P4.1.1.3.b	81	R2_PFASChildren	Peer reviewed scientific article for development of NTS methods for PFAS measurement in serum	ONIRIS, SpF	M81	
P4.1.1.3.b	81	D4.6	D4.6. 1st Progress report on targeted surveys	VITO	M48	
P4.1.1.3.b	81	D4.15	D4.15. 2nd Progress report on targeted surveys	VITO	M81	
P4.1.1.3.c	72	R1_Time Pattern	Statistical Analysis Plan updated	VITO	M56	
P4.1.1.3.c	72	R1_Time Pattern	Final report	VITO	M72	
P4.1.1.3.c	72	D7.1	D7.1 Data management plan	TNO	M6	M6
P4.1.1.4.a	48 29	AD4.8	AD4.8. Report on the occupational exposure in general population surveys: analysis of existing data and recommendations for future general population studies (postponed from M18 to M34)	TTL	M34	
P4.1.1.4.b	84 36	R_SentinelSystem	Mapping and preparation of proof-of-concept	KULeuven	M36	
P4.1.1.4.b	84 36	D4.13	D4.13. Concluding report summarizing the outcome of all studies for a future monitoring approach	INERIS	M81	
P4.1.1.4.c	48	L1_HealthCareSurvey	Study protocol	RUMC	M12	M14
P4.1.1.4.c	48	L1_HealthCareSurvey	Ethical applications (M12-M18, delayed M18-26), Ethical permissions (M26-M34)	RUMC	M34	
P4.1.1.4.c	48	D4.7	D4.7. 1st Progress report on occupational surveys.	TTL	M48	
P4.1.1.4.d	48	D4.7	D4.7. 1st Progress report on occupational surveys.	TTL	M48	

P4.1.3.1.a	36 81	R1_DerivationofHBM-GVs	Substance dossier on UV filter Uvinul A plus and HBM-GVs for the general population, coordinated at project level (postponed from M24 to M36)	UBA	M36	
P4.1.3.1.a	36 81	R2_DerivationofHBM-GVs	Substance dossier on Cyhalothrin (pyrethroid) and proposal of HBM-GVs for the general population, coordinated at project level (postponed from M24 to M36)	UBA, Unisanté	M36	
P4.1.3.1.a	36 81	R3_DerivationofHBM-GVs	Chromium VI - Derivation of further HBM-EECRs	TTL, RUMC, Unisante, SECO	M36	
P4.1.3.1.a	36 81	R4_DerivationofHBM-GVs	Substance dossier on nickel and derivation of HBM-GVs for the general population and for workers	TTL	M36	
P4.1.3.1.a	36 81	R5_DerivationofHBM-GVs	Substance dossier on DEHTP and derivation of HBM-GVs for the general population	UBA	M36	
P4.1.3.1.a	36 81	R6_DerivationofHBM-GVs	Substance dossier on DINP and derivation of HBM-GVs for the general population	UBA	M36	
P4.1.3.1.a	36 81	R7_DerivationofHBM-GVs	Substance dossier on aluminium and compounds and HBM-GVs for the general population and workers (postponed from M24 to M36)	ANSES	M36	
P4.1.3.1.a	36 81	R8_DerivationofHBM-GVs	Substance dossier on benzophenone-3 and derivation of HBM-GVs for the general population	UBA	M36	
P4.1.3.1.a	36 81	R9_DerivationofHBM-GVs	Substance dossier on acetamiprid and derivation of HBM-GVs for the general population	UBA	M36	
P4.1.3.1.a	36 81	R10_DerivationofHBM-GVs	Substance dossier on imidacloprid and derivation of HBM-GVs for the general population	UBA	M36	
P4.1.3.1.a	36 81	R11_DerivationofHBM-GVs	Update mercury – HBM-GVs	NIPH-FHI, TTL	M36	
P4.1.3.1.a	36 81	R12_DerivationofHBM-GVs	PFAS - scoping review, HBM-GVs for individual PFAS, if applicable	MOH-IL, NIPH-FHI, LNS	M36	
P4.1.3.1.a	36 81	R13_DerivationofHBM-GVs	Substance dossier on arsenic and derivation of HBM guide values for the general population and for workers	ANSES	M36	
P4.1.3.1.a	36 81	R14_DerivationofHBM-GVs	Derivation of HBM-GVs for the pyrethroid metabolites cis and trans DCCA for the general population and for workers	ANSES	M37 to M48	
P4.1.3.1.a	36 81	R15_DerivationofHBM-GVs	Derivation of HBM-GVs for the pyrethroid's metabolites cis and trans DCCA (for the general population and workers), continuation of work started in the first project part	ANSES	M45	
P4.1.3.1.a	36 81	R16_DerivationofHBM-GVs	Derivation of HBM-GV for prioritised phthalate or phthalate substitute (general population)	UBA	M48	
P4.1.3.1.a	36 81	R17_DerivationofHBM-GVs	Derivation of HBM-GVs for Lithium (general population and workers)	ANSES	M48	
P4.1.3.1.a	36 81	R18_DerivationofHBM-GVs	Derivation of HBM-GV for cobalt (for workers)	TTL	M54	
P4.1.3.1.a	36 81	R19_DerivationofHBM-GVs	Update of HBM-GV for bisphenol A	UBA	M54	
P4.1.3.1.a	36 81	R20_DerivationofHBM-GVs	Derivation of HBM-GVs for manganese (general population and workers)	ANSES	M54	
P4.1.3.1.a	36 81	R21_DerivationofHBM-GVs	Derivation of HBM-GV for insecticide chlorpyrifos (general population)	UBA	M60	
P4.1.3.1.a	36 81	R22_DerivationofHBM-GVs	Derivation of HBM-GVs for platinum (for workers)	TTL	M66	
P4.1.3.1.a	36 81	R23_DerivationofHBM-GVs	Derivation of HBM-GVs for pyrethroid's metabolite 3-PBA (for workers)	TTL and further partner tbd	M72	

P4.1.3.1.a	36 81	R24_DerivationofHBM-GVs	Derivation of HBM-GVs or other assessment tools for PFAS in body fluids	LNS, MOH-IL, NIPH;	M76	
P4.1.3.1.a	36 81	R25_DerivationofHBM-GVs	Further HBM-GVs according prioritisation, available inhouse-expertise, and available PMs	tbd	M81	
P4.1.3.1.a	36 81	AD4.3	AD4.3. Derivation of HBM-GVs (postponed from M12 to M36) ((will include all reports with submission date until M36)	UBA	M36	
P4.1.3.1.a	36 81	AD4.15	AD4.15. Derivation of HBM-GVs/ HBM-EECRs – second set of toxicological assessment values (will include all reports with submission date until M60)	UBA	M60	
P4.1.3.1.a	36 81	AD4.17	AD4.17. Derivation of HBM-GVs/ HBM-EECRs – third set of toxicological assessment values (will include all reports with submission date until M81)	UBA	M81	
P4.1.3.1.b	81	R1-Health-based-IA-GV_LNS	Report on the methodology to derive IA-GV	LNS, tbd	M50	
P4.1.3.1.b	81	R2-Health-based-IA-GV_LNS	Substance dossiers and derivation of IA-GV for general population	All partners	M64	
P4.1.3.1.b	81	R3-Health-based-IA-GV_LNS	Substance dossiers and derivation of IA-GV for general population	All partners	M78	
P4.1.3.1.b	81	R4-Health-based-IA-GV_LNS	Inventory of IA-GV	All partners	M78	
P4.1.3.1.b	81	AD4.18	AD4.18. Derivation of IA-GV	LNS, NCPHP (support all partners)	M81	
P4.1.3.3.a	52	R1_RoadmapLinkingHBMhealth	Scoping document of a list of health measurements to be included in the HBM/HES surveys including Standardized procedures and materials for collecting health, dietary and occupational data	SpF	M14	M14
P4.1.3.3.a	52	R2_RoadmapLinkingHBMhealth	Effect biomarker implementation plan for PARC general and occupational surveys	VITO	M12	M13
P4.1.3.3.a	52	R3_RoadmapLinkingHBMhealth	Progress report on investigation of the links between exposure and adverse health outcomes, from analyses of biobanked samples within Health examination cohorts (postponed from M24 to M34)	SpF	M34	
P4.1.3.3.a	52	R4_RoadmapLinkingHBMhealth	Roadmap for exploration of the links between HBM data and existing health outcome	SpF & VITO	M52	
P4.1.3.3.a	52	MS10	MS10 Finalisation of study design for the HBM surveys	VITO	M12	M13
P4.1.3.3.a	52	AD4.1	AD4.1. Periodic report on available supporting materials for HBM studies (postponed from M12 to M14)	SPF	M14	M16
P4.1.3.3.a	52	AD4.2	AD4.2 Periodic report on analytical methods and measurements for exposure and effect biomarkers (postponed from M12 to M36)	ISCHH	M36	Cancelled
P4.1.3.3.a	52	D4.3	D4.3. 1st Progress report on the general survey	VITO	M36	
P4.1.3.3.a	52	D4.8	D4.8. 2nd Progress report on the general survey	VITO	M48	
P4.1.3.3.a	52	D4.12	D4.12. 3rd Progress report on the general survey	UBA	M60	
P4.1.3.3.a	52	D2.22	D2.22. 2nd PARC sustainability report	INSERM	M81	
P4.1.4.2.a	36 48	R1_DataAnalysisHBM4EU	Statistical analysis plan	VITO	M18	M19
P4.1.4.2.a	36 48	L1_DataAnalysisHBM4EU	Access to the HBM4EU data is granted	VITO	M14	M14

P4.1.4.2.a	36 48	D7.1	D7.1 Data management plan	TNO	M6	M6
P4.1.4.2.a	36 48	MS7	MS7 Establishment of working groups	ANSES	M12	M11
P4.1.4.2.a	36 48	AD4.11	AD4.11. Progress report statistical analyses (postponed from M36 to M48)	VITO	M48	
P4.1.5.a	66	R1_SustainHBMSystem	1st Interim progress report (postponed from M24 to M36)	VITO	M36	
P4.1.5.a	66	R2_SustainHBMSystem	2nd interim progress report	VITO	M48	
P4.1.5.a	66	R3_SustainHBMSystem	Final report	VITO	M66	
P4.1.5.a	66	D2.22	D2.22. 2nd PARC sustainability report	INSERM	M81	
P4.2.a	36 42	R1_ENVMonitoringPilotSurvey	Final report on on-going projects	INERIS/AU	M42	
P4.2.a	36 42	AD4.5	AD4.5. Technical specifications of the study (project design, hypothesis and research question as well as analytical procedures including QA/QC and data flows) (postponed from M12 to M14)	INERIS, AU	M14	M17
P4.2.a	36 42	AD4.4	AD4.4 Procedures for agreement on transparent use of existing data, access to samples and involvement of external laboratories (M12) (postponed from M12 to M24)	INERIS, AU	M24	Cancelled
P4.2.a	36 42	D4.4	D4.4. 1st Progress report on on-going monitoring projects (postponed from M36 to M42)	AU	M42	
P4.2.b	30 36	R1_Monitoringframe	Final project report (PR) (postponed from M30 to M36)	AU/INERIS	M36	
P4.2.b	34 36	D4.1	D4.1. Description of a mechanism for selection of chemicals / matrices / endpoints for projects (postponed from M20 to M22)	INERIS	M22	M25
P4.2.b	32 36	AD4.9	AD4.9. Final report on the prioritization project (postponed from M34 to M36)	AU/INERIS	M36	Cancelled (see D4.4)
P4.2.b	32 36	D4.4	D4.4. 1st Progress report on on-going monitoring projects (postponed from M36 to M42)	AU	M42	
P4.2.c	72	R1_Human exposure	Workshop report (postponed from M30 to M33)	LNS, CSBT, AU, INERIS	M33	M33
P4.2.c	72	R2_Human exposure	Description of the study concept	LNS, CSBT, AU, INERIS	M36	
P4.2.c	72	R3_Human exposure	Progress report	LNS, CSBT, AU, INERIS	M50	
P4.2.c	72	R4_Human exposure	Project report	LNS, CSBT, AU, INERIS	M72	
P4.2.c	72	AD4.10	AD4.10. Description of the study concept	AU/INERIS/LNS/CSBT	M36	Cancelled (see D4.4)
P4.2.c	72	D4.4	D4.4. 1st Progress report on on-going monitoring projects (postponed from M36 to M42)	AU	M42	
P4.2.c	72	AD4.16	AD4.16. Project report	AU/INERIS/LNS/CSBT	M72	
P4.2.d	60	R1_Siloxanes	Review of existing data and methods for CVMS and LVMS in the environment, results from initial tests, critical discussion of the feasibility of chemical analyses based on project-derived performance	AU	M47	

			indicators and conclusion if an environmental monitoring campaign should be started.			
P4.2.d	60	R2_Siloxanes	Protocols for sampling and chemical analysis of CVMS and LVMS, incl. QA/QC concept	IVL	M50	
P4.2.d	60	AD4.14	AD4.14. Project report	INERIS	M60	
P4.3.1.a	12	R1_T01-Concept Paper	Common definitions for NTA/EDA approaches	MU	M12	M14
P4.3.1.a	12	AD4.6	AD4.6 Concept paper regarding common definitions and short to medium term support to policy objectives of innovative (self-) sampling, suspect screening and NTA/EDA approaches - M12 (postponed from M12 to M14)	INRAE, VUA	M14	M16
P4.3.1.b	36 60	R1_T02-QAQC	Protocol/guidances for QA/QC in suspect and non-target screening methods (postponed from M36 to M48)	WR	M48	
P4.3.1.b	36 60	R2_T02-QAQC	Protocol/guidances for normalisation/semi-quantification of results in suspect and non-targeted screening to improve comparability of results between studies/laboratories	WR	M60	
P4.3.1.b	36 60	R3_T02-QAQC	Inventory of existing QA/QC procedures and guidelines in bioeffect assays/EDA	WR	M60	
P4.3.1.b	36 60	MS7	MS7 Establishment of working groups	ANSES	M12	M11
P4.3.1.b	36 60	AD4.5	AD4.5 Technical specifications of the study (project design, hypothesis and research question as well as analytical procedures including QA/QC and data flows) (postponed from M12 to M14)	INERIS, AU	M14	M17
P4.3.1.b	36 60	AD4.12	AD4.12. General guideline for QA/QC in non-target screening	WR	M60	
P4.3.1.c	60	D4.10	D4.10. 3rd Proof-of-concept assessing the usefulness of innovative (self-) sampling combined with integrated suspect/NTS/EDA approaches	VUA/SLU	M60	
P4.3.1.d	60	R1_T04-Data Processing Workflow	Report on the Establishment of necessary advanced data processing methodologies and bioinformatic tools for NTS – EHESP	EHESP	M60	
P4.3.1.d	60	D4.9	D4.9 Workflow for data processing and annotation of HRMS based chemical profiles generated from suspect/NTS approaches (e.g. inspired from W4M/Galaxy)	INRAE	M54	
P4.3.2.a	48	D.4.5	D4.5. 2nd Proof-of-concept illustrating the usefulness of innovative (self-)sampling combined with integrated suspect/NTS/EDA approaches as a contribution to early warning system and risk assessment for human monitoring	INRAE	M48	
P4.3.2.b	60	L1_Occupational exposure	Refined study design of case studies co-built and completed with all involved partners	INRS	M24	M26
P4.3.2.b	60	L2_Occupational exposure	Sample sourcing and sharing completed (postponed from M30 to M42)	INRS	M42	
P4.3.2.b	60	L3_Occupational exposure	At least 50% of planned analyses completed	INRS	M48	
P4.3.2.b	60	L4_Occupational exposure	All planned analyses completed and data processing on-track	INRS	M60	
P4.3.2.b	60	L5_Occupational exposure	Identification of emerging chemicals and contribution to the prioritisation process of chemicals of interest	INRS	M60	
P4.3.2.b	60	D4.10	D4.10. 3rd Proof-of-concept assessing the usefulness of innovative (self-) sampling combined with integrated suspect/NTS/EDA approaches	VUA/SLU	M60	
P4.3.2.c	72	R1_Complementary developments	Report on the development of complementary approaches/matrices for application in HBM surveys	JSI and UAntwerpen with the	M49	

				contribution of all partners		
P4.3.2.c	72	R2_Complementary developments	Report on the application of the complementary approaches/matrices to real samples from HBM surveys as a contribution to early warning system and risk assessment for human monitoring	JSI and UAntwerpen with the contribution of all partners	M70	
P4.3.2.c	72	AD4.13	AD4.13. Proof-of-concept on the application of the complementary approaches/matrices to real samples from HBM surveys	JSI and UAntwerpen with the contribution of all partners	M70	
P4.3.3.a	36 48	R1_E01-Wastewater based epidemiology	Final report (postponed from M36 to M48)	UFZ	M48	
P4.3.3.a	36 48	D4.2	D4.2. 1st Proof-of-concept illustrating the usefulness of innovative (self-) sampling combined with integrated suspect/NTS/EDA approaches as a contribution to early warning system and risk assessment for environmental monitoring (postponed from M35 to M48)	VUA	M48	
P4.3.3.b	60	R1_E02-Sentinel animals	Report on the application of innovative methods combined with suspect/NTS/EDA approaches for animal sentinel species	ONIRIS	M60	
P4.3.3.b	60	D4.14	D4.14. Final report on the application of new exposure assessment approaches (i.e. from sampling to data interpretation) to support regulatory needs (i.e. lessons learnt and conclusions/perspective for sustainable follow-up)	INRAE	M81	
P4.3.4.a	48	R1_F02-Food items exposure	Final report on the application of the developed suspect screening/NTS/EDA approaches to real samples originated from food survey designed by other PARC components	ANSES	M48	
P4.3.4.a	48	D4.10	D4.10. 3rd Proof-of-concept assessing the usefulness of innovative (self-) sampling combined with integrated suspect/NTS/EDA approaches	VUA/SLU	M60	

WP5

Project ID	Project end	D_AD_M-R_L number	Title	Partner Responsible	Expected delivery date	Achievement date
P5.1.1.a	36 48	R1_Toxins_BfR	Submission of two review papers on Enniatins and Alternaria toxins addressing the relevant endpoints of the project	UNIVIE, BfR	M11 (Alternaria), M13 (Enniatins)	M20 (Alternaria, published), M22 (Enniatins, finalised)
P5.1.1.a	36 48	R2_Toxins_BfR	Reports available with data generated (postponed from M36 to M48)	UNIVIE, BfR	M48	
P5.1.1.a	36 48	L1_Toxins_BfR	First test item available to start experimental studies	BfR	M13	M13
P5.1.1.a	36 48	D5.1	D5.1. 1st NAMs Report (postponed from M18 to M22)	BfR	M22	M23
P5.1.1.a	36 48	D5.3	D5.3. 1st new AOPs Report	INSERM	M24	M26
P5.1.1.a	36 48	D5.4	D5.4. 1st Closing data Gaps Report	ANSES	M36	
P5.1.1.a	36 48	D5.11	D5.11. 2nd closing data gaps report (has been shifted from M60 to M54)	ANSES, BfR	M54	

P5.1.1.b	36 54	R1_BPA_HumTox	Closing data gaps report: Gathering the data obtained within this project with the contribution from each one of the five mentioned endpoints.	BfR	M36	
P5.1.1.b	36 54	AD5.1	AD5.1. Report on the workshop organised with national and EU agencies (ECHA and EFSA) and stakeholders on the of-concern bisphenol A (BPA) alternatives.	BPI, MU	M9	M10
P5.1.1.b	36 54	D5.1	D5.1. 1st NAMs Report (postponed from M18 to M22)	BfR	M22	M23
P5.1.1.b	36 54	D5.3	D5.3. 1st new AOPs report	INSERM	M24	M26
P5.1.1.b	36 54	D5.4	D5.4. 1st closing data gaps report	ANSES	M36	
P5.1.1.b	36 54	D5.11	D5.11. 2nd closing data gaps report (has been shifted from M60 to M54)	ANSES, BfR	M54	
P5.1.1.c	60	R1_TG+ EnnB1	Protocols	ANSES	M38	
P5.1.1.c	60	R1_TG+ EnnB1	Study report	ANSES	tbd	
P5.1.1.c	60	D5.4	D5.4. 1st closing data gaps report	ANSES	M36	
P5.1.1.c	60	AD5.8	AD5.8. Study report	ANSES	M41	
P5.1.1.c	60	D5.5	D5.5. 2nd NAMs report (postponed from M36 to M48)	BfR	M48	
P5.1.1.c	60	D5.8	D5.8. 3rd New approach methodologies report	BfR	M60	
P5.1.1.c	60	D5.11	D5.11. 2nd closing data gaps report (has been shifted from M60 to M54)	ANSES, BfR	M54	
P5.1.1.d	81	R1_PlasticLeach	Hazard ranking of leachates from various plastic types tested	tbd	M68	
P5.1.1.d	81	R2_PlasticLeach	The most hazardous chemicals identified in leachates from plastics tested	tbd	M81	
P5.1.1.d	81	D5.11	D5.11. 2nd closing data gaps report (has been shifted from M60 to M54)	ANSES, BfR	M54	
P5.1.1.d	81	D5.15	D5.15. 3rd closing data gaps report	ANSES, BfR	M81	
P5.1.2.a	36	R1_NaturalToxinsAqua	Ecotoxicity data for Lymnaea for single toxins	SLU	M24	M26
P5.1.2.a	36	R2_NaturalToxinsAqua	Ecotoxicity data for Daphnia/marine copepods for single toxins	UGent	M24	M26
P5.1.2.a	36	R3_NaturalToxinsAqua	Ecotoxicity data for Lymnaea for mixtures of toxins	SLU	M36	
P5.1.2.a	36	R4_NaturalToxinsAqua	Ecotoxicity data for Daphnia/marine copepods for mixtures of toxins	UGent	M36	
P5.1.2.a	36	R5_NaturalToxinsAqua	Ecotoxicity data for Chlorella vulgaris for single toxins	UAVR	M24	M27
P5.1.2.a	36	R6_NaturalToxinsAqua	Ecotoxicity data for Chlorella vulgaris for mixture of toxins and toxins with other chemicals	UAVR	M36	
P5.1.2.a	36	D5.4	D5.4. 1st closing data gaps report	ANSES	M36	

P5.1.2.b	42 48	R1_BPAalternatives	Progress report - advancing NAMs for the assessment of chemical mixtures including BPA alternatives (relevant for activities iii, iv and v) (postponed from M12 to M22)	MU	M22	see D5.1 (M22)
P5.1.2.b	42 48	R2_BPAalternatives	Report on the results of toxicity assessment of BPA alternatives single compounds & mixtures (selected based on available existing data) on different organisms (relevant for activities i & ii). (postponed from M24 to M35)	BPI	M35	
P5.1.2.b	42 48	R3_BPAalternatives	Progress report - advancing NAMs for the assessment of chemical mixtures including BPA alternatives (relevant for activities iii, iv and v).	MU	M42	
P5.1.2.b	42 48	R4_BPAalternatives	Report on the results of toxicity assessment of BPA alternatives single compounds & mixtures (selected based on available existing data) on different organisms (relevant for activities i & ii).	BPI	M42	
P5.1.2.b	42 48	L1_BPAalternatives	Selection of the compounds and mixtures to be tested based on available existing data and discussion among partners / stakeholders	BPI	M9	M9
P5.1.2.b	42 48	L3_BPAalternatives	Selection of the compounds and mixtures to be tested based on PARC environmental monitoring data (postponed from M30 to M34)	BPI	M34	
P5.1.2.b	42 48	AD5.1	AD5.1. Report on the workshop organised with national and EU agencies (ECHA and EFSA) and stakeholders on the of-concern bisphenol A (BPA) alternatives.	BPI, MU	M9	M10
P5.1.2.b	42 48	AD5.3	AD5.3 List of first assays to be developed for prioritised endpoints (postponed from M12 to M18)	DTU, VUB	M18	M18
P5.1.2.b	42 48	D5.1	D5.1. 1st NAMs Report (postponed from M18 to M22)	BfR	M22	M23
P5.1.2.b	42 48	D5.4	D5.4. 1st closing data gaps report	ANSES	M36	
P5.1.2.b	42 48	D5.5	D5.5. 2nd NAMs Report (postponed from M36 to M48)	BfR	M48	
P5.1.2.b	42 48	D5.11	D5.11. 2nd closing data gaps report (has been shifted from M60 to M54)	ANSES, BfR	M54	
P5.1.2.c	60	R1_TG+MP	Public tender	ANSES	tbd	
P5.1.2.c	60	D5.5	D5.5. 2nd NAMs Report (postponed from M36 to M48)	BfR	M48	
P5.1.2.c	60	D5.8	D5.8. 3rd New approach methodologies report	BfR	M60	
P5.1.2.c	60	D5.11	D5.11. 2nd closing data gaps report (has been shifted from M60 to M54)	ANSES, BfR	M54	
P5.2.a	81	D5.5	D5.5. 2nd NAMs Report (postponed from M36 to M48)	BfR	M48	
P5.2.a	81	D5.8	D5.8. 3rd New approach methodologies report	BfR	M60	
P5.2.a	81	D5.12	D5.12. 4th New approach methodologies report	BfR	M81	
P5.2.1.a	60	R1_NGTXCs	Evaluating NAMs for the assessment of chemicals with potential NGTxC activity	INRAE, BfR	M24	M24
P5.2.1.a	60	R2_NGTXCs	Combining NAMS for the evaluation of various NGTxC activities	INRAE, BfR	M42	
P5.2.1.a	60	R3_NGTXCs	Development of an efficient and reliable testing strategy for the identification of NGTxC	INRAE, BfR	M54	
P5.2.1.a	60	AD5.2	AD5.2. Guidance on animal studies in PARC	ANSES, BfR	M12	M15

P5.2.1.a	60	AD5.3	AD5.3. List of first assays to be developed for prioritised endpoints (postponed from M12 to M18)	DTU, VUB	M18	M18
P5.2.1.a	60	D5.1	D5.1. 1st NAMs Report (postponed from M18 to M22)	BfR	M22	M23
P5.2.1.a	60	D5.3	D5.3. 1st new AOPs report	INSERM	M24	M26
P5.2.1.a	60	D5.5	D5.5. 2nd NAMs Report (postponed from M36 to M48)	BfR	M48	
P5.2.1.a	60	D5.8	D5.8. 3rd New approach methodologies report	BfR	M60	
P5.2.1.b	36 48	R1_MD-EDC	Extended assessment of NR activities testing using transfected cell lines, and application of this testing strategy to major BPA alternatives, metabolites and other compounds (postponed from M30 to M38)	INSERM	M38	
P5.2.1.b	36 48	R2_MD-EDC	In vitro assays and whole organism test for screening MBD	BfR/UIBK	M34	
P5.2.1.b	36 48	AD5.3	AD5.3. List of first assays to be developed for prioritised endpoints (postponed from M12 to M18)	DTU, VUB	M18	M18
P5.2.1.b	36 48	D5.1	D5.1. 1st NAMs Report (postponed from M18 to M22)	BfR	M22	M23
P5.2.1.b	36 48	D5.4	D5.4. 1st closing data gaps report	ANSES	M36	
P5.2.1.b	36 48	D5.5	D5.5. 2nd NAMs Report (postponed from M36 to M48)	BfR	M48	
P5.2.1.c	48	R1_EDThDisruption	Expand on available THSD MIEs by delivering a test battery of MIEs related to thyroid hormone transporters across physiological barriers	VUA	M36	
P5.2.1.c	48	R2_EDThDisruption	Establish plausible links between TH system MIEs and downstream effects using transcriptomics of TH target tissues and of 2D-and 3D-liver (stem) cell-based cultures; validate MIEs of THSDs and provide a framework for interpretation of in vitro and molecular data	DTU/VUB/BfR	M48	
P5.2.1.c	48	R3_EDThDisruption	Establishment and testing of in vitro assays, in silico and zebrafish/amphibian assays to identify MIEs	ISCI	M36	
P5.2.1.c	48	R4_EDThDisruption	Investigate the use of non-mammalian NAMs for extrapolation to human health for THSD: zebrafish embryo assays to be used in a case study for cross-species extrapolation	SDU/UAntwerpen	M36	
P5.2.1.c	48	R5_EDThDisruption	Release of QSAR predictions for 650,000 substances including 80,000 REACH-preregistered / 11,000 registered substances and QMRF documentation in free Danish (Q)SAR Models website	DTU	M48	
P5.2.1.c	48	AD5.2	AD5.2. Guidance on animal studies in PARC	ANSES, BfR	M12	M15
P5.2.1.c	48	AD5.3	AD5.3. List of first assays to be developed for prioritised endpoints (postponed from M12 to M18)	DTU, VUB	M18	M18
P5.2.1.c	48	D5.1	D5.1. 1st NAMs Report (postponed from M18 to M22)	BfR	M22	M23
P5.2.1.c	48	D5.3	D5.3. 1st new AOPs report	INSERM	M24	M26
P5.2.1.c	48	D5.5	D5.5. 2nd NAMs Report (postponed from M36 to M48)	BfR	M48	
P5.2.1.d	36 48	R1_Immunotox	Characterization of in vitro systems relevant for respiratory immunotoxicity (postponed from M36 to M48)	INSERM	M48	
P5.2.1.d	36 48	R2_Immunotox	Immunosuppression and response to vaccination (postponed from M36 to M48)	INSERM	M48	

P5.2.1.d	36 48	R3_Immunotox	In vitro systems to assay key events in the immune system function or dysfunction (postponed from M36 to M48)	INSERM	M48	
P5.2.1.d	36 48	AD5.2	AD5.2. Guidance on animal studies in PARC	ANSES, BfR	M12	M15
P5.2.1.d	36 48	AD5.3	AD5.3. List of first assays to be developed for prioritised endpoints (postponed from M12 to M18)	DTU, VUB	M18	M18
P5.2.1.d	36 48	D5.1	D5.1. 1st NAMs Report (postponed from M18 to M22)	BfR	M22	M23
P5.2.1.d	36 48	D5.5	D5.5. 2nd NAMs Report (postponed from M36 to M48)	BfR	M48	
P5.2.1.e	36 48	R1_DNT-ANT	Development of NAMs relevant for detection of ANT (postponed from M36 to M48)	IUF, UKON, INSERM, UFZ	M48	
P5.2.1.e	36 48	R2_DNT-ANT	Fill existing gaps in the DNT IVB (postponed from M36 to M48)	NIPH, IUF, RIVM	M48	
P5.2.1.e	36 48	R3_DNT-ANT	Complementary zebrafish assays for the DNT and ANT IVB	UFZ, IUF, NIPH	M36	Cancelled
P5.2.1.e	36 48	R4_DNT-ANT	Final Report (postponed from M36 to M48)	UFZ, UIF, UU	M48	
P5.2.1.e	36 48	AD5.2	AD5.2. Guidance on animal studies in PARC	ANSES, BfR	M12	M15
P5.2.1.e	36 48	AD5.3	AD5.3. List of first assays to be developed for prioritised endpoints (postponed from M12 to M18)	DTU, VUB	M18	M18
P5.2.1.e	36 48	D5.1	D5.1. 1st NAMs Report (postponed from M18 to M22)	BfR	M22	M23
P5.2.1.e	36 48	D5.5	D5.5. 2nd NAMs Report (postponed from M36 to M48)	BfR	M48	
P5.2.1.f	81	D5.5	D5.5. 2nd NAMs Report (postponed from M36 to M48)	BfR	M48	
P5.2.1.f	81	D5.8	D5.8. 3rd New approach methodologies report	BfR	M60	
P5.2.1.f	81	D5.12	D5.12. 4th New approach methodologies report	BfR	M81	
P5.2.1.g	81	R1_DIT-NAM	Development of a physiological map of the developing immune system	IUF	M48	
P5.2.1.g	81	D5.5	D5.5. 2nd NAMs Report (postponed from M36 to M48)	BfR	M48	
P5.2.1.g	81	D5.8	D5.8. 3rd New approach methodologies report	BfR	M60	
P5.2.1.g	81	D5.12	D5.12. 4th New approach methodologies report	BfR	M81	
P5.2.1.h	60	R1_SDHEPATOX	Establishment of hepatic liver cell models with sexual dimorphism and differential responses induced by a prototypal compound	ANSES/VUB/BfR	M60	
P5.2.1.h	60	D5.5	D5.5. 2nd NAMs Report (postponed from M36 to M48)	BfR	M48	
P5.2.1.h	60	D5.8	D5.8. 3rd New approach methodologies report	BfR	M60	
P5.3.1.a	36 48	R1_SystemsToxicology	Report on the inventory of in vitro, in vivo and human omics data, biochemical data, other relevant readouts and bioinformatics approaches in public domain repositories at PARC partners for all selected adverse outcomes.	UL-LACDR/SCIENSANO	M12	see AD5.4 (M19)

P5.3.1.a	36 48	R2_SystemsToxicology	Report on the applicability domain of systems toxicology bioinformatics approaches for regulatory implementation (postponed from M26 to M30 due to the delayed project)	UL-LACDR/SCIENSANO	M30	
P5.3.1.a	36 48	R3_SystemsToxicology	Report on translation of systems toxicology data from in vitro NAM to human in vivo.	UL-LACDR/SCIENSANO	M36	
P5.3.1.a	36 48	AD5.4	AD5.4. Inventory of omics data, biochemical data, other relevant readouts in public domain repositories for all PARC selected adverse outcomes and mapping of the available information sources and datasets related to human pathophysiology focusing on the prioritised endpoints (postponed from M12 to M19)	UL-LACDR	M19	M19
P5.3.1.a	36 48	AD5.7	AD5.7. Draft strategy for the development of bioinformatics tools that are needed to link omics data and other mechanistic information to human relevant disease mechanisms (postponed from M12 to M20)	UL-LACDR, SCIENSANO	M20	M22
P5.3.1.a	36 48	D5.3	D5.3. 1st new AOPs report	INSERM	M24	M26
P5.3.1.a	36 48	D5.4	D5.4. 1st closing data gaps report	ANSES	M36	
P5.3.1.a	36 48	D5.7	D5.7. Systems Toxicology (and AOPs) report	INSERM	M48	
P5.3.1.b	81	R1_grOMICS	OPRF and developed database and interface system to handle reporting HTTr and HTPP data	UL (NL), IISPV (ES), BfR (DE), INSERM (FR), UHC(GE), WP7 support via MU and VITO (PARC Data Hub)	M60	
P5.3.1.b	81	R2_grOMICS	the TXG-MAPr HTTr and HTPP network models for screening test systems and a tox-oriented, interoperable ontology of biological entities	UL (NL), UFZ (GE), INSERM (FR), IISPV (ES), UGENT (BE), BHAM (UK)	M68	
P5.3.1.b	81	R3_grOMICS	guideline document to integrate structural and (physio)chemical (including metabolism), mode of action (from HTTr) and cellular morphology (HTPP) in grouping and read-across approaches: the three case studies	UL (NL), IRFM (IT), UHC (GE), INSERM (FR), IISPV (ES), UGENT (BE), UFZ (DE), KIT (DE), Sciensano (BE), BHAM (UK)	M84	
P5.3.1.b	81	D5.7	D5.7. Systems Toxicology (and AOPs) report	INSERM	M48	
P5.3.1.b	81	D5.10	D5.10. 3rd new AOPs report	INSERM/UL-LACDR/Sciensano	M60	
P5.3.1.b	81	D5.14	D5.14. 4th new AOPs report	INSERM/UL-LACDR/Sciensano	M81	
P5.3.2.a	36 48	R1_AOPDevelopment	Inventory of the available (networks of) AOPs, prioritization and establishment of the framework for further development in PARC.	INSERM	M12	see AD5.5 (M17)
P5.3.2.a	36 48	R2_AOPDevelopment	Progress report on AOP development in priority endpoints	INSERM	M36	
P5.3.2.a	36 48	AD5.5	AD5.5. Inventory of the available (networks of) AOPs, prioritisation and establishment of the framework for further development in PARC (postponed from M12 to M17)	INSERM	M17	M17
P5.3.2.a	36 48	AD5.4	AD5.4. Inventory of omics data, biochemical data, other relevant readouts in public domain repositories for all PARC selected adverse outcomes and mapping of the available information sources and datasets related to human pathophysiology focusing on the prioritised endpoints (postponed from M12 to M19)	UL-LACDR	M19	M19

P5.3.2.a	36 48	D5.7	D5.7. Systems Toxicology (and AOPs) report	INSERM	M48	
P5.3.4.a	36 48	R1_PBK_Kinetics	Report on <i>in vitro</i> and <i>in silico</i> ADME models available and needed for PBK case studies on model and priority compounds (postponed from M12 to M36 to be included in D5.2)	ITEM-Fraunhofer	M36	see D5.2 (M36)
P5.3.4.a	36 48	R2_PBK_Kinetics	Report on conceptual data gaps in IVIVE-PBK models and the thereof started case studies (postponed from M24 to M36 to be included in D5.2)	ITEM-Fraunhofer	M36	see D5.2 (M36)
P5.3.4.a	36 48	R3_PBK_Kinetics	Report on the first uncertainty analyses of case studies	ITEM-Fraunhofer	M36	
P5.3.4.a	36 48	L1_PBK_Kinetics	Workshop with T5.1 and 5.2 on data requirement and strategy for their implementation for the proposed case studies	ITEM-Fraunhofer	M13	M13
P5.3.4.a	36 48	D5.2	D5.2. 1st new PBK models report (postponed from M24 to M36)	Fraunhofer-ITEM	M36	
P5.3.4.a	36 48	D5.6	D5.6. 2nd new PBK models report	Fraunhofer-ITEM	M48	
P5.3.4.b	81	R1_RESUPT	Data gap analysis on air liquid dosimetry, <i>in vitro</i> biokinetic approaches and permeability models	RIVM, ITEM, INERIS, UG-PL/QSARLab, STAMI	M43	
P5.3.4.b	81	R2_RESUPT	Selection of test compounds	All	M43	
P5.3.4.b	81	R3_RESUPT	Data measured for 4 model compounds on plastic binding and evaporation for <i>in vitro</i> biokinetic modelling	INERIS, AUTH	M54	
P5.3.4.b	81	R4_RESUPT	Data measured for 4 model compounds on barrier models and integrated into PBK models	ITEM, RIVM, INERIS, VITO, STAMI, AUTH, IBMT	M73	
P5.3.4.b	81	R5_RESUPT	Guidance document on dosimetry and the use of respiratory <i>in vitro</i> models for uptake assessment	RIVM, INERIS, STAMI	M84	
P5.3.4.b	81	D5.6	D5.6. 2nd new PBK models report	Fraunhofer-ITEM	M48	
P5.3.4.b	81	D5.9	D5.9. 3rd new PBK models report	Fraunhofer-ITEM	M60	
P5.3.4.b	81	D5.13	D5.13. 4th new PBK models report	Fraunhofer-ITEM	M81	

WP6

Project ID	Project end	D_AD_M-R_L number	Title	Partner Responsible	Expected delivery date	Achievement date
P6.1.1.a	36	AD5.5	AD5.5 Inventory of the available (networks of) AOPs, prioritisation and establishment of the framework for further development in PARC (postponed from M12 to M17)	INSERM	M17	M17
P6.1.1.a	36	AD6.1-AD6.9	AD6.1-AD6.9 Report on draft IATAs for selected endpoints (ED, genotoxicity and STOT) and recommendations/strategies for future IATA development for more complex endpoints (postponed from M24 to M34)	Sciensano/U L-LACDR/RIVM	M34	
P6.1.1.a	36	D6.5	D6.5 Reports on IATAs and associated case studies	Sciensano	M42	
P6.1.1.a	36	D6.11	D6.11. Harmonized workflow for human relevance assessment of AOPs and associated NAMs	RIVM	M72	

P6.1.1.a	36	D6.12	D6.12. 2nd Report on IATAs and associated case studies	Sciensano	M81	
P6.1.1.b	36	AD5.5	AD5.5 Inventory of the available (networks of) AOPs, prioritisation and establishment of the framework for further development in PARC (postponed from M12 to M17)	INSERM	M17	M17
P6.1.1.b	36	AD6.1-AD6.9	AD6.1-AD6.9 Report on draft IATAs for selected endpoints (ED, genotoxicity and STOT) and recommendations/strategies for future IATA development for more complex endpoints (postponed from M24 to M34)	Sciensano/U L- LACDR/RI VM	M34	
P6.1.1.b	36	D6.5	D6.5 Reports on IATAs and associated case studies	Sciensano	M42	
P6.1.1.b	36	D6.11	D6.11. Harmonized workflow for human relevance assessment of AOPs and associated NAMs	RIVM	M72	
P6.1.1.b	36	D6.12	D6.12. 2nd Report on IATAs and associated case studies	Sciensano	M81	
P6.1.1.c	36 48	R1_IATA_GENTOX	Annual report 2025	Sciensano & INRAE	M37	
P6.1.1.c	36 48	R2_IATA_GENTOX	Final project report	Sciensano & INRAE	M49	
P6.1.1.c	36 48	D5.3	D5.3. 1st new AOPs report	INSERM	M24	M26
P6.1.1.c	36 48	AD5.5	AD5.5 Inventory of the available (networks of) AOPs, prioritisation and establishment of the framework for further development in PARC (postponed from M12 to M17)	INSERM	M17	M17
P6.1.1.c	36 48	AD6.1-AD6.9	AD6.1-AD6.9 Report on draft IATAs for selected endpoints (ED, genotoxicity and STOT) and recommendations/strategies for future IATA development for more complex endpoints (postponed from M24 to M34)	Sciensano/U L- LACDR/RI VM	M34	
P6.1.1.c	36 48	D6.5	D6.5 Reports on IATAs and associated case studies	Sciensano	M42	
P6.1.1.c	36 48	D6.11	D6.11. Harmonized workflow for human relevance assessment of AOPs and associated NAMs	RIVM	M72	
P6.1.1.c	36 48	D6.12	D6.12. 2nd Report on IATAs and associated case studies	Sciensano	M81	
P6.1.1.d	36 48	AD5.5	AD5.5 Inventory of the available (networks of) AOPs, prioritisation and establishment of the framework for further development in PARC (postponed from M12 to M17)	INSERM	M17	M17
P6.1.1.d	36 48	AD6.1-AD6.9	AD6.1-AD6.9 Report on draft IATAs for selected endpoints (ED, genotoxicity and STOT) and recommendations/strategies for future IATA development for more complex endpoints (postponed from M24 to M34)	Sciensano/U L- LACDR/RI VM	M34	
P6.1.1.d	36 48	D6.5	D6.5 Reports on IATAs and associated case studies	Sciensano	M42	
P6.1.1.d	36 48	D6.11	D6.11. Harmonized workflow for human relevance assessment of AOPs and associated NAMs	RIVM	M72	
P6.1.1.d	36 48	D6.12	D6.12. 2nd Report on IATAs and associated case studies	Sciensano	M81	
P6.1.1.e	81	tbd	tbd	tbd	tbd	
P6.1.1.f	81	R1_HumanRelevance	Progress report	AUTH & RIVM	M48	

P6.1.1.f	81	R1_HumanRelevance	Progress report	AUTH & RIVM	M60	
P6.1.1.f	81	D6.11	D6.11. Harmonized workflow for human relevance assessment of AOPs and associated NAMs	RIVM	M72	
P6.1.1.f	81	D6.12	D6.12. 2nd Report on IATAs and associated case studies	Sciensano	M81	
P6.2.1.a	36	AD6.3	AD6.3 Roadmap on aggregated exposure strategy through different living environments sources and routes	UNISANTE, ANSES	M12	M14
P6.2.1.a	36	D6.1	D6.1. 1st Report on aggregate exposure for general population and workers, and source to dose models applied to case studies	ANSES	M36	
P6.2.1.b	48	AD6.3	AD6.3 Roadmap on aggregated exposure strategy through different living environments sources and routes	UNISANTE, ANSES	M12	M14
P6.2.1.b	48	D6.1	D6.1. 1st Report on aggregate exposure for general population and workers, and source to dose models applied to case studies	ANSES	M36	
P6.2.1.b	48	AD6.21	AD6.21. Report describing the results of the aggregate strategy and its application	ANSES	M48	Cancelled
P6.2.2.a	48	R1_PBPk_INERIS	Refinement of existing/development of PBPk models towards multi-route and lifelong exposure	AUTH	M36	
P6.2.2.a	48	R2_PBPk_INERIS	Case studies of the application of refined/developed PBPk models in the risk assessment process	tbd	M48	
P6.2.2.a	48	AD6.4	AD6.4 Inventory of PBPk models for assessing the internal exposure through life	INERIS, AUTH	M12	M14
P6.2.2.a	48	AD6.22	AD6.22. Case studies of the application of refined/developed PBPk models in the risk assessment process	INERIS	M48	Cancelled
P6.2.2.a	48	D6.2	D6.2. 1st report on innovative methods based on PBPk models (M36)	AUTH	M36	
P6.2.3.a	48	AD6.5	AD6.5 Development of the strategy for mixture risk assessment using HBM data and its application to prioritized mixtures	RIVM, ANSES	M12	M14
P6.2.3.a	48	D6.3	D6.3. 1st Report on innovative approaches for real-life mixture RA	RIVM	M36	
P6.2.3.a	48	AD6.23	AD6.23. Report describing the results of the mixture RA strategy and its application	RIVM	M48	Cancelled
P6.2.4.a	66	R1_HIADDataAvailability	Case studies on EBD (environmental burden of disease) for PARC prioritized chemicals replaced by a combined report on the status of the 6.2.4 project (on case studies, data availability, methodology): Data, methods and indicators linked to environmental burden of disease case studies for chemicals prioritized in PARC	VITO, UU-IRAS	M24	M24
P6.2.4.a	66	AD6.6	AD6.6 Inventory of existing HIA, exposure and exposure-effect data for chemicals prioritised in PARC	VITO, UU-IRAS	M12	M14
P6.2.4.a	66	D6.4	D6.4. 1st Report on health impact indicators and their policy implications	VITO	M36	
P6.2.4.b	66	R1_HIAMethod	Challenges in performing Environmental Burden of Disease and Health Impact Assessments for chemicals to be addressed in the PARC case studies replaced by a combined report on the status of the 6.2.4 project (on case studies, data availability, methodology): Data, methods and indicators linked to environmental burden of disease case studies for chemicals prioritized in PARC	VITO, UU-IRAS	M24	M24
P6.2.4.b	66	AD6.6	AD6.6 Inventory of existing HIA, exposure and exposure-effect data for chemicals prioritised in PARC	VITO, UU-IRAS	M12	M14

P6.2.4.b	66	D6.4	D6.4. 1st Report on health impact indicators and their policy implications	VITO	M36	
P6.2.4.c	42	R1_HIACaseStudies	Framework for case study selection (criteria, weighing, documentation, ranking)	VITO, UU-IRAS	M12	see AD6.6 (M14)
P6.2.4.c	42	R2_HIACaseStudies	Reporting on design and results of case studies for health impact assessment replaced by a combined report on the status of the 6.2.4 project (on case studies, data availability, methodology): Data, methods and indicators linked to environmental burden of disease case studies for chemicals prioritized in PARC	VITO, UU-IRAS	M24-36-48-60-72-81	M24
P6.2.4.c	42	AD6.6	AD6.6 Inventory of existing HIA, exposure and exposure-effect data for chemicals prioritised in PARC	VITO, UU-IRAS	M12	M14
P6.2.4.c	42	D6.4	D6.4. 1st Report on health impact indicators and their policy implications	VITO	M36	
P6.2.4.d	42	R1_HIAIndicators	Inventory of existing indicator types of relevance for PARC	VITO, UU-IRAS	M12	see AD6.6 (M14)
P6.2.4.d	42	D6.4	D6.4. 1st Report on health impact indicators and their policy implications	VITO	M36	
P6.3.1.a	48	R1_SubstanceRA_SU - CS12_MethodOSOA (M1-M36M42)	CS12 interim report	SU	M36	
P6.3.1.a	48	R2_SubstanceRA_SU - CS12_MethodOSOA (M1-M36M42)	CS12 final report	SU	M42	
P6.3.1.a	48	R1_SubstanceRA_SU - CS13_Plasticizers RA (M1-M24M36)	CS13 final report	UCL	M36	
P6.3.1.a	48	R1_SubstanceRA_SU - CS14_Biocides RA (M1-M24)	CS14 final report (postponed from M24 to M29)	SU	M29	M29
P6.3.1.a	48	D6.6	D6.6. 1st Report on conclusions from case studies reviewing RA methodologies	KEMI	M42	
P6.3.1.a	48	MS13	MS13 Mid-term review of the PARC activities, performance and budget	ANSES	M42	
P6.3.1.a	48	D6.17	D6.17 2nd Report on conclusions from case studies reviewing RA methodologies	KEMI	M81	
P6.3.1.b	48	R1_EffectRA_BPI - CS9_SKINSENSIRISK (M6-M54)	CS9 first phase progress report	REGIONH	M36	
P6.3.1.b	48	R1_EffectRA_BPI - CS10_ED-cosmetics (M8-M32M42)	CS10 interim report on NGRA work performed	VUB	M32	M32
P6.3.1.b	48	R1_EffectRA_BPI - CS10_ED-cosmetics (M8-M32M42)	CS10 final report	VUB	M42	
P6.3.1.b	48	R1_EffectRA_BPI - CS11_GenotoxCarc (M1-M48)	CS11 interim report	ISS	M36	
P6.3.1.b	48	R2_EffectRA_BPI - CS11_GenotoxCarc (M1-M48)	CS11 final report	ISS	M48	
P6.3.1.b	48	R1_EffectRA_BPI - CS15_DNT (M1-M36M48)	CS15 interim report	SU	M36	
P6.3.1.b	48	R1_EffectRA_BPI - CS15_DNT (M1-M36M48)	CS15 final report	SU	M48	
P6.3.1.b	48	R1_EffectRA_BPI - CS17_ED-in vitro (M1-M36M48)	CS17 interim report	BPI	M36	

P6.3.1.b	48	R2_EffectRA_BPI - CS17_ED-in vitro (M1-M36M48)	CS17 final report	BPI	M48	
P6.3.1.b	48	R1_EffectRA_BPI - CS18_ED-classes (M1-M36M48)	CS18 interim report	BPI	M36	
P6.3.1.b	48	R2_EffectRA_BPI - CS18_ED-classes (M1-M36M48)	CS18 final report	BPI	M48	
P6.3.1.b	48	D6.6	D6.6. 1st Report on conclusions from case studies reviewing RA methodologies	KEMI	M42	
P6.3.1.b	48	MS13	MS13 Mid-term review of the PARC activities, performance and budget	ANSES	M42	
P6.3.1.b	48	D6.17	D6.17 2nd Report on conclusions from case studies reviewing RA methodologies	KEMI	M81	
P6.3.2.a	48	R1_ToolsRA_SU - CS1_CARB (M1-M36M48)	CS1 final report	SYKE	M48	
P6.3.2.a	48	R1_ToolsRA_SU - CS2_RiskReduction (M1-M24M36)	CS2 final report	SU	M36	
P6.3.2.a	48	R1_ToolsRA_SU - CS3_WorkplaceRA (M1-M36)	CS3 final report	TTL	M36	
P6.3.2.a	48	R1_ToolsRA_SU - CS4_SecPoisoning (M2-M38M48)	CS4 interim report	INERIS	M36	
P6.3.2.a	48	R1_ToolsRA_SU - CS4_SecPoisoning (M2-M38M48)	CS4 final report	INERIS	M48	
P6.3.2.a	48	R1_ToolsRA_SU - CS7_REGPREP (M1-M36+48)	CS7 first phase progress report	Eawag	M36	
P6.3.2.a	48	R1_ToolsRA_SU - CS7_REGPREP (M1-M36+48)	CS7 second phase progress report	Eawag	M77	
P6.3.2.a	49	R1_ToolsRA_SU - CS7_REGPREP (M1-M36+48)	CS7 final report on pesticide environmental risk assessment under different regulations – water, sediment and soil	Eawag	M81	
P6.3.2.a	48	R1_ToolsRA_SU - CS8_OccupReproDev_K I (M1-M36M48)	CS8 interim report	KI	M36	
P6.3.2.a	49	R1_ToolsRA_SU - CS8_OccupReproDev_K I (M1-M36M48)	CS8 report Potential prioritisation criteria for derivation of occupational exposure limits for reproductive toxicants	KI	M48	
P6.3.2.a	48	R1_ToolsRA_SU - CS16_UncertaintyRA (M1-M36M48)	CS16 interim report	ULUND	M36	
P6.3.2.a	48	R2_ToolsRA_SU - CS16_UncertaintyRA (M1-M36M48)	CS16 final report	ULUND	M48	
P6.3.2.a	48	R1_ToolsRA_SU - CS19_DataGapFilling (M13-M24M30)	CS19 final report	KEMI	M34	
P6.3.2.a	48	R1_ToolsRA_CS20_Y3_PESTNAM (M25-M48)	CS20 interim report	ISS	M36	
P6.3.2.a	48	R2_ToolsRA_CS20_Y3_PESTNAM (M25-M48)	CS20 final report	ISS	M48	
P6.3.2.a	48	D6.6	D6.6. 1st Report on conclusions from case studies reviewing RA methodologies	KEMI	M42	
P6.3.2.a	48	MS13	MS13 Mid-term review of the PARC activities, performance and budget	ANSES	M42	

P6.3.2.a	48	D6.17	D6.17 2nd Report on conclusions from case studies reviewing RA methodologies	KEMI	M81	
P6.4.1.a	36 40	R1_OPREMIXCS1	Evaluation of the stakeholder feedback collected from a survey and expert interviews on the usefulness of current mixture assessment tools (postponed from M22 to M35)	RWTH, BUL	M35	
P6.4.1.a	36 40	R2_OPREMIXCS1	Comparative assessment of mixture tools with respect to application domain, feasibility, data demands, protectiveness, reliability, bias (postponed from M24 to M35)	RWTH, BUL	M35	
P6.4.1.a	36 40	R3_OPREMIXCS1	Draft for a European mixture framework, accompanied by a validated toolbox of instruments for mixture risk assessment and management (postponed from M36 to M40)	RWTH, BUL	M40	
P6.4.1.a	36 40	AD6.17	AD6.17 Optimizing regulatory risk assessment and management of chemical mixtures in Europe (postponed from M36 to M40)	RWTH	M40	
P6.4.1.a	36 40	D6.18	D6.18 Final report on risk assessment and management methods for chemical mixtures across legislations	AGES	M81	
P6.4.1.b	36 40	R1_MONAMMIXCS2	Literature review on use of NAM and monitoring data for describing mixture exposure relevant for regulation (postponed from M18 to M22)	UFZ, UBA	M22	M23
P6.4.1.b	36 40	R2_MONAMMIXCS2	Guidance document for use of NAM data for specific regulatory options	UFZ, UBA	M36	
P6.4.1.b	36 40	AD6.17	AD6.17 Optimizing regulatory risk assessment and management of chemical mixtures in Europe (postponed from M36 to M40)	RWTH	M40	
P6.4.1.b	36 40	AD6.18	AD6.18: Dealing with mixtures in regulatory risk assessment through the use of monitoring data and NAMs	UFZ/UBA	M40	Cancelled (see AD6.17)
P6.4.1.b	36 40	D6.18	D6.18 Final report on risk assessment and management methods for chemical mixtures across legislations	AGES	M81	
P6.4.1.c	72	R1_Skinsenmix	An overview (scientific paper/report) of current knowledge and practices concerning mixtures	RegionH/ST AMI	M36	
P6.4.1.c	72	R2_Skinsenmix	In-vitro (NAM) testing of skin sensitizers in mixture, preliminary results	RegionH/ST AMI	M48	
P6.4.1.c	72	R3_Skinsenmix	In-vitro testing of mixtures of skin sensitizers and irritants. Preliminary results	RegionH/ST AMI	M60	
P6.4.1.c	72	R3_Skinsenmix	Mixtures, results	RegionH/ST AMI	M72	
P6.4.1.c	72	D6.18	D6.18 Final report on risk assessment and management methods for chemical mixtures across legislations	AGES	M81	
P6.4.1.d	81	R1_RE-MIX	Mid-Report” State of play of project and identification of further needs”	UBA and EAWAG	M60	
P6.4.1.d	81	R2_RE-MIX	Final Report “Outcome of the project, based on summaries of case studies, conceptual analyses and Forum for Exchange”	UBA and EAWAG	M81	
P6.4.1.d	81	D6.18	D6.18 Final report on risk assessment and management methods for chemical mixtures across legislations	AGES	M81	
P6.4.2.a	36	R1_LandscapingSurv	Interim technical report: Landscaping exercise assessing the status of integration and use of NAMs across sectorial frameworks	UNIBAS	M12	M13
P6.4.2.a	36	R2_LandscapingSurv	Technical report: Status of integration and use of NAMs in the EU chemical regulatory risk assessment landscape – a mapping exercise and gaps & needs analysis (AD6.16, postponed from M24 to M36)	UNIBAS	M36	
P6.4.2.a	36	R3_LandscapingSurv	Workshop/webinar report: Prioritization of regulatory-relevant scenario-based case studies	UNIBAS	M36	
P6.4.2.a	36	R4_LandscapingSurv	Technical report summarizing the key learnings from the case studies	UNIBAS	M36	

P6.4.2.a	36	AD6.16	AD6.16: Status of integration and use of NAMs in the EU chemical regulatory risk assessment landscape – a mapping exercise and gaps & needs analysis (postponed from M24 to M36)	UNIBAS	M36	
P6.4.2.a	36	D6.19	D6.19 Report on regulatory acceptance and use of new methods (NAMs)	UNIBAS	M81	
P6.4.2.b	36 81	R1_NGRApractice	Protocol for designing INVITES-IN, a tool for assessing the internal validity of in vitro studies	NIPH, represented by VKM	M11	M17
P6.4.2.b	36 81	R2_NGRApractice	Protocol for the user testing and validation of INVITES-IN, a tool for assessing the internal validity of in vitro studies	NIPH, represented by VKM	M17	M17
P6.4.2.b	36 81	R3_NGRApractice	Creation of INVITES-IN, a focus group study	NIPH, represented by VKM	M16	M17
P6.4.2.b	36 81	R4_NGRApractice	Protocol for harmonizing and cross-walking SR and CRA terms	NIPH, represented by VKM	M18	M20
P6.4.2.b	36 81	R5_NGRApractice	Creation of INVITES-IN, a Delphi survey (postponed from M20 to M34)	NIPH, represented by VKM	M34	
P6.4.2.b	36 81	R6_NGRApractice	Core SR and CRA terms; definitions and cross-walking two disciplines (postponed from M26 to M35)	NIPH, represented by VKM	M35	
P6.4.2.b	36 81	R7_NGRApractice	Protocol; creating an overview of external validity items	NIPH, represented by VKM	M23	Cancelled
P6.4.2.b	36 81	R8_NGRApractice	Creation of INVITES-IN, user testing and validation (postponed from M23 to M35)	NIPH, represented by VKM	M35	
P6.4.2.b	36 81	R9_NGRApractice	INVITES-IN, a tool for evaluation of internal validity of in vitro studies (postponed from M24 to M36)	NIPH, represented by VKM	M36	
P6.4.2.b	36 81	R10_NGRApractice	Protocol for designing INVITES-EX, a tool for assessing the external validity of in vitro studies (postponed from M29 to M36)	NIPH, represented by VKM	M36	
P6.4.2.b	36 81	R11_NGRApractice	External validity items, a comprehensive overview	NIPH, represented by VKM	M35	
P6.4.2.b	36 81	R12_NGRApractice	Protocol for the user testing and validation of INVITES-EX, a tool for assessing the external validity of in vitro studies	NIPH, represented by VKM	M36	
P6.4.2.b	36 81	R13_NGRApractice	Creation of INVITES-EX, a focus group study	NIPH, represented by VKM	M39	
P6.4.2.b	37 81	R14_NGRApractice	Report Year 1-3	NIPH, represented by VKM	M41	
P6.4.2.b	36 81	R15_NGRApractice	Creation of INVITES-EX, a Delphi survey	NIPH, represented by VKM	M42	
P6.4.2.b	36 81	R16_NGRApractice	Protocol for the creation of a tool for assessment of external validity	NIPH, represented by VKM	M42	
P6.4.2.b	36 81	R17_NGRApractice	Cross-mapping core systematic review and chemical risk assessment terms	NIPH, represented by VKM	M43	
P6.4.2.b	36 81	R18_NGRApractice	INVITES-IN: User test	NIPH, represented by VKM	M44	
P6.4.2.b	37 81	R19_NGRApractice	INVITES-IN: a tool for assessment of internal validity of in vitro studies	NIPH, represented by VKM	M44	
P6.4.2.b	38 81	R20_NGRApractice	Checklist for reporting of in vitro studies for internal validity assessment	NIPH, represented by VKM	M44	

P6.4.2.b	36 81	R21_NGRApractice	Creation of INVITES-EX, user testing and validation	NIPH, represented by VKM	M46	
P6.4.2.b	36 81	R22_NGRApractice	INVITES-EX, a tool for evaluation of internal validity of in vitro studies	NIPH, represented by VKM	M48	
P6.4.2.b	37 81	R23_NGRApractice	Protocol for the user testing of the tool for assessment of external validity	NIPH, represented by VKM	M49	
P6.4.2.b	36 81	R24_NGRApractice	Checklist for reporting of in vitro studies	NIPH, represented by VKM	M49	
P6.4.2.b	36 81	R25_NGRApractice	Study 1 in the creation of the external validity tool	NIPH, represented by VKM	M52	
P6.4.2.b	36 81	R26_NGRApractice	SR Principles – online information/training session	NIPH, represented by VKM	M61	
P6.4.2.b	36 81	R27_NGRApractice	Study 2 in the creation of the external validity tool	NIPH, represented by VKM	M64	
P6.4.2.b	36 81	R28_NGRApractice	Internal validity tool training	NIPH, represented by VKM	M73	
P6.4.2.b	36 81	R29_NGRApractice	The external validity tool user testing	NIPH, represented by VKM	M77	
P6.4.2.b	36 81	R30_NGRApractice	The external validity tool	NIPH, represented by VKM	M81	
P6.4.2.b	36 81	R31_NGRApractice	Checklist for reporting of in vitro studies for external validity assessment	NIPH, represented by VKM	M81	
P6.4.2.b	36 81	R32_NGRApractice	External validity tool training	NIPH, represented by VKM	M82	
P6.4.2.b	36 81	L1_NGRApractice	Ethical approval of creation of INVITES-IN	NIPH_represented by VKM	M10	M10
P6.4.2.b	36 81	AD6.16	AD6.16: Status of integration and use of NAMs in the EU chemical regulatory risk assessment landscape – a mapping exercise and gaps & needs analysis (postponed from M24 to M36)	UNIBAS	M36	
P6.4.2.b	36 81	D6.19	D6.19 Report on regulatory acceptance and use of new methods (NAMs)	UNIBAS	M81	
P6.4.2.c	36	R1_NAMAM	Overview of exploratory analysis and identification of research priorities and requirements (postponed from M12 to M24)	UT	M24	M29
P6.4.2.c	36	R2_NAMAM	Framework to facilitate an adequate reporting for the AI/ML NAMs to be used for regulatory purposes (postponed from M24 to M34)	UT	M34	
P6.4.2.c	36	R3_NAMAM	Final report on the main outcomes of the project	UT	M36	
P6.4.2.c	36	AD6.16	AD6.16: Status of integration and use of NAMs in the EU chemical regulatory risk assessment landscape – a mapping exercise and gaps & needs analysis (postponed from M24 to M36)	UNIBAS	M36	
P6.4.2.c	36	D6.19	D6.19 Report on regulatory acceptance and use of new methods (NAMs)	UNIBAS	M81	
P6.4.2.d	81	R1_RegulatoryNAMs	1 st Progress report	ISS	M48	
P6.4.2.d	81	R2_RegulatoryNAMs	2 nd Progress report	RIVM	M60	

P6.4.2.d	81	R3_RegulatoryNAMs	3rd Progress report	ISS	M72	
P6.4.2.d	81	D6.11	D6.11. Harmonized workflow for human relevance assessment of AOPs and associated NAMs	RIVM	M72	
P6.4.2.d	81	D6.12	D6.12. 2nd Report on IATAs and associated case studies	Sciensano	M81	
P6.4.2.d	81	D6.17	D6.17. 2nd Report on conclusions from case studies reviewing RA methodologies	KEMI	M81	
P6.4.2.d	81	D6.19	D6.19 Report on regulatory acceptance and use of new methods (NAMs)	UNIBAS	M81	
P6.4.2.e	81	R1_READYAI	1 st Progress report	UNIBAS	M48	
P6.4.2.e	81	R1_READYAI	2 nd Progress report	UNIBAS	M60	
P6.4.2.e	81	R1_READYAI	3rd Progress report	UNIBAS	M72	
P6.4.2.e	81	D6.19	D6.19 Report on regulatory acceptance and use of new methods (NAMs)	UNIBAS	M81	
P6.4.3.a	36	R1_SuProM	Report on LCA incorporation of chemical hazards (postponed from M24 to M39)	MU	M39	See AD6.15
P6.4.3.a	36	AD6.14	AD6.14: Report on current screening and enforcement structures (postponed from M24 to M28)	TUKES	M28	M30
P6.4.3.a	36	AD6.15	AD6.15. Report on existing database structures with recommended structures (postponed from M24 to M39)	MU	M39	
P6.4.3.a	36	D6.20	D6.20. Framework & case studies for articles & recycled materials for systematic identification of priority substances, materials, & articles from market data	MU	M81	
P6.4.3.b	72	R1_ENFORCE	A proof-of-concept methodology for testing compliance with the proposed -PFAS restriction in selected groups of consumer articles	Rise	M54	
P6.4.3.b	72	R1_ENFORCE	A proof-of-concept methodology for rapid quantification of regulated substances in selected types of plastics M60(VU	VUA/MU	M67	
P6.4.3.b	72	AD6.26	AD6.26. New methods to support a systematic and effective enforcement of chemicals	MU/KEMI	M72	
P6.4.3.b	72	D6.20	D6.20. Framework & case studies for articles & recycled materials for systematic identification of priority substances, materials, & articles from market data	MU	M81	
P6.4.4.a	42 81	R1_CRNCS1	Clarifying regulatory needs (Drivers of change, Problem description, Future state of ERA, Gap analysis, Short term-remedies and potential long-term solutions, Prioritised Areas of work and research questions)	KEMI	M22	M22
P6.4.4.a	42 81	R2_CRNCS1	Clarifying regulatory needs	KEMI	M34	
P6.4.4.a	42 81	R3_CRNCS1	Clarifying regulatory needs and preliminary recommendations for new ERA guidance documents	KEMI	M46	
P6.4.4.a	42 81	R4_CRNCS1	Clarifying regulatory needs (iteration after Stakeholder feedback and update of Activity 6.4.4 (projects 6.4.4.a-e) results)	KEMI	M58	
P6.4.4.a	42 81	R5_CRNCS1	Clarifying regulatory needs	KEMI	M70	
P6.4.4.a	42 81	R6_CRNCS1	Recommendations for new ERA guidance documents	KEMI	M81	
P6.4.4.a	42 81	AD6.7	AD6.7. Regulatory needs for ERA – collaborative approaches for effectiveness and resource efficiency (postponed from M24 to M36)	UBA/KEMI/FOEN	M36	

P6.4.4.a	42 81	D6.21	D6.21. Recommendations for new ERA guidance documents	UBA	M81	
P6.4.4.b	36 81	R1_PPPEXPCS2	Technical report describing comparison of different existing methods for predicting PPP concentrations in surface waters within agricultural catchments validated against monitoring data from various European geographical regions. The report will also study which are the most relevant factors for predicting PPP concentrations in surface waters within agricultural catchments (this report will be included in AD6.7 and therefore postponed to its due date M36)	SLU	M36	
P6.4.4.b	36 81	R2_PPPEXPCS2	Technical report describing the most relevant factors for predicting PPP concentrations in surface waters within agricultural catchments.	SLU	M36	Cancelled
P6.4.4.b	36 81	R3_PPPEXPCS2	Report about PEC model sensitivity analysis	Fraunhofer IME	M48	
P6.4.4.b	36 81	R4_PPPEXPCS2	Report about part 1 and 2: Contextualizations of MECs, RECs and comparison with PECs	RPTU	M61	
P6.4.4.b	36 81	R5_PPPEXPCS2	recommendations for new ERA Guidance Documents	All partners (RPTU)	M81	
P6.4.4.b	36 81	R6_PPPEXPCS2	Final Report of PARC 6.4.4.b - Exposure	All partners (RPTU)	M81	
P6.4.4.b	36 81	AD6.7	AD6.7. Regulatory needs for ERA – collaborative approaches for effectiveness and resource efficiency (postponed from M24 to M36)	UBA/KEMI/FOEN	M36	
P6.4.4.b	36 81	AD6.20	AD6.20. Technical report on factors and processes needed to be included in robust aquatic exposure predictions for regulatory use, including an assessment of geographic representativeness	UBA/KEMI/FOEN	M36	Cancelled (see AD6.7)
P6.4.4.b	36 81	D6.21	D6.21. Recommendations for new ERA guidance documents	UBA	M81	
P6.4.4.c	36 81	R1_PPPEFFCS3	Technical report on the most relevant factors describing the transfer function that enables a link between laboratory lower-tier tests and effects at ecosystem level. Ranking the relevance of the factors describing the lab to field transfer function. Identification to which extent interactions between PPPs and additional environmental factors increase the sensitivity of field populations.	UFZ	M24	M24
P6.4.4.c	37 81	R2_PPPEFFCS3	Situation of pesticide effects in EU freshwaters	UFZ	M40	
P6.4.4.c	37 81	R3_PPPEFFCS3	Theoretical basis for adaptation-based PPP risk assessment	UFZ	M46	
P6.4.4.c	36 81	R4_PPPEFFCS3	Software package software to make the framework for an improved ERA accessible to the regulators. The usability and integration of software tools needs to be developed within a structured feedback process involving the regulators within an extended timeframe.	UFZ	M48	
P6.4.4.c	36 81	R5_PPPEFFCS3	Stress Addition Model (SAM) for risk assessment of multiple stress, including data on mixture effects.	UFZ	M54	
P6.4.4.c	36 81	R6_PPPEFFCS3	Link biodiversity assessments (e.g. SPEAR, SAM etc.) to output from the AOP- and NAM-informed STOPredictor for deterministic and probabilistic risk assessment.	NIVA	M72	
P6.4.4.c	36 81	AD6.7	AD6.7. Regulatory needs for ERA – collaborative approaches for effectiveness and resource efficiency (postponed from M24 to M36)	UBA/KEMI/FOEN	M36	
P6.4.4.c	36 81	AD6.19	AD6.19 Technical report informing on factors and processes needed to be included in the ERA to obtain an improved balance between reduced complexity and increased ecological realism	UBA/KEMI/FOEN	M36	Cancelled (see AD6.7)
P6.4.4.c	36 81	D6.21	D6.21. Recommendations for new ERA guidance documents	UBA	M81	

P6.4.4.d	42 81	R1_PPPBENCHCS4	Compiled data for internal risk benchmarking (postponed from M20 to M27)	UKOLD	M27	M28
P6.4.4.d	42 81	R2_PPPBENCHCS4	Analyses for internal risk benchmarking accomplished	UDE	M35	
P6.4.4.d	42 81	R3_PPPBENCHCS4	Database of ERA results and complementary data	UDE	M35	
P6.4.4.d	42 81	R4_PPPBENCHCS4	Data compiled for external risk benchmarking	tbd	M38	
P6.4.4.d	42 81	R5_PPPBENCHCS4	Analyses for external risk benchmarking accomplished	tbd	M44	
P6.4.4.d	42 81	R6_PPPBENCHCS4	Technical report on results of benchmarking analyses with suggestions for methodology and most important factors having an impact on the result of the ERA	tbd	M53	
P6.4.4.d	42 81	R7_PPPBENCHCS4	Report on the implementation of the comparability methodology into the risk assessment paradigm	tbd	M81	
P6.4.4.d	42 81	D6.21	D6.21. Recommendations for new ERA guidance documents	UBA	M81	
P6.4.4.e	42 81	R1_PPPOSCS5	Conceptual models for aggregate and combined exposure to pesticides at landscape level covering the local and regional needs as well as national and EU needs. The tools will support the selection of the best IPM approach allowing an ERA-based scientifically sound assessment of sustainability regarding pesticide use as well as a comparative impact with other stressors (postponed from M12 to M24)	ISCIII	M24	M24
P6.4.4.e	42 81	R2_PPPOSCS5	Case studies report (postponed from M30 to M36)	ISCIII for the compilation, case study leaders for each case study report	M36	
P6.4.4.e	42 81	R3_PPPOSCS5	Final conceptual approach, including problem formulation and implementation options	ISCIII	M36	
P6.4.4.e	42 81	R4_PPPOSCS5	Follow-up case studies report	ISCIII for the compilation, case study leaders for each case study report	M78	
P6.4.4.e	42 81	R5_PPPOSCS5	Final conceptual approach for using landscape-based approaches in , including	ISCIII	M82	
P6.4.4.e	42 81	R6_PPPOSCS5	Recommendations for new ERA Guidance Documents	ISCIII	M82	
P6.4.4.e	42 81	AD6.24	AD6.24. Applicability of landscape ERA approaches for refining the risk and assessing the impacts of PPPs	ISCIII	M81	
P6.4.4.e	42 81	AD6.25	AD6.25. Opportunities and challenges for addressing spatial and temporal variability in the regulatory context through landscape-based approaches	ISCIII	M83	
P6.4.4.e	42 81	D6.21	D6.21. Recommendations for new ERA guidance documents	UBA	M81	

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Project ID	Project end	D_AD_M-R_L number	Title	Partner Responsible	Expected delivery date	Achievement date
P7.2.2.a	36 42	D7.1	D7.1 Data management plan	TNO	M6	M6
P7.2.2.a	36 42	MS11	MS11 Network of trained FAIR data stewards	TNO	M12	M13
P7.2.2.a	36 42	D7.2	D7.2 PARC FAIR Data Policy (PFDP)	TNO	M18	M18
P7.2.2.a	36 42	MS12	MS12. Architecture of PARC FAIR data hub & its integration with the COPCSD	VITO	M24	M29
P7.2.2.a	36 42	D7.3	D7.3. 1st report on Data infrastructure, tools and services for FAIRification and reuse of chemical RA data	VITO	M36	
P7.2.2.a	36 42	D7.5	D7.5. 1st review of the Data Management Plan (DMP)	TNO	M42	
P7.2.2.a	36 42	D7.6	D7.6. 2nd review of the Data Management Plan (DMP)	TNO	M72	
P7.2.2.a	36 42	R-ENVIROdata.1	The level of FAIRness of the existing major data resources on chemicals in the environment (potponed from M30 to M36)	MU	M36	
P7.2.2.a	36 42	R-ENVIROdata.2	FAIR solutions to manage newly generated environmental data (lessons learned from the project use cases) (postponed from M36 to M42)	MU	M42	
P7.2.2.b	42 48	R-HBMdatasets.1	HBM data landscape (postponed from M18 to M34)	VITO	M34	
P7.2.2.b	42 48	R-HBMdatasets.2	Assessment of federated systems for privacy-preserving analysis (postponed from M18 to M34)	VITO	M34	
P7.2.2.b	42 48	R-HBMdatasets.3	FAIR and sustainable storage of human biomonitoring (HBM) datasets: final report (postponed from M42 to M48)	VITO	M48	
P7.2.2.b	42 48	MS11	MS11 Network of trained FAIR data stewards	TNO	M12	M13
P7.2.2.b	42 48	D7.2	D7.2 PARC FAIR Data Policy (PFDP)	TNO	M18	M18
P7.2.2.b	42 48	MS12	MS12 Architecture of PARC FAIR data hub & its integration with the COPCSD	VITO	M24	M29
P7.2.2.b	42 48	D7.3	D7.3 1st report on Data infrastructure, tools and services for FAIRification and reuse of chemical RA data	VITO	M36	
P7.2.2.b	42 48	D7.5	D7.5 1st review of the Data Management Plan (DMP)	TNO	M42	
P7.3.3.a	60	R1_ALT-IST	Scoping study of AI, text mining and ontology-assisted hazard identification and risk assessment (postponed from M18 to M36)	IISPV	M36	
P7.3.3.a	60	R2_ALT-IST	Report on the available tool and framework, and different methodologies (like NLP and text mining) used for human health risk assessment, including ontology development.	IISPV	M48	
P7.3.3.a	60	D7.4	D7.4 1st Evaluation of innovative analytical approaches and uncertainty approaches for introduction in chemical RA	IISPV	M36	